

STOCK EXCHANGE PRACTICES

HEARINGS

BEFORE THE

COMMITTEE ON BANKING AND CURRENCY UNITED STATES SENATE

SEVENTY-THIRD CONGRESS

FIRST SESSION

ON

S. Res. 84

(72d CONGRESS)

A RESOLUTION TO INVESTIGATE PRACTICES OF STOCK
EXCHANGES WITH RESPECT TO THE BUYING AND
SELLING AND THE BORROWING AND LENDING
OF LISTED SECURITIES

AND

S. Res. 56 and S. Res. 97

(73d CONGRESS)

RESOLUTIONS TO INVESTIGATE THE MATTER OF BANKING
OPERATIONS AND PRACTICES, TRANSACTIONS RELATING TO
ANY SALE, EXCHANGE, PURCHASE, ACQUISITION, BORROW-
ING, LENDING, FINANCING, ISSUING, DISTRIBUTING, OR
OTHER DISPOSITION OF, OR DEALING IN, SECURITIES OR
CREDIT BY ANY PERSON OR FIRM, PARTNERSHIP, COMPANY,
ASSOCIATION, CORPORATION, OR OTHER ENTITY, WITH A
VIEW TO RECOMMENDING NECESSARY LEGISLATION, UNDER
THE TAXING POWER OR OTHER FEDERAL POWERS

PART 3

Kuhn, Loeb; Pennroad Corporation

JUNE 27, 28, 29, 30, and JULY 5, 1933

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STOCK EXCHANGE PRACTICES

TUESDAY, JUNE 27, 1933

UNITED STATES SENATE,
SUBCOMMITTEE OF THE COMMITTEE
ON BANKING AND CURRENCY,
Washington, D.C.

The subcommittee met, pursuant to call of the chairman, as a resumption of hearings recessed on Friday, June 9, 1933, at 10 o'clock a.m. in the Caucus Room of the Senate Office Building, Senator Duncan U. Fletcher presiding.

Present: Senators Fletcher (chairman), Barkley, Costigan, Goldsborough, Townsend, and Steiwer.

Present also: Senator Adams.

Present also: Ferdinand Pecora, counsel to the committee; Julius Silver and David Saperstein, associate counsel to the committee; and Frank J. Meehan, chief statistician to the committee; Carl A. de Gersdorff, Robert T. Swaine, and M. T. Moore, counsel for Kuhn, Loeb & Co.

The CHAIRMAN. The subcommittee will please come to order. We will proceed with the hearings. Mr. Pecora, who is your first witness?

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Otto H. Kahn.

The CHAIRMAN. Mr. Kahn will come forward to the committee table, hold up his right hand, and be sworn. You solemnly swear that you will tell the truth, the whole truth, and nothing but the truth, regarding the matters now under investigation by the committee. So help you God?

Mr. KAHN. I do.

TESTIMONY OF OTTO H. KAHN, A PARTNER OF KUHN, LOEB & CO., NEW YORK CITY

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, will you be good enough to give the committee reporter your full name and address, both residence and business?

Mr. KAHN. Otto H. Kahn; business address, 52 William Street, and residence address, 1100 Fifth Avenue, New York City.

Mr. PECORA. What is your business?

Mr. KAHN. I am a banker.

Mr. PECORA. Are you a member of any banking firm in the conduct of your business?

Mr. KAHN. I am a member of the banking firm of Kuhn, Loeb & Co.

Mr. PECORA. How long have you been connected with that firm?

Mr. KAHN. Since 1897.

Mr. PECORA. As a partner?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; as a partner.

Mr. PECORA. What is the personnel in that firm as at present constituted, Mr. Kahn?

Mr. KAHN. Shall I read the names, or give you the paper?

Mr. PECORA. If you will just give us the names.

Mr. KAHN. Felix M. Warburg, Otto H. Kahn, George W. Bove-nizer, Lewis L. Strauss, Sir William Wiseman, John M. Schiff, Gilbert W. Kahn, Frederick M. Warburg, Benjamin J. Bittenwieser, Hugh Knowlton, Elisha Walker.

Mr. PECORA. How long has the firm of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. been in existence?

Mr. KAHN. About 65 years.

Mr. PECORA. And has its principal office during that time always been in the city of New York?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And does it maintain offices in any other city, Mr. Kahn, at the present time?

Mr. KAHN. It maintains offices in no other city.

Mr. PECORA. Has it at any time within the past 6 years maintained an office in any other city?

Mr. KAHN (after conferring with an assistant). I am sorry to have paused for a moment to ask a question or two, but I wanted to be precise. For a couple of years, during 1927 to 1929, I believe, or 1930, Mr. Leith, of London, was a partner in our firm, and he resided in London. We paid the office expenses. But it would be going rather beyond the spirit of our arrangements if I should say that we had an office in London. We had no offices, so to speak, but one of our partners for 2 or 3 years resided in London.

Mr. PECORA. Since 1927, and inclusive of that year, has the firm had any contract affiliation with any other bank or banking firm or banking house?

Mr. KAHN. None, sir.

Mr. PECORA. How would you describe the nature of the business conducted by the firm of Kuhn, Loeb & Co.?

Mr. KAHN. The firm of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. buys and sells securities from and to its clients. It accepts deposits from its clients but not from the general public, and it is not in the business of soliciting deposits. It buys and sells securities on the stock exchange, again for its regular clients, but not for the general public, and does not maintain any kind of special department for the service of clients that may wish to buy securities on the stock exchange through its offices.

Senator TOWNSEND. Do you maintain a stock-exchange membership?

Mr. KAHN. We maintain a stock-exchange membership in that one of our partners is a member of the stock exchange. But may I finish my answer, Senator, if you please?

Senator TOWNSEND. Yes.

Mr. KAHN. The part of our business which I was going to complete was: That it is our function to advise our clients, or those who wish to become our clients, upon financial affairs in general. And may I emphasize the word "financial", because our business is

a financial business and is not to run anybody else's business, only to run our own business as best we can in a financial way.

Mr. PECORA. Does that complete your answer, now?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. You have referred to clients. Does the clientele of your firm consist of any particular kind of persons—that is, persons engaged in any particular kind of business?

Mr. KAHN. The clientele of our firm, Mr. Pecora, is primarily corporations engaged in different lines of business. We have few private clients. We have some inherited European clients, some of the leading European banks maintain relations with us and have maintained them for a great many years. But not of any significance, rather minor accounts. Generally speaking, it would be correct to say that our relationship is mainly with corporations.

Mr. PECORA. With what kind of corporations?

Mr. KAHN. Railroad corporations, and some industrial corporations. We have no public utility affiliations, and never have had any unless you consider the Western Union a public utility, or the American Telephone & Telegraph Co. in the financing of which we have for a number of years had an interest together with others.

Mr. PECORA. Would you say that railroad corporations constitute your principal corporation clients?

Mr. KAHN. I should say they would constitute the majority of our clients, yes.

Mr. PECORA. And has that generally been so in the past 10 years or 20 years?

Mr. KAHN. Mr. Pecora, it has been so long that I should say almost since the beginning of the firm we have specialized in the business of marketing railroad securities.

Mr. PECORA. That is, of railroad financing.

Mr. KAHN. Railroad financing; yes. That is, we have specialized in that line, perhaps unduly, and perhaps to the exclusion of a good many other opportunities which might have been more tempting. We have some industrial clients, but you are right in saying that the majority of our clientele is railroads.

Mr. PECORA. What is the general method, or what has been the general method by which your firm has financed railroad operations?

Mr. KAHN. May I ask, in order that I may correctly understand your question before I answer: Do you mean the general method in detail of buying railroad securities, or the general method in approaching railroads?

Mr. PECORA. Well, take the latter part of your inquiry, for instance, the general method of approaching railroads.

Mr. KAHN. Well, I should say precisely the same method by which a lawyer approaches clients. [Laughter.]

Mr. PECORA. Well, lawyers are not supposed to approach clients.

Mr. KAHN. I was coming to that, Mr. Pecora. Or the method by which a doctor approaches a patient who is sick. He does not go after him. Ethically and as a standard of the legal profession you are not permitted to go after him. And I do not suppose that a doctor would be permitted to go after a patient under the ethical standards of the medical profession. For instance, he could not go

if someone told him that "Mr. Smith in the next block is very sick with pneumonia, you better run in and try to find out if you can get him." That would not be the way to do it. He gets his clients by reason of his reputation for ability and for successful cures and for sound advice given. And so it is with the lawyer. So it is with the architect. And so in our case it has long been our policy and our effort to get our clients, not by chasing after them, not by praising our own wares, but by an attempt to establish a reputation which would make clients feel that if they have a problem of a financial nature, Dr. Kuhn, Loeb & Co. is a pretty good doctor to go to.

Mr. PECORA. Well, the contact having been established between doctor and patient, or in your case between banker and railroad, what is the next step in the operation of financing the railroad?

Mr. KAHN. A railroad, or some particular officer of a railroad—who, by the way, might be personally unknown to us before he was appointed to that particular position—would come to us and would say: "We have such and such a problem to solve, being a problem of a financial nature. We would like to get your advice as to the best kind of security to issue for that purpose—and, by the best kind of security I mean a security which on the one hand gives to the railroad the most useful instrument, not only for immediate purposes but for long-time purposes, and gives to the public the greatest possible protection without tying up the railroad unduly and beyond what is safe for it." So, he says: "Will you tell us what is the best kind of instrument to use for that purpose? Should it be a mortgage bond? Should it be a debenture? Should it be a convertible bond? Should it be preferred stock? Should it be an equity? We would like you to look into it and tell us. Here are our facts and figures. Go through them."

Then we would say: "It is of very great importance to know what kind of securities you want." And I might say that we have sometimes been stuck by not knowing what kind of securities would be most advantageous from all standpoints to issue. There is a great deal of importance in knowing when the market is receptive for a security. We would know that in a short while from now other large security issues are likely to come upon the market. It is our business to know that as far ahead as we can. We would know what is the general disposition of the security market. Is it favorable or is it unfavorable. Is there an investment demand or isn't there an investment demand. And that situation varies. Sometimes we can sell nothing but equities. Sometimes equities are thrown into the discard and people want safety. Again, that is our job, to know.

They would say: "Tell us your best judgment as to the time when we ought to have our bond, or whatever you advise us to use, ready for disposal. We should like your opinion as to that. We should like your opinion as to what is a fair price, both to the public and the railroad, or both to the public and the seller corporation."

I think it is essential that it should be a fair price equally to both, because if it is not you are liable to lose good-will of either of the two, and our business can only persist so long as we have the confidence and good-will of both our corporate clients and the public.

For instance, we haven't got a show window as you have in Fifth Avenue, where goods are attractively displayed and one can look in

and be enticed by quality and good taste on the part of the displayer. We have no show window. Our only attractiveness is our good name and our reputation for sound advice and integrity. If that is gone our business is gone however attractive our show window might be. We hold our position, and every leading banker holds his position, solely by reason of the confidence of the community in his skill, in his sponsorship, in his integrity, in his desire to be thorough and to advise correctly.

And, I might say, we hold our position subject to recall. It can be recalled by the public at any time they choose. It can be recalled by a corporation at any time they choose; if they think we are no longer the people they thought we were they are entirely at liberty to go elsewhere. And the public is entirely at liberty to go elsewhere, and both the public and corporations have done that in the past more than once. It would be ungracious for me to mention names, but there have been ups and downs in banking prestige, and there has been a rise and fall of banking firms. I hope you will not ask me to mention any names, but the history of finance is fairly full of them.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, isn't there the fairly well recognized principle, or canon of ethics we will say, that has been developed in the banking business, in pursuance of which a private banking firm which once undertakes the financing of a corporation continues to do its financing practically to the exclusion of any others, unless it voluntarily chooses to give up the client?

Mr. KAHN. Mr. Pecora, may I use the same simile again? If I am known to be a pretty good doctor I am liable to keep my patients. If I am not, and if for any reason it is possible to think somebody is coming up who is better, the patient will quit me, he will quit me cold. And so will the financial community, and so will corporations. If we do not live up to what they believe is our capacity, and to what they believe is the value of our sponsorship, of our trade mark, they will quit us. And we have no means to prevent them. We are not tied to them and they are not tied to us through any legal instrument or any fiscal agency agreement.

Senator BARKLEY. Is that cold-quitting process to which you refer reciprocal? I mean, is there any habit by which banking institutions, like yours, quit a patient cold if there is any good reason for it?

Mr. KAHN. If they find that the patient does not obey their competent advice in the one field where they ought to be competent, namely, the field of sound financing; if they find that the patient goes his own, in their opinion, dangerous, hazardous way, it is their duty to quit that patient.

The CHAIRMAN. And the next step, Mr. Kahn, after you establish that relationship and are prepared to give your advice, is the question of your compensation for services, isn't it?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, Senator Fletcher.

The CHAIRMAN. Is that based upon any general rule or is that the result of negotiation with each individual client?

Mr. KAHN. It is the result of negotiation—which, however, by this time is pretty well stabilized and normalized. As far as railroad securities are concerned the Interstate Commerce Commission fixes the price. We do not get any commission from the railroads, no fixed compensation. We buy the bonds that we buy at a price

arranged between the railroads and ourselves, and which in our judgment is fair to the railroads and to the public. And I cannot emphasize too much that the element of reciprocal fairness is of the essence of any banker's business. And if it is violated the banker will pay the price. But we agree with the railroad upon a price which we, reciprocally, consider a fair price, to the railroad and to the public, under the prevailing condition of the investment market.

For instance, a railroad will go to the Interstate Commerce Commission and say: "We wish to issue such and such bonds. We have been offered such and such a price by Kuhn, Loeb & Co." The Interstate Commerce Commission, as you well know, investigates the matter and gives its decision. Nothing is said in the contract as to the price at which those bonds which we have bought, we will say at 95, shall be issued to the public. But it is very well understood by practice and by usage at what price the securities will be offered to the public, what spread shall be allowed between the price at which we bought them and the price at which the public shall get them. And that spread is, I can say more than generally, and somewhat uniformly, known to the Interstate Commerce Commission. If we buy bonds at 95 the Interstate Commerce Commission would say: "Now, how much spread do they count on making as between the price at which they buy them from you and the price at which they sell them to the public?" Of course, that would be disclosed. If that spread should be unreasonable we get a pretty strong hint that it is unreasonable, and we better had obey that hint.

Senator TOWNSEND. On what basis is the spread fixed?

Mr. KAHN. The spread is fixed upon, first, reasonable compensation for the originators. Second, reasonable compensation for those who are called distributors, or who may be called underwriters, for their risk, for their effort, and for their responsibility. Again, that has become pretty well stabilized and normalized by usage. In the case of railroads almost uniform. In the case of corporations other than railroads it is a matter of negotiation depending upon the risk involved, the responsibility involved and the greater or lesser difficulty of placing the securities.

The CHAIRMAN. Say you pay 95; what would be a reasonable spread between that and the price the public pays?

Mr. KAHN. A reasonable spread, Senator, dependent upon the kind of issue, dependent upon the size of the issue, dependent upon the prevailing conditions in the market, would be between $2\frac{1}{4}$ and $2\frac{1}{2}$ percent gross, out of which would come all expenses, out of which would come the compensation to the distributors, and out of which would come, Senator, not merely the originator's compensation for his work and his effort, but would come the compensation for the fact, which is not very generally known, that the originator, however many syndicates he may form, remains responsible with his entire fortune and good name to the railroad company for the contract which he has made, for the money which he has undertaken to pay, until that money is paid. He cannot say to the railroad, "I have divided that up amongst five or six hundred people; you will get your money from Tom, Brown, Smith, and Jack." They would say, "We do not know them. You are responsible to us for every one of your 600 subparticipants, distributors, or underwriters. We

look to you, and to you only. And if any of them fail, if any of them are not solvent, you are responsible, and you only."

Our responsibility frequently extends to 5 or 6 weeks in having the syndicate stand in the breach, and during that time the originators are responsible for every single participant in that syndicate, for his solvency and for his making good.

Senator COSTIGAN. Does the percentage vary with the amount involved?

Mr. KAHN. No; I should not think, Senator, it would vary materially with the amount involved. It would vary with the amount involved only to the extent of the increasing difficulty and risk if the amount is unduly large. It would not vary if the amount was unduly small. And we would not charge a man more because he sent us a small issue. We might charge him more if he sends us a large issue, an issue of unusual size, because it involves unusual effort, unusual responsibility, unusual risk.

Senator COSTIGAN. In your judgment is the responsibility measured by the size of the investment?

Mr. KAHN. I beg your pardon, Senator?

Senator COSTIGAN. Read the question, please.

(Thereupon the last question was read by the reporter, as above recorded.)

Mr. KAHN. The responsibility is measured to a certain extent naturally by the size of the investment, because if we take an issue of \$50,000,000 it means that we take a risk of \$50,000,000, and we take the responsibility of it ourselves, however many groups may be involved in its final distribution.

Senator COSTIGAN. You regard the risk as 50 times as great as in the case of a \$1,000,000 issue?

Mr. KAHN. Mathematically so; yes. Mathematically; yes. Actually we do not regard it. Actually we have by long experience gained complete confidence in that list of distributors with whom we generally do business. It happened that we stood in the breach for syndicates at the time that the *Lusitania* went down, which was a very unpleasant experience and gave us some sleepless nights—but no worse than we had yesterday with the first touch of the heat, unfortunately.

We stood in the breach for a very large issue at the time that the great panic in October 1929 broke upon the country. Again it was not a pleasant experience.

But with few exceptions, even in the face of these unforeseen calamities, our list of tested and well selected distributors and friends all made good. And, generally speaking, we have complete confidence in them. Therefore I do not consider the risk of a \$50,000,000 issue 50 times as large as that of a \$1,000,000 issue. I do consider the work greater, I do consider the effort greater, I do consider the responsibility greater.

Senator GOLDSBOROUGH. May I ask a question, Mr. Chairman?

The CHAIRMAN. Yes.

Senator GOLDSBOROUGH. Mr. Kahn, does not the nature of the security back of the issue have a tendency to increase or lessen the percentage of spread?

Mr. KAHN. I should say that the percentage of spread, as I said to Senator Costigan, before, by this time has become so stabilized

that it is a matter of a relatively trifling difference. There is some difference. The nature of the security has something to do with it. For instance, Senator, if we bring out an issue which we know is the kind of security that our savings banks and the insurance companies will be glad to buy because it is the kind of thing they like to buy—

Senator GOLDSBOROUGH. What you would call a triple-A security?

Mr. KAHN. Yes. If we bring that out, it is naturally easier to sell than if we bring out a security that has got to be explained, where we know the insurance companies will not under the law be permitted to buy them, savings banks probably will not buy them either, the extra prudent, old-fashioned investor probably will not buy them either, and we have got to go out and make a special effort to find people who are inclined to buy that kind of security. Now, that would have an influence upon the nature of the spread.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, to go back to the relationship between the banker and his railroad corporation client, as an example. You have said, of course, that the client has the right at any time to transfer his financing to another banker. There is no obligation, contractual or otherwise, which binds the client to the banker. I recognize that. But has there not developed a rule or custom among bankers to keep hands off the client when they know that client has had its financing done by another banker?

Mr. KAHN. I should think, Mr. Pecora, that rule is very much in the spirit of the kind of code which the legislature has now adopted, or is about to adopt, to regulate the business activities of all branches of business in the country. In other words, instead of cutthroat competition, which is not to the interest of the public; instead of the kind of competition which we had between 1926 and 1928, when, to my own knowledge 15 American bankers sat in Belgrade, Yugoslavia, making bids, and a dozen American bankers sat in a half a dozen South and Central American States, or in Balkan States—instead of that kind of competition, cutthroat competition, one outbidding the other foolishly, recklessly, to the detriment of the public, compelling him to force bonds upon the public at a price which is not determined by the value of that security so much as by his eagerness to get it—that kind of competition I hope is ended.

As far as we are concerned we have always endeavored to observe the rules of fair competition. And I think some other bankers have. I hope most other bankers have. But it is exactly the same, again, as if an architect had built a house for me; no other decent architect would come to me and say, "I can build a better house for you." The architect relies upon his reputation. He will show by what he has done that he has built a better house. I have seen it, no doubt; I pass it every day on my way to my office.

The competition which exists is in my opinion a competition of service and of performance. The competition of attracting clients. Not by chasing after business. Not by trying to get another fellow out of business who is doing business legitimately and well, but by proving to the client that he would do better by coming to me. That has happened.

Senator COSTIGAN. Mr. Kahn, will you describe in greater detail the competition of bankers in Europe to which you made reference a few moments ago?

Mr. KAHN. I am not certain what reference I did make.

Mr. PECORA. You spoke of a dozen or more bankers competing with one another in Belgrade in some ruinous fashion.

Mr. KAHN. Oh, Senator, I beg your pardon. I referred to the competition by American bankers for European and foreign issues in general through the two mad years of 1926 and 1928 when, just as in 1929, nothing counted but pieces of paper, equities; so in the two or three preceding years before that the public had a mania for buying high-interest-bearing bonds.

Senator COSTIGAN. Where were these bankers assembled?

Mr. KAHN. Oh, in all the capitals of the various nations.

Senator COSTIGAN. Were they the leading bankers of the United States?

Mr. KAHN. It is a little ungracious of me to graduate them, Senator. They were bankers engaged in the business of buying securities. And I hope you will not ask me whether they were leading bankers or less leading bankers.

Senator COSTIGAN. Well, among them were there some leading bankers of this country?

Mr. KAHN. I hesitate—I hate to seem evasive to you, and I know I could not if I tried, but would it not be embarrassing and ungracious if I answered that question?

Senator COSTIGAN. Perhaps you will specify who the bankers were.

Mr. KAHN. Personally I do not know all of those bankers. Six years have gone by. I have grown 6 years older. My memory is not as keen as it used to be.

Senator COSTIGAN. Was your firm represented in this competition?

Mr. KAHN. Never, Senator. Not once.

Senator COSTIGAN. You added a statement to the effect that some compulsion was brought by those bankers on others to market the securities, if I understood you. Is that an accurate observation?

Mr. KAHN. I did not mean to imply that, Senator Costigan. I meant to say that the compulsion was rather upon the banker himself. He had the bear by the tail. He had to get rid of him somehow. I will give him credit for believing that he had a bear that was well worth disposing of. But the fact that he had him—the compulsion of getting rid of the bear was upon him.

Senator ADAMS. That would be true of most any bear, would it not, if you had him by the tail?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Senator BARKLEY. As a matter of fact he had a bull by the tail when he thought he had a bear.

Mr. KAHN. That has happened many times, as we all know to our cost. But the fact of the compulsion, and, as I have tried to bring out, by an unduly competitive system, by a cutthroat competitive system, by endeavoring to break in at whatever cost the public is damaged because the public pays an unduly high price. And the banker who has been triumphant in getting that issue will very soon find himself regretful that he did get it. And in any event he will be under the compulsion for his own solvency, to try and get rid of it. Therefore I say that kind of competition is harmful both to the corporations and to the public and to the government involved, because those governments by this very method have seen their credit spoiled, and have also seen money given to them which it would have been very much better if they had never had.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, in answering the question that I put to you a few moments ago I tried to follow your answer, which was illuminating, and I am still uncertain as to whether you intended to inform this committee in your answer that a custom had developed among bankers in pursuance of which a banker will not seek to gain a client whom he recognized already to be a client of some other banker. Has such a custom developed in the banking profession, Mr. Kahn?

Mr. KAHN. I should not say, Mr. Pecora, in the banking profession peculiarly. I should say it has developed more or less in all professions by a process of enlightenment.

Mr. PECORA. Well, we are confining ourselves now to the banking profession. I simply want the committee to know whether or not that custom has developed and exists in the banking profession?

Mr. KAHN. The custom which has developed and which is in the banking profession, and which has long existed among bankers, and not only the top-notch bankers, but among reputable bankers, is that of competing with one another on the basis of their services and their performance. Precisely as the railroads, now that the rates are regulated, can only attract clients by their service and their performance.

The corporations concerned are the ones who determine what bankers they want to deal with. It is not the banker who determines what corporation he wants to deal with. He might like to very much. But it is for the corporation to say, "Well, I am very happy where I am; I have picked that banking house and I will stick to it until they make a mistake. After they make a mistake I will quit it and go to another."

If a railroad corporation or any other corporation comes to us and says "We have determined to terminate our existing financial sponsorship and advice and we would like to get yours", I do not believe we would hesitate to act upon that, in decency, fairly, and with proper regard for our neighbors, whether they be bankers or whatever they may be. But that is our whole method of competition, and has been our whole method of competition always, and it is not merely between us and any one particular banker. It is between us and all bankers. I can give you a few instances—that I would rather not give—but I can give you a few instances where business heretofore done by us has gone to other bankers, and where business heretofore done by other bankers has gone to us. I would rather not mention names, but it has occurred. But our effort, and I hope the effort of all bankers, is that this thing shall be done decently, fairly, with a mutual respect for one another, and not a cutthroat competition, and not an undignified scramble for business.

Mr. PECORA. Then there is not that spirit or kind of competition among bankers which would cause a banker to seek to do the financing for a railroad corporation, for example, when he knows that that railroad corporation in the past has had its financing or banking done by some other banker?

Mr. KAHN. I do not believe, Mr. Pecora, that that is the element which would enter into the conclusion.

Mr. PECORA. Well, whether or not it is the element, is it the fact that bankers do not engage in that competitive kind of business one with another?

Mr. KAHN. I cannot answer yes or no without amplifying my answer by saying there is distinct and keen competition between bankers, but that competition is based not upon one banker trying to undercut the other banker's bid by an eighth or a quarter, but it is based upon services, upon accomplishments, and upon the choice of the corporation in question.

We do not go, and I do not believe any banker usually does go, to corporations of our own initiative. We would say, "These people, we hope, know that we have a good reputation. We hope that if there is business they will come to us." Our minds and our activities are wide open to do business with anybody who comes to us. But we will not chase after business. And I can only speak for ourselves. I cannot speak for other bankers, but I can say for ourselves, we will not chase after business. We will not engage in competition which we consider unfair and from which we consider neither the corporations nor the public benefit. But we welcome eagerly any new opportunity to do business. And it has happened to us that business which we heretofore have done with certain railroads has been done by others henceforth, and it has happened that certain issues heretofore done by large concerns that I could mention, but I prefer not to, have been done by us, because the business came legitimately and fairly.

Mr. PECORA. Well, those instances are relatively few and far between, are they not?

Mr. KAHN. They are relatively few and far between; yes.

Mr. PECORA. And do you know of a case where a prominent banking firm which had done the financing, we will say, for a railroad corporation, loses that client where the banking firm has indicated its willingness to continue financing for that road?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; Mr. Pecora, I do.

Mr. PECORA. Are those instances also relatively very few?

Mr. KAHN. They are relatively few; yes.

Mr. PECORA. Now, to be specific, let us assume that A. B. & Co., a private banking firm of standing and recognized prestige, has done the financing for the X. Y. Z. Railroad, you would not as a banker if you learned that the X. Y. Z. Railroad wanted to borrow, we will say, \$50,000,000, offer your banking services without the consent of A. B. & Co., or unless the X. Y. Z. Railroad originally come to you?

Mr. KAHN. It does not depend upon anybody's consent, Mr. Pecora. It depends—

Mr. PECORA. No; but what has been the custom?

Mr. KAHN. It depends upon our own sense of what is fit and proper and decent to do.

Mr. PECORA. Well, you would not consider such a thing fit and proper and decent to do, would you?

Mr. KAHN. I would not; no.

Mr. PECORA. And that rule is observed generally by bankers, is it not?

Mr. KAHN. I can only speak as to my own firm.

Mr. PECORA. Well, can you not speak also from your knowledge of the banking business generally as to what the rule and custom is?

Mr. KAHN. I can say that I believe generally amongst houses of standing the ethics of the business is not to indulge in cutthroat competition and steal things away the one from the other, unless

there is a situation where the corporation concerned of its own volition or by the good offices of somebody comes and says, "We have determined to change our relations. We have come to you. Are you willing to do it?" "Gladly."

Mr. PECORA. For instance, if you learned that a railroad corporation wanted to borrow \$50,000,000 and you knew that that railroad corporation had had its financing previously done by another banking firm, you would not think of going to that railroad corporation on your own initiative and offering to handle the financing operation, would you?

Mr. KAHN. I think, Mr. Pecora—I hate to take your time and the committee's time any longer than necessary, but I thought I had explained pretty clearly what our attitude in such a case would be.

Mr. PECORA. Well, in order to make sure that the answer is clearly in the record will you answer the question that I put to you, the present question? If you can answer it categorically, I think that will dispose of the question.

(The pending question was thereupon read by the reporter, as above recorded.)

Mr. KAHN. Well, if you want a categorical answer, Mr Pecora, I can only say it is always the other way around; has been with us for 50 years perhaps, or certainly for the last 30 or 40 years. It is not we that go to the corporations and ask them to do business with us. We hope that we have established a reputation which is our show window, which attracts customers. We hope that our trade mark, our sponsorship is recognized of some value to the corporation. We do not go after them. That may be conceited, but we do not. We would rather do less business. We do not go after them. But if a railroad comes to us, or if any corporation comes to us and says: "We want to place a \$50,000,000 issue through you", and we know they have been doing business with somebody else, we ask them fairly and openly the question, "We know that you have been doing business with so and so; are you not doing business any longer with them?" "No, we have severed our connection". Then we consider ourselves entirely free to do their business.

Senator BARKLEY. But, if you knew that in the preliminary stages of the floating of the \$50,000,000 loan they had been under negotiations with some other bank you would not step in voluntarily and seek to take that client away from the other bank?

Mr. KAHN. I would not seek to take any client away from anybody. I am seeking to develop in our own business and my associates are seeking to develop in our own business.

Senator BARKLEY. Is there not a very well developed code of ethics among bankers that one banker will not try to take business away from another banker?

Mr. KAHN. I think it is a well-recognized code of ethics, and it is getting better through the country.

Senator BARKLEY. That is undoubtedly a fact, though, is it not? It seems to me that a very simple proposition which a simple answer would clear up.

Mr. KAHN. I am not prepared to say that it is a fact, Senator. No; I am not.

Senator BARKLEY. Well then, the conditions are not as ethical as you might hope that they could be?

Mr. KAHN. I believe I have already shown that in 1926 to 1928 the conditions were such as I am far from approving. But I believe that especially under the new Recovery Act it will be more and more recognized that that kind of competition is detrimental, and is perhaps slightly unethical. I can speak for ourselves. We do not go after other people's business. We do not go after business at all. We have our shop window, as I call it. If somebody comes to us and says, "I would like to do business with you. I have heretofore done business with John Smith. I would like to do business with you." We would say, "Do you mean to say you have definitely broken with them?" "Yes." "And you tell us you are free, without infringing upon our conscientious scruples, to do business with us?" "Yes." I would not then hesitate to do business.

Senator BARKLEY. Do you know instances where other bankers have gone after your business?

Mr. KAHN. I have some, Senator. I hope you will not press me.

Senator BARKLEY. I am not going to press you, but it has occurred?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Senator BARKLEY. Are they reputable bankers—without giving their names?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Has it succeeded? Has the effort succeeded in those instances?

Mr. KAHN. In some instances, yes. We are poorer for that effort.

Senator BARKLEY. Do you still regard them as reputable bankers?

Mr. KAHN. I regard them as reputable bankers. I would not have done what they did, but who am I to sit in judgment upon others? "Let him who is without sin first cast the stone." I guess I am guilty of other sins, too. But this particular thing I do not believe in.

Mr. PECORA. Would you say fairly, Mr. Kahn, that in the banking profession a system or code of ethics exists among the well-recognized bankers, bankers of reputation, in pursuance of which there is no competition among them for the business of a corporation which has had financing previously done for it by some banker?

Mr. KAHN. As far as we are concerned, that is correct. As far as our firm is concerned, that is correct.

Mr. PECORA. Opinions will differ among individuals honestly and fairly, will they not, as to the measure of risk involved in a piece of financing?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And the measure of risk is an element that enters into the determination of the profit or spread to the banker?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Now, in view of the fact that there is that normal and natural difference of opinion among bankers as to the element of risk involved in a financial operation, and hence as to what should be a fair and reasonable profit or spread to the banker in assuming the risk, would not the corporation seeking financing be likely to obtain better terms if there were more competition among bankers for these financial operations?

Mr. KAHN. You may think I am speaking pro bono in the answer I am going to give. I am too old to have axes to grind. I am trying

to answer according to my best judgment and through long experience, and if the answers I give can be of any service to your committee I shall be only too happy and too satisfied to have been able to be of that little service. And so I hope you will believe me that I am going to answer the question you have asked me, because it is a slight embarrassment, because it affects my pocket for the next few years that I still have, but not for very, very long. I hope that you will be convinced that I am answering without considering my personal or my firm's interest.

I do not believe, Mr. Pecora, that competition of that nature, either public or confined to a few banking houses, would be to the benefit of the corporations.

Perhaps I may be permitted to submit for the record a pamphlet which I wrote on that subject about 10 years ago—and I wrote it myself—and another pamphlet which a distributing house in New York wrote in 1928, quite unknown to me, as I only heard about it a few days ago, that it existed, on the question of competitive bidding. I do not know whether you want to clutter your record with it, but here they are, in case you should wish them.

But to sum up, I think if you have bidding for public issues on the part of the public you are leaning on a broken reed. The public does not bid. The public has proved again and again that you cannot entice it to go into competitive bidding.

Mr. PECORA. But, Mr. Kahn, my question did not involve the element of competitive bidding on the part of the public; it involved the element of competition among bankers for a financing operation.

Mr. KAHN. Well, I was coming to that particular phase of it. If you have competition amongst bankers for a certain issue you create what to my mind is one of the most undesirable conditions which you could create in the investment community, namely, bidding at the expense of the public.

If I make a bid, if any reputable house makes a bid, he knows he must consider for his own reputation both the interest of the corporation, to whom it must make a fair bid—if it does not make a fair bid it will lose the business—and the interest of the public to whom it must make a fair offer or it will lose the public clientele.

But if you stimulate me by saying, "Now, there are a dozen bidders bidding for that thing", you screw yourself up, screw yourself up a quarter percent, half percent, 1 percent, you will get rid of it to the public. I am gambling with the back of the public. I am damaging the public for my benefit. In order to enable me to retain that business I am bidding a price which is an unduly high price. That unduly high price does not do the community any good, because ultimately the price will find its own level. It does not do the corporation any good, because the price will go down and the corporation will lose a part of its public good will.

I do not see in what way that kind of competition has more good than harm in it.

Mr. PECORA. Has it been tried out so that that effect has been observed?

Mr. KAHN. I beg your pardon?

Mr. PECORA. Has that kind of competition been indulged in or tried out?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

MR. PECORA. So that you can point to that effect that you are now referring to?

MR. KAHN. That effect is set forth in those two pamphlets at some length, but I do not want to impose them upon you by reading them.

SENATOR BARKLEY. I think it would be valuable to have those pamphlets printed in the record, and I ask that they be printed as a part of the hearing.

THE CHAIRMAN. Without objection, they will be admitted and filed and carried in the record, both of them, and marked as exhibits.

(Pamphlet presented by Mr. Kahn entitled "The Marketing of American Railroad Securities, Memorandum for the Interstate Commerce Commission submitted by Kuhn, Loeb & Co.", dated October 25, 1922, was thereupon marked "Committee Exhibit 1, June 27, 1933." See p. 1034.

(Pamphlet presented by Mr. Kahn, entitled "Competitive Bidding for Equipment Trusts, A Discussion", written by Ernest L. Nye, Freeman & Co., New York, in 1928, was thereupon marked "Committee Exhibit 2, June 27, 1933." See p. 1052.

MR. PECORA. We will read those pamphlets, but they are rather voluminous documents, I am afraid. Can you give us your own judgment with regard to the matters that I am questioning you about and not refer us at this time to these two pamphlets?

MR. KAHN. Gladly. Gladly, Mr. Pecora. I am sorry I interrupted my answer.

I say as far as the public is concerned that kind of competition is, and has proved, especially during 1926 and 1928, exceedingly costly to the public, because it is more than human nature to expect that under the stimulus of having a price hung up someone, in order to get that price, is not going to pay a price which is not justified by the circumstances.

MR. PECORA. Do you think a banker would pay a price not justified by the circumstances?

MR. KAHN. Frequently.

MR. PECORA. And he has remained in the banking business after frequently making those mistakes?

MR. KAHN. He has remained in the banking business not as prosperous as he was before, but the public had paid the price in the meantime. The public had bought those bonds.

Moreover, Mr. Pecora, I want to say there is a constant check. The corporations are not dependent upon them for telling them "Your bonds are worth so much." The corporations, and especially the financial officers of the corporations, have a very definite duty to go around and inform themselves what is a fair price. The railroad corporations have not only a very definite duty, but a legal duty, because the Interstate Commerce Commission has to approve what is a fair price and what price they are willing to sanction. It is not because I impress my views on corporations. We have constant competition, the potential competition of every other banking house, and if the particular official in question should lunch with Mr. Brown and say, "Here, we have your bond to sell. What do you think it is worth?" Mr. Brown says, "I think it is worth 95", and I have told him I think it is worth 92, I do not think it is likely to come back to me very frequently. There is a constant competition.

Mr. PECORA. Your judgment might be the better of the two?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; but unfortunately he might not take it, and it might be bad for him not to take it, because I do not believe that it is in the best interest of a corporation always to squeeze out the last dollar at a particular moment that the securities can be sold for, because whom do they squeeze it out of? They do not squeeze it out of the banker. I get exactly the same commission whether I sell a bond at 95 or sell a bond at 92½. But the public is paying an unfair price. My capacity to serve industry—and that is really the whole test of a private banker's usefulness—

Senator ADAMS (interposing). Mr. Kahn, that result only comes about in the event that you are able to definitely force the public to pay the added price to cover the commission, does it not? That is, that assumes that you can fix the price so as to cover the commission?

Mr. KAHN. I cannot fix the price to cover the commission, but as a matter of fact, in order to enable me to go ahead and do my business I have got to have a certain spread, which is not a commission; but I have to have a certain spread in order to compensate my distributors.

Senator ADAMS. Can you fix the spread or fix the price to the public so that you will secure that spread, or are you held back by the occasional unwillingness of the public to take the offer?

Mr. KAHN. Sometimes it is held back by an occasional unwillingness of the public, but generally speaking it is a recognized fact that the public will buy bonds that are offered to it by recognized distributors and recognized banking houses at a fair rate and a rate which is attractive to the public.

Senator ADAMS. That is, the public as a practice will accept the price which is fixed by the banking house?

Mr. KAHN. Under responsible sponsorship, yes, because that is where your securities bill comes in now, that henceforth the public will know about those facts.

Senator ADAMS. May I ask you: This pamphlet which you offer, Mr. Kahn, was written in 1922, I notice.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Senator ADAMS. Is there anything in the experiences of the years since then to change the conclusions which you have expressed in that pamphlet?

Mr. KAHN. If I had to write it again I would write it exactly the same way. I would change a few words.

Senator ADAMS. You were a fortunate man, that you did not have to learn anything like the rest of us.

Mr. KAHN. But as to this particular thing, I think my convictions are so deep-seated and so long, and my observation is an observation of 40 years, not only here but in Europe, in various countries in Europe, that I do not believe I am open to reconsideration, even though I may seem obstinate about it.

I really do believe I know that subject. I have seen it work in England, in France, in Germany, and I have seen that they have always come back in those countries to the same system; that if I want a plumber's job done I go to the plumber that I think is the best fellow, and as long as he does his job well I stick to him. If he

overcharges me I go to somebody else. If he tries any crooked business on me I go to somebody else.

But generally speaking, I do not gain much by having people compete with one another on what at best can only be a trifling difference.

And that is so in England; it is so in France; it is so in Germany; it is so in Holland and Belgium, that the corporations pick out the men of the firm that they want to do business with, and as long as they are satisfied and the service is good to them and they do not believe, and the experience has been—as far as I have had experience, that is over 40 years—has proven, that they have nothing to gain by inviting competition other than based on performances and services, they will continue with that firm.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, who fixes the price to the public of these issues that are underwritten by bankers for railroad corporations?

Mr. KAHN. That price is fixed between the corporation and the banking house to which they go, and it is fixed by comparison of views, and sometimes those views are very wide apart. Ultimately a conclusion is reached as to what is fair to the corporation, what is fair to the public, and at what price can the issue be sold successfully. It certainly would not be to the corporation's interest to force the issue to be sold at a price where it would be a failure, because then it would be soiled goods and would not be salable any more.

Mr. PECORA. Well, let us see: First the banker negotiates with the railroad corporations for an issue, doesn't he?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And the price to the banker is fixed as a result of such negotiations?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And that is the price that the railroad corporation receives for its securities?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Thereafter the price at which that security is sold to the public is primarily of concern to the banker, isn't it?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. So that, if there is a conflict or difference of opinion between the banker and the railroad company as to the price at which the security shall be offered to the public, the banker's judgment would usually control, would it not?

Mr. KAHN. It would usually control, except in the case of railroad securities, where the Interstate Commerce Commission's judgment absolutely controls. The Interstate Commerce Commission absolutely says: "If you are putting on a spread more than so-and-so we will disapprove it." In the case of railroad securities that element simply does not exist. It is definitely fixed by the Interstate Commerce Commission.

Mr. PECORA. If the Interstate Commerce Commission then fixes the price of the security to the public—

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And I understand that is what you mean to tell us—

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Then why could not there be a free competition among bankers for the financial operation for the railroad company in fashion calculated to produce a narrowing of the spread and a consequent benefit to the railroad company?

Mr. KAHN. For the reasons, Mr. Pecora, which I have endeavored to indicate, that somebody would depress that spread to a point where it would be, instead of being beneficial, damaging, because it would be a cut rate, it would be a cut price, it would drive reputable, responsible concerns more and more out of the business, and the result would be a diminished protection for the public.

Mr. PECORA. How does the public interest become diminished by those means, if the price to the public is fixed by the Interstate Commerce Commission?

Mr. KAHN. The public interest is diminished—and I assume that is why the Interstate Commerce Commission is interested in that spread—the moment that its service rendered to it is not rendered in the best possible way. The moment that the railroad concerned has not got the best advice as to the kind of security which it should issue, as to the mortgage which should be drawn, as to the instruments which should be prepared for the future, as to its clientele, as to its selling, if it could not get that service, and the people who render that service—and it is a year-round service—if it could not get the service of me and my associates, and we did not get a fee, after having given hours and days of time and thought to this matter, another concern would take the business away from us. The service which the investment banker now gives the railroads would be absolutely cut off, if, after having given the service, we haven't got a fair percent to do business from the railroad to which we have rendered great services and have advised.

Now, you may say that service is worth nothing. My experience and my belief is that service is a very valuable service.

Mr. PECORA. There has been no indication by anybody around this table that the service of the investment banker is worth nothing. But under this method that you have been testifying about, that is, with this absence of competition among investment bankers—

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Is not the spread to the banker placed largely within the control of the banker, because of that absence of competition?

Mr. KAHN. No; it is placed within the control of the Interstate Commerce Commission.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know of a single case where the Interstate Commerce Commission has disapproved a price of a security to the public because the spread to the banker was too small?

Mr. KAHN. I do not recall at this moment. I have very good—[After conferring with associates.] No.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know of instances where the I.C.C. has disapproved the price to the public because the spread to the banker was too large?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, informally.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recognize the fact that the presence of a free competition among investment bankers for the financing of a railroad company operation would have a tendency to reduce the spread to the banker?

Mr. KAHN. For a while, but only for a while. I think there is no guaranty whatsoever that what has now become a recognized norm amongst reputable bankers and what the Interstate Commerce Commission constantly watches, would remain permanently unused. I do not for a moment believe it would. Perhaps I can give an instance which one of my associates has just put before me to show the futility of that kind of competition.

On July 14, 1928, the Southern Pacific Co. sent invitations to 60 banks and bankers inviting bids on an issue of \$4,815,000 of its equipment trust certificates. Kuhn, Loeb & Co. were also invited, but in accordance with our usual practice, along with others who were unwilling to make those bids for the certificates, we also wrote that if the company did not receive from others satisfactory service we should be prepared nevertheless to continue to serve the needs of the company.

Only three bids were received, the highest of which was $97\frac{1}{4}$ percent, which meant an annual percent of cost to the company of about 4.94 percent.

Those bids being unsatisfactory, they were rejected. On July 24, when advised by the Southern Pacific Co. as to the result of these bids, we offered to purchase the certificates at $98\frac{1}{4}$ instead of $97\frac{1}{4}$, which was the best bid that they received by competition between 60 firms. We offered to pay $98\frac{1}{4}$, and we promptly sold the certificates.

Mr. PECORA. Is that an exceptional case, Mr. Kahn?

Mr. KAHN. My partner just tells me that happened in other cases. For instance, in the Cincinnati Union Station Co. issue. We are speaking about something as to which naturally I can only put my experience and judgment against the questions which you are asking.

My experience and judgment and my absolute conviction is that if you control the spread your corporations in the long run would not gain anything. You would drive out the most responsible and reputable bankers. We would not bid—I beg your pardon for including ourselves among responsible and reputable bankers—but I know we would not bid. We do not do business on those lines. It is not the kind of business which we believe is compatible with dignity, and with the hard work done and with the services performed all the year round by a banker, and those services cannot be performed from one day to the next; they must be learned. They required the accumulated experience of three generations in our case. We pay for them by steady application to our job. We pay for them by not letting ourselves be distracted from our job. We pay for them by not going into things which would distract us from our job.

Just as if you have a suit of clothes to buy, you would have to pay to one tailor much more than you pay to another tailor. It is the same. The suit keeps you warm if you buy it from a cheap tailor, too. But the other tailor puts the experience and the reputation of making good suits into it, and you go to him.

Now, my definite conviction is that by limiting the spread the corporation gains nothing. The reputable bankers are eliminated. The services which are now freely at the disposal of corporations

without their paying anything for it except an occasional business, but otherwise no fee is charged to them; any of our connections can come to our office and can sit there for days and days and come again and again and they will get our best advice for the corporation and they will pay us nothing for it whatsoever—no fee, no retainer. We rely upon doing business once in a while. If that is taken away from us we would not do it.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, is it your judgment and experience that competition among bankers for the financing, we will say, of a railroad corporation would have a tendency to reduce the spread to the banker?

Mr. KAHN. I do not.

Mr. PECORA. Is it your judgment and experience that that competition would have a tendency to increase the spread to the banker?

Mr. KAHN. I do not believe it would have any material effect.

Mr. PECORA. It would not have any effect on the spread of any material consequence one way or the other?

Mr. KAHN. It might in a few cases. It would not generally, and I believe the price which you would pay for that advantage, if it is an advantage, is much too high. I think the corporations and the public would suffer from it.

Mr. PECORA. How would they suffer, Mr. Kahn?

Mr. KAHN. They would suffer from it by losing—I beg your pardon. [After conferring with associates.] Mr. Pecora, I think it is conceivable that in a few cases, at the beginning particularly, but in a few cases the spread between what the corporation gets and what the public gets might be diminished. I do not dispute the possibility of that existing. I do not believe it would exist for long, but I believe there is a possibility of its existing. I do not believe that the spread in city bonds, for instance, has been materially modified by public competition or by competition between bidders.

Mr. PECORA. Have you any figures which would determine that one way or the other, or any instances?

What illustrations of any kind have you that would support the belief you have just expressed, that in the case of competitive biddings on municipal issues the price to the municipality has not been materially affected?

Mr. KAHN. I do not say so much as to the price to the municipality, because some one may have paid a very foolish price. I say, the spread to the public. If you get, by a lucky chance, a municipal issue at various prices you are going to offer it to the public, not on the basis of the price you paid; you are going to offer it to the public on the basis of the price which you believe it is worth, and therefore this does not determine it in any way.

Mr. PECORA. Would it not in such a case cause a person to make a higher bid for the issue if he thought he could dispose of it at an attractive profit to the public because it was worth that price?

Mr. KAHN. The reverse of that holds good equally. If I have no responsibility, if I am one of a number of bidders, I will try to buy as cheaply as I can, naturally. I have no responsibility; it is not my job to see that the railroads get the best possible price or that clients get the best possible price, as long as they are not my clients, as long as they are outsiders and I am an outsider. I will give you a case in point, Mr. Pecora.

Not so very long ago some of our clients wanted to sell bonds, wanted to sell them to us at 89. They were 4½-percent bonds or maybe 5-percent bonds—5-percent bonds, at 89. We told them we did not believe they would be wise in doing that, that “I think if you wait a little while you should get a much better price for them. The bond market just at present is not receptive. Take our tip and wait.” They waited, and within a relatively short time those bonds which they wanted to sell to us at 89 they received 97 for. If there had been competition I would have been delighted to buy them at 89. I knew they were too cheap.

Senator ADAMS. Mr. Kahn, in this pamphlet, not the one lying by you, but the other pamphlet you handed in, there is contained quite a large number of letters on the subject of competitive bidding. I notice the letters are from dealers in securities, and they are all, or practically all, saying that they are opposed to competitive bidding because it results in over-buying securities or in lessening the margin to the dealers so that they cannot afford to deal in them, and thereby, they say, it is going to lessen the market.

Mr. KAHN. That is the very thing I was trying to bring out, that unless you pay the laborer what his hire is worth, if you compel people to go the limit in bidding at prices that they can just barely get away with, I do not believe you are serving anybody. The corporations, in the long run, will not be benefited. I am sure they will not be. I know that the most responsible bankers will not enter that kind of business, and I know that the railroads will be deprived of the service of the advice of their bankers, which advice is based upon generations of special study, and that they will be deprived of the advice of people whom they can rely upon in telling them what is the best time to sell bonds, for instance, telling them, “In a month or two a lot of other bonds are coming out. Hurry up and sell these bonds.” You cannot get all these services unless the people who give you such services have a reasonable assurance that if the railroad has any business it will come to them.

Mr. PECORA. In the course of an answer that you made a few moments back you said, among other things, that you tried to get a security or an issue at as low a price as possible. That is quite natural, but—

Mr. KAHN. My partner suggests that I did not say I tried, but I said I would be delighted if I had an opportunity of getting a bond away below its value unless I have the responsibility for it. But if I have the responsibility for it, I will not let the corporation sell the bonds, if I have the power to prevent it, below their value. I tell them that such and such is my opinion.

Mr. PECORA. Let us go back to the answer you made. I think you said that in the course of an answer you were making to the question immediately prior to the question that Senator Adams asked you.

Mr. Reporter, will you go back to the answer immediately before Senator Adams' question, and read what the witness said?

(The reporter read as follows:)

Mr. KAHN. The reverse of that holds good equally. If I have no responsibility, if I am one of a number of bidders, I will try to buy as cheaply as I can, naturally.

Mr. PECORA. In saying that, were you referring to the attitude of the banker in case of competitive bidding for an issue?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Is it also the attitude of the banker where it concerns an issue without competition?

Mr. KAHN. No; it is not. It may seem quixotic, but it is good business that it should not be. A banker can only persist before the public and the corporations if they believe they can get a fair deal from it. I am not speaking as an altruist, but I think I know my business sufficiently to know that it rests entirely upon confidence. Since I have nothing else to offer but confidence, if I betray that confidence or, even without betraying it, if I make a mistake once or twice, they will say, "We will stop doing business with you; we will go elsewhere."

Mr. PECORA. The judgment, then, which controls as to the matter of giving a fair deal to the public is the judgment of the banker where there is no competition?

Mr. KAHN. No, Mr. Pecora. It is the banker's judgment. But the corporation is under a very definite duty to see that the judgment is right, and if it is not right, to decline to accept it. Moreover, the corporation is under a definite duty to submit such judgment to the Interstate Commerce Commission. There are three checks.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, I understand that you were requested to produce here a copy of the articles of copartnership which bind together the members of your firm. Are you prepared to do that?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Will you kindly produce a copy of those articles?

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. Mr. Chairman, I have here the original copartnership agreement. I do not want to take up the time of the committee in making any motion. We have already communicated with Mr. Pecora's office. We hope that this original agreement will be considered by the committee in executive session, and that when it comes to be spread on the record certain things as to the contribution of capital, the division of profit, and other minor matters which we have submitted in another part of the records which I will also hand up, may be omitted from the record.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. de Gersdorff's firm has taken that up with us, Mr. Chairman, and I have expressed the opinion, feeling that I represented also the attitude of the committee, that for the public record we need only take a copy of the articles of copartnership which have deleted the respective rights and interests of the copartners and their respective contributions to the capital of the firm.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. There are certain other minor provisions which we hope will be deleted, which do not concern anybody or anything except the relations between the parties. I would be very glad to take that up with you or with the chairman. I have the original in full.

The CHAIRMAN. You do not have a copy of the one with the deleted portions?

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. Yes; I have both of them here.

The CHAIRMAN. Are you willing that that should go into the record?

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. Yes, sir.

The CHAIRMAN. The other copy you will leave with the committee to consider in executive session?

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. I suggest that that course be taken.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. Do you want the original or just a copy?

The CHAIRMAN. We do not care about the original copy.

Mr. PECORA. A complete copy of the original will suffice for the purposes of the committee in executive session, and a copy with the deletions which you have referred to will suffice for the public record, I assume.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. The copies that I have here have not the signatures. I suppose you want them?

Mr. PECORA. For the executive session?

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. I can write them in now and will hand them to you.

The CHAIRMAN. Let the copy be admitted for the record.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. Do you want the original before you?

Mr. PECORA. I am not going to use it in the examination for the moment.

Senator BARKLEY. You may present it later.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. We will give it to you at the recess.

The CHAIRMAN. It will be admitted later.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. I am perfectly willing to give a deleted copy to the press.

Mr. PECORA. I am going to offer it in evidence now and ask that it be spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. That may be done.

(A copy of articles of copartnership dated Dec. 31, 1932, by and between Felix M. Warburg, Otto H. Kahn, George W. Bovenizer, Lewis L. Strauss, William Wiseman, Frederick M. Warburg, Gilbert W. Kahn, John M. Schiff, Benjamin J. Bottenwieser, Hugh Knowlton, and Elisha Walker, was received in evidence, marked "Committee Exhibit No. 3, June 27, 1933. See p. 1080.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, you have already testified that your firm, while it does not solicit deposits, nevertheless does accept them from its clients?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Let me ask you now what has been the highest amount of deposit accounts that your firm has carried for its clients?

Mr. KAHN. I have the figures here, and I will get them from my partners.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. That only goes back to 1927.

Mr. KAHN. Mr. Pecora, I find from the papers which I have here and which I will be glad to submit in detail in reply to your question, that the highest total deposits which we held on December 31 of any one year was \$88,549,566.

Mr. PECORA. That was for the fiscal year 1929?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Have you furnished me upon my request with balance sheets of your firm showing its financial condition as of the end of each fiscal year from the period between 1927 and 1931, both of those years inclusive?

Mr. KAHN. I so understand, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. I show this document to you, consisting of a number of typewritten sheets, and ask you if that is a correct copy of those balance sheets for those years.

Mr. KAHN. We are sure they are right.

Mr. PECORA. I offer that in evidence, Mr. Chairman, and ask that it be spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. It will be admitted.

(Copies of balance sheets of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. for the period between 1927 and 1931, both inclusive, were received in evidence, marked "Committee Exhibit No. 4, June 27, 1933." See p. 1085.)

The CHAIRMAN. Have you any affiliates?

Mr. KAHN. No, sir; we have not and never had.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know a concern called the European Merchants Banking Co., Ltd., of London?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Is the firm of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. in any way directly or indirectly connected with that concern?

Mr. KAHN. Perhaps one of my partners could go into that matter of detail more accurately than I could. May I ask Mr. Bittenwieser to answer that particular question?—because it is more in the line of his knowledge than of mine.

The CHAIRMAN. That will be agreeable.

Mr. PECORA. All right, if you will answer that question, Mr. Bittenwieser.

The CHAIRMAN. Please stand and be sworn.

TESTIMONY OF BENJAMIN J. BUTTENWIESER, A MEMBER OF THE FIRM OF KUHN, LOEB & CO.

The CHAIRMAN. You solemnly swear that you will tell the truth, the whole truth, and nothing but the truth, regarding the matters now under consideration by the committee, so help you God?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do.

Mr. PECORA. Will you give your name and address to the reporter, please?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Benjamin J. Bittenwieser.

Mr. PECORA. Are you a member of the firm of Kuhn, Loeb & Co.?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. One of the copartners thereof?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. How long have you been a member of that firm as a copartner?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Since January 1, 1932.

Mr. PECORA. Prior to that time had you been connected with the firm in any other capacity than as a partner?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. For what period of time?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Since September 1918.

Mr. PECORA. In what capacity?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. In varying capacities, starting pretty far down the line.

Mr. PECORA. Will you just briefly enumerate them?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I think, like Mr. Kahn once said, pretty close to the line of licking postage stamps, through varying capacities; but at the time of your inquiry, head of the foreign department.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know a concern called the European Merchants Banking Co., Ltd.?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Is the firm of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. connected with that concern in any way, shape, or form?

Mr. KAHN. The answer is, No. We are in no way connected with that firm. Excuse me for interrupting. We are in no way connected with that firm and have not been since 1930. We were connected with that firm for 3 years. Mr. Buttenwieser will give you the details.

Mr. PECORA. That is what I wanted.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That was a stock corporation of which we owned the shares. It was in existence from March 31, 1927, to December 31, 1930, during which period we owned the shares of that company; the ordinary shares.

Mr. PECORA. What was the business of that company?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I believe that was called "merchant bankers."

Mr. PECORA. What was its business?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is the current name in England for such bankers, merchant bankers.

Mr. PECORA. Was it a private banking concern?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Accepting deposits from clients or customers and making loans?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Relatively small.

The CHAIRMAN. You owned all the shares?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. We owned all the ordinary shares. There were some few other shares, I believe, which, under the laws of England, had to be owned over there.

Mr. PECORA. Qualifying shares?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I believe that was it. I understand there were 5,000 manager shares which had to be owned in England, by Mr. Godron Leith, who was our resident partner.

Mr. PECORA. Has the company been liquidated?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. When?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. December 31, 1930.

Mr. PECORA. In the questionnaire which I caused to be submitted to your firm in behalf of the committee I asked for a copy of the balance sheet of that company, and I was furnished with this document [indicating]. Will you kindly look at it, Mr. Buttenwieser, and tell me if you can identify it as being a true copy of balance sheets of the European Merchants Banking Co.?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I have no doubt it is correct.

Mr. PECORA. I offer this in evidence.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted and entered on the minutes.

(A copy of balance sheets of European Merchants Banking Co., Ltd., was received in evidence marked "Committee Exhibit No. 5, June 27, 1933." See p. 1086.)

Mr. PECORA. I will now resume the examination of Mr. Kahn on another subject.

Senator GORE. Were you going to go to another subject now, Mr. Pecora?

Mr. PECORA. Yes, Senator Gore.

Senator GORE. I wanted to ask this, Mr. Chairman, with your permission. I want it developed in the record somewhere, if not in

this connection in some other connection, the fact of Mr. Paul Warburg's activities in organizing the International Acceptance Bank. I think it was granted by Congress rediscount privileges with the Federal Reserve bank. It then formed a connection with some other bank in New York, the name of which has slipped my mind. What was it, Mr. Kahn?

Mr. KAHN. I suppose, Senator, what you are referring to is that later on it was absorbed by the Bank of Manhattan Co.

Senator GORE. Yes; that is it. I thought it was the Bank of Manhattan, but I was not sure enough to say so. I think this International Acceptance Bank has gone out of existence now, perhaps. I have had some information about it which seems like an interesting chapter, and I wish, Mr. Pecora, you would develop that sooner or later.

One other question, Mr. Chairman. I notice in this morning's paper a portion of Mr. Wilkins' testimony out in Detroit. I believe it was last night. It was in regard to the withdrawal of deposits and the clearing of certain checks after the holiday was declared. I want to ask now if that comes within the purview of your plans to develop that sooner or later.

Mr. PECORA. Senator Gore, may I ask you to repeat that? I was conferring with one of my associates.

Senator GORE. I noticed in the paper last night some reference to the clearing of checks in Detroit after the holiday had gone into effect. It was in the testimony of Mr. Wilkins. I do not know upon what foundation he bases his testimony. It seems to me that it would be worth looking into, because he alleges—upon what ground I do not know—that certain interests in New York deliberately closed those banks and brought about the crash, in order to embarrass Mr. Ford. I do not know whether that is true or not. It grew out of the investigation or the testimony of Mr. Wilkins before the grand jury. If there is any foundation to it, it ought to be developed, and if there is not, it ought to be developed—in either case, because it creates a terribly bad impression if it is untrue, and if it is true it is a matter of the highest importance.

The CHAIRMAN. I do not know whether Mr. Kahn knows anything about that or not.

Senator GORE. I am not on this committee, but I just dropped in, and I hope the chairman will pardon me for the interruption.

The CHAIRMAN. If Mr. Kahn has any information on that subject, the committee would be glad to hear it.

Mr. KAHN. I am afraid that I have no information on the subject. The International Acceptance Bank was formed by Mr. Paul Warburg as his personal venture and the venture of some of his friends, many years after he ceased to be a partner in my firm. That was after he left his official position in Washington. I could not possibly of my own knowledge testify to that.

Senator GORE. I knew you could not, Mr. Kahn, but I thought you might put into the record suggestions that would enable Mr. Pecora to develop the history of it.

Mr. KAHN. I am afraid that of my own knowledge I know of no way in which I could be helpful in that connection. I would be only too glad to be, if I could.

The CHAIRMAN. Have you any information regarding the Detroit matter that Senator Gore inquires about?

Mr. KAHN. No information of that or of any similar character came to my knowledge.

TESTIMONY OF OTTO H. KAHN, A MEMBER OF THE FIRM OF KUHN, LOEB & CO., NEW YORK CITY—Resumed

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, are there any meetings of the partners of your firm that are held at regular intervals for the transaction of the business of the firm?

Mr. KAHN. No, sir; we have no regular meeting of that kind. It varies. Once in a while we meet fairly regularly, twice a week or three times a week, when business happens to be active. Much more frequently we have no such meetings. I should say that the proportion between the years when we have such meetings and when we have no such meetings regularly, would be about one to five. I think, five times when we have no such meetings to one time when we have such a meeting.

Mr. PECORA. Are any written records or memoranda maintained of the proceedings at those meetings or conferences of the partners, Mr. Kahn?

Mr. KAHN. No, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Have they ever been?

Mr. KAHN. Never.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, has there been any reason, any special reason, for not recording those proceedings by way of any written record?

Mr. KAHN. None whatever. The mere fact that they were held so irregularly proves that they were nothing but exchanges of opinion, that there were no new resolutions of any kind passed. For instance, if one partner had something in mind which he wanted all of the partners to know he would ask that a meeting be held. But there is no significance to the meetings. They are thoroughly informal and merely informative.

Mr. PECORA. Well, because they are informative wouldn't certain advantages be served by keeping a written record of those proceedings?

Mr. KAHN. I do not believe so, Mr. Pecora. That has not been our experience. We are a family affair. A number of us sit close together all day long, and we know pretty well what goes on. But once in a while, and sometimes more than once in a while, sometimes regularly for 2 or 3 or 4 weeks, there is a tacit understanding that we will have meetings. Then we find out, after having observed those meetings for 3 or 4 weeks, that we are wasting our time, and that too much is said, too much talk is indulged in, that everyone wants to "shoot off his face", so to speak.

Senator BARKLEY. Sometimes what you might say is like the Senate?

Mr. KAHN. Well, Senator Barkley, I would not dare say that.

Mr. PECORA. But the Senate's proceedings are duly recorded.

Mr. KAHN. And then we drop them again. We find that no useful purpose is served by making any formal record of such meetings, and we have never done so.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, is your firm subjected to examination with respect to its banking business by any public officer or authority either of the State of New York where its office is located or of the United States?

Mr. KAHN. No, sir. I know that you are familiar, much more familiar than I, with the laws of the State of New York in respect to private bankers' accepting deposits, and under the definition of that law we have accepted no such deposits and therefore are subject to no such examination.

Mr. PECORA. That is, you have conformed to those provisions of the banking laws of the State of New York which do not subject your firm to examination or inspection at the hands of the State superintendent of banks of New York?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know whether or not counsel for your firm had any part in the drafting of those provisions of the banking law of the State of New York?

Mr. KAHN. Not to my knowledge; but it might well be so. I know that one of my partners was consulted about it, and it is quite the reasonable thing that he consulted one of counsel. But I do not really know, of my own knowledge. I do not know, because I was not consulted.

Mr. PECORA. Don't you know, or have you heard, rather, that counsel for your firm appeared with or collaborated with counsel for other private banking firms in the city of New York and helped to draft the legislation which is now on the statute books of the State of New York with regard to private bankers?

Mr. KAHN. Not to my knowledge, Mr. Pecora, but it may well be so.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recognize any disadvantages that would attach to your firm in the conduct of its business if it were subjected to examination by the State superintendent of banks of New York in the same fashion that commercial banks, State banks in New York are subjected to examination by the State superintendent of banks?

Mr. KAHN. Isn't that water over the dam, Mr. Pecora, under the new laws that have been enacted?

Mr. PECORA. Well, I am not so sure that it is, but at any rate I should like to have your answer.

Mr. KAHN. Well, my answer is that as far as examination is concerned, I personally—and I haven't conferred with my partners about it—but I personally see no reason why we should not be examined.

Mr. PECORA. Has that always been your attitude or state of mind on that subject?

Mr. KAHN. I do not really know when I last gave it consideration, but I should think, knowing my slant of mind, that it probably has always been my attitude.

Mr. PECORA. Well, whether or not that was always your attitude, the fact is that the actual conduct of your banking business has been such as to avoid examination by the State superintendent of banks in New York, hasn't it?

Mr. KAHN. May I respectfully object to the use of the word "avoid"?

Mr. PECORA. Or it has been such as not to subject yourselves legally to such examination, if I may put it that way.

Mr. KAHN. Well, there was certainly no conscious avoidance of it.

Mr. PECORA. I am willing to let you use your own terminology in describing the fact.

Mr. KAHN. The fact is that there was no conscious avoidance. It simply happens that our business, which is not to solicit deposits, and not to take small deposits, and not having deposits subject to check, did not fall within the province of the law which would have implied an examination by the State superintendent of banks.

Mr. PECORA. Wasn't that provision put in the law for the benefit of a few private banking firms, to your knowledge?

Mr. KAHN. To my knowledge; no. Moreover, it would not appear to be to their benefit in my humble opinion. I see no benefit in not being examined.

Mr. PECORA. You could still have placed a limitation, a minimum amount on deposits that you would receive, and be subject to examination if it were not for that provision of the law; isn't that so?

Mr. KAHN. If it had not been for that provision of the law; yes.

The CHAIRMAN. Are your deposits time deposits or demand deposits, or what?

Mr. KAHN. Our deposits (conferring with associates) my partners tell me, and this is a little bit beyond my own activities in the firm; but they tell me that they change, sometimes being time deposits and sometimes being demand deposits. There is no definite rule either the one way or the other.

Senator BARKLEY. You say they are not subject to check?

Mr. KAHN. Pardon me, Senator, but I did not hear your question.

Senator BARKLEY. Did you say a moment ago that your deposits are not subject to check?

Mr. KAHN. They are not subject to check in any ordinary understanding of that term; no.

Senator BARKLEY. How does a depositor get his money out of your institution?

Mr. KAHN. He asks for it.

Senator BARKLEY. Sir?

Mr. KAHN. He asks for it and we transfer it to him.

Senator BARKLEY. Well, there has to be some written order, I suppose, in order to get it?

Mr. KAHN. It is subject to his order, but it is not subject to check as that term is generally understood. That is, as far as anyone except individual partners and relatives of the firm are concerned, no one possesses Kuhn, Loeb & Co. check books. If they want their money they ask for it and they get it.

Mr. PECORA. At any time?

Mr. KAHN. At any time, unless it is a time deposit.

Senator BARKLEY. And in that case you issue a Kuhn, Loeb & Co. check to the depositor?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Senator BARKLEY. And he cashes that check somewhere else?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir. But it would go, probably, through our bank in the ordinary course of events.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, are your depositors corporations?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; and some, quite a number of them, hold European connections, banks that leave certain amounts here on deposit, but no very great amount at any one time. And yet we have quite a number of European depositors with whom we have had business relations for many years. And we have small amounts with them, and they have small amounts with us.

The CHAIRMAN. You do not have any savings deposits?

Mr. KAHN. I beg your pardon, Senator Fletcher?

The CHAIRMAN. Have you any savings deposits, Mr. Kahn?

Mr. KAHN. No, sir.

Senator BARKLEY. Does every member of your firm make a financial contribution, or put in a certain amount of money as though he were buying stock in a corporation, when he becomes a partner?

Mr. KAHN. No, sir. The articles of incorporation make that perfectly plain—or, my attention has been called to a misuse of a term there. I should have said the articles of copartnership make that perfectly plain. But whether he does or does not make a deposit, his liability so far as the firm is concerned is unlimited.

Senator BARKLEY. I understand. But a man is taken into the firm for what he may be worth as an addition to it and not by reason of what he puts into it by way of money; is that it?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Senator BARKLEY. Where he might put in money, or in case he does not, upon what basis does he share in the profits?

Mr. KAHN. Upon a basis which is determined by mutual agreement.

Senator BARKLEY. Is that basis set out in the articles of copartnership?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Senator BARKLEY. And those articles are changed every time you take in a new partner or lose one?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, in the questionnaire which I submitted to your firm in behalf of this committee some time ago, I asked for the number of corporations engaged in interstate commerce having bank deposits with your firm, and the total amount of such corporation deposits at the end of each calendar year during the 5-year period from 1927 to 1931, both inclusive.

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. I show you this typewritten document, and ask you if that constitutes the answer prepared by your firm and the correct answer to that question.

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Chairman, I offer that in evidence and ask that it may be spread on the record of the hearings.

The CHAIRMAN. It will be received and will be made a part of the record by the committee reporter.

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 6

QUESTION NO. 21

Total amount of deposits of corporations engaged in interstate commerce at the end of each of the calendar years 1927-31, inclusive, and the number of such corporations

Year ending—	Number of corporations	Total deposits
1927.....	14	\$24, 151, 503. 54
1928.....	17	33, 338, 974. 89
1929.....	18	59, 703, 040. 79
1930.....	19	31, 245, 767. 37
1931.....	15	12, 891, 901. 47

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, question no. 22 of the questionnaire which I submitted to your firm in behalf of this committee asked for the names of all corporations engaged in interstate commerce having banking deposits with you in excess of \$50,000 during that same 5-year period. And I received this document, which I now show you, as an answer to that question. Will you kindly look at it and tell us if that constitutes a correct and complete answer to that question?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. I offer that in evidence and ask that it be spread on the record of the committee's hearings.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted and be made a part of the record.

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 7

QUESTION 22

Names of all corporations engaged in interstate commerce having banking deposits with us in excess of \$50,000 during period 1927-31, inclusive

Balaban & Katz Corporation.
 Baltimore & Ohio Railroad Co.
 Chesapeake & Ohio Railway Co.
 Chicago, Milwaukee, St. Paul & Pacific Railroad Co.
 Chicago & North Western Railway Co.
 Delaware & Hudson Co.
 Denver & Rio Grande Western Railroad Co.
 Gulf, Mobile & Northern Railroad Co.
 Hudson Coal Co.
 Hudson-Manhattan Railroad Co.
 Illinois Central Railroad Co.
 Indiana & Illinois Coal Corporation.
 Inland Steel Co.
 International-Great Northern Railroad Co.
 Kansas City Southern Railway Co.
 Mid Continent Petroleum Corporation.
 Missouri-Kansas & Texas Railroad Co.
 Missouri Pacific Railroad Co.
 National Malleable Steel Castings Co.
 New Orleans, Texas & Mexico Railway Co.
 Pacific Oil Co.
 Paramount Famous Lasky Corporation.

Paramount Publix Corporation.
 Pennroad Corporation.
 Pennsylvania Co.
 Pennsylvania Railroad Co.
 Southern Pacific Co.
 Texas & Pacific Railway Co.
 Transportation Products Corporation.
 Union Pacific Railroad Co.
 Utah Fuel Co.
 Wabash Railway Co.
 Western Maryland Railway Co.
 Western Union Telegraph Co., Inc.
 Westinghouse Electric & Manufacturing Co.
 Westinghouse Lamp Co.
 Youngstown Sheet & Tube Co.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, in looking over committee's exhibit no. 7, June 27, 1933, which is an answer to my question no. 22 of the questionnaire submitted to your firm, I notice the names of many railroad companies among corporations engaged in interstate commerce which maintain deposit accounts in excess of \$50,000 with your firm. Are these railroad corporations companies for which your firm has done the financing in the past?

Mr. KAHN. May I have a look at it, Mr. Pecora, to see what it is?

Mr. PECORA. Yes; certainly.

Mr. KAHN. I have a copy here, I am told. I am sorry.

Mr. PECORA. All right. Please look at it and answer the question.

Mr. KAHN. Generally speaking, the answer to your question is "Yes." There may be one or two minor ones where that is not so, but generally speaking the answer to your question is "Yes."

Mr. PECORA. Were these deposits maintained by those railroads with your firm time deposits or were they deposits payable on demand?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; I give the same answer as before, that it depends upon the arrangement and the convenience of our depositors. Sometimes they prefer to keep it on time, when they have no immediate use for the money; and sometimes they are call deposits. There is no definite rule.

Mr. PECORA. Do you allow interest to them where the deposits are time deposits?

Mr. KAHN. Do we allow interest?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Do you allow interest where they are time deposits, was my question.

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. What controls the rate of interest that you allow on such deposits?

Mr. KAHN. The best that we can afford, the best that the condition of the market permits.

Senator TOWNSEND. About what is the rate of interest paid on deposits?

Mr. KAHN. It varies, Senator Townsend. At the present time I am sure it is not very much, but we adjust it to the conditions prevailing in the money market at the time.

Senator TOWNSEND. Do you know what the rate of interest is at the present time?

Mr. KAHN. I will have to confer with some of my associates.

Senator TOWNSEND. All right.

Mr. KAHN. At the present time they tell me—well, I am afraid I am dependent upon information as to that, and do you want me to answer what is given to me?

Senator TOWNSEND. That will be all right.

Mr. KAHN. At the present time they tell me the deposits with us are very small, and that the rate which we allow varies from one half of 1 percent for call deposits to 1 percent for time deposits.

Senator TOWNSEND. Those rates were very much higher, I take it, during the boom period of 1929?

Mr. KAHN. Oh, yes; much higher.

Senator TOWNSEND. What was the highest rate at that time? Do you recall?

Mr. KAHN. I am having it looked up.

Senator TOWNSEND. That will be all right, and you can answer when you receive the information. In the meantime, Mr. Pecora may go ahead.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, in the questionnaire that we submitted to your firm, question no. 4, we called for the names of all banks and trust companies in which your firm maintained deposits during the 5-year period, 1927 to 1931, both inclusive, and the amounts of those deposits at the present time in any such banks and trust companies; and we also called for the names of all other banks and trust companies in which deposits are now maintained. In answer thereto I received from your firm a typewritten document which I will ask you to kindly look at and tell us if you can identify it.

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Is that a correct and complete statement in answer to the question submitted to you?

Mr. KAHN. It is.

Mr. PECORA. I now offer it in evidence and ask that it may be spread on the record of the hearings.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted and the committee reporter will make it a part of the record of the hearings.

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 8

QUESTION 4

A. Names of banks and trust companies in which this firm maintained deposits during the years 1927 to 1931, inclusive

Mechanics & Metals National Bank, New York.
 National City Bank, New York.
 Chase National Bank, New York.
 National Bank of Commerce, New York.
 Chemical National Bank (title changed), New York.
 Guaranty Trust Co. of New York.

B. Balances as of Mar. 31, 1933

Guaranty Trust Co. of New York	\$748,624.61
National City Bank, New York	161,792.08
Chase National Bank, New York	60,498.36
Chemical Bank & Trust Co., (title changed) New York	300,392.84
Bank of The Manhattan Co., New York	57,293.26

C. Foreign banks and trust companies in which deposits were maintained during the period 1927-31; balance as of March 31, 1933 (dollar equivalent)

Bank of Montreal, London, debit.....	\$10. 99
National Provincial Bank, Ltd., London.....	Account closed
Swiss Bank Corporation, London.....	Do
Westminster Bank, Ltd., London.....	\$35, 188. 23
Dresdner Bank (formerly Darmstaedter & National-Bank), Berlin..	316. 67
Deutsche Bank & Disconto-Gesellschaft, Berlin.....	251. 70
Deutsche Effecten- & Wechsel-Bank, Frankfurt a/M.....	1, 078. 18
Deutsche Vereinsbank, Frankfurt a/M.....	Account closed
Direction der Disconto-Gesellschaft, Berlin.....	Do
Oesterreichische Creditanstalt, Vienna.....	\$64. 00
Banque de Paris at des Pays-Bas, Paris.....	2, 011. 35
Comptoir National d'Escompte de Paris, Paris.....	Account closed
Credit Lyonnais, Paris.....	\$957. 00
Chase Bank (formerly Equitable Trust Co.), Paris.....	504. 49
Société Générale pour favoriser, etc., Paris.....	480. 34
Banque Centrale Anversoise, Antwerp.....	93. 00
Banque de Bruxelles, Brussels.....	90. 35
Crédit Suisse, Zurich.....	255. 71
Banque Fédérale, Zurich.....	202. 00
Amsterdamsche Bank, Amsterdam.....	101, 476. 50
Nederlandsche Handel-Maatschappij, N.V., Amsterdam.....	460. 00
Centralbanken for Norge, Oslo.....	14. 63

The CHAIRMAN. Did your firm make many of what are known as "brokers' loans" prior to October of 1929?

Mr. KAHN. Did we?

The CHAIRMAN. Yes.

Mr. KAHN. Yes. It is a part of the way in which we employ our money.

The CHAIRMAN. Would you give us an idea of the extent of those transactions in a general way?

Mr. KAHN. I am informed that it shows on our balance sheet, of which you have an exhibit.

The CHAIRMAN. Do you remember the rate of interest that you received on those loans?

Mr. KAHN. It varied, Senator Fletcher. Yes; it varied.

Mr. PECORA. Are those brokers' loans that are referred to in your answer as call loans secured by stock-exchange collateral?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Senator TOWNSEND. Mr. Kahn, have you secured that interest in 1929 that I asked about?

Mr. KAHN. Fourteen percent, I am informed, was the highest rate.

Mr. PECORA. That is, prior to November of 1929?

Senator TOWNSEND. That is, on your deposits?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Senator ADAMS. Inasmuch as two questions came in there at about the same time, I am wondering whether Mr. Kahn answered the one or the other.

The CHAIRMAN. Fourteen percent was your highest rate on those loans?

Mr. KAHN. That was on deposits, and I am trying to look it up. You realize that the renewal rate of the stock exchange is not fixed by the banker but by the stock exchange. It is a part of a ruling made every day, as to what shall be the rate which stock-exchange brokers are permitted to pay for renewal loans, and we are advised about that. I am trying to find out how high that rate was as a maximum, but we have not received it as yet.

The CHAIRMAN. Did you say you paid as high as 14 percent on deposits, or did you mean to say that those were the rates you received on call loans?

Senator TOWNSEND. I am wondering if we are not confused a little about the questions. My question of a few minutes ago was as to the highest rate you were paid for call loans during 1929.

Mr. KAHN. I am informed that in one or two cases we took deposits on the understanding that we would allow whatever the rate was that we might succeed in obtaining, less 1 percent for our services, that in one or two cases, or at least in a few cases, we received as high as 14 percent.

Mr. PECORA. What you mean to say is this—

Mr. KAHN. (continuing). And I find I made a mistake in that last answer. My associates tell me that it was one half and one quarter of 1 percent.

Mr. PECORA. Do you mean by that answer that in those one or two instances your firm made call loans of moneys of clients, depositors, or customers, whatever you may choose to call them, and agreed to pay to those clients, depositors, or customers, the same rate of interest you got in the call money market for those loans, after deducting 1 percent for your commission?

Mr. KAHN. I am informed, Mr. Pecora, that I was wrong about deducting 1 percent, that it was less, and that I did ourselves an injustice, that we did it much cheaper. Now, what was it?

Mr. LANGENBACH. It was one quarter of 1 percent on time, and it was not in just a few instances but in many instances.

Mr. KAHN. Mr. Langenbach answered that.

Mr. PECORA. Is he a partner?

Mr. KAHN. No; he is our chief bookkeeper.

Mr. PECORA. Who handled those call loans for your firm in 1929; what members of the firm?

Mr. KAHN. The head of our loan department, whoever he happened to be at that time. I do not really know now who he was at that time.

Mr. PECORA. Were they partnership decisions, those decisions that were made with regard to moneys that would be loaned on call, or was that left to an employee?

Mr. KAHN. There were no partnership decisions made. But I presume one of the partners had general supervision over the department business. I know that I did not.

Mr. PECORA. Who did have? Which one of the partners did have that general supervision over the matter of loans?

Mr. KAHN. That would be my greatly esteemed former partner, Mr. Jerome J. Hanauer, who is here and in whose province that particular supervision lay.

Mr. PECORA. But he is no longer a partner?

Mr. KAHN. No.

Mr. PECORA. How did the interest rates that were allowed by your firm to these various corporations who maintained deposit accounts, balances in excess of \$50,000 enumerated on committee exhibit no. 7 of this date, compare with the interest rates allowed by commercial banks at that time?

Mr. KAHN. I am sorry to have to consult about that. It is not within my knowledge.

Mr. PECORA. Well, give us the benefit of your consultation.

Mr. KAHN. Would you like to have Mr. Hanauer answer that question or shall I tell you what he says to me?

Mr. PECORA. I have no objection to his giving you the information and you can communicate it to us as having been obtained from him.

Mr. KAHN (after consulting). Mr. Pecora, I am sorry to have delayed you but it is not within my personal knowledge. But my former partner tells me that he depended upon the arrangements that were being made in each case with the corporations or their financial officers concerned. It depended on our own determination to a certain extent, about what they could tell us informally, how soon they were likely to use that money. There was no definite assurance given, but they would tell my partner something like this: We are not likely to need the money for 10 days or a fortnight, or possibly 3 weeks, as the case might be. And on the strength of that information, and on the strength of personal negotiations, the rate was fixed. Usually it was for the same rate as commercial banks were allowing or a trifle better. It was to the best of my knowledge never less than that, never less than they could get elsewhere and sometimes a trifle better.

Mr. PECORA. Did the rates vary with depositors?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; the rates varied.

Mr. PECORA. What was the range at any one time?

Mr. KAHN. Oh, I did not understand your question. Did you ask if the rates varied?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. KAHN. I thought you asked as of the time. The rates did not vary as to depositors. They were as nearly alike as possible considering the circumstances of the case in each instance, as nearly as they could be considered.

Mr. PECORA. Where you regarded a deposit as a time deposit did you allow the same rate of interest to all depositors who maintained time deposits with you?

Mr. KAHN. For the same length of time?

Mr. PECORA. Yes, sir.

Mr. KAHN (after consulting with associates). Yes. They tell me, Mr. Pecora, if he deposited at the same time, for the same period, under the same circumstances, yes. We treat them all alike. But if times were different, if the circumstances were different, if the length for which they left it with us were different, the rate is different. But the answer to your question is generally yes.

Mr. PECORA. And your firm, I presume, made a use of these deposit funds profitable to it?

Mr. KAHN. Slightly to us. Not very. We allowed the closest rate that we could afford.

Mr. PECORA. You employed those funds in the making of loans generally speaking, did you not, for the most part?

Mr. KAHN. In the making of loans immediately available; yes.

Mr. PECORA. Now, were those deposit funds used in connection with the securities or the securities business handled by your firm?

Mr. KAHN. Perhaps I can answer that best by saying—and you will correct me if I am not right (addressing his associates) that our

first purpose and our first policy was always to have ample funds at hand to pay off our deposits. That was the first policy. Beyond that we did not distinguish, discriminate formally between deposits and between our capital, except that we always reserved against our deposits sufficient funds to pay them off at once.

Senator TOWNSEND. Do you mean in cash?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Senator TOWNSEND. In cash?

Mr. KAHN. I mean to pay them off in cash immediately. For instance, if you would make what we call immediately available assets that would mean that we could sell or dispose of them, liquidate them, within 24 hours, and such assets we always had against our deposits to a more than ample extent.

Senator TOWNSEND. You mean you were liquid to the point of where you carried a great quantity of Government securities and cash?

Mr. KAHN. Government securities, cash, and other liquid assets. For instance, we would call stock-exchange loans against collateral approved by us liquid funds, because it has never happened that they were not paid off the next day when called for.

Senator BARKLEY. Was there any increase in your deposits about the time the call money rate went up to 15 percent or 20 percent in 1929?

Mr. KAHN. I believe there was. (After conferring with his associates.) We did get a material increase in deposits in 1929. Yes, Senator. In 1929 our deposits reached their climax. They varied with the times. And our climax was in 1929.

Senator TOWNSEND. Did you stipulate any amount that railroads for which you did the financing should leave with you on deposit?

Mr. KAHN. We stipulated no amount; no.

Senator TOWNSEND. That was left to their own discretion?

Mr. KAHN. And to our acceptance. We would not have accepted a trifling amount. We would have said in such case, "Go to your banks. That is not our business."

The CHAIRMAN. Do you have any regular period for settling with the partners? An adjustment time, a date at the end of the year, or what time?

Mr. KAHN. Settling with the partners?

The CHAIRMAN. Settling with the partners; yes.

Mr. PECORA. That is, distribution of profits among the partners; was there any fixed time for that?

Mr. KAHN. Yes. The 31st of December, every year.

Mr. PECORA. I believe I understood you to say in answer to a question put to you by one of the Senators a little while ago that not every partner in the firm is required to make a contribution to the capital of the firm upon his being accepted as a partner.

Mr. KAHN. That is right.

Mr. PECORA. Or admitted as a partner?

Mr. KAHN. That is right, Mr. Pecora.

Senator GOLDSBOROUGH. May I ask just a question. Mr. Kahn, when you made collateral loans did you require the borrower to maintain a certain percentage of balance with you?

Mr. KAHN. The borrower?

Senator GOLDSBOROUGH. Yes.

Mr. KAHN (after consulting with his associates). No; we did not.

Senator ADAMS. Your call borrowers are not necessarily depositors? You make those call loans through the stock exchange, do you not?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Senator ADAMS. And you do not know, oftentimes, the individual to whom they go? In most cases you do not know that?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; that is true.

Mr. PECORA. You make them on the responsibility of the broker?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. As well as on the security of the collateral?

Mr. KAHN. Mainly on the security of the collateral.

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. KAHN. And we pick good brokers. We do not make—

Mr. PECORA. You mean good brokers pick you.

Mr. KAHN. Thank you. Thank you.

Senator BARKLEY. There are a lot of people who were neither bankers nor brokers who got picked in 1929.

Senator GOLDSBOROUGH. Mr. Kahn, more fully explaining my recent question: If you had certain depositors with your corporation or firm and they wanted to make a collateral loan would you require them to maintain a certain balance against that collateral loan? I am not speaking about the ordinary brokerage loan.

Mr. KAHN. No.

The CHAIRMAN. The committee will take a recess now until 2 o'clock.

Mr. KAHN. Senator, may I correct, or rather make plain one thing as to which my partner said I did not express myself very clearly? When I suggested that I would like to put in the statement by Freeman & Co., I said I did not know about that statement before. My partner understood me to say that I did not know about that firm before. They want me to say that that is incorrect, because it is an old, established and well-known firm. So, I did not wish to say that the firm was unknown to me. I wish to say that the statement was unknown to me until a few days ago.

The CHAIRMAN. You did not give the name of your partner who was a member of the stock exchange.

Mr. KAHN. John M. Schiff.

Senator BARKLEY. Shaefer?

Mr. KAHN. Schiff.

The CHAIRMAN. We will meet then at 2 o'clock.

(Thereupon, at 12.35 p.m. a recess was taken until 2 o'clock p.m. the same day, Tuesday, June 27, 1933.)

AFTER RECESS

The subcommittee reconvened at 2 p.m., Tuesday, June 27, 1933, at the expiration of the noon recess.

The CHAIRMAN. The subcommittee will come to order. You may resume the stand, Mr. Kahn.

**TESTIMONY OF OTTO H. KAHN, A PARTNER OF KUHN, LOEB & CO.,
NEW YORK CITY—Resumed**

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, in the course of your testimony at the forenoon session you read into the record from some typewritten statement that I observed was handed to you by someone in connection with the Southern Pacific Railway Co. financing.

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know who prepared that statement?

Mr. KAHN. I presume Mr. Percy Stewart, who is sitting by me, prepared it.

Mr. STEWART. I prepared it.

Mr. PECORA. Was it prepared before you came to this hearing?

Mr. KAHN. Oh, yes.

Mr. PECORA. What was the purpose of preparing that statement with regard to that episode?

Mr. KAHN. Perhaps the purpose was to pat ourselves gently on our backs.

Mr. PECORA. I beg pardon?

Mr. KAHN. Perhaps the purpose was to pat ourselves gently on our backs, and show that we of our own volition paid a great deal more than the company was able to obtain by competition.

Mr. PECORA. Was that such an outstanding event in the history of financing by your firm that you considered it important enough to prepare the statement in advance for use at this hearing?

Mr. KAHN. It was an outstanding event to that extent, that, generally speaking, as I mentioned this morning, we do not participate in competitive bidding, and this was a conspicuous instance where the company did much better by dealing with us than they could have done by competitive bidding.

Mr. PECORA. Would you say that because of that conspicuous incident, as you have characterized it, it proves the contention you were subscribing to, that competitive bidding is calculated to bring less beneficial results to the corporation seeking to do public financing?

Mr. KAHN. I am convinced of that; yes.

Mr. PECORA. Just from that one incident?

Mr. KAHN. Not from that one incident. From general experience and observation both in this country and many other countries.

Mr. PECORA. Does your experience include any other incidents than this conspicuous one that you have referred to?

Mr. KAHN. I cannot at this moment search my memory sufficiently to give you an answer under oath, but—

Mr. PECORA. Well, as a matter of fact, you had forgotten this conspicuous incident in the course of your testimony this morning until one of your associates gave you that typewritten statement to which reference was made, had you not?

Mr. KAHN. I do not say that I had forgotten it, but I did not have it in my memory.

Mr. PECORA. Now your firm, as I understood your testimony this morning, specialized—if I may use that term—in railroad financing?

Mr. KAHN. Largely, yes.

Mr. PECORA. Largely. In connection therewith, do you keep abreast or do you seek to keep abreast of the reports and decisions of the Interstate Commerce Commission?

Mr. KAHN. We seek to keep abreast; yes.

Mr. PECORA. You have no difficulty in obtaining them, do you?

Mr. KAHN. No.

Mr. PECORA. The reports and decisions of the Commission are public property and readily available to those who seek them?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know what has been the history as reflected in the reports of the Interstate Commerce Commission in the past few years of competitive bidding for the equipment obligations of railroads? Equipment Trust certificates?

Mr. KAHN. I believe that history is pretty definitely set forth in the pamphlet which I presented this morning, by Freeman & Co.

Mr. PECORA. Well, I have not seen that pamphlet yet, and I have not the advantage of examining the authors of that pamphlet here, because they are not here, but I want to ask you as a banker who largely specializes in railroad financing if you know what the history has been as that history has been recorded and reported in the public documents of the Interstate Commerce Commission with regard to Equipment Trust obligations or certificates?

Mr. KAHN. My own judgment is that it has narrowed and made more difficult the market for equipment trusts.

Mr. PECORA. When you say that it has narrowed and made more difficult the market for equipment trusts, what do you mean by that, so that there may be no misunderstanding of your statement?

Mr. KAHN. I mean by that that the distributors, who are a valuable portion of the investment business, have to a considerable extent shown a reluctance to go into the purchase or into the distribution of equipment-trust certificates unless they are sponsored by responsible bankers, and unless an adequate margin was secured to make it worth their while to go to the effort and the responsibility of going out and distributing such equipment trusts.

Mr. PECORA. Who has shown that reluctance?

Mr. KAHN. The distributors.

Mr. PECORA. The distributors?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. That is, the jobbing agencies?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. That are relied upon by the underwriting bankers; the issuing bankers? Is that right?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And the reason for that reluctance is because of the narrowness of the spread or profit to themselves, is it not?

Mr. KAHN. Only in part, Mr. Pecora. I think the distributors, and I venture to say the public, do attach considerable importance to have securities that are offered to them under the sponsorship and bearing the trade mark of responsible bankers, which bankers over a course of many years have shown that they are thorough, that they are experienced, and that they are men of integrity. That is a fact.

Mr. PECORA. Are we to understand from that, Mr. Kahn, that the distributors rely in selling an issue to their customers or to the investing public upon the sponsorship of the underwriting banker or the issuing banker?

Mr. KAHN. Reliance is perhaps too strong a word, but it is undoubtedly an element which affects their judgment.

Mr. PECORA. Is it the most decisive single influence?

Mr. KAHN. That asks me to answer for every distributor, which I cannot do.

Mr. PECORA. I merely want your general observation.

Mr. KAHN. But my general observation is in this and in other instances that the trade mark and the sponsorship of a responsible banker, which means the examination he has made, the advice he has given, the thoroughness which he has devoted to a thing, the record of integrity which he has made, is an important element in influencing not only the distributors but also influencing the public.

Mr. PECORA. The investing public who buy from the distributors?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Well, I repeat the question: Would you refer to that element as the most important single element which influences the distributor and the retail buyer, so to speak?

Mr. KAHN. It is difficult to say what is the most important single element.

Mr. PECORA. Well, do you know any single element more important than that?

Mr. KAHN. There ought be no single element more important than the assurance of the investor and of the distributor that he is buying something which has the best kind of sponsorship in the way of reliability and thoroughness. I do not know whether that is always so or not.

Mr. PECORA. And that is the sponsorship of the underwriting or issuing banker?

Mr. KAHN. Providing that underwriting and original banking has a reputation for thoroughness and integrity; yes.

Mr. PECORA. Yes. Issues such as equipment-trust certificates are now made as the result of competitive bidding, are they not?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And do you know what the effect has been of that competitive bidding for those securities, upon the spread?

Mr. KAHN. I could not answer that offhand.

Mr. PECORA. Well, let me read to you from the report of the Interstate Commerce Commission which I have before me, the Forty-fourth Annual Report, dated December 1, 1930, page 11:

The amounts of equipment-trust obligations in respect of which carriers have been authorized by us to assume obligation and liability are shown above. All the equipment obligations, except those issued directly to the builders, were sold at competitive biddings. The table given on page 12 of our Annual Report for 1928 shows certain data with respect to the sale of equipment obligations and bonds in amounts of \$100,000 and over to bankers, and resales by them to the public, in cases where complete sales information is available. The table is here reproduced with additional data for the last 6 months of 1928, the calendar year 1929, and the first 6 months of 1930 included.

Then in the table which follows, Mr. Kahn, it appears that for 7 months in 1920 the spread in the price to bankers and to the public per \$100 unit was \$1.91; that in 1921 it was \$2.29½; in 1922, \$2.33; in 1923, \$2.33; in 1924, \$1.86; in 1925, \$1.80; in 1926, \$1.47; in 1927, \$0.66; in 1928, \$0.64; in 1929, \$0.89; and for the first 6 months of 1930, \$0.72.

And reading from the forty-fifth annual report of the Interstate Commerce Commission dated December 1, 1931, and at page 10 thereof, we find a corresponding table for the first 6 months of 1931, which shows the spread in the sale of equipment obligations of 0.43.

And that the average spread for the entire year 1930 in the price to bankers in the sale of equipment obligations was 0.78.

Now you would accept these figures as authentic, would you not?

Mr. KAHN. Undoubtedly.

Mr. PECORA. Embodied as they are in the report of the Interstate Commerce Commission?

Mr. KAHN. Undoubtedly.

Mr. PECORA. Were you aware of that general trend downward of the spread in securities of this kind before I read it to you from these reports?

Mr. KAHN. I cannot say now that I was aware of it. As I said before, this pamphlet only came to my attention a few days ago. I brought it along because I thought it seemed to me a very eloquent statement corroborative of what I said to you gentlemen before. I have not compared it with this book and with these records.

The CHAIRMAN. What would happen, Mr. Kahn, in case there were no competitive bidding? Would the whole business be confined to one or two distributors?

Mr. KAHN. If there were no competitive bidding?

The CHAIRMAN. Yes.

Mr. KAHN. I think if there is no competitive bidding, Senator, the result will be that the railroads and other corporations are free to choose whom they want to do business with, and no one can say them nay. There is no one to control them. It has happened in our case more than once that a new financial vice president came into office; we did not know him before; we did not know who he was. We had no possible influence in bringing him in there. We had no possible influence in keeping him in there. But he would gradually acquaint himself with the facts as to the records of our dealings with that particular railroad, and the result was that he went on doing business with us. But it was entirely his doing. He can go to anybody else he chooses. And it is no more competitive or no less competitive than a doctor is competitive or an architect is competitive.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, you recognize that there is a very sharp difference in principle between the analogy that you have drawn in the relations between a doctor and a patient, and the banker and the common carrier, do you not? There is a public interest in the latter classification that is not present in the relationship between a doctor and a patient, is there not?

Mr. KAHN. As far as the patient is concerned that does not enter. As far as the community is concerned of course it does.

Mr. PECORA. Yes. And that public interest and the service of that public interest is something that should be kept in mind.

Mr. KAHN. By all means.

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Now in the case of the issuance and the sale of equipment trust obligations or certificates by common carriers, I believe it was in 1925 the Interstate Commerce Commission required those to be issued as the result of competitive bidding?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And you have seen that the result has been a very appreciable narrowing of the spread to the banker?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Now do you consider that has been harmful to the interests of the carrier or to the public?

Mr. KAHN. It may have been very harmful to the interests both of the carrier and of the public.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know of any instance that would establish that?

Mr. KAHN. I believe that the pamphlet I submitted does prove that it has been harmful; yes.

Mr. PECORA. You are referring now to the pamphlet of Freeman & Co.?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Well I say again, I have not read that pamphlet and I have not the advantage of examining the authors of the pamphlet to see what their foundation for their conclusions was. But do you know of any instance within your personal knowledge where this rule of the Interstate Commerce Commission requiring competitive bidding in the issuance and sale of equipment trust certificates has worked to the detriment either of the carrier or of the public?

Mr. KAHN. I have given you one, Mr. Pecora, which I read to you this morning. I am not prepared without going into the thing more fully and examining the matter, to say whether there have been other instances. It is very difficult from a statement such as the Interstate Commerce Commission has made to know in what cases the offerings of equipment-trust certificates have been wholly unsuccessful. I have given you one instance in which they were wholly unsuccessful. There may be plenty of others. I do not know.

Senator ADAMS. Mr. Kahn, are you able to give us an approximate figure as to the prices at which equipment-trust certificates have been marketed during this period? Has there been a decline or an increase in the price of equipment-trust certificates?

Mr. KAHN. I see from Mr. Pecora's statement that there has been a decline. But I—

Senator ADAMS. No; his figures were a decline in the spread.

Mr. PECORA. A decline in the spread?

Senator ADAMS. Yes. I am talking about the price, which might be an entirely different thing.

Mr. KAHN. It might be an entirely different thing, as you rightly say, Senator, and I am not prepared now to say whether there has or has not been, because I do not know.

Senator ADAMS. The equipment-trust certificate has been regarded as a rather high-grade type of security, has it not?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; very high grade. And the question is, Mr. Pecora—and that was my whole point this morning—that there enter the interests of the public and the interests of the corporation in the first instance. The whole test of whether the investment banker is of any use or not depends on whether his services are of value to the industrial community, including the railroads, in enabling them to meet their long term requirements. If not, then the

investment banker might just as well go out of business. I am convinced, and the history of the other countries has shown, that these services are of real importance and of real usefulness. I cannot offhand tell you what elements in the particular passages you have read to me sustain your point and what elements sustain my point.

Mr. PECORA. I am not seeking to make any point. I am seeking to find out your view.

Mr. KAHN. Well, my point is that I am quite sure that you can bring some cases to my attention which seem to show that the non-competitive bidding costs more than competitive bidding. But I am prepared to bring to you a whole raft of cases showing that competitive bidding has been most detrimental to the public, has compelled the public to pay unnecessarily high prices. Has in some cases destroyed the credit of corporations and of governments. And that if you weigh the one against the other, the thing to do, in my humble opinion, is to go to the people who have the greatest experience, who are most thorough, who have a good reputation, enlist their services and pay them what is a fair compensation—or not pay them any compensation at all, which is the usual case, but simply tell them, “We are willing to sell you that at such and such a price, and now you go out and resell them to the public at a fair increase”; and in selling them to the public at a fair increase we are perfectly willing to bear in mind that the investment banking business requires the services of a great many specialists. It requires the maintenance of a very large overhead. It involves a very great responsibility. It involves, if you want to maintain your reputation, your capacity to say no to a hundred tempting opportunities in order to maintain your reputation.

Mr. PECORA. That is true of business generally, isn't it?

Mr. KAHN. Not of all businesses as much as it is of the investment business, which is built upon one thing only, and that is—

Mr. PECORA. The difference is one of degree rather than of principle, is it not?

Mr. KAHN. I think it is to a considerable extent one of principle, because, as I tried to express this morning, we haven't got a show window. We do not advertise. We have no salesmen. We send nobody out to tout our goods. The only thing which keeps us alive is the confidence of the people, and that confidence is subject to being recalled. If we haven't got it any more we can just as well go out of business. And to maintain that confidence requires not only character and judgment, it requires also the capacity to say no to a hundred tempting opportunities.

Senator ADAMS. Mr. Kahn, if I might interrupt. Perhaps Mr. Pecora has grasped your explanation, but it has escaped me. I gather that your view is that it had been detrimental to the public as well as to the carrier to have competitive bidding on these equipment trust certificates. I find from these statistics that there is a smaller spread, so far as that is concerned; and apparently from the pamphlet, which I think has been identified as the Freeman & Co. pamphlet, the investment bankers or brokers say in that rather one after the other that it has resulted in a higher price of these equipment securities. Now I am not quite clear as to the point you make, as to why under those conditions it is detrimental to the public

and to the carrier, the carrier getting more money for his certificates, and, of course, rates and things of that kind are based upon the actual amount of money that comes in. It is more for the benefit of the public, I should think, if they get a dollar for a dollar obligation than if they get 97 for a dollar obligation. So I am really asking for information.

Mr. KAHN. Well, Senator, I am not—beg your pardon. [After conferring with associates.] Senator, I am getting valuable advice from the rear.

Senator ADAMS. You are fortunate in having it available. Most of us have to travel here without reserves or recruits back of us.

Mr. KAHN. What the rear tells me and what I fully approve is this: The statement which you have read me does not show whether on the whole the railroad obtained a better price or not in consequence of elimination of those sources of capital which they used to deal. It does show a lesser commission was paid. But if I am willing to pay, as I was willing to pay to the Southern Pacific, 98 $\frac{1}{4}$, and others were willing to pay only 97 $\frac{1}{4}$, I do not see in what way the fact that, if they could have sold them they might have sold them at 97 $\frac{3}{4}$, which would have been a half a cent spread to the officials of the railroad—I hate to argue with the master of the law—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). Please do not embarrass me.

Mr. KAHN. And to put my very poor knowledge or my very poor argument against yours. But how did I know that was beneficial to the railroad, or how do I know in your instance what the railroads would have obtained and what they would have obtained if they had come to us? How could anyone prove that? I know we would have to pay the top price that was possible to pay. How do I know that was the result, that either the bondholders or railroad was benefitted? I have given you one case showing where the railroad benefitted through the fact that they came to us instead of going to competitive bidding.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, perhaps this would be of some information or enlightenment to you on that very proposition. You were pleased to refer to the conspicuous instance of the Southern Pacific Railroad Co. this morning. You have made reference to it again this afternoon as illustrating the advantage to the carrier in that particular case of disposing of their bonds on your bid of 98 $\frac{1}{4}$ instead of accepting the best bid of 97 and a fraction which it received through competitive bidding.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. At what price did you sell those bonds to the public?

Mr. KAHN. 98 $\frac{1}{2}$.

Mr. PECORA. 98 $\frac{1}{2}$. That is, your profit was only one quarter of 1 percent?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Wasn't that unusually small as compared to the profit in railroad bonds generally?

Mr. KAHN. That was an unusually small profit. The circumstances were unusual.

Mr. PECORA. Then if that was an unusual circumstance, why do you rely upon it to prove a generalization?

Mr. KAHN. It is merely one of the incidents which I happened to have at hand. I might be able to find others, or probably could

find others, which were eloquent of what I tried to prove this morning. That is not the only one. I told Mr. Pecora that the Cincinnati Union Station came to us and wanted to sell bonds to us at 89, and we said, no, don't sell them at that price. You can do much better. And shortly afterwards, a few months afterwards, it obtained 97 for them.

I can give you plenty of similar examples where, if bonds had been offered to competitive bidding at the time that the railroads wanted to offer them, they would have done infinitely worse than by waiting for the matured advice of their bankers who could afford to be disinterested—I do not pose as an altruist in business, but who could afford to be disinterested—because they knew that if they gave good service it would be appreciated and the business would come to them. No one would have given them that advice on competitive bidding. The railroads made up their minds they would sell at 89.

The CHAIRMAN. Mr. Kahn, since the Interstate Commerce Commission not only recommends but insists upon competitive bidding, would you recommend any legislation on that subject?

Mr. KAHN. Senator, the Interstate Commerce Commission, in my opinion, very wisely only insists on competitive bidding in the case of equipment trusts, and they are basing that upon certain premises, with some of which I agree, some of which I am a little doubtful about; but I haven't the slightest, not the slightest, fault with that going on as is.

My argument is in response to Senator—pardon me, Mr. Pecora's question. As Mr. Lamont says, perhaps I anticipate. My argument was—

Senator BARKLEY (interposing). Are there any vacancies in the diplomatic service? [Laughter.]

Mr. KAHN. A much broader one, Senator. I say it is a question for a decent investment banker to bear in mind the advantage of the corporation and of the public, and that the present method comes as near as is possible with our imperfect human nature, and has been found so everywhere in the world. But I don't say that this particular rule should be repealed.

The CHAIRMAN. Of course, it was this equipment trust matter that they were talking about, where they insist on the competitive bidding.

Mr. KAHN. Equipment trusts are a somewhat different class of securities from a bond. They are interested in other securities to a very large extent. The element of experienced banking advice as to what is the best kind of securities to offer—

The CHAIRMAN (interposing). Well, of course, they do not insist on competitive bidding as to stocks and bonds?

Mr. KAHN. Oh, no; they do not. Only as to equipment trusts.

Mr. PECORA. Now, the Southern Pacific Co. instance you cited related to bonds, not to equipment trust certificates?

Mr. KAHN. No; it related to equipment trusts, equipment trust certificates.

Mr. PECORA. In 1927 you recall that an application was made by the Southern Pacific Co. to the Interstate Commerce Commission for leave to issue \$5,786,000 of equipment trust certificates. Do you recall that?

Mr. KAHN. I do not recall it, but I say the instance which I have given to you relates to equipment trust certificates, and I am not arguing, not attempting to argue now, with the wisdom of competitive bidding, for equipment trust certificates. I doubt very much whether either the railroad or the public gains anything by it, but I am not arguing about it.

Mr. PECORA. What was the date of that issue that you speak of?

Mr. STEWART. July 14, 1928.

Mr. PECORA. Are you familiar with the application that was made to the Interstate Commerce Commission in behalf of the Southern Pacific Co. on July 14, 1927, for leave to issue \$5,786,000 of equipment trust certificates?

Mr. KAHN. I am not.

Mr. PECORA. Well, I am reading now from the report or decision of the Interstate Commerce Commission on that application, entitled "Finance Docket No. 6389, Southern Pacific Equipment Trust, Series J, submitted July 14, 1927, decided July 18, 1927." I merely want to read the following paragraph from it:

Bids for the proposed issue of equipment trust certificates were solicited from 34 banks and bankers, and 8 bids were received, representing 16 banks and bankers. Subject to our approval the certificates have been sold to the Mellon National Bank, Pittsburgh, Pa., and Salomon Bros. & Hutzler, New York City, the highest bidders, at 99.52 percent of par and accrued dividends from July 1, 1927.

I see that in that instance, a year before this conspicuous example that you put into the record here, 5¾ million equipment trust certificates were sold to the highest bidder at 99.52.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Which is even better than the 98¼ that you regard as a conspicuous example.

Mr. KAHN. Well, Mr. Pecora, times were different.

Mr. PECORA. Did you submit any bid on the occasion of this 1927 application?

Mr. KAHN. We did not.

Mr. PECORA. The year 1927 was, generally speaking, a good year for business, wasn't it?

Mr. KAHN. The year 1927?

Mr. PECORA. It was one of the so-called "boom" years?

Mr. KAHN. A very good year for business; yes.

The CHAIRMAN. Did you have anything to do with the Baltimore & Ohio issue of stocks and bonds?

Mr. KAHN. Very likely, Senator. We act as their bankers usually.

The CHAIRMAN. I have a statement showing that the stock of the Baltimore & Ohio Railroad selling for 150 on the market and they issued \$150,000,000 more.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

The CHAIRMAN. Giving to their stockholders the right to purchase at par, \$100.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

The CHAIRMAN. The privilege practically ate up the whole issue.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

The CHAIRMAN. Do you remember that?

Mr. KAHN. I do not recall it, but I haven't any doubt that if such an issue was made it was underwritten by us and our associates.

The CHAIRMAN. It is said that the participants in the financing, or rather the bankers who did not participate in the financing probably paid \$7,500,000 for them, just as though they had underwritten the issue but they did not.

Mr. KAHN. I do not have the instance in my memory, but I am quite sure that no railroad could expose itself to the risk of having that amount of stock offered to the public without being protected by some kind of underwriter. In fact, I have the issue here.

(At the close of the session Mr. Kahn submitted the following testimony for the record, bearing on this issue: Mr. Kahn. One of my associates informs me there was to his recollection no such issue of \$150,000,000 of stock of the Baltimore & Ohio Railroad Company and suggests that perhaps the chairman has in mind an issue of 632,425 shares of that company's common stock which was offered by the company to its stockholders at 107½ on June 9, 1927, the issue being underwritten by my firm. The stock ranged in the market during the month of June 1927 between 114 and 125.)

The CHAIRMAN. If you are familiar with that subject matter, and I presume you are, Mr. Kahn, I am reminded that the total capital debt issued up to the time of the war of the railroads in this country was only 11 billion dollars.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

The CHAIRMAN. And after that there was issued 12 billion more?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

The CHAIRMAN. Making the total capital debt today something like 23 billion dollars?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Senator GOLDSBOROUGH. Billion?

The CHAIRMAN. Doesn't that look like an enormous increase in the capital debt of a railroad, 23 billion dollars issued up to now?

Mr. KAHN. It looks like an enormous effort on the part of the railroads to render that additional service to the public which had become probably necessary through the run-down condition that was a necessary matter permitted to exist during the war.

When the railroads were returned to private hands after the war they found that their expenditures had to be very large, because during the war other things were more important than maintaining the excellency of the railroads. The railroads made a very great effort to put themselves back on the map and to fight for their existence and to give the best possible service. In fact, they may have gone too far. Nearly every other industry went much too far in increasing its plant capacity and in raising money for the purpose of improving its service. It would have been very much better for the country if there had been generally more moderation and less eagerness for expansion and for perfection of service. But they all did it.

I do not know: I have not the figure in mind. I accept it, of course. But whatever the railroads did they did for what was not only the interest of the country, a laudable purpose, but what in their best judgment was the necessary purpose in order to maintain their position as a great branch of the national industry. It gave work to many people. It increased the general activity of the coun-

try. I haven't any doubt, in the light of hindsight, that it would have been much better if a little more moderation and restraint had been observed.

The CHAIRMAN. Does not such a large capitalization result in an increase of rates and repairs and freights and all that sort of thing, and put more burden on the people?

Mr. KAHN. But these expenditures since the resulting increases, if any, in rates, were subject to the approval of the Interstate Commerce Commission.

The CHAIRMAN. Yes.

Mr. KAHN. They must have approved it or the expenditures could not have been made.

Senator BARKLEY. Do you think that this 12 billion dollars increase in the bonded indebtedness of railroads since the war was reflected in the purchase of equipment or in physical benefits?

Mr. KAHN. Not all of it, I am afraid, Senator.

Senator BARKLEY. That would represent at least half of the total value of all the railroads, and it is not my observation that they spent anything like that amount of money on equipment.

Mr. KAHN. I am afraid I cannot contradict you.

Senator BARKLEY. What were they doing with the rest of the money?

Mr. KAHN. You see, there happened from 1926 to 1929, and particularly in 1929, a perfect mania of everybody trying to buy everybody else's property, and the railroads were not excluded from that. New organizations sprung up. Money was so easy to get. The public was so eager to buy equities and pieces of paper that money was—just as it was pressed upon foreign governments, so it was pressed upon domestic corporations.

The result was that many of the railroads became fearful, and with good reason, that lest somebody should imperil their just interests in their own territory many of them felt either like being aggressors or like defending themselves against aggressors, very much the European situation all over again, only instead of leading to warfare it led to expenditures.

In consequence of that I believe that a good many of the expenditures that were made in those years were made for the purpose either of buying strategically located railroads or for the purpose of railroads defending themselves against the apprehended aggression on the part of other railroads or other corporations.

Senator BARKLEY. What sort of defense was necessary on the part of the railroads to keep one from selling itself out to some other road that would require the expenditure of billions of dollars for the issue of bonds? They did not have to sell. What sort of aggression was it that they had to defend themselves from?

Mr. KAHN. May I give you a case in point in answer to that?

Senator BARKLEY. Yes.

Mr. KAHN. In 1929 the Pennsylvania Railroad, representing as it did no one large holding or no combined large holding of stock but representing hundreds of thousands of small stockholders, became apprehensive that its legitimate territory, the legitimate assets of its hundreds of thousands of stockholders, most of them small stockholders, was being imperiled by the other railroads coming into that

territory and buying up strategically important pieces of railroading in their territory. They considered very carefully, to our own knowledge, what they ought to do to defend themselves, and they finally reached the conclusion that the only way in which they could defend themselves was to unite their own stockholders in a defensive organization, which had the name of Pennroad Corporation and which would be strong enough financially and which would be elastic enough constitutionally to go and buy strategically important pieces of railroad before somebody else snatched it away from them.

It was not a question of these newcomers wanting to buy the Pennsylvania Railroad; it was a question of these newcomers purchasing properties that were of strategic value to the Pennsylvania Railroad, which they were perfectly willing to leave independent but if somebody else was going to get them, it would be very damaging to their own property; and their own property represented not the holdings of a few rich men or of a small body of compact holdings but a percentage of holdings of much more than a hundred thousand of small investors. They felt called upon, and in my opinion they felt rightly called upon, even though it was costly, to do what they could to defend the assets entrusted to their care.

That is how this particular case arose, and I have mentioned it to you as an answer to your question.

Senator BARKLEY. Just one other question. Did that operation necessitate the enormous increase, or an enormous increase, in the bonded indebtedness of the Pennsylvania Railroad or of any of these companies which it was seeking to control through the formation of the holding company known as the "Pennroad Co."?

Mr. KAHN. In this particular case it did not, and if I may continue to indulge in a practice which I have started of saying pleasant things about ourselves, we most urgently warned the Pennsylvania Railroad that nothing should be done which would involve any increase in fixed charges and that the things should be handled in such a way that it would involve nothing but equity, which it was perfectly proper, within the choice of the Pennsylvania stockholders, to put up for their defense or not put up as they thought best. But there was not a dollar of fixed charge incurred. There was not even a dollar of preferred stock incurred. And I do claim a little of a credit of having most urgently advised that there should be no increase in the fixed charge and there should be no preferred stock.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, you have already stated that the year 1927 generally speaking was a good business year.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Was 1928 a better year for business generally?

Mr. KAHN. I cannot say exactly it was better, but it was a good year, too.

Mr. PECORA. Well, insofar as prices of securities were concerned, did securities, generally speaking, bring higher prices in 1928 than they did in 1927?

Mr. KAHN. I don't really recall.

Mr. PECORA. In 1927, which we have seen from the record that I have read and reports of the Interstate Commerce Commission decision on the application of the Southern Pacific Railway for leave to issue five million and odd hundred thousand dollars of

Equipment Trust dividends—we have seen that as a result of competitive bidding—

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. The roads sold those to the Mellon Bank and to Salomon Bros. & Hutzler for 99.52.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. You said that the following year, the year 1928, this conspicuous example arose where your firm obtained an issue of Equipment Trust certificates from the same road at 98¼.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Why didn't they bring as high in 1928 as they did in 1927?

Mr. KAHN. That depends upon circumstances.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know what the circumstances were?

Mr. KAHN. I do not, except—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). Can you tell us at this time?

Mr. KAHN. Except unwillingness on the part of the many people who were invited to submit a bid.

Senator TOWNSEND. Was the rate of interest the same?

Mr. KAHN. The rate of interest in that case was—the basis at which they were sold was 4.7785, and I believe they were 4½ percent bonds, 4½ percent equipment trusts. I could not possibly tell you what were the motives which induced the many people who were invited to bid to refuse to do so. But they must have been motives of self-interest. They must have believed they could not sell them.

Mr. PECORA. Now, you said something about what you described as a "perfect mania" on the part of everybody to buy everybody else's property in 1928 and 1929.

Mr. KAHN. Yes; particularly 1929.

Mr. PECORA. Particularly 1929 prior to October?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Referring to 1929, you found quite a change after October 24 for the balance of that year?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. The Senator wants to know why I bring that up. Perhaps it is because of painful memories.

Now, like most manias, you found that mania an unhealthy one, didn't you, for the common good—it proved to be so?

Mr. KAHN. It proved to be so, and some of us were in before the event too early, and some of us were in after the event—

Mr. PECORA. But too late?

Mr. KAHN. But too late. And some of us reached the conclusion, let us say March, to give you an arbitrary date, that things could not go on, and then we were persuaded by the course of events that the thing could go on and did go on, and then we were in a position of the twelfth juror, who said, "I have never seen 11 such obstinate men", and we thought, well, probably—at least some of us thought—probably we are wrong. Everybody else says, "This thing is going on for a few years longer anyhow. There is no sign of a reaction, and probably we are wrong. We do not want to assume that our judgment is right as against everybody else's."

We did do one thing, we did not join in the general scramble to create affiliates and to create securities corporations. Not one of them

bears our trade mark. Not one of them was set up by us. But we were not—at least I was not—determined enough when I found that my judgment was in defiance of the almost unanimous sentiment of the community. I for one was not willing to say, "Well, I am right and everybody else is wrong."

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, when did you first realize that this was a mania?

Mr. KAHN. That this was——

Mr. PECORA. A mania, what you have called a "perfect mania"?

Mr. KAHN. Well, I realized off and on that it was a mania. I believed in 1928 already that it had reached the proportions of a mania, and then it went on and the public seemed determined——

Mr. PECORA (interposing). The mania became more furious and intense, did it?

Mr. KAHN. It was not the bankers, Mr. Pecora, that did that. Just as the bankers are not making the violent bull market in New York now. That is not the banking business. No banker can do that. No one individual or group of individuals can do that.

Mr. PECORA. If the bankers do not do it, can you tell us what group of persons can do it and do do it?

Mr. KAHN. There is nothing as strong as the determination of vast numbers of public opinion to be in the making of—no, that is not the right word—to be in when a great movement is going on. They want to be in. They do not want to sit outside and have their neighbors guess right and they guess wrong. So they go along, and the combined power of millions of people in doing that is infinitely stronger than anything that a combination of bankers can do, and no combination of bankers can make a market such as exists today in New York. No combination of bankers can make a market such as existed in 1929 in New York. They can participate in it, and some of them did to their cost, but they cannot make it.

Mr. PECORA. Do you think that bankers are in a position to apply influence or brakes to such mania?

Mr. KAHN. They should be.

Mr. PECORA. You have been a banker practically all of your adult life?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. I want to ask you, in the light of your experience over many years in the banking field, what corrective influence, if any, bankers are in position to apply to such a situation?

Mr. KAHN. Perhaps I can answer that by saying that in England, where they are very old in experience and very wise, because they have to be wise in order to live—it is a poor country and they can only live if they are wise; nature has not given them very much else—in England the governor of the Bank of England, who has no extraordinary executive power outside of the Bank of England, surrounds himself with a number of wise heads whom he selects, and if they reach the conclusion that something ought to go down the line in the way of advice to the community at large, especially the financial community, it does go down the line, and it goes down the line in such a way that it is heeded and obeyed.

We have no similar thing in this country. It is true that in 1929 the Federal Reserve Board—late in 1929—tried to stem the tide. It

is equally true that they did not do anything of the kind earlier; and the time to prevent something serious happening to the financial community is earlier, and not later. But I know of no one who can exercise that influence in this country except the Federal Reserve Board, or perhaps the Treasury. It is very difficult for the Treasury to do it, because if it gives wrong advice the Secretary of the Treasury is accused. If he gives wrong advice everybody will say, "You prevented me from doing the right thing." It is still more difficult for the President to say anything. I know of no agency in this country that is fitted to exercise that function except the Federal Reserve Board.

Mr. PECORA. Did not the Federal Reserve Board attempt to apply corrective influences early in 1929? You say it did not do it until late in 1929.

Mr. KAHN. It was too late, in my opinion.

Mr. PECORA. Did it not attempt to do it early in 1929, and even in 1928?

Mr. KAHN. It did not do it in 1928, to the best of my recollection, and the damage was done—again, to the best of my recollection—in 1927 when money was made far too easy, when we tried to help Europe to get back to the gold standard and when, for this purpose and for the purpose of facilitating the transactions of our Treasury, money was made far too easy, at a time when the handwriting on the wall—

Mr. PECORA. You say money was made far too easy. By what agency?

Mr. KAHN. By the Federal Reserve Board.

Mr. PECORA. Not by bankers generally?

Mr. KAHN. Bankers generally had to follow, because the Federal Reserve Board set the pace. The Bank of Chicago, early in 1929, if I remember rightly, tried to raise its discount rate as a warning, but the Federal Reserve Board forbade it. They would not have it; and they could not do it without the Federal Reserve Board.

Mr. PECORA. I recall that in February of this year at hearings held by a corresponding committee to this committee, of the Seventy-second Congress, officers of the National City Co. and the National City Bank were examined here and testimony was adduced to the effect that in March 1929 the Federal Reserve Board sought to apply the brakes to this speculative mania, and its action was nullified by the action of a certain bank or its officers in sending \$25,000,000 to the New York Stock Exchange. Do you recall the incident?

Mr. KAHN. I recall the incident.

Mr. PECORA. Is it not a fact that one of the strongest tell-tale signs of the development and existence of a speculative mania is the loans made to brokers?

Mr. KAHN. That is one of them; yes.

Mr. PECORA. One of the signs; one of the almost incontrovertible signs, is it not?

Mr. KAHN. It never happened before. This was the first instance where it happened. We have nothing to judge it by.

Mr. PECORA. Did not private banking firms as well as commercial banks help along the development of that mania by freely making brokers' loans in unprecedented amounts?

Mr. KAHN. To put it mildly, Mr. Pecora—

Mr. PECORA. I want to be conservative.

Mr. KAHN. To put it mildly, they certainly did not do sufficient to prevent it or stop it. And would it have been human nature that they should prevent it or stop it, in view of the fact—

Mr. PECORA. If we cannot look to bankers to guide us, to what group can we look in periods of that sort, if they are not qualified to do it?

Mr. KAHN. I do not say they are not qualified to do it; but it is an exceedingly difficult thing in the face of an utter, complete, and unprecedented determination by the public to take the bit in its teeth. It is an extraordinarily difficult thing. If it were a possible thing for the private banking community or the banking community to stop it, they would be brushed aside and people would not pay any attention to them. I know that one of my partners, Mr. Warburg, made a speech warning against what was coming, and they paid not the slightest attention; and even as late as, I believe, in September 1929 Lehman Bros. made an issue of a securities corporation called the Lehman Corporation. There was nothing that they had to offer except their certificates. Not a single transaction had been consummated; not a single business was planned.

The public took that stock which was offered at par and bought it at 135. How could they defend themselves against a public mania like that? They did not put it to 135; they offered it to the public at par. The public went in and bought it at 135 simply because they were determined to speculate. They were determined that every piece of paper would be worth tomorrow twice what it was today. I do not believe the whole banking community together could have prevented it. While far from excusing some of the things they have done—I greatly deplore some of the things that were done, including the one that you mention—I doubt whether anything but a catastrophe could have stopped that violence unless it had been stopped earlier by the Federal Reserve Board.

I think in my own mind—and I may be all wrong—we might have been able to stop it earlier, but when it had taken full sway of the people and there was an absolute runaway feeling throughout the country, I doubt whether anyone could have stopped it before calamity overtook us.

Mr. PECORA. Could it not have been stopped or checked or retarded appreciably if the banking profession generally had declined to make these brokers' loans in the amounts in which they did?

Mr. KAHN. Mr. Pecora, you referred to loans for others. That is the very thing which happened. When the bankers tried to pull in their horns, some of them, outsiders came and said, "Oh, there is a chance to loan money at 15 percent. If the banks will not loan enough, we are going to loan, ourselves." And every industrial corporation, or most of them, came in and competed with the bankers for loans for the stock market.

Mr. PECORA. Did not many of those corporations invest their surplus funds through private banks in that very market?

Mr. KAHN. Not very many, I should think. Most of them, I should think, if my memory serves me rightly, did it through the regular banks.

My mentors want me to correct something which perhaps might give rise to international complications. I said England was a poor

country. I did not mean "poor" in that sense. I meant England is a country which by nature is not endowed with riches comparable to what we have here.

Mr. PECORA. It is poor in natural resources?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; poor in natural resources as compared with what we have. But I wish to make it plain that I did not mean to refer to England as a poor country.

The CHAIRMAN. England has an advantage over our system, has it not, in that the Bank of England is, as you express it, able to "go down the line", very largely because they have £175,000,000 equalization fund?

Mr. KAHN. Well, Senator Fletcher, before that fund ever existed England was able to do it. It is a tradition. It is a moral influence, more than anything else; and what I am praying for is that some similar moral influence may come to prevail in this country. I doubt whether it can be done through any legislation. I think it can be done through the force of one or two or three men who gradually acquire a moral force such as the Governor of the Bank of England has, because there is also with the Governor of the Bank of England the power over the purse. He can discount or refuse to discount bills. But his main influence is a moral one, and that is a matter of tradition. I hope very much that we in this country will develop a tradition which will place somewhere that power to control and restrain, and be listened to and heeded, utterly impartially and disinterestedly except for the good of the country. But I do not see how it can be done except through moral influence.

Mr. PECORA. I want to ask you about an issue of \$20,000,000 of guaranteed sinking fund 6½ percent gold bonds, which was made by your firm in conjunction with the Guaranty Co., on about June 25, 1925, on behalf of the Mortgage Bank of Chile. Are you familiar with the transaction?

Mr. KAHN. You have touched a sore point.

Mr. PECORA. I did not know how sore it was.

Mr. KAHN. It is the only issue which my firm has made since the war, the only foreign issue which is in default. We made it after what we believed to be a very careful and thorough examination. We had before us the record of a country which for over 70 years had never been in default. We had before us the record of a country whose constitutional history was almost free from revolutions and which for many, many years had had a favorable balance of trade, and had a favorable balance of trade then. We had before us the history of a concern whose business was the making of first mortgages, which was guaranteed by the Government of Chile and which was vouched for by the Department of Commerce in records that we found. The record was not furnished to use, but we found it in the records, which said that they knew of no bank better managed, more carefully managed, than the Mortgage Bank of Chile. Everything that we could find out seemed to prove that this was a bond that we were justified in sponsoring.

Mr. PECORA. Prior to this \$20,000,000 issue of June 1925 the external financing of Chile had been done in Europe, principally by French banks, had it not?

Mr. KAHN. Most of it; yes.

Mr. PECORA. Who brought this particular proposition relating to this proposed issue of 1925 to the notice of your firm?

Mr. KAHN. It was brought to the notice of my firm first by our old friends, a very conservative old banking house which had been the agents of the Mortgage Bank of Chile for many years—Dreyfus & Co.—

Mr. PECORA. Of Paris?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; of Paris. That is how it started. We insisted, after having looked into it, that although the business seemed tempting we would not do it unless the Government of Chile guaranteed it. We would not take merely the first mortgages. We insisted that the Government of Chile guarantee it. The Government of Chile refused to do so; at least, as far as Dreyfus & Co. could handle it, it was not possible, and therefore we declined to do the business.

About 6 months later our friends, Lehman Bros., came over and said, "There is some one here from the Mortgage Bank of Chile who wants us to do that business. It is out of our line. Does it interest you?" We examined into it and we said to them, "If you can get us the guarantee of the Chilean Government it will interest us in principle."

Then a little later, about June, we learned that the Guaranty Trust Co. was also trying to do that business; and from this point on I think my associate had better take up the story, because he is much better posted than I am. The business was done primarily from that spot on by my late partner, Mortimer Schiff, who died in 1931, and he was closely associated as to all details with Mr. Bottenwieser and Mr. Stewart; and they can tell you the details much better than I can tell them. If it meets with your approval, I would suggest that he tell the story from that point on—

Mr. PECORA. I will examine them in detail about that. I want to ask you a few questions about it before I examine those two gentlemen.

When did you learn that the Guaranty Co. of New York was interested in this financing?

Mr. KAHN. I believe in June.

Mr. PECORA. Of 1925?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. That was some 6 months after the proposal had been brought to your notice by the French firm of Louis Dreyfus & Co., was it not?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Eventually your firm, after it learned of the interest of the Guaranty Co., which is the affiliate of the Guaranty Trust Co. in this proposed financing, instead of competing with them, joined forces with them in the financing?

Mr. KAHN. Yes. There was no reason why American investors should pay the competitive price and should pay the Chilean Government more money than it was entitled to.

Mr. PECORA. And was any fee paid Louis Dreyfus & Co. for finding the business for you?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. That is termed "finding." "Finding" is a term that is a familiar one in your business, is it not?

Mr. KAHN. It is; yes.

Mr. PECORA. One who finds a financial operation for a bank is rewarded by the payment of a commission?

Mr. KAHN. Of a reasonable commission.

Mr. PECORA. And Louis Dreyfus & Co. received such a commission in connection with this Chilean financing?

Mr. KAHN. It did.

Mr. PECORA. Did anyone else receive any commission or compensation as a finder or a promoter of the negotiation?

Mr. KAHN. From us?

Mr. PECORA. You or the Guaranty Co.

Mr. KAHN. From us; nobody else. From the Guaranty Co.; yes.

Mr. PECORA. Who?

Mr. KAHN. Mr. Norman Davis.

Mr. PECORA. How much did he receive?

Mr. KAHN. He received, for the first business which we did in the intermediaries' and negotiators' commission, \$25,000.

Mr. PECORA. Did not your firm contribute \$15,000 to that?

Mr. KAHN. My firm contributed nothing. The syndicate contributed, as part of the syndicate expenses, \$15,000; and the Guaranty Co. contributed \$10,000. Afterwards the second business was done and Mr. Davis received another fee of \$10,000; so that his total fees received were \$35,000.

Senator BARKLEY. What was the nature of that service?

Mr. KAHN. Here [exhibiting a paper] we have the memorandum for which we asked, from the Guaranty Co. of New York. Inasmuch as they were the originators of the relationship with Mr. Norman Davis, with your permission I will read it; it is very short [reading]:

The Guaranty Trust Co. of New York and the Guaranty Co. of New York from time to time had discussions with Mr. Davis regarding certain loan transactions with Latin-American countries because of his knowledge of Spanish-American affairs and financial questions in general. At such times and at the time of the Chile Mortgage Bank loan Mr. Davis was a private citizen. In 1925 Mr. Davis informed us that the representative of the Chile Mortgage Bank had consulted with him with regard to the placing of a loan in New York and wished to know if we would be interested in considering it, to which we replied in the affirmative. He accordingly presented to us Mr. Berisso, who had been sent to this country to negotiate a loan for the bank. As the Chile Mortgage Bank then had a long record of uninterrupted payments on its obligations, and the loan which it proposed to negotiate was guaranteed by the Chilean Government which had a similar financial record, the business proposed seemed sound. Accordingly, Mr. Davis was instrumental in putting us in touch with the Mortgage Bank of Chile business and in helping to conclude the negotiations.

Perhaps I might add here, Mr. Pecora, that to the best of my recollection Mr. Davis was present at one or two of the subsequent negotiations after the Guaranty Co. and we had agreed to join issue, and he assisted in the negotiations.

The Guaranty Co.'s memorandum goes on [continuing reading]:

There was no agreement with Mr. Davis as to the amount he was to receive for his services, though it was understood that he was to be compensated. Upon conclusion of the deal the bankers without previous consultation with Mr. Davis decided that the fee for his work in connection with the successful conclusion of the negotiations should be fixed at \$15,000, to be paid by the banking group—

Which means the syndicate—

and an additional \$10,000 was paid by the Guaranty Co. of New York with which Mr. Davis had originally discussed the matter. The representative of the Mortgage Bank of Chile and the Chilean Ambassador were informed of the bankers' intention to compensate Mr. Davis and were in accord therewith. Subsequently, a second loan was made and in this connection a further fee of \$10,000 was paid by the banking group to Mr. Davis. No payment was made to him on any succeeding issues.

Mr. PECORA. What is the date of that memorandum?

Mr. KAHN. June 2, 1933.

Mr. PECORA. By whom was that memorandum prepared?

Mr. KAHN. It is initialed "J. R. S. (initialed)."

Mr. PECORA. Do you know to whom those initials refer?

Mr. KAHN. J. R. Swan, president of the Guaranty Co.

Mr. PECORA. And was this memorandum addressed to Kuhn, Loeb & Co.?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Under date of June 2 of this year?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And had your firm requested this memorandum for its information?

Mr. KAHN. We understood, Mr. Pecora, that you wished to be informed of the facts, and therefore we asked for the facts, and this is the result.

Mr. PECORA. This memorandum was sent you in compliance with your request for such information?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

The CHAIRMAN. You say Mr. Davis was at that time a private citizen?

Mr. KAHN. He was at that time a private citizen; yes.

Senator BARKLEY. Was he practicing law in New York?

Mr. KAHN. I do not know whether he was practicing law or whether he was engaged in general business. I could not tell you that, Senator.

Senator BARKLEY. He is a lawyer, I believe, is he not?

Mr. KAHN. When I first met him he was a banker in Cuba; he was the president of a bank in Cuba, many years ago.

Senator BARKLEY. He has had considerable experience in Latin-American and European diplomatic and financial matters?

Mr. KAHN. So I understand.

Senator BARKLEY. Was he acting in the capacity of an adviser as to this particular loan; or in what capacity was he compensated?

Mr. KAHN. He brought this particular loan to the attention of his friends, the Guaranty Co., and he brought also to their office a representative of the Mortgage Bank of Chile, and that was his first, and I assume, his controlling service. To the best of my recollection he assisted in one or two of the subsequent negotiations, when the details of the business were being determined; but his controlling service was as here reported.

Senator BARKLEY. The parties in interest, then, as I understand it, felt that his services in bringing the business to them should be compensated for, and they fixed this amount as a reasonable sum? Is that correct?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. When did your firm decide to join forces with the Guaranty Co. in the flotation of this twenty-million dollar issue of Mortgage Bank of Chile?

Mr. KAHN. Mr. Pecora, I learn, but do not know it from my own knowledge, that it was probably early in June of that year.

Mr. PECORA. Are you familiar with the correspondence that passed between Mr. Davis and the Guaranty Co. of New York—

Mr. KAHN (interposing). I am not—

Mr. PECORA (continuing). In connection with this flotation?

Mr. KAHN. I am not at all familiar with it.

Mr. PECORA. Was there any competition at all between your firm and the Guaranty Co. with regard to this issue, Mr. Kahn, before the two institutions joined forces?

Mr. KAHN. Mr. Pecora, from the time that I stopped I have no longer any detailed knowledge, because I went away; I believe I went to Europe, and the matter was taken up by my partner, Mr. Mortimer Schiff. But I think Mr. Buttenwieser can tell you all the facts. I could only tell you by asking him, and will be glad to do it if you prefer it done in that way.

Mr. PECORA. Who is Mr. Laval? Is he a gentleman connected with Louis Dreyfus & Co.?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir. I know that he was the New York representative of Louis Dreyfus & Co. of Paris.

Mr. PECORA. Had Louis Dreyfus & Co. been interested previously in any Chilean financing?

Mr. KAHN. They were and had been for a long time the European representatives of the Chilean Mortgage Bank. Whether they did any business with the Government of Chile I do not know.

Mr. PECORA. Did you or any member of your firm have any conferences with the Chilean Ambassador in connection with this proposed loan?

Mr. KAHN (after conferring). No. We had no direct conference with the Chilean Ambassador in relation to this loan. But after the contract had been concluded he came there and signed the bonds and affixed to them, by authority of the Chilean Government, the guarantee of the Chilean Government. And to the best of my recollection and knowledge that was all the relation we had with him. He signed the contract.

Mr. PECORA. At the time of this issue of \$20,000,000 for the Mortgage Bank of Chile, what kind of government existed in Chile?

Mr. KAHN. At that particular time—and I am now speaking subject to correction, but at that particular time they had what in Chile they called an election—no; they had what here we call an election; they had a new deal, and a new government came in. They did not come in by the peaceful means which characterizes the situation in this country; they came in with a moderate degree of violence.

Senator BARKLEY. It might have been called a raw deal.

Mr. PECORA. It was cold steel.

Mr. KAHN. But we were advised by counsel that the acts of that Government were absolutely valid in law and in every other way.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know what the present market quotations are for those bonds?

Mr. KAHN. Unfortunately I do know; yes.

Mr. PECORA. Well, will you impart your knowledge to us?

Mr. KAHN. They are quoted at about 13, now, between 13 and 14.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, how much, all told, of those mortgage bonds issued by the Mortgage Bank of Chile were underwritten by your firm and the Guaranty Co. of New York and thereafter sold to the American investing public?

Mr. KAHN. I believe \$90,000,000.

Mr. PECORA. Over what period of time?

Mr. KAHN. From 1925 to 1929. And after that—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). There were five different issues, weren't there?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And four of them were for \$20,000,000 each and one for \$10,000,000.

Mr. KAHN. Yes. And after that, Mr. Pecora, we were foolish enough, or right enough, or loyal enough, whatever might be the proper term, to put our own money into an additional loan of \$8,000,000, which we did not offer to the public but which was our own money and the money of some of our associates, and which money is still there. We did not offer that issue to the public.

Mr. PECORA. That was a short-time advance that you made, wasn't it?

Senator GOLDSBOROUGH. It has turned out to be pretty long term.

Mr. KAHN. It did not turn out that way, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. But it was intended as a short-term advance, wasn't it?

Mr. KAHN. It was hoped that in the course of time—and our confidence really had not diminished at that time—and as I say, it was hoped that within a year or so it would be possible to float another issue out of which that loan would be liquidated. But that was never possible, and therefore that money is still there.

The CHAIRMAN. Was that loan made after the other issues were floated?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

The CHAIRMAN. And all guaranteed by the Government of Chile?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; except this last loan, Senator Fletcher, where we were foolish enough even not to insist upon the guarantee of the Government.

Mr. PECORA. This eight-million-dollar short-term loan, which has proven to be not a short-term loan, you say was made by Kuhn, Loeb & Co.

Mr. KAHN. By Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and a small group of friends of theirs.

Mr. PECORA. How much of the funds of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. actually went into that eight-million-dollar advance?

Mr. KAHN. Originally, we took, as I take it, the whole responsibility.

Mr. PECORA. Together with the other participants?

Mr. KAHN. Together with the Guaranty Co. Then we succeeded in getting some other participants, with the result that our ultimate investment is—(turning to Mr. Battenwieser)—How much is it? (After conferring.) Our original responsibility was \$3,600,000, and then other people were not only willing but eager, strange as it may seem in the light of hindsight, to get a part of that loan, which car-

ried a very good rate of interest. They felt, and we felt, it was merely a temporary loan at a time when a good rate of interest for short-term loans was very desirable. But ultimately we found that \$3,000,000 of our \$3,600,000 were snapped up by others. We urged nobody to go in, but they liked it.

Mr. PECORA. How much of the actual funds of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. went into this eight-million-dollar loan eventually?

Mr. KAHN. Originally it was \$3,600,000.

Mr. PECORA. Eventually, yes; but you passed a part of that to other participants.

Mr. KAHN. Now it is \$600,000.

Mr. PECORA. Then \$600,000 is the extent of your participation in that eight-million-dollar advance?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

The CHAIRMAN. What was the rate of interest?

Mr. KAHN. Originally the rate was 5½ percent. Since then it has vanished into thin air, since no longer is there any rate of interest.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, you said with reference to this Mortgage Bank of Chile issue that you insisted on a guaranty by the Chilean Government before you would underwrite that issue.

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And you got that guaranty?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And the Government from which you got that guaranty was a government that had instituted itself in power by what you call a moderate show of force or violence.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Did you consider that that was a safe guaranty on which to pass on \$90,000,000 of securities to the American investing public?

Mr. KAHN (after conferring). What about these, Mr. de Gersdorff?

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. Let me see them.

The CHAIRMAN. While Mr. de Gersdorff is looking at those papers, Mr. Kahn, let me ask you: Was it the same government that guaranteed all those issues?

Mr. KAHN. Yes. It remained in power for quite a while.

Mr. PECORA. Are you sure of that?

Mr. KAHN. Well, I haven't answered your question, I am afraid.

Mr. PECORA. You stated before that you preferred to have Mr. Bittenwieser and Mr. Stewart examined with regard to this Mortgage Bank of Chile issue or issues, so I will adopt your suggestion.

Mr. KAHN. I think it would save your time, because, as you see, I have to turn to the right and to the left to get information.

Mr. PECORA. Well; I will do that. I think with advantage to yourself it should be done.

The CHAIRMAN. Where is that bank located, at Santiago?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; Senator Fletcher.

Mr. PECORA. I will examine Mr. Bittenwieser, if I may suspend with Mr. Kahn at this point, with the understanding that he is not excused from further attendance.

The CHAIRMAN. That will be all right.

Mr. DE GORSBORFF. Mr. Pecora, let me show you these letters. Have you any objection to their going on the record?

Mr. PECORA. This is the first time these documents have been shown to us.

Mr. DE GERSBORFF. It is the first time I have seen them.

Mr. PECORA. I will see what they are.

Mr. DE GERSBORFF. You can hold them over if you so desire. The second one of them I think is the most important.

Mr. PECORA. I will read the whole series in chronological order. (After scanning over the letters.) Just leave these letters with us for the present.

Mr. DE GERSBORFF. All right.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Buttenwieser, I suggest that you now take the chair that has been vacated by Mr. Kahn.

TESTIMONY OF BENJAMIN J. BUTTENWIESER, A PARTNER OF KUHN, LOEB & CO.—Resumed

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Buttenwieser, your name has been suggested by your associate, Mr. Kahn, as the gentleman in the firm of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. most familiar with the issuance of these bonds by the Mortgage Bank of Chile, floated by your firm in conjunction with the Guaranty Co. of New York, in the period between 1925 and 1929. So I am going to examine you with respect to those issues.

Now, take the first one in point of time, the one of June 25, 1925, and that consisted of an issue of \$20,000,000 of guaranteed sinking fund 6½ percent gold bonds due June 30, 1957, did it not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. Now, at the risk of traversing some of the ground that Mr. Kahn has covered but in view of the fact that I am going to examine you in detail about those issues, will you tell us how this proposal was first brought to the notice of your firm?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. In a general way Mr. Kahn outlined it to you. That is, that late in 1924 our old friends, Messrs. Louis Dreyfus & Co., of Paris, were in communication with us as to whether or not we would be interested in a Mortgage Bank of Chile issue, with which bank they had had relations before the war and whose securities they had offered before the war. And, as Mr. Kahn told you, after some study of the facts they submitted to us we told them we would be interested only if we could obtain a guaranty of the bonds by the Republic of Chile.

Mr. PECORA. Now, which particular gentleman in your firm handled the proposition at its inception?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Mr. Mortimer Schiff.

Mr. PECORA. Did you assist him?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. All right. Had you up to that time, or had your firm up to that time done any Chilean financing?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. As I recall, we had made one issue of Chilean securities in conjunction with others, which issue has been repaid since then.

Mr. PECORA. Were you at that time familiar with political conditions in the Republic of Chile?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. What were they?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Well, at the particular time of which you speak, which was December of 1924, I believe the regular government was in effect. I think the provisional government to which you referred subsequently, only came into being in the spring of 1925.

Mr. PECORA. When this proposal was first brought to the notice of your firm by Louis Dreyfus & Co. in December of 1924, you indicated your willingness to underwrite the issue provided the Chilean Government guaranteed its payment?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. Was that guarantee to extend to the payment of interest as well as to the payment of the principal at maturity?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. A full guarantee, of interest, sinking fund, and principal, by endorsement.

The CHAIRMAN. Have you got that guarantee here, or a copy of it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir. It is embodied in the loan agreement, which in turn contains a facsimile, or not a facsimile but the text of the bond and the guarantee endorsement.

Mr. PECORA. Tell us what kind of bonds they were, these so-called "bonds" of the Mortgage Bank of Chile.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Do you mean that you want me to outline what is the type of bond of the Mortgage Bank of Chile?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It is a bank which makes first-mortgage loans against any bonds which it issues.

The CHAIRMAN. You mean that it makes first-mortgage loans and issues bonds against those loans, do you not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

The CHAIRMAN. You had it the other way around.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Pardon me.

Mr. PECORA. Go ahead with your answer.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Perhaps I could do better by reading this circular.

The CHAIRMAN. Do they make first-mortgage loans on real estate?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Perhaps I could serve the purpose better by submitting to you a copy of the prospectus descriptive of the bank and the issue of bonds in question.

Mr. PECORA. All right. If you have a set of prospectuses please produce them.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. This is the first issue. I believe you already have a copy of it.

The CHAIRMAN. What did you sell those bonds at?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. At 97 $\frac{3}{8}$ percent.

The CHAIRMAN. For the whole \$90,000,000?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No. We are speaking now of the first issue of \$20,000,000.

The CHAIRMAN. What was the next?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The next issue was another issue of \$20,000,000, of which we bought only \$18,330,000.

The CHAIRMAN. At what were they sold?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. At 99 $\frac{1}{4}$.

The CHAIRMAN. What about the next \$10,000,000?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That second issue, Senator Fletcher, was a $6\frac{3}{4}$ -percent issue.

The CHAIRMAN. Go ahead with your answer.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The next \$10,000,000 were 6-percent notes due in 5 years, which we sold at $98\frac{3}{4}$.

Mr. PECORA. And the fourth issue was one of \$20,000,000?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes; 6-percent bonds, for a longer term, which we sold at $95\frac{3}{4}$. And the last issue was an issue of 6-percent bonds, made in 1929 and sold at 92.

Mr. PECORA. That was a \$20,000,000 issue; that last issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And do you mean you sold them at 92?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

The CHAIRMAN. And those are now worth 13 or 14?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Now, hadn't you better give me for the record a printed copy of the prospectus issued in connection with the first loan that does not contain lead-pencil notations?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I believe you have a copy of that prospectus already, Mr. Pecora. This is the only copy we have here, but we can furnish it.

Mr. PECORA. I offer this for the record, that is, the printed portions of it, and ask that it may be spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. It will be admitted and the committee report will make it a part of the record.

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 9

TWENTY MILLION DOLLAR MORTGAGE BANK OF CHILE (CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO) GUARANTEED SINKING FUND $6\frac{1}{2}$ PERCENT GOLD BONDS DUE JUNE 30, 1957, UNCONDITIONALLY GUARANTEED, AS STATED BELOW, AS TO PRINCIPAL, INTEREST, AND SINKING FUND BY ENDORSEMENT BY THE REPUBLIC OF CHILE

Coupon-bearer bonds in denominations of \$1,000 and \$500 each. Principal and interest to be payable at the option of the holders in the New York City office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, in United States gold coin of or equal to the standard of weight and fineness existing June 30, 1925, or in Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja by sight draft on New York City without deduction for any taxes, imposts, levies, or duties of any nature now or at any time hereafter imposed by the Republic of Chile or by any State, Province, municipality, or other taxing authority thereof or therein, and to be payable in time of war as well as in time of peace, and whether be a citizen or a resident of a friendly or a hostile State.

INTEREST PAYABLE JUNE 30 AND DECEMBER 31

For further information regarding this issue of bonds reference is made to the accompanying letter received from His Excellency the Honorable Beltran Mathieu, Ambassador Extraordinary and Plenipotentiary of the Republic of Chile, and from which the following is summarized:

The bonds are unconditionally guaranteed as to principal, interest, and sinking fund, by endorsement, by the Republic of Chile, pursuant to decree law of the Governing Council, dated March 9, 1925, and an Executive decree, dated June 15, 1925 (supplementing said decree law), issued under the authority of President Alessandri and his Cabinet, who are functioning as the Government of Chile, Congress having been dissolved in September 1924 pending the adoption of a new Constitution which is now being drafted. The guaranty thus authorized is valid and binding upon the Republic of Chile.

Beginning December 31, 1925, the bonds will be redeemable through a cumulative sinking fund calculated to retire the whole issue by June 30, 1957, to be

applied on each semiannual interest date to the redemption by lot of bonds at par. The Caja will have the right to increase the amount of any sinking-fund payment for the redemption of additional bonds on any interest date, and in any such case appropriate reductions will be made in subsequent sinking-fund payments. This right is reserved because repayments on the mortgage loans can be made by the borrowers either in cash or in bonds of the Caja in excess of the fixed premium amortization payments, and the Caja is not permitted by law to have its bonds outstanding in excess of the mortgage loans against which they are issued.

THE UNDERSIGNED WILL RECEIVE SUBSCRIPTIONS FOR THE ABOVE BONDS SUBJECT TO ALLOTMENT, AT 97 $\frac{3}{8}$ PERCENT AND ACCRUED INTEREST TO DATE OF DELIVERY, TO YIELD 6.70 PERCENT TO MATURITY

The undersigned reserve the right to close the subscription at any time without notice, to reject any application, to allot a smaller amount than applied for, and to make allotments in their uncontrolled discretion.

The bonds and the guaranty are, in the opinion of American and Chilean counsel, valid obligations respectively of the Caja de Credito Hipotecario and the Republic of Chile.

The above bonds are offered, if, when, and as issued and received by the undersigned, and subject to the approval of counsel. In the first instance, interim certificates of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York will be delivered against payment in New York funds for bonds allotted, which interim certificates will be exchangeable for definitive bonds when prepared.

Application will be made in due course to list these bonds on the New York Stock Exchange.

KUHN, LOEB & Co.
GUARANTY Co. OF NEW YORK.

NEW YORK, *June 25, 1925.*

WASHINGTON, D.C., *June 25, 1925.*

Messrs. KUHN, LOEB & Co. and GUARANTY Co. of New York, N.Y.:

DEAR SIR: Referring to the issue of \$20,000,000 guaranteed sinking fund 6 $\frac{1}{2}$ -percent gold bonds due June 30, 1957, of the Mortgage Bank of Chile (Caja de Credito Hipotecario, Chile), I beg to give you the following information:

The bonds are unconditionally guaranteed as to principal, interest, and sinking fund, by endorsement, by the Republic of Chile, pursuant to decree law of the governing council, dated March 9, 1925, and an executive decree, dated June 15, 1925 (supplementing said decree law), issued under the authority of President Alessandri and his Cabinet, who are functioning as the Government of Chile, Congress having been dissolved in September 1924, pending the adoption of a new constitution which is now being drafted. The guaranty thus authorized is valid and binding upon the Republic of Chile.

The Caja de Credito Hipotecario was created by law of August 29, 1855, for the purpose of making available credit facilities on reasonable terms for the development and improvement of real property in Chile. The board of directors is selected by both legislative chambers of Chile, and the chairman of the board, the chief counsel, the cashier, the controller, and the secretary are appointed by the President of the Republic.

During its entire existence of 70 years, the Caja has operated successfully and has never failed to meet its obligations. The record of its loan collections is very satisfactory. The losses incurred by the Caja on property foreclosed under its mortgages have not exceeded \$40,000 in the aggregate for the last 10 years. In his report, published February 1, 1924, to the Department of Commerce of the United States, Mr. Charles A. McQueen, special agent of the Bureau of Foreign and Domestic Commerce of the Department, states that in the course of its long existence the Caja has conducted its affairs with uniform safety and success.

The Caja has no capital stock and is not operated for profit. It has power to charge a commission to provide for its expenses and for a reserve fund, as additional security for its bonds, but having accumulated a sufficient reserve, the Caja has now discontinued charging such commission.

The Caja issues its bonds only against mortgages registered in its name. It makes only first-mortgage loans. The loans are made on a conservative basis and the risk is greatly diversified. On December 31, 1924, the Caja had out-

standing various issues of bonds aggregating \$84,995,700, at approximate rates of exchange, against which it had made more than 9,800 mortgage loans, being an average of not more than \$9,000 per loan. The aggregate appraised improved value of the properties mortgaged as security for these loans amounted to more than four times the amount of the loans. As further security for its bonds, the Caja has accumulated a reserve fund of approximately \$5,118,000, at approximate present rates of exchange.

The law of September 10, 1892, authorizes the Caja to issue bonds and to make mortgage loans payable in foreign currencies. It is the practice of the Caja to make its mortgage loans, against which bonds payable in a foreign currency are issued, also payable in the same currency, except in cases where it has obtained a guaranty of the Republic of Chile for any loss resulting from exchange fluctuations. This was done in 1912 when Fcs. 58,823,500 gold bonds were issued (of which there are still Fcs. 28,444,500 gold now outstanding), and is also being done in the case of the present issue against \$15,000,000 of which mortgage loans in Chilean currency will be outstanding. The mortgage loans against the balance of \$5,000,000 of this issue will be made at the request of the Republic of Chile, for special purposes at lower interest rates than the Caja is paying on the bonds, and the Republic has agreed to pay the difference and to guarantee these mortgage loans. The entire present issue of bonds will also be guaranteed by endorsement by the Republic of Chile. No other issue of bonds of the Caja is endorsed with the guaranty of the Republic.

The bonds of the Caja are legal investments for savings banks and trust funds in Chile.

Prior to the war, in 1911 and 1912, three issues of 5 percent bonds of the Caja, not endorsed with the guaranty of the Government, were made in Europe, at prices from 96¼ to 99¼ percent.

The present debt of the Republic of Chile, including the present and all other obligations guaranteed by it, aggregates about \$250,000,000, at approximately present rates of exchange. The proceeds of the Government loans have been largely used for the construction or improvement of railways, harbors, and other public works. The Government owns 3,624 miles of railroads, telegraph lines, and other property, of an estimated value of approximately \$650,000,000, at approximate present rates of exchange, which is well in excess of the entire amount of the debt. In addition, the Government owns large and very valuable tracts of nitrate lands.

Chile is a mining and agricultural country. Its mineral products are largely raw materials for essential industries. Exports consist chiefly of nitrates and byproducts of the nitrate industry, copper, borax, wool, and a limited amount of agricultural products. The nitrate deposits are the only large natural deposits so far discovered in the world. The copper industry has been extensively developed, largely by American capital.

The trade balance of Chile is favorable. The total foreign trade for 1923 (the last year for which official figures are available) aggregated \$318,000,000 at the approximate present rate of exchange, and the balance of exports over imports amounted to \$78,000,000. The unofficial estimates for 1924, both for the total trade and for the favorable balance, exceed the results for 1923. Since 1915 imports have exceeded exports in only 1 year.

The present currency circulation of Chile at the present rate of exchange of about 11½ cents per peso, is equivalent to \$35,855,645. Part of this currency is covered by gold reserves, part by commodities, and part by mortgage loans and other obligations. The total gold reserve amounts to approximately \$41,800,000, which is in excess of the dollar equivalent, as stated above, of the present currency circulation.

The \$20,000,000 guaranteed sinking fund 6½ percent gold bonds of the Caja, constituting the loan designated "Emprestito oro Caja Hipotecaria", 1925, which you have agreed to purchase, will be in coupon-bearer form, in denominations of \$1,000 and \$500, will be dated June 30, 1925, will mature June 30, 1957, and will bear interest at the rate of 6½ percent per annum from June 30, 1925, payable semiannually on June 30 and December 31 of each year. Principal and interest will be payable, at the option of the holders, in the borough of Manhattan, in the city of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co., or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co., of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of or equal to the standard of weight and fineness existing June 30, 1925, or in Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, without deduction for any taxes, imposts, levies, or duties of any nature now or at any time hereafter imposed by the Republic

of Chile, or by any State, Province, municipality, or other taxing authority thereof or therein, and will be paid in time of war as well as in time of peace, and whether the holder be a citizen or a resident of a friendly or a hostile state.

Beginning December 31, 1925, the bonds will be redeemable through a cumulative sinking fund calculated to retire the whole issue by June 30, 1957, to be applied on each semiannual interest date to the redemption by lot of bonds at par. Notice of redemption is to be given by advertisement, the first advertisement to appear at least 30 days before each redemption date. The Caja will have the right to increase the amount of any sinking fund payment for the redemption of additional bonds on any interest date, and in any such case appropriate reductions will be made in subsequent sinking-fund payments. This right is reserved because payments on the mortgage loans can be made by the borrowers either in cash or in bonds of the Caja in excess of the fixed minimum amortization payments, and the Caja is not permitted by law to have its bonds outstanding in excess of the mortgage loans against which they are issued.

Application will be made to list the bonds on the New York Stock Exchange.

Very truly yours,

BELTRAN MATHIEU,
*Ambassador Extraordinary and Plenipotentiary of the
Republic of Chile to the United States.*

The CHAIRMAN. Are all these issues in default, Mr. Buttenwieser?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

The CHAIRMAN. And have been in default for some time?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. And have been since July of 1931.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Buttenwieser, your firm would never have underwritten this issue, and I am referring to the first issue, of June of 1925, without a governmental guarantee made by the Chilean Government, would it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I cannot answer as to that. I know that we wanted the guarantee.

Mr. PECORA. You so notified Louis Dreyfus & Co. when they called the proposal to your attention, didn't you?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir; in 1924.

Mr. PECORA. And that was because you did not consider the security of the issuing bank, that is, the Mortgage Bank of Chile, sufficient in and of itself to justify your underwriting the issue and offering it to the American public?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That was partly it, Mr. Pecora; and because the American public might not have appreciated how good or how bad the Mortgage Bank of Chile was. The guarantee of the Government of Chile was what we wanted to rely on; yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. You wanted that as a selling argument?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No; as the security.

Mr. PECORA. You wanted it because you needed it as security for the payment of both principal and interest?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. I see. It is a fair inference, then, that you did not consider the security of the Mortgage Bank of Chile, or the responsibility of the Mortgage Bank of Chile itself sufficient.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is a fair inference; yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Well, now, you said that at the time when this proposal was first brought to your notice, in December of 1924, you requested a governmental guaranty. But that Government changed in the spring of 1925, did it not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I find from a memorandum which has just been furnished to me by Mr. McEldowney, that the Government had changed in September of 1924.

Mr. PECORA, Oh, it was in September of 1924?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes; and my memory about it was wrong.

Mr. PECORA. The Government had come into power in September of 1924, which was a Government that obtained its power through a show of force. It was a revolutionary Government, wasn't it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I believe so.

Mr. PECORA. That established itself by means of revolution?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I think it was what you would call a de facto government.

Mr. PECORA. It wasn't a constitutional government, was it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is a legal question, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. Well, it is considered by your firm, isn't it? Legal questions are considered by your firm, are they not, in making up its decision on the underwriting of issues of foreign governments or of foreign institutions?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. On a problem like that, of course, we would consult our counsel.

Mr. PECORA. And you had advice with regard to the nature of this government risk?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And your advices were to the effect that the government was established by a revolutionary force?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Our advice was that it was a government whose acts would have to be recognized.

Mr. PECORA. By whom? By all succeeding governments?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I think that was the information.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. I think that was written advice, and if we have it here he could give it to you, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. This is the gentleman who has been suggested as the one connected with Kuhn, Loeb & Co. who should be examined with regard to these loans.

The CHAIRMAN. Did you issue any prospectus with reference to this loan?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That was the prospectus, the one that I just submitted.

The CHAIRMAN. I thought that was the Chilean bank.

Mr. PECORA. It was the prospectus of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and the Guaranty Co. of New York.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It embodied what was represented by the bank, and the government by the Chilean Ambassador.

The CHAIRMAN. Did you represent anything in that prospectus as to the attitude of this Government, as to this loan?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Do you mean the United States Government?

The CHAIRMAN. Yes.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No. We are not permitted to do that, as that letter quite clearly states.

The CHAIRMAN. You made no reference in your prospectus as to the attitude of the Government?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. As to the attitude of our Government we are not permitted, as that letter clearly sets forth.

The CHAIRMAN. But I am not aware whether you observed what the State Department required or not. I do not know.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. We always observe what the State Department asks us to do.

The CHAIRMAN. The public seemed to have got the impression, is the reason I mention that, that this Government was behind this issue of bonds by the Chilean Government in some way.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not think there is any ground for it in any circular that we issued.

Senator BARKLEY. Are you one of a syndicate that floated the Colombian bond issues?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No, sir.

Senator BARKLEY. So you were not subject to pressure there from the State Department in another direction?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. We had nothing whatever to do with any of the Colombian issues.

Mr. PECORA. Now, have you produced here a copy of a written communication sent by your firm to Louis Dreyfus & Co. under date of January 9, 1925?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Will you let me have it, please?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Here it is. It is the only copy I have.

Mr. PECORA. I want to offer this in evidence and ask that it may be spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. That may be done.

(The letter dated January 9, 1925, from Kuhn, Loeb & Co. to Louis Dreyfus & Co. is as follows:)

Mr. PECORA (reading):

JANUARY 9, 1925.

Confidential.

Messrs. LOUIS DREYFUS & Co.,
Paris.

Caja de Credito Hypotecario—

I suppose that is the Chilean title of this bank?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Mortgage bank; yes.

Mr. PECORA. Which we called and continue to call for the purpose of convenience the Mortgage Bank of Chile.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes.

Mr. PECORA (continuing reading):

DEAR SIR: We beg to acknowledge receipt of your favor of December 27 which we have perused with much interest. In leaving out of consideration that part of the institution's balance sheet which is in francs and sterling, and the meaning of which is not entirely clear to us, we gather from the balance sheet submitted to us that the reserve fund of the institution amounts to just about 5 percent of its circulation of mortgage bonds, and that, inasmuch as the institution has no capital, thus constitutes the sole equity behind the mortgage bonds. This in itself would make it impossible for us to consider offering these bonds for public subscription without the bonds being additionally secured by a guaranty of the Government endorsed on the bonds. We also notice from the profit and loss account that the total profit of the year was less than one quarter of 1 percent of the circulation of the mortgage bonds.

We cabled you to inform you of our decision. If it should be possible for you to arrange that the Government give its guaranty for an issue of bonds, of the institution in the United States, we would, of course, be prepared to consider this matter further. In this connection, may we not call to your attention that the very fact that the mortgages are expressed and collectible in Chilean money, which is now quoted roughly at about one third of its official gold parity, and which is subject to wide fluctuations, would make it impossible for the institution to assume a debt expressed in gold dollars, without obtaining for its own protection some guaranty on the part of the Government to make good any loss incurred through differences in exchange. If the Government of Chile should deem it desirable that the institution raise a loan in

the United States, and if our impression is correct that on account of the exchange situation a certain guaranty would be necessary in any event, it might be possible to convince the Government that it should go one step farther and guarantee the bonds and the interest and sinking-fund payments thereon entirely.

If the matter could be reopened again on the basis of a government guaranty we should for our own guidance like to receive from you some additional information with regard to the nature of the repurchase of the bonds of the French loans of 1911 and 1912 at a sum exceeding their par value in francs. Was this done on account of some question having come up as to the right of holders to collect in some other currency than French francs, and was the repurchase of the bonds at a premium the outcome of a compromise on such question?

Believe us, dear sirs,

Very truly yours.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. Who is it signed by?

Mr. PECORA. I do not know.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I would have to see the initials to say.

Mr. PECORA. The letters are L. K.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is Leonard Keesing.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. Well, in their office. What I was getting at is whose letter was it? Kuhn, Loeb & Co.'s letter?

Mr. PECORA. Kuhn, Loeb & Co. letter; yes, sir. This is a letter sent by your firm to Louis Dreyfus & Co. after they had called to your attention this Chilean financing proposal?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. Now, some stress is laid in this letter, or rather, mention is made of the lack of capital of the Mortgage Bank of Chile. And reference in this letter is made to that circumstance as one which would preclude you from taking over this issue and offering it to the public here without a government guaranty.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. What information did you get from Louis Dreyfus & Co. or from any other source in reply to the request you made in this letter for information respecting the nature of the repurchase of the bonds of the French loans of 1911 and 1912 at a sum exceeding their par value in francs?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. We have a reply which is in French.

Mr. PECORA. Well, what is the contents of it? The substance of it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. You will have to pardon the substance of my translation of it. It says—do you want it read in French or do you want me to try to give a translation of it?

Mr. PECORA. No; just give us a free translation of it.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It says:

As concerns the question which you have raised on the subject of the repurchase of the obligations issued in France in 1911 and 1912, it concerns in effect an equitable arrangement arrived at between the mortgage bank and the French holders who wished to cash their coupons in sterling, an arrangement which was concluded at the time under the auspices of the National Association of Holders of Securities in France.

A better scholar of French has told me that instead of saying "it concerns," I should said "it constitutes."

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. "It constitutes in effect."

The CHAIRMAN. They do not make any reference to the smaller amount of profits that they made? The smaller amount of reserve?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. To clarify that point I might state that I haven't that 6½ percent prospectus before me because it has just

been submitted for the record, but my recollection is clear that we pursued the same line in that prospectus as we did in this prospectus, which says:

The Caja has no capital stock and is not operated for profit. It has power to charge a commission to provide for its expenses and for a reserve fund, as additional security for its bonds, but having accumulated a sufficient reserve, the Caja has now discontinued charging such commission.

Mr. PECORA. What information or advice did your firm have with respect to the value of, the soundness of, the security behind the mortgage loans made by the Chilean Bank? Did you have any advices or information on that at all?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. We had an unbroken record of 70 years during which the largest loss in the aggregate of 10 years was \$40,000. And, of course, we could have no information as to the mortgages themselves. We only had this long record of the Mortgage Bank whose securities in Chile sold as well or better than the Chilean Government's own securities. And in addition to that we insisted on having the guaranty, the unqualified guaranty, endorsed on the bonds of the Republic of Chile itself.

The CHAIRMAN. It seems to have been a kind of public corporation that was not operating for profit?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It was. The closest analogy I can think of is our Federal land banks, operated very much along the same line, although, of course, there is the technical difference that they had stock and this bank had no stock. It is the usual form of credit foncier.

The CHAIRMAN. The Federal land banks all had capital, you know. The Government subscribed to the capital, but they had capital.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Now, at the time your firm, with the Guaranty Co., underwrote this \$20,000,000 issue, had not the Chilean Congress been dissolved?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I think it had, and if I had that circular here, I could read you exactly.

Mr. PECORA. Haven't you the circular before you?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No. You see the circular of the 6½ percent issue went to the stenographer for the record, and that handicaps me.

Mr. PECORA. Is not the stenographer that has it here?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I think Mr. McEldowney has another copy.

Mr. PECORA. Let me read from the copy of that circular which I have before me the following statement:

The bonds are unconditionally guaranteed as to principal, interest, and sinking fund, by endorsement, by the Republic of Chile, pursuant to decree law of the governing council, dated March 9, 1925, and an executive decree, dated June 15, 1925 (supplementing said decree law), issued under the authority of President Alessandri and his cabinet, who are functioning as the Government of Chile, Congress having been dissolved in September 1924, pending the adoption of a new constitution which is now being drafted. The guaranty thus authorized is valid and binding upon the Republic of Chile.

Did your banking firm think, Mr. Buttenwieser, that a guaranty by a government that was in existence under the circumstances indicated by this prospectus was a proper and sound guaranty?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Our counsel, the Guaranty Co. counsel, and most eminent counsel in Chile, all agreed that it was a valid and

binding guaranty of the Republic of Chile, and it has never been questioned by the Government of Chile, the validity of that guaranty, or any of the proceedings surrounding the guaranty of the issuance of the bonds.

Mr. PECORA. Well, did you not recognize that unstable and unsettled political conditions in Chile would affect the value of that guaranty from a practical standpoint, if not from a legal standpoint?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The Chilean Government, over a long period of time, had been stable. Chilean politics, as I recall, had been stable for many years. Chile had—

Mr. PECORA. But a change took place in 1924.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is right.

Mr. PECORA. And this stable Chilean Government that I presume functioned under a constitution adopted by the Chilean people, was replaced in September 1924, by a government which obtained power by the use of power and force?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And dissolved the congress and was about to adopt a new constitution?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. That was the situation presented in the spring of 1925 when these bonds were offered and sold to the American investing public, was it not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Well, I think that question resolves itself into two parts. It is the legal aspect of it and the intrinsic merit of the guaranty. Now as to the legal aspect, we had competent legal advice.

Mr. PECORA. I am passing on to the intrinsic merit, as you call it, and which I call the practical merit of the guaranty.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The practical merit of the guaranty, as far as I can see, is not affected by the Government, or the form of government that happens to be in power at the moment.

Mr. PECORA. If the government is an unstable government would you accept the guaranty of such a government as readily as you would that of a stable government?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. If I were advised—

Mr. PECORA. Away from the legal aspects now, on the practical consideration of the question?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Well, it was the only government that existed, and we were advised that its acts were binding upon the Republic of Chile.

Mr. PECORA. Well, even though it were the only government that existed there, it was nevertheless a government of the nature that has been referred to. Now, would you consider a guaranty of such a government, functioning by decree, under a decree rather than under a constitution, invested in office through the exercise of force and violence, a good practical guaranty upon which to pass on \$90,000,000 of securities?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not want to quibble on this, but it seems to me either the guaranty is binding or it is not binding. The best legal advice that we could get was that it was binding. And the proof of it is that it was always considered a valid and binding thing.

Mr. PECORA. Now you are discussing the legal effect of the guaranty rather than its intrinsic value. Now, address yourself to what you call the intrinsic value of the mortgage, and what would you say?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I say if it were binding that would not affect its intrinsic value.

The CHAIRMAN. How about the securities on which these bonds were based? Did the value of property go down, or what became of the value of the mortgages? Did that continue under this new government?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The value did continue, as far as I know, under the new government; yes.

The CHAIRMAN. There must have been depreciation in the value of their securities or their bonds would not have dropped so.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I did not catch that question, Senator.

The CHAIRMAN. I say there must have been a depreciation in the value of the securities held by the bank or their bonds would not have dropped so.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Well, I think it is more than just the value of the securities back of these bonds that affects the market price of these securities. There are many other problems involved.

Mr. PECORA. We all understand that legally one endorsement is as good as another, but practically they are not alike, are they? They depend on the financial responsibility of the endorser, do they not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. Now, would you not say the same principle would apply to governments?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Well, then, did you consider that the endorsement of a revolutionary government in Chile was a sound and safe endorsement or guarantee?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Well, first, again, Mr. Pecora, I must say that if it were a valid, binding obligation of that Government the form of that government, as far as I can see, makes no particular difference.

Mr. PECORA. Suppose a revolutionary government cannot continue in power, and chaos and disorder prevails, that is reflected in the ability of the government to make good on its guarantee, is it not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It does not follow that the form of government has any bearing on the ability of the government to make good under its guaranty.

Mr. PECORA. Have you not heard as a banker of governments repudiating the acts of prior governments?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, and we had competent advice, I repeat, to state that the Republic of Chile could not repudiate the acts of this Government, and have not.

Mr. PECORA. Well, here you were given this guaranty at the time when this Government of Chile was functioning without a constitution and without a congress, which had been previously dissolved by the usurping government.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Mr. Pecora, I can only rely on the previous statement that I have made, that all the counsel that we consulted, two eminent firms in New York, leading counsel in Chile, said that as it was the only apparent government there its acts could not be repudiated under international law. And the fact is its acts were not repudiated. The validity of this guaranty has never been questioned.

Mr. PECORA. Did that control your judgment as to the intrinsic value of the guaranty?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The intrinsic value is predicated on other considerations than the legal question.

Mr. PECORA. I agree with you, but did the fact that this guaranty was obtained from a government that existed under the circumstances that then prevailed in Chile have any bearing in your mind upon the sufficiency, from a practical standpoint, of this guaranty?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No. I do not see that it has any bearing.

Mr. PECORA. And it was in pursuance of such judgment that you accepted the guaranty and underwrote this issue and passed it on to the public here? Is that right?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Guided, once again, by competent legal advice that this guaranty would be valid and legally binding. And if I may consult counsel as to whether or not I may read into the record a copy of the telegram which we had from the State Department on the subject? But I do not know whether we are permitted to make that public.

The CHAIRMAN. From our State Department?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes. Supplementing that letter that you saw, Senator Fletcher.

The CHAIRMAN. Well, they simply say that there has been no change in their recognition of the Government there. No objection to reading that in, I do not think. You might read that into the record. Just read the telegram. Have you got it with you?

Mr. PECORA. I have here a copy of a cable addressed to Manuel Foster, Esq., Santiago, Chile. Under date of June 22, 1925. Have you got a copy of that cable before you?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Who sent that cable?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Did you say June 22, to Manuel Foster?

Mr. PECORA. June 22, 1925. File no. 1123-6.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I have one of June 21 to Manuel Foster.

Mr. STEWART. How does it start, Mr. Pecora?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. What is the first of it?

Mr. PECORA. It starts:

N.Y., June 22, '25.

Copy of cable to Manuel Foster, Esq., Santiago, Chile: Answering questions your cable 19th instant.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Well, that is "from."

Mr. STEWART. That is received from.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is why I could not place it.

Mr. PECORA. I have here "Copy of cable to Manuel Foster."

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It is "from." I think you will find it reads that way.

Mr. PECORA. Well, the copy we have says "to."

Mr. STEWART. Here is the original.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Is that the one that says: "Answering questions your cable 19th instant"?

Mr. PECORA. Yes. "Your cable 19th instant." Well, the copy you furnished us reads: "Copy of cable to." Undoubtedly a typographical error.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I am sorry. I just wanted to make clear.

Mr. PECORA. Well, that was a cable, then, from Manuel Foster?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes; that is right.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Manuel Foster represented your firm, did he?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. In Chile?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. He was our counsel in this transaction in Chile.

Mr. PECORA. Yes. He said as follows in this cable:

Answering questions your cable 19th instant: First president was duly elected under constitution, but present cabinet was appointed by former military council and practically confirmed by the president. Constitutionally they have no authority to recognize debts unless by law enacted by Congress. But in this case their decrees as proceeding from a de facto government recognized by the country and respected by all the citizens are valid and binding upon the Republic.

Second. As I have stated in the preceding point your assumption is right.

Third. It depends on decree law 308 dated March 9 up to 50,000,000 pesos Chilean currency but said decree law was complemented by executive decree dated June 15 extending authorization up to \$20,000,000 United States currency in order to authorize the negotiation of one single loan. This last decree, although not shaped in the form of the so-called "decree laws", enforced the same binding upon the Republic.

Fourth. The simple fact of using the word "guaranty" conveys the idea of a collateral obligation and indicates the existence of a principal debtor which in this case is the Caja but decree 8 of June authorizes endorsement of direct guaranty to bondholders on temporary and definitive bonds.

Fifth. Both decrees have been signed by President and by minister of finance as it is observed in the promulgation of laws passed by Congress.

Sixth. I insist in my opinion that insofar as the legal aspects of this negotiation is concerned there is no danger in the operation.

The Caja Hipotecario is a state institution or organism created by the state and administered by a director and a board appointed by government and its bonds are signed by a high government official. Therefore, in my opinion the government is ultimately responsible for its operations. In this very sense it was considered by France and Germany when gold bonds were issued in 1911 and 1912. Therefore even without any declaration from the government its guaranty or final responsibility is absolutely clear, as arising from acts of its own organism. I must also add that as you are acting bona fide with the only apparent government of this country you shall be placed under the protection not only of the Chilean but also of even the international law.

Now, your firm sent a reply to that cable to Mr. Manuel Foster, did it not, under date of June 23, 1925?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And in that cable did you say as follows:

Is it not correct to refer to council as governing council which we prefer instead of military council?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Now, your legal adviser resident in Chile said that this Government whose guaranty you were seeking, or rather the President of the Government whose guaranty you were seeking, was appointed by a former military council, or rather the Cabinet was appointed by a former military council. You did not like that term "military council" and suggested a modification or change to "governing council", is that correct?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. If he felt they were synonymous.

Mr. PECORA. Yes. And that is the term that you used in your prospectus to the American public, was it not, "governing council" instead of "military council"?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Which it was.

Mr. PECORA. Why did you prefer the term "governing council" to "military council" for the purpose of your prospectus?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Well, I think "governing council" is a more accurate statement of what a government is than "military council", which might be misinterpreted.

Mr. PECORA. Were you overruling the advice conveyed to you by your counsel resident in Chile when you referred to it as a "military council" and you suggested you preferred the term of "governing council"?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. We were not overruling it, Mr. Pecora. We merely wanted to get the most accurate statement in English of what that council was.

Mr. PECORA. Well, hadn't he given you a very definite designation or characterization of it when he said it was a military council?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It was doubtless a governing council or else he would not have agreed to the word "governing."

Mr. PECORA. Had not Mr. Foster accurately designated or described this council as a military council when he cabled your firm under date of June 22, 1925?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. In English he had suggested that it was a military council.

Mr. PECORA. He did not suggest it. He stated it.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. He stated it was a military council.

Mr. PECORA. Yes. He stated it "By former military council", and then you cable the following day and say: "Is it not correct to refer to council as governing council which we prefer instead of military council." Now the reason you had that preference was because you thought that it would sound better in the prospectus to the investing public here to say that this Government or the Cabinet of the President had been confirmed by a governing council rather than a military council? Is not that plainly the reason?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I would say that "governing council" is less susceptible to misinterpretation than "military council", because, as you see, it takes a long legal explanation to show that military council is that—the guaranty of this Government under this military council was a valid, binding obligation of the Republic of Chile under Chilean law and under international law.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know the personnel of that council that you preferred to call a "governing council"?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No; I do not know.

Mr. PECORA. Was it not all composed of military and naval officers?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not know that.

The CHAIRMAN. Did you ever approach the Government of Chile with the idea of making good their guaranty?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir. We protested to the Chilean Government with reference to making good their guaranty on all these \$90,000,000 of bonds, and we sent a very comprehensive protest first to the State Department asking them to forward it, and I have it here, if you desire it, the reply of the State Department wherein they stated why they could not forward it, and subsequently we forwarded it ourselves to the Republic of Chile and to the Mortgage Bank, both.

Mr. PECORA. By the way, had the American Government recognized this de facto government at that time?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The State Department advised us in that telegram, of which you have a copy, that they had recognized no change in the Government. I believe that is the exact wording of it.

Mr. PECORA. Well, did you interpret that as meaning that our Government had recognized formally this de facto government? Or does it mean that it had not extended such recognition to it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I cannot answer that.

Mr. PECORA. Well, who can answer it for your firm?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I believe the fact that it had recognized no change, that they considered the Government of Chile existed under the same circumstances as it had existed. In other words, they recognized that no change had taken place.

Mr. PECORA. In other words, they recognized that the de facto Government was merely a de facto government, did they not? Is that not what that means?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is a legal point again on which I am really not qualified to pass. But I believe these legal opinions amply cover that point.

Mr. PECORA. Well, I do not know, Mr. Buttenwieser. Your legal adviser in Chile refers to this council as a military council. You asked him to correct it and refer to it as a governing council because you preferred that to a military council. Now whose opinions control your judgment, your own or the advices of your lawyers with regard to these questions?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. On legal subjects of course the advice of our counsel.

The CHAIRMAN. What response did the Chilean Government make to your protest?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. They wrote us a letter stating why it was impossible for them to live up to the payments under their guaranties. The whole subject was covered in the text of the Chilean moratorium law of July 1931.

The CHAIRMAN. The effect of their reply was that while they did not deny the guaranty they were unable to perform the contract?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is it exactly. They have never denied in any way the validity of their contract.

The CHAIRMAN. Did they give any reason why they could not live up to the guaranty?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes. They furnished many statements—they published some statements as to why it was impossible for them to service their foreign obligations. Their own obligations and their guaranteed obligations.

The CHAIRMAN. Did they make any promise to do it in the future?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes. They said they hoped to be able to do it.

The CHAIRMAN. I think we had better take a recess. We will now recess until 10 o'clock tomorrow.

(Thereupon, at 4:30 o'clock p.m. Tuesday, June 27, 1933, an adjournment was taken until 10 o'clock a.m. the next day, Wednesday, June 28, 1933.)

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT 1

(In the matter of terms and conditions to be prescribed by the Commission in connection with the issuance of securities under section 20a of the Interstate Commerce Act, as amended)

THE MARKETING OF AMERICAN RAILROAD SECURITIES

INTRODUCTION

THE PROBLEM

No more important problem today challenges the skill and wisdom of American railroad managements—and the public authorities charged with the function of regulation—than that of how to obtain the capital necessary to provide the facilities required to transport the commerce of our growing country.

It has been estimated by several high authorities that in order to meet with any degree of adequacy the requirements for new construction, for additional main tracks, sidings, and yards, for equipment and terminal facilities, for elimination of grade crossings, especially in the larger cities, for block signaling and other safety appliances, and the requisite general strengthening and improvement of existing properties, expenditures are called for, aggregating as much as \$1,000,000,000 a year for a series of years to come.

There is never-ceasing demand in the United States for more and better railway services. Unless this demand is to remain unsatisfied the railway management must find some way to attract to the railway industry an uninterrupted and steadily augmenting flow of new capital.

The problem is no less vital to the public whose prosperity and convenience so largely depend upon the adequacy of its transportation service. At the same time the public, which pays the rates providing the return earned upon capital invested in railroads, has a clear interest in having the railroads sell their securities—and obtain their new capital—upon terms which involve no burden upon rates beyond that actually necessary to attract the required capital.

Capital already invested in railroad facilities is irrevocably committed, but any and all new capital must be attracted from the investing public upon terms and under conditions which appeal to that public.

It is thus of essential importance that the following purposes be accomplished:

1. Obtain the capital.
2. Attract it upon fair and reasonable terms.
3. Have a broad and stable market for railroad securities and a favorable disposition on the part of investors toward such securities.

Generally speaking, the existing method of disposing of railroad securities is by three processes:

1. Offering stocks pro rata to existing shareholders, the issue usually being underwritten by bankers;
2. Selling bonds at a fixed price to bankers, who through the medium of a syndicate and with the cooperation of distributing houses throughout the country, market them to the public; and
3. Selling an issue through a banker to the public, with a commission to the banker for his services. (This method is very rarely employed.)

The question is now raised whether it would be well that the existing practice be changed and that railroad securities hereafter be sold by one of the following methods, viz, (1) unrestricted public bidding, or (2) competition among bankers.

Such a change would, of course, involve the abandonment of the heretofore prevailing method, under which a railroad company usually selects a banking house of high standing and, so long as the services of that banker are satisfactory, makes its issues of securities customarily through or with the aid of that house.

The suggested change contemplates that the relationship between the railroad and the investment market shall be similar to that between American municipalities and the investment market, wherein issues of securities are usually sold by competitive bidding.

In considering this problem, the paramount question is, How can it be made certain that the vast amounts of new capital required by the railroads, year in and year out, shall be forthcoming upon the most advantageous terms?

I. THE EXISTING PRACTICE OF DEALING THROUGH BANKERS

A. WITH AMERICAN RAILROADS

As a rule, railroad companies of the United States, like those of other countries, market their bonds by selling them either to or through bankers. In cases where securities are offered for pro rata subscription to stockholders it is customary for the corporation to protect itself by arranging with bankers to underwrite, or to form a group to underwrite, their sale, that is, to agree to purchase such of the securities as are not taken by the stockholders.

Most of the important railroad companies, as well as industrial corporations, make a practice of dealing with a particular banking house or a particular group of bankers in marketing securities. This relationship rarely rests on formal contract. As a rule, the relationship is informal and tacit and its duration, as will be developed in detail further on, depends wholly upon the satisfaction of the railroad with the services rendered. A railroad company gradually comes to recognize a particular banking house as its banker.

The existence of such a relationship means that the railroad has at its disposal continuously the services, skill, standing, experience, advice, and financial influence and capacity of the banker.

Among the banker's functions are to keep track of the financial situation and requirements of the railroad, to assist in the preparation, in advance of the need, of a proper and serviceable system for financing such requirements; to advise as to the class, kind, and denomination of securities to be issued and as to the best time for selling them, so that his clients may not miss an opportune moment for meeting their requirements; to indicate from his survey of the markets of the world his judgment as to the amount of securities which could be absorbed in one or the other market; to scrutinize the mortgages and deeds of trust under which securities are to be issued, with a view to their provisions being, on the one hand, carefully protective of the investor, and, on the other hand, sufficiently broad and elastic not to hamper and restrict the corporation unduly in respect of its future requirements.

The terms of a negotiation are by no means imposed by the banker, for it is easily within the means, and is recognized as an important and responsible duty, of those conducting negotiations on behalf of the railroad company, to acquaint themselves with the reasonable market value of the securities which it desires to sell and to insist upon obtaining a fully adequate price.

The railroads for whom bankers act nowadays can have no inducement to continue that affiliation except satisfaction with the services rendered.

A railroad company generally is, and always ought to be, free to terminate its relationship with its bankers at any time and entirely within its own discretion.

That changes in the relationships between railroads and bankers do occur is indicated by the variations which take place in the course of time, in the connections, and the relative influence and position of the prominent banking firms which deal in railroad securities.

The relationship between the railroad and its bankers is one which, whilst not limiting the railroad's freedom of action according to its own judgment of its best interest, does involve upon the part of the bankers certain definite and continuous duties and obligations, more fully referred to later on.

B. WITH INDUSTRIAL CORPORATIONS

Industrial corporations, unlike railway companies subject to public regulation, are entirely free to sell their securities in whatever way they deem most advantageous. Their managers, or presidents, are very frequently among the larger stockholders, and indeed, in numerous cases, are the principal stockholders, of the respective concerns, and therefore have a more direct and important pecuniary stake in their enterprises than can be the case with the chief executives of our large railroad corporations, the ownership of which is scattered in the hands of several hundred thousand shareholders.

Yet there are hardly any industrial concerns either here or in Europe which dispose of their securities by competitive bidding among bankers or by direct offering to the public. Practically all such corporations pursue the course of negotiating with one particular bank or group of bankers and entrusting the

handling of their security issues to such banker or group of bankers so long as their services prove satisfactory. Their action is conclusive evidence that the system of competitive bidding is found unsuitable and disserviceable by the consensus of opinion of those in charge of industrial affairs, here and in Europe.

II. HOW RAILROAD SECURITIES ARE PLACED WITH THE PUBLIC

The great complexity involved in the sale of securities will readily be seen from a brief outline of the method usually adopted in marketing a large issue of bonds. The railroad, in the first instance, sells the issue to a strong banking firm at a price mutually agreed upon through negotiation. That firm then associates with itself a syndicate consisting of many (usually hundreds) of other banking, brokerage, investment, and distributing houses throughout the country, each having its clientele of investment customers.

Bankers, of course, do not buy securities for permanent investment by themselves. If bankers or syndicates permanently kept the securities which they bought from the railroads their capacity to undertake such transactions would be exhausted very soon.

If securities are to be placed, they must ultimately find lodgment with investors, and, while the amounts of securities taken by large investors, such as the life insurance companies, savings banks, and capitalists, appear large, their aggregate, especially since the advent of the high surtaxes, is small compared with the investments of the rank and file of small investors.

Pending the formation of a syndicate, the firm which has contracted with the railroad stands in the breach, and is responsible to the railroad whether or not it succeeds in forming the syndicate. Even after the formation of the syndicate, the practice is that the responsibility of the contracting firm continues and it remains liable to the railroad for the due fulfillment by each syndicate member of the obligation undertaken by him.

Then begins the laborious process of selling securities to ultimate investors, through advertising, letters and circulars, and personal presentation, and in this labor are engaged large numbers of dealers in securities, each with his own clientele. In time, if the issue is a success, the securities are absorbed.

If the issue is not a success the participant in the syndicate must either sell the securities at a loss or carry them along until the advent of propitious times enables them to dispose of them.

The selling of securities to the public has in recent years undergone a radical change. Formerly, the principal buyers of railroad bonds were wealthy individuals and large corporations, especially insurance companies and savings banks. The former, owing to the surtaxes, have practically been eliminated as absorbers of railroad bonds and confine their investments very largely to tax-exempt securities, while the insurance corporations and savings banks do not invest as largely as before the war in railroad securities.

It has therefore been found necessary to discover new channels for the absorption of railroad bonds. This has been accomplished within the past few years by a most intensive campaign of education and distribution among the rank and file of investors.

The result has been exceedingly gratifying in that a vast army of small investors has been developed. The achievement is of great public consequence from the social and economic point of view.

III. THE PROPOSAL TO MARKET RAILROAD SECURITIES BY COMPETITIVE BIDDING

It is now urged in certain quarters that railroad companies would do better if they should discontinue dealing habitually with particular banking houses, and, whenever they have securities to sell, would offer them for sale by competitive bidding among bankers, regardless of past affiliations.

Some even go so far as to advocate that bankers, as such should not be used at all, not even upon a competitive basis, but that the railroad companies should sell their securities directly to their own stockholders or to the public at large, preferably offering them for public tender and accepting the proposals of the highest bidders.

If railroads offered bonds direct for public subscription in limited amounts, the result might be fairly satisfactory in good or normal times, although even then, deprived of the facilities, the skill, and the sponsorship of responsible bankers, the prices obtained would probably be lower than those which would have been realized by dealing with a banker, and that consideration takes no

account of the uncertainty in which the railroad would necessarily find itself as to what portion of the funds it required would be in fact realized as the result of the public offering.

Moreover, the public demand would naturally concentrate itself upon the issues of the best known and most prosperous railroads, making it very difficult for railroads not enjoying high credit to obtain necessary funds—all the more difficult, as the system of competitive bidding would offer no inducement to bankers to take upon themselves the risk and responsibility of acquiring such issues.

Under that plan there would likewise be less assurance of the pursuance by railroads of a sound and consistent financial policy such as a prudent and conservative banker requires as a basis for commending securities to the confidence of the investing public which looks to the banker for advice and leadership.

In unfavorable times, of course, the public's response to an offering of securities is small, at times exceedingly small. It occurs frequently that bankers or syndicates have to carry issues of bonds, which they have purchased, for many months or even years, until investment demand revives. If an issue of bonds offered by a railroad for competitive bids on direct public subscription resulted in nonsuccess, the issue, if saleable at all, could only be disposed of at a very heavy sacrifice.

The failure of a public offering and the consequent public knowledge that the railroad had been unable to obtain the funds it requires, would cause grave damage to a railroad's credit, if it did not for the time entirely destroy it, would cause alarm amongst investors, and in not a few cases might cause bankruptcy.

That is the vital and fundamental difference between the risk incurred by municipalities and that incurred by railroads in the disposal of their bonds by public bidding. If a municipality fails to dispose of its bonds, the situation thereby created, though embarrassing, does not ordinarily involve grave harm, and can be dealt with. If a railroad fails, however, the damage done is exceedingly grave at best—and may be irremediable.

THE PUBLIC DOES NOT BID

As a matter of fact, unrestricted public competition does not in practice mean what the term implies, because all experience has shown that the public does not care for such bidding and actually refrains from participating therein to any appreciable extent. Even in the case of municipal securities, it is amply demonstrated that the offerings are not taken by the public in the process of competitive bidding, except in a very limited measure. The successful bidders both as to quantity and price are almost invariably bankers or banking syndicates who buy for resale to the investor.

The public wisely requires, even in the case of municipal securities, the advice and moral responsibility of bankers. They want to be sure that all legal matters have been properly looked into by somebody, not the seller, and that the soundness and validity of the security is vouched for by a competent and reliable firm.

If, as experience has shown, the public cannot be depended on to cover the offering even of municipal bonds by competitive bidding, this would be so in a still more pronounced degree in the case of railroad securities. It follows that public competition would really mean not offering securities to the public, but offering them to the bankers.

The banker, if he were—as he would be in this case—entirely free to bid or not to bid, to pick and choose, to take the best and leave the less good alone, would actually leave the less good alone, with the result that many railroads would find themselves faced with the grave consequences of the failure of public offerings.

Municipal and State securities possess the immense advantage of being tax free. Yet it has happened, in the past quite often, and even not unfrequently of more recent dates, that such issues were not covered when offered for public bidding, the failure, entire or partial, being due usually to their being unsuited to the market or because of some doubt as to their legality. Can it be doubted that the same result would occur much more frequently in the case of railroad securities if offered for public bidding?

THE EXPERIENCE OF CITIES

It is true that Government and municipal securities in this country are usually offered for competitive bidding, but Government, State, and municipal financing is not comparable with corporation financing. In the former case the securities based upon the taxing authority are in the simplest form—generally little more than a plain promise to pay—and in recent years, since the advent of high surtaxes, a ready market is usually assured by the tax-exemption feature.

Nevertheless, public officials usually deem it wise to consult bankers before determining their financial policies and particularly before issuing large loans, and at times have sought and obtained in advance informal guarantees from bankers that offerings will be covered. They can, of course, rely upon bankers rendering assistance as a matter of civic duty. In the case of railroads, with the element of habitual clientage between railroad and banker eliminated, it would naturally be impossible to count upon any such uncompensated advice and assistance.

As illustrating the point that the financing of State and even the highest grade municipal bonds has not always been successful in spite of the tax-exemption feature, it may be mentioned that in June and August 1907, the city of New York offered two issues of bonds of \$29,000,000 and \$15,000,000, respectively, for which bids of only \$2,100,000 and \$2,700,000, respectively, were received. The issues were sold by private sale to bankers a few months later.

About the same time a small offering of bonds by the State of New York met with a similar result.

In 1914, shortly after the outbreak of the war, the city of New York, finding itself in immediate need of \$100,000,000 of gold to pay notes maturing in England and France, turned to J. P. Morgan & Co. and Kuhn, Loeb & Co., who, without compensation, as a matter of public duty, undertook to organize, and in the midst of conditions of unprecedented difficulty, did organize a syndicate to provide the necessary funds.

In more than one instance in the years preceding that occurrence, the city was compelled, in order to avoid failure of an issue offered for public tender for the purpose of meeting pressing requirements, to have recourse to one or the other of the leading banking houses. In numerous cases it was only large subscriptions by such banking houses—made often without any expectation of profit and resulting none too rarely in losses—which avoided the, at least partial, failure of public offerings of the bonds of the city of New York.

There is no reason to believe that the cities have been better off under the practice of selling bonds at public offering to the highest bidders than they would have been had they been permitted to deal privately with the bankers as do the railroads. But, even if it were otherwise, it is manifest that railroad companies could not possibly expect to fare as well as do the municipalities if they had to depend upon the uncertain and fluctuating public demand when they attempt to sell their securities at public offering to the highest bidder.

Especially does this hold true in the case of the less strong railroads, where a careful analysis and study of the condition of the company and sometimes even an auditor's or an expert's report is required before a conservative banker will stand sponsor for the company's securities. The investing public will neither take the trouble, nor does it possess the qualifications, to analyze for itself the position of the securities of the less well-known properties and to form a reasoned estimate as to their degree of safety, based, as such estimate must be, upon the compilation and study of statistical and other data, which it is among the functions of the banker to gather and to make available to his investment clients in convenient and easily understood form.

In this connection it is significant that the Farm Loan Bureau of the United States Treasury has found it advantageous to issue the bonds of the farm-loan banks not by competitive bidding but through a group of bankers selected by the Bureau whom it may at all times feel free to consult and who watch the markets in the interest of the Bureau.

EUROPEAN PRACTICE

In not a single European country does the system prevail of competitive sale, either general or limited, of securities on the part of corporations. Moreover, many even of the governments and municipalities, in placing their loans,

have recourse not to competitive bidding but to regularly established and continuous connections with a banking house or a group of banking houses. Not one of the foreign governments, belligerent or neutral, which during the European war have found access to the American investment market for the securities of their respective countries, had recourse to competitive bidding amongst bankers or otherwise. In each instance the government concerned has dealt with some one particular banker or group of bankers whom it selected as efficient and worthy of confidence.

A cabled inquiry addressed within a week to eight different countries in Europe, and also to Japan, to find out whether, since the war, the practice has been modified in those countries of dealing with selected bankers for the sale of public service and other corporate securities and even, in numerous cases, governmental or municipal bonds, elicits the information that no reason has been found to change that practice and that it continues to prevail.

IV. THE PRESENT METHOD OF UNDERWRITING THE SALE OF STOCKS TO SHAREHOLDERS

Under the laws of most States and the charters of most corporations, it is necessary that new issues of stock, or of bonds carrying the privilege of conversion into stock, must first be offered for pro rata subscription to the corporations' stockholders. In such cases the banker's knowledge of markets is valuable to advise the corporation of the character of securities which its shareholders are likely to accept or for which the subscription rights would command a market value.

When an offering of new stock is made to shareholders of a corporation it creates a technically weak market position, inasmuch as both the existing stockholder and the speculator know that there is a mass of new stock about to issue, and the market must absorb it. Consequently the speculator is apt to incline toward rushing into the market, arguing to himself, "I will sell that stock. I will get it back cheaper. The market must absorb such and such a number of millions of new stock, and it cannot do that without going down. I am quite safe in selling some."

Experience has shown that in many cases the stockholder to whom the so-called right to subscribe for new stock is offered, does not exercise that right. He is not always prepared to put up additional cash. He frequently sells his "rights" for whatever may be their market value.

Consequently, by the very issue of additional stock, offered to existing stockholders, there is created an unfavorable and somewhat hazardous market condition. Naturally, the tendency invariably is for the offering of stock to depress the existing level of the stock. That may go so far as to remove any inducements to the stockholder to subscribe for the new stock, and to render "rights" valueless. An unprotected offering, i. e., an offering not protected by underwriters, is a target for selling.

Moreover, not to mention the damage to its credit in case of the failure of such an offering, the railroad is uncertain pending the time in which the securities are under offer to the stockholders (usually not less than from 45 to 60 days) whether or not, or to what extent, the stockholders will subscribe, and is, consequently, in doubt whether, at the end of the subscription period, it will come into possession of the funds it requires.

All of this is obviated by the formation of an underwriting syndicate inasmuch as it guarantees to take and pay for any part of the offering which the stockholders may not want to take. The existence of such a syndicate and the resulting guarantee of the success of the offering has a strong moral effect upon the stockholders in encouraging them to subscribe, and an equally strong effect in discouraging speculators from "short selling" while an unprotected offering invites such selling.

It follows that a railroad can safely afford to offer securities at a much higher price when underwritten than they would risk fixing when not secured and protected by an underwriting.

A characteristic illustration of the foregoing is furnished by the experience of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., than which there is no stronger railroad corporation in the country, when, in 1903, it, without underwriting, offered \$75,000,000 of its stock for subscription by its stockholders at 120 percent. The market price of the stock at the time was, and for some time had been, around 145 percent. Owing to the large difference between the market price and the price of the offering, the officers and directors of the railroad deemed it unnecessary to insure success by an underwriting.

As a result of changes in market conditions, sales of rights by stockholders, and selling by speculators, it being known that there was no underwriting syndicate, the market value of the stock rapidly declined. When the price in its descent had reached 125½ and the failure of the offering appeared imminent, the railroad finally called upon its bankers to form a syndicate to underwrite the issue, which was promptly done. The reassuring effect of the mere public announcement that a syndicate had guaranteed to take and pay for any part of the offering which was not subscribed for by the stockholders was such as to arrest immediately the selling on the part of alarmed stockholders as well as by speculators. The decline in the market stopped, and a threatened failure, which might have involved serious consequences and affected railroad credit generally, was turned into a complete success.

Even after taking into consideration the expense of an underwriting syndicate, a railroad will usually obtain materially higher net proceeds from an underwritten offering than from one not underwritten, in addition to the advantage of being certain of securing the required funds.

Manifestly, it is more advantageous to a railroad's financial position and the maintenance of the price level of its securities to offer a security, even to its stockholders, at, say, 110, and pay a reasonable underwriting commission, rather than to offer it at par without an underwriting.

The cases in which railroad companies or other corporations have successfully sold their securities direct to the investor are exceedingly rare, and even then usually at prices below what could have been obtained from bankers.

To quote only one example of nonsuccess in the case of direct dealing with the public, the Vermont Valley Railroad in 1914 offered for competition by sealed tenders an issue of \$2,300,000 of its 6 percent 1-year notes. Although the Vermont Valley Railroad was a very prosperous concern, having a record at that time of having paid dividends at the rate of 10 percent per annum for 9 years, and the notes had the additional security of being guaranteed by the Connecticut River Railroad Co., the offering resulted in complete failure, practically no bids having been received.

On the other hand, the case of the case of the American Telephone & Telegraph Co. which recently sold a large issue of stock at par directly to its stockholders, without the intermediation of bankers, has been cited as significant and indicative of the possibilities of effective results without the co-operation of bankers. The real significance in that case, however, lies in the patent fact that had that issue been underwritten by bankers a considerably higher price for the company could have been obtained. The security sold by the American Telephone & Telegraph Co. was seasoned stock paying 9 percent dividends. It was offered at par. Bankers, in consideration of a reasonable commission, would gladly have underwritten the offering at a considerably higher price. It should be understood that this does not imply any suggestion of criticism as to the course pursued by the company. There were valid considerations of broad policy which guided the decision of those in responsible charge, to give to the vast body of its stockholders the benefit of a stock offering at a particularly attractive price.

V. EFFECTIVE COMPETITION PREVAILS UNDER PRESENT METHODS

There are ever present elements of actual or potential competition which assure favorable terms to a railroad company dealing habitually with the same bankers.

The price and the margin of profit or commission at which a banker concludes a negotiation with a railroad company for its securities is necessarily in competition with the terms upon which other bankers negotiate with other railroad companies for their securities.

The prices at which railroads sell their securities are now matters of public record. Moreover, the terms of a contract between the railroad and the bankers are subject to the approval of the Interstate Commerce Commission. No banker expecting to maintain his regular connection with a railroad company can do otherwise than pay full and fair value for the securities which it has to sell. It is a matter of necessity and self-interest for him to do so.

Railroad companies, through various means, are well able to place an accurate estimate upon the market value of securities which they have for sale, and no board of directors could afford to incur the approbrium and responsibility of selling securities to their regular banking connections otherwise than on the basis of what they are reasonably and fairly worth, considering the time and the conditions.

The prevailing market prices of existing issues fix very closely the prices at which new securities can be sold to investors. The banker who would make a practice of marketing the securities of his clients at prices materially below the prevailing prices for issues of similar character and quality would soon lose his clients.

In isolated instances, for the purpose of obtaining advertisement or position, or even, in certain instances, for reasons of a less legitimate kind, others than the regular banking connections of particular railroads may conceivably be willing to pay a somewhat higher price for an issue of securities than such regular connections; but there is no reason whatever to think that such "occasional" bidders would be able or willing to do better for the railroads, year in and year out, than the bankers usually acting for those railroads. On the contrary, there is every reason to expect the reverse.

Whether through a system either of unrestricted public bidding or of competitive bidding limited to bankers, the railroads year in and year out would obtain higher prices for their securities than have been and are being realized under the existing time-tested system, is a matter of opinion and cannot be anything else. Whether that opinion is pro or con, there can be no question that as against gaining a wholly problematical and uncertain benefit the railroads stand to lose the certain, well-established, and weighty advantages which now accrue to them through the responsibility and moral and practical obligations toward them of the bankers with whom they habitually deal.

To market railroad securities on a large scale requires a combination of skill, experience, capital, reputation, and connections that, from the nature of the case, can be possessed by only a limited number of concerns at any one time, because only the test of time will produce most of these necessary qualities.

That skill, experience, and reputation it is the business of the banker to make available to his clients, together with his financial potency and relationships.

A banker of long experience with a record of success, conservatism, and integrity develops a power to place securities that is of great value to his clients, cumulatively so the longer the relationship is maintained.

RESULTS MUST BE JUDGED OVER PERIOD COVERING BOTH RISING AND DECLINING MARKETS

The question of the best and most serviceable method of selling railroad securities must be determined not from the wholly exceptional and fortuitous circumstances which have prevailed during the last year, but in the light of the experience of the longer past and the needs of the future.

In the marketing of securities, as in other businesses, there are occasional periods of excessive activity, usually of comparatively short duration, occasional periods of acute depression, and longer periods of normal activity.

It happens that this year has been a period of unparalleled activity in the marketing of securities of domestic issues, simultaneously with and partly caused by growing reluctance to invest in issues of European countries. There has been a vast and almost insatiable demand for new domestic securities, particularly bonds, an almost uninterrupted decrease in interest rates and a corresponding increase in the market value of securities.

The result has been that bankers and syndicates have been much more than usually successful in marketing the domestic security issues which they have purchased and that as a rule new security issues have advanced in the market and reached prices in excess of the issue price. The upward trend of security values is illustrated by the fact that in the last 10 months the average market price of 10 standard railroad bond issues taken at random has increased about 13 points.

It has been a time when it was possible to indulge in improvident bidding or "spite-bidding", without being deterred by the swift penalty of nonsuccess in marketing, which follows such practices under normal circumstances.

Under these conditions, it is easy for critics who consider only recent experience, and whose knowledge does not carry them back to the pre-war years (which, after all, furnish the best standards for judging the future), to jump at the conclusion that the railroads have not been receiving the best possible prices for the securities they have marketed and that higher prices would have been realized if the sale of railroad securities had been opened up for competition.

Criticism has been especially easy and abundant on the part of those who have little or no background of experience in the marketing of railroad

securities to guide them, who have not had to bear the responsibility of financing the requirements of great railroad properties in normal times and during periods of depression and who do not realize the necessity of looking ahead to the future periods of depression or of more normal demand for securities when the railroads of the country will have the same need for new capital as now.

VI. PRESENT PROCEDURE HAS PROVED OF ADVANTAGE TO THE RAILROADS

To deal through bankers in accordance with present practice, has actually proved itself a source of distinct financial advantage to railroads—even the most prosperous and soundly financed companies.

A few conspicuous cases may be cited here to illustrate the point:¹

1. In March 1905 the Pennsylvania Railroad arranged with its bankers to form a syndicate to underwrite the offer to its shareholders at par of \$100,000,000 Pennsylvania Railroad 3½ percent convertible bonds (convertible into stock at 150 percent). The stockholders subscribed for less than 10 percent of the offering and, consequently, the underwriting syndicate had to take and pay for about \$90,000,000 of the bonds. The bonds within the year declined to 97½ percent and never again reached par, the price at which they were first offered.

If it had not been for the underwriting syndicate, the situation, resulting from the failure of the stockholders to subscribe and thus provide the money needed by the railroad, would have been very embarrassing to the railroad and very serious in its effect upon the general financial and investment situation of the country.

2. In 1908 a situation had arisen which had brought the market for railroad bonds in this country to a complete standstill. Railroads for many months were unable to obtain funds except, to a limited extent, by means of the costly and dangerous expedient of selling short-term notes. The effect was cumulative and far-reaching and threatened to bring about serious consequences. As this juncture the bankers of the Pennsylvania Railroad succeeded in inducing the two foremost banking houses in England, Messrs. N. M. Rothschild & Sons, and Messrs. Baring Bros. & Co., Ltd. (the former of whom had not issued an American security for many years), to purchase and bring out jointly with them at 96 percent an issue of \$40,000,000 Pennsylvania Railroad 4 percent consolidated bonds.

Largely in consequence of the prestige and placing power and investment following of the issuing houses, the public offering was a complete success and its effect, as recognized by many published comments here and abroad, was to break the deadlock which had existed, and to cause capital to flow again freely into the investment market.

3. In August 1913 bankers formed a syndicate to underwrite the offer to Union Pacific stockholders of \$88,000,000 Southern Pacific stock trust certificates at 92 percent. The effectuation of that sale was of very great importance as, falling it by a certain very near date, the Southern Pacific stock in question would have been placed, under a court decree, in the hands of a receiver, the sentimental and actual effect of which course would have been grave.

In the face of many predictions that a syndicate to guarantee the sale of so vast an amount of stock could not be formed under the then prevailing generally disturbed and unfavorable conditions, the bankers, with the aid of their connections throughout America and Europe, succeeded in the undertaking, the syndicate as finally made up consisting of nearly a thousand participants. It is entirely safe and well within bounds to say that if that mass of stock had been offered without guaranty and protection of an underwriting syndicate, it would not have been sold—if at all, within the time limit set by the court—at a price averaging better than 80 percent.

4. In connection with the first plan for the dissolution of the Union Pacific-Southern Pacific combination approved by Attorney General Wickersham (which failed of adoption because of the refusal of the California Railroad Commission to approve certain of its features), he imposed the condition that the sale of the Union Pacific Co.'s holdings of Southern Pacific stock (which would be offered for pro rata purchase to the stockholders in the Southern Pacific Co.) should be underwritten by a syndicate.

¹ A number of additional instances of a similar value to the railroads will be found on pages 33 to 37.

He imposed that condition for the manifest reason that the sale of the stock, however attractive the price to the stockholders might be, could be insured only in case definite arrangements were made for a sale of the stock that might not be taken by the stockholders upon the offering.

None of the aforementioned transactions, under the circumstances of the cases and the times, could have been effected equally well, if at all, by any method of competitive negotiating or bidding.

VII. THE PAYMENT TO THE BANKER IS FOR ASSUMING A SUBSTANTIAL RISK AND PERFORMING A VALUABLE SERVICE

The risk taken by the banker and the syndicates he may organize is always a real and at times a very great one. There is widespread misapprehension as to the profits made by bankers and syndicates upon the underwriting and purchase of securities of railroad companies.

There is also a frequently encountered misconception to the effect that the railroads are in the habit of paying a commission to the banker when selling securities to him.

When the banker forms a syndicate to underwrite an offer of securities to shareholders a fixed commission is naturally stipulated, commensurate with the advantage secured by the railroad company in obtaining through the underwriting the certainty of the success of its offering, and with the risk incurred by the banker and the syndicate affiliated with him.

On the other hand, in the case of the sale of railroad securities to or through bankers without an offering to stockholders, it is very unusual for the sale to be on a commission basis. As a rule, the procedure is that the banker makes a firm bid to the railroad for such securities at a fixed price, said price with the addition of a reasonable standardized percentage for his own compensation being the figure at which he expects to be able to form a syndicate. That compensation is in return for his preparatory work, his moral and actual responsibility and risk and his services in managing the syndicate. It is a charge made by the banker to the syndicate.

The compensation of the banker and the anticipated profit of the syndicate are practically a fixed percentage. The banker's method is not to buy low and sell high. In fixing the selling price to the public, he merely adds to the purchase price a certain percentage to cover his own and his syndicate's compensation and expenses, and that percentage does not vary materially irrespective of whether the purchase price was say 90 or 95 or 100 percent.

His aim and inducement are to buy at a price which will enable the securities to be sold to the public after adding to that price the customary compensation. He has no inducement whatever to buy at a lesser price because his compensation would not be increased thereby, but on the other hand the good will and approval of the railroad concerned would be jeopardized.

When a syndicate is formed the banker's financial risk is by no means ended, as, in practically all cases, he is himself a large participant in the syndicate—is, in fact, expected to be. Moreover, generally he remains financially responsible to the railroad for the commitment of each individual syndicate participant. The railroad looks to him for the due performance of the contract, and not to the hundreds of syndicate members.

Again his moral risk and responsibility toward the syndicate is great, inasmuch as he is relied upon by its members to have examined carefully into the soundness of the security, to have scrutinized the mortgage, to have taken competent legal advice, to have correctly gauged the moment and estimated the price at which the securities can be advantageously placed with the public, to do the principal work in marketing them, and to guide the work done by others.

If the banker is found wanting in any of these respects, or his judgment proves to be faulty, he loses the confidence of those who habitually participate in syndicates and with it his capacity to engage in financial transactions on a large scale, as it is only with the cooperation, financial or otherwise, of syndicates that large transactions can be carried through.

The spread on which the syndicate figures as between the purchase price and the price of resale to the public is not more than sufficient to cover the expense of "overhead", the outlay for advertising, circularizing and counsel fees, and reasonable compensation divided over hundreds of syndicate participants and distributing houses for their risk and their work in placing the securities with the public. In view of the change which has taken place, as previously referred to, in the clientele for railroad bonds (owing to the pref-

erence of large investors for tax-exempt bonds) the selling of railroad securities has become both a more laborious and intensive and a more costly process than formerly. In addition to a highly trained and expensive office staff, bond houses nowadays must employ an army of traveling salesmen.

In order to get issues of railroad securities well placed among, and absorbed by, bona fide investors, it is necessary, under the conditions created by the advent of high surtaxes, to employ retail distributing houses throughout the country to a far greater extent than used to be the case. The margin upon which the calculations of the syndicate and its managers are based must therefore be sufficient to enable reasonable compensation to be afforded to such retail distributing houses so as to give them a fairly adequate inducement to put forth their efforts in placing the securities.

If, through an excessive narrowing of the margin, whether due to vagaries of competitive bidding or to other causes, such adequate inducement cannot be given to that Nation-wide force of distributing houses in the case of railroad securities, the inevitable result would be that these houses would more and more relinquish that field and devote their principal attention to pushing the distribution of industrial and other securities, of which a constantly growing supply is available.

Under the methods now prevailing it is wholly impossible that the originating banker, the syndicate participants and the distributing houses can make an undue profit as between the railroads and the public. The expected compensation for their respective services is expressed in practically standardized percentages, varying somewhat in accordance with the quality of the security and the risk and difficulty of the business. There can be no profit to bankers, syndicates or distributors over and above these percentages, but of course there can be a loss if the banker's judgment as to the price which a given security is worth or as to the general condition of the investment market is at fault, or if a sudden change occurs in that market owing to unforeseen events. The limit of possible profit is fixed, the limit of possible loss is indeterminate.

It is worth mentioning in this connection that the banker in England does not render the same measure of service to the corporations whose securities he sells to the public, as does the American banker. It is the practice of the London banker, immediately after the public issue has taken place, to dissolve his syndicate, distribute amongst the syndicate participants any bonds remaining unsold and leave it to them to sell at the best price they can get. He does not usually consider himself responsible to endeavor to protect the stability of the issue price.

The practice of the American banker, on the contrary, in cases where a public issue has not resulted in placing with the public the entire amount offered, is to keep his syndicate together for a certain length of time (sometimes for a great length of time), to retain charge of the disposal of the unsold balance and to continue his efforts to place the same with the investing public at the original issue price—a practice fairer and more serviceable both to the railroads and to the public. Even in the case of wholly successful issues, it is the usual practice here to keep the syndicate together for from 2 to 3 months, so as to be ready to "protect" the market, as more fully explained later.

SOME INSTANCES OF SYNDICATE RISKS TURNED INTO LOSSES

The following actual cases, which are by no means exhaustive, indicate the risks incurred by banking syndicates, and illustrate the losses and vicissitude to which they are subject:

1. In September 1905 the Erie Railroad arranged with its bankers to form a syndicate to underwrite the offer to its shareholders at 100 percent of \$12,000,000 convertible 4 percent bonds, series "B" (convertible into common stock at \$60 per share). The result of the offering was that the stockholders subscribed for only 18 percent and, consequently, the syndicate had to take and pay for \$9,840,000 of the bonds. The syndicate was dissolved in December 1906, none of the bonds taken by it having been disposed of. The bonds were listed on the stock exchange in February, 1907, when they sold at 85 percent.

2. In January 1906 the Missouri, Kansas & Texas Railway arranged with its bankers to form a syndicate to underwrite the offer to its shareholders at 87½ percent of \$10,000,000 general mortgage 4½ percent bonds. The stockholders subscribed for only 50 percent of the offering and the syndicate had to take \$5,000,000 of the bonds. The syndicate was dissolved in December 1907, only a few of the bonds taken by it having been disposed of.

3. In May 1907 the Union Pacific arranged with its bankers to form a syndicate to underwrite the offer to its stockholders at 90 percent of \$75,000,000 4 percent convertible bonds (convertible into stock at 175 percent). The stockholders subscribed for barely 5 percent of the offering and, consequently, the syndicate had to take and pay for about \$70,000,000 of the bonds. The bonds in the course of the following 6 months declined to 78¼ percent.

4. In January 1913 the Baltimore & Ohio Railroad Co. arranged with its bankers to form a syndicate to underwrite the offer to its stockholders at 95½ percent of \$63,000,000 4½ percent convertible bonds (convertible at 110 percent). The stockholders subscribed for barely 30 percent of the offering and, consequently, the syndicate had to take and pay for about \$44,000,000 of the bonds. In the course of a few months the bonds declined to 88½ percent.

5. In April 1906 the Wisconsin Central Railway arranged with bankers to form a syndicate to underwrite the offer to its shareholders at 89 percent and interest, of \$7,000,000 Superior & Duluth Division & Terminal first mortgage 4 percent bonds. The stockholders subscribed for only 1 percent of the offering and the syndicate had to take \$6,930,000 of the bonds. The syndicate expired by limitation July 1, 1908, none of the bonds taken by it having been disposed of in the interval.

6. In March 1910 the Atchison, Topeka & Santa Fe Railway Co. arranged with its bankers to form a syndicate to underwrite the offer to its shareholders at 102½ percent of \$43,686,000 convertible 4 percent bonds due 1960. The stockholders subscribed for only about 12½ percent of the offering, leaving about \$38,000,000 of the bonds to be taken by the syndicate.

7. In February 1906 the Southern Railway sold to its bankers \$20,000,000 development and general mortgage 4 percent bonds at 89 percent less commission. The syndicate formed by the bankers to handle this transaction remained in existence for nearly 2½ years, i. e., till July 1, 1908, at which time the syndicate members had to take up 68 percent of their participations. The market price of the bonds at that date was 74 percent.

8. In January 1909 the Western Maryland Railroad sold to bankers \$6,500,000 first mortgage 4 percent bonds. On January 18, 1909, about 90 percent of the bonds had to be taken up by syndicate participants. No bonds were disposed of by the syndicate until September 1910, and from then on, at various dates up to February 28, 1911; thus the syndicate lasted more than 2 years.

9. In June 1909 the Seaboard Air Line arranged with bankers for the formation of a syndicate to guarantee the sale of \$18,000,000 adjustment bonds at 70 percent. November 1, 1909, syndicate members took up about 90 percent of the bonds, which were disposed of in small lots between February 1910 and November 30, 1910, the syndicate thus lasting about 1½ years.

10. In January, 1910, bankers purchased \$22,000,000 Chicago City & Connecting Railways collateral trust 5 percent bonds, and formed a syndicate at 91 percent. The syndicate expired in February 1912, leaving syndicate members with almost 90 percent of the total amount unsold in their hands.

It will be observed that all the above examples, the list of which could be considerably prolonged, relate to the period preceding the war. The selection has been so made purposely, because ever since the beginning of the war the conditions of the investment market have not been normal. During the greater part of that period they were abnormally adverse, while since the beginning of the present year they have been abnormally favorable. Therefore, the war and post-war periods offer no basis upon which to found permanent conclusions. However, a few examples from these periods, which might be greatly multiplied, may be inserted here:

11. In March 1916, bankers formed a syndicate to underwrite the offer to stockholders of \$40,180,000 Chesapeake & Ohio Railway Co. 30-year 5 percent secured convertible gold bonds at 97½ percent and accrued interest. The stockholders subscribed for but slightly over 5 percent of the offering and the syndicate had to take and pay for \$38,047,500 of the bonds, equal to 94¾ percent of the issue. At the time when the syndicate was called upon to make good its obligation, the bonds were selling in market at 94⅞ percent.

12. In January 1917, the Chicago, Milwaukee & St. Paul Railway sold to its bankers at 93½ percent \$25,000,000 general and refunding mortgage 4½ percent bonds, series "A", due January 2014. On April 24, the syndicate was dissolved, the members having to take up 43 percent of their participations. The bonds at that time were selling in the market at 88½ percent.

13. In June 1919, the Baltimore & Ohio Railroad Co. sold to its bankers at 93½ percent \$35,000,000 of 10-year 6 percent secured gold bonds. The syndicate

remained in force until January 30, 1920, when the members had to take up 23 percent of their participations. The bonds were then selling in the market at 83½ percent.

14. In July 1919, the Cleveland, Cincinnati, Chicago & St. Louis Railroad Co. sold to its bankers at 95½ percent \$15,000,000 6 percent bonds. On December 1, 1919, the syndicate was dissolved, the members having to take up 11 percent of their participations. The bonds were then selling in the market at about 86 percent.

VIII. THE NATURE AND VALUE OF AN ESTABLISHED BANKING RELATIONSHIP

The considerations which make a system under which railroads would offer their securities direct for public bidding precarious, hazardous, and futile are so patent and so conclusive that it may well be assumed that no reasonably informed person will contend seriously that it would be either advantageous or safe for railroad companies to pursue the course of attempting to market their securities without the trained cooperation of bankers.

The question remains to be discussed whether it is in the public interest that a railroad company should habitually deal with a particular banker and give that banker the preference when it has securities to be sold or underwritten as long as—and only so long as—it is satisfied with his services. The following considerations are offered in support of this, the existing practice:

1. The present plan enables a railroad to be certain of its ability to secure the necessary funds for its commitments.

It is of the greatest importance for a railroad, when making commitments for expenditures for improvements, new construction, equipment, etc., to be certain that it will be able to sell the requisite securities when such commitments come due and must be met. That is a fundamental principle of sound railroad financing.

In dealing regularly with a banking house of ample financial strength and wide connections, the railroad company is assured that it will be able to obtain the requisite funds, even in unfavorable times, because the banking house, in order to insure the continuity of the connection and the solvency of the railroad, cannot do otherwise than use to the utmost the resources and the facilities of connections and credits at its disposal to provide for the requirements of the railroad.

If, on the other hand, the railroad had been in the habit of selling its securities on a competitive basis, it would have no such friend in need, and the various bond and banking houses would naturally buy its securities only as it suited their own purposes. The strongest railroads have found themselves in the situation where large sums of money have been imperatively needed in most unfavorable times and where only their claims upon their regular bankers have enabled them to obtain the necessary funds.

It has of late years been a matter of not infrequent occurrence that during the pendency of applications for the approval by a public service commission of proposed bond issues, railroads have found themselves in need of temporary financial accommodation. For such accommodation, if not readily or opportunely obtainable from the railroad's banks and trust company connections, the railroad would turn to its banker.

Furthermore, in the case of bonds, the application for the issue of which is pending before a public service commission, it is not unusual for the banker, at the railroad's request, to obligate himself to purchase such bonds, subject to the approval of their issue by such commission, so that the railroad is protected against an unfavorable change in the investment markets while its application is being considered and is certain of obtaining the needed funds as soon as the application is granted.

The temporary financial accommodation previously referred to, and the definite sale of bonds in advance of, and subject to action by public-service commissions, have at times been of great service and value to railroads. It is doubtful whether either expedient would be at the service of a railroad if securities were sold by competitive bidding among bankers.

There have also been numerous instances when railroads which found themselves confronted with grave financial problems or in need of large sums for refunding purposes have applied to bankers to evolve plans and inaugurate measures for dealing with these problems comprehensively, for strengthening their credit, or for their financial rehabilitation without the expense and detriment of a receivership. The accomplishment of this task on the part of

the banker involves much time, thought, and study as well as a degree of financial risk and the assumption of great moral responsibility toward investors who, following the banker's advice, may aid in furnishing the requisite funds and who look to the banker to safeguard such investments.

Last April, for example, the New York, New Haven & Hartford Railroad Co. was faced with the maturity of \$28,000,000 of debentures of which one half were held in France and one half in this country. The company's credit was not sufficient to make a new issue of securities possible. Failure to meet or extend the debentures at maturity would have meant bankruptcy.

With the active aid of banking houses through whom the debentures had been placed originally and with whom the company had been in consultation many months in advance, a voluntary extension of the debentures was secured. The negotiations involved a great deal of time, thought, skill, and effort, and, it is fair to say, could not have been successfully concluded, except through the influence, prestige, skill, and activity of the banking houses concerned.

It is a significant fact that most of the railroads which have gone into receivers' hands in recent years had followed the practice of selling their securities to different bankers at different times, and for the financing and support of, and advice to, such railroads, and the preservation of their solvency, accordingly, no single banking house felt itself responsible.¹

2. A railroad's financial requirements must be foreseen and assured long in advance of the actual need, and the present practice makes that possible.

In July 1921, when investment conditions had not yet become propitious, an issue of the combined bonds of the Northern Pacific and Great Northern Co.s aggregating \$200,000,000 fell due. The refunding of this vast amount of bonds was successfully accomplished with the aid of the bankers who had been concerned in their issue originally. The preparations for this refunding operation had been in progress for the best part of a year and were necessarily of the most elaborate character.

Manifestly, this immense operation could have been successfully carried through on an acceptable basis only by experienced bankers of high standing and Nation-wide connections, who were familiar with the history of the transaction and the manner in which the securities to be refunded were held, and who had adequate inducement to give to this complex and difficult negotiation the time and thought and the painstaking effort which its preparation required.

In June 1906, when the investment market in this country was practically at a standstill, American bankers placed an issue of 250,000,000 francs Pennsylvania Co. 3¾ percent bonds in France; in February 1907 an issue of 145,000,000 francs New York, New Haven & Hartford Railroad Co. 4 percent bonds in France and Germany; in March 1910 an issue of 150,000,000 francs Chicago, Milwaukee & St. Paul 4 percent bonds in France and England; and in February 1911 an issue of 250,000,000 francs Central Pacific Railway Co. 4 percent bonds in France and England.

All of these loans were negotiated at times when it was of great advantage to the railroads as well as to the general financial situation to obtain money abroad. They took many weeks of preliminary negotiation and complex arrangements and could not possibly have been negotiated on a competitive basis.

One railroad company alone must provide for \$130,000,000 of maturities in 1925 and another for \$50,000,000 the same year. It will inevitably be necessary for these companies to consult with bankers a long time before the maturity date, and devise plans for refunding, and obtain competent advice as to the best moment and method for carrying out these large transactions.

No banker could reasonably be expected to undertake the task and assume the responsibility of building up a railroad's credit, of studying and advising upon financial policies and methods, and putting his skill and placing power and sponsorship at its disposal if he had to expect that after having devoted his time, effort, and reputation to the work, the security-issues of the railroad would be thrown open to competitive bidding, whether general or confined to bankers, regardless of whether or not his own services were faithful and efficient and satisfactory to the board of directors and management.

3. The technical advice and the assistance growing out of the practical experience of the banker are of great value to the railroad.

¹ EXAMPLES: Wabash, Western Maryland, Wheeling & Lake Erie, Kansas City, Mexico & Orient, St. Louis & San Francisco, Norfolk & Southern, Chicago Great Western, Chicago, Rock Island & Pacific, etc.

A. IMPORTANCE OF ADVICE AS TO THE BEST TIME TO ISSUE SECURITIES

In dealing regularly with one banking house, a railroad obtains the benefit of expert advice (and that from someone thoroughly familiar with, and interested in, its affairs) as to financial policy, as to the best and most opportune time for selling securities, and for providing for its financial requirements, as to the class and kind of securities best suited to conditions prevailing and to be anticipated, and as to the best method of offering them to the public.

The element of the selection of time is of much importance in itself, for it happens not infrequently that the lapse of a single week or less measures the difference between reasonably favorable and unfavorable or even totally forbidding conditions.

The ebb and flow of the currents in the investment markets depend on many and complex conditions and considerations, and it is one of the functions of the competent banker to keep himself posted as to affairs, aspects, and prospects in America, Europe, and elsewhere, and to anticipate in his judgment and advice their results and their effects upon the money and investment markets.

The advice and cooperation of the banker are especially important to railroad companies during periods of declining security values, with which the Interstate Commerce Commission has not yet had occasion to deal, inasmuch as during the more recent past there has been an almost continuous upward trend of prices. In times of declining markets for securities quick action and sound advice are particularly essential. Premature publication of a company's intention to issue new securities must be guarded against. Apart from other considerations, holders of its securities already outstanding might hasten to sell their holdings without waiting for full information. Such premature selling might so affect the market as to make the new transaction more costly or perhaps impossible.

Furthermore, public knowledge that one or more issues of railroad securities are contemplated might cause industrial concerns or foreign governments or municipalities to hasten offerings of their own securities, as indeed has occurred in the past, so as to anticipate the railroads' offerings and get prior access to the investment market. The supply of available investment capital has, of course, its limitations, and in normal times the rule "first come, first served" does apply to a certain degree.

If a sale by public tender or by competitive negotiating or bidding among bankers were required, no one would be interested in supporting the market for a company's outstanding securities; in fact, prospective bidders would be benefited by a decline. On the other hand, with bankers having a continued interest in its welfare and a publicly recognized moral responsibility for its securities, the situation is quite different.

In this connection the question may be pertinent as to the relative desirability of the practice of selling securities before (or simultaneously with) the application to the Interstate Commerce Commission for approval, the transaction being made subject to the Commission's subsequent approval, or of delaying the offering until the Commission's approval has actually been obtained. On the whole, the first method, although not free from objection, would seem to be the safer and more desirable from the point of view of the railroads. It is quite impossible for any banker to definitely advise a corporation, with any degree of positiveness, as to the price its securities will command several weeks later. Too many elements of uncertainty are involved. The publication, weeks in advance of the actual consummation of the transaction, of the intention of railroad companies to make issues of securities might prove seriously detrimental as indicated in the preceding paragraph.

Everything considered, it would seem best that the companies should be accorded discretion to exercise their own best judgment in each instance whether they should sell subject to subsequent approval by the Commission, or should first obtain the Commission's leave for selling, at a price not below a stated minimum.

B. IMPORTANCE OF ADVICE AS TO TECHNICAL DETAILS SURROUNDING ISSUANCE OF SECURITIES

It is of great importance that care should be taken that new issues of bonds should comply with the statutory requirements of various States respecting legal investments of insurance companies, savings banks, and other fiduciary

institutions. Whether or not a given issue of bonds meets these requirements will often make a difference of several points in their value.

Investors attach considerable importance to knowing that the mortgages, trust deeds, etc., and all legal steps relating to the issue of securities which they are asked to buy have been carefully examined by bankers of repute and experience and their counsel, with a view to safeguarding the interest of the holders of the bonds as distinguished from those of the railroads, the makers of the bonds.

The mortgages and trust deeds under which the securities are to be issued, before being put in final shape, are carefully gone over by the banker, and his advice is given with the view to creating the best and most salable instrument satisfactory both to the public and to the railroad company, and having due regard both for the protection of the investor and for the future financial requirements of the railroad. Such advice is frequently, especially in the case of large refunding mortgages which are meant to be the principal means of raising money for the railroads for years to come, of very great utility. It is likewise greatly valued by the investor who has come to rely upon the tried and tested thoroughness and competence of experienced and highly reputed bankers to protect the interests of the investing public in respect of not only the intrinsic goodness of a security for which they become sponsors, but also in respect of the provision of the mortgage or trust deed appertaining to such security.

4. The bankers' dual obligation to the investing public, on the one hand, and, on the other, to the corporation whom he serves constitutes a protection to both.

The leading bankers could not maintain their position as such if they did not have the confidence of the investing public and a large following amongst investors, large and small, both here and abroad.

Careful analysis, continuous and watchful scrutiny, in respect of securities issued by him and of the companies concerned, are essential functions of the banker. In buying securities and offering them for sale, he gives public notice, so to speak, that he has examined into and satisfied himself as to their safety and merit.

The banker does not safeguard merely the technical and, to the best of his ability, the intrinsic soundness of the securities he issues; it is alike his duty and to his own self-interest to protect and stand behind the securities for which he is recognized as sponsor, just as it is his duty and to his own self-interest to satisfy himself by careful investigation as to the soundness of such securities, because the banker whose clients suffer loss through following his advice will very soon lose his reputation and the confidence and patronage of his clients.

The banker knows well that such reputation and confidence are the mainstays of the prosperity and success of his own business and, once forfeited, are exceedingly difficult to regain.

"PROTECTING" THE MARKET

The function of the banker in "protecting" the market for services issued through his house is of peculiar importance.

Reference has been made to the altered character of the investment market, in which a great army of small investors has come into existence to take the place of the larger investors who because of preference for tax-exempt securities can no longer be counted upon to be a considerable factor in absorbing railroad securities.

If that army, so important and desirable from the social and economic viewpoint, and created at such great cost and effort, is not to disintegrate again, it is absolutely indispensable that the market for the securities which they have bought be "protected" at least for a reasonable length of time after the offering (barring exceptional economic or financial changes)—which protection is one of the useful and legitimate functions of leading issuing houses and has no relationship whatever to what is usually termed manipulating or "rigging" the market.

It must be made somebody's business to see to it that if the investor wishes to sell within a reasonable time after having bought, he can, under normal conditions, find a market at or near the price at which he bought.

To provide such a market by being able and willing to a reasonable extent to repurchase bonds sold by him is part of the business of the banker who made the public offering—provided that he has a definite and acknowledged relationship toward the company whose bonds he has offered. If he has no such relationship, if the public offering is simply the result of competitive

bidding, either general or limited, the banker may be expected to be apt to feel that his functions are completed when he has marketed the securities.

The result would be that the immensely valuable work which had been done lately of popularizing railroad bonds might be largely undone, the vast clientele which had been created for railroad bonds might be materially curtailed, and the resulting diminished demand for railroad bonds could not fail to be reflected in the price level which they would command.

The continuing responsibility of the banker for bonds which he has offered and sold under the existing system of dealing between bankers and railroads is an exceedingly valuable element from the point of view of the small investor and a strongly steadying factor in the market for railroad securities. That responsibility would be jeopardized by competitive bidding, whether general or limited.

It is interesting to note in this connection that even so eminently successful a public offering as that of the recently issued United States Government $4\frac{1}{4}$ percent bonds, was followed by a substantial decline in the market price of those bonds below the price of issue. There being no one responsible for the "protection" of the market for those bonds, the price declined quickly from the issuing price of 100 to 98.90 percent, which in the case of the world's premier government security has considerably greater significance than a like decline would have in the case of a corporate issue.

It is to the interest of a railroad company that its securities should be absorbed by the investing public and that their market value should be maintained, under normal conditions. It is more important to the railroad industry at large that a favorable reputation, the good will of the investing public, and a broad, steady demand for its securities should be preserved than that in every instance the very top-notch price should be obtained to which, through taking advantage of fortuitous circumstances, the purchasing banker may be driven. To disappoint and disgruntle the investor by selling him securities at unduly high prices, which will not stand the test of the workings of ordinary supply and demand, is in its ultimate consequences to be "pennywise and pound-foolish", especially since railroad securities are more and more coming into competition for public favor with industrial securities.

The end the railroad company should always have in mind is to maintain a broad and stable market for its securities, and to that end wise discretion in the interest of railroad credit generally and of the particular borrower may even make it desirable in given instances, under all the surrounding circumstances of the case, to accept an offer which would enable resale to the public under tested and responsible auspices at a fair and reasonable price, rather than an offer of an extreme price with the resulting consequence of the resale to the public being attempted necessarily at an unduly high level.

It may safely be said that such railroad issues as are known to be under the habitual sponsorship and consequent moral responsibility of well known and strong bankers have a wider and steadier market and command better prices among investors than those which are not under such auspices and responsibility.

If the sale of securities were thrown open to competitive negotiating or bidding, either general or limited, the possession of large capital would tend to become prime requisite for dealing in securities, and the financier or combination of financiers controlling the largest amount of capital would have a much more potent advantage over others than under now existing conditions.

The exercise of care, skill, industry, scrutiny, and the sense of moral responsibility toward clients, which now are and always have been the prerequisite for acquiring the reputation and the public confidence upon which an investment banker's position depends, and without which it cannot be maintained for any length of time, would no longer be essential.

IX. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

A. The vital necessity is to obtain for the railroads the assurance of adequate capital upon favorable terms.

B. The existing practice of selecting, and dealing with, a particular banking house as long as its services give satisfaction, is an outgrowth of actual experience in the effective marketing of securities.

C. In dealing with so delicate a matter as security markets it is of primary consequence that any plan adopted for the sale of securities shall command the utmost confidence on the part of investors.

D. The existing practice has proven itself, in numerous instances, of the greatest utility to railroad corporations, and actual experience demonstrates that the remuneration to bankers and syndicates is but a fair equivalent for very real services actually performed and risks assumed, and that the average of such remuneration, over a term of years, has afforded no more than a reasonable return upon the capital involved, and due compensation for the work rendered.

E. The existing practice has been found effective by industrial corporations not subject to public regulation, and it is the method employed by many foreign governments and municipalities in the issuing of securities.

F. Some of the advantageous characteristics of the present practice are:

1. The relationship between railroad and banker is wholly informal and continues only as long as it is deemed advantageous to the railroad by its officers and directors.

2. The relationship, while in no way limiting the railroad's freedom of action, does impose upon the banker definite and continuous duties and obligations.

3. The bankers have no power to determine the decision of railroads in such matters.

4. The banker is not only the distributor of and propagandist for railroad securities, but he fulfills, at his own risk and cost, the important and valuable function of steadying and protecting the market for such securities.

5. The railroad receives continuously the knowledge, services, skill, standing, financial advice, and financial potency of the banker in both good and evil times.

6. The banker advises as to the financial situation and policy of the railroad, prepares plans for meeting requirements, recommends the kind and character of the security to be created, scrutinizes mortgages and trust deeds, and indicates the best moment at which to sell.

7. The bonds of the corporation represent a promise to pay. The value of that promise depends not merely upon the tangible security offered, but also upon excellence and fidelity of management. While strictly refraining from any attempt to influence the operating and tariff policies of the railroad, it is the banker's duty and self-interest, to the best of his ability, to promote wise and sound management and safe financial policies on the part of the corporation, the securities of which he has issued and for which he has consequently assumed moral sponsorship before the investing public.

8. Even where affiliations between particular bankers and railroads avoid nominal competition, there is a potential competition which operates powerfully in the following particulars:

(a) The fact that complete publicity is by law enforced as to the terms upon which security issues are obtained by bankers naturally causes both the banker and the railroad to seek to give, on the one hand, and to obtain on the other, the best terms which conditions and circumstances warrant.

(b) The fact that the terms involved in a contract between the railroad and the banker must be approved by public authority is a moral guaranty that such terms will be proposed as will stand well-informed scrutiny.

(c) If railroads find that other companies are securing better terms through other bankers, it is inevitable that other bankers will ultimately obtain the business.

(d) If railroads cannot obtain what they consider satisfactory terms from their regular bankers, they are entirely free to terminate the negotiations and do business with others.

(g) There is no reason to think that, year in and year out, railroads would obtain higher prices for their securities under any form of competitive negotiating or bidding than under the present practice. There is every reason to think that the stability and broad receptiveness of the market for railroad securities would be lessened and the interests of the investors less carefully and responsibly safeguarded.

(h) Many, if not all, of the effective values of the advantages (both to the railroads and to the investing public) inherent in the present practice, would be eliminated by competitive negotiating or bidding, whether unrestricted or confined to bankers. No banker could be expected to give his time, effort, reputation and responsibility, material and moral, to the financial affairs of a corporation if he is wholly uncertain whether he will reap any return for his services, as must necessarily be the case in the event of competitive negotiating or bidding.

I. To change the prevailing practice would mean to give up definite and tested benefits, alike to the railroads and to the public, for the sake of one wholly problematical advantage.

J. Practical experience shows that the operation of the present method under public supervision and with full publicity attending it, assures more success than any other plan yet proposed or practiced in obtaining the necessary capital for the railroads upon favorable terms.

K. To the extent that the terms upon which securities are sold have a bearing upon the rates paid by the public for railroad service, the present method secures to the public, insofar as that item is concerned, the lowest burden upon the rates and the greatest assurance of the railroads being able to obtain the capital to provide necessary facilities.

CONCLUSION

To compel railroads to have recourse for the sale of their securities to competitive negotiating with or bidding on the part of bankers and brokers, or to direct offerings to the public, would be to run counter to the practice and experience of every country in the world.

It would confuse and trouble the investing public and destroy elements and features of evident and proved value for public protection.

It would tend to make the possession of capital the sole requisite for dealing in securities, irrespective of skill, care, reputation, and the confidence of investors.

It would limit, hamper, and restrain the flow of capital into American railroad securities and cause delay, uncertainty, risk, and damage to railroad corporations.

Railroads and other corporations should be left free, under the responsibility of their board of directors, and subject to such authority over the issue of their securities as is now exercised by the Interstate Commerce Commission, to deal with whatever banking houses they deem it in their best interest to employ.

They should neither be bound by contract or control to deal with any one banking house exclusively, nor forced by statute or regulation to take the chances involved in competitive negotiating or bidding among bankers or of direct dealing with the public.

Respectfully submitted.

KUHN, LOEB & Co.

OCTOBER 25, 1922.

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT (No. 2)

COMPETITIVE BIDDING FOR EQUIPMENT TRUSTS

FOREWORD

An article on the subject of competitive bidding for equipment trusts appeared at some length in the New York Times of January 30, 1928, and therein the writer of this booklet was quoted as follows:

"Due to extraordinarily easy conditions in the money market, banking firms have been basing bids in competition for equipment trust securities on a narrow margin of profit not at all commensurate with the services performed or the banking risk entailed through a possible reaction in bond prices.

"As a result, equipment trusts have been offered at prices which many of the former large buyers of car trusts, such as insurance companies, have not hesitated to call excessive and out of line with the market. The small investor and less experienced buyer has been invited to pay prices for equipment trusts which the larger and better versed buyers consider to be above the market and in fact the larger buyer, by avoiding the original offering, has been able to wait out a situation and make a 'close-out' bid at a lower price for an unsold balance, which more than once has remained on the shelves.

"The actual sufferer, therefore, is the small investor, or the very individual the protection of whose interests has appealed most strongly to the governmental authorities. If the protection of the investor has not been accomplished during a rising and very favorable bond market, there is much less likelihood that he will benefit during a period of declining prices, for at such times not only is the larger institutional buyer unwilling to purchase offerings unless they are priced exactly on the current market conditions, but his experience

even then causes him to hold back because of his expectation of lower prices for all investment securities."

Shortly after this quotation appeared a distinct tightening of conditions in the money market became evident, and with it a drop in the price for equipment trusts which was not only severe but also more drastic than it should have been, owing to the artificial price level created through competitive bidding. Railroads which contemplated the placing of equipment trusts quickly found that houses which enthusiastically pursued every opportunity to bid for such offerings under easy-money conditions were reluctant to bid at all in the face of tightening money. Equipment trusts as money continued to tighten became an unpopular security with bankers who had been "stung" at top prices, and when at a later date one of the leading railroads of the country came into the market to dispose of a substantial issue of car-trust certificates it found that instead of 30 or 40 bidders being anxious to submit bids for its car-trust obligations only a few laggard bidders were in evidence, these being actuated, perhaps, by a desire for publicity, and whose bids were then found to be even lower than conditions warranted. Finally, with the approval of the Commission, this road, the Southern Pacific, was allowed to dispose of its car-trust certificates to its own bankers.

In selling this issue to its bankers the carrier received a better price than the highest bid offered in competition, and the issue was sold in a prompt manner calculated to strengthen the entire equipment-trust market. As this news became public it was rumored that the Interstate Commerce Commission, because of the recent criticism leveled at competitive bidding, was willing to give the original order of doing business a new trial. Unfortunately, such rumors may have been regarded as a reflection on the judgment of those responsible in the first place for the inauguration of competitive bidding.

There are officials in Washington who at one time sincerely believed that all railroad securities should be sold under terms of competitive bidding. In some channels the 1926 ruling on equipment trusts was reported to be an entering wedge which would lead to competitive bidding for all forms of railroad securities. It has been shown that such a system would have been a great detriment to the credit of the carriers.

Competitive bidding for equipment trusts was an experiment and as such developed unfavorable factors which were not originally apparent. However, the Commission still firmly maintains its position and in its approval of the Chicago, St. Paul, Minneapolis & Omaha issue dated August 31, 1928, restates its attitude as follows:

"During the early part of the current year equipment obligations sold in some instances on such bases that the cost to the carriers was as low as 4.23 percent. Certain developments in the financial situation during the past few months have narrowed the investment market, with a resulting increase in rates on long-term securities, including equipment obligations. We feel, however, that this condition does not warrant a change in our policy with respect to the disposition of equipment obligations. Moreover, we are of the opinion that we should do nothing that would tend to discredit the method of disposing of equipment obligations that has been employed with success for the last 2 years or that would result in the withdrawal of the support of the investment houses that have participated in the sale of such securities. We can hardly expect bankers to continue to submit tenders for equipment obligations on invitation from carriers if the carriers may reject all bids and after thus testing the investment market place the obligations privately. We are of the opinion that if the offers received for the equipment obligations are not satisfactory the carriers should again call for tenders and accept the most favorable bid or should reject all bids and resort to temporary financing until there is such an improvement in the investment market as will enable a sale to be made on satisfactory terms. In accordance with these views, authority to assume obligation and liability in respect of the certificates under consideration will be granted upon condition that the certificates again be offered for sale at competitive bidding and sold to the highest bidder."

The recommendation which forms the basis of this most recent report, namely, that equipment trusts under conditions where acceptable bids are not forthcoming should be readvertised or that the equipment should be temporarily financed is make-shift advice, in the opinion of the writer. The obligation of a recognized municipality may be so handled but it is on an entirely different basis. Whether a municipal obligation is sold to one investment house or to another is of little consequence, and if an issue is not disposed of under

terms of the original sale, it can be readvertised at a later date and sold with no adverse consequence to the obligor.

The issuance of equipment trusts is predicated upon orders placed with car and locomotive builders for the purchase of new equipment to be delivered at a very definite time, and which must be paid for as this equipment is delivered. Under the time-honored practice of doing business with its own bankers, the officials of a railroad, even in an unfavorable market, felt in position to arrange if necessary for a temporary loan with such bankers, rather than be forced to offer its equipment trust certificates under unfavorable market conditions.

Generally speaking, it is impossible for a carrier to provide for temporary financing of equipment purchases without the assistance of bankers closely associated with the carrier. The validity and security of equipment trusts is based entirely on the theory of a conditional sale, that is, a purchase of the equipment by the carrier from the trustee on such terms that title to the equipment is retained by the trustee as security for the payment of the equipment obligations. Obviously, when a carrier has once acquired title to equipment by the use of treasury funds or as a result of temporary financing, a conditional sale of such equipment to the carrier can no longer be made and the whole basis for the equipment trust is destroyed. Moreover, most carriers have outstanding mortgages which contain either a general clause subjecting after-acquired property to the mortgage, or, even in the absence of a general after-acquired property clause, a clause providing that any equipment or interests therein which the carrier acquires after the date of the mortgage shall become subject to the mortgage. Whenever there is such a mortgage, the carrier's interest in any equipment acquired through temporary financing would become subject to the mortgage, and it would not thereafter be possible to place an equipment trust on such equipment except subject to the lien of the mortgage.

If, however, the carrier proposes to sell equipment trust certificates to bankers closely associated with it, it may procure the use of the necessary equipment when it is needed and still await a favorable market for the issue of its equipment obligations by having its bankers arrange to purchase the equipment and to lease it to the carrier. Thus no title to the equipment vests in the carrier and, when the equipment trust is to be issued, the bankers can transfer title to the equipment to the trustee, free from incumbrances. However, such an arrangement necessarily involves close contact between them and the carrier, since bankers would not be interested in acquiring equipment for a carrier except as part of the service rendered by them to their regular clients in anticipation of permanent financing.

Competitive bidding, however, has impaired the relationship between the railroad and its bankers, and has actually relieved the bankers of responsibility for arranging any emergency accommodations.

Moreover, the readvertisement of an issue unless the market itself has given strong evidence of a more favorable trend will not result in any improvement of the bids received by the carrier and if a readvertisement produces a lower bid this is a decidedly unfavorable reflection on the credit of the carrier—or will the Commission recommend a third, fourth, or fifth readvertisement?

The opinion is therefore widespread that the relationship between the carrier and its accepted bankers is not only a valuable one but one to be protected and encouraged, as evidenced through quotations which are attached at the end of this discussion, and which were received from investment dealers through the country in answer to a brief inquiry sent out by Freeman & Co. in January 1928.

COMPETITIVE BIDDING FOR EQUIPMENT TRUSTS

It is undoubtedly very hard for the members of any governmental regulatory body to accept facts which cannot actually be substantiated with tabulations of figures. The writer feels that it is fair, however, for the Interstate Commerce Commission to admit as evidence hundreds of adverse opinions received from investment dealers throughout the country in connection with the question of competitive bidding for equipment trusts.

A serious impairment of the popularity of equipment trusts with the public has occurred. This situation, unless corrected, may eventually deny to the carriers the cheapest and soundest method of financing the purchase of rolling stock.

The regulation of the issuance of railroad securities, as is well known, was vested originally in the Interstate Commerce Commission under the Esch-

Cummins bill. A portion of this bill, namely, section 20a, outlines the powers of the Commission in relation to the approval of securities issued and gives the processes through which railroad securities are to be sold.

It is set forth that the Commission not only may supervise the price received for an issue of securities but that it may also, to a certain extent, supervise the disposition of the cash received for such securities. This, in effect, gives to the Commission a privilege formerly entirely controlled by the board of directors of a railroad. It is claimed that the original intent of section 20a of the Transportation Act of 1920 was only to regulate the issuance of securities in the public interest, and that when the Commission arbitrarily takes upon itself what at times amounts to the function of management, it acts in excess of its authorized powers. This contention has been prominently brought to the foreground through the recommendation issued in 1926 to the effect that issues of equipment trust certificates should thereafter be sold under terms of competitive bidding.

It is perhaps in order at this point to outline most briefly the usual method employed by the Commission in supervising the financial arrangements of the carriers. Division 4 of the Interstate Commerce Commission has been entrusted with this work and under section 20a of the Transportation Act of 1920 any railroad wishing to sell its obligation must make application through this division for authority to issue such obligation according to the rules and regulations as embodied in the act.

Division 4 is under the supervision of a director of finance, who is in close touch with security market conditions from day to day, and while the judgment exercised is tremendous, in order that an unbiased survey of the situation be presented, it is proper to state that the viewpoint taken by the director of finance usually has been a broad and reasonable one. It is not with the personnel of division 4 nor with that of the Commission that the writer has predicated his argument. During 1922 a public hearing was held on the subject of competitive bidding and it was evident then that the trend of the opinion of certain Government officials was toward competitive bidding, not only for equipment trust certificates but also for all forms of railroad securities. It was not until 1926 that a definite recommendation was issued to the effect that competitive bidding must be employed by the carriers in disposing of equipment trust certificates.

At the time of the issuance of the 1926 recommendation covering competitive bidding the Commission stated its opinion more or less as follows: In the first place it took the position that equipment trust certificates were so standardized and were of such similarity, both as to the legal procedure governing the issuance of such securities and as to the collateral underlying the same, that their issuance became more or less a matter of form. It also set forth that it believed that such substantial savings could be made in discounts through competitive bidding that the public interest would be greatly served through the natural broadening of the market for equipment trust securities. A paragraph from the opinion issued by the Commission dealing with the issuance of equipment trusts during 1926 follows:

"It is our opinion, however, that the sale of equipment trust certificates by public competitive bidding will be effective in so widening the market for these securities as to assist in the effective and economical financing of railroads by means of other securities, such as may from time to time become necessary."

In other words, the Commission at that time felt that a broadening of the market for equipment trusts would come about as a result of competitive bidding and that, therefore, his broadening would tend to improve the entire credit structures of the various carriers.

The Commission then summed up its attitude more or less as follows:

"Equipment trust certificates are of a uniform character, and the relative financial strength of the issuing carriers is not a very important factor in determining the price at which these securities are to be sold. Equipment trust securities, which at one time were sold largely to purchasers such as insurance companies and large banks, have become popular with the smaller investors, and it seems to us that the sale under competitive bidding will tend to widen the market for these securities and produce capital for the railroads under cheaper terms."

The writer does not hesitate to state his belief that these two major contentions of the Commission have been proved to be wrong and that not only has the public interest been damaged through competitive bidding, but also that competitive bidding, far from broadening the market for equipment

trusts, has resulted in creating a feeling of distrust regarding the marketability of equipment trust securities which has narrowed the market for car trusts in all parts of the country. This contention is backed by letters on file received from dealers throughout the Nation whose contact with investors bears a relationship similar to that existing between lawyer and client and physician and patient.

The writer, therefore, is not at all concerned with the much-mooted question as to whether or not the Commission in prescribing competitive bidding for equipment trusts has usurped the functions of management of the carriers in what may be an unwarranted manner. He believes that the action of the Commission has not been a sound one and that a reversal of its recommendations should be forthcoming to correct a condition which in the long run will spell economic loss for the carriers.

He believes that the Commission's position that equipment trust securities are uniform as regards methods of issuance and types of collateral is not a correct one. In a very ample textbook on equipment obligations issued by Kenneth Duncan, Ph.D., after a study made at the University of Michigan, the reader may quickly find that history shows that the legal procedure attendant upon issues of equipment trust securities is most important and that a very critical attitude has been evidenced in past years by courts throughout the country in the adjudication of contentions arising through foreclosure under equipment trust liens.

Professor Duncan states that quite a number of years ago the confidence of investors was badly shaken through neglect by those creating equipment trust obligations to see that there were no irregularities and in very recent years the Investment Bankers Association found it necessary to recommend that laxity on the part of corporate trustees of equipment trusts be corrected before serious damage resulted to the holders of such notes, certificates, or bonds. Professor Duncan states that while the judicial status of railroad equipment obligations has been greatly strengthened during the past years by court decisions, there exist divergent attitudes under different jurisdictions throughout the United States, which have not been uniformly determined at common law. To understand that this may be true it is only necessary for the reader to realize that equipment trusts, for example, may be issued under various procedures, the three most important of which are absolute sale, conditional sale, or lease with option to purchase.

It is therefore evident that the issuance of equipment trust securities should be supervised by banking institutions and lawyers familiar with such matters. It is not fair to investors to permit the drawing of the governing indenture to be handled exclusively by the lawyers for the carriers. The correct marking of the units of equipment, for example, may be of the greatest importance in certain States of the Union which even prescribe the exact size of the letters which the name of the trustee-owner must take to effectively establish its position in foreclosure proceedings.

The Commission itself, through its regulation issued regarding equipment trusts secured on rebuilt equipment, entering into lengthy requirements concerning the question of the actual cash percent of the original equipment, the depreciated value of the same at the contemplated time of rebuilding, and other technical matters, admits that equipment trust certificates are by no means uniform in issuance.

To the mind of the equipment trust specialist, many conditions affecting the solidity of an equipment trust obligation exist which on the surface are not apparent to the small investor who may be the purchaser of the given equipment trust certificate. Fluctuations in the cost of units of equipment make it evident that an issue secured on equipment purchased under very favorable terms, even though the cash payment be smaller, may be preferred over one secured on equipment purchased at temporary peak prices of any one year though the actual down payment in cash be larger on the latter issue. Moreover, certain kinds of equipment, such as standard types of box cars, have a readier resale and are to be preferred as collateral over such types of equipment as gasoline motor cars, ditching machines, lifting cranes, and wrecking machinery, all of which types have been included in latter-day equipment trusts.

A very recent application filed by a well-known carrier with the Commission included second-hand dining cars in the equipment. The question of the inclusion of rebuilt equipment is also an important factor, as is the setting up of the maturities with regard to the actual ratio of depreciation on the collateral. In recent years it has become somewhat of a practice to defer the earlier

maturities under an equipment trust, which to the equipment specialist is simply a method of diluting the security and also of modifying the rather stringent procedure which heretofore surrounded the methods employed in setting up an equipment trust unless the original amount of cash equity has been commensurately increased. Because of such situations the position of the Commission that all equipment trusts are alike and that the question of the credit of the carrier is more or less a minor one, in the opinion of the writer, is not acceptable.

At the original hearing in 1922 regarding the proposition of competitive bidding, it was strongly argued that the marketing of such securities should be made not only through investment houses entirely familiar with equipment trust procedure but through the actual bankers for the railroads expecting to issue such securities. The writer heartily subscribes to this opinion and believes that no investment house is so well able to dispose of an equipment trust as is the banking house which through long association with the problems of the carrier is able to give it not only a fair price but expert advice in marketing its securities. He believes that the present unpopularity of the equipment trusts can be directly traced to the handling of such issues by houses who felt no responsibility whatsoever with regard to supporting the market for such securities after the original sale.

The writer feels whole-heartedly that the supervision of the Interstate Commerce Commission regulating the issuance of railroad securities has been of benefit. However, it seems that "a penny wise and a pound foolish" policy has developed with regard to equipment-trust securities.

It is certainly impossible to obtain the proper national distribution for equipment-trust securities without giving to the small investment broker throughout the country a fair commission for his services in placing equipment trusts with investors. There is no doubt but that equipment-trust certificates are easier to sell than are many other forms of securities, and it is not the contention of the writer that this commission should be a large one. He believes that enough leeway should be given to the purchasing house, which in his opinion should be the accepted banker for the carrier, to enable this banking house to redistribute a portion of its limited profit in order to obtain permanent distribution and to be in position to protect the secondary market of the securities so sold.

Certainly to the mind of a specialist in equipment-trust securities who has watched the marketing of this form of security for a good many years, the prices paid by inexperienced bidders under the recent money conditions prevailing were nothing short of amusing. This is an advertising age and an extreme premium has been placed in business channels upon publicity of every sort so that investment houses are now using every available method to keep their names before the public, even including the use of radio circuits.

It is therefore easy to see that a house which has not been successful in obtaining business through its regular channels may be persuaded to enter a bid for an equipment-trust issue, feeling that no profit or even a small loss will be a worth-while procedure from the standpoint of publicity. A house specializing in inactive or high yield industrial issues may decide that a conservative railroad equipment-trust offering helps, as the saying goes, to "dress up the list." Of course, in such an instance the sufferer is the general public, which may be invited to purchase such securities at too high levels. Thirty-five or forty houses bidding on practically no margin of profit for equipment-trust issues during 1 month and a few weeks later under tightening money conditions less than five very weak bids available for a better issue, is a situation for the Commission to ponder over at some length.

What has actually happened during 1928 was foretold in 1926 by a committee of the Investment Bankers Association when it was predicted then that while in good times high prices would be realized, in a tight money situation the railroads would not only fail to receive proper prices for their securities under competitive bidding but that they would lose the contact with their regular bankers, which despite many attacks on the part of radical politicians may be conceded as a most valuable connection for any corporation, whether it be railroad or industrial. It is certainly the feeling among investment houses throughout the country that securities brought out by the regular bankers for railroads are more fairly priced than those offered to the public by investment houses which have purchased such securities under terms of competitive bidding and as a matter of opportunity to do business.

It is therefore to be hoped that the members of the Interstate Commerce Commission will be ready to recognize that an actual error occurred in the inaugu-

ration of competitive bidding for equipment-trust securities. Proof is contained in the following comments received from all parts of the country. An overwhelming preponderance of opinion, not only to the effect that competitive bidding for equipment trusts has been a failure but that the market for these bonds has been greatly narrowed through the regulatory action on the part of the Commission, cannot be lightly dismissed.

EXTRACTS FROM LETTERS RECEIVED BY US, CONCERNING COMPETITIVE BIDDING FOR
EQUIPMENT TRUSTS

POPULAR POSITION CAN BE LOST

To not practice competitive bidding in the selling of securities, appears on first thought, to be derogatory to economic law. Looking at the matter from all angles we can see lurking dangers in this method used by the railroads to sell their equipment trust securities. While it is undoubtedly true that the railroad companies will receive slightly higher prices for their securities now, the narrow margin of profit made by dealers in distributing these securities, and the high price the public is obliged to pay in buying them, will most certainly ultimately act to the disadvantage of the railroads. The popular position now occupied by this class of securities with the investing public can certainly be lost through a process of overpricing. Even the handling of the securities can lose favor with the investment dealers if the profits are not permitted to remain reasonable, and their customers be well served by a security which is not overpriced.

To save the popularity of equipment trust securities with the public and thereby help the railroads ultimately, we recommend the discontinuance of the practice of competitive bidding in the sale of equipment-trust securities by the railroads. This is an expression of our feelings as well as that of our constituency.

THE CITIZENS NATIONAL BANK OF EVANSVILLE,
Evansville, Ind.,
By CHARLES E. HOWARD, *Manager Bond Department.*

—
MORE HARM THAN GOOD

However it has been our thought that competitive bidding in the buying of securities has perhaps done more harm than good, and has resulted in undue high prices to the public. Too often, therefore, after the closing of the syndicate, prices have not been maintained.

W. M. CAVALIER & Co.,
San Francisco, Calif.

—
LIABLE TO OVERPRICE

In addition I do not believe that competitive bidding on equipment trusts will make the strongest issues still more prominent. The various types of houses who may become interested are liable to overprice some issues just because of their desire to get equipment trusts to sell—the answer is obvious, that the general regard for equipment trusts must suffer.

ROBERT GENNERT MACKS,
Denver, Colo.

—
CHARACTER OF PAST PERFORMANCES MATERIAL FACTORS

In the second paragraph of your letter you have brought out certain points which we believe to be correct, and which need not be recited. While the idea of awarding to the highest bidder on first blush appears to be the correct attitude, yet where a party has a piece of work to be done, and asks for competitive bids, and where it would seem that the lowest bidder for the performance of a certain job would be the one to select, yet we all know that other circumstances enter into the situation, the responsibility of the bidder, and the character of his past performances are very material factors, and frequently a higher bidder will get a certain job for such reasons. Coming back to the

question of competitive bidding for equipment issues, a certain firm of bankers with small distributive capacity, in a market such as we are having now, might overtop a bid made by another firm with good distributive capacity and the result would be that the equipment trust issues would lie on the first dealer's shelf a long time, thereby hurting the market for subsequent issues of bonds of the same railroad, when next in the market.

WURTS, DULLES & Co.,
Philadelphia, Pa.

SO HIGH PRICED

Among the principal reasons that we are not interested in equipment trusts today is the fact that they are so high priced and that the margin of profit is not sufficient to warrant our taking a chance on being able to distribute them successfully.

FREEMAN, SMITH & CAMP Co.,
Portland, Oreg.

FAVOR THE OLD METHOD

From the standpoint of the dealer, we are inclined to favor the old method of sale and this attitude, we feel, is not entirely selfish. As you say, over-pricing has resulted from competitive bidding, which together with the small margin of profit now available to the retail distributor, makes participation in the sale of equipment trust securities less desirable than it formerly was. This latter condition also tends to produce sales in large rather than small blocks which makes for a less satisfactory secondary market, besides, as you say, contributing to the possibility of "a situation which may prove costly when less favorable conditions govern the money markets."

The discussion, as we see it, really boils down to the question as to whether the public will benefit most by having the railroads receive a somewhat higher price for these securities temporarily, or whether more profit would accrue from having securities brought out on a strictly conservative basis, and with a satisfactory market after the original offering. The latter, we think, would be the more desirable of the two.

THE HUFFMAN Co., *Dayton, Ohio.*

DISTRIBUTORS ENTITLED TO REASONABLE PROFIT

It seems to me, with reference to equipment-trust issues, that a more sound and advantageous policy for all concerned would be for the Interstate Commerce Commission to allow customary bankers for railroads to buy equipments in the former way, the Commission reserving the right to order competitive bidding if the price was not, in its judgment, fair and satisfactory. The difference of $\frac{1}{4}$ or $\frac{1}{2}$ percent in the amount received by the railroad would hardly justify its putting its securities in a position of disfavor and uncertainty with the public.

It is also to be considered that there are certain necessary costs of distribution and that distributors are entitled to this cost plus a reasonable profit.

With the Commission exercising the control and authority it has in the manner suggested above the interests of the public, railroads, distributor, and investor—all of whom have rights in the matter—could be properly protected.

WM. MARRIOTT CANBY,
Philadelphia, Pa.

PRICED TOO HIGH

Have always felt in offering an equipment-trust security was offering my clientele one of the safest type of investments. No doubt you have noticed that my business with you on this particular class of issues has not been as large as in days gone by, due to the fact that my clientele feel that this type

of security is priced too high, which have understood has been caused by competitive bidding by the brokers for this business.

WARREN C. M. BINCKLEY,
Reading, Pa.

DISTRUSTFUL OF PRACTICE

We have your letter of February 2 regarding sale of equipment-trust securities, and while our experience with these has been simply that of the small distributor and not at all from the angle of the original purchaser, we are distrustful of the practice of competitive bidding for railroad securities of all kinds.

In our opinion the point that you make as to the deviation of car trust indenture provisions under stress of competitive bidding from the standard safeguards which have given equipments their remarkable record for security is one of the strongest arguments against competitive bidding for this particular type of security.

WILLIAM O. KIMBALL & Co.,
Boston, Mass.

SECURITY NEGLECTED

While, of course, it is true that the railroads have been receiving more for these securities under this practice, it just seems to us that perhaps the restrictions surrounding their issuance are not quite as well regarded as they were before the sales were made to some one particular house. The competition by banks and bond houses for good loans has been so strong, that many times these good old-time customs of seeing that plenty of security is obtained are being neglected to a great extent, and we notice it more and more every day. We are so far away from the source of the issuance of bonds and securities of the type mentioned, that we want to know we are doing business with a reliable house, and one that is going to take everything into consideration, before buying an issue. This might not be watched so closely if the securities are sold under terms of competitive bidding.

CEDAR RAPIDS SAVINGS & BANK TRUST Co.,
Cedar Rapids, Iowa,
By L. J. DERFLINGER, *Cashier.*

PROFIT MATERIALLY REDUCED

Since the profit has been materially reduced through competitive bidding methods we have been forced to discontinue what little effort we had put forth in the distribution of this type of security, on account of the small volume which we would be able to handle not offering us sufficient profit to bother with.

We can readily see that competitive methods might work out advantageously for the railroads themselves under existing conditions, but feel that in the long run the practice formerly followed would have a more beneficial effect from the standpoint of the investor, the distributor, and the railroads. It would be our opinion that we would welcome a return to the old practice.

M. E. TRAYLOR & Co., INC.,
Denver, Colo.,
By WALTER E. OLIN, *Vice President.*

REGRET SUCH CLOSE TRADING PHILOSOPHY

We regret that such intense, competitive, dollar-and-cents, close trading philosophy has crept into a business as personal as the retail distribution of investment securities. After all, if a house of retail distribution has any economic justification, it is that it renders a personal service to an individual

who has funds to invest and to a corporation which needs funds for the conduct of its business.

BANKS, HUNTLEY & Co.,
Los Angeles, Calif.

RETURNS TO CUSTOMER LOW

Reading the orders of the Interstate Commerce Commission, permitting the sale of these bonds as the same appear in the United States Daily, it has been obvious to me that the underwriting houses were not making enough money to continue in business if they were forced to handle this kind of securities alone, and I know from the offerings which we have received, including yours, that the selling commission you were able to pass along to the retail distributor has been so small that the handling of these securities has been unprofitable. Incidentally, the returns to the customer have been ordinarily so low that the customers to whom one is able to distribute the securities have been greatly reduced. Probably to date in a bull market the result has been at least temporarily advantageous for the borrower, but that this condition can continue indefinitely is at least doubtful.

CANTON O'DONNELL, *Vice President,*
THE UNITED STATES NATIONAL Co.,
Denver, Colo.

INVARIABLY TAKE A LOSS ON LIQUIDATION

Please be advised that within the last year we have refrained from taking on any equipment issues, only in such cases where an urgent demand compels us to do so, for the reason that our experience has been that the prices are so extremely high when the offering is made, that if any of our loyal clients wish to liquidate, invariably it means that they must take a loss.

ZIMMERMAN & Co., *Pittsburgh, Pa.*

DOUBT RAILROADS WOULD BENEFIT

It is our opinion that if money conditions get bad, the railroads would naturally receive a lower price for their equipment trust obligations, and in the long run it is doubtful to us if the railroads would benefit from competitive bidding.

COURTS & Co., *Atlanta, Ga.*

MARGIN OF PROFIT SO LIMITED

We have always specialized in equipment trust securities as you know, but the margin of profit has been so limited in the last few years that our business has fallen off 50 percent and it pays us to devote our efforts to other classes of securities. Even in very high class railroad bonds, we receive three fourths to a point profit for handling bonds of this character.

NEWBOLD & Co., INC.,
By THOMAS R. NEWBOLD, *President,*
Colorado Springs, Colo.

RAILROADS BETTER SERVED BY NONCOMPETITIVE SALE

Generally speaking, it is our feeling that the railroads in the long run will be better served by the noncompetitive sale of equipment trust securities. We feel that such a method gives to the railroad companies greater continuity of banking service, and therefore more interested and helpful financial advice. It is very distinctly our feeling that equipment trusts during the last few years have not received the excellent distribution that they formerly enjoyed.

Whether this is the fault of public competitive bidding or not is another question. We are inclined to think the competitive bidding is largely responsible.

It is our feeling that financial service and proper financial interest are of such paramount importance to our railroads that the mere question of cheapness should be accepted with a great deal of caution.

STANLEY & BISSELL, INC.,
Cleveland, Ohio,
By EDWARD S. LITTLE, *Vice President.*

COMPETITIVE BIDDING HAS CAUSED LOSS OF DISTRIBUTION

In answer to your letter of January 30, with reference to the present method of selling railroad equipment trust obligations, we feel that competitive bidding has caused the price of these obligations to become so high that the distribution in this section has been materially cut down.

It has been our intention in this department to place some railroad equipment obligations on our list, but in view of their present yield we do not think that it would be advisable for us to materialize this plan at this writing.

DALLAS TRUST & SAVINGS BANK,
Dallas, Tex.
By J. LEWELL LAFFERTY, *Manager Bond Department.*

NO BENEFIT IN OVER PRICED OFFERINGS

It is our experience that a company does not benefit by having an issue of securities over priced on original offering. The inevitable result is an unsatisfactory secondary market which affects unfavorably the opinion not only of the original purchaser, but also of prospective buyers. The net result is that any subsequent issue has to be priced so as to overcome unfavorable market conditions. This is, of course, likely to be intensified when the margin of profit to the distributors is too narrow to permit really good distribution.

CHARLES W. SCRANTON & Co.,
New Haven, Conn.

FORCES HIGHER PRICE THAN MARKET WARRANTS

Competitive bidding, however, frequently results in forcing the successful bidder, in order to realize a profit, to put a higher price on the securities than market conditions actually warrant, which in turn leads to an unsatisfactory secondary market for the securities and a consequent adverse effect on the credit of the issuing company.

This is an age of expert advice, and if a railroad executive feels that he can dispense with the advice and cooperation of some specialist in the banking field, he is at perfect liberty to make his own set-up and shop his bonds to the highest bidder; but in this case the margin of profit to the banker is apt to be so small and his grip on future business so insecure that it does not pay him to consider more than his own immediate problem of marketing the bonds, so as to quickly realize his profits or losses.

STONE & WEBSTER AND BLODGET, INC.,
New York City.,
By R. H. CARLETON, *Vice President.*

GREAT DEAL AGAINST PRESENT METHOD

We have your letter of February 2 in regard to our opinion on the present policy of competitive bidding for car-trust securities. While we do not claim to be at all expert in this line of financing, we are rather of the opinion that in the long run the present method of competitive bids will not prove as satisfactory as the former method of each road dealing with their own particular banking house. While the railroads are probably getting a slightly higher

price for their car-trust securities with the present bond and money situation, when this situation changes and the price of money goes up and the sale of securities is made more difficult, it is quite probable the railroads, not having any particular banking house under obligations to them, will not get as high a price for securities as they have in the past. There is certainly a great deal to be said against the present method.

WOOLFOLK, WATERS & Co.,
New Orleans, La.

RAILROADS AND INVESTING PUBLIC BETTER OFF

Our feeling has been that the bankers commonly associated with the railroads should be permitted to continue to finance the railroads with which they have been associated. This feeling is based on the belief that over a long period of time the railroads and the investing public are better off under such a policy. This is without reference to what might be considered fair play in allowing the banking houses to profit by years of association and building up of railway credit.

METROPOLITAN NATIONAL Co.,
Minneapolis, Minn.,
By CHARLES A. FULLER, Jr., *Manager Bond Department.*

FICTITIOUS MARKET CONDITIONS CREATED

Competitive bidding for bond issues has created a speculative state of mind within many underwriting circles, and fictitious market conditions have been created which have been detrimental to participating dealers and to their clients.

DAVIS, SKAGGS & Co.,
San Francisco, Calif.

FAVOR OWN BANKING CONNECTIONS

In reply to your letter of February 2, we are very much in favor of the policy of railroad companies selling their bonds and car-trust securities through their own banking connections rather than by competitive bidding. We believe that competitive bidding is likely to cause too many issues to be overpriced and as a result cause dissatisfaction among the ultimate consumers.

RUFUS E. LEE & Co.,
Omaha, Nebr.,
By F. W. PORTER, *Vice President.*

COMPETITIVE BIDDING UNSATISFACTORY

It has been our observation in municipal bond issues and also in the farm loan business that competitive bidding for business proves very unsatisfactory. The bond houses and trust companies who take part in such competition are usually led to take more chances in order to get the business which in a good many cases afterward proves unsatisfactory.

THE FIRST NATIONAL BANK,
Friend, Nebr.,
By H. J. SOUTHWICK, *President.*

WOULD PROVE COSTLY IN THE LONG RUN

In reply to your letter of January 31 in regard to the policy of the Interstate Commerce Commission asking for competitive bids on equipment trusts, we might say that we feel this system does lead to overpricing and in the long run would make the cost of financing high to railroads.

We feel that the investment bankers for this type of security can adequately price the issues, and in a great majority of cases they are priced more favorably than as a result of competitive bidding.

HUGH B. MCGUIRE & Co.,
Portland, Oreg.,
By HUGH B. MCGUIRE.

FEW INVESTORS INTERESTED

It would seem to us that this has resulted in paying the railroads a slightly higher price for equipment-trust certificates, but we feel it is a debatable point as to whether this is of real benefit to the roads themselves. As the result the interest basis on equipment-trust certificates has declined to a point where very few of our western investors are interested in this paper, and the margin of profit which can be offered to houses who retail equipment-trust certificates has declined so very much that we do not feel that we can afford to handle them. We presume that other houses in the West have had the same experience.

Some time ago we handled quite a number of equipment-trust certificates. During the past 12 months our volume in this class of paper has been negligible. Therefore it would seem that the market is being restricted, and in our opinion a greater proportion now than formerly is being absorbed by insurance companies and large financial institutions. In a period of tight money this may react on the roads to their disadvantage.

BOSWORTH, CHANUTE, LOUGHBRIDGE & Co.,
Denver, Colo.
By ARTHUR H. BOSWORTH.

WILL REMOVE A TREMENDOUS DISTRIBUTION ORGANIZATION

As it is generally recognized, the volume of bond distribution in United States is done to a very large extent by the smaller dealer whose channels, if closed to equipment-trust certificates through lack of adequate profit in the business, will remove eventually a tremendous distributing organization from equipment-trust certificates.

C. T. WILLIAMS & Co., INC.,
Baltimore, Md.,
By JOHN ROBERTSON, *Vice President.*

SHOULD PICK BANKER WITH CARE

On the other hand, it has led to very high prices being paid by underwriting houses, and in some cases not enough profit left to pay for the trouble of marketing the securities in a comprehensive manner, thus making the market for the security narrow and in a very vulnerable position in the case of a declining market.

The writer feels strongly that large companies borrowing large amounts of money from time to time should pick their investment banker with care and then use him as their agent in all offerings of their securities. By doing this the company insures itself against poor treatment in bad financial times. This was certainly demonstrated by the railroads and public utilities during and immediately after the war.

NORTHERN TRUST Co.,
Duluth, Minn.,
STANLEY L. YONCE, *Vice President.*

MUST LOOK TO FUTURE REQUIREMENTS

Looking at the matter through the eyes of the railroad president, there is little doubt that the open and competitive bidding system brings somewhat higher prices for the securities. Or rather, such is the case just now, in this period of

widespread demand for investments. Yet railroads must look to their financial requirements for years to come, and if this country should once again run into the financial storms of 1920-21, most of the houses which are so active in their competitive bidding today would completely withdraw from the market. The inevitable result, of course, would probably be inadequate prices received by the railroads for their securities.

DUNN & CARR, *Houston, Tex.*

TENDENCY TO RESTRICT MARKET

Due to the low yields which new equipment offers have afforded, except in isolated cases, we have been compelled to be nonparticipants. Undoubtedly these prices are the results of competitive bidding, and it is my opinion that while the railroads have been receiving the benefits of higher prices received for their equipments, I think the effect on dealers has had a tendency to restrict the market, and should money conditions change it might be difficult to get the cooperation of the dealer in distribution.

Take, for instance, our own case; many channels in which we have placed equipment obligations we have since diverted into other more profitable securities, more profitable not only to ourselves but to our clients, and I think you can multiply this situation many times.

R. E. PROCHNOW & Co., INC.,
Chicago, Ill.,
By R. E. PROCHNOW, *President.*

SHOULD PROVIDE FOR EFFECTIVE DISTRIBUTION

If the distribution of equipment trusts among the general investment public is of interest, it is impossible to get such distribution with the margins now prevailing on that line of securities. For ourselves we sell a few but only when we have to. This business cannot be handled except at a loss on the present margins prevailing. If it is in the interests of the railroad corporation to get the most on a dollar for their securities, then competitive bidding in equipment trusts will probably accomplish that result. If, on the other hand, it is desirable for the railroad corporation itself to have a wider public interest in their securities, particularly in the territory in which they operate, and we believe it is, there should be a sufficient margin provided in the difference between the issue price and the price to the railroads to provide for effective distribution.

ANDERSON, PLOTZ & STEWART, INC.,
Chicago, Ill.,
By J. A. ANDERSON, *Vice President.*

WOULD SELL ONLY TO SPECIALISTS

If the writer had equipment-trust certificates to dispose of, he would see to it that they were sold to underwriting houses who were specialists in such distribution. On the other hand, he would not sell an issue of oil bonds to an equipment specialist. We have in mind one particular instance where a substantial issue of oil bonds were sold to a New York underwriter who had no particular ability to retail or wholesale them. The bonds are without question sound, but the offering was not favorably received because of the underwriter's unfitness to distribute it, and as a result the bonds declined 8 percent in price and are now out of line with equally desirable securities of the same class, and when this company again comes into the public market it will find it will have to pay for its failure to recognize the necessity of accepting not only a fair price for its bonds but moreover of selecting some distributor who has the ability to successfully accomplish this work.

COMMERCE TRUST Co.,
Kansas City, Mo.,
By GERALD PARKER, *Vice President.*

INSURANCE IN FINANCE IMPORTANT

We are told that a new era of finance has arrived and that precedents have no value, but from my point of view, if I were president of a railroad, I would think it an advantage to the railroad in the long run, and also to the public, that I should deal in the sale of new securities with some established house or houses with whom I had long associations, knowing that I would be fairly treated and that I could rely on them that the securities would be well placed. If I sold my securities at auction I might temporarily get a slightly better price but I would feel that in time of stress I would have very few friends, and I think that insurance in matters of finance is as important as insurance against fire or other casualties.

WALKER BROTHERS, *New York City*,
N. S. WALKER, *Esq.*

ARGUMENTS VERY SOUND

The arguments advanced by you are very sound and I believe most private corporations, where not subject to public supervision, adopt this method of selling their securities; however, in view of the fact that railroads are under the supervision of the Interstate Commerce Commission, doubt very much if they could be convinced of the wisdom of doing otherwise than by asking for public bids on these securities.

WHITNEY-CENTRAL TRUST & SAVINGS BANK,
New Orleans, La.,
C. G. RIVES, JR., *Vice President.*

POSITION OF INDEPENDENT DEALER UNSATISFACTORY

Formerly I have sold a good many equipment bonds to corporations and investors when there was a fair profit to the distributing house. Now, as an independent dealer, it is not profitable for me to handle any of this type of security. Furthermore, the low yield which equipment bonds now offer does not tempt me to offer them to my customers. If that is the general attitude, would the result not be that the railroads might lose any advantage they may gain through competitive bidding?

ALANSON G. FOX, *New York City.*

GREATEST SERVICE THROUGH STRONG BANKING HOUSES

As you know, we are not bidders for this special type of security. We are thus enabled to disclaim any direct concern in the matter. A long experience in the securities business, however, confirms us in the opinion that the greatest ultimate service is obtained both for the obligor corporation and the investing public, if strong banking houses are permanently allied in financing the recurring requirements of growing railroads. It thus becomes for them a matter of enlightened self-interest to render the best possible professional services.

F. S. SMITHERS & Co.,
New York City.

RESULTS IN FALSE VALUES

Competitive bidding for railroad car trust issues: These reasons impel us to register a "negative" on the present method in vogue through the interposition of the I.C.C. with reference to the sale of railroad-car trust issues:

(a) It deprives the railroad of a serious, tangible, dependable financial connection.

(b) It frequently involves hasty and ill-advised buying judgment on the part of too-eager executives of buying departments of security houses.

(c) It results in a false level of values, i.e., bottomed on temporary, fluid commercial credits, whereas due consideration should be accorded the long-term capital lock-up and the intervening economic (and other) possibilities.

(d) Finally, it robs the distributing dealer of any real incentive to effect a worthy lodgment of the securities, due to the prohibitively small profit involved, in a time of almost terrifying overhead expenses.

BOWMAN & Co., *St. Louis, Mo.*
By D. ARTHUR BOWMAN.

MANY FORMER BUYERS NO LONGER INTERESTED

Replying to your letter of the 30th instant, will say that it has been our experience that many who formerly bought equipment trusts no longer are interested in them because of the high prices at which they must be purchased. We have certain clientele that will buy them. but I think that the market could be greatly broadened if the price were more consistent with the character of the security.

PARTRIDGE-PATMYTHES Co., INC.,
Milwaukee, Wis.,
By JOHN C. PARTRIDGE, *President.*

INSTITUTIONS NOT INTERESTED

Your letter of February 1 was received several days ago, since which time the writer has given considerable thought to the matter contained therein. In the first place, we have not been particularly active in equipment trust obligations the past few years, due principally to the fact that the yield has, generally speaking, become so low that our institutions have not been interested.

Relative to your inquiry regarding competitive bidding, we are somewhat at a loss as to what to say. We do feel that this undoubtedly has been the cause of severe overpricing, not only in the case of equipment trust securities, but other issues as well. with the result that underwriting houses and those participating with them, have lost money and the credit of the issuing corporation has by no means been enhanced. On the whole it seems to us that competitive bidding might be eliminated to advantage. We feel that railroads and other corporations would receive practically as good prices, and that distributing houses and the public would probably fare better.

PUTNAM & Co., *Hartford, Conn.*

APT TO WORK A HARDSHIP

In other words, we believe that competitive bidding, particularly in the equipment trust business, is apt to work a hardship in the long run on the borrower. We also feel that any fair-minded borrower should take into consideration the assistance which has been given him in past years by a banking house, before breaking off relations for some slight concession in price made by another banking house. The writer has a very strong feeling on this point as he has seen competitive bidding in commercial paper transactions work very decidedly to the detriment of the borrower in the long run.

It goes without saying that any high grade, reputable banking house would certainly not take unfair advantage of a client in making him a price on his financing, simply because the banking house knew they were bidding without competition.

SIDLO, SIMONS, DAY & Co.,
Denver, Colo.,
By RICHARD M. DAY.

DISTRIBUTION BEING CURTAILED

We realize that the railroads are securing good prices at the present time but feel that distribution of the securities through a number of small dealers is being curtailed through lack of adequate profit. This curtailment may in time react to the disadvantage of the distribution of equipment trusts at a time when money is not so plentiful for investment.

MARSHALL & Co., *Pittsburgh, Pa.*,
By R. B. MARSHALL, *President.*

SUCH ISSUES LOSING FAVOR

We align ourselves on the side of the critics of this method and agree that severe overpricing has been one of the results. This may have benefited the roads temporarily but is causing such issues to lose favor in the investment markets. We cannot see the advantage to the roads in dealing now with one group of bankers, again with another group, and so on ad infinitum and are thorough believers in the theory that a corporation's finances may be most successfully handled through the consistent and sustained cooperation of one banking house.

BANK OF NORTH AMERICA & TRUST Co.,
Philadelphia, Pa.
By J. H. MASON, Jr., *Vice President.*

HIGH PRICES WOULD BE OFFSET

The increased demand for credit for commercial and industrial purposes from customers of the banks could very easily result in a congestion of equipment trust notes that would affect their market unfavorably and in the long run result in the railroad companies finding it necessary to sell such securities at such a disadvantage that the high prices obtained through competitive bidding during easy money times would be more than offset.

We feel that the firms of high standing who have specialized in certain classes of bonds over a long period are in better position to know the real value of such securities and handle them to better advantage both for the borrower and the investor than the firms interested only in the commission on a specific issue and not in the general and lasting good market for that class of bond.

THE NATIONAL STOCK YARDS NATIONAL BANK,
National Stock Yards, Ill.
By OWEN J. SULLIVAN, *President.*

FAVOR RECIPROCITY

The writer's experiences as a director in the United Light & Railways Co. and the General Gas & Electric Co. showed him most impressively that it was most important and beneficial for those companies to have friends during the troublous times of the World War.

A corporation which merely puts out its securities on a competitive basis and does nothing to warrant receiving help in bad times in our opinion is not in such a strong position as if it took the opposite course of having friends and working under a reciprocity arrangement.

MOORS & CABOT, *Boston, Mass.*

FINAL RESULTS NOT BENEFICIAL

In reply to your letter of January 31, we beg to say that we believe the final results of the new practice in the sale of equipment trust securities will not be beneficial, with the two main thoughts in mind, that the distributor will not

receive a profit commensurate with his efforts and that the former wide distribution of these securities will be cut down with the higher prices, and the investor will probably put his funds in inferior securities as a substitute.

In other words, regarding the two main objects of the investment business being the welfare of the investor and a profit to ourselves (two points so closely related that it is hard to consider one over a period of time except in the light of the other), we feel that both the investor and the dealer are better served in the long run under the old system.

Also, as we see it, the credit of the railroads is not helped in the long run by the sale of securities, bearing their name to the public, which are over-priced as some have been under the new plan.

SMITH, STROUT & EDDY, INC.,
Seattle, Wash.
 By E. A. STROUT, Jr., *Secretary and Treasurer.*

PUBLIC SHOULD BE ENCOURAGED TO BUY

In a favorable market such as this one it is true that competitive bidding may get slightly higher prices for the railroads. On the other hand, over a period of time we do not believe this balances the good to be derived from the old-fashioned relationships between corporation and banker. The railroad should make its money out of operating a railroad and not out of banking. Furthermore, the public should be encouraged to buy railroad securities, and the way to do this is not to see at how high a price they can be unloaded on the public.

BACON, WHIPPLE & Co., INC.,
Chicago, Ill.,
 By W. T. BACON, *President.*

FANCY PRICES PAID

No doubt, in some instances, the originating house has paid a very fancy price for the issue with the idea that the advertisement of the origination by them would be advantageous to them otherwise and also with the idea that their dealer clientele would help them bear their loss, if any, in distributing the issues. This same originating house will, of course, be the unsuccessful bidder for the same road's issues when the bond market is in a bad way and naturally the banking house sponsoring the railroad will then have to buy them and take their chances, and my argument would be that they should be allowed to purchase equipments through good and bad times by negotiations only.

SECURITY TRUST Co., *Lexington, Ky.,*
 By J. D. VAN HOOSER, *Vice President.*

ADVANTAGE OF WIDE DISTRIBUTION DEFEATED

We feel that the increase in price of Equipment Trust securities has made it almost impossible for the dealers in the smaller communities to distribute them. This has undoubtedly led to a greater concentration of securities in this class in the financial centers, and particularly New York. While there would seem to be an advantage to the railroads in selling their securities at a high price, we feel that it is quite possible that in the long run this advantage may be lost by the decrease in the railroad security holders. If there is an advantage in wide distribution of securities of any corporation, we feel that this advantage is defeated in the case of competitive bidding for investment trusts.

NORTHERN BOND & MORTGAGE Co.,
Green Bay, Wis.

OPPOSED TO PRESENT METHODS

We have your favor of February 1 regarding present methods of selling equipment trust securities by the railroads. From a purely selfish standpoint we are opposed to the present methods as we find that the margin of profits is

so small that we could only afford to handle them if we knew we had an immediate turnover. As it is, the price is usually so full that the offering is not attractive and the interest in the offering on the part of institutions is decidedly lessened. In other words, there is too much sales resistance on account of price and the profit to the dealer is so small that there is no incentive to overcome this. We agree with you that this will limit the distributoin of such securities and when we again get into a lender's rather than a borrower's market, considerable missionary work will have to be done to re-establish equipment trust securities with a broad list of investors.

HILL, JOINER & Co., INC., *Chicago, Ill.*,
By C. C. ADAMS, *Vice President.*

MARKET ACTION UNSATISFACTORY

We feel that your position on this subject, as outlined in your letter, is absolutely correct. So far as we are concerned, we have practically discontinued over the past year or so the handling of equipment trust securities because of the close margin of profit. Consequently we are gradually losing contact with any market for this class of obligation, and as we build up other lines of distribution, we doubt if our interest could be revived in equipment trust securities in a less favorable money market when there might be more profit in the distribution of equipments.

It has always been our experience that when securities are offered to us by originating houses who have been forced into competitive bidding to secure the business, the market action of the securities after the expiration of the syndicate has not been satisfactory as a general proposition. This is usually true because the securities are over priced.

On the other side of the picture we have always felt that any corporation, be it railroad, public utility or otherwise, is in a much more satisfactory position so far as its public financing is concerned during the period of stress, if it has had satisfactory and continued relations with a banking or originating house who feels under obligations to take care of its wants. Certainly such an obligation does not exist if, for every piece of financing that the corporation desires to put out, the bankers have to enter into competitive bidding.

We feel very strongly that your position as outlined is entirely correct.

ROBINSON-JENKINS-TAYLOR Co., *Minneapolis, Minn.*,
By H. R. TAYLOR, *Vice President.*

SHORT-SIGHTED VIEWPOINT

The writer's views on this subject are very much in accordance with your ideas as outlined in your letter. It has always been our opinion here that competitive bidding, although it unquestionably is very advantageous to the issuing company in a favorable market, has a tendency to undermine banking relationships of a character very necessary to the company whose securities are being sold. We have always felt that for a railroad, utility, or industrial company to form a powerful banking connection of a semipermanent nature might be of great benefit to the company in future years when the security markets might not be anywhere near as good as at this time. It is quite possible that the practice inaugurated by the Interstate Commerce Commission may be successful and may operate to the advantage of the issuing company in the next few years over the period of cheap money which can be expected for some time, but when the reaction sets in we believe the loss of permanent connections will operate to the disadvantage of these same companies.

Summing up the above, we take the position that the Interstate Commerce Commission is looking at the practice from a rather short-sighted viewpoint, and also that time alone will prove which theory is correct.

CHICAGO TRUST Co., *Chicago, Ill.*,
By J. W. MARSHALL, *Vice President.*

DO NOT FAVOR ORDER

We do not favor the order of the Interstate Commerce Commission that equipment trust certificates or other railroad securities should be sold as the result of competitive bidding. Our opinion is that over a period of years the interests of the weaker railroads, and in fact of practically nearly all of such corporations, except the very strongest, would be better served by having their securities marketed through bankers who would feel a responsibility for the properties.

WM. E. BUSH & Co., *Augusta, Ga.*

COMPETITIVE BUSINESS NOT FAVORED

It has always been our opinion that railroad business of all kinds, including both the majority finance and equipments, should be done by the banking houses sponsoring the railroads concerned, not by any system of competitive business by investment bankers. We are therefore very much in sympathy with this movement in regard to bringing this matter to the attention of the Interstate Commerce Commission, and I hope that your efforts will meet with success.

FOURTH & FIRST NATIONAL Co., *Nashville, Tenn.*,
By B. O. CURREY, *Sales Manager.*

WOULD NOT PURCHASE FROM INEXPERIENCED BANKERS

Replying to your favor of the 31st ultimo; we have been large buyers of equipment certificates during the last 20 years and have always regarded them prime investments. This type of investment security has increased in favor among certain classes of investors upon recommendation of investment houses. This has primarily been the reason for the success in financing this requirement of our railroad systems. The high standing of the investment house specializing in this type of security brings a corresponding investment standing and credit to the railroad which desires to sell such instruments of indebtedness. We would not purchase this form of investment if brought out and handled by inexperienced bankers or investment houses who have no particular interest in the security except to handle it at a profit. Convertibility, rating, and character of the investment banker bringing out the certificates all enter into the value. If competitive bidding is adopted or forced upon the railroads, car-trust securities will be changed from high grade ultra conservative investments to speculative investments and they would therefore be unacceptable to our clients.

AMBROSE R. CLARK Co., *New York City.*

SHOULD RECEIVE SERIOUS CONSIDERATION

Of course, we agree that the purchase of issues of the equipment trust by competitive syndicate houses has had a tendency to raise the price which the railroads have received for these securities, and reduced the return basis to the holding public. We believe that the equipment trust securities should be sold with the market as it is when the securities are brought out, and we do not feel that this should be influenced as it is by the competition of syndicate houses in the purchase of these securities. We feel as you do that this should receive very serious consideration.

WILKES-BARRE DEPOSIT & SAVINGS BANK,
Wilkes-Barre, Pa.,
By BENJAMIN F. WILLIAMS, *Cashier.*

COMPANY'S CREDIT WOULD SUFFER

If bonds are offered at a higher price than they are really worth and the secondary market is unable to hold the price, it would seem to us that the

credit of the company would suffer and that on future issues they might not obtain as good a price as would have been possible under the old system.

CORNING TRUST Co.,
Corning, N.Y.,
 By G. A. HEERMANS, *Secretary.*

DEFINITE BANKING CONNECTIONS OUTWEIGH HIGHER PRICES

We have your letter of January 31, and it is our opinion that the benefits to the railroads of definite banking connections upon whom they can depend in bad times as well as good, considerably outweigh the possibly somewhat higher prices which they may obtain for their securities through competitive bidding under favorable market conditions.

HUNTINGTON JACKSON & Co.,
New York City.

PROFITED DURING EASY MONEY

In other words, the railroads no doubt have profited by selling their securities to the highest bidder during this time of very easy money, but if and when the conditions change materially we feel that they may regret not having tied up to dealers who can always take care of their requirements.

SECURITY SAVINGS & TRUST Co.,
Portland, Oreg.,
 By EDW. H. GEARY, *Vice President.*

BETTER TO SELL TO OWN BANKER

In reply to your letter of February 2, 1928, in regard to railroads selling their equipment-trust securities by competitive bidding, we have always been of the opinion that over a term of years it is better for the railroad company to sell all their securities to their own banker.

It is true that under the present conditions the railroads are getting a better price for their equipment-trust securities by competitive bidding, but we are not so sure that this practice will prove profitable to them during the time of stringent money.

HOWZE, SPENCER & Co., *Duluth, Minn.,*
 By GERALD HOWZE, *President.*

CARE OF THE AFTERMARKET

Generally speaking, we are not interested in participating in any syndicate if there is a possibility that no one is going to take care of the aftermarket. The danger to the small house from lack of a proper aftermarket is accentuated in the equipment-trust field due to the small amount of the various maturities outstanding.

In the past we have seen many cases where a banking house has taken an issue and distributed it and supported it until the issues of the corporation in question had a market standing far superior to any previously experienced. We have seen such corporations sell succeeding issues of securities to other banking groups at higher prices, such higher prices being made possible in many cases because of the good work of their first banking connection. Such action is morally improper and we believe economically unsound.

The Interstate Commerce Commission has done great things for the American railroads, but not all its action has been sound. It can certainly reverse itself from time to time and thereby gain a greater respect from the general public.

S. C. PARKER & Co., INC., *Buffalo, N.Y.,*
 By SELBY C. PARKER, *President.*

THOUGHT COMMISSION MAKING A MISTAKE

Replying to your letter of February 1, we have to say, at the time the I.C.C. insisted on competitive bidding for the sale of equipment-trust securities of some prominent railroad company, whose petition to sell the equipments was then under consideration, I thought the Commission was making quite a mistake, and I have found no reason since, in further considering the subject, to change my mind. I still believe the best results can be obtained by the railroads in negotiating direct with their bankers.

THE INDIANA TRUST Co., *Indianapolis, Ind.*
J. P. FRENZEL, *Chairman of the Board.*

SUCH A POLICY UNWISE

Responding to your request for an expression of my opinion as to the desirability of competitive bidding as a policy in the sale by railroads of their car-trust obligations, I think such a policy is unwise because its tendency is to create an artificial primary market for such securities, leaving the secondary market stale when owners desire to sell them, which must eventually be detrimental to car-trust obligations as a class.

HENRY T. KEELER.

NOT PRONE TO PUSH THIS CLASS OF SECURITY

We are in touch with quite a few buyers of equipment trust securities and when brought to their attention at the present prices, they are very loath to purchase. In addition, we are not as prone to push this class of security as we would if the margin of profit were greater, because at the present margin, after taking into consideration the expense of obtaining the business, handling, etc., we are actually handling equipment-trust securities at a loss and no house wishes to handle anything at a loss.

Summarizing our opinion, therefore, we are pleased to advise you that we feel that were the bankers given more consideration in the handling of equipment-trust securities as regards profit and in addition, by means of this profit, distribution, that while the railroads would probably not get as good prices as they have at the present time, their securities would actually be in better shape, marketwise and from a point of investment to the actual holder.

KUECHLE & Co.,
Milwaukee, Wis.,
By C. E. REDEKER, *Vice President.*

CEASE TO FEEL ANY OBLIGATION

It seems to us, while we are not particularly active in equipment trusts, we nevertheless participate in some of the syndicates and selling groups, that an occasional issue will sell entirely too high, others issues perhaps too low. We have experienced in the Iowa municipal market that when a dealer pays too much for an issue of bonds, in order to keep other dealers from purchasing a similar issue in the near future, he buys it for more than it is worth in order to keep the price up, thereby protecting his original purchase. This is of course a very vicious procedure, but I presume it could possibly happen with equipment trusts. I think the most unfortunate part of the competitive bidding is that certain dealers who have understood that they would be required to handle the equipment trusts of certain railroads will now cease to feel any sense of obligation and will buy the bonds as cheaply as possible; in other words, the roads will not have a sort of understood financial arrangement, which has worked out so satisfactorily in the past.

PRIESTER-QUAIL & CUNDY, INC.,
Davenport, Iowa,
By JOHN J. QUAIL, *Vice President.*

DISTRIBUTION WILL BE SERIOUSLY AFFECTED

Naturally, we have been forced to begin operations in this highly competitive market at small profit on large turnover. If the competitive bidding results in continued buying of new issues by larger banking houses at prices which show them practically no profit, we are convinced that our operations will be narrowed to such an extent that distribution will be seriously affected. As distribution narrows the popular criticism of poor market becomes true and outweighs the advantage of security.

HATHAWAY & Co.,
Chicago, Ill.,
By CHARLES D. MARSH, *Manager Bond Department.*

COMPETITIVE BIDDING RESPONSIBLE FOR NARROW DISTRIBUTION

Our experience has been that equipment trust securities have been so overpriced that it has been next to impossible for us to move any in our territory. During the summer season we have a very heavy demand for high-grade, short-term paper, and equipment trusts, if reasonably priced, would allow us to place a considerable block of these short-term securities. We feel that competitive bidding is responsible for the narrow distribution and overpricing of these securities and it would seem more satisfactory if the railroads would sell these securities as they previously did.

DAVIS & WEST,
Norfolk, Va.

EQUIPMENT ISSUES IN DANGER

In connection with the subject of equipment trust securities and the advisability of having competitive bidding therefor, we are strongly of the opinion that for the good of the purchasers of the bonds the first consideration is to have the financing handled by houses that are thoroughly acquainted, through experience, with the necessary legal requirements to guarantee protection to such issues. We believe that this is vital because in the long run the record of the equipment trust issues with respect to security and final payment has a very definite relation to the selling price.

In other words, if equipment trust issues are continued to be carried through a house such as your own—which has demonstrated its ability to see that issues are properly protected—there is little likelihood that the good record that these issues enjoy will be marred. On the other hand, if we get into wholesale competitive bidding without consideration to the requirements above enumerated, we are apt to have occasions arise that would mar not only the record of the specific road putting out the issue, but the equipment issues as a class.

MERCHANTS SECURITIES CORPORATION,
Worcester, Mass.
By HARRY R. McINTOSH, *Treasurer.*

NOT INTERESTED IN NEW ISSUES

The very low yield on these securities of late has forced us to strike them even from considering their purchase, and until the yield becomes very much more attractive and we can be sure that there will be a constant substantial market for the certificates in the event a sale is necessary, we do not see how we can be interested in new issues. It seems to us that this grade of securities should be treated in a somewhat different manner than the sale of ordinary securities, and we should be pleased to see the equipment trust handled as of old.

COMMERCE TRUST Co.,
Lincoln, Nebr.
By M. L. SPRINGER, *Secretary-Treasurer.*

PUBLIC CARRYING THE BAG

Claims have been made by several of our customers that severe overpricing has been the result, which has caused an attitude of disfavor on the part of these purchasers. The customers, as well as ourselves, agree that the protection of public interests should be the first consideration. However, they seem to feel, because of this overpricing, that the public is carrying the bag and that the railroads are receiving all the benefit of this practice.

SULLIVAN & SMITH,
Wellsboro, Pa.,
By M. J. SULLIVAN.

COMPETITIVE BIDDING UNSOUND IN POOR MARKET

Competitive bidding brings into the market anyone who is able to pay for the securities, and of course those people are very numerous on a good market. However, on a poor market it is only those who have established clienteles and who have dealt with concerns regularly who will then, even at their own disadvantage, take care of borrowing corporations. As mentioned above, it is true in all kinds of negotiations.

WHELLOCK & Co.,
- Des Moines, Iowa,
By L. F. WHELLOCK.

OLD SYSTEM THE BETTER

In reference to your letter in regard to competitive bidding for equipment trust securities, we feel that in the long run the old system of having one of several houses identified with the securities of each road is perhaps the better system, as their handling of the securities tends to stabilize the market, and they are more inclined to lend their support to the road when conditions are unfavorable. These facts, we think, offset the immediate advantage of somewhat better terms resulting from competitive bidding.

J. WM. MIDDENDORF & SONS,
Baltimore, Md.

BECOME INDIFFERENT TO THIS CLASS OF SECURITY

We think you are doing a good work in securing a cross-section of the opinions of houses which have in the past offered equipment trust certificates. Since the Interstate Commerce Commission has ruled that equipment trust securities offered by the railroads should be sold to the highest bidder, we have found it impractical and unwise to be actively interested in the distribution of them.

We have felt in nearly every case that the bonds were being offered at the very highest price at which they could hope to be sold.

Disregarding for the moment the selling price of such offerings, we have also become indifferent to this class of security, inasmuch as we felt we could not afford to purchase them, put them on our list, and offer them to the people to whom we used to sell them, due to the fact that there would be a great sales resistance in moving them off, and we might have them on our list for some little time with little or no profit to ourselves.

We feel, too, that our banking institutions, which at one time bought great amounts of equipment trusts, also believe that they are being brought out at the very highest price, and that once they are purchased it is difficult to secure a market at anywhere near the price which they paid for them, in case they found it necessary to resell them.

As we look at it, the only benefit derived from the distribution of the equipment trusts under the present arrangements is the publicity which certain originating houses feel they are receiving when they are the successful bidders.

After an investor or banking institution has been urged into the purchase of such securities under this plan and then has occasion to resell them and learns

of the unsatisfactory market, we think they too must become prejudiced; and a continuance of this policy is unquestionably going to spoil in time what has been a very fine market for this form of investment.

MERRILL, HAWLEY & Co.,
Cleveland, Ohio.

NOT WORKING IN PRACTICE

We believe that in theory this is all right, but in practice that it is not working out to the real advantage of the railroads or the investing public, not to mention the banker. Apparently in good bond markets such as the present one many houses will buy equipment at exceedingly high prices to be offered as "window dressing" and feel that they have done a good piece of advertising even though they only break even on the deal. In a declining bond market such houses would not be willing to bid and the railroads would have to go to their regular bankers and probably take a price lower than they would have received if these bankers had had all their business.

HILL BROS. & Co., *St. Louis, Mo.*

NOT IN THE PUBLIC INTEREST

During a period when bond prices have been steadily rising it is difficult to present convincing arguments against the sale by railroads or car trust securities by competitive bidding. Although during the period that it has been in operation this practice has undoubtedly resulted in the railroads securing higher prices, we believe that it is not in the public interest for the following reasons: It is a specialized business and great care should be exercised in drawing up the various indenture and trust provisions. Poor distribution results from overpricing and an insufficient margin of profit. There is no incentive for bankers to help out roads in times of stress.

In the past where a railroad's entire financing has been handled by one banker there may have been cases where this relationship has been abused. However, we feel that at the present time the possibility of such abuse is negligible in comparison with advantages to be gained, both by the railroads and the public through more intelligent handling and better distribution.

MAYNARD, OAKLEY & LAWRENCE,
New York City.

WILL RESULT IN OVERPRICING

It occurs to me, although I have no experience in original purchases along this line, that open competitive bidding for these securities will result in overpricing, which will ultimately result in a reluctance on the part of the individual distributing dealers to handle equipment certificates and will therefore have a tendency to concentrate holdings so that if any unforeseen break takes place in the market this type of security is apt to be offered in such volume that the market effect will be decidedly disturbing. I believe it to the interest of those who wish to borrow money in this form to keep the market position of securities in such shape as to inspire the public's confidence in that particular type of security.

W. E. HUTTON & Co.,
Cincinnati, Ohio,
By CAMPBELL S. JOHNSTON,
Manager Bond Department.

NECESSARY THAT DEALER MAKE PROFIT

Equipment trust securities are not at present, as a class, on an equal rank with Liberty bonds and municipal bonds. To a certain extent, a secondary market must be maintained. Therefore, we believe it is necessary that the dealer be given a certain amount of profit in order to make it worth his while

to handle such a market. Otherwise, it is possible that the securities might decline in price very shortly after the offering.

E. G. CHILDS & Co., INC.,
Syracuse, N. Y.

NOT FOR THE BETTER INTERESTS OF THE RAILROADS OR THE PUBLIC

It is therefore our opinion that the policy of competitive bidding is not for the better interest of the railroads or the public from the broader viewpoint. The railroads of the United States are directed by men of sufficient intelligence, well enough acquainted with economic conditions, not to be milked by any unscrupulous bond companies in underwriting their equipment trust issues.

Furthermore, a close, permanent connection with a reputable banking firm will result in greater economy in marketing equipment issues, due to the fact that such banking connection could adequately educate its clientele in the character of the roads, and in such fashion eliminate much of the sales resistance that must be overcome by strange houses who competitively bid and secure car trust issues.

MORTGAGE & SECURITIES Co.,
New Orleans, La.
By FRED. N. OGDEN,
Manager Bond Department.

OFFERINGS DECLINED

Of course, we are small dealers in a far-away section, but if our experience is any indication of the general experience, we would certainly feel that the public interest is better protected by not enforcing competitive bidding. We know that several of our large bank customers constantly decline any offerings of equipment trust certificates since the inauguration of competitive bidding, on account of the feeling that under competitive methods there is naturally a tendency for investment bankers to pay too much for the issues offered.

GUARDIAN TRUST Co.,
Houston, Tex.
By L. B. DUQUETTE,
Vice President.

CANNOT FAIL TO DETRACT

From the prices asked for various issues of car trust securities recently offered to us, we are inclined to agree with your contention that competitive bidding frequently results in over-prices, with the attendant weakness in after-markets which cannot fail to detract somewhat from the favor in which this type of securities is normally held.

We agree also that less favorable conditions in the future may serve to emphasize still further the value of a permanent connection as above.

THE COMMERCIAL NATIONAL BANK,
Peoria, Ill.
By A. B. LLOYD,
Manager Bond Department.

CARE OF REQUIREMENTS IN BAD TIMES

In response to your letter of February 2, regarding the sale of equipment trust securities by the railroads at private or public sale, I do not see where the railroads or any other corporation particularly profit in this manner, as I am firmly convinced that the average corporation of that class has enough able-bodied men who know the value of securities and who are in close touch with the market in general, they can demand from their bankers the price they should receive for this class of securities, thereby favoring the bank and bond house who in turn will favor them in a depreciated period.

This may not be true, however, when it comes to the sale of municipal bonds, as the average small town citizenship is not made up of that class of director-

ship. I still favor, and always will, new business with the party who will be able to take care of the requirements in bad times as well as in good times.

HOME TRUST Co., *Kansas City, Mo.*,
JOSEPH DUNER, *Manager Bond Department.*

SLIGHT SAVING IN TIMES OF LARGE DEMAND

As long as the demand for equipment obligations is greatly in excess of the supply, and the credit of all railroads is improving, there is probably a slight saving to the roads through the method of competitive bidding, but we believe that in the long run it is more advantageous to have all the financing of a railroad, equipment and otherwise, handled by one house.

It is our belief that in recent years the great power held by the large financial interests in New York has been more wisely and more justly used than ever before, and that they can be safely trusted to deal justly with all borrowers.

LLOYD & PALMER, *Philadelphia, Pa.*

LESS DISTRIBUTION TO INVESTORS

Referring to your letter of February 1, relative to equipment trusts, it is our opinion that due to overpricing as a result of competitive bidding, the distribution of equipment trusts to investors has acted adversely.

We formerly could distribute many more equipment trusts than we can under the present competitive bidding arrangement.

YOUNG & BLAIR, INC., *Buffalo, N.Y.*,
By C. D. BLAIR.

BENEFITS NOT GREAT

The policy of competitive bidding has undoubtedly resulted in higher prices to the railroads for their securities, but we do not think that the benefits have been as great as at first seemed probable because of the uncertainty of the after-market and the discouragement that many investors felt in buying issues that were priced too high.

BAINBRIDGE & RYAN, *New York City.*

TREAT SAME AS MORTGAGE-BOND ISSUE, OR STOCK

We believe equipment issues should be part of the general financing program of a railroad and be handled by that road's bankers. We can see no reason why a railroad about to sell an equipment-trust issue should not consult its bankers as it would if it were about to sell a mortgage-bond issue, or stock.

MACCALL, FRASER & WHEELER,
Providence, R.I.

SOUND BASIS FOR CRITICISM

The situations are, in any event, not entirely analogous as there can be no control of the set-up of municipal issues nor often any vital need to borrow in an emergency, and these two elements provide, in my opinion, the soundest basis for the criticism of competitive bidding for other types of corporate financing.

DEAN WITTER & Co., *San Francisco, Calif.*,
DEAN WITTER, *President.*

DEALERS REQUIRE A FAIR MARGIN OF PROFIT

Usually we like equipment-trust securities. We have sold very few of them recently, because of the fact that the margin of profit has been so small, that it has not been worth the effort to go out and push them.

We believe something ought to be done to give dealers a fair margin of profit on which to work, and we also believe something should be done to stop the overpricing of these bonds.

If competitive bidding has caused this condition, it seems as if steps to change the situation should be taken.

Goss & Co., *South Bend, Ind.*,
By HAROLD K. FORSYTHE, *President.*

WOULD NOT BENEFIT RAILROADS OR PUBLIC

In regard to the question contained in your communication, we are of the opinion that competitive bidding for equipment trust certificates, as suggested by the Interstate Commerce Commission, would not to any degree benefit the railroads, and indirectly, of course, the general public. We are of the opinion that the business judgment and sound management and fiscal policies of the majority of railroads provide automatically the safeguard of realizing the actual worth of equipment-trust certificates sold to underwriters. It is our belief further that competitive bidding would make necessary the acceptance on the part of railroad management the proposals of institutions which were not properly qualified to set up, distribute originally, or maintain subsequent markets for the securities so awarded them. We feel that the possibility of obtaining slightly higher prices for their securities on the part of the railroads would only be temporary, and would be more than offset by the ultimate weakening off due to improper handling of distributions and markets.

BLANKENHORN & Co., *INC., Los Angeles, Calif.*,
By EDWARD V. CARTER, *Vice President.*

COMPETITIVE BIDDING NOT TO BEST INTEREST OF PUBLIC

We have your letter of February 1 in relation to equipment-trust securities issued by the railroads under terms of competitive bidding. Due to the high standing of the banking houses who have specialized in equipment financing, we are firmly of the opinion that the public interest has been in the past, is now, and will be in the future, well served by the continuance of this general practice.

We have seen in the municipal bond business, situations arise whereby municipalities have received far less money for their bonds under competitive bidding than would have been the case had they been privileged to sell direct to some reputable banking house who were really interested in their financing.

PORTER, ERSWELL & Co., *Portland, Me.*,
By W. H. PORTER, *President.*

FAVOR RESPONSIBLE BANKERS

We feel that in most cases corporation borrowers can secure better service, greater protection, and, on the whole, as low rates and favorable terms by dealing privately with responsible bankers rather than asking for competitive bids on their special financing.

FERRIS & HARDGROVE, *Spokane, Wash.*,
By J. E. FERRIS, *President.*

SHORTSIGHTED POLICY

It seems to us that railroads are following a rather shortsighted policy in severing valuable connections which have extended over a long period of years with banking houses which have represented them in the distribution of their securities. They are taking this action to avail themselves of more favorable bases of issuing securities, which we believe result purely from the competitive situation at the present time. In the future, if there should be another period of stringent money, as there may very well be, these corporations would probably receive a cold reception upon returning to the houses which have represented them so long, and they would scarcely be in a position to criticize the reception received in view of the action they are taking.

JAMES H. CAUSEY & Co.,
Denver, Colo.,

By JOHN C. ROBERTS, *Treasurer.*

FUTURE INTEREST OF INESTIMABLE VALUE

We have never felt that the public sale of this type of security, that is, railroad or utility securities, works to the ultimate interest of the company. The future interest that an underlying house has in the welfare of the companies whose securities it underwrites is of inestimable value. Wherever competitive bidding enters, this is destroyed.

MILLER, VOSBURG & Co.,
Los Angeles, Calif.,

By L. REVEL MILLER, *President.*

EXCESSIVE PRICES

While undoubtedly under present money market conditions the railroads have been receiving a somewhat higher price for this class of securities, we know that as far as our own actual working under the new plan, that we have distributed practically no equipment trust securities on the basis that it has been our own feeling that practically all new issues have been brought out at excessive prices and without any possible margin of profit to reimburse us for the cost of effecting distribution.

THE NATIONAL BANK OF COMMERCE,
Seattle, Wash.,

By DIETRICH SCHMITZ, *Vice President.*

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT 3

Articles of copartnership, dated December 31, 1932, by and between Felix M. Warburg, Otto H. Kahn, George W. Bovenizer, Lewis L. Strauss, William Wiseman, Frederick M. Warburg, Gilbert W. Kahn, John M. Schiff, Benjamin J. Buttenwieser, Hugh Knowlton, and Elisha Walker

A majority of the parties hereto are transacting business in the city of New York as partners, under the firm name of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. Said firm succeeded other partnerships transacting business under the same firm name, and it and its predecessors have transacted business in the city of New York under the same firm name for more than 60 years, during which time they have also had business relations in and with foreign countries. The parties hereto desire to continue such business from and after January 1, 1933, as a general partnership under the same partnership name.

The parties hereto accordingly agree as follows:

I. The parties hereto hereby continue in general partnership under and pursuant to the laws of the State of New York for the purpose of carrying on the business transacted by them, and such partnership shall be conducted under the firm name of Kuhn, Loeb & Co.

II. The partnership shall continue from year to year unless and until terminated in the manner provided in article IX hereof.

III. The capital of the partnership shall be ———, which shall be contributed by the partners as follows: ———

Each partner, as an expense of the business, shall be entitled to receive interest at the rate of ——— percent per annum from December 31, 1932, payable semiannually on June 30 and December 31 of each year, upon the capital contributed by him as aforesaid, and shall not be entitled to any profits of the business on account of the capital so contributed by him. No part of the capital so contributed by any partner shall be withdrawn without the consent of all the partners so long as he shall remain a member of the partnership.

John M. Schiff, as an expense of the business, shall be entitled to receive interest at the rate of ——— percent per annum from December 31, 1932, payable semiannually on June 30 and December 31 in each year, upon the value of his New York Stock Exchange seat, which value shall be taken at the last price paid for a New York Stock Exchange seat in the year preceding the year for which interest is computed. By contributing the use of his membership in the New York Stock Exchange, John M. Schiff agrees that insofar as it may be necessary for the protection of the creditors of the partnership said membership may be treated as an asset of the partnership.

IV. The partnership shall take over all the assets and assume all the liabilities and commitments of the predecessor firm as of the close of business December 31, 1932.

V. The net profits of the partnership shall be shared by and between the partners in the following proportions: ———

If, instead of net profits, there shall be a net loss in any year, such net loss shall be borne by the partners in the same proportion in which they are entitled to share in the net profits, except that neither ——— nor ———, shall be liable for any share of such net loss, and what would otherwise be their respective shares of such net loss, shall be borne by ——— and ———, who shall be jointly and severally liable therefor, but who as between themselves shall bear such net loss in the proportion that their respective interests in the net profits of the partnership for such year bear to their aggregate interest in such net profits: *And provided further*, That as between themselves, ——— and ——— shall be jointly and severally liable for the aggregate amount of such net loss which the two of them shall be obligated to bear as above, and ——— and ——— shall be obligated to bear as above, and ——— and ——— shall be jointly and severally liable for the aggregate amount of such net loss which the two of them shall be obligated to bear as above. The above-named partners who are liable for net losses further guarantee to each of the following-named partners that his interest in the net profits, as specified in this article V, shall be not less than the following-named amounts in each year, that is to say, ———, which amounts each of said partners shall be entitled to draw in equal monthly installments in each year. Such guaranty shall be joint and several, but as between the partners making the same shall be borne in the same proportion in which they shall bear net losses as hereinabove set forth.

VI. All questions concerning the course of business of the partnership and the transactions which it shall undertake shall be determined, if possible, by unanimous action of the partners, but in case of disagreement such questions shall be determined by a vote of a majority of ———, ———, and ———. No partner shall, without the written consent thereto of the other partners, directly or indirectly speculate or be interested in speculation in stocks or any other article whatsoever. No partner shall directly or indirectly make investments in any securities of which a majority of said ———, ———, and ——— shall disapprove, and in case of such disapproval, such investments shall be promptly disposed of by such partner. No partner shall, without the written consent thereto of the other partners, use the name of the partnership, except in the business of the partnership, or become surety, or, for the accommodation of another, incur any liability either in the name of the partnership or in his individual name. No partner shall borrow or take to his own use any securities or property of the partnership.

VII. In the event of the death or withdrawal or termination of the interest of any partner or partners, the partnership shall be continued by the remaining partners without further action on their part, unless and until terminated as in article IX hereof provided. The interest of any deceased partner shall remain until the December 31, next succeeding his death, up to which time his executors or administrators or other legal representatives (hereinafter referred

to as personal representatives) shall be entitled to the same share of profits, and shall bear the same share of losses, as would have been received or borne by him had he survived; *Provided*, That if such partner shall die on December 31 of any year his interest shall terminate on that date. Upon the termination of the interest of any partner, his interest in the profits and his responsibility, if any, for losses shall be allocated by the unanimous action, if possible, of the surviving or remaining partners, but in case of disagreement, such allocation shall be made by the vote of a majority of _____, _____, _____, and _____. The same procedure shall be followed in case any interest in profits or responsibility for losses arising from the reduction of the interest of any partner or otherwise, is to be allocated.

VIII. In the event of the death of any partner, the survivors shall value the assets of the partnership as of the December 31 next succeeding his death, or if he shall die on a December 31, as of such December 31, at the fair market value thereof at that time according to their judgment. Pursuant to the practice that has prevailed since the beginning of the business, no value shall be included for good will, nor for the right to use the name of the partnership. The parties have entire confidence that a valuation by the survivors, in case of the decease of a partner, will be fairly made, and for reasons which are satisfactory to the parties they regard it as to their interest that the survivors shall make such valuation. The survivors shall make such valuation notwithstanding their interest and notwithstanding that one or more of them may be executor or administrators of the deceased partner. On the basis of such valuation, the interest of the deceased partner shall be ascertained and settled. In case at the time of his death any partner shall be indebted to the firm, the amount of such indebtedness, with interest, shall be taken into account as a set-off and deducted in ascertaining and settling the interest of such deceased partner. In case of the death of a partner, the survivors shall furnish to his personal representatives a statement of the amount of the interest of his estate in the partnership on the basis of such valuation, and the same shall be accepted by the personal representatives of the deceased partner, and without examination of the books of account of the partnership except by such of the personal representatives of the deceased partner, if any, as may happen to be partners. The parties enjoin upon their personal representatives the observance of this provision, which is made for mutual benefit.

In case of the death of a partner the survivors shall (except as herein otherwise provided) have 6 months succeeding such December 31 in which to pay his interest in the capital and profits of the partnership as the same shall have been ascertained. The survivors may at their option pay the whole or any part of the amount due from time to time during such 6 months. Interest upon all unpaid amounts shall run at the rate of _____ percent per annum from such December 31. The survivors may at their option, to be exercised by 30 days' written notice given not later than such December 31, or if such partner shall have died between December 1 and December 31, inclusive, of any year, not later than 30 days after such death, turn over to the personal representatives of a deceased partner; and the personal representatives of a deceased partner may at their option, to be exercised by like notice, require delivery of (in each case at valuations to be fixed as hereinbefore provided) an amount of any or all securities or loans belonging to the partnership (certificates of interest therein in cases where suitable subdivision cannot be made), not, however, greater in the case of any security or loan than the proportion of his obligation for losses, if any, of the business, even though the same may exceed the amount due him on capital and profit accounts: *And provided further*, That so long as the firm or any successor which has assumed its obligations shall exist the surviving partners shall, and they hereby agree that they will, in disposing of such securities and loans as shall remain to them, make a similar disposition of those which shall come to the representatives of the deceased partner, if such personal representatives so desire; that is to say, they shall treat all alike.

If such securities and loans, either or both, shall be subject to any syndicate agreement or other agreement to which the partnership with other persons shall be a party, which affect such securities or loans, the proportion therein of such deceased partner so to be turned over to his personal representatives, shall remain subject to such agreement. The surviving partners shall have said period of 6 months, however, in which to turn over the securities and loans to be received by the personal representatives of a deceased partner and may turn over the same from time to time during that period. If the

amount of securities and loans which shall come to the personal representatives of the deceased partner as hereinbefore provided shall exceed the amount due him on partnership account, such personal representatives shall pay such surviving partners the amount of such excess, and they shall have 6 months from such December 31 within which to do so, and during that 6 months they may at any time and from time to time make payments on account. Interest on all unpaid amounts at the expiration of such 6 months shall run at the rate of _____ percent per annum. The right to deliver securities shall not apply to any partner not contributing capital to the firm, nor shall the right to require such delivery apply to any such partner unless there shall have been a net profit for the year. All of the foregoing provisions of this article VIII shall be applicable to a case of a partner whose interest in the partnership is terminated by withdrawal, dissolution, or in any other manner.

The term "survivors" as used herein shall mean surviving or remaining partners, as the case may be. It is expected that all action required on the part of the survivors hereunder will be taken by unanimous vote but in case of disagreement, such action shall be taken by the vote of a majority of _____, _____, and _____, or the survivors of such four partners.

IX. The right to use the name Kuhn, Loeb & Co., and to use the books and records and the place of business of the partnership shall be confined to _____, _____, _____, _____, _____, and _____. Such right shall continue in said five partners so long as they are partners in the partnership, or in any partnership succeeding it, and shall cease as to any one of said five partners who shall for any reason cease to be a partner in the partnership or in any partnership succeeding it.

It is hoped and expected that any action involving the exercise of the rights and privileges reserved to the partners named in this article as having the right to use the name Kuhn, Loeb & Co., will be by unanimous agreement of said partners, but in case there should be disagreement, such action shall be determined by a majority vote of _____, _____, _____, as long as they are partners in the partnership. If in the case of death or of other incapacity of any of the partners named in this article, there shall not at any time any action is proposed to be taken under this article be a partner living who shall be entitled to cast the vote as stated above of such _____ the personal representatives of the partner who shall have last represented such _____ shall be entitled to designate any partner of the partnership to cast the vote to which _____ would otherwise be entitled under this article. Any action so taken by a majority vote shall for all purposes be deemed to be the unanimous action of said partners.

On December 31 of any year, having given, on or before November 1 of such year, notice in writing to the other partners, such of said partners named in this article as shall then have the right to use the name Kuhn, Loeb & Co., or a majority of them voting as hereinbefore provided, shall have the right to dissolve the partnership and after such dissolution, with the consent of such of said partners named in this article as shall then have the right to use the name Kuhn, Loeb & Co., or a majority of them voting as hereinbefore provided, one or more of the partners of the dissolved partnership shall have the right to form a new partnership, corporation, or association under the name Kuhn, Loeb & Co., with or without other partners or stockholders, subject, however, to the conditions hereinabove provided.

On December 31 in any year, having given, on or before November 30 of such year, notice in writing to the other partners, such of said partners named in this article as shall then have the right to use the name Kuhn, Loeb & Co., or a majority of them voting as hereinbefore provided, shall have the right to admit an additional partner or partners into the partnership and to determine the proportions in which the net profits of the partnership shall thereafter be shared and the net losses borne by and between the partners: *Provided*, That if any such notice is given, any partner not wishing to remain in the partnership may withdraw from the partnership on December 31 of such year by giving at least 2 weeks' notice in writing to all the other partners.

Notwithstanding any other provisions of this agreement, on December 31 of any year, the interest of any partner in the partnership may be terminated by notice in writing given to him on or before November 1 of such year by such of said partners named in this article as shall then have the right to use the name Kuhn, Loeb & Co., or a majority of them voting as hereinbefore provided.

X. On December 31 of any year, having given on or before October 1 of such year, notice in writing to the other partners (except in the particular case hereinabove in the fourth paragraph of article IX referred to providing for two weeks' notice of withdrawal), any partner may withdraw from the partnership.

XI. If any partner shall withdraw from the partnership, or if the interest of any partner is terminated, or if the partnership shall be dissolved, and after such dissolution and with the consent aforesaid, a new partnership, corporation, or association shall be formed as hereinbefore provided, each partner so withdrawing or whose interest is terminated, and each partner who shall not be a member of the new partnership or a stockholder of the corporation or association so to be formed, covenants and agrees that he will not, for a period of 3 years thereafter, conduct, or in any way become interested directly or indirectly (either individually, as a member of a partnership, or as an officer of, or through an active interest in, a corporation or association), in, or in the vicinity of, the city of New York, in a business similar to that which has been conducted, or similar to that which under these articles of copartnership shall be conducted, by the partnership of Kuhn, Loeb & Co.; but this provision may be waived in writing at any time, as to any partner, wholly or in part, by the partners named in article IX hereof who shall at the time of such waiver have the right to use the name Kuhn, Loeb & Co., or a majority of them voting as in said article IX provided. In case of the dissolution of the partnership and the continuation of the business thereof by a new partnership, corporation, or association in accordance with the provisions of this article XI, the liquidation of the interest of the partner or partners of the dissolved partnership who do not become members of the new partnership, or stockholders of the corporation or association so to be formed, shall be conducted by the remaining partners in accordance with the provisions of the article VIII hereof.

XII. In case the partnership is dissolved and its business is not continued by a new partnership, corporation, or association, the business shall be liquidated by such partner or partners as shall be selected by a majority or _____, _____, _____, and _____, any of whom may themselves be selected, and upon such terms and conditions not inconsistent with this agreement and for such compensation to said liquidating partner or partners as such majority may determine. Interest at the rate of _____ percent per annum shall continue upon capital and other moneys of partners until the same shall be actually paid. The distribution among the partners or the personal representatives of a deceased partner shall be in proportionate shares and in monthly installments as the business shall be liquidated.

In case any vote or other action on the part of _____, _____, _____, and _____ shall be required by the provisions of articles VI, VIII, or this article XII of this agreement, and _____ and/or _____ shall have died or for any reason be incapacitated from voting or acting, _____ may vote or act in the place of _____ and _____ may vote or act in the place of _____ and the then executors or personal representatives of _____ or _____, respectively, may designate any partner to so vote or act in his place.

XIII. Should differences arise among the partners or with a partner withdrawing from the partnership or with a partner whose interest is terminated or with the personal representatives of a deceased partner with respect to the dissolution of the partnership, or the payment of the interest of a deceased or withdrawing partner or of a partner whose interest is terminated or the delivery of securities or loans, or other matters growing out of the partnership, the same shall be settled by arbitration as follows: Either party to such differences may select an arbitrator, and in writing notify the other party of such selection. Within 5 days after receipt thereof, the other party may select an arbitrator and give written notice thereof to the first party. The determination of the arbitrator first chosen, unless another shall be so selected, and, in such case, the determination of the two thus chosen or, in the event of their disagreement, of two out of three consisting of such two and a third to be agreed upon in writing by them, shall be final and conclusive. If such two first chosen arbitrators cannot in such event of disagreement agree upon a third arbitrator within 10 days after such disagreement, the third arbitrator shall be appointed at the request of either of such two arbitrators by the senior judge of the United States Circuit Court of Appeals for the Second Circuit.

For the purposes of this agreement any notice to be given to any of the partners shall be sufficiently given if delivered to him personally in writing or

sent by registered mail addressed to him in care of Kuhn, Loeb & Co., 52 William Street, New York City.

XIV. Every position of trustee or director of a financial or business corporation or association or of membership in a reorganization committee, and every other position having relations to financial or other business enterprises, which may be held by any of the partners, shall be held by him, as between the partners, on behalf of the partnership. Each partner hereby severally agrees that he will relinquish any such position at any time upon a demand of a majority of _____, _____, _____, and _____.

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 4

QUESTION NO. 14

Kuhn, Loeb & Co. balance sheet, Dec. 31, 1927

Cash on hand and in banks.....	\$1, 904, 952. 28
Call loans secured by stock-exchange collateral.....	60, 825, 000. 00
Time loans secured by stock-exchange collateral.....	1, 150, 000. 00
All other loans.....	6, 478, 136. 67
Accounts receivable.....	16, 457, 667. 76
State and municipal bonds.....	2, 931, 668. 91
Other bonds and stocks.....	7, 427, 202. 40
New York Stock Exchange membership.....	70, 000. 00
Total.....	97, 244, 628. 02
Capital.....	20, 000, 000. 00
Deposits.....	69, 449, 016. 08
Accounts payable.....	7, 795, 611. 94
Total.....	97, 244, 628. 02

Kuhn, Loeb & Co. balance sheet Dec. 31, 1928

Cash on hand and in banks.....	\$747, 157. 81
Call loans secured by stock-exchange collateral.....	46, 180, 000. 00
All other loans.....	2, 077, 670. 01
Accounts receivable.....	6, 455, 582. 74
State and municipal bonds.....	15, 859, 779. 25
Other bonds and stocks.....	15, 043, 781. 10
Total.....	86, 363, 970. 91
Capital.....	20, 000, 000. 00
Deposits.....	58, 821, 113. 02
Accounts payable.....	7, 542, 857. 89
Total.....	86, 363, 970. 91

Kuhn, Loeb & Co. balance sheet, Dec. 31, 1929

Cash on hand and in banks.....	\$1, 999, 739. 30
Call loans secured by stock-exchange collateral.....	39, 350, 000. 00
Time loans secured by stock-exchange collateral.....	10, 000, 000. 00
All other loans.....	8, 634, 640. 82
Accounts receivable.....	10, 796, 770. 75
State and municipal bonds.....	27, 080, 026. 22
Other bonds and stocks.....	22, 540, 926. 69
Total.....	120, 402, 103. 78
Capital.....	25, 000, 000. 00
Deposits.....	88, 549, 766. 13
Accounts payable.....	6, 852, 337. 65
Total.....	120, 402, 103. 78

Kuhn, Loeb & Co. balance sheet, Dec. 31, 1930

Cash on hand and in banks.....	\$3,435,565.80
Call loans secured by stock-exchange collateral.....	8,725,000.00
All other loans.....	9,339,298.61
Accounts receivable.....	9,012,002.35
U.S. Government certificates of indebtedness.....	9,146,956.00
State and municipal bonds.....	24,403,922.07
Other bonds and stocks.....	21,093,007.69
Total	85,155,752.52
Capital.....	25,000,000.00
Deposits.....	57,032,847.08
Accounts payable.....	3,122,905.44
Total	85,155,752.52

Kuhn, Loeb & Co. balance sheet, Dec. 31, 1931

Cash on hand and in banks.....	\$16,295,242.63
Call loans secured by stock-exchange collateral.....	300,000.00
All other loans.....	8,378,314.21
Accounts receivable.....	777,409.31
U.S. Government Treasury bills and certificates.....	24,919,859.72
State and municipal bonds.....	9,953,051.25
Other bonds and stocks.....	6,350,968.34
Total	66,974,845.46
Capital.....	21,250,000.00
Deposits.....	29,118,918.20
Accounts payable.....	16,605,927.26
Total	66,974,845.46

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT 5

QUESTION 14

European Merchant Banking Co., Ltd., London, balance sheet as at December 31, 1927

ASSETS

	£	s.	d.
Cash in hand.....	89	14	5
Investments (quoted stocks at market prices ruling at Dec. 31, 1927. Unquoted stocks as valued by the managing directors).....	111,826	8	6
Sundry debtors and debit balances:			
Foreign currency credit balances.....	316	12	7
Stockbrokers' accounts (in respect of securities sold for future settlement).....	42,573	3	0
Loans, advances, and amounts due from clients.....	2,882	3	7
Syndicate participations at cost.....	61,917	19	8
Sundry debit balances.....	1,534	18	1
Total	109,224	16	11
Preliminary expenses.....	3,667	19	8
Profit and loss account (loss for the 9 months ended Dec. 31, 1927).....	7,501	10	11
Total	232,310	10	5

LIABILITIES

Capital:

	£	s.	d.
Authorized:			
5,000 management shares of £1 each	5,000	0	0
300,000 ordinary shares of £1 each	300,000	0	0
Issued:			
5,000 management shares of £1 each, fully paid	5,000	0	0
300,000 ordinary shares of £1 each, 5 shillings paid	75,000	0	0
Total	80,000	0	0

Sundry creditors and credit balances:

Westminster Bank, Ltd., overdraft	8,073	19	0
Stockbrokers' accounts (in respect of securities purchased for future settlement)	5,504	5	1
Sundry accounts	138,732	6	4
Total	152,310	10	5

Grand total 232,310 10 5

NOTE.—Contingent liabilities at December 31, 1927, in respect of: (1) Partly paid investments held, £437 10s. 0d., (2) Options outstanding, £16,500.

European Merchant Banking Co., Ltd., London, balance sheet as at Dec. 31, 1928

ASSETS

	£	s.	d.
Cash at bankers	8,088	7	9
Loans at call	125,000	0	0
Investments	77,680	6	1
Participations	6,418	8	3
Profit and loss account ¹	1,953	2	11
Debtors	4,470	2	9
Stockbrokers	16,808	13	1
Sundry suspense accounts, income tax, etc. (mostly recoverable)	1,501	7	7
Formation expense account	3,667	19	8
Office decoration account	5,041	3	10
Total	250,629	11	11

LIABILITIES

Capital account	80,000	0	0
Creditors	169,850	12	8
Sundry suspense accounts	778	19	3
Total	250,629	11	11

European Merchant Banking Co., Ltd., London, balance sheet as at December 31, 1929

ASSETS

	£	s.	d.
Cash at bankers	9,519	15	3
Loans at call	90,000	0	0
Investments	65,207	3	2
Participations	8,966	2	3
Stockbrokers' account	12,617	8	8
Debtors	6,992	18	3
Sundry suspense accounts, income tax, etc.	413	17	11
Formation expense account	3,667	19	8

¹ After allowing for the loss of £7,501 10s. 11d. carried forward from 1927.

	£	s.	d.
Office decorations account.....	4,850	9	4
Profit and loss account.....	32,360	10	2
Total	234,596	4	8

LIABILITIES

Capital account.....	80,000	0	0
Creditors.....	152,364	4	11
Sundry suspense accounts.....	2,231	19	9
Total	234,596	4	8

European Merchant Banking Co., Ltd., London, balance sheet as at Dec. 31, 1930

ASSETS

	£	s.	d.
Cash at bank.....	7,477	15	11
Money on short notice.....	40,000	0	0
Sundry debtors and outstandings:			
Foreign currency balances.....	126	9	6
Stockbrokers' accounts in respect of securities sold for future settlement.....	2,562	16	6
Loans, advances and amounts due from clients.....	5,221	16	9
Sundry debtors and outstandings.....	1,232	7	11
Total	9,143	10	8
Office decorations, furniture, and fittings at cost, less depreciation			
Per last balance sheet.....	4,850	9	4
Less: Amount written off.....	4,850	9	4
Preliminary expenses at cost, less amount written off:			
Per last balance sheet.....	3,667	19	8
Less: Amount written off.....	3,667	19	8
Profit and loss account:			
Balance at debit, Dec. 31, 1929.....	32,360	10	2
Add:			
Loss for the year ended Dec. 31, 1929.....	24,159	19	5
Office decorations, furniture and fittings, amount written off.....	4,850	9	4
Preliminary expenses written off.....	3,667	19	8
Total	65,038	18	7
Grand total	121,660	5	2

LIABILITIES

Capital:			
Authorized:			
5,000 management shares of £1.....	5,000	0	0
300,000 ordinary shares of £1 each.....	300,000	0	0
Total	305,000	0	0
Issued:			
5,000 management shares of £1 each, fully paid.....	5,000	0	0
300,000 ordinary shares of £1 each, 7s. paid.....	105,000	0	0
Total	110,000	0	0

Sundry creditors:

	£	s.	d.
Stockholders' accounts in respect of securities purchased for future settlement.....	207	1	1
Deposit and current accounts.....	9,941	13	5
Sundry creditors.....	1,511	10	8
Total	11,600	5	2
Total	121,660	5	2

NOTE.—The unpaid accrued cumulative preferential dividend on the management shares at December 31, 1930, amounted to £750.

European Merchant Banking Co., Ltd., London, liquidator's statement of account from Jan. 1 to Dec. 30, 1931

To assets realized:

	£	s.	d.
Cash at bankers.....	7,477	15	11
Cash at call.....	40,000	0	0
Foreign currency balances.....	126	9	6
Stockbrokers' accounts.....	2,562	16	6
Loans, advances, and amounts due from clients.....	5,221	16	9
Sundry debtors.....	1,232	7	11
Total	56,621	6	7
To net amount realized, brought down.....	44,961	1	5
To directors' fees received.....	193	16	6
To interest received.....	197	18	2
To sundry receipts.....	9	15	1
To dividends and other amounts collected on behalf of clients.....	1,841	9	11
Total	47,204	1	1

By liabilities discharged:

Stockbrokers.....	207	1	1
Deposit and current accounts.....	99,941	13	5
Sundry creditors.....	1,511	10	8
Sundry net amount realized carried down.....	44,961	1	5
Total	56,621	6	7
By legal charges.....	252	0	1
By postage, telephone calls, lighting and sundry expenses.....	33	13	5
By income tax.....	50	4	0
By liquidator's remuneration.....	525	0	0
By amounts paid to, or on behalf of, clients.....	1,841	9	11
By payments authorized by extraordinary general meeting on 2d April, 1931:			
Gordon Leith.....	34,000		
Harold Wooding.....	4,500		
	38,500		
By balance, available for distribution among members, carried down.....	6,001	13	8
Total	47,204	1	1

STOCK EXCHANGE PRACTICES

WEDNESDAY, JUNE 28, 1933

UNITED STATES SENATE,
SUBCOMMITTEE OF THE COMMITTEE
ON BANKING AND CURRENCY,
Washington, D.C.

The subcommittee met, pursuant to adjournment on yesterday, at 10 a.m. in the caucus room of the Senate Office Building, Senator Duncan U. Fletcher presiding.

Present: Senators Fletcher (chairman), Barkley, Goldsborough, Townsend, and Steiwer.

Present also: Ferdinand Pecora, counsel to the committee; Julius Silver and David Saperstein, associate counsel to the committee; and Frank J. Meehan, chief statistician to the committee; Carl A. de Gersdorff, Rober T. Swaine, and M. T. Moore, counsel for Kuhn, Loeb & Co.

The CHAIRMAN. The subcommittee will come to order. We will proceed with our hearings. Mr. Pecora, you may go ahead.

TESTIMONY OF BENJAMIN J. BUTTENWIESER, A MEMBER OF THE FIRM OF KUHN, LOEB & CO.—Resumed

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Buttenwieser, in the course of your testimony yesterday afternoon you stated in answer to a question that was addressed to you by the chairman of this committee that—

They—

Meaning the representatives of the Chilean Government—

wrote us a letter stating that it was impossible for them to live up to the payments under their guarantees. The whole subject was covered in the text of the Chilean moratorium law of July 1931.

That answer of yours appears at page 188 of the stenographic minutes of the hearing of yesterday. Have you that letter with you, or a copy thereof?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Mr. Pecora, it wasn't a letter. They were telegrams and letters. Yes, sir; I have those.

Mr. PECORA. Can you produce them readily?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir. And, Mr. Pecora, I should like to point out that this was in July of 1931.

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. And the default only occurred, as you appreciate, 6 years after the issue which we have been discussing.

Mr. PECORA. That is, the first issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. After the first issue; yes.

Mr. PECORA. And some 2 years after the last one?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Correct, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Which was in 1929?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Right. Do you want me to read that letter?

Mr. PECORA. If you will.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Would you like to see one of them first, to see if it is the one?

Mr. PECORA. Let me see the file of correspondence.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. All right.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. I think you have those, Mr. Pecora. Your examiners have seen all those.

Mr. PECORA. All right. Now, one of the letters submitted to me by the witness reads as follows—and, Mr. Chairman, if there is no objection I will read it into the record.

The CHAIRMAN. All right.

Mr. PECORA. It is on the letterhead of the Republic of Chile, Minister of Finances, Santiago, December 2, 1922, and is addressed to Messrs. Kuhn, Loeb & Co., New York:

I beg to acknowledge receipt of your letter dated October 19, 1932, in which certain protests are expressed against the failure of the services on the loans issued through the mediation of your bank. In this regard I write to declare that in view of the enormous decline of the exportation of Chilean products of every kind has deprived the nation of the possibility to dispose of foreign exchange in order to attend to the services on the foreign obligations with you. The undersigned hopes as soon as the decline in world prices permits of an improvement of the foreign commerce of Chile the creditor will be in a position to resume service on its foreign obligations.

Then he says "I remain", and so forth, and signs his name as Minister of Finances. Now, Mr. Buttenwieser, let me ask you what study was made, if any, of the financial condition or status of the Mortgage Bank of Chile prior to the time when your firm agreed, with the Guaranty Co., to underwrite the first issue of \$20,000,000 of these bonds?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. We made a careful study of its past record.

Mr. PECORA. That is a characterization. Tell us what you really did.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. We noted that it had a 70-year record of performance where the maximum losses over a period of 10 years preceding this issue had been \$40,000; that their securities in the home market sold as well or better than government securities. And in addition to that, as I stated on yesterday, we insisted upon having and placed great reliance on the guarantee of the Republic of Chile endorsed on the bonds.

Mr. PECORA. What study, if any, did you make of the appraisal basis upon which this Mortgage Bank of Chile made its mortgage loans?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. We could not make any study of the appraisal value. We could, of course, rely on the statements contained in that prospectus and confirmed in the report of the Department of Commerce that the bank had handled its affairs—well, I should rather quote the exact text than to rely on my memory, but I think the words were—I have them right here and will refer to them—

Had conducted its affairs with uniform safety and success.

Mr. PECORA. Well, that is the statement embodied in the letter by the Chilean Ambassador, isn't it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It is taken from a report of a special agent of the Bureau of Foreign and Domestic Commerce of the Department of Commerce of the United States.

Mr. PECORA. Well, is there anything in that letter or in that report which informed you of the appraisal basis of the mortgage loans made by this mortgage bank of Chile?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It states that—

It makes only first-mortgage loans. The loans are made on a conservative basis, and the risk is greatly diversified.

Mr. PECORA. Is that included in that report?

Mr. BUTTENWEISER. I think substantially that sense is embodied in that report. But I am quoting now from the letter again, and it says—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). Have you got the report itself?

Mr. BUTTENWEISER. Yes, sir. I am continuing from this prospectus—

The aggregate appraised improved value of the properties mortgaged as security for these loans amounted to more than four times the amount of the loans.

Which is just what they had always told us, that the loans were made approximately up to 25 percent of the appraised improved value of the property. But I want to stress again that we placed the greatest reliance, of course, on the unconditional guaranty of the Republic of Chile endorsed on the bonds.

Mr. PECORA. Did you place a greater degree of reliance upon that guaranty than you did upon the security of the mortgage loans made by the bank?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I would say that we relied on both.

Mr. PECORA. Which was the principal inducing factor, the guarantee of the Government or the security behind those bonds, the security consisting of the mortgage loans, or the loans secured by mortgages, I mean?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It is impossible to differentiate what the degree was between the two.

Mr. PECORA. The fact of the matter is, that you did make some differentiation in view of the fact, as testified to here on yesterday, that you would not have underwritten the bond issue on the security of the mortgage bonds themselves, but you insisted on a Government guarantee.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recall that, in a communication which was put into the record on yesterday that passed between your firm and your representatives in Chile, attention was called, among other things, to the lack of capital on the part of the Mortgage Bank of Chile?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That was to Louis Dreyfus & Co. in Paris, when we were first discussing the loan.

Mr. PECORA. That is right.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

The CHAIRMAN. Let me ask you a question right there: Did you consider those mortgages made by the bank and which they held, probably a trustee being somewhere, as security for those bonds?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir. All loans made by the Mortgage Bank of Chile are security for all of these obligations.

The CHAIRMAN. Why cannot the bondholders go after that security?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Because there is at present a moratorium in effect in Chile. It was put into effect toward the end of July of 1931, and it is still in effect.

Mr. PECORA. When did the first default occur on any of those issues?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. After that moratorium.

The CHAIRMAN. Did you make any investigation as to the public debts in Chile? You must have regarded that as necessary, to have the government guarantee of those bonds looked into. Do you remember what the public debt of Chile was at that time?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes; and we stated that in the prospectus:

'The debt of the Republic and all other obligations guaranteed by it aggregate about \$250,000,000 at that time.'

The CHAIRMAN. At the time of the first loan?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. In 1925; yes, sir.

The CHAIRMAN. How much is that total?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It is \$250,000,000.

The CHAIRMAN. Has that debt been increased since?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. That \$250,000,000 indebtedness was, of course, exclusive of the \$90,000,000 bond issues that you floated?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Certainly. The debt I gave was in 1925.

Mr. PECORA. So that between 1925 and 1929 your firm and the Guaranty Co. of New York jointly floated bond issues exceeding one third of the preexisting total indebtedness of Chile?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is quite correct.

Mr. PECORA. Was not a study made of any balance sheet of the Republic of Chile prior to your acceptance of the first issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I know of no balance sheet of any government.

Mr. PECORA. Well, you know what I mean by that.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. We made a careful study of the trade figures of Chile which, after all, are the most important factor surrounding the external debt of any country.

Mr. PECORA. Now, those trade reports informed you, didn't they, that the principal export of Chile was nitrates?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. And copper.

Mr. PECORA. Yes; and copper.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. But nitrates more than copper, isn't that a fact?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I haven't those figures in my memory, Mr. Pecora. I do not know which is the principal of the two. And, of course, it would depend upon the world price of each of those commodities before we could determine which formed the major portion of those exports. But the balance of trade was very favorable and had been very favorable as far back as 1900. I believe I stated, and I am relying on my memory now, that there were only 3 years between 1900 and 1924 when Chile had not had a substantial favorable trade balance.

Mr. PECORA. Didn't your study of those trade reports acquaint you with the fact, among other things, that with regard to this nitrate industry, which you admit was probably the principal export product, that Chile's natural nitrate product was coming more and more into competition with synthetic nitrates being manufactured by various European nations?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Not being an expert on nitrates it is very difficult for me to answer that question. But my understanding of it was, and still is, that one needed the natural nitrates to mix with synthetic nitrates. However, I repeat again that I am not an expert on nitrates and yet I believe the nitrate situation in Chile at that time was quite favorable. The fact that it had such a large favorable trade balance, and the fact that nitrate was one of its important items of export, must show that the nitrate situation in Chile was still very favorable.

Mr. PECORA. Are you familiar at all with the production of nitrates?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No; not at all.

Mr. PECORA. Is anybody in your firm familiar with that subject?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No. We have no one who would be conversant with a highly technical subject like nitrates.

Mr. PECORA. Well, apart from the technical character of the subject or the technical aspects of the subject, didn't you have some one in your personnel who was familiar with business conditions?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I think and hope we are all familiar—

Mr. PECORA (continuing). Sufficiently to enable you to determine whether or not the guarantee of the Chilean Government was a guarantee that could be lived up to if it wanted to live up to it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It had been lived up to for 100 years, and it seemed it would be lived up to. But I do not see how anyone could have foreseen in 1925 the world cataclysm that came in 1931, when, through an unprecedented drop in world commodity prices the Chilean export balance dropped. And I might point out that it so happened that the decline in most other countries, occurring as it did before that, showed that Chile was a sound country. Naturally, when the price of nitrates and copper dropped in the world markets, and in some cases below cost of production, that vitally reflected on the trade balance of Chile.

Mr. PECORA. When did the decline in the nitrate industry of Chile commence?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I could not tell you that definitely.

Mr. PECORA. Wasn't it around 1925 and 1926 markedly?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not think so. But, again, I would have to have that checked. My recollection is that it was at a later time, not in 1925.

Mr. PECORA. Have you any recollection at all of when it was, or have you any knowledge of when it was?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I have no direct knowledge. And once again I must emphasize that we took the composite favorable trade balance of Chile and relied on that. We relied on the unbroken record of Chile for, I believe, 100 years of living up to its every obligation; and that included the period of the World War, which was a trying time for all countries, including South American countries.

Mr. PECORA. You recognize the fact, don't you, that the American investing public looks to the issuing house's responsibility, or rather reputation and prestige, in buying its issues?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn testified quite at length about that on yesterday. He emphasized that several times, if you recall.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. And I fully subscribe to that.

Mr. PECORA. So that you feel it was the duty of the issuing house, of your house in this instance, to make a complete study of the situation in Chile before you underwrote its bonds with a view to disposing of them to the American investing public?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Correct. We thought we should, and we did.

Mr. PECORA. Now, I am trying to find out exactly what study you made of the internal economy of Chile with a view of fortifying your own minds as to the security of these bonds. So far you have told us, and the thing you have emphasized is that you looked to a long record of honoring its obligations by Chile, over a period of 70 or 80 years. Is that the sum and substance of the study you made?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Oh, no.

Mr. PECORA. What else did you do?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I stated that we looked at its trade figures as far back as 1900.

Mr. PECORA. Did you analyze its industrial situation?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I don't think we did that except—

Mr. PECORA (continuing). Beyond looking at the figures?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Don't the figures speak for themselves?

Mr. PECORA. In other words, you made no breakdown of the figures, did you?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I don't see how figures like that are susceptible of a break-down. The figures speak for themselves. There was a very favorable trade balance for 24 years preceding the time when we made the issue, and there was a very favorable trade balance for 6 years after we made the issue. Chile continued as long as world commodity prices were maintained, that is, until the very severe decline, an unprecedented decline came, Chile continued to have this very considerable favorable trade balance, which enabled it to meet its obligations.

Mr. PECORA. After you took the first issue in 1925 and before you underwrote the four subsequent issues, or any of them, did you make any study of the nitrate industry, not only of Chile but of the world?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I must repeat again, we relied upon the export balance of Chile, a part of which was nitrates, of course.

Mr. PECORA. Did you make any study of the nitrate industry throughout the world?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. As I recall, we made no specific study of the nitrate situation, though, of course, we realized.

Mr. PECORA. You realized what?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. We had not seen, as far as I can recall, any reason to change our opinion as to the favorable trade situation of Chile.

The CHAIRMAN. Did you make any examination into the political situation there?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. How can anyone make a study of the political situation of another country? And there I must repeat, we relied

on the advice of counsel as to the validity of the guarantee endorsed on those bonds.

The CHAIRMAN. Well, you knew of the tendency toward revolution down there. Did you make any study as to whether the revolutions were due to the depressed economic conditions or were the economic conditions due to the revolution?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Senator Fletcher, I hate to differ from you, but I do not think there was a tendency toward revolution in Chile. As I recall, that was one of the very few they have had down there. I would term it rather a liberal movement than a revolution.

The CHAIRMAN. It had one turnover just before the Government went in that guaranteed your issue here, and then there came this one, and I think they have had one or two since.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. This was all the same liberal movement, I believe.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Buttenwieser, will you look among your files and see if you can find a document entitled "Chile First Mortgage Bank Bonds"?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Could you read the first sentence of that again to see if I have the right one?

Mr. PECORA. It is:

The following memorandum outlines the political situation in Chile at the time of the negotiations for the First Mortgage Bank loan of 1925.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I have that before me.

Mr. PECORA. Well, now, I have what purports to be a copy of that, which was furnished to us by your firm. You follow me as I read from my copy of it, so that the record will get it in accordance with your copy. The memorandum proceeds to say as follows:

Chile has had a de facto government since the first week of September 1924, when military and navy officers formed a council and announced that they were going to take charge of public administration until certain reforms were effected. The cause of this movement was a general feeling of dissatisfaction with political and economic conditions of the country. The President and the House of Deputies represented the popular feeling, but the reactionary majority in the Senate had brought about a deadlock in administration.

Various ministers appointed by the President had been able to hold office for very short terms since their tenure was dependent upon congressional approval. The military council announced that upon the dissolution of the Congress preparations would be made to hold popular elections of delegates to a constituent assembly which would promulgate a new constitution, and then elections will be held in July of 1925. And there also will be an election for a new President. The first military council held power until in January of 1925 it was ousted by a similar council composed, however, of younger officers more in sympathy with general public opinion, meaning the middle classes and the proletariat as opposed to that of the old conservative vested interests. President Alesandro was then recalled from his "vacation" in Europe. Military councils have promulgated laws and decrees, and exercised all the functions of government. The Chilean Embassy says that the judiciary has recognized such laws and decrees as a part of the legal code. Of course questions have been raised as to the actual status of such measures, but in the meantime they have been effective. There is only one political event like this in the past Chilean history; in 1891 there was a short civil war caused by political differences. Afterward the currency issued by both sides was recognized, and there is no record of the abrogation of administrative measures of a general nature.

Now, before I read further from this memorandum I want to ask you who prepared the memorandum.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. This memorandum was shown to me yesterday, and I cannot tell you who prepared it.

Mr. PECORA. Well, it was shown to you as being one of the documents in your files with regard to these Chilean issues, was it not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Only yesterday, and I had to have it sent from New York, and I cannot tell you who prepared this memorandum. It was among the papers which were marked "preliminary papers." My belief is that this is a translation of papers which came from Chilean counsel. But I say again it is my belief, and I do not know, and of course my recollection cannot be so clear when going back 6 years, and—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). Is it your present belief that the first time your attention was ever called to this memorandum in your files was yesterday?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Oh, no. I believe I had seen it in 1925.

Mr. PECORA. Have you any recollection of knowing of the existence of this memorandum and familiarity with its contents prior to June 1925 when your firm participated in the flotation of the first \$20,000,000 issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not know that I saw it prior to June of 1925. I am certain I saw it in 1925, of course. And—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). Don't you know—

Mr. BUTTENWIESER (continuing). Pardon me. I believe it came from our Chilean counsel. And in connection with that I should like to read an excerpt from the opinion of our Chilean counsel on this subject, because it refreshes my belief that it was he who furnished it, because he goes into some detail.

Mr. PECORA. Well, I will come to that, and you will have every opportunity to present it.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. With your indulgence I could read it now, because it is right along that line.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It says [reading]:

VALIDITY OF THE BONDS

As I have already stated above, the Caja was duly authorized by its organic laws and regulations and by the decree laws of March 9 and June 15, 1925, to issue these bonds and the director of the treasury to sign the State guaranty in behalf of the Government.

It only remains to see whether these so-called "decree laws" are valid and binding upon the Republic of Chile.

I am decidedly of the opinion that they are. It is quite true that the matters of these decree laws are the subject of a law enacted in the form prescribed by our constitution, and that Congress having been dissolved, they can justly be qualified as unconstitutional; but as I pointed out to you in my telegraphic dispatches they are none the less valid and binding upon the Republic, as dictated by the only supreme authority of the country.

Decree law dated March 9, 1925, is shaped in the form adopted by the Government for the dictation of its resolutions of a general character; but decree dated June 15, 1925, was only dictated in the form of a simple decree, because it only refers to a particular case. I do not give, though, to this difference the least importance. It is simply a question of names. We have now a de facto Government which has assumed all the faculties; the constitution has been left aside as if it did not exist, while a new one is being drafted and prepared, to be adopted by the people by the means of a plebiscite, and all the Government resolutions, let them be called decree or decree laws, have the same bearing and binding force all through the Republic.

It is a well-known doctrine adopted by all the authorities on international law and confirmed by a uniform practice in the whole world that no State has

the right to qualify the resolutions or acts of governments of other States, provided they are not contrary to international laws and that any obligations contracted by such governments are perfectly valid and binding especially in regard to foreign parties acting bona fide.

This doctrine is accepted even in cases where there are two factions governing in certain parts of the territory of a nation; but doubtless it acquires more strength in a case like the case of Chile where there is but one single Government acting with the tacit consent of all the citizens of all the authorities and of all the armed forces.

A great number of decree laws have been dictated by the present Government and of the most varied description, and all of them have been respected by the citizens, by the authorities, and by the courts of justice.

New organization has been given to many branches of the public administration, many decree laws of a special character have been enacted, heavy taxes have been imposed; but every citizen considers himself bound to obey them.

If a de facto government should dictate a law granting some special concessions to private individuals without receiving a just compensation from them, it might be contended that they are null and void and therefore disavowed by a succeeding legal government; but in our case it is not the question of a concession or special favor accorded by the Government; it is a contract by whose fulfillment the country shall be highly benefited; it is an act in which both parties give as much as they receive; it creates reciprocal obligations, and unless trespassing over the clearest principles of morality nobody would ever dare to raise any doubt as to the perfect validity and binding force of your agreement with the Caja.

Furthermore, apart from the direct responsibility that this agreement imposes upon the Caja, I am strongly of the opinion that the State is also responsible for any acts of this institution, since, as I have already explained, it is an organ of the State, governed by State officials, controlled by the State controllers, and even if the Government had not placed its signature on the agreement and on the bond, it could never waive its responsibility derived from acts of its own institutions.

It seems to me idle to dwell any longer on this purely academic digression and I close this report by repeating once more that in my opinion the temporary bond issued by the Caja de Credito Hipotecario and with the endorsed guaranty signed by the director of the treasury and the definitive bonds to be issued in substitution for the temporary ones are, or shall be, perfectly valid documents in the hand of their holders of whatever citizenship or residence and are binding upon said Caja and upon the Republic of Chile in time of war as well as in time of peace, in accordance with their terms and with the provisions of the agreement signed in New York on the 25th of June 1925.

And subsequent de jure governments have recognized the validity of the guaranty, which has never been questioned.

Mr. PECORA. Well, I am not considering so much the naked validity of the guaranty as I am considering the question of actual physical or financial ability of the Government under the conditions which were existing at that time to live up to its guaranty. Now, in the advice from your counsel, Manuel Foster, which you have just read, there is contained this statement:

This doctrine is accepted even in cases where there are two factions governing in certain parts of the territory of a nation; but doubtless it acquires more strength in a case like the case of Chile where there is but one single government acting with the tacit consent of all the citizens of all the authorities and of all the armed forces.

Now, Mr. Buettenwieser, did it not appear from this memorandum that you were reminded of yesterday afternoon that the government that was in power in Chile at the time your firm underwrote this issue with the Guaranty Co. was a government established by force, at a time when the Congress had been dissolved, and when there was an election pending for the selection of delegates to what is called a constituent convention or assembly which was to formu-

late a new constitution? Could you say that that was the kind of government that was acting with the tacit consent of all the citizens?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The election was held. The Government was recognized as de jure shortly thereafter.

Mr. PECORA. Now, the election was not to be held until July 1925, according to this memorandum from which you read?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. The first issue of these bonds was made in June 1925?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. So that the election for delegates to a constituent assembly had not yet been held?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No.

Mr. PECORA. And there was no way of determining at that time what form of government would be established by the new constitution, was there?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. There was no way of determining it ahead of time; no. As I said before—

Mr. PECORA. There was no way of determining whether or not in the creation of a new government based upon a new constitution recognition would be given to this indebtedness or this guaranty of the Government, was there?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Under all principles of international law, I repeat again that our counsel advised us they would have to be recognized, and the fact remains they were recognized, and I reiterate they never were questioned. And interest and sinking fund on them was paid regularly until 6 years later, and there was never any connection between the validity of the guaranty of this Government and the nonpayment of interest.

Mr. PECORA. Does it not strike you that the advice your counsel was giving you was similar to the classical advice of the lawyer who advised his client in jail that they could not put him in jail, and the client said, "Well, here I am"?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not really follow the analogy, Mr. Pecora.

Senator BARKLEY. Does the present Chilean Government still recognize the validity of these issues?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Sir?

Senator BARKLEY. Does the present Government still recognize the validity of these issues?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Certainly. That letter which Mr. Pecora just read earlier from the Finance Minister of Chile recognized the validity of the bonds.

Senator BARKLEY. I do not recall the date. What date was that letter?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That was October 1932, I believe.

Mr. PECORA. December 1932.

The CHAIRMAN. Was this letter the latest expression that you had from the Government?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is the latest we have from the Chilean Government; yes, sir. That followed, of course, after our sending the protest to our State Department and having it returned.

Mr. PECORA. Now, the laws and decrees under which the de facto government was functioning were laws and decrees that were formulated by the military council, were they not, and not by any popular assembly or congress?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Formulated by the only authority that existed at the time in Chile.

Mr. PECORA. And that only authority was composed of this military council, was it not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Which was the governing council.

Mr. PECORA. It was a military council composed of military and naval officers, was it not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not know. The entire situation—

Mr. PECORA. You do not know. Does not the memorandum in your files inform you of that specifically? Does it not say, for instance, "Chile has had a de facto government since the first week of December 1924, when military and navy officers formed a council and announced that they were going to take charge of public administration until certain reforms were effected"? And does it not say further that, "The first military council held power until in January 1925 it was ousted by a similar council composed, however, of younger officers more in sympathy with general public opinion", and so forth?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir. That is why I answered I did not know whether this younger—this second council of which you spoke was all officers. But it may have been. And I do not see that it changes the situation any. This government had been in power under this council form for 9 months. The election was held shortly thereafter. The government was recognized. And no one has ever questioned the validity of the bonds.

Mr. PECORA. Did you not know that the first military council was ousted within 4 months by a second military council?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Again, there was a change in the council; correct, sir.

Mr. PECORA. In other words, there was a change in the personnel of what you are pleased to call the de facto government?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Which was more in sympathy with the general public opinion, meaning the will of the middle classes and the proletariat.

Mr. PECORA. Yes; and which continued to function under its own laws and decrees rather than under laws passed by a popular assembly or Congress?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. An election for which they were going to hold shortly thereafter.

Mr. PECORA. And the election for which was not to be held until after you took over the first issue of \$20,000,000?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct, sir. And I repeat again, we had the best of legal advice that the bonds and the guaranty would be legally binding. And while I realize of course one cannot judge by results, the fact is the validity of the bonds and the guaranty never has been questioned.

Mr. PECORA. Well, do you not inquire into something more than the mere naked validity? Do you not give some consideration to the practical question of financial ability to meet the obligations apart from the legal validity of the obligation?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Certainly we do. We separate the two. As I tried to say yesterday: The one is the legal aspect of it; the other is the economic aspect. We tried our best to assure ourselves on

both. We got the best advice we could on the legal side and we got the best information we could on the economic side.

Mr. PECORA. Now, on the economic side: Did you learn in your study of the economic side of the question that the railroads of Chile, which were owned by the Government, had been operating at a deficit in 1924?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I think I know of many places where the railroads had been operating at a deficit for several years.

Mr. PECORA. Well, we are talking about Chile now, where the railroads were government-owned, and hence could be regarded as a source of revenue with which the government could meet its obligation or guaranty. Did you know that, Mr. Buttenwieser?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I think I knew that; yes. But I again want to lay great stress on the composite picture, which was that Chile did have this very sizable trade balance which enabled it to meet all its obligations, contingent and direct, for 6 years after the issuance of these bonds.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know whether Chile had balanced its budget in 1924 or 1925?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not think it had. I might add I do not think there is any reason why one should not buy bonds of a government just because it has not balanced its budget.

Mr. PECORA. Well, the fact that it has not balanced its budget is not an argument in favor of the security of the bond, is it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No. But, on the other hand, I think there are—

Mr. PECORA. If anything it is an argument against it, is it not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I think you will agree, though, that there are very many prime securities—our own Government securities—which one should not hesitate in buying just because the Government has a very substantial deficit, and in Chile it did not have a substantial deficit.

Mr. PECORA. Did the fact that the nitrate industry began to show disturbances, marked disturbances, shortly after you took over the first issue in 1925, influence your judgment in taking over the second issue of \$20,000,000 in 1926?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not know that there was any marked falling off in that.

Mr. PECORA. Well, now, let us see. You have already testified that in one of the informative documents that you consulted in order to reach a determination as to whether or not you would take over these bond issues were reports of the United States Department of Commerce. Did you know what statement was made about the economic condition of Chile in the Commercial Year Book for the year 1926 that was issued by the United States Department of Commerce?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not know which particular statement you refer to, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. Well, this statement:

The principal factor in Chile's economic position during 1926 was the weakening demand for nitrate brought about by competition from European artificial fertilizers.

Did you ever come across that statement in the Year Book of the United States Department of Commerce for the year 1926?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I think it was down for the year 1926; then went up again. I believe I recall that statement; yes.

Mr. PECORA. You could not tell in 1926 if it was going up again, could you, any more than you could tell that, after it went up, it suffered a more serious decline?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No; I could only judge by the figures that we had, and the figures we had were that the favorable trade balance which had been \$77,000,000 in 1925 did drop to \$42,000,000 in 1926, but still left a very sizable favorable trade balance. And then in 1927, I might add, went up again to \$72,000,000. In 1928 it went up to—

Mr. PECORA. And what did it go down to after that?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. In 1928 it was up to \$92,000,000. And the following year, 1929, \$81,000,000. In 1930, which was the one time it became unfavorable, it was \$8,000,000, but in 1931 it became favorable again, \$26,000,000. And I might add it seems to have had even a favorable trade balance for the first 2 months of this year.

Mr. PECORA. Let me ask you: Who prepared the prospectus that accompanied the offering of the first issue of these bonds in 1925 to the American public?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The controller of the Mortgage Bank of Chile was up here at the time negotiating this loan. He prepared it, doubtless, in consultation with us.

Mr. PECORA. Well, you say "doubtless in consultation with us." Can you make any such statement unqualifiedly?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It is difficult for me to remember exactly, but I think we consulted with him as to the form of the prospectus certainly.

Mr. PECORA. Who actually wrote the prospectus that was put out to the public here?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. We all worked on it, that is, certain of us in consultation with the Mortgage Bank controller who was up here, in consultation probably with our lawyers. Several of us worked on it, I should say.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recall whether you worked on it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes; I think I worked on it.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recall whether any other associates of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or any of its partners as then existing worked on it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Oh, yes.

Mr. PECORA. Who?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No one of us would write a prospectus like that alone.

Mr. PECORA. Who sat around the composing board for this prospectus from the house of Kuhn, Loeb & Co.?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. My recollection is that Mr. Mortimer Schiff was consulted on it. My former associate, Mr. Leonard Keesing, who was at that time the head of the foreign department, and I. And no doubt various others. Those are the ones that I just recollect.

Mr. PECORA. Now, it was known to you at the time, I believe you stated, that at that time and for some years prior thereto the Chilean Government had not balanced its budget, but that its expenditures far exceeded its income. Was any mention made of that fact in the prospectus?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It did not far exceed it. And that budget included capital expenditures.

Mr. PECORA. Was any mention made in the prospectus of the fact that the Chilean Government for some years before that had not balanced its budget, but that its expenditures had exceeded its income?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. As I recall, there was no statement made of the budget of the Chilean Government in that circular.

Mr. PECORA. Do you not think the investing public here whom you sought to have purchase these bonds were entitled to that knowledge through the medium of your prospectus?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I must repeat again, Mr. Pecora, I think what is of far vaster importance in the ability of any government to meet its external obligations is its ability to remit those funds to the creditor country. Therefore, the favorable trade balance of Chile was the all-important factor in the ability of Chile to meet its obligations in external centers.

Mr. PECORA. I repeat, do you not think that the American investing public was entitled to know what you people knew, namely, that the Government of Chile, whose guaranty you relied upon more than you did upon any other factor, had not balanced its budget for a number of years prior to this issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It had not balanced its budget by a small amount for several years before that, which included, I repeat, capital outlays. And I might add that our own Government when it sells its obligations puts in no budget statement.

Mr. PECORA. I repeat again, do you not think that the American investing public was entitled to have the knowledge that you possessed when the circular or prospectus was given to the public in connection with the offering of this issue to it, to the effect that the Chilean Government had not balanced its budget for a number of years prior thereto?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No; the trade figures were more important, Mr. Pecora. And I might point out that when it had a favorable budget we did not put it in the prospectus either, which happened in later years.

Mr. PECORA. Now, when you talk about favorable trade balance you simply mean that the exports exceed in value the imports, do you not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Well, what bearing has that on the ability of the Government to meet its obligations? Exports are not the exports of the Government, but of individuals living under the Government, are they not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. A government, as I understand it, of a country which has a favorable trade balance is one whose people are therefore prosperous. Therefore it can raise funds in its own market which it remits to the foreign country where it owes its debts.

Mr. PECORA. What was the population of Chile at that time?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I haven't that figure in mind. I will try and get it.

Mr. PECORA. Around 4,000,000, was it not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I will take your figure. I do not just know.

Mr. PECORA. No; I do not want you to take my figure. I have not

made an exhaustive study of it, and I do not want you to trust to my defective knowledge.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I will be willing to bow to that, Mr. Pecora. I have not the figure before me. I do not know. I will take it for 4,000,000 for the purposes of discussion.

Senator BARKLEY. As a matter of fact, is it not true that until within the last 2 or 3 decades over large periods of our history there were unfavorable balances of trade?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Do you mean the United States?

Senator BARKLEY. The United States.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. If my memory serves me rightly we have had a favorable trade balance. That has been our great strength.

Senator BARKLEY. In the last 20 or 30 years, yes; but prior to that have we not had short periods in which we had unfavorable balances?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It is a little before my day, Senator.

Senator BARKLEY. Well, mine too.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I think that is probably true, and that is just the time we did borrow money abroad.

Senator BARKLEY. That is the point I want to get at; that we have not always had a favorable balance of trade since we were established as a nation 150 years ago.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. But it is a very comfortable feeling to have one.

Senator BARKLEY. I realize that. I am not certain that it always has a bearing upon the ability of the Government to pay its debts.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Well, the places where we borrowed our money when we had the unfavorable balance of which you spoke seemed to think it had a bearing because they loaned us the money. Europe loaned us vast amounts.

Senator BARKLEY. They loaned it to us when we had an unfavorable balance, too.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Well, I guess they thought as well of us as we do of ourselves.

Senator BARKLEY. For a long time after this Government was established we brought in more stuff than we shipped out.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Do you mean the United States Government?

Senator BARKLEY. Yes. We imported more than we exported. Yet the Government was able to borrow money. We did not have any occasion to borrow very much until the Civil War.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not know those figures, Senator Barkley. Of course, I would yield to your recollection on it, but I think it has been our proud boast that we have had a favorable trade balance for many years. I do not know how far back you would want to go.

Senator BARKLEY. But I mean we have not had it all during our history?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No; I should think not.

Mr. PECORA. Now, did you analyze these trade balances of Chile with a view of ascertaining the diversified character of its exports or what diversification there was in its exports?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I think we mentioned what the major exports were. I think we stated:

Chile is a mining and agricultural country. Its mineral products are largely raw materials for essential industries. Exports consist chiefly of nitrates and byproducts of the nitrate industry, copper, borax, wool, and a limited amount of agricultural products. The nitrate deposits are the only large natural deposits so far discovered in the world. The copper industry has been extensively developed, largely by American capital.

We stated quite clearly that copper and nitrates were the major factors of export. Mr. Pecora, I want to take this opportunity to compliment you on your memory. The population in Chile was about 4,000,000—3,753,000—in 1920. I would like to make public recognition of your excellent memory.

Mr. PECORA. No; I knew that when I was a schoolboy.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Well, you have got a very retentive memory then. Some one has called my attention to the fact that you do not look as though you were a schoolboy in 1920.

Mr. PECORA. Now, you have said in the course of your testimony heretofore, Mr. Buttenwieser, that this Caja or Mortgage Bank of Chile was only empowered or only made first-mortgage loans.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Against bonds which it issued.

Mr. PECORA. Now, as a matter of fact, was it not also empowered and did it not also make second-mortgage loans?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not think it made second-mortgage loans. And if it did it did not issue bonds against it. I tried to make quite clear yesterday that it issued its bonds only against first-mortgage loans that it made.

Mr. PECORA. Now, your prospectus contains this statement, does it not:

The Caja issues its bonds only against mortgages registered in its name. It makes only first-mortgage loans.

Does it contain that statement?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The 1925 prospectus?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir. Subsequent prospectuses, where it did issue notes against other things, changed that wording; that is, supplemented the wording.

Mr. PECORA. Have you in your files a report made by this gentleman who was formerly the manager of the foreign department of your firm, Mr. Leonard Keesing, dated June 4, 1926, in which reference is made to the kind of mortgage loans which were made by the Caja?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not know which memorandum you refer to, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. Well, I have given it to you by date—June 14, 1926.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is a year after this issue.

Mr. PECORA. Yes. And before the four subsequent issues.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Do you mean that part that says:

The Caja makes loans on first mortgages only, except, of course, temporarily when a loan is made by it to pay off the previous first mortgage, in which case the Caja temporarily obtains a second mortgage which becomes a first mortgage after the old first mortgage is repaid.

Is that what you mean?

Mr. PECORA. That is the memorandum I mean. Now, will you continue reading from the point where you stopped, from that memorandum?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER (reading):

There is one provision in the fundamental law of the Caja which has never been cleared up. This was discussed at the time of the last issue, but the point was not insisted upon, because we had the Government's guaranty.

Mr. PECORA. Do not read it so fast. I cannot follow you.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Shall I start over again, Mr. Pecora?

Mr. PECORA. Well, go ahead from the point where you left off.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER (continuing reading):

This provision is as follows:

"The Caja may loan on property already mortgaged, provided the loan does not exceed one half of the value in excess of prior liens."

Mr. PECORA. So the Caja may loan on second mortgage to an amount not exceeding 50 percent of the equity over and above an existing first mortgage?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That seems to be the case from this. But in that case it would not issue its bonds against such a loan.

Mr. PECORA. Was the public ever told that the Caja could make loans on second mortgage?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not think it did to an appreciable extent ever make second-mortgage loans. It may, however, as is stated here, temporarily, of course. But I do not think it made any substantial second-mortgage loans.

Mr. PECORA. No; it does not say that it may temporarily. The provision that you yourself read is this:

The Caja may loan on property already mortgaged, provided the loan does not exceed one half of the value in excess of prior liens.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Quite right. It says it may.

Mr. PECORA. That does not refer to temporary loans.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It says it may. But I repeat, I believe it was its practice not to.

Mr. PECORA. Well, was the American investing public informed that the Caja had the right to make loans on second mortgage?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I would have to look up not alone the prospectus but the listing applications and things like that. I do not know of my own memory whether it went in the prospectus or not.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know of your own memory whether or not the Caja actually made any of these second mortgages?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No; I do not know.

Mr. PECORA. You do not know. Were any steps taken to keep yourself informed currently as to the kind of mortgage loans the Caja was making?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes; against any bonds that it issued.

Mr. PECORA. Well, now, were these bonds issued against the mortgages or were they issued against the general credit of the bank?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Both.

Mr. PECORA. Where is the provision in the agreement controlling that?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It is the provision in the bond, the text of the bond, that the bond represents the full faith and credit of the Mortgage Bank protected by all its assets.

Mr. PECORA. That is just the point I am seeking to make. The obligation of the bond is merely to the effect—or the statement in the bond is to the effect that it is issued against the credit of the bank?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It is stipulated that they will not issue bonds except against a stipulated equal sum of mortgages.

Mr. PECORA. But without limiting it to first mortgages?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes; the bonds were limited to first mortgages.

Mr. PECORA. Show me the provision in the bond that was sold to the American investor to that effect.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. In answer to your question, Mr. Pecora, I would like to read this statement from the prospectus signed by the Ambassador of the Republic of Chile, which says:

The Caja issues its bonds only against mortgages registered in its name.

Then farther along it says:

The Caja is not permitted by law to have its bonds outstanding in excess of the mortgage loans against which they are issued.

Mr. PECORA. Well, that does not mean that the mortgages themselves are applicable to the liquidation of the bond, does it? It simply means that the bond is issued on the credit of the bank, fortified by the guaranty of the Government, does it not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. But it had to have that many first mortgages against any bonds that it issued.

Mr. PECORA. But a bondholder could not proceed to enforce those mortgage-loan obligations in order to receive payment of his bonds, could he?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. He could proceed against the Mortgage Bank.

Mr. PECORA. Yes?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. For all of its securities.

Mr. PECORA. Certainly.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. All of its assets.

Mr. PECORA. That is just the point I have been trying to make, Mr. Buttenwieser. Now, at what prices did the underwriting houses, namely, your firm and the Guaranty Co., take over this first issue of \$20,000,000 in 1925?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. At 93 percent.

Mr. PECORA. 93. At what price were they offered to the public?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. 97 $\frac{3}{8}$ percent.

Mr. PECORA. That was a spread of 4 $\frac{3}{8}$ percent to the bankers?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I want to make it quite clear there was a spread of 4 $\frac{5}{8}$ percent, because there was a one fourth of a percent interest gain in the purchase of those bonds at 93.

The CHAIRMAN. What rate of interest did it have?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Six and one half percent, this issue.

Mr. PECORA. And they matured in 1957?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is right; with, of course, a sinking fund. Senator TOWNSEND. What amount was set up for the sinking fund?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. A 1 percent approximately cumulative sinking fund, which is a sinking fund which will eat up a 6 $\frac{1}{2}$ percent—will mature a 6 $\frac{1}{2}$ -percent obligation in 32 years. It was so set up that the sinking fund would mature the entire loan by 1957.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Bittenwieser, what banking houses or firms participated in this original underwriting?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. In the original?

Mr. PECORA. Yes. And what was the extent of their respective participations?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The Guaranty Co., 45 percent; Lehman Bros., 10 percent; Kuhn, Loeb & Co., 45 percent.

Mr. PECORA. How were these bonds floated?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. They were issued by public offering.

Mr. PECORA. Well, were any groups formed between the original group and the selling to the public?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes; there was a syndicate and there was a selling group.

Mr. PECORA. Well, now, which came after the original group? The syndicate?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The syndicate.

Mr. PECORA. Who formed that syndicate?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The Guaranty Co. and ourselves.

Mr. PECORA. And who were invited to participate in that syndicate?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. A larger group of retailing houses which were regularly or habitually members of our usual syndicates.

Mr. PECORA. Have you got the names of the participants in that group or that syndicate?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. They would appear in the—no; not for 1925. I have not got that. I was going to say they would appear in your questionnaire there, but they do not. The 1925 group do not. You did not ask for that; so, of course, I did not bring it, but I can easily get it. Probably three or four hundred. I do not know.

Mr. PECORA. And they consisted of dealers?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Dealers throughout the country.

Mr. PECORA. And their names were taken from a list kept in your office?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. We have a list of—a relatively large list of names; that is, we think it is large—I think in comparison with most other houses a relatively small list—of dealers throughout the country located in various cities and centers where bonds are distributed.

Mr. PECORA. On what terms were the participants or members of this syndicate permitted to participate?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Pardon me; I have the letter here. [After referring to documents:] They purchased them from the originating group at $94\frac{1}{2}$ percent and interest.

Mr. PECORA. So that gave the original group, composed of yourself, Guaranty Co., and Lehman Bros., a point and a half profit—

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. Between the origination group and the syndicate?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No; that is not exactly the figure.

Mr. PECORA. Well, what is it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I think I can aid you in that. We bought it at 93. As I said, there was a quarter of a percent interest gain on it. That brought it down to $92\frac{3}{4}$. We paid a half a percent commission to Louis Dreyfus & Co., which brought it up to $93\frac{1}{4}$, and we sold it to the syndicate at $94\frac{1}{2}$, which left a spread of a point and a

quarter for the originating group which took the original commitment, from which expenses had to be deducted.

Mr. PECORA. Now, how did this syndicate pass on the bonds offered them to the public?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Through a selling group at 97 $\frac{3}{8}$ percent and allowed a selling commission of 1 $\frac{3}{4}$ percent.

Mr. PECORA. Who organized this syndicate?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. We organized it; the Guaranty Co. and we organized the syndicate.

Mr. PECORA. And who organized the selling group that came after the syndicate?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The Guaranty Co. and we organized it on behalf of the syndicate.

Mr. PECORA. Who managed the syndicate? Who managed the operations of the syndicate?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Kuhn, Loeb & Co.

Mr. PECORA. And who managed the operations of the selling group that came after the syndicate?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. As is customary, the syndicate managers managed the selling group on behalf of the syndicate.

Mr. PECORA. So that means that Kuhn, Loeb & Co. managed the operations of the selling group?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Correct, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And then the selling group is composed of a much larger group than the syndicate group, I assume?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Larger. How much larger it was I do not know.

Mr. PECORA. And they were scattered in various parts of the country?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Correct, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And it was the members of the selling group that passed the bonds on to the investing public; is that right?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is right.

Mr. PECORA. At 97%?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is right.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Battenwieser, why was it necessary to organize so many intermediate groups between the original group and the investing group, each group taking a profit?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The originating group, as was discussed yesterday, took the original commitment.

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. A very sizable commitment. It had to stand in the breach until all of the bonds were paid for. It was a larger commitment than one would want to carry comfortably, so naturally we would form a larger group to share that responsibility with us, although, of course, it does not one bit diminish your original commitment from the party from whom we bought the bonds.

Mr. PECORA. What I am trying to get at is this, Mr. Battenwieser: I am trying to find out the reason why the original group composed of yourselves, the Guaranty Co., and Lehman Bros. found it necessary to organize first a syndicate, composed of a large number of persons, and then after that to organize a selling group composed of a still larger number of persons, in order to dispose of these bonds to the investing public.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It is very analogous to an insurance company which spreads its risk. We had that original commitment of \$20,000,000, and we wanted to diversify that risk, although, I repeat, we had the original commitment, and then it being a new issue for this market, we wanted as diversified distribution as we could get, therefore we formed this larger selling group, which got its compensation for distributing the bonds.

Mr. PECORA. Why could not you form the larger selling group without the intervention of the syndicate between the original group and the selling group?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That would not spread the risk. The selling group merely sells for a commission, a selling commission.

Mr. PECORA. Are you speaking now of merely spreading the underwriting risk?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Then the original group or the underwriters which took over the issue at 93 from the Chilean bank was not assuming a risk that it wanted to carry all alone?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It continued to carry that risk. It merely tried to redistribute its risk, but it continued that original risk.

Mr. PECORA. When you say redistribute its risk, what you really mean is to try to get other shoulders in addition to its own shoulders to support that risk?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, that is correct.

Mr. PECORA. To sustain that risk?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct. Just like—I come back to the insurance analogy—if an insurance company writes a very large risk it likes to redistribute that among others who can share that risk with them.

Mr. PECORA. But the insurance company does not pass on the cost of the spreading of that risk to the insured, does it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I rather expect it does. I do not think the other insurance companies would take that risk for it for nothing.

Mr. PECORA. Don't you know, as a matter of fact, that the premium paid by the insured is a fixed figure based upon tables in the office of the insurer irrespective of the subsequent spreading of the risk by the original insurer?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Surely. So was the spread here, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. No; each group took a different profit, didn't it? Didn't each group take an independent profit?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It is again the insurance analogy. If the insurance company wanted to make the entire premium it would take the entire risk itself. If we had wanted to take that entire risk ourselves for the larger margin, we could have, but we did not think it was a prudent risk to take.

Mr. PECORA. The price at which you offered these bonds to the public was not a fixed actuarial figure, was it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No, sir.

Mr. PECORA. It is one that is arbitrarily determined by the underwriters, by the issuers, isn't it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not want to quibble over words, Mr. Pecora, of course. It is not arbitrarily fixed. It is fixed commensurate with what similar securities are selling for in the investment market.

Mr. PECORA. And that figure is determined by the original group, isn't it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That figure is determined by—you mean the price at which securities are selling in the market?

Mr. PECORA. No; the price at which it is offered to the public.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes; that is determined by the originating group.

Mr. PECORA. In the analogy that you draw of an insurance company distributing its risk among other companies the premium paid by the insured is a fixed figure, isn't it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not know, but I rather think insurance rates vary according to companies. I know it seems that way to me when I pay my insurance premiums.

Mr. PECORA. But the premium, the figure is a fixed figure, fixed by each company for its own business?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. So that persons coming within certain age classifications pay the same rate of premium, don't they?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. In each company.

Mr. PECORA. Yes. Now, in a case of the distribution of bonds by the original group, an originating group, to the investing public, you say that the originators seek to distribute among others' shoulders the risk which they have assumed in the underwriting?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes; if they so desire, yes.

Mr. PECORA. And in order to enable them to do that they organize syndicates or groups intermediate between themselves and the investing public?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. And in this instance there were two such groups organized, one after the other?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No; there was only one such underwriting group. The other is a selling group.

Mr. PECORA. There are two such groups organized at the instance of the underwriters, first the syndicate, then the selling group?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, but the selling group does not take any risk. The selling group merely sells for a commission. It takes no obligation, no commitment.

The CHAIRMAN. The point, as I understood it, is, why didn't you as the original underwriters distribute these securities yourself without these intervening agencies?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. We ourselves, Senator Fletcher, are not retail distributors. As I think we brought out yesterday, we maintain no selling organization at all. We are what they call wholesalers.

Mr. PECORA. You sell through these distributing agencies?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is right.

Mr. PECORA. Throughout the country?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And you have a list in your office and you invite them to participate in the organization of selling groups from time to time, don't you?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. In other words, they are part of your machinery for selling bonds to the public, aren't they?

Mr. BUTTENWEISER. They are part of everyone's selling machinery.

Mr. PECORA. Well, I am now inquiring into yours.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Senator ADAMS. This selling group, they actually buy the bonds from you, don't they? They do not merely have them on consignment? That is, if they should fail to sell them they cannot return them to you or to the syndicate?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No. Your description is quite accurate. The day that they offer the bonds if some customer, Jones or Smith, comes to them and says, "I want 10 bonds of that issue," they order from us 10 bonds. The moment those bonds are allotted to them against that subscription then they are responsible for them.

Senator ADAMS. So to that extent they are carrying that much of the risk; in other words, of disposing of that part of the bonds? They have bought the bonds; they are no longer acting for you?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No.

Senator ADAMS. They are the owners of those bonds, and it is up to them to dispose of them if they wish?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. After they have ordered them from us, predicated on the sale to some one of their clients, then they are committed to us; yes.

Senator ADAMS. That is, the distributing group, yourself, send out telegrams offering to them an allotment of so much and they will say yes or no to that?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No; not the distributing group. To the syndicate we offer a certain underwriting, and if they accept they are committed for that share of the underwriting. To the distributors we send another letter or telegram saying these bonds are for sale, and we send along a description of them. Then if their clients, their retail clients, want to purchase those bonds they go to their distributor, from whom they have been purchasing bonds, or through whom, and say "We would like to buy a certain number of those bonds." That distributor in turn communicates with us and says "We would like so many bonds", sending in an order to cover what all of their clients together have ordered. As soon as they have given us that order and we have confirmed to them the number of bonds that we can give them against that order, then they are committed.

Senator ADAMS. But this ultimate distributor sells no bonds that he does not own, that he has not asked for and contracted finally to pay you or pay the syndicate for?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. Now, will you describe, step by step, the history, in chronological order, of the underwriting, syndicating, distribution, and selling of this first issue of bonds to the public? Let me assume that we are all schoolboys and we want to get some elementary education into this financing operation.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I hesitate to be the "little child leading", but I will try my best to give you a picture of how this is done.

The first step is to sign your contract with the borrower. That is the originating group. It may be one; in this case it was two.

Mr. PECORA. Three; wasn't it? Lehman Bros. were given a sub-sequent participation?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. They were not co-contractors. They participated with us on the original terms, but they were not co-contractors. The Guaranty Co. and ourselves were the original contractors, and we, of course when I say we I mean the Guaranty Co. and ourselves—remained responsible to the party from whom we purchased those bonds, in this case the Mortgage Bank, throughout the entire operation.

Mr. PECORA. When you say you remained responsible, let me ask you, did you discharge that responsibility by turning over to the Chilean bank the price at which you took over these bonds, which was 93?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And when did you do that?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. At the request of the Mortgage Bank, which wanted those funds over a period of time, we paid them four million six hundred—and wherever I say “we” I mean, of course, the Guaranty Co. and ourselves—paid them \$4,650,000 on July 1, \$4,650,000 on July 10, \$9,300,000 on July 29, all of these dates 1925. That is a total of \$18,600,000, which is the purchase price at 93 percent for 20,000,000 bonds, and I repeat again the installment purchase was done at their request, and that accounts for that one quarter of a percent interest gain to which I called your attention.

Mr. PECORA. All right. Now when was the syndicate organized?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Then after we had signed the contract with the Mortgage—

Mr. PECORA. Give us the date of that event.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. June 25, 1925.

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. On the evening of June 25, 1925 we would send out the syndicate letters, a letter seeking to form a syndicate to share this risk with us.

Mr. PECORA. And when was the organization of that syndicate completed?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Only when the parties to whom we had sent such invitations accepted them and took the commitment.

Mr. PECORA. When did that happen?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That may have been the next day or in the course of the next 2 days. I cannot tell you just when all of them accepted the invitation to join.

Mr. PECORA. Then the syndicate was organized within a few days after June 25?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes. But after the signing of the contract.

Mr. PECORA. After the signing of the contract, which was on June 25?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Right, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And did the members of that syndicate pay to the originating group any moneys representing the extent of their participation in the syndicate?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No. In this case they did not have to, because the bonds were purchased by the members of this selling group. So they were all paid for by the selling group. But they stood committed to.

Mr. PECORA. They stood committed. They merely assumed a risk but did not part with a dollar, is that right?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. In that particular case, that is correct.

Mr. PECORA. Yes. Now, when was the selling group formed?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. At the same time we would send out invitations to this larger list to which you have referred inviting them to sell these bonds to offer them to the public.

Mr. PECORA. I understood you to say in answer to certain questions that were put to you by Senator Adams that the members of the selling group were the ones who bought the bonds and then they in turn retailed them to the public. Did I misunderstand your testimony?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No; I do not think you misunderstood it. Maybe I did not make it quite clear. What I meant to show was that they purchased no bonds; at least, I assume they purchased no bonds, until they had clients who wanted to purchase those bonds from them. In other words, the exact situation is this, Mr. Pecora: If you would want to purchase some bonds you would go to the dealer through whom you normally purchase bonds and say, "I have seen this issue advertised today; I would like to buy some of those bonds", whatever the number may be. I do not want to estimate your fortune. And the dealers in turn would communicate with us and say, "We want a certain number of those bonds." Then when we had his order we would confirm to him an allotment of a certain percentage against his subscription.

Mr. PECORA. When was this selling group definitely organized and their sales to them confirmed?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The sales to them confirmed the next day, if they succeeded in selling all those bonds for the syndicate the next day.

Mr. PECORA. What was the date when your selling group was fully organized, completed, and allocations made to their respective members?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The next day.

Mr. PECORA. The next day from what?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I believe they were all sold the next day.

Mr. PECORA. The day following which date?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That would be June 26.

Mr. PECORA. So that, at the time the original group who were the underwriters organized the syndicate, they also organized the selling group and got their commitments on their orders. Is that right?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct, except I want to make it quite clear that the underwriting risk had not been definitely consummated at the time we sent out these invitations to the selling group to sell these bonds. In other words, the two go out simultaneously, but there is no assurance to the originators that the syndicate to whom it wants to distribute will accept that responsibility. Does that make it quite clear, Mr. Pecora?

Mr. PECORA. No; I still do not understand when the originating group were informed by the various persons whom they invited into the selling group that the entire issue had been or would be absorbed by the selling group members. Do you see what I am after?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That depends on the public response to the offering. In other words, if the offering is quickly absorbed by the investing public, then the orders come in relatively quickly during

the first day of the offering, and you are enabled that evening to make your allotments against the subscriptions which you have received from the many members of this selling group.

Mr. PECORA. When do you receive finally all the subscriptions from the members of the selling group?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. On the 26th of June in this particular case.

Mr. PECORA. On the 26th day of June. So that within 24 hours after the originators committed themselves to this entire issue or agreed to pay, in other words, \$18,600,000 for these \$20,000,000 par value of bonds, it had definite commitments from many members of the selling group to the effect that the entire issue would be absorbed by them?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct. In this particular instance it is correct.

Mr. PECORA. I am speaking of this particular instance.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. There have been many cases, you appreciate, of course, where the public response has not always been that satisfactory, and then we had—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). I want to see the history of this particular issue.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Quite right, sir.

The CHAIRMAN. Then you had in your possession remittances covering the entire amount that you transmitted to the Mortgage Bank?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. We had the commitment, Senator Fletcher, yes, but we did not have the money.

Mr. PECORA. Well, you had succeeded in 24 hours' time after you had assumed the risk by the original underwriting in passing on that risk or distributing it to the syndicate and to this selling group?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct. We distributed, but we did not have the money, and I repeat again, and I cannot overemphasize it, we were still committed for \$18,600,000, and we did not have that money in our till from these distributors for quite some days.

Mr. PECORA. And when did you get the remittances from the distributors for the issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. July 15.

Mr. PECORA. July 15. That is when payment was finally made for all the issue, to the entire issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is when the distributors paid for the entire issue; yes, sir.

Senator STEIWER. You received it, then, in one payment?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The bonds we sold we sold to distributors, and they paid for them in full.

Senator STEIWER. Did they pay all in one payment?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. All made in one payment.

Senator STEIWER. On one day?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. On one day. The delivery of the bonds is made simultaneously.

Mr. PECORA. Now, these dealers who composed in the main the distributing group, the selling group, were all persons of known responsibility to you, were they not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes; we esteemed them as being responsible.

Mr. PECORA. Persons with whom you had dealt on similar matters on many prior occasions?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. You felt that their responsibility would be respected and would be lived up to by them to you?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. We try to be scrupulously careful to do business only with people that we think are thoroughly responsible.

Mr. PECORA. And with regard to this particular issue that responsibility, I suppose, was lived up to fully by the members of the selling group?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It was.

Mr. PECORA. So that you received all remittances covering the entire issue or the purchase of the entire issue from the members of the selling group by July 15?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Now, what profits accrued to the members of the original group from this issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The original profit?

Mr. PECORA. All the profits that accrued to Kuhn, Loeb & Co. for their participation in this underwriting?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Our profit in this issue was \$111,207.24.

Mr. PECORA. Is that the entire profit?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That was our entire profit in that originating group; yes, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. No; I mean the entire profit that you got, not only as a member of the originating group but as a member and manager of the syndicate and as a member and manager of the distributing group.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Pardon me a minute. I will have to see what further profit we may have made. [After referring to documents.] Mr. Pecora, I am sorry, I haven't any data to show whether or not we had any participation in that syndicate. I haven't that figure with me, but I can readily have it looked up and will let you know. It could not have been anything sizable, and my associate, Mr. Stewart, says his recollection is there was no further profit to us in that transaction. Subject to our checking that, I would like to make that my reply. If there is any correction, I will see that you get it this afternoon or tomorrow morning if it can be determined.

Mr. PECORA. Is that net or gross, this figure of \$111,207.24?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is net.

Mr. PECORA. What was the gross?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. You appreciate, of course, when I say "net", that does not include any allowance for our overhead expense of our doing business, which was described to you yesterday.

Mr. PECORA. What was the gross profit?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. In this particular transaction the gross and the net to the originating group was exactly the same.

Mr. PECORA. Now, I assume from the fact that the Guaranty Co.'s interest in the originating group was equivalent to yours that they obtained a similar profit?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And that Lehman Bros. obtained a proportionate profit for their 10 percent interest in the originating group?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. What were the total profits to the originating group?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. \$247,127.20, which you will see is just about that 1¼ percent that you and I arrived at a little earlier.

Mr. PECORA. And that was the profit accruing to the members of the original group or the underwriters from this transaction in which they assumed a risk, which they succeeded in passing on in its entirety in 24 hours to hundreds of dealers throughout the country. Is that a fair statement?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. In this case it is correct, Mr. Pecora, but I must point out again in many other cases that was not our experience, to our regret, and I can refer again, for instance, to the case where the *Lusitania* sank, where we were committed for the issue and where it did not go off quite so smoothly and untrammelled as this did.

Mr. PECORA. In these various bond issues that you underwrite you do not often have *Lusitania* sinkings?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Fortunately not, but there are other events which might equally affect the ability to distribute that risk and to sell the bonds.

Mr. PECORA. Have you the contract that was entered into between the underwriters and the Mortgage Bank of Chile?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. You mean between the original group?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Will you produce it, please, so I may offer it in evidence?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Mr. Pecora, here again, this is the only copy I have.

Mr. PECORA. The reporter will be very careful to return it to you.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. This is not a signed copy.

Mr. PECORA. That is all right. It embodies all the terms and provisions of the agreement.

I offer this in evidence and ask that it be spread on the record. The CHAIRMAN. It may be marked and spread on the record.

(Document entitled "Agreement Between Caja de Credito Hipotecario and Kuhn, Loeb & Co., and Guaranty Co. of New York", dated June 25, 1925, was thereupon designated "Committee Exhibit 10, June 28, 1933", and appears on page 1154.)

Mr. PECORA. Now, in order that we may get a second lesson in this, Mr. Buttenwieser—

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I appreciate the flattering term.

Mr. PECORA. Let me ask you what your custom was with respect to allocating or offering these bonds to the selling group, the distributors in other words. Was it the custom for the underwriters or originators to offer more in amount than they actually had to sell?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No. You would offer the original issue. You would state quite clearly that you had an issue of such and such proportion to sell, and then you would hopefully await their orders.

Mr. PECORA. Well, as a matter of fact, wasn't it customary and isn't it customary for the original group to confirm sales to an amount in excess of the actual amount that is to be offered?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Very often the case.

Mr. PECORA. Was it done in this instance?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. What was the extent of that excess in percentage, or in dollars and cents?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. In amount \$539,000 of principal amount of bonds.

Mr. PECORA. Why is that done, Mr. Buttenwieser?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is done because a great many people feel that they want to purchase those securities. They very often over-estimate their ability to pay for them, or for some reason or other they change their mind between the time they order the bonds and the time the time comes to pay for them. To use the analogy of the retail department store, you cannot very well give it back. You can sell it in the market.

Therefore, in the case of a new issue, until it becomes thoroughly absorbed, the syndicate or the selling group, or whatever it may be, must be standing ready to purchase any bonds from customers who want to, so to speak, return their goods from a sale; and, therefore, in order to be able to repurchase these bonds and give them a proper market till they find their ultimate investment status, you must stand ready to purchase them.

Mr. PECORA. That is, you must stand ready to stabilize or give support to the market during the period of time that is usually fixed for disposing of the issues to the investing public?

Mr. KAHN. May I for a moment "butt" in, Mr. Pecora? Have I your permission?

Mr. PECORA. Certainly.

TESTIMONY OF OTTO H. KAHN, A PARTNER OF KUHN, LOEB & CO.—Resumed

Mr. KAHN. Our experience is that when we have 20 million bonds for sale we have, as a matter of fact, 21 millions or 21½ millions. It is not guessing. It is based upon many years of experience, that there are perhaps 5 percent, perhaps 2½ percent, perhaps 3 percent, of the subscribers who take more than they really mean to keep. They either take it more as I might go into a department store and buy something that appeals to me, and when I got home my wife would say to me, "What on earth did you buy that for? There isn't a bit of use for it." I say, "Well, I will try and get rid of it again." And I go to the department store, and they say, "No; no giving back here." So I will try and sell it.

And there are a number of distributors—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). Mr. Kahn, isn't that a rather unfortunate analogy, in view of the growing practice of the department stores to make refunds?

Mr. KAHN. As far as I know that practice does not prevail. It has never prevailed in my instance.

Mr. PECORA. Then you do not shop in the same stores as Mrs. Pecora does. [Laughter.]

Mr. KAHN. And furthermore, Mr. Pecora, there are a number of distributors—and again I want to emphasize I am not now guessing; I am speaking of what a long experience has taught us to be a definite and reliable fact—there are a number of distributors who, either because their optimism is greater than their placing power or

because they want to make a good impression, subscribe for rather more than they can get rid of.

Now there are people also—1928 and 1926 have shown that lamentably—there are people also who might be persuaded by a plausible distributor that they had better buy some of those bonds, and when the man has thought it over for a day or two and the date of payment comes along he says, "Well, I better get out of that if I can."

Now, I think it is the duty of the originator to see to it as far as he reasonably can and as far as his means permit him without "busting" himself in the process, to see to it, not that a market is made for the time that the ordinary distribution takes, but that a market is made for a reasonable length of time for the people at large, including distributors, to make up their minds whether these bonds are really definitely placed.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, what is that reasonable period of time usually?

Mr. KAHN. Pardon?

Mr. PECORA. What is the extent of that reasonable period of time?

Mr. KAHN. Well, it varies, Mr. Pecora, depending upon the nature of the bond.

Mr. PECORA. Well, in the average case?

Mr. KAHN. If you have a bond which has a ready, current, well-established market, a kind of bond that savings banks and insurance companies and conservative investors have been trained to buy, it would not take very long, I should say a month or two.

Mr. PECORA. It is usually a period that does not exceed 60 days, isn't it?

Mr. KAHN. No; not usually; except that sometimes the banker of his own volition, or the originator, go beyond that period. But that depends upon the circumstances of the case. If it is a bond that is unusually difficult to place it may take a little longer, but ordinarily you are right in saying it is about 60 days.

Now, a bond is not like a stock that shoots up like weeds. A bond is a tender plant. It has got to be nursed. It has got to be watered. I do not mean "watered" in the sense of stock. [Laughter.] I do not mean "watered" in the sense the word is used as applied to "stock watering." But the bond is in no way like a stock, especially in this country. In this country we are naturally—well, I don't want to say speculators, but we prefer something that has got life and movement to it rather than something which brings 4 percent or 5 percent or 3 percent, and we cannot get any more. We are optimists. We like to take a chance on these things that we have bought turning out well. Therefore, a stock is a very different thing to deal with from a bond.

Senator ADAMS. Mr. Kahn, if one of your optimistic distributors overestimates his capacity, do you let him simply rescind to that extent or do you simply take it off his hands at the market?

Mr. KAHN. We take it off his hands at the market.

Senator ADAMS. So that if the market has gone down, why, he suffers a loss to that extent?

Mr. KAHN. I should say in the market, rather. We put orders to a reasonable extent in the market which are to enable people that have overbought to get out without extra loss or without a

loss of any more than the commission that they have counted on. And we feel that this is the duty of a banker, both toward the public and toward the corporation whose credit he is called upon to protect. A very small offering of bonds for which there is no market may depreciate the price to an almost unbelievable extent. I have seen four or five bonds hanging over the market when there was no purchaser, by accident, by chance, and those four or five bonds depreciated the market by several percent until someone came along and bought them. We do not think that is the right thing to do, and we think it is part of our duty and part of our syndicate's duty to put our money in at our own risk and expense and the syndicate's risk and expense and say, "Well, now, we will see that decent protection is offered to those who bought the bonds."

As Mr. Pecora says, it does not take more than 60 days, but it may take more.

Senator ADAMS. Mr. Pecora, I was going to tell you of an instance that happened in one of the committee hearings. There was an issue of stock brought out and they wanted to protect it, and in order to do so they bought back more stock than the total issue. That came out in one of these hearings.

Mr. KAHN. The very reverse of the system—if I may go on one minute longer; I will only be 1 minute—that prevails in England, and I think ours is a far more ethical system and a much more protective system. In England when you issue a bond the issuing house sends around a broker and that broker forms an underwriting group who get a certain, definite percentage for the underwriting. After the issue is made, whether it was a success or it was no success, the issuing house says, "Well, now my job is done. What is not taken goes to the so-called 'underwriters' and they can sell it at any price they please, and if in selling it that depreciates the price down 2 percent or 3 percent, it is not my job to stand in the breach, it is not my job to do anything to protect the market." The public understands very well that they take the risk of the underwriters being "stuck." We do not want the public to be stuck any more than we can help it.

TESTIMONY OF BENJAMIN J. BUTTENWIESER, A MEMBER OF THE FIRM OF KUHN, LOEB & CO.—Resumed

The CHAIRMAN. Is the contract there, for a subsequent issue of these bonds, similar to the contract that you put in evidence?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. I am not sure that the witness understood what may have been in your mind, Mr. Chairman. Are you referring to the four subsequent issues?

The CHAIRMAN. Yes; and are those contracts the same as this that has been put in here?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Similar; yes.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Buttenwieser, this period of time that was referred to by Mr. Kahn in the statement he just made, is fixed in advance by the originating group with the selling group, is it not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct, sir.

Mr. PECORA. What was the period of time that was fixed in connection with this first Chilean issue of 1925?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Sixty days.

Mr. PECORA. It was 60 days?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And during that time the originating group virtually took a short position on those bonds to the extent of from 2½ to 5 percent of the total issue, didn't it, under this plan that has been described by Mr. Kahn?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Mr. Pecora, just so that we may keep this technically correct, the syndicate.

Mr. PECORA. The syndicate did, which was organized by the originating group.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And it included the members of the originating group.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir; that is correct, made an overallotment of just slightly more than 2½ percent.

Mr. PECORA. Have you with you here a copy or the form of the offering letter to the selling group from the members of the originating group in connection with this issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Kindly produce it for the record.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Here it is.

Mr. PECORA. I thank you. Mr. Chairman, I offer this in evidence, and ask that it may be spread on the record of the subcommittee's hearing.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted and placed in the record.

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 11

[Confidential]

NEW YORK, June 25, 1925.

DEAR SIR: We have agreed to purchase \$20,000,000, principal amount, guaranteed sinking fund 6½ percent gold bonds, due June 30, 1957, of the Mortgage Bank of Chile (caja de Credito Hipotecario, Chile), unconditionally guaranteed as to principal and interest by endorsement by the Republic of Chile, as more fully described in the enclosed copy of a letter from His Excellency, the Hon. Beltran Mathiou, Ambassador of Extraordinary and Plenipotentiary of the Republic of Chile to the United States.

We are offering these bonds for subscription, subject to allotment at 97½ percent and accrued interest, payable in New York against delivery of interim certificates, deliverable if, when, and as issued and received by us. At the offering price, the bonds will yield 6.70 percent to maturity.

We shall allow you a commission of 1¾ percent on all bonds allotted to you, of which you may realow not exceeding one-fourth percent to bankers, brokers, financial institutions, and insurance companies. This 1¾ percent commission will be payable about August 24, 1925, and will not be paid as to any bonds that before that date may have been repurchased by us in the market at or below the offering price mentioned above. The right is reserved to close the subscription at any time without notice, to reject any application, to allot a smaller amount than applied for, and to make allotments in our uncontrolled discretion.

The allotment of any bonds to you is subject to the agreement on your part that you will not, for a period of 60 days from the date hereof, directly or indirectly sell or offer any of such bonds for sale below the terms authorized in this letter and is subject to the approval by our counsel of all legal proceedings in connection with the issuance and guaranty of the bonds.

Yours very truly,

KUHN, LOEB & Co.,
GUARANTY CO. OF NEW YORK,
By KUHN, LOEB & Co.

Mr. PECORA. Now, in this letter which has been marked "Committee Exhibit No. 11" of this date, the concluding paragraph reads as follows:

The allotment of any bonds to you is subject to the agreement on your part that you will not, for a period of 60 days from the date hereof, directly or indirectly sell or offer any of such bonds for sale below the terms authorized in this letter and is subject to the approval by our counsel of all legal proceedings in connection with the issuance and guaranty of the bonds.

Why are the dealers, or rather the members of the selling group, restricted to such a condition?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Obviously, we pay them, or the syndicate pays them a selling commission to sell them to ultimate investors, not at the offering price, not immediately to sell them in the market right back to us, for that we wouldn't have to pay a selling commission;

Mr. PECORA. In your experience isn't it a fact that practically upon the expiration or termination of this 60-day period there is a depreciation in the market value of bonds?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No, not as a general rule. I wouldn't say that that was the general thing. That depends, of course, on market conditions at the time that the selling group period happens to expire. In some cases, if the price, if the market for that type of security has depreciated, then of course that price would depreciate. If, on the other hand, the investment rating, the investment market, for bonds of that category has risen these bonds will equally rise.

Mr. PECORA. Now, will these dealers sell to investors these bonds at the offering price of $97\frac{3}{8}$ and accrued interest within the 60-day period, and will any of those investors or purchasers within that 60-day period throw back their bonds on the market, and if so, doesn't the originating group stand by to absorb those bonds at $97\frac{3}{8}$ in the market?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes; and that is just the operation that Mr. Kahn sought to describe to you.

Mr. PECORA. So that one of the main purposes, if not the main purpose, of this operation is to support the market at the offering price for the 60-day period in order to enable distributors or the selling group to sell to the public at the offering price and not less, isn't that it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Well, the ultimate investors will absorb the new offering.

Mr. PECORA. Now, do you know what happened to the market immediately after the expiration of the 60-day period in this particular instance?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I have those figures here.

Mr. PECORA. What have you on that score?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The market for these bonds temporarily, at the expiration of the syndicate or selling group, did decline somewhat.

Mr. PECORA. To what figure?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. To about 95, and very shortly thereafter, or I wouldn't say very shortly but thereafter, they recovered their price again. But I want to make clear this, too, which I forgot to mention—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). Wait a minute. You said 95.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. 94½.

Mr. PECORA. Didn't the market the week of August 29, which was practically upon the expiration of this 60-day period, go down to 94 for these bonds?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I haven't that figure, but it may be correct. Ninety-four and a half is the low figure I have, but it may well have been 94. I want to make clear, though, where you said something about pegging, that we do not stand ready to buy or take them all at 97⅞, or whatever was the issue price.

Mr. PECORA. I didn't use the word "peg." But I was going to ask you if that wasn't the process of pegging the market.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No. Because one does not necessarily keep the price that you say, or I may say is pegged at any level. You try to absorb the bonds which seem to be hanging over the market.

Mr. PECORA. Well, isn't that a species of pegging the market at the market price until all of the bonds are disposed of?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. We do not maintain a fixed bid, which is what I understand from hearsay, because we do not indulge in it, to be a pegging operation.

Mr. PECORA. Why did you use that word yourself, then—that word "pegging"?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It is a colloquialism.

Mr. PECORA. It is a pretty accurate description of the operation, isn't it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I shouldn't say that colloquialism and accuracy are synonymous.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know of any word better than pegging or a term that is more descriptive of the operation?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes; supporting.

Mr. PECORA. You wouldn't say, of course, rigging?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No, sir.

Mr. PECORA. It is too harsh.

Mr. KAHN. I would use the words "aiding the market" to absorb the bonds which have been offered to investors until they are definitely placed in the hands of bona fide investors. That is the purpose of a bond issue as distinguished from a stock issue. As to a stock issue you don't care where it is placed. It will find its level somehow by and by. A bond issue is not placed to our satisfaction or to the satisfaction of the corporation until it has found its level in the hands of ultimate investors. And that sometimes takes a little time, and sometimes you have overestimated the market value which is properly placeable upon those bonds, and sometimes conditions change.

We are not pegging, we are not supporting; we are trying to aid the distribution of bonds, which is our duty as agents for the corporation, and it is our duty toward investors to help them, if need be, to get those bonds placed that for one reason or another they might try to get rid of. If you were to peg them, they would always be 97⅞. We use our judgment as to what is a fair level as to which we should come to the rescue of the market.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Buttenwieser, as a matter of fact, during the 60-day life of this selling group wasn't the range of those bonds in the market from 97⅞ to 97½?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. So that, call it supporting the market or pegging the market or aiding the market or what you will, the fact is that during the 60-day period the operation of pegging or supporting or aiding resulted in keeping the price in the market for those bonds at the offering price, $97\frac{3}{8}$, or a little above that. That was the actual result, wasn't it, in this case?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That was the actual result in this instance, but I am quite certain we were not the people who bought them above that issue price.

The CHAIRMAN. Did they ever go above that price?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Do you mean in subsequent years, Senator Fletcher?

The CHAIRMAN. At any time.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes. I have right before me where they were 98, and $97\frac{3}{4}$. Yes; I see them here on this list selling quite often above that price. Here is $98\frac{1}{2}$.

Mr. PECORA. How far above?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Well, I have them here at one spot selling at $99\frac{1}{8}$.

The CHAIRMAN. When was that?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That was the 2d of May 1928.

Mr. PECORA. That was when all securities were selling high, wasn't it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I rather expect so. These wouldn't be an exception to any market level.

Mr. PECORA. Now, isn't it a fact that by the time of the expiration of this 60-day life of this selling syndicate, the bankers had disposed of all of their bonds to the public?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The syndicate through the selling group had sold all the bonds.

The CHAIRMAN. The subcommittee will now stand in recess until 2 o'clock p.m. of this day.

(Thereupon, at 12:30 p.m., Wednesday, June 28, 1933, the subcommittee recessed until 2 o'clock p.m. of the same day.)

AFTER RECESS

The subcommittee resumed at 2 p.m. on the expiration of the noon recess.

The CHAIRMAN. The subcommittee will come to order. Mr. Pecora may proceed.

TESTIMONY OF BENJAMIN J. BUTTENWIESER, A MEMBER OF THE FIRM OF KUHN, LOEB & CO.—Resumed

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Buttenwieser, reference was made in the testimony on yesterday with respect to the Chilean bank loans, to the payment of a commission to Louis Dreyfus & Co. Who paid that commission?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The originating group.

Mr. PECORA. That means your firm, the Guaranty Co., and Lehman Bros.?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. What did that commission amount to?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. One half of 1 percent.

Mr. PECORA. Of the total issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Of the total issue; yes. That was the total, you understand.

Mr. PECORA. Was it \$100,000?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And was that paid out of this profit that you mentioned this morning to the originating group, of \$247,127.20, or was it paid in addition thereto?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It was paid before that profit had been made. In other words, the figure I gave you was our net profit.

Mr. PECORA. Well, I asked you this morning to give me the gross, and I understood you to say, in substance, that this was the net, this figure of in round numbers \$247,000, which you gave as gross, was also virtually net. Now, the gross was at least \$347,127.20, wasn't it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I am sorry if you got that impression then. I must have misunderstood your question. What I meant to say was that that was the net of the spread to the originating group, because the originating group really considered that it had that one-half-percent expense charged to itself, so to speak, before it realized its own profit.

Mr. PECORA. Now, were there any other payments that were made by the originating group out of their gross profits before they realized this net profit of \$247,000?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No, sir. Mr. Pecora, I should like to make it perfectly clear: If you mean that the selling group commission should be deducted from the gross profit, and the syndicate gross spread should be deducted from the gross spread, then, of course, I must amend the answer I made this morning. But that was not the way I understood your question. In other words, there was a gross spread, as I indicated, of $4\frac{1}{8}$ percent. If you want me to rephrase my answer that our gross profit was so and so, and the net profit was the figure which I gave you, I can do that.

Mr. PECORA. Will you do that then?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. All I would have to do is to calculate $4\frac{1}{8}$ percent on \$20,000,000.

Mr. PECORA. All right.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is \$925,000.

Mr. PECORA. Now, how was this gross profit of \$925,000 distributed?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. First, there was one half percent to Messrs. Louis Dreyfus & Co. Then $1\frac{1}{4}$ percent, which was the originating group spread, and that was the figure I indicated this morning. The reason it is not exactly \$250,000 is because that one fourth percent to which I made reference this morning was an interest gain and naturally had to be estimated, and instead of being \$250,000 that profit was \$247,000. That was as close as we could estimate it. Then the syndicate gross spread was $1\frac{1}{8}$ percent less all expenses, which reduced its actual profit to eighty one hundredths percent. And the selling group commission was $1\frac{3}{4}$ percent.

Mr. PECORA. Did your firm participate in the $1\frac{1}{4}$ percent spread to the syndicate?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes. That was the figure you asked for this morning, and I told you I would get it during the luncheon recess.

Mr. PECORA. Have you got it now?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir. We had a participation of \$1,400,000 principal amount of bonds in that syndicate, on which we realized a net profit of \$11,198.83.

Mr. PECORA. Now, did your firm participate or did it receive any compensation for the managing of the selling group?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No, sir; none whatsoever.

Senator STEIWER. To what did you refer this morning when you said the net and the gross were one and the same thing?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I was referring, Senator, to the originating group profit, and there was no expense chargeable to that original margin which we retained for ourselves, or which we kept for ourselves, and that was what led me to make the statement that the net and the gross were exactly the same on that originating group profit.

Mr. PECORA. Which group paid the \$25,000 to Mr. Norman H. Davis?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. As was embodied in that memorandum we read yesterday, Mr. Norman Davis on that loan received a commission of \$25,000, of which the syndicate paid \$15,000, and the Guaranty Co. of New York paid \$10,000.

Mr. PECORA. Now, is this finder's commission of one half of 1 percent the usual commission or perquisite in such instances?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The paying of a finder's commission is very usual. The size of that varies, of course.

Mr. PECORA. What is the range of the commission paid to the finder in such issues?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. So far as our own experience is concerned I think it varies anywhere from one fourth to one half percent.

Mr. PECORA. In this case, then, Louis Dreyfus & Co. received the maximum that is usually allowed?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I have no way of telling whether that is the maximum. I would say that between one fourth and one half percent is a usual range. It may be less than one fourth percent, too. It varies in each particular instance.

Mr. PECORA. You stated it varies from a range that reaches to one half of 1 percent.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir; and by that I mean——

Mr. PECORA (continuing). In this case I assume that Louis Dreyfus & Co. received the maximum that is usually allowed to a finder.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. So far as our experience is concerned; yes. And I might add that as you will see in the Louis Dreyfus & Co. correspondence, that was a reciprocal arrangement which we entered into with Dreyfus & Co.

Mr. PECORA. What do you mean by that?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That on issues which we made in this country they would receive a commission, and on issues which they made in Europe we would get an interest.

Mr. PECORA. That is, where you were the finders and Louis Dreyfus & Co. were the underwriters of any European issue, you would get one half of 1 percent finder's commission?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Well, Mr. Pecora, we could not make any general arrangement as to how large or how small the commission would be. We merely said that that would be arranged. Nor did we make any arrangement with Louis Dreyfus & Co. that their commission would always be one half of 1 percent. We said they would be compensated on future issues which might be made in our country by us, and we would be compensated on issues which they might make on their side.

Mr. PECORA. Was this one half of 1 percent paid as a maximum because it was considered by your firm that this issue was an especially attractive and profitable undertaking?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No. I think we considered that this was an important piece of business, and it was a new relationship which had been brought to us.

The CHAIRMAN. Did they receive that on the total issues of \$90,000,000?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. That is, they received that one half of 1 percent on each of the four subsequent issues?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And would have received it had there been any other or additional issues underwritten by the same group?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Well, each case would, of course, have to be determined by the circumstances that surrounded it. But if we could we hoped to compensate them on the same basis.

Mr. PECORA. Isn't that a rather large commission to pay merely for introducing a piece of business of this kind?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not think it is a large commission.

Mr. PECORA. Well, in this particular instance, where your firm and the Guaranty Co. of New York underwrote these five loans for the Mortgage Bank of Chile, aggregating \$90,000,000, they received a total commission of \$450,000, didn't they?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. A finder's commission aggregating \$450,000.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Merely for introducing the subject to you.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Well, other commissions, some of which are even fixed by law, are as I understand it, very much higher. Real estate and brokerage commissions of that kind, for instance, are much higher. There are other commissions that are as a rule much higher. The amount sounds large in the aggregate, but percentage-wise I do not think it is unduly large. And you realize, of course, that Messrs. Louis Dreyfus & Co. are an important banking house. They were not merely a broker or a finder, they were an old established firm of the first rank.

Mr. PECORA. The only service they rendered here was that of finder, wasn't it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No; they were in a position to be more than that. If it became, because of market conditions, impossible to issue bonds of the Mortgage Bank of Chile in this country they stood ready to sponsor those issues for the Mortgage Bank in France.

Mr. PECORA. Would not they have gotten an additional compensation for that service?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No. Mr. Pecora, the point I am trying to make is that they were more than just a finder. They were definitely interested in this business.

Mr. PECORA. But the only function they served here was that of bringing the business to your attention, wasn't it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. They rendered considerable service in the actual negotiation of this business, as you will notice in the correspondence and cables which we had with the representative of the Mortgage Bank of Chile. Some of the negotiations were handled through them.

Mr. PECORA. Then what service did Mr. Norman H. Davis render?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Mr. Davis, as yesterday's memorandum shows, was the man who brought this business to the attention of the Guaranty Co.

Mr. PECORA. You have a copy, haven't you, of a cable that was sent by Mr. Leval, the manager of Louis Dreyfus & Co., on June 26, 1925, to the director of the Mortgage Bank of Chile?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Pardon me a moment while I try to find that.

Mr. PECORA. All right.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not seem to find that, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. Well, it reads as follows, and is addressed to Mr. Louis Barros Borgono, director of the Mortgage Bank of Chile:

Congratulations on the result of negotiations, which constitute a great triumph for the bank as well as for Chile.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not think I have a copy of it here, but there may very well have been such a cable. Oh, I beg pardon. Yes; I find it here, and that was the June 26 cablegram?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It was embodied in a copy of a number of cables, and that was why I could not find it on my first search of the files.

Mr. PECORA. Do you think that he advisedly limited the extent of his congratulations to the Mortgage Bank of Chile?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I am sorry, but I did not get that question.

Mr. PECORA. I will ask the committee reporter to read it. (Which was done.)

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It is very difficult for me to tell you what was in another man's mind 8 years after he sent the cablegram.

Mr. PECORA. Very well. Now, let us pass on to the second Chilean loan of \$20,000,000 of July 1926.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. All right.

Mr. PECORA. Have you a copy of the prospectus that was issued when this second issue was floated to the American public?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Will you produce it for our record, please?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I say again, Mr. Pecora, this is my only copy, and it has certain pencil markings on it. If it is agreeable to the committee I should like to have it returned.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Chairman, I offer this in evidence and ask that it may be spread on the record of the hearing.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted, and the committee reporter will make it a part of the hearings, omitting the pencil markings that may appear thereon.

(The prospectus issued by Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and the Guaranty Co. of New York for the second loan of \$20,000,000 to the Mortgage Bank of Chile, was marked "Committee Exhibit No. 12, June 28, 1933", and will be found on page 1164.)

The CHAIRMAN. This is a similar prospectus to the first prospectus introduced in evidence, is it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

The CHAIRMAN. But the rate of interest here was $6\frac{3}{4}$ percent instead of $6\frac{1}{2}$ percent as was shown there.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

The CHAIRMAN. What is the price?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The price was $99\frac{1}{4}$ percent and accrued interest.

Mr. PECORA. To the public?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. What was the price to the underwriters?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Do you mean the original price that we paid?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. $95\frac{5}{8}$ percent. And here again I want to point out that there was an interest gain, which made the actual price $94\frac{3}{4}$ percent.

Mr. PECORA. What did you say was the offering price to the public?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It was $99\frac{1}{4}$ percent.

Mr. PECORA. What was the political condition of Chile at the time of this second issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That was July 29, 1926, and my recollection is that there was a de jure government in power, which was after the election which we had been discussing this morning, after that election had been held. I should like to refresh my memory on that, too.

Mr. PECORA. All right. [After waiting a few minutes and the witness had not refreshed his memory Mr. Pecora continued.] At the time that your firm and the Guaranty Co. agreed to underwrite this second issue of \$20,000,000 in 1926 did you know that the United States Department of Commerce had said in its yearbook concerning Chile as follows:

The principal factor in Chile's economic position during 1926 was the weakening demand for nitrates, brought about by competition from European artificial fertilizers, and lack of buying for future delivery caused plants to close down, until in December only one third as many were operating as at the beginning of the year. The Government's financial situation was adverse. Total revenues, owing to a decline in the yield of the tax on nitrate exports, which did not increase to the extent expected, and expenditures were higher in 1925. The Government was therefore obliged to resort to borrowing. Depression in the nitrate industry produced an unfavorable situation for commerce, and an acute problem of unemployment was created. The nonsettlement of the Tacna-Arica question complicated the situation and increased taxation, and the burden of new social legislation reducing the purchasing power. The year 1926 closed with the nitrate industry in a very serious situation and with no prospect of improvement. The effects of overproduction, coupled with a lessening demand, began to be felt early in the year.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Before I answer that, may I complete the answer to your previous question? I did not have the date before me then and I have it now. In December of 1925 Emiliano Figuarno Lorrain was elected president, and I have here a note which says that on December 23 he assumed the chief magistracy, and that the

former relations were maintained with this Government, and that the United States Ambassador attended his inauguration in his official capacity.

Mr. PECORA. Well, I suppose that helped to make the guarantee more secure, but I asked you if you were familiar with that portion of the United States Department of Commerce report on the economic situation of Chile.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I merely wanted to complete my answer to your previous question. Now, answering the excerpt which you have read from the United States Department of Commerce report, may I ask you what was the date of that?

Mr. PECORA. It was in their year book for 1926.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Well, the bond issue was made July 29, 1926. So while I haven't that before me, of course, I cannot tell when that was published, but inasmuch as the excerpt speaks of the close of 1926 I should doubt that it could have been available to us at the end of July of 1926.

Mr. PECORA. But the Department of Commerce said in that report:

The effects of overproduction, coupled with lessening demand, began to be felt early in the year.

Now, this bond issue was brought out in July of 1926. Had your firm caused to be made a study of economic conditions in Chile prior to bringing out this second bond issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I have no doubt we did. And I am perfectly ready to repeat what I said this morning, that it is true the trade figures of Chile diminished somewhat during 1926, and that the favorable trade balance of Chile had been reduced from \$77,000,000 in 1925 to \$42,000,000 in 1926. But it was still a considerable favorable trade balance.

Mr. PECORA. In view of the economic situation pointed out in this report of the United States Department of Commerce, why did you pay $94\frac{3}{4}$ for the issue, whereas you had paid 93 for the previous issue in the year before, when economic conditions seemed to be better?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. This bond was a $6\frac{3}{4}$ -percent bond, and the other was $6\frac{1}{2}$ percent. One would naturally pay a higher price because of the higher coupon. And—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). Well, doesn't it seem—

Mr. BUTTENWIESER (continuing). Might I complete this? The yield to the public on the first issue was 6.70 percent, while the yield on the second issue was 6.80 percent. So that you will see we did bring it out at a somewhat lower basis to the public.

Mr. PECORA. Does the increase in interest rate between the second issue and the first issue indicate that the risk at the time of the second issue was greater than at the time of the first issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No. It is the basis that counts. The coupon rate is merely a matter of convenience of the borrower. It is the actual return basis to the borrower that is the determining factor.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know what were the determining factors that brought about an increase in the rate of interest on the bonds, over the rate of interest paid on the first issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes; there are two possibilities, but on this I want to say this is only a guess: One is that the mortgages which they got in Chile and which were issued out of the proceeds of this loan may have had a higher coupon rate. The other is that the sinking fund would operate on a slightly different basis for a 6¾-percent bond than it would for a 6½-percent bond. The sinking fund in each case being what one calls a cumulative sinking fund.

Mr. PECORA. Your firm underwrote the second issue in conjunction with the Guaranty Co. of New York, didn't it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I beg pardon?

Mr. PECORA. I asked, your firm underwrote the second issue in conjunction with the Guaranty Co. of New York?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And I assume that in the course of the negotiations leading up to that underwriting of the second issue, your firm kept in touch with the officers of the Guaranty Co. with respect to this proposed second issue.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Are you familiar with the fact that Mr. B. Atterbury, at that time in Santiago, Chile, representing the Guaranty Co. of New York, cabled to Mr. Stanley, the then president of that company, as follows:

The nitrate situation, figures on Government finances, and the general commercial feeling, not encouraging.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir. Mr. Atterbury at the time was correct, and I dislike reiterating all these things, but the fact remains that, while the nitrate situation was for the time being unfavorable, and while I appreciate, of course, that one cannot go by results, the ultimate result was that, while the trade balance did diminish somewhat for the year 1926, due in part, I have no doubt, to the nitrate situation, none the less the favorable trade balance remained substantial. And I might add that that was evidently a rather temporary situation because in the following year the favorable trade balance increased again to a point where it was almost as much as in 1925.

Mr. PECORA. You could not tell what was going to happen the following year, could you?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I prefaced my remark by saying one cannot go by results, but that was the fact.

Mr. PECORA. But you had the definite statement from a representative of the Guaranty Co. of New York in Chile that the general commercial feeling was not encouraging.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That was his survey of the situation, I admit, and I admit that at the time he was correct, but—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). And you were not deterred by that report in taking over the second bond issue, were you?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Well, the point is this: The situation might not have been as good as it was in 1925, but it was still favorable. And, after all, one does not stop buying bonds of a country itself because its favorable trade situation declines somewhat.

Mr. PECORA. Have you here with you any reports from your own advisers or from any other advisers of the Guaranty Co. of New York, showing just how favorable conditions were prior to your taking over the second bond issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It is stated in the circular on those trade figures.

Mr. PECORA. What advices did you have that caused you to put that in the circular and to underwrite the second bond issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Well, you see at the time we were negotiating this issue the Controller of the Mortgage Bank of Chile was in New York, and we could discuss those figures with him, and he assured us that while temporarily those figures did show some decline, yet they still reflected a substantial favorable trade balance.

Mr. PECORA. Were you induced to buy the second bond issue by the representations of the representative of the borrower?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No; by the facts which he adduced to support his statement.

Mr. PECORA. Did you make any independent study of the economic situation of Chile?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I have no doubt that we did have figures before us as to the trade situation.

Mr. PECORA. Did you make any independent study? In other words, did you have any trained or expert advisers to go down and make an independent study and render confidential reports to yourselves?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not know what confidential reports we could have gotten that would have weighed quite so heavily as the actual trade figures which we had.

Senator STEIWER. Do you mean by that that your answer is no?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Sir?

Senator STEIWER. Do you mean to say that your answer is in the negative to that question?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. My answer is that the figures which we had seemed more eloquent than any independent study that could be made or any opinion of Mr. Atterbury's.

Senator STEIWER. I am not quarreling with you at all, and that possibly is full justification for what you did, but do I understand that your answer to the question propounded by counsel to the committee is no? In other words, you did not send anybody down there?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The answer to that question is no.

Mr. PECORA. What is the answer to the question as to whether or not you made or caused to be made any independent study or investigation of economic conditions in Chile?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The answer to that is that it cannot be answered categorically. We did make a study of the figures which were available to us here, and that, I repeat, showed that while temporarily the figures had declined somewhat, they still reflected a favorable trade balance.

Mr. PECORA. Well, is that all you acted upon, Mr. Buttenwieser, in underwriting this issue with a view to offering it to the investing public here?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No, Mr. Pecora, that is not all. It was one of the important factors.

Mr. PECORA. Well, what were the other important factors?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Well, I must go back again to the long record of Chile for having met all its obligations; to the fact that its trade had for many years been favorable, and to the general standing of Chilean credit throughout the world.

Senator BARKLEY. You made this loan, then, on the general situation as you understood it—from the reputation of Chile over a period of years and such figures as you had—but you did not make any particular investigation with reference to this particular loan that was out of the ordinary from what you did in any case of that sort; is that true?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is substantially correct, Senator; yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Do you not think that an independent study or investigation of economic conditions undertaken for you or in your behalf with a view of enabling you to determine the real risk involved in taking over this second issue would have revealed to you the information that was obtained by the United States Department of Commerce when it said in its Year Book for 1926:

The year 1926 closed with the nitrate industry in a very serious situation and with no prospect of improvement. The effects of overproduction, coupled with lessening demand, began to be felt early in the year.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Frankly I do not, Mr. Pecora, because the following year proved that there was an improvement, when the figures improved from \$42,000,000 to \$72,000,000.

Mr. PECORA. But you did not know—you did not have the facts which the United States Department of Commerce apparently had succeeded in gathering when you took over this second issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. But they were wrong in their forecast, so any other person that we might have sent down there would very likely have been equally wrong.

Mr. PECORA. Were they wrong in their statement that “The effects of overproduction, coupled with lessening demand, began to be felt early in the year 1926”?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Doubtless they were not wrong about early in the year, but that forecast that they showed no signs of improving was wrong.

Mr. PECORA. Were they wrong in their statement when the United States Department of Commerce said:

Heavy accumulations of stocks—
meaning of nitrate stocks—

and lack of buying for future delivery caused plants to close down until in December only one third as many were operating as in the beginning of the year. The Government's financial situation was adverse?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It might very well be, Mr. Pecora—and again I want to say I do not want to quibble about these things—but it might very well be that shutting down some of the nitrate plants might better the situation in Chile—the nitrate situation in Chile—just the same as restrictive measures in production of other commodities elsewhere in the world have improved conditions in that particular commodity in that country.

Mr. PECORA. Now, bearing in mind that you knew that the American investing public to which you expected to sell these bonds were going to buy those bonds largely upon their reliance on the integrity and standing of your firm and the Guaranty Co., you felt that you and the Guaranty Co. owed a duty to the American investing public to make a complete, full, and independent investigation of all the factors that entered into the risk, did you not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The main factor, I repeat, that entered into this was the general credit, all the resources of Chile which were pledged with us as well as the general good name of Chile which stood behind its unconditional guaranty of the bonds.

Mr. PECORA. Well, whatever else was done by you to assure yourself of the safety of this issue, you did not make or cause to be made any independent investigation of the economic situation, did you?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. All right.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. But I might add that as regards any government it is difficult to make an independent economic study of its situation.

Mr. PECORA. Well, the United States Department of Commerce apparently was doing it year after year?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Well, with all due deference to the Department of Commerce their forecast was not extremely accurate.

Mr. PECORA. But their statement of existing conditions was accurate, was it not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes; it was a temporary situation.

Mr. PECORA. And nobody knew how long that temporary situation was going to last or whether it was going to get better or worse?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. And you took a chance against that, did you not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. But I must add again: There is no reason why one should not buy securities of a country of good standing just because temporarily the situation might not be as good as it was, though it is still favorable.

Mr. PECORA. And you considered a country of good standing to be one whose government was based upon armed force and upon the dissolution of its popular assembly and the nullification or setting aside of its constitution, did you?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I am sorry, Mr. Pecora—at that time there was a perfectly constitutional, recognized government—we are speaking now of the 1926 issue—elected government, and it was recognized by our Government, and it was a government which was elected by the people.

Mr. PECORA. But the government in 1925 was not such a government?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Now, how long did that government of 1926 remain in power—this stable government that you are speaking of now?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I believe it stayed right through until 1931. The data I have before me seems to indicate that.

Mr. PECORA. Who became the president of the government after the adoption of the constitution in 1926?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Carlos Ibanez, it seems, in July of 1927.

Mr. PECORA. No; I said in 1926.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. This man that I mentioned before, Emiliano Figueroa Larrain.

Mr. PECORA. Had he supplanted Alessandri, who apparently was at the head of the government, with the aid and assistance of this military council in 1925?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. This Figueroa is the president who was elected. Now, the exact date of his election, I think, was December 23, 1925, from this little memorandum I have.

Mr. PECORA. How long did he remain the head of the government?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It seems until May 23 of 1927.

Mr. PECORA. So that this constitutional government lasted a little over a year?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No; I believe there was an election in 1927 where Carlos Ibanez was elected.

Mr. PECORA. Well, are you familiar with the political conditions that existed in connection with Ibanez's administration?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not know what conditions you are referring to, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. Well, the conditions that were indicated by what I understand to be the fact that he arrested all of his political rivals in order to maintain himself in office. Are you acquainted with those facts?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I have not seen those facts stated.

Mr. PECORA. Now, was a syndicate formed by the original group with regard to this second issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No, Mr. Pecora; there was no syndicate in this transaction.

Mr. PECORA. Well, what was formed? A selling or distributing group?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And that was formed by the members of the original group, namely, yourselves and the Guaranty Co.?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct, sir.

Mr. PECORA. On what terms did the members of the selling group participate?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. They offered them to the public at 99¼ percent, and they received 2¼ percent selling commission.

Mr. PECORA. That is one half of 1 percent over the commission allowed to the selling group of the preceding year on the occasion of the first issue, was it not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. They rendered the same kind of service, did they not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Well, in the previous issue a great many of the members of the selling group were also members of the syndicate. So that in effect while it is true they performed two services, to a considerable extent they participated in a spread which was 1⅛ percent for one and 1¾ percent for the other.

Mr. PECORA. What was the gross profit to the original group in connection with the second issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Do you want the entire gross now, Mr. Pecora?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. \$824,850. That is 4½ points. And to clarify that figure for you, Mr. Pecora, that was the issue of which the total it was of \$20,000,000 but we only purchased and offered \$18,330,000. The remaining \$1,670,000 having been taken by the Mortgage Bank itself for its reserve fund.

The CHAIRMAN. Do you remember what that reserve fund amounted to at that time?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It was approximately \$5,000,000—slightly over \$5,000,000.

Mr. PECORA. What do they do? Take as their reserve fund their own bonds?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir. They would have that many more mortgages against which there would not be bonds publicly outstanding.

Mr. PECORA. Do you mean that they took as their reserve fund their own obligation?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is customary among very many public bodies. I might mention any number of them. New York City does that.

Mr. PECORA. Now, let us pass on to the third loan of \$10,000,000. But before I pass on to that, will you produce the contract covering the underwriting of the second issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes. I make my usual request. Do you mean the loan agreement, Mr. Pecora?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes [handing same to Mr. Pecora].

Mr. PECORA. I offer this in evidence and ask to have it spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. It will be admitted in evidence and spread on the record.

(Agreement between Caja de Credito Hipotecario (Chile) and Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and Guaranty Co. of New York. July 29, 1926. Guaranteed sinking fund 6¾ percent gold bonds of 1926, was received in evidence, marked "Committee Exhibit 13, of June 28, 1933." See p. 1167.)

Mr. PECORA. Now, in connection with this second issue, Mr. Buttenwieser, was a 60-day period fixed between the underwriters and the selling group for the marketing of the bonds?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The second issue; yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And during that 60-day period did the underwriters or bankers succeed in disposing of the entire issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And in this instance, as on the occasion of the first issue of the preceding year, was the selling group formed and commitments for the entire issue received from its members by the underwriters within 24 hours after the agreement between the underwriters and the Mortgage Bank of Chile was consummated?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I cannot be certain, of course, about the 24 hours, but the bonds were successfully sold.

Mr. PECORA. Is the investing public ever advised in these matters by the underwriters or the selling group of this 60-day period during which support will be given to the market by the underwriters?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It is not officially stated, but I think—

Mr. PECORA. Is it unofficially stated?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. But I think it is rather well known.

Mr. PECORA. Why is the letter embodying that agreement between the underwriters and the members of the selling group marked "confidential"?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Practically any letter of ours which would involve a statement of a selling commission allowed or any such other matter would be marked "confidential."

Mr. PECORA. Well, does not that imply that no information concerning those terms and provisions of the agreement between the underwriters and the selling group is to be made public?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It is implied. How well it is respected I am not prepared to state. I might add that it is done largely because of the fact that the dealers will tell the investing public to whom they sell those bonds that if they want to resell them they prefer to have them resold to them rather than to have them pressing on the market.

Mr. PECORA. And the reason for that is to maintain the price during the process of unloading on the public, is it not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No; I think it is not that.

Mr. PECORA. What is it for?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I think it is because the distributor would rather get those bonds back again from some client who does not want them for investment, and redistribute them to some other client who might want them for investment.

Mr. PECORA. And redistribute them at the offering price to the public rather than to take the risk of the original investor selling them at a lower price in the open market?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Not necessarily at a lower price; no. He gets his commission for placing these bonds with ultimate investors. Consequently, it is to his advantage if there be an instance where the investor to whom he has first sold changes his mind, to get them back so that he can place them again with the investor who wants them for permanent investment and thereby earn his commission.

Mr. PECORA. You are not receding, are you, from the position that was very frankly stated during the forenoon session today, that during this 60-day period of the life of the selling syndicate or group the market is maintained or supported or aided or pegged, whatever term you want to use?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not think there is any conflict between the statement I made and the statement you have just made.

Mr. PECORA. It still is the desire of the underwriters to see that the market is supported, aided, or pegged during the life of the selling group?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It is the desire of the underwriters to see that the issue is absorbed by real investors.

Mr. PECORA. And absorbed at the offering price rather than a lower price during that 60-day period?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It is obviously our intention that they be placed with the public at that price.

Mr. PECORA. And after the expiration of that 60-day period the underwriter's interest in the public market for the bonds practically ceases?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Oh, no; I would not say that. I would not subscribe to that statement at all.

Mr. PECORA. Well, do they continue to do anything to peg the price?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. We very often repurchase sizable amounts of bonds long after a syndicate is terminated and lose a fair amount of money on that sometimes.

Mr. PECORA. Did you do that in this instance?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. In this instance I do not think the market required it.

Mr. PECORA. Did you do it in the first instance when, as it appeared in this morning's testimony, upon the expiration of the 60-day period the market dropped to 94 and 94½?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not think we did.

Mr. PECORA. Now, the third issue was one of \$10,000,000, was it not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And that was underwritten in December 1926?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is right.

Mr. PECORA. And those were 5-year 6-percent notes?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Now, did your firm cause any independent investigation to be made, before it agreed to underwrite this issue, of the political and economic conditions in Chile?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I think I will have to stand on the answer I made previously.

Mr. PECORA. The answer, then, is no?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The answer is no, except that by that time we had figures for a longer period of 1926, so that our judgment could be reinforced by the figures as they existed for practically the entire year.

Mr. PECORA. Now at what price did you and the Guaranty Co. take over these \$10,000,000 par value of 5-year 6 percent notes?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. 95½ percent.

Mr. PECORA. At 95½. At what price were they offered to the public?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. 98¾ percent.

Mr. PECORA. And accrued interest?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. And accrued interest; yes, sir.

The CHAIRMAN. Do you know the purpose of this loan?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes; Senator Fletcher. As we stated in our circular, the notes were issued for the purpose of making loans secured by agricultural products or implements, which loans may not exceed 50 percent of the estimated value of the collateral.

The CHAIRMAN. Do you know what the purpose was of securing these loans by agricultural products? What do you mean by that? What did the bank do? Did it take mortgages on agricultural products?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Or implements.

The CHAIRMAN. Or implements?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Agricultural implements.

Mr. PECORA. Your firm was appointed the fiscal agent for the Mortgage Bank of Chile in connection with the first two issues, was it not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Our firm and the Guaranty Trust Co. were appointed fiscal agent for each of the loans.

Mr. PECORA. What commission did you get for your service as such fiscal agent?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. One fourth of 1 percent of the amount of all payments made for interest and sinking fund.

Mr. PECORA. Have you got any calculation that could give us the aggregate sums that you received in connection with all five of these loans for your services as fiscal agents?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I haven't that, and it would be a rather tedious operation to get those figures. But we can get them for you if the committee desires.

Mr. PECORA. Can you give us any approximation at this time?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It would be almost impossible for me to approximate that now with any degree of accuracy. You appreciate, of course, that is for a totally different service and has nothing to do with the issuance. It is for the payment of coupons and payment of bonds.

Mr. PECORA. It is for acting as fiscal agents?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, exactly.

Mr. PECORA. Now, did your firm keep on deposit any of the proceeds from the sale of these first two issues of bonds for any period of time?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I haven't that fact before me.

Mr. PECORA. Well, what is your recollection of it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. My recollection is that they disposed of those sums as they needed them. But here again I am relying on my memory. And that is why I brought out that we only paid them a certain portion of the proceeds of the loan at certain periods, because they felt they did not require those funds in the first instance, and preferred to have the payments made over a period, and that accounted for the interest gain which we enumerated in each instance.

Mr. PECORA. Well, now, during the time that any of those funds remained on deposit with you, did you allow the Mortgage Bank of Chile any interest thereon?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. What rate?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That would vary, of course. Whatever the rate for such funds was in New York. I do not remember that it was fixed, but I am not certain about it.

Mr. PECORA. Are you certain that any interest at all was allowed on those funds?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Oh, yes; I am quite certain of that.

Mr. PECORA. As a matter of fact, whatever commissions or fees you earned as fiscal agents came to you directly by reason of the flotation of these issues, did they not, because the loan agreements provided that you were to be the fiscal agents?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct, sir. But of course the service of fiscal agent had to be performed by someone. The coupons had to be paid in New York. The bonds drawn for sinking fund had to be paid in New York. And the commission which we got for paying them is almost a standardized rate.

Mr. PECORA. Now, how was this third issue disposed of to the public?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. In the same manner as the second.

Mr. PECORA. That is, by the organization of a selling group?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct, sir.

Mr. PECORA. With no intervening syndicate?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And what was the gross profit that accrued to the original group in connection with this third issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Three and one quarter percent, which is \$325,000. Do you want the split-up of that, Mr. Pecora?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. One half percent went to Messrs. Louis Dreyfus & Co.; $1\frac{3}{4}$ percent, less expenses, to the original group, which in that case was the underwriter. And 1 percent selling commission to the selling group. There was no interest gain in that transaction.

Mr. PECORA. Now, when was the fourth issue brought out?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. April 30, 1928.

Mr. PECORA. And the par value of that was \$20,000,000, was it not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Six percent bonds?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Maturing in 1961?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Who were the members of the original group in that instance?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The Guaranty Co., the National City Co., Lehman Bros., and ourselves.

Mr. PECORA. Well, now, for the first time in connection with these Chilean issues the National City Co. was brought into the original group. What was the reason for that?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. As I recall, that was at the request of the Chilean Government.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know what prompted that request?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not really know what prompted that request.

Mr. PECORA. You complied with it readily?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. What were the respective interests of these four participants in the original group in connection with the fourth loan?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Lehman Bros. 10 percent; each of the other three, 30 percent.

Mr. PECORA. You did not need the financial assistance of the National City Co. in the flotation of this fourth loan, did you?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. We did not need it. We welcome any financial assistance. Refreshing my memory now I believe the National City Bank or company—I do not recall which—had been appointed fiscal agent of the Chilean Government in the United States at that time, and that probably accounts for that request. I was trying to see whether it was about that time, and I believe it was.

Mr. KAHN. May I interrupt a minute, Mr. Pecora? I can tell you positively from my recollection.

Mr. PECORA. All right, sir.

Mr. KAHN. So you do not have to guess.

Mr. PECORA. If you will.

Mr. KAHN. I do not want to try your patience. But the National City Bank at that time, after lengthy negotiation, was appointed fiscal agent for all the financial affairs of the Chilean Government, direct or guaranteed by the Chilean Government. The whole thing

by the wish of the Chilean Government was contemplated under the auspices of the National City Bank.

Mr. PECORA. I recall of some testimony given before this committee last February in which one of the officers of the National City Co., in testifying with regard to some external financing which that company undertook with some South American country, said that somebody was trying to chisel in. Is this an instance where the National City Bank tried to chisel in on your firm and the Guaranty Co.?

Mr. KAHN. May I leave that to your own interpretation, Mr. Pecora? May I leave that to your own interpretation?

Mr. PECORA. Would you be satisfied with my conclusion about it?

Mr. KAHN. Wouldn't that—

Mr. PECORA (after a pause). Now, I will resume with Mr. Buttenwieser. With regard to the fourth Chilean Bank loan of \$20,000,000, when was that brought up?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is the one of April 30, 1928.

Mr. PECORA. And the par value of that was \$20,000,000?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Six percent bonds due in 1961, is that right?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Now, at what price did the underwriters buy this issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Ninety-two percent.

Mr. PECORA. Wasn't it 91¾?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No. We allowed them one fourth percent more after the signing of the contract, our agreement being that if we were able to issue above 95½ percent they would get the increase. Those bonds were issued at 95¾ percent, and consequently the bank got the extra one fourth percent.

Mr. PECORA. Well, that was an arrangement that was entered into subsequent to the original agreement for this issue, was it not?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It was simultaneous, I think.

Mr. PECORA. Have you a copy of the original agreement?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Covering this issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Will you produce it, please, for the record?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. What is the date of this?

Mr. PECORA. The date of this is April 30, 1928. Well, now, I notice that under the terms of this contract or agreement the Guaranty Co. and the firm of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. are named also as fiscal agents for this loan.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct, sir.

Mr. PECORA. The fact, then, that the National City Co. had meanwhile become fiscal agents for the Chilean Government did not extend that agency to cover this issue, did it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No, sir. We were fiscal agents for this issue, which is a Mortgage Bank issue.

Mr. PECORA. Now, where is the other agreement under which you permitted or sanctioned the National City Co. coming in as a participant on equal terms with yourself and the Guaranty Co.?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That was done by letter.

Mr. PECORA. Will you produce the letter?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes. [Handing same to Mr. Pecora.] The arrangements were made verbally, Mr. Pecora. That is the confirmation letter, of which Mr. McEldowney has a copy. The fact is that is a copy he made.

Mr. PECORA. What did you say was the cost to the underwriters for this fourth issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Ninety-two percent.

Mr. PECORA. Well, the agreement provides for a price of 91¾ percent.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct, but we supplemented that agreement by assuring the Mortgage Bank that if we issued above 95½ percent they would get the difference, and the bonds were issued at 95¾ percent and the Mortgage Bank got the extra one-fourth percent.

Mr. PECORA. Have you got a copy of that supplemental agreement here?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It was embodied in a cable which was sent to the Mortgage Bank by Mr. Laval of Louis Dreyfus & Co.—I believe it is Mr. McEldowney's copy, exhibit 1—which says—

The bankers plan to issue at 95½ percent, but if the market for Chile 6 percent bonds permits we will try to issue higher and if so we will give Caja full benefit of such higher price.

Mr. PECORA. Now, the letter that you have produced, or rather the copy of the letter which you have produced here with respect to the admittance of the National City Co. as a participant with yourselves and the Guaranty Co. in the original group is dated April 30, 1928, which is the date of the loan agreement with the Chilean Bank?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct, sir.

Mr. PECORA. I offer this copy of the letter in evidence. Is this a correct copy of the original?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir. It has a very slight change in pencil, because all these copies were made by your staff and we compared them. There is a slight change there. That pencil correction should go in there.

Mr. PECORA. Should go into the record?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. It is merely a typographical error.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes; it is merely a typographical error.

Mr. PECORA. Yes. I offer it in evidence and ask that it be spread upon the record.

The CHAIRMAN. It will be admitted in evidence and spread upon the record.

(Copy of letter of April 30, 1928, from Kuhn, Loeb & Co. to the National City Co., was marked "Committee Exhibit 14", of June 28, 1933, and is here printed in the record in full, as follows:)

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT 14

APRIL 30, 1928.

RONALD M. BYRNES, Esq.,

Vice President the National City Co., New York City, N.Y.

DEAR SIR: Jointly with the Guaranty Co. of New York we have agreed to purchase \$20,000,000 principal amount Mortgage Bank of Chile (Caja de Crédito Hipotecario, Chile) guaranteed sinking fund 6 percent gold bonds of 1928, due April 30, 1961, as more fully described in the enclosed circular.

We hereby confirm that you have been ceded an interest of 30 percent in this business on original terms. The cost of the bonds will be 91¾ percent and accrued interest to May 21, 1928, payable as follows: \$7,912,000 on May 21, 1928, \$1,500,000 on June 15, 1928, and the balance of the purchase price, being \$9,008,000, on August 1, 1928, this last installment to remain on deposit until September 29, 1928, at interest at the rate of 1½ percent per annum. An intermediary fee of one-half percent is to be paid.

No syndicate will be formed, but the bonds are to be offered for public subscription by us, the Guaranty Co. of New York, and yourselves at 95¾ percent and accrued interest, less a selling commission of 2 percent, of which one fourth percent may be reallocated to bankers, brokers, national banks, State banks, savings banks, trust companies, and insurance companies.

Kindly confirm that the above is in accordance with your understanding, and oblige,

Yours very truly,

KUHN, LOEB & Co.

Mr. PECORA. I also want to offer in evidence and ask to have spread on the record the printed copy of the loan agreement with regard to this fourth issue, furnished by the witness.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted and placed in the record.

(Agreement between Caja de Credito Hipotecario (Chile) and Kuhn, Loeb & Co., and Guaranty Co. of New York. April 30, 1928. Guaranteed sinking fund 6 percent gold bonds of 1928, was received in evidence, marked "Committee Exhibit 15, of June 28, 1933." See p. 1177.)

Mr. PECORA. Now I see no mention in this letter to the National City Co. of April 30, 1928, of any request made of you by the Chilean Government or the Mortgage Bank of Chile to cede an interest in this underwriting to the National City Co. Have you any written evidence of that request?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes; I think that was embodied in a cable. It is embodied in a cable, of which you have a copy.

Mr. PECORA. Will you read the cable?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Do you want me to read the cable or that excerpt?

Mr. PECORA. Well, the portion of it relating to the interest to be given the National City Co.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The Mortgage Bank said:

We can add that Government will be very glad to learn our bankers and Chilean Government bankers cooperate in this loan.

Mr. PECORA. How does that read?

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. Who is that from?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. This is a cable from the Mortgage Bank of Chile, which says:

We can add that Government—

Mr. PECORA. Addressed to whom?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I can not tell definitely. It was obviously addressed to us, but whether it was addressed to us through Dreyfus & Co. I don't know.

Mr. PECORA. What is the date of it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. It is your copy that I am reading from, Mr. Pecora, and I do not find the date on that, but it would appear to be April 10.

Mr. PECORA. And what is the statement in it referring to the request to include the National City Co.?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER (reading):

We can add that Government would be very glad to learn our bankers and Chilean Government bankers cooperate in this loan.

Mr. PECORA. Well, that is not the request, is it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is the request.

Mr. PECORA. Was that the only request that was made, couched in those terms?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is the only request I find, but that request is ample reason, I should think, for us to be glad to have the National City Co. join hands with us for that loan.

Mr. PECORA. What were the gross profits accruing to the original group on the flotation of this fourth Chilean loan?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The gross spread was 4.315 percent, which included the interest gain, because you see the margin was $3\frac{3}{4}$ percent. The interest gain was 0.565 percent.

Mr. PECORA. What was the gross profit in dollars and cents?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. \$863,000. And at this point, Mr. Pecora, might I add for the record what the original group's profit was in each of these transactions, so that in addition to the gross you have the net?

Mr. PECORA. What was the net, now?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The net to the originating group was \$199,562. The way that was split up was one half percent to Louis Dreyfus & Co., 1.815 percent less expenses for the originating group, and 2 percent selling group commission.

Mr. PECORA. How was this issue marketed?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The same as the previous issue, through a selling group.

Mr. PECORA. Not through an intermediate syndicate between the selling group and the original group?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No; no syndicate.

Mr. PECORA. Was the personnel of the selling group practically the same in all these issues?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I would say it varied. The people on our selling group list would vary from year to year. Substantially the same, but naturally we kept on our list only those that we considered desirable people with whom to do business. Would you want for the record the net profits on these other issues which we have had under discussion, because I can dictate it very easily?

Mr. PECORA. Well, you can prepare a statement on that, if you will, after today's session, that we can put in the record tomorrow.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. All right, sir. It is only three figures.

The CHAIRMAN. You have already stated the other profits?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. We stated the original group profit in the first transaction. In the second and third we did not. It is a matter of dictating six figures.

Mr. PECORA. All right; if you have the figures there.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. In the $6\frac{3}{4}$ percent issue of 1926 the original group's profit was \$252,975.87. That was split 10 percent to Lehman Bros., 45 percent Guaranty Co., 45 percent to Kuhn, Loeb & Co.

In the third issue, which is the 6-percent notes issued December 1926, the originating group's profit was \$159,386.82, split on the same basis, 10 percent Lehman Bros., 45 percent Guaranty Co., 45 percent Kuhn, Loeb & Co.

The 6-percent issue of 1928, which is the one we are at present discussing, the original group's profit, as I stated, was \$199,562.87, divided Lehman Bros., 10 percent; Guaranty Co., National City Co., Kuhn, Loeb & Co., 30 percent each.

Thank you, sir.

Mr. PECORA. In between the third and fourth issues did your firm and the Guaranty Co. make a loan of \$8,000,000 to the Mortgage Bank of Chile?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. For a short term?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Will you give us the details of that?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. On February 3, 1928, we made them an \$8,000,000 loan.

Mr. PECORA. For what period?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. For 6 months. That is, it was to be due August 1, 1928. At par less discount at the rate of 5½ percent per annum. There no intermediary commission.

Mr. PECORA (interposing). Did you distribute that loan among any other participants than yourself and the Guaranty Co.?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No; the Guaranty Co., Kuhn, Loeb Co., and Lehman Bros. had that entire loan.

Mr. PECORA. In the respective proportions of 45, 45, and 10 percent?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Now, that \$8,000,000 short-term advance was repaid when?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That was repaid out of the proceeds of the fourth issue, as was contemplated in that loan arrangement.

Mr. PECORA. In which loan arrangement, the one for the \$8,000,000 short-term advance?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Was any statement made to the investing public at the time the fourth issue was circularized and offered to indicate that out of the proceeds of that fourth issue—\$20,000,000—\$8,000,000 was to be repaid on account of this short-term advance?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The bonds which were security for this \$8,000,000 loan were the bonds which were offered to the public. So you see there was no change in the status of the Mortgage Bank so far as the issue in question was concerned. It was merely a temporary loan made in contemplation of the issuance of this \$20,000,000 of bonds.

Mr. PECORA. But no representation about that was made in the prospectus offering the fourth issue, was it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not think it was, Mr. Pecora.

The CHAIRMAN. This was the only loan that was ever paid?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Sir?

The CHAIRMAN. This was the only loan that was ever paid?

Mr. PECORA. This short-term advance of \$8,000,000?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Well, they paid interest and substantial sinking funds on the other issues, until the time that they were precluded from doing it by the Chilean moratorium.

Mr. PECORA. But this loan was repaid both as to principal and interest in full?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Very shortly afterwards; yes. It was a temporary loan.

I suppose I might mention the other \$8,000,000 temporary advance which was referred to yesterday, which was temporary only at its inception and then became long term. That is the one that is not repaid. It was a loan undertaken similarly, intended to be repaid by an issue of bonds, but the issue was never consummated.

The CHAIRMAN. When was that loan made?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That was made August 7, 1930.

The CHAIRMAN. Eight million?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. \$8,000,000. It was intended to come due February 6, 1931.

The CHAIRMAN. That was never paid?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Never paid.

The CHAIRMAN. Didn't you share that with the Guaranty Co.?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. He said they shared that and their total participation of that loan amounted to only \$600,000.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Not originally. Originally our participation was \$3,600,000.

Mr. PECORA. But you distributed that among other participants until you were left with only \$600,000 of it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. The real fact is at that time it was considered by the people who sought it as a desirable means of investing their short-term funds, and they wanted to participate.

Mr. PECORA. And it was granted to them, with the result that you were left with only \$600,000 participation of your original \$3,600,000?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. Did you in the case of this fourth issue, Mr. Buttenwieser, cause any independent study or investigation to be made of the political, financial, and economic conditions of Chile?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No; but if we had it would have reflected a very good picture.

Mr. PECORA. When was the fifth loan brought out?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. In 1929; June 26.

Mr. PECORA. And that was of a par amount of \$20,000,000?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. \$20,000,000.

Mr. PECORA. Six percent interest, and due in 1962?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. In any of the underwriting of this issue did you cause any independent investigation or study to be made of the political, financial, or economic conditions in Chile?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No. I repeat again, the figures spoke for themselves there. At the end of 1928—I think I said this this morning—the favorable trade balance of Chile was close to \$93,000,000. At the end of 1929 it was \$81,500,000.

The CHAIRMAN. This short-time loan of eight million, was that evidenced by bonds or debentures or notes?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That was evidenced by discount notes with the bonds as collateral, the bonds that it was planned to issue but which never were issued.

Mr. KAHN. May I interject one remark, Mr. Pecora? Our total profits, my firm's total profits on those four transactions, which have been set forth by my partner, were less than \$370,000. Our loss on the loans we made is \$600,000. In other words, "loss" is a strong word to use. I hope it will not be a loss, but at present we are stuck with \$600,000, against which we have an offset of total profits made over a number of years aggregating less than \$370,000. I hope the future will present a pleasanter picture, but that is the picture today.

Mr. PECORA. You might complete the picture, Mr. Kahn, by indicating what the loss to the investing public is from its purchase of these \$90,000,000 of the bonds under existing conditions.

Mr. KAHN. I do not wish, Mr. Pecora, to take any more of your time than I have to, but if you permit me to answer, if you will go through the list of American investments that were considered thoroughly safe and sound in 1929, and even at 1930, and even at the beginning of 1931, I am afraid you will find similar dismal pictures, fully as dismal.

Mr. PECORA. I haven't any doubt of that, but I thought we might put in the whole picture, include the loss to the investing public from the purchase by it of this \$90,000,000 worth of these Chilean bank bonds.

Mr. KAHN. I cannot dispute that. I regret it fully as much as you do, and I hope that the public in the future, just as we with our loss, will see a pleasanter picture and have a pleasanter story to tell.

The CHAIRMAN. The public have some bonds left and may get something, but you do not even have any bonds left?

Mr. KAHN. I beg your pardon?

The CHAIRMAN. I said the public has some bonds left from which they may get something yet, but you do not have any bonds?

Mr. KAHN. We have a note, Senator Fletcher. We hope for the best.

Mr. PECORA. Now, at what price did you and the Guaranty Co. take over the fifth issue in June 1929?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. At 89½ percent. There was an interest gain of 1¾ percent. Do you want the rest, Mr. Pecora?

Mr. PECORA. At what price were they disposed of?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. They were issued at 92 percent and accrued interest. That made the total spread 4¼ percent. Do you want me to continue with the split-up of that?

Mr. PECORA. Yes; if you will.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. One half percent went to Messrs. Louis Dreyfus & Co., 2¼ percent went to the selling group as selling group commission, 1½ percent less expenses was for the originating group, and I regret to add the actual loss on that turned out to be 0.16 percent.

So that our net figure on that to the group was a loss of \$33,518.32, split 10 percent to Lehman Bros., 30 percent to Guaranty Co., 30 percent National City Co., 30 percent Kuhn, Loeb.

Mr. PECORA. Did you have any independent investigation or study made of the political, financial, and economic conditions of Chile for the purpose of determining whether or not you would underwrite this issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. In June of 1929 everything seemed flourishing throughout the world, but my answer to your question is, no. But I repeat again that conditions at that time were very favorable.

Mr. PECORA. There was a 4 point spread there?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Four and one quarter spread; yes. That interest accounted for that.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Buttenwieser, had not the financial condition respecting the Chilean bank materially changed between the fourth and fifth issues?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. I do not know to what you allude, Mr. Pecora. If you will amplify it.

Mr. PECORA. Have you got the balance sheet of the Mortgage Bank of Chile as of December 31, 1928?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Will you look at the balance sheet of the bank as of December 31, 1928?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir; I have it before me.

Mr. PECORA. And you find an item there, don't you, amounting to \$26,262,491.12, among its assets?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. What does that represent?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is a guaranty of the Chilean Government in respect of bonds issued under the law of June 15, 1925, and January 31, 1928.

Mr. PECORA. And that was the guaranty of the Government to that extent back of some of these mortgage bonds, wasn't it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is their way of entering the guaranty of the Government on particular bonds; yes.

Mr. PECORA. And the total assets, inclusive of that figure, of the bank was \$88,732,000 odd dollars?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No, Mr. Pecora. In Chilean pesos it was 1,526,000,000. In pounds sterling it was 133,000. In French francs it is 44,000,000. And United States dollars it was 88,000,000.

Mr. PECORA. Well, I am speaking of it now in terms of American dollars.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. No. You have got to add them crosswise. In other words all the assets of the bank are not 133,000 pounds. You have got to add that crosswise. They keep their balance sheet in Chilean pesos, pounds sterling, French francs and United States dollars, the way they had obligations outstanding, just the same as the liabilities of the bank are kept that way. They had for instance \$88,000,000 of United States dollar, obligations. They had assets of \$88,000,000. You have to take the cross total of these two columns.

Mr. PECORA. Have you a copy of the loan agreement covering this fifth issue?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. Will you produce it for the record?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Yes, surely [producing document].

Mr. PECORA. I offer that in evidence and ask that it be spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be received.

(Document headed "Agreement between Caja de Credito Hipotecario (Chile) and Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and Guaranty Co. of New York,

May 1, 1929, guaranteed sinking fund 6 percent gold bonds of 1929", was thereupon designated "Committee Exhibit 16, June 28, 1933." See p. 1187.)

Mr. PECORA. I think I would like to examine Mr. Kahn now for a while, if I may.

TESTIMONY OF OTTO H. KAHN, A PARTNER OF KUHN, LOEB & CO.—Resumed

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, who prepares the income-tax returns to the Federal Government for your firm?

Mr. KAHN. Mr. Langenbach, our chief accountant.

Mr. PECORA. And does he also prepare the income-tax returns for the individual members of the firm, do you know?

Mr. KAHN. Some of them, yes, I believe.

Mr. PECORA. Did he prepare them in your individual behalf?

Mr. KAHN. No.

Mr. PECORA. Who prepared yours?

Mr. KAHN. That is rather a confused story. Mine was being prepared until a couple of years ago mainly with the cooperation of one gentleman who has since died. It is now being prepared with the cooperation of a number of people, one of them being my secretary.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recall whether or not you paid any income taxes for the year 1930?

Mr. KAHN. No, sir.

Mr. PECORA. That is, you do not recall, or you recall that you did not?

Mr. KAHN. I recall that I paid no income tax for 1930.

Mr. PECORA. How about for the year 1931?

Mr. KAHN. None for 1931.

Mr. PECORA. How about for the year 1932?

Mr. KAHN. And none for 1932. I hope there will be a different picture for 1933.

Mr. PECORA. You did pay a very substantial one for 1929?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. And for 1928?

Mr. KAHN. Also, yes.

Mr. PECORA. Now, do you recall having made any sales of securities during the last part or, to be specific, on about December 30, 1930, at an indicated loss of \$117,584, the securities in question being 1,000 shares of Electric Power & Light Corporation, 1,000 shares of International Nickel Co., 500 shares of Manhattan-Dearborn Co., 250 shares of Reynolds Metal Co., and 600 shares of Tubize Chatillon Co., series B?

Mr. KAHN. Do I recall having made those sales, Mr. Pecora? Is that your question?

Mr. PECORA. I beg your pardon, sir?

Mr. KAHN. Is your question whether I recall having made those?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. KAHN. I am afraid I do not.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recall owning securities of the kind that I have mentioned?

Mr. KAHN. I am afraid I may be forfeiting whatever opinion for knowledge I may have gained heretofore, but if there is one

subject on which my knowledge is less than it is on income-tax affairs I do not know it. My ignorance of income-tax affairs is abysmal, and always has been, I am afraid always will be, and I am afraid, with every desire to answer your questions categorically, I cannot tell you anything about it which would be any more than the merest guesswork.

Mr. PECORA. No; I simply asked you if you recall owning securities of the kind that I have referred to or mentioned. I will repeat: Electric Power & Light Corporation, International Nickel Co., Manhattan-Dearborn Co., Reynolds Metal Co., Tubize Chatillon Co., series B.

Mr. KAHN. Some of them have a gloomily familiar sound. [Laughter.]

Mr. PECORA. You say a gloomingly familiar sound?

Mr. KAHN. A gloomily familiar sound.

Mr. PECORA. Why are they gloomily familiar?

Mr. KAHN. Because, according to my recollection, they did not turn out well. They turned out lemons, most of them, not all of them.

Mr. PECORA. Well, perhaps because they did not turn out well it might refresh your recollection as to whether or not, on December 30, 1930, you sold blocks of those securities at an indicated total loss of \$117,584.

Mr. KAHN. I am afraid I cannot answer anything differently, but that I do not recall.

Mr. PECORA. Is there anything, any record or memoranda in your possession, that would refresh your recollection about any such sale of those securities on that date, namely, December 30, 1930?

Mr. KAHN. There are none in my possession.

Mr. MOORE. You asked Mr. Kahn's office for a schedule, and we might check to see, if you call those off again. I don't know whether it refreshes Mr. Kahn's memory or not, but there are—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). One thousand shares of Electric Power & Light Corporation.

Mr. MOORE. Wait just a minute. Yes; we found 1,000 shares of Electric Power & Light.

Mr. PECORA. One thousand shares of International Nickel Co.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. MOORE. Yes; rights.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. Rights.

Mr. MOORE. Rights or shares? Oh, here it is up here, 1,000 International Nickel Co.

Mr. KAHN. Right.

Mr. PECORA. Five hundred shares of Manhattan-Dearborn Co.

Mr. MOORE. How many shares?

Mr. PECORA. Five hundred. I understand they are included in a block of 2,000.

Mr. MOORE. Oh, yes; 2,000 shares.

Mr. PECORA. Two hundred and fifty shares of Reynolds Metal Co., which I understand are included in a block of 1,000 shares.

Mr. MOORE. Yes; a thousand shares.

Mr. PECORA. Six hundred shares of Tubize Chatillon Co. B, which I understand is included in a block of 2,400.

Mr. MOORE. There is 2,400 on this list.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Now, from the records I see before you, can you refresh your recollection, then tell us whether or not on December 30, 1930, you sold those securities at an indicated or reported loss of \$117,584?

Mr. KAHN. I am trying to find out, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. MOORE. Will you read off the amounts of that again, because the only thing we have are the amounts sold?

Mr. PECORA. What amounts do you want me to read off?

Mr. MOORE. I mean the number of shares you refer to, because we haven't got it here.

Mr. PECORA. One thousand shares of Electric Power & Light.

Mr. MOORE. All right.

Mr. PECORA. One thousand shares of International Nickel Co.

Mr. MOORE. Right.

Mr. PECORA. Five hundred shares of Manhattan-Dearborn.

Mr. MOORE. Out of 2,000? Is that right?

Mr. PECORA. I understand so. Two hundred and fifty shares of Reynolds Metal Co.

Mr. MOORE. Out of 1,000? Two hundred and fifty Reynolds Metal Co.

Mr. PECORA. And 600 shares of Tubize Chatillon Co. B out of a block of 2,400.

Mr. MOORE. How many, 600?

Mr. PECORA. Six hundred shares.

(Mr. Kahn and Mr. Moore and others conferred and referred to documents.)

Mr. PECORA. Have you any recollection of those transactions, Mr. Kahn?

Mr. KAHN. I have no recollection, Mr. Pecora. I am afraid I would have to give you the same answer as to pretty nearly anything that you may ask about my income-tax returns. They were prepared, they were put before me by people in whom I had implicit confidence, and who are good enough to charge themselves with relieving me, an exceedingly busy man, of the details of these accounting matters, of which I am particularly little competent—an exceedingly busy man not merely in my own business but in a great many other matters that interest me and take by time, and probably less interested in my own financial affairs than in anything else which I am paying attention to and having a duty towards.

Therefore, I fear, with the greatest desire to give you all the facts, you will not find me as responsive a witness as I would like to be, not from any lack of desire but from lack of actual knowledge.

Now, I find these stocks that you have indicated on this list, and the presumption from this list is that they were sold, but I cannot tell you from my own knowledge.

Mr. PECORA. Did you direct the sales of securities owned by you?

Mr. KAHN. Some of them I would. Some of them others would. A good many people butted in, with my full willingness and consent. I was only too glad to be relieved of looking after these matters.

Mr. PECORA. Well now, do you recall that on December 30, 1930, there were assigned to you by your daughter, Maude E. Marriot,

certain securities which included the five blocks of stock that I have enumerated?

Mr. KAHN. Not to my knowledge, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recall having been questioned by any representative of the Internal Revenue Department with respect to these particular sales of securities that I have referred to?

Mr. KAHN. No, Mr. Pecora; I have not been so questioned, but I know that every return of mine has been gone over by a revenue officer very carefully, spending days at my office, and I have been asked no such question.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, have you in your possession—by that I mean anywhere under your control, if not physically in your possession at the moment—a copy of your income-tax return for the year 1930?

Mr. KAHN. I believe Mr. Moore has one; yes.

Mr. PECORA. Is it with you?

Mr. MOORE. Yes.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Have you got it before you?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Will you refer to it and from it see if you can refresh your recollection as to whether or not you made on December 30, 1930, sales of the five blocks of securities that I have already enumerated?

Senator TOWNSEND. Mr. Kahn, you are not in the habit of making your own income-tax report, I am sure?

Mr. KAHN. Oh, no indeed.

Senator TOWNSEND. Is there anyone here who makes your reports for you?

Mr. KAHN. No. Mr. Pecora, I wonder whether you would help me a little. Those things are quite unfamiliar to me. Can you tell me where I can find that? You probably have a copy of that report before you.

Mr. PECORA. Will you look in the itemized list known as "schedule C" attached to your report?

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. Mr. Pecora, the items you have inquired about, I understand, were made the subject of an objection by the internal-revenue examiner. The matter was taken up, I think, at Washington and finally decided in Mr. Kahn's favor. I knew nothing about it. I know nothing about it now. Mr. Stroock, who handled it, is here, and he can explain it to you if you wish him to do so. The protest was made while Mr. Kahn was in Europe. He never saw it. He didn't sign it, and it was signed by somebody on his behalf, and I suppose that is why he is so utterly ignorant about it.

Mr. PECORA. Well, if he can refresh his recollection from the sheet before him right now, I have no objection to that being a means of refreshing his recollection.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. The statement has just been made to me. I do not know anything about it.

Mr. PECORA. What is that?

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. That statement has just been made to me by Mr. Stroock, who is sitting behind me and who conducted this protest in Washington.

The CHAIRMAN. Protest as to what items?

MR. DE GERSDORFF. These items were deducted as losses in this report, and the internal-revenue examiner disallowed them.

MR. PECORA. Disallowed the deduction?

MR. DE GERSDORFF. Yes.

MR. PECORA. Of one hundred seventeen thousand-odd dollars?

MR. DE GERSDORFF. Yes; whatever the amount was. And an appeal of the protest to that was taken up with the Department at Washington and was decided in Mr. Kahn's favor, so I am advised. That was while he was in Europe. He did not sign the protest.

MR. PECORA. Substantially that accords with my information, Mr. de Gersdorff.

MR. KAHN. Would that explain my incapacity to find what you want me to find?

MR. PECORA. Well, now, what I would like to have you refresh your recollection about is with respect to a certain assignment to you by Maude E. Marriott, who, I understand, is your daughter.

MR. KAHN. Yes.

MR. PECORA. Of certain securities, under an assignment that bears date December 31, 1930. Do you recall such an assignment, Mr. Kahn?

MR. KAHN. I recall certain assignments, the same way in which I recall other events which have passed out of my consciousness and out of my knowledge. Perhaps I may be permitted to say that in order to recall those matters which are of real importance in the duties which I fulfill I deliberately discharge from my mind those things which I think I do not have to remember. I do it by habit and by training, and this is one of the things which I do not remember, because, presumably, I did not have to remember it. I am far from disputing that it occurred, but I cannot tell you that it did occur.

MR. PECORA. Well, have you completely forgotten anything about such an assignment made to you by your daughter under an instrument dated December 31, 1930?

MR. KAHN. I have a recollection that there was such an assignment. I do not recollect the circumstances of the case. I do not recollect the details. I could not possibly tell them to you.

MR. PECORA. I would suggest, then, Mr. Kahn, that between now and the session tomorrow morning you seek to refresh your recollection, either by consulting records or by consulting the recollection of any of your counsel, with respect to this particular instrument of assignment.

MR. KAHN. I will diligently do so. I will try my best to do so, Mr. Pecora, and I hope to be able to be a more competent witness tomorrow than I am just now.

MR. PECORA. I suggest, then, Mr. Chairman, that we adjourn until tomorrow morning.

The chairman (after informal discussion off the record). We will take a recess now until tomorrow morning at 10 o'clock.

(Whereupon, at 4:20 o'clock p.m., a recess was taken until tomorrow, Thursday, June 29, 1933, at 10 o'clock a.m.)

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 10, JUNE 28, 1933

Agreement, dated June 25, 1924, made in the city and State of New York, in the United States of America, between Caja de Credito Hipotecario, of Santiago, Chile, organized under the laws of Chile (hereinafter called the Caja) acting

by His Excellency, the Honorable Beltran Mathieu, Chilean Ambassador to the United States of America, thereunto duly authorized, and Kuhn, Loeb & Co., a copartnership of the city and State of New York, and Guaranty Co. of New York, a corporation organized under the laws of the State of New York (hereinafter called the bankers).

In consideration of the mutual covenants hereinafter set forth, it is agreed as follows:

1. The Caja will forthwith create an issue of bonds to be known as "the guaranteed sinking fund 6½ percent gold bonds of the Caja" (hereinafter called the bonds) limited to \$20,000,000 principal amount, to constitute the loan designated "amprestito oro Caja Hipotecario, 1925." The bonds shall be issued in accordance with the law of the Republic of Chile of August 29, 1855, establishing the Caja, and the law of the Republic of Chile, dated September 10, 1892, which authorizes the issue of obligations payable in foreign moneys, and in accordance with the decree law dated March 9, 1925, and the Executive decree dated June 15, 1925 (supplementing said decree law), which authorize the guaranty of the bonds by the Republic of Chile.

The bonds shall be in coupon form, payable to bearer, shall be dated June 30, 1925, shall mature June 30, 1957, shall bear interest from June 30, 1925, at the rate of 6½ percent per annum, payable semiannually on June 30 and December 31 in each year and shall be in the denominations of \$1,000 and \$500 in such proportions as the bankers may request. The principal of and interest on the bonds shall be payable without deduction for any taxes, imposts, levies, or duties of any nature, now or at any time hereafter imposed by the Republic of Chile or by any State, Province, municipality, or other taxing authority thereof or therein, and shall be paid, at the option of the holders, in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the Office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co., or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of or equal to the standard of weight and fineness existing June 30, 1925, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, and shall be paid in time of war as well as in time of peace and whether the holder be a citizen or resident of a friendly or hostile state. The bonds shall be authenticated by the certificate endorsed thereon of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, registrar of the loan hereinafter appointed.

The Republic of Chile shall unconditionally guarantee to the holders of the bonds prompt payment of the principal of, and the interest on, the bonds, as and when the same shall become due and payable, and also prompt payment to the fiscal agents, hereinafter appointed, of the semiannual payments for the service of interest and amortization of the bonds hereinafter mentioned as and when the same shall become due and payable, and such guaranty shall be endorsed on the bonds. The text of the guaranty shall be substantially in the form hereto annexed and marked "schedule B".

2. The text of the definitive engraved bonds shall be in the English language substantially in the form hereto annexed and marked "schedule A", and shall bear a notation in Spanish substantially in the form shown on said schedule A. The text of the usual certificate of the Treasury Department of the Republic of Chile on bonds of the Caja shall be in Spanish, or in both English and Spanish, as the bankers may elect, in such form as may be required by Chilean law. The Caja hereby authorized the bankers to cause to be prepared without delay engraved bonds for execution by or on behalf of the Caja, such bonds to be engraved and printed in New York in accordance with the requirements of the New York Stock Exchange. The bankers may issue or cause to be issued by a bank or trust company in New York temporary interim certificates which, if issued, shall in due course be exchangeable without cost or expense to the bankers or the holders for definitive engraved bonds.

The definitive bonds shall bear the facsimile signature of Don Louis Barros Borgono, the president of the board of directors of the Caja, and shall be manually signed by Don Francisco Bahamondes, the cashier of the Caja, or other duly authorized officer of the Caja. The certificate of the Treasury Department shall be signed manually or otherwise as may be required by Chilean law. The coupons shall bear the facsimile signature of Don Louis Barros Borgono, the president of the board of directors of the Caja. The guaranty of the Republic of Chile endorsed on the bonds shall be manually signed by His Excellency, the Honorable Beltran Mathieu, the Chilean Ambassador to the United States of America, thereunto duly authorized by the Government of

the Republic of Chile or by some other duly authorized representative of the Republic of Chile.

3. Until all of the bonds shall have been retired or redeemed, the Caja shall pay to the fiscal agents as an annuity for the service of interest and amortization of the bonds the sum of \$1,492,800 per annum in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid, except as hereinafter in this article provided. Such sums shall be paid in equal semiannual instalments at least 15 days before the 30th day of June and the 31st day of December in each year as hereinafter in article 5 hereof provided.

The fiscal agents shall apply each installment to the payment of the interest maturing on the next succeeding interest date on the bonds then outstanding and shall apply the part of each such installment not required for the payment of such interest as a sinking fund for the redemption of bonds on such interest date as hereinafter provided.

The Caja may, at its option, increase the amount of any semiannual installment to be applied to the redemption of bonds on any semiannual interest date, and, in the event of any such increase, all subsequent semiannual installments shall be reduced to an amount sufficient to provide for the semiannual service of interest and amortization of the bonds which shall be outstanding after the application of such increased sinking-fund installment to the redemption of bonds, such amount to be calculated as a cumulative sinking fund compounded semiannually at the rate of 6½ percent per annum to redeem, on or before June 30, 1957, all of the bonds so outstanding. Any such reduced semiannual installment may similarly be increased in which event subsequent semiannual installments shall be similarly reduced. This right is reserved because repayments of the mortgage loans made by the Caja may be made by the borrowers either in cash or in bonds of the Caja in excess of the fixed minimum amortization payments, and the Caja is not permitted by law to have its bonds outstanding in excess of the mortgage loans against which they are issued.

The part of each semiannual installment available for the redemption of bonds shall be applied to the redemption of bonds by lot at 100 percent of their principal amount on the interest date next succeeding the date of such payment.

The numbers of the bonds to be redeemed on each such interest date shall be drawn by lot in any usual manner. The drawings shall be held in public at the principal office of the Caja in the city of Santiago. The Caja shall notify the fiscal agent of the aggregate principal amount and numbers of the bonds to be redeemed on each interest date and such notification shall be sent to the fiscal agents at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. in the city of New York so as to be received at said office at least 45 days prior to such interest date. The numbers of the bonds so drawn for redemption shall be advertised at least twice in two daily newspapers of general circulation in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, the first advertisement to appear not less than 30 days prior to the redemption date. If the New York Stock Exchange so requires, the advertisement shall be further published.

The bonds so called for redemption shall on the redemption date designated in such notice become due and payable at one hundred percent of their principal amount and shall be payable, at the option of the holders, in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, and shall be paid by the Caja on and after the redemption date at the redemption price aforesaid on presentation and surrender of such bonds at any of said offices, together with all coupons thereto appertaining maturing after the redemption date. If any bond so presented shall not be accompanied by all coupons maturing after the redemption date, then said bond shall be paid at the redemption price aforesaid less the aggregate principal amount of all coupons maturing after the redemption date not presented and surrendered with said bonds; provided that if more than four such coupons are not presented and surrendered with said bond, the fiscal agents or the Caja may refuse to pay said bond. Notice having been so given by publication, the bonds so called for redemption shall cease to bear interest from the redemption date unless they shall not be so paid by the Caja upon presentation and surrender thereof with all coupons maturing after the redemption date.

No expenses in connection with the redemption of the bonds or the operation of the sinking fund shall be charged against the sinking fund, but such expenses shall be paid by the Caja.

4. All notices or other announcements relating to the redemption of the bonds, the payment of the coupons or any other matter in connection with the bonds may be given or made by the fiscal agents, jointly or severally, on behalf of the Caja as the fiscal agents shall deem proper, but all expenses in connection therewith shall be paid by the Caja.

All bonds redeemed through the sinking fund with all unmatured coupons thereto appertaining and all coupons paid by the fiscal agents shall deem proper, but all expenses in connection therewith shall be paid by the Caja.

All bonds redeemed through the sinking fund with all unmatured coupons thereto appertaining and all coupons paid by the fiscal agents shall be cancelled by the fiscal agents and by them delivered to a representative of the Caja, for that purpose in the city of New York or sent by registered mail insured to and at the risk and expense of the Caja. All bonds paid in Santiago by the Caja, and all bonds delivered to the Caja in payment of its loans shall be sent, as soon as practicable after such payment or delivery, to the fiscal agents for cancellation at the risk and expense of the Caja, and no bonds delivered to the Caja in payment of its loans shall be re-issued or renegotiated by the Caja.

5. So long as any of the bonds shall be outstanding the Caja covenants to pay to the fiscal agents at their respective offices in the city of New York in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid—

(a) At least 15 days before June 30 and December 31 in each year the sum of \$746,400 (or, in the event that the Caja shall have increased the amount of any previous semiannual installment as provided in art. 3 hereof, such lesser amount as may be due as provided in said art. 3) to be applied to the service of interest and amortization of the bonds as provided in art. 3 hereof, the first payment to be made at least 15 days before December 31, 1925, and the last payment to be made at least 15 days before June 30, 1957; and if the Caja shall elect to increase the amount of any such semiannual installment as provided in art. 3 hereof, the amount of any such increase at least 15 days before the interest date on which such amount is to be applied to the redemption of bonds. One half of each payment made pursuant to this paragraph (a) shall be made to Kuhn, Loeb & Co. at their office in the city of New York, and one half of each such payment shall be made to Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, at its principal office in the city of New York:

(b) At least 15 days before June 30, 1957, a sum equal to the principal amount of all the bonds then outstanding, one half of such payment to be made to Kuhn, Loeb & Co. at their office in the city of New York, and one half of such payment to be made to Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, at its principal office in the City of New York. Any amounts in the sinking fund to be applied to the redemption of bonds on June 30, 1957, at the time of the payment made pursuant to this paragraph (b) shall be credited against such payment; and

(c) Such amounts as may be required to meet all expenses incident to the service of the loan, including the compensation and expenses of the registrar: such payments to be made from time to time, on the joint written or cabled request of the fiscal agent or agents stated in such request.

The fiscal agents shall not be required to segregate any moneys paid to or deposited with them as hereinbefore provided. The Caja irrevocably authorizes and directs the fiscal agents and each of them to pay out of the moneys paid to them as hereinbefore provided the interest on the bonds to the bearers of the coupons upon presentation and surrender thereof, and the principal of the bonds at maturity or on the redemption dates, as the case may be, to the bearers of the bonds to be paid or redeemed upon presentation and surrender thereof, and to apply the moneys in the sinking fund to the redemption of the bonds, and to make every such payment without further formality except as the fiscal agents or either of them may be advised may be necessary to comply with some law or regulation of the United States of America or other public authority therein.

6. The Caja during the life of the loan will maintain in the Borough of Manhattan, in the City of New York, a fiscal agency or fiscal agencies of the loan and a registry of the loan. The Caja appoints Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, of the city and State of New York, United States of America, to be fiscal agents of the loan during the life of the loan subject to the terms and conditions of this agreement. The Caja also appoints said Guaranty Trust Co. of New York as registrar of the loan during the life of the loan subject to the terms and conditions of this agreement.

7. Neither the fiscal agents nor the registrar shall be liable otherwise than for good faith and the exercise of reasonable care. The fiscal agents and the registrar and each of them shall be protected in any action which any of them may take in acting on any bond or coupon or any notice, request or other paper believed by them or it be genuine as well as in or in respect of any action taken or suffered in good faith under the advice of counsel. Neither of the bankers and neither of the fiscal agents shall be liable for any act or omission of the other.

8. The Caja shall pay each of the fiscal agents as compensation for their services a commission of one quarter of 1 percent of the amount of all payments made to such fiscal agent pursuant to paragraphs (a) and (b) of article 5 hereof, such compensation to be paid to the fiscal agents at the time when such payments are made to the fiscal agents. The Caja shall also pay the fiscal agents as compensation for their services a compensation of one quarter of 1 percent of the principal amount of all bonds delivered to the Caja in payment of its mortgage loans; one half of such compensation to be paid to each of the fiscal agents at the time when such bonds are sent to the fiscal agents for cancellation as provided in article 4 hereof.

9. In case any of the bonds shall become mutilated, destroyed, or lost, a new bond (having endorsed thereon the guaranty of the Republic of Chile in this agreement provided for) of like amount, tenor, and date, bearing the same number and bearing all unmatured coupons, shall be issued by the Caja, but only if permitted by and in accordance with Chilean law, and the registrar shall authenticate the same for delivery in exchange for, and upon cancellation of, the bond so mutilated and its unmatured coupons, or in lieu of the bond so destroyed or lost and its unmatured coupons, but in the case of destroyed or lost bonds only upon receipt by the Caja and the registrar of evidence satisfactory to each of them that such bonds were destroyed or lost and, if required, upon receipt also of indemnity satisfactory to each of them in their discretion. The registrar shall incur no liability for such action.

10. The Caja agrees to sell and deliver to the bankers and the bankers agree to purchase from the Caja and pay for \$20,000,000 aggregate principal amount of the bonds at the price of 93 percent of the principal amount thereof, being \$18,600,000.

In the first instance an appropriately executed temporary bond (which may be printed, written, or typewritten) for \$20,000,000 in substantially the form hereto annexed and marked "Schedule C", and endorsed with the guaranty of the Republic of Chile substantially in the form hereto annexed and marked "Schedule D", shall be delivered on or before June 30, 1925, to Banco de Chile, in Santiago, Chile, which is hereby designated as the agent of the bankers to receive such delivery. The charges of such representative in Santiago, Chile, shall be paid by the Caja. Payment of \$4,650,000, the first installment of the purchase price, shall be made on July 1, 1925, unless such time be extended by the bankers at the request of the Caja, and, in that case, within the period of such extension on 5 days' notice to the bankers in writing, but such payment shall not be made until after receipt of cable advice from Banco de Chile by Guaranty Trust Co. of New York of the delivery of such temporary bond. Payment of \$4,650,000, the second installment, of the purchase price, shall be made on the ninth day following the payment of the first installment, and payment of \$9,300,000, the final installment of the purchase price, shall be made on the nineteenth day following the payment of the first installment.

Such payments shall be made by placing the amount of each installment of the purchase price to the credit of the Caja in dollars in the city of New York, one half of each such installment to be credited to the account of the Caja with Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and one half of each such installment to be credited to the account of the Caja with Guaranty Trust Co. of New York. The amounts so credited to the Caja shall be withdrawn upon the order of such person or persons as may be authorized to draw upon the same by the Caja, and all withdrawals shall be made in substantially equal amounts from Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and from Guaranty Trust Co. of New York.

Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and Guaranty Trust Co. of New York shall each credit the Caja with interest at the current rate which New York Clearing House banks may then be paying on the amounts so credited with them respectively, until disbursed by the Caja.

11. Forthwith upon the execution of this agreement the Caja will deliver or cause to be delivered to the bankers a prospectus letter or letters con-

taining information concerning the financial position of the Caja and of the Republic of Chile, its debts, income and expenditures and financial administration and such other information and in such form as the bankers may reasonably request and as shall be satisfactory to the bankers' consul, such letter or letters to be signed by the Chilean Ambassador to the United States of America.

12. It is a condition precedent to any obligation of the bankers hereunder (a) that the Caja shall have promptly delivered a prospectus letter as set forth above in article 11 hereof, and (b) that on or before June 30, 1925, unless the time be extended by the bankers at the request of the Caja as hereinbefore provided, and, in that case, within the period of such extension, (1) the Caja shall have delivered to the representative of the bankers in Chile duly authenticated copies of the laws or decrees or other instruments authorizing the issue of the bonds by the Caja and the guaranty of the bonds by the Republic of Chile in accordance with the terms of this agreement and also duly certified copies of all proceedings of the Caja and all executive and other decrees of the Government of the Republic of Chile necessary to comply with said laws in connection with the execution and delivery of the bonds hereunder; (2) the bankers shall have received an opinion satisfactory to the bankers' counsel in New York, approving the proceedings of the Caja authorizing the creation, issue, and sale of the bonds and approving the guaranty of the bonds by the Republic of Chile, in accordance with the terms of this agreement, and the validity of the bonds, both temporary and definitive, in the hands of holders of whatever citizenship or residence, in accordance with the terms of the bonds and of this agreement; and (3) that the bankers' counsel in New York shall have approved the form of the bonds and coupons.

13. The Caja will pay all stamp and other duties, if any, to which under the laws of Chile or of the United States of America this agreement or the bonds may be subject. The Caja will also pay the cost of printing, engraving, executing, and authenticating the temporary and definitive bonds and interim certificates, the expense of exchanging the temporary bond and interim certificates for definitive bonds and of transporting the temporary and definitive bonds to and from Santiago, and the compensation and expenses of the registrar. The Caja will also pay the fees and disbursements of the Chilean counsel referred to in article 12 hereof.

14. The Caja hereby covenants and agrees that no bonds issued or guaranteed by it other than the bonds purchased by the bankers hereunder shall be sold or offered for sale in the United States of America prior to January 1, 1926, except with the written consent of the bankers.

The Caja will deliver to the bankers on or before June 30, 1925, in form satisfactory to the bankers' counsel, the written assurance of the Republic of Chile that no issue of bonds of the Republic of Chile or guaranteed by the Republic of Chile, will be sold or offered for sale in the United States of America prior to October 1, 1925, at a price which will yield to maturity a higher rate of interest than the rate which the bonds purchased by the bankers hereunder will yield to maturity at the price at which the bonds shall be offered for public subscription by the bankers.

15. The Caja hereby covenants and agrees that it will not issue or sell any securities of the Caja in the United States of America, or issue or sell any securities intended to be sold or offered for sale in the United States of America prior to July 1, 1928, without first giving the bankers a 30-day option to purchase such securities on terms and conditions at least as favorable to the bankers as the Caja is able to obtain from other sources at the time when such issue or sale is proposed. If the bankers shall not exercise such option within the 30-day period, the Caja shall have the right to offer such securities elsewhere on terms and conditions not less favorable to the Caja than those offered to the bankers. The Caja will not reoffer such securities, or accept offers therefor, on terms and conditions less favorable to the Caja without giving the bankers a 30-day option to purchase such securities on such less favorable terms and conditions. The Caja, however, reserves the right to negotiate through an agent who will be instructed to work in accordance with these conditions.

16. The Caja will at the request of the bankers make or cause to be made application for the listing of the bonds and interim certificates on the New York Stock Exchange or the bankers may themselves make such application for and on account of the Caja. The Caja will furnish to the bankers all documents deemed by the bankers to be advantageous for the making of such appli-

ation and it will take and undertake all such action as may be requisite in accordance with the requirements of said exchange in order to secure such listing. The cost and expenses of such application, whether made by the bankers or by the Caja, shall be paid by the Caja.

17. Reference in this agreement to the fiscal agents or either of them shall be deemed to include any successor firm or corporation however constituted continuing the business of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and/or Guaranty Trust Co. of New York. Reference in this agreement to the registrar shall be deemed to include any successor corporation continuing the business of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York. Reference in this agreement to the bankers, or either of them, shall be deemed to include any successor firm or corporation however constituted continuing the business of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and/or Guaranty Co. of New York.

In witness whereof Caja de Credito Hipotecario has caused this agreement to be signed in its behalf by His Excellency the Honorable Beltran Mathieu thereunto duly authorized and Kuhn, Loeb & Co. have signed this agreement and Guaranty Co. of New York has caused this agreement to be signed by its president or one of its vice presidents and its corporate seal to be affixed hereto and attested by its secretary or an assistant secretary as of the day and year first above written.

CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO,
By B. MATHIEU.
KUHNS, LOEB & CO. [L. S.]
GUARANTY CO. OF NEW YORK,
By H. STANLEY, *President*.

[SEAL]

Attest:

W. R. NELSON, *Secretary*.

The undersigned accept their appointment as fiscal agents under the foregoing agreement upon the terms and conditions thereof; and the undersigned Guaranty Trust Co. of New York also accepts its appointment as registrar thereunder upon the terms and conditions thereof.

KUHNS, LOEB & CO.
GUARANTY TRUST CO. OF NEW YORK,
By H. STANLEY, *Vice President*.

SCHEDULE A

[Form of definitive bond]

No. _____

§ _____

CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO (CHILE) (MORTGAGE BANK OF CHILE) GUARANTEED
SINKING FUND 6½ PERCENT GOLD BOND DUE JUNE 30, 1957

Letra de credito al Portador, por U.S.—\$—— oro (dollars americanos) que ganan el 6½ percent de interes anual.—Reembolsable por sorteos semestrales a mas tardar en 32 anos.—Los interes y amortizaciones se pagan el 31 de Diciembre y 30 de Junio, en cambio del cupon respectivo o de la letra amortizada.—Caja de Credito Hipotecario (herein called the Caja), for value received, promises to pay to the bearer on June 30, 1957, the sum of \$—— and to pay interest thereon from June 30, 1925, until the principal of this bond is paid at the rate of 6½ percent per annum, semi-annually, on June 30 and December 31 in each year, upon presentation and surrender of the coupons hereto annexed as they severally mature.

The principal of, and interest on, this bond are payable at the option of the holder, in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of or equal to the standard of weight and fineness existing on June 30, 1925, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, and will be paid without deduction for any taxes, imposts, levies or duties of any nature now or at any time hereafter imposed by the Republic of Chile or by any State, Province, municipality, or other taxing authority thereof or therein, and will be paid in time of war as well as in time of peace and whether the holder be a citizen or resident of a friendly or hostile State.

This bond is one of an issue of bonds known as the "Guaranteed sinking fund 6½ percent gold bonds of the Caja" (herein called the bonds) limited to \$20,000,000 principal amount, issued in accordance with the laws of the Republic of Chile dated August 29, 1855 and September 10, 1892, the decree law dated March 9, 1925, and the Executive decree dated June 15, 1925, supplementing said decree law, constituting the loan designated *Emprestito oro Caja Hipotecaria*, 1925.

Until all the bonds shall have been retired or redeemed the Caja will pay to the fiscal agents as an annuity for the service of interest and amortization of the bonds the sum of \$1,492,800 per annum in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid, except as hereinafter provided. Such sums shall be paid in equal semiannual installments before the 30th day of June and the 31st day of December in each year, the first payment to be made before December 31, 1925, and the last payment to be made before June 30, 1957. The fiscal agents shall apply each such installment to the payment of the interest maturing on the next succeeding interest date on the bonds then outstanding and shall apply the part of each such installment not required for the payment of such interest as a sinking fund for the redemption of bonds on such interest date as hereinafter provided. The Caja may, at its option, increase the amount of any semiannual installment to be applied to the redemption of bonds on any semiannual interest date, and, in the event of any such increase, all subsequent semiannual installments shall be reduced to an amount sufficient to provide for the semiannual service of interest and amortization of the bonds which shall be outstanding after the application of such increased sinking fund installment to the redemption of bonds, such amount to be calculated as a cumulative sinking fund compounded semiannually at the rate of 6½ percent per annum to redeem, on or before June 30, 1957, all of the bonds so outstanding. Any such reduced semiannual installment may similarly be increased in which event subsequent semiannual installments shall be similarly reduced.

The part of each semiannual installment available for the redemption of bonds shall be applied to the redemption of bonds by lot at 100 percent of their principal amount on the interest date next succeeding the date of such payment. The numbers of the bonds to be redeemed on each such interest date shall be drawn by lot in any usual manner. The drawings shall be held in public in the principal office of the Caja in the city of Santiago. The numbers of the bonds so drawn for redemption shall be advertised at least twice in two daily newspapers of general circulation in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, the first advertisement to appear not less than 30 days prior to the redemption date. The bonds so called for redemption shall on the redemption date designated in such notice become due and payable at 100 percent of their principal amount, and shall be payable, at the option of the holders, in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Company of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja on and after the redemption date at the redemption price aforesaid on presentation and surrender of such bonds at any of said offices, together with all coupons thereto appertaining maturing after the redemption date. If any bond so presented shall not be accompanied by all coupons maturing after the redemption date, then said bond shall be paid at the redemption price aforesaid less the aggregate principal amount of all coupons maturing after the redemption date not presented and surrendered with said bond; provided that, if more than four such coupons are not presented and surrendered with said bond the fiscal agents or the Caja may refuse to pay said bond. Notice having been so given by publication the bonds so called for redemption shall cease to bear interest from the redemption date unless they shall not be so paid by the Caja upon presentation and surrender thereof with all coupons maturing after the redemption date.

This bond and the coupons appertaining thereto shall pass by delivery.

This bond shall not become valid or obligatory for any purpose until it shall be authenticated by the certificate of the registrar hereon endorsed.

In witness whereof, the Caja de Credito Hipotecario has caused this bond to be executed in its name bearing the facsimile signature of the president of its board of directors and to be manually signed by its cashier thereunto duly authorized and to be impressed with its seal and the interest coupons bearing

the facsimile signature of the president of its board of directors to be hereto annexed.

Dated June 30, 1925.

CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO,
By _____, *Cashier*,
LOUIS BARROS BORGONO,
President of the Board of Directors.

[Form of registrar's certificate]

This is one of the within-described guaranteed sinking fund 6½ percent gold bonds of the Caja de Hipotecario (Chile).

GUARANTY TRUST CO. OF NEW YORK,
Registrar.

By _____.

[Form of coupon]

No. _____.

\$ _____

On _____, 19—, unless the bond hereinafter mentioned shall have been called for previous redemption, the Caja de Hipotecario (Chile) promises to pay to bearer, at his option, in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of or equal to the standard of weight and fineness existing June 30, 1925, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City \$ _____ without deduction for any taxes, imposts, levies, or duties of any nature now or at any time hereafter imposed by the Republic of Chile or by any State, Province, municipality, or other taxing authority thereof or therein, in time of war as well as in time of peace and whether the holder be a citizen or resident of a friendly or hostile state, being 6 months' interest then due on its guaranteed sinking fund 6½ percent gold bond, dated June 30, 1925 (no. _____).

CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO,
By LOUIS BARROS BORGONO,
President of the Board of Directors.

SCHEDULE B

The Republic of Chile, for a valuable consideration, hereby unconditionally guarantees to the holder of the within bond prompt payment of the principal amount of said bond in accordance with its terms, when same shall become due and payable, whether at the maturity thereof or otherwise, and of the interest thereon at the rate and at the times specified in said bond and in the appurtenant coupons, upon presentation and surrender of said coupons as they severally mature, and also prompt payment to the fiscal agents of the semiannual payments mentioned in said bond for the service of interest and amortization of the bonds, when the same shall become due and payable.

Dated, June 30, 1925.

REPUBLIC OF CHILE,
By _____.

SCHEDULE C

[Form of temporary bond]

No. _____.

\$ _____.

CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO (CHILE) (MORTGAGE BANK OF CHILE) DUE JUNE 30,
1957, GUARANTEED SINKING FUND 6½ PERCENT GOLD BOND

The Caja de Credito Hipotecario (herein called the Caja) for value received, promises to pay to the bearer on June 30, 1957, the sum of \$20,000,000, and

to pay interest thereon from June 30, 1925, until the principal of this bond is paid at the rate of $6\frac{1}{2}$ percent per annum, semiannually, on June 30 and December 31, in each year.

The principal of, and interest on, this bond are payable at the option of the holder, in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of or equal to the standard of weight and fineness existing June 30, 1925, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, and will be paid without deduction for any taxes, imposts, levies, or duties of any nature now or at any time hereafter imposed by the Republic of Chile or by any State, Province, municipality, or other taxing authority thereof or therein, and will be paid in time of war as well as in time of peace and whether the holder be a citizen or resident of a friendly or hostile state.

This bond is a temporary bond without coupons and is one of an issue of bonds known as the guaranteed sinking fund $6\frac{1}{2}$ percent gold bonds of the Caja (herein called the bonds) limited to \$20,000,000 principal amount, issued in accordance with the laws of the Republic of Chile dated August 29, 1855, and September 10, 1892, the decree law dated March 9, 1925, and the executive decree dated June 15, 1925, supplementing said decree law, constituting the loan designated *Emprestito oro Caja Hipotecaria, 1925*.

Until all the bonds shall have been retired or redeemed the Caja will pay to the fiscal agents as an annuity for the service of interest and amortization of the bonds the sum of at least \$1,492,800 per annum in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid except as hereinafter provided. Such sums shall be paid in equal semiannual installments before the 30th day of June and the 31st day of December in each year, the first payment to be made before December 31, 1925, and the last payment to be made before June 30, 1957. The fiscal agents shall apply each such installment to the payment of the interest maturing on the next succeeding interest date on the bonds then outstanding and shall apply the part of each such installment not required for the payment of such interest as a sinking fund for the redemption of bonds on such interest date as hereinafter provided. The Caja may, at its option, increase the amount of any semiannual installment to be applied to the redemption of bonds on any semiannual interest date and, in the event of any such increase, all subsequent semiannual installments shall be reduced to an amount sufficient to provide for the semiannual service of interest and amortization of the bonds which shall be outstanding after the application of such increased sinking-fund installment to the redemption of bonds, such amount to be calculated as a cumulative sinking fund compounded semiannually at the rate of $6\frac{1}{2}$ per cent per annum to redeem, on or before June 30, 1957, all of the bonds so outstanding. Any such reduced semiannual installment may similarly be increased in which event subsequent semiannual installments shall be similarly reduced. The part of each semi-annual installment available for the redemption of bonds shall be applied to the redemption of bonds by lot at 100 per cent of their principal amount on the interest date next succeeding the date of such payment.

The numbers of the bonds to be redeemed on each such interest date shall be drawn by lot in any usual manner. The drawings shall be held in public at the principal office of the Caja in the city of Santiago. The numbers of the bonds so drawn for redemption shall be advertised at least twice in two daily newspapers of general circulation in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, the first advertisement to appear not less than 30 days prior to the redemption date. The bonds so called for redemption shall on the redemption date designated in such notice become due and payable at 100 percent of their principal amount, and shall be payable, at the option of the holders, in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, and shall be paid by the Caja on and after redemption date at the redemption price aforesaid on presentation and surrender of such bonds at any of said offices, together with all coupons thereto appertaining maturing after the redemption date. If any bond so presented shall not be accompanied by all coupons maturing after the redemption date, then said

bond shall be paid at the redemption price aforesaid less the aggregate principal amount of all coupons maturing after the redemption date not presented and surrendered with said bond; provided, that if more than four such coupons are not presented and surrendered with said bond the fiscal agents or the Caja may refuse to pay said bond. Notice having been so given by publication the bonds so called for redemption shall cease to bear interest from the redemption date unless they shall not be so paid by the Caja upon presentation and surrender thereof with all coupons maturing after the redemption date.

This temporary bond is exchangeable for definitive engraved bonds of this issue of like tenor and for a like aggregate principal amount when engraved and prepared, endorsed with the guaranty of the Republic of Chile, corresponding so far as appropriate with the guaranty hereon endorsed.

This bond shall pass by delivery.

In witness whereof, the Caja de Credito Hipotecario has caused this bond to be executed and its name bearing the signature of the president of the board of directors and of its cashier thereunto duly authorized and to be impressed with its seal.

Dated, June 30, 1925.

CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO,
By _____, Cashier.
LOUIS BARROS BORGONO,
President of the board of directors.

SCHEDULE D

The Republic of Chile, for a valuable consideration hereby unconditionally guarantees to the holder of the within bond prompt payment of the principal amount of said bond in accordance with its terms, when the same shall become due and payable, whether at the maturity thereof or otherwise, and of the interest thereon at the rate and at the times specified in said bond, and also prompt payment to the fiscal agents of the semiannual payments mentioned in said bond for the service of interest and amortization of the bonds, when the same shall become due and payable, and the Republic of Chile hereby agrees to endorse on the several definitive engraved bonds to be delivered in exchange for the within temporary bond its guaranty substantially as aforesaid with appropriate variations.

Dated, June 30, 1925.

REPUBLIC OF CHILE,
By _____.

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 12 JUNE 28, 1933

\$20,000,000 MORTGAGE BANK OF CHILE (CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO, CHILE) GUARANTEED SINKING FUND 6½ PERCENT GOLD BONDS OF 1926, DUE JUNE 30, 1961

Unconditionally guaranteed as to principal, interest, and sinking fund, by endorsement, by the Republic of Chile

Coupon bearer bonds in denominations of \$1,000 and \$500 each. Principal and interest to be payable at the option of the holders, in New York City at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, in United States gold coin of or equal to the standard of weight and fineness existing June 30, 1926, or in Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja by sight draft on New York City, without deduction for any taxes, imposts, levies or duties of any nature now or at any time hereafter imposed by the Republic of Chile or by any State, province, municipality or other taxing authority thereof or therein and to be payable in time of war as well as in time of peace and whether the holder be a citizen or a resident of a friendly or a hostile State.

Interest payable June 30 and December 31.

For further information regarding this issue of bonds, reference is made to the accompanying letter received from His Excellency, the Honorable Miguel Cruchaga, Ambassador Extraordinary and Plenipotentiary of the Republic of Chile to the United States, and from which the following is summarized:

The bonds are to be unconditionally guaranteed as to principal, interest, and sinking fund, by endorsement, by the Republic of Chile, pursuant to the law of August 29, 1855, creating the Caja, as amended by decree law, dated December 15, 1925, and pursuant to decree law, dated March 9, 1925, and to decree of the President of the Republic of Chile, dated July 27, 1926.

Beginning December 31, 1926, the bonds will be redeemable through a cumulative sinking fund calculated to retire the whole issue by June 30, 1961, to be applied on each semiannual interest date to the redemption by lot of bonds at par. The Caja will have the right to increase the amount of any sinking fund installment for the redemption of additional bonds on any interest date, and in any such case appropriate reductions will be made in subsequent sinking-fund installments. This right is reserved because repayments on the mortgage loans to be made by the Caja, against which these bonds are to be issued, can be made by the borrowers either in cash or in bonds of the Caja in excess of the fixed minimum amortization payments, and the Caja is not permitted by law to have its bonds outstanding in excess of the mortgage loans against which they are issued.

Application will be made in due course to list these bonds on the New York Stock Exchange.

The undersigned will receive subscriptions for \$18,330,000 bonds, subject to allotment, at 99¼ per cent and accrued interest to date of delivery, to yield over 6.80 to maturity. The mortgage bank is withdrawing the remaining \$1,670,000 bonds for its reserve fund.

The undersigned reserve the right to close the subscription at any time without notice, to reject any application, to allot a smaller amount than applied for, and to make allotments on their uncontrolled discretion.

The above bonds are offered if, when, and as issued and received by the undersigned, and subject to the approval of counsel. In the first instance, interim certificates of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York will be delivered against payment in New York for bonds allotted, which interim certificates will be exchangeable for definitive bonds when prepared.

KUHN, LOEB & Co.

GUARANTY TRUST CO. OF NEW YORK.

NEW YORK, *July 29, 1926.*

WASHINGTON, D.C., *July 29, 1926.*

Messrs. KUHN, LOEB & Co., and
Guaranty Co. of New York, N.Y.

DEAR SIRs: Referring to the issue of \$20,000,000 principal amount of guaranteed sinking fund 6¼ percent gold bonds of 1926, due June 30, 1961, of the Mortgage Bank of Chile (Caja de Credito Hipotecario, Chile), of which you have agreed to purchase \$18,330,000, the Caja withdrawing the balance of \$1,670,000 for its reserve fund, I beg to give you the following information:

The bonds are to be unconditionally guaranteed as to principal, interest and sinking fund, by endorsement, by the Republic of Chile, pursuant to the law creating the Caja, as amended by decree law, dated December 15, 1925, and pursuant to decree law, dated March 9, 1925, and to decree of the President of the Republic of Chile, dated July 27, 1926.

The Caja de Credito Hipotecario was created by law of August 29, 1855, for the purpose of making available credit facilities on reasonable terms for the development and improvement of real property in Chile. The board of directors, the president of the board, the chief counsel, the cashier, the controller and the secretary are appointed by the President of the Republic.

During its existence of over 70 years, the Caja has operated successfully and has never failed to meet its obligations. The record of its loan collections is very satisfactory. The losses incurred by the Caja on property foreclosed under its mortgages have not exceeded \$40,000 in the aggregate for the last 10 years. In his report, published February 1, 1924, to the Department of Commerce of the United States, Mr. Charles A. McQueen, special agent of the Bureau of Foreign and Domestic Commerce of the Department, states that in the course of its long existence the Caja has conducted its affairs with uniform safety and success.

The Caja has no capital stock and is not operated for profit. It has power to charge a commission to provide for its expenses and for a reserve fund, as additional security for its bonds, but having accumulated a sufficient reserve, the Caja has now discontinued charging such commission.

The Caja issues its bonds only against mortgages registered in its name. It makes only first mortgage loans. The loans are made on a conservative basis and the risk is greatly diversified. On December 31, 1925, the Caja had outstanding various issues of bonds aggregating \$100,219,000, at gold par of exchange, against which it had made 10,198 mortgage loans being an average of less than \$10,000 per loan. These loans aggregated less than 25 percent of the aggregate appraised improvement value of the properties mortgaged as security therefor. As further security for its bonds, the Caja has accumulated a reserve fund of approximately \$5,028,450, at gold par of exchange.

The law authorized the Caja to issue bonds and to make mortgage loans payable in foreign currencies. It is the practice of the Caja to make its mortgage loans, against which bonds payable in a foreign currency are issued, also payable in the same currency, except in cases where it has obtained a guaranty of the Republic of Chile for any loss resulting from exchange fluctuations. This was done in 1912 when Fcs. 58,823,500 gold bonds were issued (of which there are still Fcs. 27,982,500 gold now outstanding) and in 1925 when \$20,000,000 United States gold bonds were issued in the United States by you.

The mortgage loans against \$5,000,000 of the present issue will be made at the request of the Republic of Chile for special purposes at lower interest rates than the Caja is paying on the bonds and the Republic has agreed to pay the difference and to guarantee those mortgage loans. The entire present issue of bonds will also be guaranteed by endorsement by the Republic of Chile.

The bonds of the Caja are legal investments for savings banks and trust funds in Chile.

Prior to the war, in 1911 and 1912, three issues of 5 percent bonds of the Caja, not endorsed with the guaranty of the Government, were made in Europe, at prices from 96 $\frac{1}{4}$ to 99 $\frac{1}{4}$ percent. These issues are listed on the stock exchange of Paris and Berlin.

The present debt of the Republic of Chile, including the present and all other obligations guaranteed by it, aggregates about \$270,000,000, at gold par of exchange. The proceeds of the Government loans have been largely used for the construction or improvement of railways, harbors and other public works. The Government owns 3,624 miles of railroads, telegraph lines and other property, of an estimated value of approximately \$650,000,000, at gold par of exchange, which is well in excess of the entire amount of the debt. In addition, the Government owns large and very valuable tracts of nitrate lands.

Chile is a mining and agricultural country. Its mineral products are largely raw materials for essential industries. Exports consist chiefly of nitrates, byproducts of the nitrate industry, copper, borax, wool, and a limited amount of agricultural products. The nitrate deposits are the only large natural deposits so far discovered in the world. The copper industry has been extensively developed, largely by American capital.

The trade balance of Chile is favorable. The total foreign trade for 1924 (the last year for which official figures were available) aggregated \$352,000,000 at the present gold parity of exchange, and the balance of exports over imports amounted to \$96,000,000. Since 1915 imports have exceeded exports in only one year.

Chile is on a gold basis. Its currency is the peso, equivalent to United States \$0.12166. Currency notes are issued by the Central Bank of Chile, similar to the Federal Reserve banks of the United States.

The above-mentioned \$20,000,000 principal amount of guaranteed sinking fund 6 $\frac{1}{4}$ percent gold bonds of 1926 of the Caja, constituting the loan designated *Emprestito oro Caja Hipotecaria*, 1926, will be in coupon bearer form, in denominations of \$1,000 and \$500, will be dated June 30, 1926, will mature June 30, 1961, and will bear interest at the rate of 6 $\frac{1}{4}$ percent per annum from June 30, 1926, payable semiannually on June 30 and December 31 of each year. Principal and interest will be payable at the option of the holders, in the Borough of Manhattan, in the city of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or at the principal office of the Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of or equal to the standard of weight and fineness existing June 30, 1926, or in Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, without deduction for any taxes, imposts, levies, or duties of any nature now or at any time hereafter imposed by the Republic of Chile, or any State, Province, municipality, or other taxing authority thereof or therein, and will be paid in time of war as well as in time of

peace, and whether the holder be a citizen or a resident of a friendly or a hostile State.

Beginning December 31, 1926, the bonds will be redeemable through a cumulative sinking fund calculated to retire the whole issue by June 30, 1961, to be applied on each semiannual interest date to the redemption by lot of bonds at par. Notice of redemption is to be given by advertisement, the first advertisement to appear at least 30 days before each redemption date. The Caja will have the right to increase the amount of any sinking-fund installment for the redemption of additional bonds on any interest date, and in any such case appropriate reductions will be made in subsequent sinking-fund installments. This right is reserved because repayments on the mortgage loans can be made by the borrowers either in cash or in bonds of the Caja in excess of the fixed minimum amortization payments and the Caja is not permitted by law to have its bonds outstanding in excess of the mortgage loans against which they are issued.

Application will be made in due course to list the bonds on the New York Stock Exchange.

Very truly yours,

(Signed) MIGUEL CRUCHAGA,
*Ambassador Extraordinary and Plenipotentiary
of the Republic of Chile to the United States.*

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 13, JUNE 28, 1933

Agreement, dated July 29, 1925, made in the city and State of New York in the United States of America between Caja de Credito Hipotecario, of Santiago, Chile, organized under the laws of Chile (hereinafter called the "Caja"), acting by His Excellency the Honorable Miguel Cruchaga, Chilean ambassador to the United States of America, thereunto duly authorized, and Kuhn, Loeb & Co., a copartnership of the city and State of New York, and Guaranty Co., of New York, a corporation organized under the laws of the State of New York (hereinafter called the "bankers").

In consideration of the mutual covenants hereinafter set forth, it is agreed as follows:

1. The Caja will forthwith create an issue of bonds to be known as its "guaranteed sinking fund 6 $\frac{3}{4}$ percent gold bonds of 1926" (hereinafter called the "bonds") limited to \$20,000,000 principal amount, to constitute the loan designated "Emprestito oro Caja Hipotecaria, 1926." The bonds shall be issued in accordance with the law of the Republic of Chile of August 29, 1855, establishing the Caja, as amended by the decree law dated December 15, 1925, which decree law was duly approved by the commission appointed for that purpose by both Houses of Congress (and with the decree law of Mar. 9, 1925), and with the decree of the President of the Republic of Chile, dated July 27, 1926, which authorize the guaranty of the bonds by the Republic of Chile.

The bonds shall be in coupon form, payable to bearer, shall be dated June 30, 1926, shall mature June 30, 1961, shall bear interest from June 30, 1926, at the rate of 6 $\frac{3}{4}$ percent per annum, payable semiannually on June 30 and December 31 in each year, and shall be in the denominations of \$1,000 and \$500 in such proportions as the bankers may request. The principal of, and interest on the bonds shall be payable without deduction for any taxes, imposts, levies, or duties of any nature, now or at any time hereafter imposed by the Republic of Chile or by any State, Province, municipality, or other taxing authority thereof or therein, and shall be paid, at the option of the holders, in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co., or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York in gold coin of the United States of America of or equal to the standard of weight and fineness existing June 30, 1926, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, and shall be paid in time of war as well as in time of peace and whether the holder be a citizen or resident of a friendly or hostile state. The bonds shall be authenticated by the certificate endorsed thereon of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, registrar of the loan hereinafter provided.

The Republic of Chile shall unconditionally guarantee to the holders of the bonds prompt payment of the principal of, and the interest on, the bonds, as and when the same shall become due and payable and also prompt payment to the fiscal agents, hereinafter appointed, of the semiannual payments for the service of interest and amortization of the bonds hereinafter mentioned as and

when the same shall become due and payable, and such guaranty shall be endorsed on the bonds. The text of the guaranty shall be substantially in the form hereto annexed and marked "Schedule B."

2. The text of the definitive engraved bonds shall be in the English language substantially in the form hereto annexed and marked "Schedule A," and shall bear a notation in Spanish substantially in the form shown on said schedule A. The text of the usual certificate of the Treasury Department of the Republic of Chile on bonds of the Caja shall be in Spanish, or in both English and Spanish, as the bankers may elect, in such form as may be required by Chilean law. The Caja hereby authorizes the bankers to cause to be prepared without delay definitive engraved bonds for execution by or on behalf of the Caja, such bonds to be engraved and printed in New York in accordance with the requirements of the New York Stock Exchange. The bankers may issue or cause to be issued by a bank or trust company in New York temporary interim certificates which, if issued, shall, in due course be exchangeable without cost or expense to the bankers or the holders, for definitive engraved bonds.

The definitive bonds shall bear the facsimile signature of Don Louis Barros Borgono, the president of the board of directors of the Caja, and shall be manually signed by Don Francisco Bahamondes, the cashier of the Caja, or other duly authorized officer of the Caja. The certificate of the Treasury Department shall be signed manually or otherwise as may be required by Chilean law. The coupons shall bear the facsimile signature of Don Louis Barros Borgono, the president of the board of directors of the Caja. The guaranty of the Republic of Chile endorsed on the bonds shall be manually signed by His Excellency, the Honorable Miguel Cruchaga, the Chile Ambassador to the United States of America, thereunto duly authorized by the Government of the Republic of Chile or by some other duly authorized representative of the Republic of Chile.

3. Until all of the bonds have been retired or redeemed, the Caja shall pay to the fiscal agents as an annuity for the service of interest and amortization of the bonds the sum of \$1,500,000 per annum in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid, except as hereinafter in this article provided. Such sums shall be paid in equal semiannual installments at least 15 days before the 30th day of June and the 31st day of December in each year, as hereinafter in article 5 hereof provided.

The fiscal agents shall apply each such installment to the payment of the interest maturing on the next succeeding interest date on the bonds then outstanding, and shall apply the part of each such installment not required for the payment of such interest as a sinking fund for the redemption of bonds on such interest date as hereinafter provided.

The Caja may, at its option, increase the amount of any semiannual installment to be applied to the redemption of bonds on any semiannual interest date, and in the event of any such increase all subsequent semiannual installments shall be reduced to an amount sufficient to provide for the semiannual service of interest and amortization of such increased sinking-fund installment to the redemption of bonds, such amount to be calculated as a cumulative sinking fund compounded semiannually at the rate of 6 $\frac{1}{4}$ percent per annum to redeem, on or before June 30, 1961, all of the bonds so outstanding. Any such reduced semiannual installment may similarly be increased, in which event subsequent semiannual installments shall be similarly reduced. This right is reserved, because repayments of the mortgage loans made by the Caja may be made by the borrowers either in cash or in bonds of the Caja in excess of the fixed minimum amortization payments, and the Caja is not permitted by law to have its bonds outstanding in excess of the mortgage loans against which they are issued.

The part of each semiannual installment available for the redemption of bonds shall be applied to the redemption of bonds by lot at 100 percent of their principal amount on the interest date next succeeding the date of such payment.

The numbers of the bonds to be redeemed on each such interest date shall be drawn by lot in any usual manner. The drawings shall be held in public at the principal office of the Caja in the city of Santiago. The Caja shall notify the fiscal agents of the aggregate principal amount and numbers of the bonds to be redeemed on each interest date and such notification shall be sent to the fiscal agents at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. in the city of New York so as to be received at said office at least 45 days prior to such interest date. The numbers of the bonds so drawn for redemption shall be advertised at least twice

in two daily newspapers of general circulation in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, the first advertisement to appear not less than 30 days prior to the redemption date. If the New York Stock Exchange so requires, the advertisement shall be further published.

The bonds so called for redemption shall on the redemption date designated in such notice become due and payable at 100 percent of their principal amount and shall be payable, at the option of the holders, in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, and shall be paid by the Caja on and after the redemption date at the redemption price aforesaid on presentation and surrender of such bonds at any of said offices, together with all coupons thereto appertaining maturing after the redemption date.

If any bond so presented shall not be accompanied by all coupons maturing after the redemption date, then said bond shall be paid at the redemption price aforesaid less the aggregate principal amount of all coupons maturing after the redemption date not presented and surrendered with said bond: *Provided*, That if more than four such coupons are not presented and surrendered with said bond, the fiscal agents or the Caja may refuse to pay said bond. Notice having been so given by the publication, the bonds so called for redemption shall cease to bear interest from the redemption date unless they shall not be so paid by the Caja upon presentation and surrender thereof with all coupons maturing after the redemption date.

No expense in connection with the redemption of the bonds or the operation of the sinking fund shall be charged against the sinking fund but such expenses shall be paid by the Caja.

4. All notices or other announcements relating to the redemption of the bonds, the payment of the coupons or any other matter in connection with the bonds may be given or made by the fiscal agents, jointly or severally, on behalf of the Caja as the fiscal agents shall deem proper, but all expenses in connection therewith shall be paid by the Caja.

All bonds redeemed through the sinking fund with all unmatured coupons thereto appertaining and all coupons paid by the fiscal agents shall be canceled by the fiscal agents and by them delivered to a representative of the Caja for that purpose in the city of New York or sent by registered mail insured to and at the risk and expense of the Caja. All bonds paid in Santiago by the Caja, and all bonds delivered to the Caja in payment of its loans shall be sent, as soon as practicable after such payment or delivery, to the fiscal agents for cancellation at the risk and expense of the Caja, and no bonds delivered to the Caja in payment of its loans shall be reissued or renegotiated by the Caja.

5. So long as any of the bonds shall be outstanding the Caja covenants to pay to the fiscal agents at their respective offices in the city of New York in gold coin of the United States of the standard aforesaid—

(a) At least 15 days before June 30 and December 31 in each year the sum of \$750,000 (or, in the event that the Caja shall have increased the amount of any previous semiannual installment as provided in article 3 hereof, such lesser amount as may be due as provided in said article 3) to be applied to the service of interest and amortization of the bonds as provided in article 3 hereof, the first payment to be made at least 15 days before December 31, 1926, and the last payment to be made at least 15 days before June 30, 1961; and if the Caja shall elect to increase the amount of any such semiannual installment as provided in article 3 hereof, the amount of any such increase at least 15 days before the interest date on which such amounts are to be applied to the redemption of bonds. One half of each payment made pursuant to this paragraph (a) shall be made to Kuhn, Loeb & Co. at their office in the city of New York, and one half of each such payment shall be made to Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, at its principal office in the city of New York;

(b) at least 15 days before June 30, 1961, a sum equal to the principal amount of all the bonds then outstanding, one half of such payment to be made to Kuhn, Loeb & Co. at their office in the city of New York, and one half of such payment to be made to Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, at its principal office in the city of New York. Any amounts in the sinking fund to be applied to the redemption of bonds on June 30, 1961, at the time of the payment made pursuant to this paragraph (b) shall be credited against such payment; and

(c) such amounts as may be required to meet all expense incident to the service of the loan, including the compensation and expenses of the registrar; such payments to be made from time to time, on the joint written or cabled request of the fiscal agents, to the fiscal agent or fiscal agents stated in such request.

The fiscal agents shall not be required to segregate any moneys paid to or deposited with them as hereinbefore provided. The Caja irrevocably authorizes and directs the fiscal agents and each of them to pay out of the moneys paid to them as hereinbefore provided the interest on the bonds to the bearers of the coupons upon presentation and surrender thereof, and the principal of the bonds at maturity or on the redemption dates, as the case may be, to the bearers of the bonds to be paid or redeemed upon presentation and surrender thereof, and to apply the moneys in the sinking fund to the redemption of the bonds, and to make every such payment without further formality except as the fiscal agents or either of them may be advised may be necessary to comply with some law or regulation of the United States of America or other public authority therein.

6. The Caja during the life of the loan will maintain in the Borough of Manhattan, in the city of New York, a fiscal agency or fiscal agencies of the loan and a registry of the loan. The Caja appoints Kuha, Loeb & Co. and Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, of the city and State of New York, United States of America, to be fiscal agents of the loan during the life of the loan subject to the terms and conditions of this agreement. The Caja also appoints said Guaranty Trust Co. of New York as registrar of the loan during the life of the loan subject to the terms and conditions of this agreement.

7. Neither the fiscal agents nor the registrar shall be liable otherwise than for good faith and the exercise of reasonable care. The fiscal agents and the registrar and each of them shall be protected in any action which any of them may take in acting on any bond or coupon or any notice, request, or other paper believed by them or it to be genuine as well as in or in respect of any action taken or suffered in good faith under the advice of counsel. Neither of the bankers and neither of the fiscal agents shall be liable for any act or omission of the other.

8. The Caja shall pay each of the fiscal agents as compensation for their services a commission of one quarter of 1 percent of the amount of all payments made to such fiscal agent pursuant to paragraphs (a) and (b) of article 5 hereof, such compensation to be paid to the fiscal agents at the time when such payments are made to the fiscal agents. The Caja shall also pay the fiscal agents as compensation for their services a commission of one quarter of 1 percent of the principal amount of all bonds delivered to the Caja in payment of its mortgage loans; one half of such compensation to be paid to each of the fiscal agents at the time when such bonds are sent to the fiscal agents for cancellation as provided in article 4 hereof.

9. In case any of the bonds shall become mutilated, destroyed, or lost, a new bond (having endorsed thereon the guaranty of the Republic of Chile in this agreement provided for) of like amount, tenor, and date, bearing the same number and bearing all unmatured coupons, shall be issued by the Caja; but only if permitted by and in accordance with Chilean law, and the registrar shall authenticate the same for delivery in exchange for, and upon cancellation of, the bond so mutilated and its unmatured coupons, or in lieu of the bond so destroyed or lost and its unmatured coupons, but in the case of destroyed or lost bonds only upon receipt by the Caja and the registrar of evidence satisfactory to each of them that such bonds were destroyed or lost and, if required, upon receipt also of indemnity satisfactory to each of them in their discretion. The registrar shall incur no liability for such action.

10. The Caja agrees to sell and deliver to the bankers and the bankers agree to purchase from the Caja and pay for \$18,330,000 aggregate principal amount of the bonds at the price of 95½ percent of the principal amount thereof, being \$17,528,062.50. The remaining \$1,670,000 principal amount of the bonds will be retained by the Caja for its reserve fund, and the Caja agrees that it will not sell or offer for sale said \$1,670,000 principal amount of the bonds until January 1, 1927, and thereafter will sell or offer same for sale only to the bankers.

In the first instance an appropriately executed temporary bond (which may be printed, written, or typewritten) for \$20,000,000 in substantially the form hereto annexed and marked "Schedule C" and endorsed with the guaranty of the Republic of Chile, in substantially the form hereto annexed and marked

"Schedule D", shall be delivered on or before July 31, 1926, unless the bankers consent to postpone this date, to Banco de Chile, for account of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York. The charges of Banco de Chile shall be paid by the Caja. As promptly as practicable after the delivery of the temporary bond for \$20,000,000, as aforesaid, Guaranty Trust Co. of New York shall deliver to or upon the order of the Caja an interim receipt or receipts representing said \$1,670,000 principal amount of the bonds and shall deliver to or on the order of the bankers interim receipts representing said \$18,330,000 principal amount of the bonds. Payment of \$4,382,015.62, the first instalment of the purchase price, shall be made on August 2, 1926, unless the time for such delivery shall be extended by the bankers at the request of the Caja, as above provided, and, in that case, within the period of such extension on 5 days' notice to the bankers in writing, but such payment shall not be made until after receipt of cable advice from Banco de Chile to Guaranty Trust Co. of New York of the delivery of such temporary bond. Payment of \$4,382,015.62, the second instalment of the purchase price, shall be made on the eighteenth day following the payment of the first instalment, and payment of \$8,764,031.26, the final instalment of the purchase price, shall be made on the twenty-second day following the payment of the first instalment.

Such payments shall be made by placing the amount of each installment of the purchase price to the credit of the Caja in dollars in the city of New York, one half of each such installment to be credited to the account of the Caja with Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and one half of each such installment to be credited to the account of the Caja with Guaranty Trust Co. of New York. The amounts so credited to the Caja shall be withdrawn upon the order of such person or persons as may be authorized to draw upon the same by the Caja, and all withdrawals shall be made in substantially equal amounts from Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and from Guaranty Trust Co. of New York.

Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and Guaranty Trust Co. of New York shall each credit the Caja with interest at the current rate which New York clearing house banks may then be paying on the amounts so credited with them respectively, until disbursed by the Caja.

11. Forthwith, upon the execution of this agreement the Caja will deliver or cause to be delivered to the bankers a prospectus letter or letters containing information concerning the financial position of the Caja and of the Republic of Chile, its debts, income and expenditures, and financial administration, and such other information and in such form as the bankers may reasonably request and as shall be satisfactory to the bankers' counsel, such letter or letters to be signed by the Chilean Ambassador to the United States of America.

12. It is a condition precedent to any obligation of the bankers hereunder (a) that the Caja shall have promptly delivered a prospectus letter as set forth above in article 11 hereof, and (b) that on or before July 31, 1926, unless the time be extended by the bankers at the request of the Caja as hereinbefore provided, and, in that case, within the period of such extension,

(1) the Caja shall have delivered to the representative of the bankers in Chile duly authenticated copies of the laws or decrees or other instruments authorizing the issue of the bonds by the Republic of Chile in accordance with the terms of this agreement and also duly certified copies of all proceedings of the Caja and all executive and other decrees of the Government of the Republic of Chile necessary to comply with said laws in connection with the execution and delivery of the bonds hereunder;

(2) the bankers shall have received an opinion satisfactory to the bankers' counsel in New York, of Chilean counsel approved by the bankers' counsel in New York, approving the proceedings of the Caja authorizing the creation, issue, and sale of the bonds and approving the guaranty of the bonds by the Republic of Chile, in accordance with the terms of this agreement, the sufficiency of all action taken thereunder, the validity of this agreement, and the validity of the bonds, both temporary and definitive, in the hands of holders of whatever citizenship or residence, in accordance with the terms of the bonds and of this agreement; and

(3) that the bankers' counsel in New York shall have approved the form of the bonds and coupons.

13. The Caja will pay all stamp and other duties, if any, to which under the laws of Chile or of the United States of America this agreement or the bonds may be subject. The Caja will also pay the cost of printing, engraving, executing, and authenticating the temporary and definitive bonds and interim certificates for definitive bonds and of transporting the temporary and definitive

bonds to and from Santiago, and the compensation and expenses of the registrar. The Caja will also pay the fees and disbursements of the Chilean counsel referred to in article 12 hereof.

14. The Caja hereby covenants and agrees that no bonds issued or guaranteed by it other than the bonds purchased by the bankers hereunder shall be sold or offered for sale in the United States of America prior to January 1, 1927, except with the written consent of the bankers, and except as hereinafter provided. The bankers understand that the Caja intends to issue before said January 1, 1927, but not before October 15, 1926, unless with the consent of the bankers, up to \$10,000,000 principal amount of agricultural bonds guaranteed as to principal, interest, and sinking fund, if any, by the Republic of Chile, by endorsement, of which not more than one half may be 6¼ percent 35-year bonds with a three fourths of 1 percent cumulative sinking fund similar to the bonds of the present issue and the balance will be 6¼ percent bonds maturing serially within from 6 months to 5 years after their date; and the bankers agree, subject to the further provisions of this article, to buy from the Caja, and the Caja agrees to sell to the bankers, said agricultural bonds up to \$10,000,000 principal amount at the same net price to the bankers (considering accrued interest and dates of payment of the installments of the purchase price) as paid by the bankers for the bonds of the present issue, pursuant to article 10 hereof: *Provided, however*, That if the short-term serial bonds above mentioned should, by agreement between the Caja and the bankers, be issued with a lower coupon rate than 6¼ percent, the net price of such bonds to the bankers shall be adjusted accordingly; and provided further, that if market conditions, in the opinion of the bankers, permit, the bankers will offer more favorable prices and terms to the Caja for said agricultural bonds.

The obligation of the bankers to purchase said agricultural bonds is subject to the condition that if between the date of this agreement and the offering of said agricultural bonds for public subscription by the bankers any conditions of the nature of force majeure or any political, financial, or commercial developments or market conditions shall, in the opinion of the bankers, whose conclusion in this respect shall be final, render inadvisable the issue to the public of said agricultural bonds, or of a portion thereof, then the bankers shall be at liberty, at their option, to give the Caja notice of their determination not to proceed with the purchase of said agricultural bonds, or of a portion thereof, and thereupon the obligations of the bankers under this article 14 with respect to the purchase of said agricultural bonds, or such thereof as they shall have decided not to purchase, shall forthwith terminate, but all the other obligations of either party to the other under this agreement shall continue in force.

15. The Caja hereby covenants and agrees that it will not issue or sell any securities of the Caja in the United States of America, or issue or sell any securities intended to be sold or offered for sale in the United States of America prior to July 1, 1928, without first giving the bankers a 30-day option to purchase such securities on terms and conditions at least as favorable to the bankers as the Caja is able to obtain from other sources at the time when such issue or sale is proposed. If the bankers shall not exercise such option within the 30-day period the Caja shall have the right to offer such securities elsewhere on terms and conditions not less favorable to the Caja than those offered to the bankers. The Caja will not reoffer such securities, or accept offers therefore, on terms and conditions less favorable to the Caja without giving the bankers a 30-day option to purchase such securities on such less favorable terms and conditions. The Caja, however, reserves the right to negotiate through an agent who will be instructed to work in accordance with these conditions.

16. The Caja will at the request of the bankers make or cause to be made application for the listing of the bonds and interim certificates on the New York Stock Exchange or the bankers may themselves make such application for and on account of the Caja. The Caja will furnish to the bankers all documents deemed by the bankers to be advantageous for the making of such application and it will take and undertake all such action as may be requisite in accordance with the requirements of said exchange in order to secure such listing. The cost and expenses of such application, whether made by the bankers or by the Caja, shall be paid by the Caja.

17. Reference in this agreement to the fiscal agents or either of them shall be deemed to include any successor firm or corporation however constituted continuing the business of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and/or Guaranty Trust Co. of New York. Reference in this agreement to the registrar shall be deemed to include

any successor corporation continuing the business of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York. Reference in this agreement to the bankers, or either of them, shall be deemed to include any successor firm or corporation however constituted continuing the business of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and/or Guaranty Trust Co. of New York.

In witness whereof Caja de Credito Hipotecario has caused this agreement to be signed in its behalf by His Excellency, the Hon. Miguel Cruchaga, thereunto duly authorized, and Kuhn, Loeb & Co. have signed this agreement and Guaranty Co. of New York has caused this agreement to be signed by its president or one of its vice presidents and its corporate seal to be affixed hereto and attested by an assistant treasurer as of the day and year first above written.

CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO,
By MIGUEL CRUCHAGA.
KUHN, LOEB & Co. [L. S.]
GUARANTY CO. OF NEW YORK,

[SEAL]

By H. STANLEY, *President*.

Attest:

R. T. WILLIS, *Assistant Treasurer*.

The undersigned accept their appointment as fiscal agents under the foregoing agreement upon the terms and conditions thereof; and the undersigned Guaranty Trust Co. of New York also accepts its appointment as registrar thereunder upon the terms and conditions thereof.

GUARANTY TRUST CO. OF NEW YORK,
By C. H. PLATNER, *Vice President*.

SCHEDULE A

[Form of definitive bond]

No. _____

\$ _____

CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO (CHILE) (MORTGAGE BANK OF CHILE), GUARANTEED SINKING FUND 6¾ PERCENT GOLD BOND OF 1926, DUE JUNE 30, 1961

Letra de Credito al Portador, por United States—\$ _____ oro (dollars americanos) que ganan el 6¾ de interes anual.—Reembolsable por sorteos semestrales a mas tardar en 35 anos—Los intereses y amortizaciones se pagan el 31 de Diciembre y 30 Junio, en cambio, del coupon respectivo o de la letra amortizada.—

Caja de Credito Hipotecario (herein called the Caja) for value received, promises to pay to the bearer on June 30, 1961, the sum of \$ _____ and to pay interest thereon from June 30, 1926, until the principal of this bond is paid, at the rate of 6¾ percent per annum, semiannually, on June 30 and December 31 in each year upon presentation and surrender of the coupons hereto annexed as they severally mature.

The principal of, and interest on, this bond are payable at the option of the holder, in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co., or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of or equal to the standard of weight and fineness existing June 30, 1926, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, and will be paid without deduction for any taxes, imposts, levies, or duties of any nature now or at any time hereafter imposed by the Republic of Chile or by any State, Province, municipality or other taxing authority thereof or therein, and will be paid in time of war as well as in time of peace and whether the holder be a citizen or resident of a friendly or a hostile State.

This bond is one of an issue of bonds known as the "Guaranteed sinking fund 6¾ percent gold bonds of 1926" of the Caja (herein called the bonds) limited to \$20,000,000 principal amount, issued in accordance with the law of the Republic of Chile dated August 29, 1855, the decree law dated March 9, 1925, the decree law dated December 15, 1925, and the decree of the President of the Republic of Chile dated July 27, 1926, constituting the loan designated *Emprestito oro Caja Hipotecaria, 1926*.

Until all the bonds shall have been retired or redeemed the Caja will pay to the fiscal agents as an annuity for the service of interest and amortization of the bonds the sum of \$1,500,000 per annum in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid, except as hereinafter provided. Such sums shall be paid in equal semiannual installments before the 30th day of June and the 31st day of December in each year, the first payment to be made before December 31, 1926, and the last payment to be made before June 30, 1961. The fiscal agents shall apply each such installment to the payment of the interest maturing on the next succeeding interest date on the bonds then outstanding and shall apply the part of each such installment not required for the payment of such interest as a sinking fund for the redemption of bonds on such interest date as hereinafter provided. The Caja may, at its option, increase the amount of any semiannual installment to be applied to the redemption of bonds on any semiannual interest date, and, in the event of any such increase, all subsequent semiannual installments shall be reduced to an amount sufficient to provide for the semiannual service of interest and amortization of the bonds which shall be outstanding after the application of such increased sinking fund installment to the redemption of bonds, such amount to be calculated as a cumulative sinking fund compounded semiannually at the rate of 6¾ percent per annum to redeem, on or before June 30, 1961, all of the bonds so outstanding. Any such reduced semiannual installment may similarly be increased, in which event subsequent semiannual installments shall be similarly reduced.

The part of each semiannual installment available for the redemption of bonds shall be applied to the redemption of bonds by lot at 100 percent of their principal amount on the interest date next succeeding the date of such payment. The numbers of the bonds to be redeemed on each such interest date shall be drawn by lot in any usual manner. The drawings shall be held in public at the principal office of the Caja in the city of Santiago. The numbers of the bonds so drawn for redemption shall be advertised at least twice in two daily newspapers of general circulation in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, the first advertisement to appear not less than 30 days prior to the redemption date. The bonds so called for redemption shall on the redemption date designated in such notice become due and payable at 100 percent of their principal amount, and shall be payable, at the option of the holders, in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co., or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, and shall be paid by the Caja on and after the redemption date at the redemption price aforesaid on presentation and surrender of such bonds at any of said offices, together with all coupons thereto appertaining maturing after the redemption date. If any bond so presented shall not be accompanied by all coupons maturing after the redemption date, then said bond shall be paid at the redemption price aforesaid less the aggregate principal amount of all coupons maturing after the redemption date not presented and surrendered with said bond: *Provided*, That if more than four such coupons are not presented and surrendered with said bond the fiscal agents or the Caja may refuse to pay said bond. Notice having been so given by publication the bonds so called for redemption shall cease to bear interest from the redemption date unless they shall not be so paid by the Caja upon presentation and surrender thereof with all coupons maturing after the redemption date.

This bond and the coupons appertaining thereto shall pass by delivery.

This bond shall not become valid or obligatory for any purpose until it shall be authenticated by the certificate of the registrar hereon endorsed.

In witness whereof Caja de Credito Hipotecario has caused this bond to be executed in its name bearing the facsimile signature of the President of its board of directors and to be manually signed by its cashier thereunto duly authorized and to be impressed with its seal and the interest coupons bearing the facsimile signature of the president of its board of directors to be hereto annexed.

Dated, June 30, 1926.

CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO,
By _____, Cashier.
LOUIS BARROS BORGONO,
President of the Board of Directors.

[Form of registrar's certificate]

This is one of the within described guaranteed sinking-fund 6¾ gold bonds of 1926 of Caja de Credito Hipotecario (Chile).

GUARANTY TRUST CO. OF NEW YORK, *Registrar*,
By _____

[Form of coupon]

No. _____, 19____, \$_____.
On _____, 19____, unless the bond hereinafter mentioned shall have been called for previous redemption, Caja de Credito Hipotecario (Chile) promises to pay to bearer, at his option, in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America, of or equal to the standard of weight and fineness existing on June 30, 1926, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, \$_____ without deduction for any taxes, imposts, levies, or duties of any nature now or at any time hereafter imposed by the Republic of Chile or by any State, Province, municipality, or other taxing authority thereof or therein in time of war as well as in time of peace and whether the holder be a citizen or resident of a friendly or a hostile state, being 6 months' interest then due on its guaranteed sinking-fund 6¾-percent gold bond of 1926, dated June 30, 1926 (No. _____).

CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO,
By LOUIS BARROS BORGONO,
President of the Board of Directors.

SCHEDULE B

The Republic of Chile, for a valuable consideration, hereby unconditionally guarantees to the holder of the within bond prompt payment of the principal amount of said bond in accordance with its terms when the same shall become due and payable, whether at the maturity thereof or otherwise, and of the interest thereon at the rate and at the times specified in said bond and in the appurtenant coupons, upon presentation and surrender of said coupons as they severally mature, and also prompt payment to the fiscal agents of the semi-annual payments mentioned in said bond for the service of interest and amortization of the bonds when the same shall become due and payable.

Dated June 30, 1926.

REPUBLIC OF CHILE,
By _____

SCHEDULE C

[Form of temporary bond]

CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO (CHILE) (MORTGAGE BANK OF CHILE) GUARANTEED SINKING-FUND 6¾-PERCENT GOLD BOND OF 1926, DUE JUNE 30, 1961

Caja de Credito Hipotecario (herein called the "Caja"), for value received, promises to pay to the bearer on June 30, 1961, the sum of \$20,000,000, and to pay interest thereon from June 30, 1926, until the principal of this bond is paid at the rate of 6¾ percent per annum, semiannually, on June 30 and December 31 each year.

The principal of, and interest on, this bond are payable at the option of the holder, in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co., of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of or equal to the standard of weight and fineness existing June 30, 1926, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, and will be paid without deduction for any taxes, imposts, levies or duties of

any nature now or at any time hereafter imposed by the Republic of Chile or by any State, Province, municipality, or other taxing authority thereof or therein, and will be paid in time of war as well as in time of peace and whether the holder be a citizen or resident of a friendly or a hostile state.

This bond is a temporary bond without coupons and is one of an issue of bonds known as the "guaranteed sinking-fund 6¾-percent gold bonds of 1926 of the Caja" (herein called the "bonds"), limited to \$20,000,000 principal amount, issued in accordance with the law of the Republic of Chile dated August 29, 1855, the decree law dated March 9, 1925, the decree law dated December 16, 1925, and the decree of the President of the Republic of Chile dated July 27, 1926, constituting the loan designated "Emprestito oro Caja Hipotecaria, 1926."

Until all the bonds shall have been retired or redeemed the Caja will pay to the fiscal agents as an annuity for the service of interest and amortization of the bonds the sum of \$1,500,000 per annum in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid, except as hereinafter provided. Such sums shall be paid in equal semiannual installments before the 30th day of June and the 31st day of December in each year, the first payment to be made before December 31, 1926, and the last payment to be made before June 30, 1961. The fiscal agents shall apply each installment to the payment of the interest maturing on the next succeeding interest date on the bonds then outstanding and shall apply the part of each such installment not required for the payment of such interest as a sinking fund for the redemption of bonds on such interest date, as hereinafter provided. The Caja may, at its option, increase the amount of any semiannual installment to be applied to the redemption of the bonds on any semiannual interest date, and, in the event of any such increase, all subsequent semiannual installments shall be reduced to an amount sufficient to provide for the semiannual service of interest and amortization of the bonds which shall be outstanding after the application of such increase sinking-fund installment to the redemption of bonds, such amount to be calculated as a cumulative sinking fund compounded semiannually at the rate of 6¾ percent per annum to redeem, on or before June 30, 1961, all of the bonds so outstanding.

Any such reduced semiannual installment may similarly be increased, in which event subsequent semiannual installments shall be similarly reduced. The part of each semiannual installment available for the redemption of bonds shall be applied to the redemption of bonds by lot at 100 percent of their principal amount on the interest date next succeeding the date of such payment. The numbers of the bonds to be redeemed on each such interest date shall be drawn by lot in any usual manner. The drawings shall be held in public in the principal office of the Caja in the city of Santiago. The numbers of the bonds so drawn for redemption shall be advertised at least twice in two daily newspapers of general circulation in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, the first advertisement to appear not less than 30 days prior to the redemption date. The bonds so called for redemption shall on the redemption date designated in such notice become due and payable at 100 percent of their principal amount, and shall be payable, at the option of the holders, in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, and shall be paid by the Caja on and after the redemption date at the redemption price aforesaid on presentation and surrender of such bonds at any of said offices, together with all coupons thereto appertaining maturing after the redemption date.

If any bond so presented shall not be accompanied by all coupons maturing after redemption date, then said bond shall be paid at the redemption price aforesaid, less the aggregate principal amount of all coupons maturing after the redemption date not presented and surrendered with said bond; provided, that if more than four such coupons are not presented and surrendered with said bond the fiscal agents or the Caja may refuse to pay said bond. Notice having been so given by publication the bonds so called for redemption shall cease to bear interest from the redemption date unless they shall not be so paid by the Caja upon presentation and surrender thereof with all coupons maturing after the redemption date.

This temporary bond is exchangeable for definitive engraved bonds of this issue of like tenor and for a like aggregate principal amount when engraved

and prepared, endorsed with the guaranty of the Republic of Chile, corresponding so far as appropriate with the guaranty hereon endorsed.

This bond shall pass by delivery.

In witness whereof, Caja de Credito Hipotecario has caused this bond to be executed in its name bearing the signature of the president of its board of directors and of its cashier thereunto duly authorized and to be impressed with its seal.

Dated June 30, 1926.

CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO,
By _____, Cashier.

President of the Board of Directors.

SCHEDULE D

The Republic of Chile, for a valuable consideration, hereby unconditionally guarantees to the holder of the within bond prompt payment of the principal amount of said bond in accordance with its terms, when the same shall become due and payable, whether at the maturity thereof or otherwise, and of the interest thereon at the rate and at the times specified in said bond, and also prompt payment to the fiscal agents of the semiannual payments mentioned in said bond for the service of interest and amortization of the bonds, when the same shall become due and payable, and the Republic of Chile hereby agrees to endorse on the several definitive engraved bonds to be delivered in exchange for the within temporary bond its guaranty as aforesaid, with appropriate variations.

Dated June 30, 1926.

REPUBLIC OF CHILE,
By _____.

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT 15, JUNE 28, 1933

AGREEMENT BETWEEN CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO (CHILE) AND KUHN, LOEB & CO. AND GUARANTY CO. OF NEW YORK APRIL 30, 1928. GUARANTEED SINKING FUND 6 PERCENT GOLD BONDS OF 1928

Agreement, dated April 30, 1928, made in the city and State of New York in the United States of America between Caja de Credito Hipotecario, of Santiago, Chile, organized under the laws of Chile (hereinafter called the Caja), acting by His Excellency, the Honorable Carlos G. Davila, Chilean Ambassador to the United States of America, thereunto duly authorized, and Kuhn, Loeb & Co., a copartnership of the city and State of New York, and Guaranty Co. of New York, a corporation organized under the laws of the State of Delaware (hereinafter called the bankers).

In consideration of the mutual covenants hereinafter set forth, it is agreed as follows:

1. The Caja will forthwith create an issue of bonds to be known as its guaranteed sinking fund 6 percent gold bonds of 1928 (hereinafter called the bonds) limited to \$20,000,000 principal amount, to constitute the loan designated *Emprestito oro Caja Hipotecaria, 1928*. The bonds shall be issued in accordance with the law of the Republic of Chile of August 29, 1855, establishing the Caja, as amended by the decree law dated December 15, 1925, which decree law was duly approved by the commission appointed for that purpose by both Houses of Congress, and with the decree law no. 308 of March 9, 1925, and with the decree of the President of the Republic of Chile, dated January 31, 1928, which authorize the guaranty of the bonds by the Republic of Chile.

Eight million dollars principal amount, of the bonds, are to provide for construction purposes according to said decree law no. 308, dated March 9, 1925, and \$12,000,000 principal amount are to provide for other corporate purposes. The bonds shall be in coupon form, payable to bearer, shall be dated April 30, 1928, shall mature April 30, 1961, shall bear interest from April 30, 1928, at the rate of 6 percent per annum, payable semiannually on April 30 and October 31 in each year and shall be in the denominations of \$1,000 and \$500 in such proportions as the bankers may request. The principal of, and interest on, the bonds shall be payable without deduction for any taxes, imposts, levies, or duties of any nature, now or at any time hereafter imposed by the Republic

of Chile or by any state, province, municipality, or other taxing authority thereof or therein, and shall be paid, at the option of the holders, in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York in gold coin of the United States of America of or equal to the standard of weight and fineness existing April 30, 1928, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, and shall be paid in time of war as well as in time of peace and whether the holder be a citizen or resident of a friendly or a hostile state. The bonds shall be authenticated by the certificate endorsed thereon of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, registrar of the loan hereinafter appointed.

The Republic of Chile shall unconditionally guarantee to the holders of the bonds prompt payment of the principal of, and the interest on, the bonds, as and when the same shall become due and payable and also prompt payment to the fiscal agents, hereinafter appointed, of the semiannual payments for the service of interest and amortization of the bonds hereinafter mentioned as and when the same shall become due and payable, and such guaranty shall be endorsed on the bonds. The text of the guaranty shall be substantially in the form hereto annexed and marked "Schedule B".

2. The text of the definitive engraved bonds shall be in the English language substantially in the form hereto annexed and marked "Schedule A", and shall bear a notation in Spanish substantially in the form shown on said schedule A. The text of the usual certificate of the Treasury Department of the Republic of Chile on bonds of the Caja shall be in Spanish, or in both English and Spanish, as the bankers may elect, in such form as may be required by Chilean law. The Caja hereby authorizes the bankers to cause to be prepared without delay definite engraved bonds for execution by or on behalf of the Caja, such bonds to be engraved and printed in New York in accordance with the requirements of the New York Stock Exchange. The bankers may issue or cause to be issued by a bank or trust company in New York temporary interim certificates which, if issued, shall, in due course, be exchangeable without cost or expense to the bankers or the holders, for definitive engraved bonds.

The definitive bonds shall bear the facsimile signature of Don Luis Barros Borgono, the director of the Caja, and shall be manually signed by Don Francisco Bahamondes, the cashier of the Caja, or other duly authorized officer of the Caja. The certificate of the Treasury Department shall be signed manually or otherwise as may be required by Chilean law. The coupons shall bear the facsimile signature of Don Luis Barros Borgono, the director of the Caja. The guaranty of the Republic of Chile endorsed on the bonds shall be manually signed by His Excellency, the Honorable Carlos G. Davila, the Chilean Ambassador to the United States of America, thereunto duly authorized by the Government of the Republic of Chile or by some other duly authorized representative of the Republic of Chile.

3. Until all of the bonds shall have been retired or redeemed, the Caja shall pay to the fiscal agents as an annuity for the service of interest and amortization of the bonds the sum of \$1,400,000 per annum in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid, except as hereinafter in this article provided. Such sums shall be paid in equal semiannual instalments at least 15 days before the 30th day of April and the 31st day of October in each year as hereinafter in article 5 hereof provided.

The fiscal agents shall apply each such instalment to the payment of the interest maturing on the next succeeding interest date on the bonds then outstanding and shall apply the part of each such instalment not required for the payment of such interest as a sinking fund for the redemption of bonds on such interest date as hereinafter provided.

The Caja may, at its option, increase the amount of any semiannual installment to be applied to the redemption of bonds on any semiannual interest date, and, in the event of any such increase, all subsequent semiannual installments shall be reduced to an amount sufficient to provide for the semiannual service of interest and amortization of the bonds which shall be outstanding after the application of such increased sinking fund installment to the redemption of bonds, such amount to be calculated as a cumulative sinking fund compounded semiannually at the rate of 6 percent per annum to redeem, on or before April 30, 1961, all of the bonds so outstanding. Any such reduced semiannual installment may similarly be increased in which event subsequent semiannual installments shall be similarly reduced. This right is reserved because repayments of the mortgage loans made by the Caja may be made

by the borrowers either in cash or in bonds of the Caja in excess of the fixed minimum amortization payments, and the Caja is not permitted by law to have its bonds outstanding in excess of the mortgage loans against which they are issued.

The part of each semiannual installment available for the redemption of bonds shall be applied to the redemption of bonds by lot at 100 percent of their principal amount on the interest date next succeeding the date of such payment.

The numbers of the bonds to be redeemed on each such interest date shall be drawn by lot in any usual manner. The drawings shall be held in public at the principal office of the Caja in the city of Santiago. The Caja shall notify the fiscal agents of the aggregate principal amount and numbers of the bonds to be redeemed on each interest date and such notification shall be sent to the fiscal agents at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co., in the city of New York, so as to be received at said office at least 45 days prior to such interest date. The numbers of the bonds so drawn for redemption shall be advertised at least twice in two daily newspapers of general circulation in the borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, the first advertisement to appear not less than 30 days prior to the redemption date. If the New York Stock Exchange so requires, the advertisement shall be further published.

The bonds so called for redemption shall on the redemption date designated in such notice become due and payable at 100 percent of their principal amount and shall be payable, at the option of the holders, in the borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, and shall be paid by the Caja on and after the redemption date at the redemption price aforesaid on presentation and surrender of such bonds at any of said offices, together with all coupons thereto appertaining maturing after the redemption date.

If any bond so presented shall not be accompanied by all coupons maturing after the redemption date, then said bond shall be paid at the redemption price aforesaid less the aggregate principal amount of all coupons maturing after the redemption date not presented and surrendered with said bond, provided that if more than four such coupons are not presented and surrendered with said bond, the fiscal agents or the Caja may refuse to pay said bond. Notice having been so given by publication, the bonds so called for redemption shall cease to bear interest from the redemption date unless they shall not be so paid by the Caja upon presentation and surrender thereof with all coupons maturing after the redemption date.

No expenses in connection with the redemption of the bonds or the operation of the sinking fund shall be charged against the sinking but such expenses shall be paid by the Caja.

4. All notices or other announcements relating to the redemption of the bonds, the payment of the coupons, or any other matter in connection with the bonds may be given or made by the fiscal agents, jointly or severally, on behalf of the Caja as the fiscal agents shall deem proper, but all expenses in connection therewith shall be paid by the Caja.

All bonds redeemed through the sinking fund, with all unmatured coupons thereto appertaining and all coupons paid by the fiscal agents, shall be canceled by the fiscal agents and by them delivered to a representative of the Caja for that purpose in the city of New York or sent by registered mail insured to and at the risk and expense of the Caja. All bonds paid in Santiago by the Caja and all bonds delivered to the Caja in payment of its loans shall be sent, as soon as practicable after such payment or delivery, to the fiscal agents for cancellation at the risk and expense of the Caja, and no bonds delivered to the Caja in payment of its loans shall be reissued or renegotiated by the Caja.

5. So long as any of the bonds shall be outstanding the Caja covenants to pay to the fiscal agents at their respective offices in the city of New York in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid—

(a) At least 15 days before April 30 and October 31 in each year the sum of \$700,000 (or, in the event that the Caja shall have increased the amount of any previous semiannual installment as provided in article 3 thereof, such lesser amount as may be due as provided in said article 3) to be applied to

the service of interest and amortization of the bonds as provided in article 3 hereof, the first payment to be made at least 15 days before October 31, 1928, and the last payment to be made at least 15 days before April 30, 1961; and if the Caja shall elect to increase the amount of any such semiannual installment as provided in article 3 hereof, the amount of any such increase at least 15 days before the interest date on which such amount is to be applied to the redemption of bonds. One half of each payment made pursuant to this paragraph (a) shall be made to Kuhn, Loeb & Co. at their office in the city of New York, and one half of each such payment shall be made to Guaranty Trust Co. of New York at its principal office in the city of New York;

(b) At least 15 days before April 30, 1961, a sum equal to the principal amount of all the bonds then outstanding, one half of such payment to be made to Kuhn, Loeb & Co., at their office in the city of New York, and one half of such payment to be made to Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, at its principal office in the city of New York. Any amounts in the sinking fund to be applied to the redemption of bonds on April 30, 1961, at the time of the payment made pursuant to this paragraph (b) shall be credited against such payment; and

(c) Such amounts as may be required to meet all expenses incident to the service of the loan, including the compensation and expenses of the registrar; such payments to be made from time to time, on the joint written or cabled request of the fiscal agents, to the fiscal agent or fiscal agents stated in such request.

The fiscal agents shall not be required to segregate any moneys paid to or deposited with them as hereinbefore provided. The Caja irrevocably authorizes and directs the fiscal agents and each of them to pay out of the moneys paid to them as hereinbefore provided the interest on the bonds to the bears of the coupons upon presentation and surrender thereof, and the principal of the bonds at maturity or on the redemption dates, as the case may be, to the bearers of the bonds to be paid or redeemed upon presentation and surrender thereof, and to apply the moneys in the sinking fund to the redemption of the bonds, and to make every such payment without further formality except as the fiscal agents or either of them may be advised may be necessary to comply with some law or regulation of the United States of America or other public authority therein.

6. The Caja during the life of the loan will maintain in the Borough of Manhattan, in the city of New York, a fiscal agency or fiscal agencies of the loan and a registry of the loan. The Caja appoints Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, of the city and State of New York, United States of America, to be fiscal agents of the loan during the life of the loan, subject to the terms and conditions of this agreement. The Caja also appoints said Guaranty Trust Co. of New York as registrar of the loan during the life of the loan subject to the terms and conditions of this agreement.

7. Neither the fiscal agents nor the registrar shall be liable otherwise than for good faith and the exercise of reasonable care. The fiscal agents and the registrar and each of them shall be protected in any action which any of them may take in acting on any bond or coupon or any notice, request, or other paper believed by them or it to be genuine as well as in or in respect of any action taken or suffered in good faith under the advice of counsel. Neither of the bankers and neither of the fiscal agents shall be liable for any act or omission of the other.

8. The Caja shall pay each of the fiscal agents as compensation for their services a commission of one quarter of 1 percent of the amount of all payments made to such fiscal agent pursuant to paragraphs (a) and (b) of article 5 hereof, such compensation to be paid to the fiscal agents at the time when such payments are made to the fiscal agents. The Caja shall also pay the fiscal agents as compensation for their services a commission of one quarter of 1 percent of the principal amount of all bonds delivered to the Caja in payment of its mortgage loans; one half of such compensation to be paid to each of the fiscal agents at the time when such bonds are sent to the fiscal agents for cancellation as provided in article 4 hereof.

9. In case any of the bonds shall become mutilated, destroyed, or lost, a new bond (having endorsed thereon the guaranty of the Republic of Chile in this agreement provided for) of like amount, tenor, and date, bearing the same number and bearing all unmaturing coupons shall be issued by the Caja, but only if permitted by and in accordance with Chilean law, and the registrar shall authenticate the same for delivery in exchange for, and upon cancellation of, the bond so mutilated and its unmaturing coupons, or in lieu of the bond so de-

stroyed or lost and its unmatured coupons, but in the case of destroyed or lost bonds only upon receipt by the Caja and the registrar of evidence satisfactory to each of them that such bonds were destroyed or lost and, if required, upon receipt also of indemnity satisfactory to each of them in their discretion. The registrar shall incur no liability for such action.

10. The Caja agrees to sell and deliver to the bankers and the bankers agree to purchase from the Caja and pay for \$20,000,000 aggregate principal amount of the bonds at the price of 91¾ percent of the principal amount thereof and accrued interest to May 21, 1928, being \$18,420,000.

In the first instance an appropriately executed temporary bond (which may be printed, written, or typewritten) for \$20,000,000, in substantially the form hereto annexed and marked "Schedule C", and endorsed with the guaranty of the Republic of Chile, in substantially the form hereto annexed and marked "Schedule D", shall be delivered on or before May 17, 1928, unless the bankers consent to postpone this date, to Banco de Chile, for account of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York. The charges of Banco de Chile shall be paid by the Caja. Payment of \$7,912,000, the first installment of the purchase price, shall be made on May 21, 1928, unless the time for such delivery shall be extended by the bankers at the request of the Caja, as above provided, and in that case, within the period of such extension on 5 days' notice to the bankers in writing, but such payment shall not be made until after receipt of cable advice from Banco de Chile to Guaranty Trust Co. of New York of the delivery of such temporary bond. Payment of \$1,500,000, the second installment of the purchase price, shall be made on June 15, 1928, and payment of \$9,008,000, the final installment of the purchase price, shall be made on August 1, 1928.

Payment of the first installment of the purchase price shall be made by paying one half of the amount thereof to Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and one half of the amount thereof to Guaranty Trust Co. of New York in full payment of the \$3,000,000, 5½-percent notes of the Caja issued under the agreement between the Caja and the bankers, dated February 3, 1928. Payment of the second and third installments shall be made by placing the amount of each such installment of the purchase price to the credit of the Caja in dollars in the city of New York, one half of each such installment to be credited to the account of the Caja with Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and one half of each such installment to be credited to the account of the Caja with Guaranty Trust Co. of New York. The amounts so credited to the Caja shall be withdrawn upon the order of such person or persons as may be authorized to draw upon the same by the Caja, and all withdrawals shall be made in substantially equal amounts from Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and from Guaranty Trust Co. of New York; *Provided, however*, That no part of the final installment of the purchase price shall be withdrawn before September 29, 1928.

Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and Guaranty Trust Co. of New York shall each credit the Caja with interest at the current rate which New York Clearing House banks may then be paying on the amounts so credited with them, respectively, until disbursed by the Caja; except that they will pay interest only at the rate of 1½ percent per annum from August 1, 1928, to September 29, 1928, on the amount of said final installment on deposit with them.

11. Forthwith upon the execution of this agreement the Caja will deliver or cause to be delivered to the bankers a prospectus letter or letters containing information concerning the financial position of the Caja and of the Republic of Chile, its debts, income, and expenditures, and financial administration and such other information and in such form as the bankers may reasonably request and as shall be satisfactory to the bankers' counsel, such letter or letters to be signed by the Chilean Ambassador to the United States of America.

12. It is a condition precedent to any obligation of the bankers hereunder (a) that the Caja shall have promptly delivered a prospectus letter as set forth above in article 11 hereof, and (b) that on or before May 17, 1928, unless the time be extended by the bankers at the request of the Caja as hereinbefore provided, and, in that case, within the period of such extension.

(1) The Caja shall have delivered to the representative of the bankers in Chile duly authenticated copies of the laws or decrees or other instruments authorizing the issue of the bonds by the Caja and the guaranty of the bonds by the Republic of Chile in accordance with the terms of this agreement and also duly certified copies of all proceedings of the Caja and all executive and other decrees of the Government of the Republic of Chile necessary to comply with said laws in connection with the execution and delivery of the bonds hereunder.

(2) The bankers shall have received an opinion satisfactory to the bankers' counsel in New York, of Chilean counsel approved by the bankers' counsel in New York, approving the proceedings of the Caja authorizing the creation, issue, and sale of the bonds and approving the guaranty of the bonds by the Republic of Chile, in accordance with the terms of this agreement, the sufficiency of all action taken thereunder, the validity of this agreement, and the validity of the bonds, both temporary and definitive, in the hands of holders of whatever citizenship or residence, in accordance with the terms of the bonds and of this agreement.

(3) That the bankers' counsel in New York shall have approved the form of the bonds and coupons.

13. The Caja will pay all stamp and other duties, if any, to which under the laws of Chile or of the United States of America this agreement or the bonds may be subject. The Caja will also pay the cost of printing, engraving, executing, and authenticating the temporary and definitive bonds and interim certificates, the expense of exchanging the temporary bond and interim certificates for definitive bonds, and of transporting the temporary and definitive bonds to and from Santiago, and the compensation and expenses of the registrar. The Caja will also pay the fees and disbursements of the Chilean counsel referred to in article 12 hereof.

14. The Caja hereby covenants and agrees that no bonds issued or guaranteed by it other than the bonds purchased by the bankers hereunder shall be sold or offered for sale in the United States of America prior to November 1, 1928, except with the written consent of the bankers.

15. If between the date of this agreement and the offering of the bonds for public subscription by the bankers any conditions of the nature of force majeure or any political, financial, or commercial developments, or market conditions, shall in the opinion of the bankers, whose conclusions in this respect shall be final, render inadvisable the issue to the public of the bonds, or of a portion thereof, then the bankers shall be at liberty, at their option, to give the Caja notice of their determination not to proceed with the purchase of the bonds, or of a portion thereof, and thereupon the obligations of the bankers under article 10 hereof with respect to the purchase of the bonds, or such thereof as they shall have decided not to purchase, shall forthwith terminate, but all the other obligations of either party to the other under this agreement shall continue in force.

16. The Caja hereby covenants and agrees that it will not issue or sell any securities of the Caja in the United States of America, or issue or sell any securities intended to be sold or offered for sale in the United States of America, prior to May 1, 1931, without first giving the bankers a 30-day option to purchase such securities on terms and conditions at least as favorable to the bankers as the Caja is able to obtain from other sources at the time when such issue or sale is proposed. If the bankers shall not exercise such option within the 30-day period, the Caja shall have the right to offer such securities elsewhere on terms and conditions not less favorable to the Caja than those offered to the bankers. The Caja will not reoffer such securities, or accept offers therefor, on terms and conditions less favorable to the Caja without giving the bankers a 30-day option to purchase such securities on such less favorable terms and conditions. The Caja, however, reserves the right to negotiate through an agent, who will be instructed to work in accordance with these conditions.

17. The Caja will, at the request of the bankers, make or cause to be made application for the listing of the bonds and interim certificates on the New York Stock Exchange, or the bankers may themselves make such application for and on account of the Caja. The Caja will furnish to the bankers all documents deemed by the bankers to be advantageous for the making of such application, and it will take and undertake all such action as may be requisite in accordance with the requirements of said exchange in order to secure such listing. The cost and expenses of such application, whether made by the bankers or by the Caja, shall be paid by the Caja.

18. Reference in this agreement to the fiscal agents or either of them shall be deemed to include any successor firm or corporation, however constituted, continuing the business of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and/or Guaranty Trust Co., of New York. Reference in this agreement to the registrar shall be deemed to include any successor corporation continuing the business of Guaranty Trust Co., of New York. Reference in this agreement to the bankers, or either of them, shall be deemed to include any successor firm or corporation, however constituted, continuing the business of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and/or Guaranty Co., of New York.

In witness whereof Caja de Credito Hipotecario has caused this agreement to be signed in its behalf by His Excellency the Honorable Carlos G. Davila, thereunto duly authorized, and Kuhn, Loeb & Co. have signed this agreement, and Guaranty Co., of New York, has caused this agreement to be signed by its president or one of its vice presidents, and its corporate seal to be affixed hereto and attested by its secretary as of the day and year first above written.

CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO,
By CARLOS G. DAVILA.
KUHN, LOEB & CO.
GUARANTY Co. OF NEW YORK,
By BURNETT WALKER,
Vice President.

[SEAL]

Attest:

W. R. NELSON, *Secretary.*

The undersigned accept their appointment as fiscal agents under the foregoing agreement upon the terms and conditions thereof; and the undersigned Guaranty Trust Co. of New York also accepts its appointment as registrar thereunder upon the terms and conditions thereof.

GUARANTY TRUST Co. OF NEW YORK,
By BURNETT WALKER, *Vice President.*

SCHEDULE A

[Form of definitive bond]

No. _____.

\$ _____.

CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO (CHILE)—(MORTGAGE BANK OF CHILE) GUARANTEED SINKING FUND 6 PER CENT GOLD BOND OF 1928, DUE APRIL 30, 1961

Letra de Credito al Portador por U.S. — \$ — oro (dollars americanos) que ganan el 6 percent de interes annual. Reembolsable por sorteos semestrales a mas tardar en 33 anos. Los intereses y amortizaciones se pagan el 31 de Octubre y 30 de Abril, en cambio del cupon respectivo o de la letra amortizada.

Caja de Credito Hipotecario (herein called the "Caja") for value received, promises to pay to the bearer on April 30, 1961, the sum of dollars (&—) and to pay interest thereon from April 30, 1928, until the principal of this bond is paid, at the rate of 6 percent per annum, semiannually, on April 30 and October 31 in each year, upon presentation and surrender of the coupons hereto annexed as they severally mature.

The principal of, and interest on this bond are payable at the option of the holder in the borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co., or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co., of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of or equal to the standard of weight and fineness existing April 30, 1928, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, and will be paid without deduction for any taxes, imposts, levies, or duties of any nature now or at any time hereafter imposed by the Republic of Chile or by any State, Province, municipality, or other taxing authority thereof or therein, and will be paid in time of war as well as in time of peace, and whether the holder be a citizen or resident of a friendly or a hostile state.

This bond is one of an issue of bonds known as "the guaranteed sinking fund 6 percent gold bonds of 1928", the Caja (herein called the bonds) limited to \$20,000,000 principal amount, issued in accordance with the law of the Republic of Chile dated August 29, 1855, the decree law no. 308 dated March 9, 1925, the decree law dated December 15, 1925, and the decree of the President of the Republic of Chile dated January 31, 1928, constituting the loan designated "Emprestito oro Caja Hipotecario, 1928", of which \$8,000,000 principal amount, of the bonds are to provide for construction purposes according to said decree law no. 308, dated March 9, 1925, and \$12,000,000 principal amount, are to provide for other corporate purposes.

Until all the bonds shall have been retired or redeemed the Caja will pay to the fiscal agents as an annuity for the service of interest and amortization of

the bonds the sum of \$1,400,000 per annum in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid, except as hereinafter provided. Such sums shall be paid in equal semiannual installments before the 30th day of April and the 31st day of October in each year, the first payment to be made before October 31, 1928, and the last payment to be made before April 30, 1961.

The fiscal agents shall apply each such installment to the payment of the interest maturing on the next succeeding interest date on the bonds then outstanding and shall apply the part of each such installment not required for the payment of such interest as a sinking fund for the redemption of bonds on such interest date as hereinafter provided. The Caja may, at its option, increase the amount of any semiannual installment to be applied to the redemption of bonds on any semiannual interest date, and, in the event of any such increase, all subsequent semiannual instalments shall be reduced to an amount sufficient to provide for the semiannual service of interest and amortization of the bonds which shall be outstanding after the application of such increased sinking-fund installment to the redemption of bonds, such amount to be calculated as a cumulative sinking fund compounded semiannually at the rate of 6 percent per annum to redeem, on or before April 30, 1961, all of the bonds so outstanding. Any such reduced semiannual installment may similarly be increased, in which event subsequent semiannual installments shall be similarly reduced. The part of each semiannual installment available for the redemption of bonds shall be applied to the redemption of bonds by lot at 100 percent of their principal amount on the interest date next succeeding the date of such payment. The numbers of the bonds to be redeemed on each such interest date shall be drawn by lot in any usual manner.

The drawings shall be held in the public at the principal office of the Caja in the city of Santiago. The numbers of the bonds so drawn for redemption shall be advertised at least twice in two daily newspapers of general circulation in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, the first advertisement to appear not less than 30 days prior to the redemption date. The bonds so called for redemption shall on the redemption date designated in such notice become due and payable at 100 percent of their principal amount, and shall be payable, at the option of the holders, in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co., or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co., of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, and shall be paid by the Caja on and after the redemption date at the redemption price aforesaid on presentation and surrender of such bonds at any of said offices, together with all coupons thereto appertaining maturing after the redemption date.

If any bond so presented shall not be accompanied by all coupons maturing after the redemption date, then said bond shall be paid at the redemption price aforesaid less the aggregate principal amount of all coupons maturing after the redemption date not presented and surrendered with said bond: *Provided*, That if more than four such coupons are not presented and surrendered with said bond the fiscal agents or the Caja may refuse to pay said bond. Notice having been so given by publication the bonds so called for redemption shall cease to bear interest from the redemption date unless they shall not be so paid by the Caja upon presentation and surrender thereof with all coupons maturing after the redemption date.

This bond and the coupons appertaining thereto shall pass by delivery.

This bond shall not become valid or obligatory for any purpose until it shall be authenticated by the certificate of the registrar hereon endorsed.

In witness whereof, Caja de Credito Hipotecario has caused this bond to be executed in its name, bearing the facsimile signature of the director and to be manually signed by its cashier thereunto duly authorized and to be impressed with its seal and the interest coupons bearing the facsimile signature of the director to be hereto annexed.

Dated April 30, 1928.

CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO,
By _____, *Cashier*.

LUIS BARROS BORGONO, *Director*.

[Form of registrar's certificate]

This is one of the within described guaranteed sinking fund 6 percent gold bonds of 1928 of Caja de Credito Hipotecario (Chile).

GUARANTY TRUST CO. OF NEW YORK, *Registrar*,
By _____.

[Form of coupon]

No. _____ \$_____

On _____, 19—, unless the bond hereinafter mentioned shall have been called for previous redemption, Caja de Credito Hipotecario (Chile), promises to pay to bearer, at his option, in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of or equal to the standard of weight and fineness existing April 30, 1928, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, _____ dollars (\$____) without deduction for any taxes, imposts, levies, or duties of any nature now or at any time hereafter imposed by the Republic of Chile or by any State, province, municipality or other taxing authority thereof or therein, in time of war as well as in time of peace and whether the holder be a citizen or resident of a friendly or a hostile state, being 6 months' interest then due on its guaranteed sinking fund 6 percent gold bond of 1928, dated April 30, 1928, No. _____.

CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO,
By LUIS BARROS BORGONO, *Director*.

SCHEDULE B

The Republic of Chile, for a valuable consideration, hereby unconditionally guarantees to the holder of the within bond prompt payment of the principal amount of said bond in accordance with its terms when the same shall become due and payable, whether at the maturity thereof or otherwise, and of the interest thereon at the rate and at the times specified in said bond and in the appurtenant coupons; upon presentation and surrender of said coupons as they severally mature, and also prompt payment to the fiscal agents of the semi-annual payments mentioned in said bond for the service of interest and amortization of the bonds when the same shall become due and payable.

Dated April 30, 1928.

REPUBLIC OF CHILE,
By _____.

SCHEDULE C

[Form of temporary bond]

No. _____ \$_____

CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO (CHILE)—(MORTGAGE BANK OF CHILE) GUARANTEED
SINKING FUND 6 PERCENT GOLD BOND OF 1928, DUE APRIL 30, 1961

Caja de Credito Hipotecario (herein called the Caja) for value received promises to pay to the bearer on April 30, 1961, the sum of \$20,000,000 and to pay interest thereon from April 30, 1928, until the principal of this bond is paid, at the rate of 6 percent per annum semiannually, on April 30 and October 31 in each year.

The principal of and interest on this bond are payable at the option of the holder, in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co., or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of or equal to the standard of weight and fineness existing April 30, 1928, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, and will be paid without deduction for any taxes, imposts, levies, or duties of any nature now or at any time hereafter imposed by the Republic of Chile or by any state, province, municipality, or other taxing authority thereof or therein, and will be paid in time of war as well as in time of peace and whether the holder be a citizen or resident of a friendly or a hostile State.

This bond is a temporary bond without coupons and is one of an issue of bonds known as the guaranteed sinking fund 6 percent gold bonds of 1928 of the Caja (herein called the bonds) limited to \$20,000,000 principal amount, issued in accordance with the law of the Republic of Chile dated August 29, 1855, the decree law no. 308 dated March 9, 1925, the decree law dated December 15, 1925, and the decree of the President of the Republic of Chile dated January 31, 1928, constituting the loan designated Empróstito oro Caja Hipotecario, 1928, of which \$8,000,000 principal amount of the bonds are to provide for construction purposes according to said decree law no. 308, dated March 9, 1925, and \$12,000,000 principal amount, are to provide for other corporate purposes.

Until all the bonds shall have been retired or redeemed the Caja will pay to the fiscal agents as an annuity for the service of interest and amortization of the bonds the sum of \$1,400,000 per annum in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid, except as hereinafter provided. Such sums shall be paid in equal semiannual installments before the 30th day of April and the 31st day of October in each year, the first payment to be made before October 31, 1928, and the last payment to be made before April 30, 1961. The fiscal agents shall apply each such installment to the payment of the interest maturing on the next succeeding interest date on the bonds then outstanding and shall apply the part of each such installment not required for the payment of such interest as a sinking fund for the redemption of bonds on such interest date as hereinafter provided.

The caja may, at its option, increase the amount of any semiannual installment to be applied to the redemption of bonds on any semiannual interest date, and in the event of any such increase all subsequent semiannual installments shall be reduced to an amount sufficient to provide for the semiannual service of interest and amortization of the bonds which shall be outstanding after the application of such increased sinking-fund installment to the redemption of bonds, such amount to be calculated as a cumulative sinking fund, compounded semiannually at the rate of 6 percent per annum, to redeem on or before April 30, 1961, all of the bonds so outstanding. Any such reduced semiannual installment may similarly be increased, in which event subsequent semiannual installments shall be similarly reduced. The part of each semiannual installment available for the redemption of bonds shall be applied to the redemption of bonds by lot at 100 percent of their principal amount on the interest date next succeeding the date of such payment. The numbers of the bonds to be redeemed on each such interest date shall be drawn by lot in any usual manner. The drawings shall be held in public at the principal office of the caja in the city of Santiago. The numbers of the bonds so drawn for redemption shall be advertised at least twice in two daily newspapers of general circulation in the borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, the first advertisement to appear not less than 30 days prior to the redemption date.

The bonds so called for redemption shall on the redemption date designated in such notice become due and payable at 100 percent of their principal amount, and shall be payable, at the option of the holders, in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co., or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, and shall be paid by the Caja on and after the redemption date at the redemption price aforesaid on presentation and surrender of such bonds at any of said offices, together with all coupons thereto appertaining maturing after the redemption date. If any bond so presented shall not be accompanied by all coupons maturing after the redemption date, then said bond shall be paid at the redemption price aforesaid less the aggregate principal amount of all coupons maturing after the redemption date not presented and surrendered with said bond; provided, that if more than four such coupons are not presented and surrendered with said bond the fiscal agents or the Caja may refuse to pay said bond. Notice having been so given by publication the bonds so called for redemption shall cease to bear interest from the redemption date unless they shall not be so paid by the Caja upon presentation and surrender thereof with all coupons maturing after the redemption date.

This temporary bond is exchangeable for definitive engraved bonds of this issue of like tenor and for a like aggregate principal amount when engraved

and prepared, endorsed with the guaranty of the Republic of Chile, corresponding so far as appropriate with the guaranty hereon endorsed.

This bond shall pass by delivery.

In witness whereof, Caja de Credito Hipotecario has caused this bond to be executed in its name bearing the signature of the director and of its cashier thereunto duly authorized and to be impressed with its seal.

Dated April 30, 1928.

CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO,
By _____, *Cashier.*

SCHEDULE D

The Republic of Chile, for a valuable consideration, hereby unconditionally guarantees to the holder of the within bond prompt payment of the principal amount of said bond in accordance with its terms, when the same shall become due and payable, whether at the maturity thereof or otherwise, and of the interest thereon at the rate and at the times specified in said bond, and also prompt payment to the fiscal agents of the semiannual payments mentioned in said bond for the service of interest and amortization of the bonds, when the same shall become due and payable, and the Republic of Chile hereby agrees to endorse on the several definitive engraved bonds to be delivered in exchange for the within temporary bond its guaranty substantially as aforesaid with appropriate variations.

Dated April 30, 1928.

REPUBLIC OF CHILE,
By _____.

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT 16, JUNE 28, 1933

AGREEMENT BETWEEN CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO (CHILE) AND KUHN, LOEB & CO. AND GUARANTY CO. OF NEW YORK, MAY 1, 1929. GUARANTEED SINKING-FUND 6 PERCENT GOLD BONDS OF 1929

Agreement, dated as of May 1, 1929, made in the city and State of New York in the United States of America between Caja de Credito Hipotecario, of Santiago, Chile, organized under the laws of Chile (hereinafter called the "Caja"), acting by His Excellency, Carlos G. Davila, Chilean Ambassador to the United States of America, thereunto duly authorized, and Kuhn, Loeb & Co., a copartnership of the city and State of New York, and Guaranty Co. of New York, a corporation organized under the laws of the State of Delaware (hereinafter called the "Bankers").

In consideration of the mutual covenants hereinafter set forth, it is agreed as follows:

1. The Caja will forthwith create an issue of bonds to be known as its guaranteed sinking-fund 6 percent gold bonds of 1929 (hereinafter called the "Bonds") limited to \$20,000,000 principal amount, to constitute the loan designated "Emprestito oro Caja Hipotecaria, 1929." The bonds shall be issued in accordance with the law of the Republic of Chile of August 29, 1855, establishing the Caja, as amended by decree law no. 743, dated December 15, 1928, which decree law was duly approved by the Commission appointed for that purpose by both Houses of Congress, and with law no. 4074, dated July 27, 1926, as amended by law no. 4327, dated March 26, 1928, and with the decree of the President of the Republic of Chile, no. 2694, dated June 25, 1929, which authorize the guaranty of the bonds by the Republic of Chile. Ten million dollars, principal amount, of the bonds are to provide for agricultural loans in accordance with said laws no. 4074 and no. 4327, and \$10,000,000, principal amount, of the bonds are to provide for the redemption of outstanding bonds of the Caja. The bonds shall be in coupon form, payable to bearer, shall be dated May 1, 1929, shall mature May 1, 1962, shall bear interest from May 1, 1929, at the rate of 6 percent per annum, payable semiannually on May 1 and November 1 in each year, and shall be in the denominations of \$1,000 and \$500 in such proportions as the bankers may request.

The principal of, and interest on, the bonds shall be payable without deduction for any taxes, imposts, levies, or duties of any nature, now or at any time

hereafter imposed by the Republic of Chile or by any State, Province, municipality, or other taxing authority thereof or therein, and shall be paid, at the option of the holders, in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York in gold coin of the United States of America of or equal to the standard of weight and fineness existing May 1, 1929, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, and shall be paid in time of war as well as in time of peace and whether the holder be a citizen or resident of a friendly or a hostile state. The bonds shall be authenticated by the certificate endorsed thereon of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, registrar of the loan hereinafter appointed.

The Republic of Chile shall unconditionally guarantee to the holders of the bonds prompt payment of the principal of, and the interest on, the bonds, as and when the same shall become due and payable and also prompt payment to the fiscal agents, hereinafter appointed, of the semiannual payments for the service of interest and amortization of the bonds hereinafter mentioned as and when the same shall become due and payable, and such guaranty shall be endorsed on the bonds. The text of the guaranty shall be substantially in the form hereto annexed and marked schedule B.

2. The text of the definitive engraved bonds shall be in the English language substantially in the form hereto annexed and marked schedule A, and shall bear a notation in Spanish substantially in the form shown on said schedule A. The text of the usual certificate of the Treasury Department of the Republic of Chile on bonds of the Caja shall be in Spanish, or in both English and Spanish, as the bankers may elect, in such form as may be required by Chilean law. The Caja hereby authorizes the bankers to cause to be prepared without delay definitive engraved bonds for execution by or on behalf of the Caja, such bonds to be engraved and printed in New York in accordance with the requirements of the New York Stock Exchange. The bankers may issue or cause to be issued by a bank or trust company in New York temporary interim certificates which, if issued, shall, in due course, be exchangeable without cost or expense to the bankers or the holders, for definitive engraved bonds.

The definitive bonds shall bear the facsimile signature of Don Luis Barros Borgoño, the director of the Caja, and shall be manually signed by Don Francisco Bahamondes, the cashier of the Caja, or other duly authorized officer of the Caja. The certificate of the Treasury Department shall be signed manually or otherwise as may be required by Chilean law. The coupons shall bear the facsimile signature of Don Luis Barros Borgoño, the director of the Caja. The guaranty of the Republic of Chile endorsed on the bonds shall be manually signed by His Excellency, Carlos G. Davila, the Chilean Ambassador to the United States of America, thereunto duly authorized by the Government of the Republic of Chile or by some other duly authorized representative of the Republic of Chile.

3. Until all of the bonds shall have been retired or redeemed, the Caja shall pay to the fiscal agents as an annuity for the service of interest and amortization of the bonds the sum of \$1,400,000 per annum in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid, except as hereinafter in this article provided. Such sums shall be paid in equal semiannual installments at least 15 days before the 1st day of May and the 1st day of November in each year as hereinafter in article 5 hereof provided.

The fiscal agents shall apply each such installment to the payment of the interest maturing on the next succeeding interest date on the bonds then outstanding and shall apply the part of each such installment not required for the payment of such interest as a sinking fund for the redemption of bonds on such interest date as hereinafter provided.

The Caja may, at its option, increase the amount of any semiannual installment to be applied to the redemption of bonds on any semiannual interest date, and, in the event of any such increase, all subsequent semiannual installments may be reduced to an amount sufficient to provide for the semiannual service of interest and amortization of the bonds which shall be outstanding after the application of such increased sinking-fund installment to the redemption of bonds, such amount to be calculated as a cumulative sinking fund compounded semiannually at the rate of 6 percent per annum to redeem, on or before May 1, 1962, all of the bonds so outstanding. Any such reduced semiannual installment may similarly be increased in which event subsequent semiannual installments may be similarly reduced.

The part of each semiannual installment available for the redemption of bonds shall be applied to the redemption of bonds by lot of 100 percent of their principal amount on the interest date next succeeding the date of such payment.

The numbers of the bonds to be redeemed on each such interest date shall be drawn by lot in any usual manner. The drawings shall be held in public at the principal office of the Caja in the city of Santiago. The Caja shall notify the fiscal agents of the aggregate principal amount and numbers of the bonds to be redeemed on each interest date and such notification shall be sent to the fiscal agents at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. in the city of New York so as to be received at said office at least 45 days prior to such interest date. The numbers of the bonds so drawn for redemption shall be advertised at least twice in two daily newspapers of general circulation in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, the first advertisement to appear not less than 30 days prior to the redemption date. If the New York Stock Exchange so requires, the advertisement shall be further published.

The bonds so called for redemption shall on the redemption date designated in such notice become due and payable at 100 percent of their principal amount and shall be payable, at the option of the holders, in the borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, and shall be paid by the Caja on and after the redemption date at the redemption price aforesaid on presentation and surrender of such bonds at any of said offices, together with all coupons thereto appertaining maturing after the redemption date. If any bond so presented shall not be accompanied by all coupons maturing after the redemption date, then said bond shall be paid at the redemption price aforesaid less the aggregate principal amount of all coupons maturing after the redemption date not presented and surrendered with said bond: *Provided*, That if more than four such coupons are not presented and surrendered with said bond, the fiscal agents or the Caja may refuse to pay said bond. Notice having been given by publication, the bonds so called for redemption shall cease to bear interest from the redemption date unless they shall not be so paid by the Caja upon presentation and surrender thereof with all coupons maturing after the redemption date.

No expenses in connection with the redemption of the bonds or the operation of the sinking fund shall be charged against the sinking fund, but such expenses shall be paid by the Caja.

4. All notices or other announcements relating to the redemption of the bonds, the payment of the coupons, or any other matter in connection with the bonds may be given or made by the fiscal agents, jointly or severally, on behalf of the Caja as the fiscal agents shall deem proper, but all expenses in connection therewith shall be paid by the Caja.

All bonds redeemed through the sinking fund, with all unmatured coupons thereto appertaining and all coupons paid by the fiscal agents, shall be canceled by the fiscal agents and by them delivered to a representative of the Caja for that purpose in the city of New York or sent by registered mail insured to and at the risk and expense of the Caja. All bonds paid in Santiago by the Caja, and all bonds delivered to the Caja in payment of its loans shall be sent, as soon as practicable after such payment or delivery, to the fiscal agents for cancellation at the risk and expense of the Caja, and no bonds delivered to the Caja in payment of its loans shall be reissued or renegotiated by the Caja.

5. So long as any of the bonds shall be outstanding the Caja covenants to pay to the fiscal agents at their respective offices in the city of New York in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid.

(a) At least 15 days before May 1 and November 1 in each year the sum of \$700,000 (or, in the event that the Caja shall have increased the amount of any previous semiannual installment as provided in article 3 hereof, such lesser amount as may be due as provided in said article 3) to be applied to the service of interest and amortization of the bonds as provided in article 3 hereof, the first payment to be made at least 15 days before November 1, 1929, and the last payment to be made at least 15 days before May 1, 1962; and if the Caja shall elect to increase the amount of any such semiannual installment as provided in article 3 hereof, the amount of any such increase at least 15 days before the interest date on which such amount is to be applied to the redemption

of bonds. One half of each payment made pursuant to this paragraph (a) shall be made to Kuhn, Loeb & Co. at their office in the city of New York, and one half of each such payment shall be made to Guaranty Trust Co. of New York at its principal office in the city of New York;

(b) At least 15 days before May 1, 1962, a sum equal to the principal amount of all the bonds then outstanding, one half of such payment to be made to Kuhn, Loeb & Co. at their office in the city of New York, and one half of such payment to be made to Guaranty Trust Co. of New York. Any amounts in the sinking fund to be applied to the redemption of bonds on May 1, 1962, at the time of the payment made pursuant to this paragraph (b) shall be credited against such payment; and

(c) Such amounts as may be required to meet all expenses incident to the service of the loan, including the compensation and expenses of the registrar; such payments to be made from time to time, on the joint written or cabled request of the fiscal agents, to the fiscal agent or fiscal agents stated in such request.

The fiscal agents shall not be required to segregate any moneys paid to or deposited with them as hereinbefore provided. The Caja irrevocably authorizes and directs the fiscal agents and each of them to pay out of the moneys paid to them as hereinbefore provided, the interest on the bonds to the bearers of the coupons upon presentation and surrender thereof, and the principal of the bonds at maturity or on the redemption dates, as the case may be, to the bearers of the bonds to be paid or redeemed upon presentation and surrender thereof, and to apply the moneys in the sinking fund to the redemption of the bonds, and to make every such payment without further formality except as the fiscal agents or either of them may be advised may be necessary to comply with some law or regulation of the United States of America or other public authority therein.

6. The Caja during the life of the loan will maintain in the borough of Manhattan, in the city of New York, a fiscal agency or fiscal agencies of the loan and a registry of the loan. The Caja appoints Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, of the city and State of New York, United States of America, to be fiscal agents of the loan during the life of the loan subject to the terms and conditions of this agreement. The Caja also appoints said Guaranty Trust Co. of New York as registrar of the loan during the life of the loan subject to the terms and conditions of this agreement.

7. Neither the fiscal agents nor the registrar shall be liable otherwise than for good faith and the exercise of reasonable care. The fiscal agents and the registrar and each of them shall be protected in any action which any of them may take in acting on any bond or coupon or any notice, request, or other paper believed by them or it to be genuine as well as in or in respect of any action taken or suffered in good faith under the advice of counsel. Neither of the bankers and neither of the fiscal agents shall be liable for any act or omission of the other.

8. The Caja shall pay each of the fiscal agents as compensation for their services a commission of one quarter of 1 percent of the amount of all payments made to such fiscal agent pursuant to paragraphs (a) and (b) of article 5 hereof, such compensation to be paid to the fiscal agents at the time when such payments are made to the fiscal agents. The Caja shall also pay the fiscal agents as compensation for their services a commission of one quarter of 1 percent of the principal amount of all bonds delivered to the Caja in payment of its mortgage loans, one half of such compensation to be paid to each of the fiscal agents at the time when such bonds are sent to the fiscal agents for cancellation as provided in article 4 hereof.

9. In case any of the bonds shall become mutilated, destroyed, or lost, a new bond (having endorsed thereon the guaranty of the Republic of Chile in this agreement provided for) of like amount, tenor, and date, bearing the same number and bearing all unmatured coupons shall be issued by the Caja, but only if permitted by and in accordance with Chilean law, and the registrar shall authenticate the same for delivery in exchange for, and upon cancellation of, the bond so mutilated and its unmatured coupons, or in lieu of the bond so destroyed or lost and its unmatured coupons, but in the case of destroyed or lost bonds, only upon receipt by the Caja and the registrar of evidence satisfactory to each of them that such bonds were destroyed or lost, and, if required, upon receipt also of indemnity satisfactory to each of them, in their discretion. The registrar shall incur no liability for such action.

10. The Caja agrees to sell and deliver to the bankers and the bankers agree to purchase from the Caja and pay for \$20,000,000 aggregate principal amount

of the bonds at the price of 89½ percent of the principal amount thereof, being \$17,900,000.

In the first instance an appropriately executed temporary bond (which may be printed, written, or typewritten) for \$20,000,000, in substantially the form hereto annexed and marked "Schedule C", and endorsed with the guaranty of the Republic of Chile, in substantially the form hereto annexed and marked "Schedule D", shall be delivered on or before July 8, 1929, unless the bankers consent to postpone this date, to Banco de Chile, for account of Guaranty Trust Co., of New York. The charges of Banco de Chile shall be paid by the Caja. Payment of \$8,000,000, being the first installment of the purchase price above stated, shall be made on July 16, 1929, unless the time for such delivery shall be extended by the bankers at the request of the Caja, as above provided, and in that case within the period of such extension on 5-days' notice to the bankers in writing, but such payment shall not be made until after receipt of cable advice from Banco de Chile to Guaranty Trust Co., New York, of the delivery of such temporary bond. Payment of \$7,000,000, being the second installment of said purchase price, shall be made on September 27, 1929, and payment of \$2,900,000, being the final installment of said purchase price, shall be made on October 24, 1929.

Payment of each instalment of said purchase price shall be made by placing the amount thereof to the credit of the Caja in dollars in the city of New York, one half of each such installment to be credited to the account of the Caja with Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and one half thereof to be credited to the account of the Caja with Guaranty Trust Co. of New York. The amounts so credited to the Caja shall be withdrawn upon the order of such person or persons as may be authorized to draw upon the same by the Caja, and all withdrawals shall be made in substantially equal amounts from Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and from Guaranty Trust Co. of New York.

Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and Guaranty Trust Co. of New York shall each credit the Caja with interest at the current rate which New York Clearing House banks may then be paying on the amounts so credited with them, respectively, until disbursed by the Caja.

11. Forthwith upon the execution of this agreement the Caja will deliver or cause to be delivered to the bankers a prospectus letter or letters containing information concerning the financial position of the Caja and of the Republic of Chile, their debts, income and expenditures, and financial administration and such other information and in such form as the bankers may reasonably request and as shall be satisfactory to the bankers' counsel, such letter or letters to be signed by the Chilean Ambassador to the United States of America.

12. It is a condition precedent to any obligation of the bankers hereunder (a) that the Caja shall have promptly delivered a prospectus letter as set forth above in article 11 hereof, and (b) that on or before July 8, 1929, unless the time be extended by the bankers at the request of the Caja as hereinbefore provided, and, in that case, within the period of such extension—

(1) The Caja shall have delivered to the representative of the bankers in Chile duly authenticated copies of the laws or decrees or other instruments authorizing the issue of the bonds by the Caja and the guaranty of the bonds by the Republic of Chile in accordance with the terms of this agreement, and also duly certified copies of all proceedings of the Caja and all executive and other decrees of the Government of the Republic of Chile necessary to comply with said laws in connection with the execution and delivery of the bonds hereunder;

(2) The bankers shall have received an opinion satisfactory to the bankers' counsel in New York, of Chilean counsel approved by the bankers' counsel in New York, approving the proceedings of the Caja authorizing the creation, issue, and sale of the bonds and approving the guaranty of the bonds by the Republic of Chile, in accordance with the terms of this agreement, the sufficiency of all action taken thereunder, the validity of this agreement, and the validity of the bonds, both temporary and definitive, in the hands of holders of whatever citizenship or residence, in accordance with the terms of the bonds and of this agreement; and

(3) That the bankers' counsel in New York shall have approved the form of the bonds and coupons.

13. The Caja will pay all stamp and other duties, if any, to which under the laws of Chile or of the United States of America this agreement or the bonds may be subject. The Caja will also pay the cost of printing, engraving, executing, and authenticating the temporary and definitive bonds and interim certifi-

cates, the expense of exchanging the temporary bond and interim certificates for definitive bonds and of transporting the temporary and definitive bonds to and from Santiago, and the compensation and expenses of the registrar. The Caja will also pay the fees and disbursements of the Chilean counsel referred to in article 12 hereof.

14. The Caja hereby covenants and agrees that no bonds issued or guaranteed by it other than the bonds purchased by the bankers hereunder shall be sold or offered for sale in the United States of America prior to January 1, 1930, except with the written consent of the bankers.

15. If between the date of this agreement and the offering of the bonds for public subscription by the bankers, any conditions of the nature of force majeure or any political, financial, or commercial developments, or market conditions, shall in the opinion of the bankers, whose conclusions in this respect shall be final, render inadvisable the issue to the public of the bonds, or of a portion thereof, then the bankers shall be at liberty, at their option, to give the Caja notice of their determination not to proceed with the purchase of the bonds, or of a portion thereof, and thereupon the obligations of the bankers under article 10 hereof with respect to the purchase of the bonds, or such thereof as they shall have decided not to purchase, shall forthwith terminate, but all the other obligations of either party to the other under this agreement shall continue in force.

16. The Caja hereby covenants and agrees that it will not issue or sell any securities of the Caja in the United States of America, or issue or sell any securities intended to be sold or offered for sale in the United States of America prior to May 1, 1931, without first giving the bankers a 30-day option to purchase such securities on terms and conditions at least as favorable to the bankers as the Caja is able to obtain from other sources at the time when such issue or sale is proposed. If the bankers shall not exercise such option within the 30-day period, the Caja shall have the right to offer such securities elsewhere on terms and conditions not less favorable to the Caja than those offered to the bankers. The Caja will not reoffer such securities, or accept offers therefor, on terms and conditions less favorable to the Caja without giving the bankers a 30-day option to purchase such securities on such less favorable terms and conditions. The Caja, however, reserves the right to negotiate through an agent who will be instructed to work in accordance with these conditions.

17. The Caja will at the request of the bankers make, or cause to be made, application for the listing of the bonds and interim certificates on the New York Stock Exchange, or the bankers may themselves make such application for and on account of the Caja. The Caja will furnish to the bankers all documents deemed by the bankers to be advantageous for the making of such application, and it will take and undertake all such action as may be requisite in accordance with the requirements of said exchange in order to secure such listing. The cost and expenses of such application, whether made by the bankers or by the Caja, shall be paid by the Caja.

18. Reference in this agreement to the fiscal agents or either of them shall be deemed to include any successor firm or corporation however constituted continuing the business of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and/or Guaranty Trust Co. of New York. Reference in this agreement to the registrar shall be deemed to include any successor corporation continuing the business of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York. Reference in this agreement to the bankers, or either of them, shall be deemed to include any successor firm or corporation however constituted continuing the business of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and/or Guaranty Co. of New York.

In witness whereof Caja de Credito Hipotecario has caused this agreement to be signed in its behalf by His Excellency, Carlos G. Davila, thereunto duly authorized and Kuhn, Loeb & Co. have signed this agreement and Guaranty Co. of New York has caused this agreement to be signed by its president or one of its vice presidents and its corporate seal to be affixed hereto and attested by its assistant secretary as of the day and year first above written.

CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO,
By CARLOS G. DAVILA,
KUHNS, LOEB & CO.
GUARANTY CO. OF NEW YORK,
By B. ATTERBURY, *Vice President.*

[SEAL]

Attest:

W. FALION, *Assistant Secretary.*

The undersigned accept their appointment as fiscal agents under the foregoing agreement upon the terms and conditions thereof; and the undersigned Guaranty Trust Co. of New York also accepts its appointment as registrar thereunder upon the terms and conditions thereof.

KUHN, LOEB & Co.
GUARANTY TRUST CO. OF NEW YORK,
By BURNETT WALKER, *Vice President*.

SCHEDULE A

[Form of definitive bond]

CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO (CHILE) (MORTGAGE BANK OF CHILE) GUARANTEED SINKING FUND 6-PERCENT GOLD BOND OF 1929, DUE MAY 1, 1962

Letra de Credito al Portador por U. S.—\$ oro (dollars americanos) que ganan el 6% de interes annual.—Reembolsable por sorteos semestrales a mas tardar en 33 anos.—Los intereses y amortizaciones se pagan el 1 de Mayo y 1 de Noviembre, en cambio del cupon respectivo o de la letra amortizada.—

Caja de Credito Hipotecario (herein called the "Caja"), for value received, promises to pay to the bearer on May 1, 1962, the sum of \$———, and to pay interest thereon from May 1, 1929, until the principal of this bond is paid, at the rate of 6 percent per annum, semiannually, on May 1 and November 1 in each year, upon presentation and surrender of the coupons hereto annexed as they severally mature.

The principal of, and interest on, this bond are payable at the option of the holder, in the Borough of Manhattan, city and Sate of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co., of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of or equal to the standard of weight and fineness existing May 1, 1929, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, and will be paid without deduction for any taxes, imposts, levies, or duties of any nature now or at any time hereafter imposed by the Republic of Chile or by any state, province, municipality, or other taxing authority thereof or therein, and will be paid in time of war as well as in time of peace and whether the holder be a citizen or resident of a friendly or a hostile state.

This bond is one of an issue of bonds known as the guaranteed sinking fund 6 percent gold bonds of 1929 of the Caja (herein called the bonds) limited to \$20,000,000 principal amount, issued in accordance with the law of the Republic of Chile, dated August 29, 1855, decree law no. 743, dated December 15, 1925, law no. 4074, dated July 27, 1926, law no. 4327, dated March 26, 1928, and the decree of the President of the Republic of Chile, no. 2694, dated June 25, 1929, constituting the loan designated "Emprestito oro Caja Hipotecario, 1929," of which \$10,000,000, principal amount, are to provide for agricultural loans in accordance with said laws no. 4074 and no. 4327 and \$10,000,000, principal amount, are to provide for the redemption of bonds of the Caja.

Until all the bonds shall have been retired or redeemed the Caja will pay to the fiscal agents as an annuity for the service of interest and amortization of the bonds the sum of \$1,400,000 per annum in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid, except as hereinafter provided. Such sums shall be paid in equal semiannual installments before the 1st day of May and the 1st day of November in each year, the first payment to be made before November 1, 1929, and the last payment to be made before May 1, 1962. The fiscal agents shall apply each such installment to the payment of the interest maturing on the next succeeding interest date on the bonds then outstanding and shall apply the part of each such installment not required for the payment of such interest as a sinking fund for the redemption of bonds on such interest date as hereinafter provided. The Caja may, at its option, increase the amount of any semiannual installment to be applied to the redemption of bonds on any semiannual interest date, and, in the event of any such increase, all subsequent semiannual installments may be reduced to an amount sufficient to provide for the semiannual service of interest and amortization of the bonds which shall be outstanding after the application of such increased sinking fund installment to the redemption of bonds, such amount to be calculated as a cumulative sinking fund compounded semiannually at the rate of 6 percent per annum to redeem, on or before May 1, 1962, all of the bonds so outstanding. Any such reduced semiannual installment may similarly be increased in which event subsequent semiannual installments may be similarly reduced.

The part of each semiannual installment available for the redemption of bonds shall be applied to the redemption of bonds by lot at 100 percent of their principal amount on the interest date next succeeding the date of such payment. The numbers of the bonds to be redeemed on each such interest date shall be drawn by lot in any usual manner. The drawing shall be held in public at the principal office of the Caja in the city of Santiago. The numbers of the bonds so drawn for redemption shall be advertised at least twice in two daily newspapers of general circulation in the borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, the first advertisement to appear not less than 30 days prior to the redemption date. The bonds so called for redemption shall on the redemption date designated in such notice become due and payable at 100 percent of their principal amount, and shall be payable, at the option of the holders, in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co., or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, and shall be paid by the Caja on and after the redemption date at the redemption price aforesaid on presentation and surrender of such bonds at any of said offices, together with all coupons thereto appertaining maturing after the redemption date.

If any bond so presented shall not be accompanied by all coupons maturing after the redemption date, then said bond shall be paid at the redemption price aforesaid less the aggregate principal amount of all coupons maturing after the redemption date not presented and surrendered with said bond; provided, that if more than four such coupons are not presented and surrendered with said bond and fiscal agents or the Caja may refuse to pay said bond. Notice having been so given by publication, the bonds so called for redemption shall cease to bear interest from the redemption date unless they shall not be so paid by the Caja upon presentation and surrender thereof with all coupons maturing after the redemption date.

This bond and the coupons appertaining thereto shall pass by delivery.

This bond shall not become valid or obligatory for any purpose until it shall be authenticated by the certificate of the registrar hereon endorsed.

In witness whereof, Caja de Credito Hipotecario has caused this bond to be executed in its name bearing the facsimile signature of the director and to be manually signed by its cashier thereunto duly authorized and to be impressed with its seal and the interest coupons bearing the facsimile signature of the director to be hereto annexed.

Dated May 1, 1929.

CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO,
By _____, *Cashier*.
LUIS BARROS PORGENE, *Director*.

[Form of registrar's certificate]

This is one of the within described guaranteed sinking fund 6 percent gold bonds of 1929 of Caja de Credito Hipotecario (Chile).

GUARANTY TRUST CO. OF NEW YORK, *Registrar*,
By _____

[Form of coupon]

§ _____ No. _____
On _____ 19____, unless the bond hereinafter mentioned shall have been called for previous redemption, Caja de Credito Hipotecario (Chile) promises to pay to bearer, at his option, in the borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co., or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of or equal to the standard of weight and fineness existing May 1, 1929, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, _____ dollars (\$_____) without deduction for any taxes, imposts, levies, or duties of any nature now or at any time hereafter imposed by the Republic of Chile or by any State, Province, municipality, or other taxing authority thereof or therein, in time of war as well as in time of peace, and whether the holder be a citizen or resident of a friendly or a hostile State, being 6 months' interest then due on its guaranteed sinking fund 6 percent gold bond of 1929, dated May 1, 1929, No. _____.

CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO,
By LUIS BARROS BORGONO, *Director*.

SCHEDULE B

(Form of guaranty)

The Republic of Chile, for a valuable consideration, hereby unconditionally guarantees to the holder of the within bond prompt payment of the principal amount of said bond in accordance with its terms, when the same shall become due and payable, whether at the maturity thereof or otherwise, and of the interest thereon at the rate and at the times specified in said bond and in the appurtenant coupons, upon presentation and surrender of said coupons as they severally mature, and also prompt payment to the fiscal agents of the semi-annual payments mentioned in said bond for the service of interest and amortization of the bonds, when the same shall become due and payable.

Dated May 1, 1929.

REPUBLIC OF CHILE,
By _____.

SCHEDULE C

[Form of temporary bond]

\$ _____

No. _____

CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO (CHILE) (MORTGAGE BANK OF CHILE) GUARANTEED
SINKING FUND 6-PERCENT GOLD BOND OF 1929, DUE MAY 1, 1962

Caja de Credito Hipotecario (herein called the "Caja") for value received, promises to pay to the bearer on May 1, 1962, the sum of \$20,000,000 and to pay interest thereon from May 1, 1929, until the principal of this bond is paid, at the rate of 6 percent per annum, semiannually, on May 1 and November 1 in each year.

The principal of, and interest on, this bond are payable at the option of the holder, in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of or equal to the standard of weight and fineness existing May 1, 1929, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sightdraft on New York City, and will be paid without deduction for any taxes, imposts, levies, or duties of any nature now or at any time hereafter imposed by the Republic of Chile or by any State, Province, municipality, or other taxing authority thereof or therein, and will be paid in time of war as well as in time of peace and whether the holder be a citizen or resident of a friendly or a hostile State.

This bond is a temporary bond without coupons and is one of an issue of bonds known as the "guaranteed sinking-fund 6-percent gold bonds of 1929 of the Caja" (herein called the "bonds") limited to \$20,000,000 principal amount, issued in accordance with the law of the Republic of Chile dated August 29, 1855; Decree Law No. 743, dated December 15, 1925; law no. 4074, dated July 27, 1926; law no. 4327, dated March 26, 1928; and the decree of the President of the Republic of Chile, no. 2694, dated June 25, 1929, constituting the loan designated "Emprestito oro Caja Hipotecaria, 1929", of which \$10,000,000, principal amount, are to provide for agricultural loans in accordance with said laws no. 4074 and no. 4327 and \$10,000,000, principal amount, are to provide for the redemption of bonds of the Caja.

Until all the bonds shall have been retired or redeemed the Caja will pay to the fiscal agents as an annuity for the service of interest and amortization of the bonds the sum of \$1,400,000 per annum in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid, except as hereinafter provided. Such sums shall be paid in equal semiannual installments before the 1st day of May and the 1st day of November in each year, the first payment to be made before November 1, 1929, and the last payment to be made before May 1, 1962.

The fiscal agents shall apply each such installment to the payment of the interest maturing on the next succeeding interest date on the bonds then outstanding, and shall apply the part of each such installment not required for the payment of such interest as a sinking fund for the redemption of bonds on such interest date as hereinafter provided. The Caja may, at its option, increase the amount of any semiannual installment to be applied to the redemption of bonds on any semiannual interest date and, in the event of any such increase, all subsequent semiannual installments may be reduced to an amount

sufficient to provide for the semiannual service of interest and amortization of the bonds which shall be outstanding after the application of such increased sinking-fund installment to the redemption of bonds, such amount to be calculated as a cumulative sinking fund compounded semiannually at the rate of 6 percent per annum to redeem, or or before May 1, 1962, all of the bonds so outstanding. Any such reduced semiannual installment may similarly be increased in which event subsequent semiannual installments may be similarly reduced. The part of each semiannual installment available for the redemption of bonds shall be applied to the redemption of bonds by lot at 100 percent of their principal amount on the interest date next succeeding the date of such payment. The numbers of the bonds to be redeemed on each such interest date shall be drawn by lot in any usual manner. The drawings shall be held in public at the principal office of the Caja in the city of Santiago. The numbers of the bonds so drawn for redemption shall be advertised at least twice in two daily newspapers of general circulation in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, the first advertisement to appear not less than 30 days prior to the redemption date.

The bonds so called for redemption shall on the redemption date designated in such notice become due and payable at 100 percent of their principal amount, and shall be payable, at the option of the holders, in the Borough of Manhattan, city and State of New York, at the office of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or at the principal office of Guaranty Trust Co. of New York, in gold coin of the United States of America of the standard aforesaid, or in the city of Santiago, Chile, at the office of the Caja, by sight draft on New York City, and shall be paid by the Caja on and after the redemption date at the redemption price aforesaid on presentation and surrender of such bonds at any of said offices, together with all coupons thereto appertaining maturing after the redemption date. If any bond so presented shall not be accompanied by all coupons maturing after the redemption date, then said bond shall be paid at the redemption price aforesaid less the aggregate principal amount of all coupons maturing after the redemption date not presented and surrendered with said bond; provided, that if more than four such coupons are not presented and surrendered with said bond the fiscal agents or the Caja may refuse to pay said bond. Notice having been given by publication the bonds so called for redemption shall cease to bear interest from the redemption date unless they shall not be so paid by the Caja upon presentation and surrender thereof with all coupons maturing after the redemption date.

This temporary bond is exchangeable for definitive engraved bonds of this issue of like tenor and for a like aggregate principal amount when engraved and prepared, endorsed with the guaranty of the Republic of Chile, corresponding so far as appropriate with the guaranty hereon endorsed.

This bond shall pass by delivery.

In witness whereof, Caja de Credito Hipotecario has caused this bond to be executed in its name bearing the signature of the director and of its cashier thereunto duly authorized and to be impressed with its seal.

Dated, May 1, 1929.

CAJA DE CREDITO HIPOTECARIO,
 _____, *Director*.
 By _____, *Cashier*.

SCHEDULE D

[Form of guaranty for temporary bond]

The Republic of Chile, for a valuable consideration, hereby unconditionally guarantees to the holder of the within bond prompt payment of the principal amount of said bond in accordance with its terms, when the same shall become due and payable, whether at the maturity thereof or otherwise, and of the interest thereon at the rate and at the times specified in said bond, and also prompt payment to the fiscal agents of the semiannual payments mentioned in said bond for the service of interest and amortization of the bonds, when the same shall become due and payable, and the Republic of Chile hereby agrees to endorse on the several definitive engraved bonds to be delivered in exchange for the within temporary bond its guaranty substantially as aforesaid with appropriate variations.

CATE, May 1, 1929.

REPUBLIC OF CHILE,
 By _____.

STOCK EXCHANGE PRACTICES

THURSDAY, JUNE 29, 1933

UNITED STATES SENATE,
SUBCOMMITTEE OF THE COMMITTEE
ON BANKING AND CURRENCY,
Washington, D.C.

The subcommittee met, pursuant to adjournment on yesterday, at 10 a.m., in the caucus room of the Senate Office Building, Senator Duncan U. Fletcher presiding.

Present: Senators Fletcher (chairman), Adams, Goldsborough, and Townsend.

Present also: Ferdinand Pecora, counsel to the committee, Julius Silver and David Saperstein, associate counsel to the committee, and Frank J. Meehan, chief statistician to the committee; Carl A. de Gersdorff, Robert T. Swaine, and M. T. Moore, counsel for Kuhn, Loeb & Co.

The CHAIRMAN. The subcommittee will come to order. Mr. Kahn, will you resume the stand, please?

TESTIMONY OF OTTO H. KAHN, A PARTNER OF KUHN, LOEB & CO.—Resumed

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, have you since the termination of the session yesterday been able to refresh your recollection with regard to the stock transactions that I questioned you about yesterday afternoon?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. What is now your recollection as to whether or not on December 30, 1930, you sold 1,000 shares of Electric Power & Light Corporation, 1,000 shares of International Nickel Co. stock, 500 shares of Manhattan-Dearborn Co., 250 shares of Reynolds Metal Co., and 600 shares of Tubize Chatillon Co. at an indicated loss of \$117,584?

Mr. KAHN. I made such sales.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recall the circumstances under which the sales of those securities were made?

Mr. KAHN. Perhaps I may be allowed to read a little statement which is based upon what my counsel told me, to whom I telephoned yesterday evening asking him to ascertain the facts before coming here, so that I would be able to tell you the precise situation as it was.

Mr. PECORA. Is it a statement prepared by your counsel or by you?

Mr. KAHN. Partly by him, but mainly upon facts within my knowledge, gone over by him.

Mr. PECORA. Have you a copy of the statement with you, in addition to one that you have there?

Mr. KAHN. No, sir. It is not really a formal statement. It is just a memorandum to help me in being sure that my facts are recorded straight.

Mr. PECORA. All right.

Mr. KAHN. I am informed this morning that the following are the facts with regard to the securities mentioned yesterday as having been sold by me in December 1930, to my daughter Maude. Counsel reports to me that in December 1930 these securities were sold by myself for cash at the regular market prices on that day, and the amount received thereafter duly credited to me. The securities sold include those which you have mentioned, Mr. Pecora. In March 1931 my daughter arrived in this country, and about that time I discussed her affairs with counsel acquainted with English law, who called in English solicitors in order to devise and carry out a plan by which trusts should be set up for her. It was part of that plan that she should turn over to me all of her securities and also cancel the trust which had been set up for her many years ago. Pursuant to this plan she made an assignment to me of a large number of her securities. This assignment was executed on March 30, 1931. It was executed at my house in the presence of counsel. The assignment was dated December 31, 1930. It was executed March 30, 1931. It was dated December 31, 1930, because counsel with whom I had consulted as to my daughter's affairs suggested that the cancelation of the old trust and the inception of the new trust take effect as of the close of the preceding calendar year, namely, December 31, 1930.

Subsequently and after the execution of the assignment on March 31, 1931, the securities were duly transferred from my daughter to me and duly recorded in the regular way on her books and mine. The securities which I sold in December, and which you mentioned, Mr. Pecora, resulted in a loss of about \$117,000. Some time later, namely, about April 1932, the field agent for the Government raised the point that the securities which I had sold in December had been reacquired within 30 days after the sale, and that, therefore, no loss could be allowed on their sale. I was in Europe at the time that this happened, and a protest was filed on my behalf by my attorneys in fact, through Messrs. Stroock & Stroock, in which the contention was that the securities were actually not reacquired until March 30, 1931, which was about 3 months after the date they had been sold. A hearing was held, at which my attorneys were present, and subsequently my original contention was confirmed and the agent's contention was disallowed, both by the revenue agent in charge in New York and by the Deputy Commissioner of Internal Revenue at Washington, to whom the matter had been referred.

My counsel arrived this morning and has brought with him the original assignment, a copy of the protest filed with the report of the revenue agent in New York sustaining my contention, and the original letter from the Deputy Commissioner of Internal Revenue also sustaining it. I understand that at the hearing the question was gone into very carefully as to when these securities were reacquired by me, and that proof was submitted that they were not reacquired until March 30, 1931, such proof being based upon the assignment

and the evidence of Mr. Levine who was present when it was executed.

Mr. PECORA. Will you be good enough to let me have the statement that you have just read into the record?

Mr. KAHN. This was just jotted down in a rough way.

Mr. PECORA. That is the one that has gone into the record. I simply want to use it in my examination.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. Let him have it.

Mr. KAHN. There are two or three things that I did not read and which perhaps should not be, for that reason, referred to.

The CHAIRMAN. Was there any bulletin issued by the collector of internal revenue or the deputy collector?

Mr. KAHN. So I understand. I believe it was referred to in this statement. No; I am told it was not.

The CHAIRMAN. They print a bulletin of their decisions. I did not know but what this case was one of that kind.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. The Board of Tax Appeals never got as far as that. It was decided by the conferees. We got a letter.

Mr. PECORA. The typewritten statement which you have just read into the record begins with the following sentence:

I was informed by counsel, who has just arrived this morning from New York, that the following are the facts with regard to the securities mentioned yesterday as having been sold by me in December 1930 to my daughter Maude.

The securities referred to, Mr. Kahn, were sold to your daughter in December 1930 by you?

Mr. KAHN. So I am informed.

Mr. PECORA. Did you cause the sale to be made?

Mr. KAHN. It is exceedingly difficult after 3 years to determine whether I caused the sale to be made or whether one of the two or three other men that were concerned in the running of my accounts. It is within my own recollection, because that was a universal rule, that my daughter Maude was informed of it, that revenue stamps were attached, that the market price was observed, that the necessary money was transferred from her to me. That I can say of my knowledge is the general rule. I cannot say with any precision as appertaining to this particular transaction, but it would be more than surprising if it did not so apply.

Mr. PECORA. Were the sales made at one time; that is, the sales of these five blocks?

Mr. KAHN. I am afraid I could not tell you, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. From the fact that they were made on the same date, namely, December 30, 1930, would you say that the sales were made of these five blocks of securities at the one time?

Mr. KAHN. That would seem plausible and natural.

Mr. PECORA. Were they made through a broker?

Mr. KAHN. Again I am afraid I could not say with any definiteness. They would either be made through a broker or would be made through my office. The resulting cash value would be settled through the accounts of my daughter and myself, respectively, in my office.

Mr. PECORA. Were those securities listed on any public exchange at the time of the sale?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Were they sold through the exchange?

Mr. KAHN. May I correct myself? I do not know whether the Manhattan-Dearborn was or not. I believe the others were, to the best of my recollection, either on the stock exchange or on the curb exchange.

Mr. PECORA. Were the sales of those blocks, which were listed on the public exchange, made to your daughter through the exchange?

Mr. KAHN. Not necessarily.

Mr. PECORA. What is your recollection of the fact?

Mr. KAHN. My recollection of the fact is, I am afraid, nil; but I am told—I mean I could not possibly recollect amongst so many hundreds of transactions which went through my books, whether in each instance a particular transaction went through the stock exchange, the curb market, the Chicago market, or in what other way; but I am told that these particular transactions did not go through the exchange but were settled at the prevailing prices in my office.

Mr. PECORA. That is, they were made directly by you to your daughter, and not through any exchange?

Mr. KAHN. So I understand.

Mr. PECORA. I want to ask you whether the purchase price was paid by your daughter directly to you.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. In what form was the payment made?

Mr. KAHN. The payment was made in cash, or what was the equivalent of cash, debiting her account and crediting my account.

Mr. PECORA. That is, by the transference of credits?

Mr. KAHN. Yes. I suppose that is the correct term. To me it was cash.

Mr. PECORA. There was no actual cash passed or any token payment, such as a check?

Mr. KAHN. There was presumably—I cannot be positive, but presumably no check passed. I never make payments with checks except for small items.

Mr. PECORA. You would not be called upon to make the payment in this case; your daughter would be?

Mr. KAHN. The same thing would hold true of my daughter.

Mr. PECORA. Had you, prior to the date of the making of the sales of these five blocks of securities, discussed the matter with your daughter?

Mr. KAHN. The matter was discussed with my daughter; yes. Whether it was discussed on that particular day, I could not swear to. The fact was that I had power of attorney for my daughter; my wife had power of attorney for my daughter; and an intimate friend of mine, Mr. Stein, had power of attorney for my daughter. I could not, 3 years after the event, tell you precisely when and by whom the matter was discussed with my daughter. I can tell you it was fully approved by my daughter.

Mr. PECORA. I thought perhaps, in view of the fact that this transaction was reviewed by the Internal Revenue Department in April of last year, your recollection of the transaction might have been considerably refreshed because of such review.

Mr. KAHN. I am afraid you are giving me credit for a more vivid recollection than I possess for matters which, as I tried to say yesterday, I do not necessarily have to remember. There are so many other things that I have to remember.

Mr. PECORA. In this particular instance, on the occasion of the review of this transaction by the officials of the Internal Revenue Department, you filed or caused to be filed a protest against the ruling or determination of the field agent who sought to assess a tax upon you?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, Mr. Pecora. I have a number of volunteer advisers here, but I can tell you without the advisers that I was in Europe at the time.

Mr. PECORA. At what time?

Mr. KAHN. In June, I believe it was, of 1932, when this protest was filed. It was never signed by me; it was signed by my attorneys in fact.

Mr. PECORA. In the typewritten statement which you read into the record, and which I have before me, you say as follows:

The securities which I sold in December resulted in a loss of about \$117,000. Some time later, namely, about April 1931—

Mr. KAHN. 1932 it should be.

Mr. PECORA (continuing reading):

The field agent for the Government raised the point—

You say that should have been 1932?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; that should be 1932.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recollect whether or not at any time prior to the making of the sale of these five blocks of securities to your daughter, you personally had any discussion relating to the proposed sale with your daughter?

Mr. KAHN. I could not say, after 3 years, Mr. Pecora. I beg your pardon for emphasizing the 3 years, but I could not say whether I personally discussed it with her prior to the sale. I am quite certain that I did discuss this and many other matters with her in the course of events when she came here, after the sale, and I am quite certain that she approved every sale. She was apprised of it either before or after.

Mr. PECORA. Was the purchase price at which these sales were made consistent with the market quotations at the time?

Mr. KAHN. To my own knowledge, I cannot say, but I am quite certain that that was so. I am informed by my mentors that that was the case.

The CHAIRMAN. Were you in New York in December 1930?

Mr. KAHN. Presumably I was. I could not say positively. I may have been in your own delightful country—I may have been in Florida, where I usually do go in the winter. But we can easily look it up. But either in December 1930 or shortly after that I was in Florida.

The CHAIRMAN. Was your daughter in New York then?

Mr. KAHN. My daughter came, I believe, a couple of months afterwards to join me in Florida.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recall whether or not at the time you made this sale to your daughter there was a falling market for these securities?

Mr. KAHN. That is trying to tax me for the recollection of things which I would much rather forget.

Mr. PECORA. I was trying to find out in asking you that question, Mr. Kahn, what might have motivated you in making the sale; in

other words, whether or not you thought at the time you made the sale that the value of these securities would continue to decline in the market, and in order not to sustain any further loss you decided to make a sale of them. Was there any such element that motivated you?

Mr. KAHN. That would be a very mean element, and I hope I was not guilty of it.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recall what prompted you to make the sale to your daughter at that time?

Mr. KAHN. I do not recall, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. Had you on other occasions, either prior or since, made sales of securities owned by you to your daughter or any other member of your family at about the end of the tax year?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, Mr. Pecora; either I myself or one of those acting on a power of attorney or as recognized agents.

Mr. PECORA. Did you do that every year for a period of years?

Mr. KAHN. Again I am not certain how frequently the occurrence was.

Mr. PECORA. And did you on each of those other occasions when you made sales of securities either to your daughter or some other member of your family at the end of the tax year reacquire by any means whatsoever the securities or like securities?

Mr. KAHN. To the best of my knowledge, never within 30 days, and very rarely at all. But I have got to say again, to the best of my knowledge, because, strange though it may sound to you, I tried as much as I could to avoid making personal decisions if I could put them on somebody else's shoulders.

Mr. PECORA. Did you have anyone else make decisions for you with regard to your purchase and sale of securities, or did you make those upon your own judgment, impulse?

Mr. KAHN. I used yesterday the term "confused", which was a very bad term to use. What I want to say is that I had power of attorney for my children, my wife. She had. My friend, in whom I had implicit confidence, Mr. Steinam, had. Another man who was in my office and who was statistician of recognized standing and adviser on value, Mr. Gourrich, had. I could not possibly pick out on what particular instance I made the decision or one of those three made the decision. My secretary sometimes had.

Mr. PECORA. Was it customary for persons other than yourself to sell or buy securities for your account without previously consulting you?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir; quite customary.

Mr. PECORA. And persons who did that on occasion bore what relationship to you?

Mr. KAHN (after conferring with an associate). I beg your pardon?

Mr. PECORA. What relation did the persons who did that for you on occasion bear to you?

Mr. KAHN. They would be friends of mine in whom I had particular confidence. They would be representatives of mine if I was here, and partly for reasons of health and for other reasons, I was unfortunately absent quite a considerable part of the year in the last 5 or 6 years. But if I was here presumably they would come to me and say they thought it was a good thing for me to buy that.

Senator TOWNSEND. Mr. Kahn, would they be acting through power of attorney from you?

Mr. KAHN. They would be acting through power of attorney from me, or they would be acting as my recognized agents, having been established as such by usage, by tradition, and by recognition both on my part and the part of others.

Mr. PECORA. What persons had authority, either by power of attorney or otherwise, to make sales or purchases of securities for you in December 1930?

Mr. KAHN. My wife through power of attorney; my wife, Mr. Steinam, possibly others, because I was at the point of going away or had just gone away, and I would leave powers of attorney for my absence with my secretary, with Mr. Gourrich. I was pretty free in giving powers of attorney.

Mr. PECORA. Well, were these powers of attorney given by you for the purpose of enabling your attorneys in fact or your representatives to physically consummate such transactions, or were they also intended to enable them and authorize them to make decisions for you without previous consultation with you with respect to the buying and selling of securities for your account?

Mr. KAHN (after conferring with Mr. Moore). When I was here——

Mr. PECORA (interposing). Is the gentleman who is whispering to you one of your counsel?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. I have no objection to his advising you before you answer any question, but I think the record ought to show that any answer you make is made after having been advised in some fashion or other by someone connected with you. Will the gentleman kindly put his name on the record here?

Mr. MOORE. It is on the record.

Mr. PECORA. What is that?

Mr. MOORE. It is on the record; and I was not advising anyone.

Mr. PECORA. What is that?

Mr. MOORE. I say it is on the record. I was not advising him, but I will gladly——

Mr. PECORA (interposing). If you do not advise him, I think it might be better for you not to interrupt the witness. It might disconcert him.

The CHAIRMAN. What is the name?

Mr. KAHN. Mr. Moore.

Your question was, if I understand it rightly, whether the people having such power of attorney would act for me when I was in New York.

Mr. PECORA. No; the question was a little bit broader than that. The question was whether or not in giving these powers of attorney to these agents you did so for the purpose merely of legally qualifying them to consummate a transaction for you or did you do it also with a view of having them make decisions without previous consultation with you on the matter of buying or selling securities for your individual account?

Mr. KAHN. I did it for the purpose of my convenience, for the purpose of relieving my mind of a mass of matters, and whilst I

was in New York, presumably and to the best of my recollection, they would come to me either before or immediately after, but they were quite at liberty to do so. But the custom, as I recall it, and the natural custom, would be that when I was in New York I would be advised.

Mr. PECORA. Well, do you want the committee to understand that in order to relieve you of a mass of detail or labor involved in making decisions as to when you should buy or sell securities without previous consultation with you, you empowered your wife to do that?

Mr. KAHN. Oh, decidedly; yes.

Mr. PECORA. To transfer that burden to her, or the responsibility, call it that if you will?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; undoubtedly.

Mr. PECORA. You do not want the committee to understand that you considered your wife just as well qualified to make such decisions in your behalf as you yourself were?

Mr. KAHN. I do not. And I do not believe she would make such decisions except under competent advice, or under what she believed to be competent advice.

Mr. PECORA. What is your recollection now as to whether or not the sale of these five blocks of securities to your daughter on December 30, 1930, were made by you directly or by some one acting under a power of attorney for you?

Mr. KAHN. My recollection now is nil.

Mr. PECORA. That is, you do not know one way or the other what the fact might have been?

Mr. KAHN. I do not. I do not even know whether at that particular date I was in New York or I was in Florida.

Mr. PECORA. Would it not be relatively easy for you to ascertain the fact as to whether or not at the time of the making of this sale you were actually in New York?

Mr. KAHN. Oh, yes; quite easy.

Mr. PECORA. Will you undertake to do that?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Before the hearing is over?

Mr. KAHN. Gladly.

Mr. PECORA. Now, do you recall whether or not your daughter, to whom these blocks of securities were sold, was in New York or was even in this country on December 30, 1930?

Mr. KAHN. Again, I do not recall precisely, Mr. Pecora. My impression is that she came somewhat later.

Mr. PECORA. How long after did she come here?

Mr. KAHN. I am guessing. And I dislike to guess under oath.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recall if she came here later where she was on December 30, 1930—that is, in what country, continent?

Mr. KAHN. In France or in England presumably. She may have been in Italy. I could not possibly know without ascertaining.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know whether or not she was consulted prior to the making of the sale to her for the purpose of ascertaining whether or not she wanted to buy these securities?

Mr. KAHN. As I tried to explain, Mr. Pecora, she had several people here who had the power of attorney for her.

Mr. PECORA. Were any of those persons the same persons to whom you had given power of attorney?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Were they in all instances the same person?

Mr. KAHN. In all instances the same person?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. KAHN. I should think so.

Mr. PECORA. And who were those persons? Give us their names, if you have not already given the names of all of them. You have already mentioned your wife.

Mr. KAHN. I have mentioned my wife.

Mr. PECORA. And Mr. Steinam—is it?

Mr. KAHN. Mr. Steinam, yes.

Mr. PECORA. Were there any other attorneys in fact for yourself and your daughter at that time?

Mr. KAHN. Attorneys in fact but without having specific power of attorney in all cases, there would be a Mr. Gourrich.

Mr. PECORA. What relationship did he bear to you?

Mr. KAHN. He was the chief statistician in my office and advisor on the intrinsic value of securities. I do not now recall whether he had a specific power of attorney or whether he acted by what I might call tacit recognition, by usage and by habit.

Mr. PECORA. Was there any special reason for making this particular sale on the 30th of December or just as the tax year was about to expire?

Mr. KAHN. I could not recall, Mr. Pecora, what the specific reason was, if any.

Mr. PECORA. Isn't it a fact that usually for a period of years during the last week of December of each year in that period you made substantial sales of many blocks of securities?

Mr. KAHN. I believe that is so.

Mr. PECORA. That was sort of an annual custom of yours, wasn't it?

Mr. KAHN. I believe it was.

Mr. PECORA. Was there any reason why you picked out that particular time in each year for the making of sales of substantial blocks of securities?

Mr. KAHN. I suppose the reason was, Mr. Pecora, to determine how much I owed the Government.

Mr. PECORA. Just what do you mean by that?

Mr. KAHN. To determine what was my loss as compared to my income.

Mr. PECORA. Well, do you mean by that that they were made in order to enable you to take what is known as a tax loss?

Mr. KAHN. Tax loss is an ugly term and is an ugly connotation. I suppose it will be abolished forever after you finish with it here.

Mr. PECORA. I hope so.

Mr. KAHN. But at that time——

Mr. I. B. LEVINE. Mr. Pecora, may I say something? It may help you. I have gone over all these records last night, and it may help if I can have a little conference with him to refresh his recollection as to all those things.

Mr. PECORA. Let us see how far his recollection may need to be refreshed, and if it does need to be refreshed, why, Mr. Kahn will

be given every opportunity to refresh his recollection. So far he is answering questions with a more or less degree of familiarity. I think the record ought to show the name of the gentleman who just addressed the committee.

Mr. MOORE. Mr. Levine, of Stroock & Stroock.

Mr. PECORA. And what are your initials, Mr. Levine?

Mr. LEVINE. I. B. Levine.

Mr. PECORA. An attorney?

Mr. LEVINE. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Connected with the firm of Stroock & Stroock, New York City?

Mr. LEVINE. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Well, you were remarking, Mr. Kahn, in answer to my last question addressed to you, that the term I used, "tax loss", had a rather ugly connotation.

Mr. KAHN. I also remarked that I hoped that it will be buried forever after you are through.

Mr. PECORA. You mean the remark or the connotation?

Mr. KAHN. Not the remark. The fact.

Mr. PECORA. You mean the custom?

Mr. KAHN. The custom. I think any law which is apt, however just in itself it may have been intended, which is apt to irritate public sentiment and cause resentment on the part of the people is a bad law and ought to be amended.

Senator STEIWER. Aside from public reaction, Mr. Kahn, don't you perceive certain objections to the capital loss and gain law?

Mr. KAHN. I do, Senator. I have long felt that it was a risky provision. I know it exists in England, and it works fairly well in England, but England has not got the tremendous ups and downs that we have in this country, and here it really means that the Government speculates on people making money or losing money. In my humble opinion, that is not the business of the Government. The Government ought to be assured of a steady revenue in good or in bad times.

Senator STEIWER. Does not the capital-gain tax prevent liquidation sometimes?

Mr. KAHN. It does.

Senator STEIWER. Keeps the investor from taking his profit, and therefore leads to inflation—is that so?

Mr. KAHN. Quite correct, Senator.

Senator STEIWER. Was it a factor in the great inflation of 1928 and 1929?

Mr. KAHN. It was, in my opinion, a very substantial factor. Over and over again I heard people tell me, come to me triumphant, and show me a slip and say, "Here, I have got such and such profits." And I said, "Well, I congratulate you." And he says, "Wait. I cannot afford to take them. I am not going to take them. I will let them run on."

And you are absolutely right that it had a great effect in causing the inflation, which was one of the reasons for the disaster of 1929.

The CHAIRMAN. They would not take the profit because of the tax?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Senator BARKLEY. On the contrary, does not the custom of selling in order to establish a loss at the end of the taxable year create an

artificial situation which may depress the value of stocks at the same time?

MR. KAHN. Exactly the same situation exists there, Senator, plus another undesirable concomitant; namely, that it encourages bear cliques who throw themselves upon the market and say "This is our chance. This is our time. Let us depress the market for a while. We will get a chance to buy back."

It seems to me that from every point of view it is for the Government a hazardous piece of business to gamble on the country's prosperity in the way of a gain-and-profit provision. It is a bad thing from the point of view of making it easier to inflate and to stop the natural flow of sales and purchases, of credit, and of currency.

It is, as you have rightly pointed out, Senator, an element which injects an artificial depression upon the market, usually at one particular month, and in my opinion all these elements are bad, and if some way can be devised by which the Government will get no less money, by which rich people will pay, as in my own opinion I believe they would pay, more money to the Government, by which this temptation to do that which the law plainly permits is definitely removed for all time and people pay what they manifestly and on the face of their income ought to pay, I think you would have rendered a very great service to the community.

THE CHAIRMAN. There has been already some modification of that.

MR. KAHN. I know, Senator, to a certain extent that has already been remedied, but I do not believe it has been completely remedied.

Senator STEIWER. You are the first witness connected with the New York banking fraternity, I believe, who has stated to this committee that the bears are able to depress the market. Do you care to elaborate that statement?

MR. KAHN. I haven't any doubt about it, Senator. Twice two makes four, and if an artificial offering of the market is created it is bound to have an effect upon the market. Now, the people who may be doing that may be acting in perfect good faith. They are doubtless acting within the law. They may be acting entirely ethically. I think it depends to a large extent upon the motives. If the bear goes about seeking whom he can devour, then I think he is a danger to the community and he ought to be restricted, and to the extent that it is possible he ought to be prevented from damaging the natural flow of prices.

I think the natural flow of prices in every way is a thing which legislation, if I may be permitted to say so, ought to encourage in whatever field of activity it may be, and anything which interferes with the natural flow of prices, whether it is artificial and conscienceless or not, exaggerated bull pools or bear pools, are in my opinion a social evil.

Senator STEIWER. Are you conscious of a difference of opinion between yourself and Mr. Richard Whitney and other officials of the New York Stock Exchange and other gentlemen who have appeared before the committee and assured us that the evils are very small with respect to this question?

MR. KAHN. Well, "very small", Senator, is a relative term. In my opinion, they are distinctly social evils, and, in my opinion, they ought to be looked into; and, in my humble opinion, whatever your

committee can do to regulate and correct the damaging effect upon the community ought to be done.

I am not prepared at this moment and without preparation to suggest any precise remedies; but whilst I do believe that buying activity and selling activity are the proper functions of the stock exchange, I do not believe that artificial activities of whatever kind are the proper functions of any exchange.

Senator STEIWER. Mr. Pecora, will you develop this later? We may have included it at the wrong place in the hearing. I do not care to pursue it.

Senator TOWNSEND. May I ask you one question: Mr. Kahn, is there a difference, in your judgment, between a "bear raid" and "short selling"?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; I think there is a difference, Senator.

Senator TOWNSEND. What would be your description of that?

Mr. KAHN. Short selling is the action of one particular individual in reaching conclusions that prices are too high, that events are likely to materialize in the remoter or nearer future upon which he is willing to back his judgment. His judgment is that he had better get out of stocks, and he had better go a little further than that, just as he would buy stocks when he thinks they are very cheap, so he would sell stocks when he thinks they are very dear or when he believes that an event is going to happen which will affect their prices. I think that is, in my opinion, a perfectly legitimate exercise of individual activity.

I think when you get "bear raids" you are doing a socially damaging thing, when you get a gang of people together and they say, "Now, we will raid the market. Now we will spread rumors. Now we will create fear. Now we will scare people out of their stocks"—I think they are doing a socially illegitimate thing.

Senator TOWNSEND. But the short seller may reach his conclusion by his intimate knowledge with corporations in which he might be a member.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Senator TOWNSEND. And then short sell. What would you think of that?

Mr. KAHN. I am afraid, Senator, you overestimate the inside knowledge of directors. I do not believe that directors do possess as a general rule that inside knowledge.

Mr. PECORA. What prevents them from having it?

Mr. KAHN. Indifference, Senator. Not only that, but you cannot run a corporation in such a way that it is taken out of the hands of the executive officials. They must necessarily run the corporation. Your board of directors is supposed to be, to a large extent, a "brain trust." They are supposed to be advisors. They are supposed to keep posted. But I do not believe that a corporation can be run by a body of 15 men. I think it has got to be run by a very small body of men.

Mr. PECORA. What is the sense of having large boards, then?

Mr. KAHN. Large boards I do not believe in. A reasonably large board, I think, is, to use the expression I used in the common parlance, a kind of a "brain trust."

Mr. PECORA. Would you say that large boards, then, are resorted to for so-called window-dressing purposes?

Mr. KAHN. Partly that and partly because there is a hope that they will bring business.

And I do not believe I had quite finished my answer to the Senator's question, or had I?

Senator TOWNSEND. I think you have. I am surprised to hear you say that you did not think the directors would have a knowledge of their own company.

Mr. KAHN. I do not say that, Senator. At least I did not mean to say it. I did not mean to imply that they did not have knowledge of their own company, but I doubt whether they would have sufficient knowledge of their own company in all cases, outside of the officers and outside of perhaps an executive committee, to draw from figures put before them, from a report put before them, a definite conclusion as to what is likely to be the future next month of that company. Are things likely to be better or things likely to be worse? It is very largely guessing. It is very largely a sixth sense. It is developed in the case of the officers, because the officers are in constant contact with their customers, and I suppose out of that they do gain some knowledge which an ordinary director would not possess, a knowledge which is very frequently wrong, as we have seen in 1929, 1930, 1931, and 1932.

But I wanted to add this thing: As I understand the law—and if it is not the law in my opinion it ought to be the law as soon as possible—but I understand the law is that no director is permitted to sell short stock of his own company. If it is not the law, it ought to be the law.

The CHAIRMAN. You have been dwelling somewhat, Mr. Kahn, on the general consequences of speculation. While on the subject I just would like to have your view as to the economic effect of speculation generally.

Mr. KAHN. I think speculation fulfills a legitimate purpose, provided it is speculation and it is not gambling. I think gambling fulfills no legitimate purpose whatsoever.

Mr. PECORA. What are the earmarks of speculation as differentiated from gambling?

Mr. KAHN. Well, speculation you must indulge in almost necessarily in every line of business in foreseeing, for instance, whether you should buy your raw material in December or in March; you must hedge against it from time to time. If you are a banker, to a certain extent you indulge in speculation every time you take the responsibility of buying a large issue of bonds. I think it is a part of business which cannot be dispensed with.

Again I would say the test is the motive. If speculation is a part of your business, a just part of your business, and not the purpose of your business, then I should say speculation is not only permitted but probably unavoidable. If your purpose is to enrich yourself through gambling then I think you are engaged in an illegitimate transaction. It may be an absolutely legal transaction, but I think from the point of view of the public welfare it is an illegitimate transaction.

It is difficult enough to meet the situation in such a way that the distribution of rewards is reasonably fairly effected. The world has not solved that problem yet. But I think we can all agree in this

way, that wealth acquired by gambling serves no good purpose, and that the man who indulges as a profession in gambling is not entitled as a part of the community to any reward.

The CHAIRMAN. Would you call trading in stocks and bonds on margin gambling or speculation?

Mr. KAHN. I would call that speculation. If people have money they must employ it.

Mr. PECORA. And when would trading in stocks and other securities on margin be gambling, as distinguished from speculation?

Mr. KAHN. When it exceeds reasonable proportions.

Mr. PECORA. Do you mean when it is successful to an inordinate degree?

Mr. KAHN. Mr. Pecora, I do not mean that. I think it is gambling when it is not in proportion to a man's available means. When the transactions he indulges in are plainly such as to endanger him if they go wrong, are plainly such as to go beyond that wise provision which he owes to his family—in other words, if they are plainly improvident and if they are plainly engaged in for the purpose of sheer gambling, then I think they are wrong.

But I see nothing wrong in a man instead of putting all his money into bonds, as against a man going to the extent of his available cash resources counted out to the last dollar—I see nothing wrong in a man saying, "Now I have got \$5,000. I see that Tom or Smith or Brown tell me that it is a good thing to buy some of this stock. I cannot afford to pay for all of it, but I can pay for a substantial part of it, sufficient not to risk my own future, not to risk the provisions for my wife, and not to risk paying my insurance premium when it comes due." I think it is a matter of motive, and I think it is a matter of moderation.

I do not believe in fact anyone would find any real difficulty in determining when a transaction is a gambling transaction and when a transaction is a reasonable market transaction.

Mr. PECORA. You say that a gambling transaction contains substantial elements of speculation?

Mr. KAHN. It does.

Mr. PECORA. And would you say that a speculation transaction contains elements of gambling?

Mr. KAHN. That is a matter of Mr. Einstein's relativity.

Mr. PECORA. That deals with time and space, so far as I understand it. I am not one of the 10 or 12 that are said to understand his theories.

Mr. KAHN. Well, time certainly enters into the element of speculation. I do not believe space does.

Senator BARKLEY. Sometimes space may cut some figure. It depends on the gyrations.

Mr. KAHN. But I think you can say that speculation is an inevitable element in almost all activities of every man who is engaged in business.

Mr. PECORA. Well, would you say that all gamblers are speculators, but not all speculators are gamblers?

Mr. KAHN. Yes. And I would be complimenting the gamblers in saying it.

Mr. PECORA. So far as I have been able to understand your distinction to the point that you have attempted to define it between

gambling and speculation, the principal element of difference between the two is one of financial ability on the part of the individual who indulges either in gambling or speculation?

Mr. KAHN. Oh, no.

Mr. PECORA. Have I misunderstood your philosophy?

Mr. KAHN. I am afraid my philosophy was badly expressed. That was merely said in response to Senator Steiwer's question as to whether a man is justified—or I believe it was Senator Fletcher's question—as to whether a man is justified in indulging in margin transactions. That was my specific answer to a specific question. I do not think that that is a test. I think the test is the motive to a very large extent—to an almost controlling extent, and the test is what good or what harm is done to the community. I can see distinct good to the community in the smaller men of the country having the opportunity in taking part in profit—sometimes they are not profitable—but in taking part in putting some of their capital into industries and benefiting from the activities of the country.

I think that is not only permitted—I think it ought to be encouraged. I think it is not right that the great mass of the people should feel that only the fellows near the stock exchange can benefit from the type of financial advantages which the prosperity of the country and the labor of the country as a whole produces. And I think that to the extent that it is possible to get the plain man, the common man, the man of small means to participate in those benefits—I cordially think he should have that opportunity, and I think it is a social advantage, and I think he is entitled to it.

I think that some of the feeling which exists in respect to the stock market activities is this very feeling that you fellows who sit next to the stock market, next to Wall Street, you get all the opportunities of benefiting from it, and we men who are a thousand or 2,000 or 3,000 miles away, we are not permitted to participate. And I think that is wrong. I think they should be permitted to participate within the limits of prudence.

Mr. PECORA. And those limits of prudence are suggested by the personal worth, the personal value of the individual, is that right?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. So that a transaction involving, we will say, investments of or risking \$5,000 by an individual whose total capital wealth might be \$5,000 would be gambling?

Mr. KAHN. It would be very unwise—

Mr. PECORA (continuing). But a similar transaction on the part of a person who might have a capital wealth of \$100,000 would not be gambling; is that right?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. The market effect is the same, is it not?

Mr. KAHN. The market effect is the same, except—I would not even say that in the one case it would be gambling and in the other case it would not be gambling. It depends upon the nature of the security involved. Now, if the man having \$100,000, as you said, puts \$5,000, which is the figure you mentioned, into the wildest kind of cats and dogs, I call it gambling, irrespective of the fact that it is only one twentieth of his capital. On the other hand, if a man, having \$5,000, actually puts, let us say, 50 or 60 percent of it in a

security which, whilst he believes in its future, whilst he would like to benefit from its capital appreciation is something that by test and trial has proved itself pretty near to being an investment, then he is not gambling.

Mr. PECORA. And when a trade is in a security that you call one of the cats and dogs you would say that was gambling?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And where it was in a stable security you would say it was not gambling?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Then you recognize, do you not, that some of the trades on the stock exchange are gambling trades?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Is that because they have cats and dogs listed there?

Mr. KAHN. No, Mr. Pecora. That enters another of the many fields into which gambling is subdivided, and into which socially undesirable practices or socially desirable practices are subdivided. That has nothing whatever to do with the nature of the security. That is an evil in itself. The raiding of the stock market, the violently marking up and down of other people's possessions is in my opinion a social evil.

Mr. PECORA. And that occurs frequently through stock exchange transactions or operations, does it not?

Mr. KAHN. Perhaps "stock exchange transactions" puts an onus where it does not quite belong. Now, the stock exchange is merely the market place. These transactions may originate many, many miles away from the stock exchange—

Mr. PECORA. That may be, but the medium through which the transaction is effected is very frequently the stock exchange?

Mr. KAHN. Yes. And the fellow who drifts into New York, into Wall Street, nowadays, and goes on a financial spree may be coming from Kalamazoo or anywhere else, and yet he would call himself a financier. He would go into the stock market. He would start to a very large extent transacting bull or bear operations, up and down, as the case may be. I do not believe that we financiers who, I hope, have some training and some experience—I do not believe we are responsible for his doings. We do provide him with a market where his transactions can be consummated.

Mr. PECORA. Do you not do more than that, Mr. Kahn? Do not the bankers frequently, and to a very considerable extent in fact, provide him with the funds with which these transactions are had?

Mr. KAHN. If you say bankers, I would say, as a rule, no. If you say commercial banks, my answer would be that, with the law as it was before the Glass bill came into effect, necessarily yes, because—

Mr. PECORA. Well, when I said "bankers", I meant not only private bankers but commercial banks.

Mr. KAHN. But again not bankers in New York only. Banks and bankers all over the country.

Mr. PECORA. I was not limiting the term "bankers" to any geographical district. I was applying it to the profession generally.

Mr. KAHN. And I include, Mr. Pecora, the Federal Reserve bank. I include every instrumentality that deals with money and with currency and with credit. And I am not sure in my own mind that the time will not come when you gentlemen will determine that

all these instrumentalities should be in one way or another under the—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). Regulation?

Mr. KAHN (continuing). Supervision—

Mr. PECORA. Regulated?

Mr. KAHN. I do not like the word "regulation."

Mr. PECORA. Supervised?

Mr. KAHN. Yes. Under the supervision of some authority which, as I said yesterday, accomplishes functions analogous to the Governor of the Bank of England. The Governor of the Bank of England cannot impose his views, but it is very unhealthy to oppose him.

The CHAIRMAN. What I was trying to get at, Mr. Kahn, was your views as to whether or not this spirit of speculation ought to be discouraged or regulated in some way, instead of being turned loose and promoted and assisted, because of its effect and its possible effect on the economic conditions of society generally.

Mr. KAHN. If you can find the means of doing that, Senator, I believe you will have accomplished an exceedingly worth-while object.

Mr. PECORA. Can you suggest any such means in the fullness of your experience, Mr. Kahn?

Mr. KAHN. These last 4 weeks, Mr. Pecora, I have been so busy with going through every transaction of my firm for the last 5 or 6 or 7 years and trying to refresh my mind on it, that I am afraid I have not quite reached the point where I would venture to put any conclusions before you. Moreover, this has happened, Mr. Pecora—

Mr. PECORA. Before you pass on from that. You do recognize, if I understand the answer you made to Senator Fletcher's question, that it would be desirable and in the public interest to have some sort of regulation or supervision or limitation—call it what you will—on the part of Government agencies to restrict the gambling in order to avoid the harmful social effects; is that correct?

Mr. KAHN. The harmful social and economic effects.

Mr. PECORA. The harmful social and economic effects. You do recognize the desirability of that in the public interest?

Mr. KAHN. I do recognize the desirability of that principle; yes.

Mr. PECORA. Well, could you not tell this committee now out of the fullness of your experience in the financial world some way, some method, some means by which that could be done?

Mr. KAHN. Possibly 3 or 4 or 5 or 6 weeks ago I might have been presumptuous enough to do that, Mr. Pecora. But this thing has happened. I beg your pardon for spreading my philosophy before you Senators, but until you stop me I will go on.

The CHAIRMAN. Proceed.

Mr. KAHN. Experience has shown that about every 30 years this country determines that it will change its economic pattern. It did so the last time under Theodore Roosevelt. It has done so now within the last few months. When this economic pattern changes, things which heretofore were orthodox become heterodox, become wiped out. For instance, in 1893, before Mr. Roosevelt's time as President, and thereafter during Mr. Roosevelt's second term, we all swore by the antitrust laws. We all wanted—

Mr. PECORA. Swore by them or at them?

Mr. KAHN. And at, too. We believed that the benefit of the country required ruthless competition, however wasteful, and the devil take the hindmost. But that there must be competition, there must be survival of the fittest. We believed in that, and our law expressed that theory for 30 years.

Now we are about to be converted to the opposite theory—rightly, in my opinion. We believed in the pioneer period in the law of the jungle. I came here in 1893, and that was just the remnant of, the last 10 years of the industrial pioneer period of the country, and the law of the jungle prevailed, and things were done at that time which would never be thought of nowadays, not even by their perpetrators. And laws were made in the full light of day, with the approval of the community—at least with a knowledge of the community—and no one changed them, and no one had any particular observations to make, except that some of our western friends began to warn us that the thing wouldn't do. And ultimately Mr. Theodore Roosevelt came along and he held up a mirror to the community, and the community did not like the picture which it saw, and very important changes were made. But that was about 30 years ago. And that has happened about every 30 years in this country.

Now, 30 years have come and gone since Mr. Theodore Roosevelt, and the "new deal" is now being made. It is of the utmost consequence economically and socially. I do not believe any man is wise enough at this moment to express any views or conclusions until these new theories and laws have been tested. May be that some of the matters which we have inherited from the past were wise after all and ought to be preserved. May be that the "new deal" is wholly right and can stand as it is. May be—and that, in my opinion, is the more likely way—we will find by test and trial what is worth preserving and what must be changed. And I know a good deal must be changed. And I know the time is ripe to have it changed. Overripe in some ways.

Now when such a 30-year period comes then we all must open-mindedly adjust ourselves to the new day. Public opinion has spoken. It has expressed itself in legislation. All of us, whether we are reactionaries or whether we are progressives, must attempt to give this new legislation a fair deal. But I do not think any of us is capable to say now "This new legislation is wrong in such and such respects", or "All of it is right in such and such respects." Some of the things of the past which are valuable ought not to have been chucked out of the window.

I think you must give a little time to us who are trying to march along with the procession, you must give us a little time to test the thing out and to ascertain after perhaps 3 months or 4 or 5 months what suggestions we whom you do the honor to consult on this occasion—what suggestions we can make, without going off half-cocked. I do not believe any of us could conscientiously answer your question now until the new laws have had a fair chance to be tested and tried and possibly corrected.

The CHAIRMAN. Would you as a kind of a starter, Mr. Kahn, favor the limiting of stock and bond issues to actual and full contribution to the capital of the enterprise? Ought there not to be by law some limitations as to the issuance of stocks and bonds by corporations so that we will know that when they are issued the

full and actual contribution to the capital of the enterprise has been made?

Mr. KAHN. By all means.

The CHAIRMAN. That has not been the case in the past.

Mr. KAHN. I know it has not been frequently the case. I fully agree with you that it ought to be the case.

Mr. PECORA. You spoke the other day, the first day that you were on the stand, of the perfect mania—I believe I am literally quoting you now—which seized people in this country in 1927 and 1928 and 1929—that is, up to October 24, 1929—on the part of everybody to buy everybody else's business.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And you think, do you not, that that mania made a very formidable contribution to the depression which followed?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. What elements went to the encouragement or the development of that perfect mania?

Mr. KAHN. What elements did not, Mr. Pecora? What elements did not?

Mr. PECORA. Well, conceivably the tides, and so forth, did not. You can think of many things that did not. We want to know what the elements were that made a primary contribution to the development of that mania.

Mr. KAHN. I fear I am trying your patience, because it will have to be a fairly complete answer.

I think the first thing which developed the mania was the megalomania. We thought we were bigger than we actually are as yet. We thought that we could swing the whole world. We thought that this ought to be the money center of the world, this ought to be the industrial center of the world, this ought to be the greatest exporting country, this ought to be necessarily an importing country, this ought to be the greatest loaning country. There was nothing which at that time we did not believe was practicable in this country.

Now, some of the things which we believed were practicable are self-contradictory. You cannot be a great exporting nation without being to a certain extent either an importing nation or a great loaning nation. We did not want to be a great importing nation; we wanted to be a great exporting nation. There was a time when we thought that we would like to be a great loaning nation, and then we did not like the fruit of that tree and we cut down that tree. We said, "We do not want to be a great loaning nation." We said, "We do not want those Europeans to get our bankers to sell us their securities and then find that we are losing our money, and find that we have built up competition besides."

Mr. PECORA. When did we get that notion?

Mr. KAHN. After things proved that that was true.

Mr. PECORA. That is, after billions of dollars of American capital had gone abroad in the past decade, or up to about 2 or 3 years ago?

Mr. KAHN. Well, billions of dollars is an enormous sum, Mr. Pecora, but many of those billions of dollars—I think a majority of them—came back with interest.

Moreover, it has nothing to do with the case, but it does give perhaps an example. If the war had lasted till the spring of 1919, as

most of us believed it would, as General Foch believed, as General Pershing believed, as most of us believed, those 6 months longer would have cost us a great deal more money, a vast deal more money than all the money which after the war we loaned to Europe and to South America, and the result would have been accumulated corpses and not a single economic advantage to this country whatsoever. At least we can say for our loans that we made abroad—and I am not by any means defending all of them, and I am not defending by any means all the methods of them—one can only plead that we were young and that we were learning, and all experience is a costly experience.

We were trying to follow the example of England, who had been in that business for generations—and who have also, I might say, lost a great deal of money. I saw statistics the other day that the Council of Foreign Bondholders in England had registered with it 125 foreign bond issues in default. I think we have registered here about 130 foreign bond issues in default.

Mr. PECORA. How many?

Mr. KAHN. One hundred and thirty, I believe. So you see the difference is not very great. And we here had thought that what was good for England would be good for us. But the economic conditions in England are altogether different, and the means by which England must make her economic living are altogether different from what we have here. However, I admit that we were not wise enough to see it. We had to learn it from experience, and I am sorry that the experience has come in part, in considerable part, out of the pockets of the American investor. It also came out of the pocket of the American banker. And I think all of us would be richer and that all of us would be a great deal happier if 1929 had never occurred, neither the beginning nor the ending, certainly not as to the ending.

But in this whole period, during which we thought everything was possible, it was stated frequently that a new era had come. University professors proclaimed a new era. Newspapers spoke of a new era. That idea spread all over the country—that here was a chance to make money, a chance not only for the rich man but for all men to make money. The statement was made all over America that with our skill, determination, and organizing capacity, such as can only be found in America, there was a new era, a new opportunity offered to all men.

Salesmen went all over America and trained the people in believing in good bonds first, in second-rate bonds afterward, and in bad bonds third, and in good stocks fourth, and in bad stocks fifth. It went all over the country that here was an opportunity the like of which the world had never seen and which would not end for years to come.

I think, Mr. Pecora, when you ask me what produced this mania, I must say to you it was a combination of elements in which we bankers, and all the brokers, and many professors, and many teachers of public opinion had a fair share and as to which it is difficult to allocate the leading share to anyone. I recall that even so conservative and careful speaking a man as President Coolidge said that for a country of the size of ours our credit structure is not unduly strained. But it was unduly strained, and—

Senator COSTIGAN (interposing). Mr. Kahn, you surprise me by your statement that the public was invited to invest in bad bonds.

Mr. KAHN. Not knowingly so, you understand.

Senator COSTIGAN. Can you give us such an illustration?

Mr. KAHN. Not knowingly so, I say, but the result has shown, hindsight has shown, that many bonds which at that time were believed to be justifiably offered to the public ought never to have been offered. It is a case of hindsight. I cannot too strongly emphasize, Senator Costigan, that at that time there was hardly a sane person in America. We were all swept away by the belief that a tremendous era, spoken of as the new era, had come upon us, and that everything was going to be good.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn—

Senator COSTIGAN (interposing). Mr. Kahn, were you at that time inviting investments in bonds which you regarded as without merit?

Mr. KAHN. Oh, no. We never did that. We have never done that, and never shall do it. As I stated on yesterday when you were not here, the only foreign bonds we have issued since the war that are in default are the bonds of the Mortgage Bank of Chile. None of our other foreign bonds issued since the war are in default. And we certainly would never have attempted to invite the public to subscribe for bonds that we did not believe to be good. And I believe that same thing is true of—

Senator COSTIGAN (interposing). What financial advisers suggested the desirability of any investments in bad bonds in preference to good stocks?

Mr. KAHN. No one in my opinion suggested investing in bad bonds; that is, with the knowledge that they were bad. But the judgment of a good many people as of that time became swayed by their hope, by their belief that things would be different in that new era from what they had ever been before.

Senator COSTIGAN. Perhaps I misunderstood the significance of your prior testimony.

Mr. KAHN. Yes. And I am sorry if I gave you such a suggestion, and am very happy that you have brought the point out so that it might be cleared up.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, in line with the questions Senator Costigan just asked you, about instances where salesmen advised the investing public to buy bad bonds, I recall the testimony given before this committee last February to the effect that the National City Co. had brought out three issues, aggregating \$90,000,000, of Peruvian bonds in the face of advice conveyed to them by their experts in Peru that the loans were bad moral, political, and economic risks. Are you familiar with that testimony?

Mr. KAHN. I did not read the testimony; no. I know that that particular loan was brought out; yes.

Mr. PECORA. Now, we probably will resume the discussion that has been engaged in during the past half hour or more, but suppose we now get back to these security sales that you made to your daughter on December 30, 1930.

Mr. KAHN. Will I be permitted, inasmuch as I now have the privilege of sitting opposite Senator Costigan, to read to him one very short line, and it won't take more than 2 minutes, which does not deal with the sales to my daughter?

Senator COSTIGAN. Certainly.

Mr. KAHN. I noticed, Senator Costigan, the other day, when Mr. Lamont was examined, you referred to the fact that the great bulk of the wealth of the country was in the hands of a trifling minority of the people. And Mr. Lamont, apparently, did not have the facts before him to answer.

Senator COSTIGAN. Attention was drawn to certain findings of the Federal Trade Commission and of the United States Industrial Relations Commission on that subject.

Mr. KAHN. Might I be permitted to read one line on this subject which I looked up after I noticed that you had made that inquiry of Mr. Lamont:

The prevailing apportionment of material award is by no means free from fault. The difficulty of the task of the wide improvement of that apportionment is one of the questions which should challenge the best thought of our statesmen. Still it may be appropriate to mention that the frequently heard assertion that the great bulk of the wealth of the Nation goes into the coffers of a small number of men is erroneous. A carefully compiled statement published last year from an authoritative source—

And the source is a book called "National Income and Its Purchasing Power", by Wilford Isobel King, published by the National Bureau of Economic Research. And Mr. King is to my knowledge a very capable man and thorough scholar.

That statement shows that according to the latest official figures then available—

And that means the latest year which he considers available in sufficient detail to enable him to base a judgment upon, was 1926—

At that time it shows that more than 87 percent of the Nation's total annual income went to those with incomes of \$5,000 or less, and that less than 13 percent went to those having incomes above \$5,000. It also shows that those possessing annual realized income—

He there uses the term "annual realized income" but I do not know what his differentiation of the term is—

of \$150,000 or more obtained altogether one sixtieth—

And that means 1.6 percent—

of the Nation's total annual realized income.

The statement shows further that if the entire income of those having more than \$5,000 a year should have it taken away from them and distributed proportionately among those having less than \$5,000 a year, the income of the latter group would be increased by such distribution to the extent of only one seventh. And Mr. King adds:

In fact, this change—

Meaning the addition of one seventh—

would be less than that which occurred from 1922 to 1926 by the general increase in the productiveness of American industry.

Senator COSTIGAN. The statement you have read is interesting but does not impress me as being in conflict with the official estimates. Have you, Mr. Kahn, by any chance the figures before you showing the number of wage earners who were earning less in 1926 than sufficed to provide a decent level of subsistence?

Mr. KAHN. I have not, but I did read it and it makes very sad reading.

Senator COSTIGAN. Have you any estimate of the aggregate of such income?

Mr. KAHN. I assume it would be very considerable. I have no such statistics, and I merely took the liberty of reading this because it seemed to be worthy of your knowledge. You probably did not have it in mind, and I happened to come across it shortly after I read your question to Mr. Lamont.

Senator COSTIGAN. I think the facts are fairly well known. Mr. King, I know, is an authority of distinction.

Mr. PECORA. Now, to get back to your stock sales to your daughter, Mr. Kahn, of December 30, 1930. At that time you owned, didn't you, other shares of the same kind of securities as were involved in those sales?

Mr. KAHN. So I observe from my income-tax return; yes.

Mr. PECORA. Was there any reason why, at the time you made these sales to your daughter, you did not sell all your holdings of those securities instead of only a part of them?

Mr. KAHN. I assume that my daughter did not have sufficient money to pay for any more than she did buy.

Mr. PECORA. Are you now assuming, also, that your daughter actually exercised her independent judgment on the question of buying the securities which you sold to her?

Mr. KAHN. She exercised, Mr. Pecora, her independent judgment as soon as the matter was brought to her knowledge, to that extent that she naturally knew I had more knowledge of securities than she did, and unless she had a particular reason to believe that my judgment in this case was unsound she would very probably feel, she would undoubtedly feel this way: Well, if my father thinks it is a good thing for him to buy, I better buy it. And she would not ordinarily put her judgment against mine. She was entirely free to do so if she wished.

Mr. PECORA. My recollection is that you have already testified that at the time of this sale your daughter was somewhere in Europe.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Have you any recollection of the proposal that she should buy these securities from you having actually been submitted to her for determination or judgment?

Mr. KAHN. I have no such recollection; but first of all, Mr. Pecora, she had men here who had her power of attorney and who were her authorized agents and who could act for her without consulting her, and consequently when she came here and when I did tell her, as you see, everything that was done, it was absolutely open to her to say: I didn't want that, and—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). But it had already been done. She had already purchased them.

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Before she returned here in 1931.

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir. And it was absolutely open to her to say, if she wanted to say it: I don't want these securities. And, of course, without any doubt, the securities would have been taken back from her, if she had said that. But it was the most remote kind of possibility that she would say any such thing. And people here had the power to act for her, to act in her behalf.

Mr. PECORA. You mean by that that when she did return to this country, some time in 1931, she was made acquainted with the fact that this sale had been made to her, and she did not repudiate or disavow it?

Mr. KAHN. Oh, undoubtedly.

Mr. PECORA. But does that give you any recollection as to whether or not at the time of the making of the sale she actually exercised and had every opportunity to exercise her independent judgment as to whether or not she should buy those securities?

Mr. KAHN. Her agents and those having power to act for her did so.

Mr. PECORA. They had the power, I presume you mean, under a power of attorney?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. But the question I propounded to you had to do with the matter of whether or not your daughter herself, not through an attorney in fact or agent, exercised and was given the opportunity to exercise her individual independent judgment with regard to buying these securities from you December 30, 1930.

Mr. KAHN. I could not say, Mr. Pecora; I do not recollect. It is 3 years back, more than 3 years back. I do not even know now where she was at that time.

Mr. PECORA. Now, when did you reacquire these five blocks of securities which you sold to your daughter as you have testified, on December 30, 1930?

Mr. KAHN. My memory having been refreshed by my counsel this morning who arrived from New York, I find on this statement that on the 30th of March, 1931, I reacquired those securities.

Mr. PECORA. And by what process did you reacquire them at that time?

Mr. KAHN. I reacquired them by reason of my daughter turning over to me, executing an assignment by which she turned over to me, a number of securities belonging to her.

Mr. PECORA. Including the securities in question?

Mr. KAHN. As to that I would not say. I do not know.

Mr. PECORA. Well, you say your counsel has produced here this morning a document purporting to be the original instrument of assignment, which you have just referred to, and I have it before me now.

Mr. KAHN. Yes; and that will doubtless show.

Mr. PECORA. Will you be good enough to look at it and tell us if you can identify that as to the actual instrument of assignment under which you reacquired these securities, as you say, on March 30, 1931?

Mr. KAHN. There is attached schedule A, and if you will be good enough, and I haven't the paper before me any more, but if you will be good enough to ask me whether there is any particular security in it or not I will answer.

Mr. PECORA. Well, among the securities which you sold to your daughter was one of 1,000 shares of Electric Power & Light. What about that?

Mr. KAHN. They are still there.

Mr. PECORA. That is, you mean you reacquired them under this assignment?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. You also sold to your daughter at that time 1,000 shares of International Nickel.

Mr. KAHN. And I reacquired those.

Mr. PECORA. Under that instrument?

Mr. KAHN. Under that same instrument; yes.

Mr. PECORA. And you also sold to your daughter 500 shares of Manhattan-Dearborn Co.?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And you reacquired those under this assignment?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. You also sold to your daughter 250 shares of Reynolds Metals Co.?

Mr. KAHN. I do not find that here.

Mr. PECORA. Look at page 4 of the schedule, a little below the middle of the page, I think.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. What is the name, again?

Mr. PECORA. Reynolds Metals Co., 250 shares.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And you also sold to your daughter 600 shares of Tubize Chattillon Co.

Mr. KAHN. Yes. Here they are.

Mr. PECORA. Now, what were the circumstances, Mr. Kahn, under which your daughter executed this assignment to you?

Mr. KAHN. She executed the assignment to me upon the advice of her English solicitor, or rather upon the advice of her independent counsel, not my counsel, but her independent counsel in America, who communicated on the subject with her English solicitor upon her request, and she acted upon his direction.

Mr. PECORA. Well, had you had any discussions or negotiations with your daughter at any time prior to her execution and delivery of this assignment to you, with respect to her transferring securities to you under this assignment?

Mr. KAHN. I do not recall that I personally had any such discussions, except, of course, I did discuss from time to time her financial affairs with her, and which was the best way of looking out for her and attending to the property that she had. But I do not recall any particular conversation on this particular subject.

Mr. PECORA. Had you expected at that time that your daughter would transfer those securities that are scheduled in that assignment to you?

Mr. KAHN. I am quite sure that at that time I had no such expectation.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Chairman, I offer the instrument of assignment in evidence and ask that it may be spread on the stenographic record of our hearings.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted.

(The instrument of assignment which was marked "Committee Exhibit No. 17, June 29, 1933", is as follows:)

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 17

ASSIGNMENT, MAUD E. MARRIOTT TO OTTO H. KAHN

Know all men by these presents, that I, the undersigned, Maud E. Marriott, herewith assign, convey, and transfer to my father, Otto H. Kahn, as of the

date of this instrument, all my right, title, and interest, if any, in and to all the securities and property specified in schedule A, annexed hereto and made part hereof;

To have and to hold the same unto the said Otto H. Kahn, his executors, administrators, and assigns forever.

In witness whereof I have hereunto set my hand and seal the 31st day of December in the year 1930.

[SEAL]

MAUD E. MARRIOTT.

Signed, sealed, and delivered on March 30, 1931, in the presence of:

I. B. LEVINE.

STATE OF NEW YORK,

County of New York, ss:

On the 30th day of March 1931, before me personally came I. B. Levine, the subscribing witness to the foregoing instrument, with whom I am personally acquainted, who, being by me duly sworn, did depose and say that he resides in the Borough of Manhattan, city of New York; that he knows Maud E. Marriott to be the individual described in and who executed the foregoing instrument; that he, said subscribing witness, was present and saw her execute the same; and that he, said witness, at the same time subscribed his name as witness thereto.

ROSE C. FRIEDMAN, *Notary Public*.

Kings County clerk's no. 499, register no. 1253; New York County clerk's no. 551, registered no. 1F379. Commission expires March 30, 1931.

Schedule A

Name of security	Bonds or shares	Book value	Market value	Annual income
Bethlehem Steel Corporation.....	333	\$30,636.00	\$18,731	\$1,998
Canadian Pacific Ry.....	800	38,000.00	32,200	2,000
Southern Pacific Ry.....	333	39,627.00	31,759	1,998
Chase National Bank of the City of New York.....	1,344	87,738.00	129,696	5,376
Rudolph Karstadt A.G. common R.M.....	71,000	28,881.67	10,138	2,027
Paramount Publix Corporation.....	950	42,714.24	40,493	3,800
Tide Water Associated Oil Co.....	5,500	66,000.00	37,125	3,300
Bendix Aviation Corporation.....	125	4,062.50	2,578	125
Briggs Manufacturing Co.....	1,000	14,000.00	19,750	1,750
Deutsche Bank Und Disconto Gesellschaft.....	500	17,007.50	13,000	714
Reynolds Metal Co.....	250	3,000.00	4,000	500
Electric Power & Light Co.....	1,000	37,000.00	50,500	1,000
International Nickel Co.....	1,000	14,500.00	17,125	600
Worthington Pump & Machinery Corporation, class A preferred.....	150	7,676.25	12,075	1,050
Price Brothers & Co., Ltd.....	250	19,024.85	9,500	500
Canadian Celanese, Ltd., preferred.....	250	12,037.50	16,500	1,750
Monsanto Chemical Works.....	305.1834	16,281.25	7,172	381
Cables & Wireless, Ltd.: Cumulative preferred.....	20334	6,856.45	611	27
A ord.....	51312		513	
B ord.....	37554		187	
National Dairy Products Corporation.....	288	20,679.33	13,608	749
Reliance International Corporation: Preferred.....	375	23,906.25	11,250	1,125
Class A.....	375		1,734	
Class B.....	9334		93	
The A. C. Gilbert Co.....	250	6,125.00	1,813	63
Public Utility Holding Corporation of America: Preferred.....	20212	23,635.00	6,986	606
Common.....	33712		1,561	
Warrants.....	47212		532	
Cities Service Co.....	271.29	15,205.86	4,951	375
Manhattan Railway, consolidated 4 percent 1990.....	27,000	16,233.75	14,141	1,080
Chemical National Bank.....	2,800		120,000	
Amalgamated Leather Co.....	300	2,475.00	600	None.
Central Oil Development Co.....	300	30.00	1	None.
Columbia Trust Co. (certificates of ben. int.).....	165		None.	None.
D. W. Griffith, class A.....	2,000	2,330.00	500	None.
Poole Engineering & Machine Co.: Class A.....	200	110.00	None.	None.
Class B.....	200			
Manhattan Dearborn Corporation.....	500	8,750.00	7,750	None.
Staked Plains Trust, Ltd.....	875	112.00	4,375	None.
Liquidation rights, certificates, class B.....	250		10,000	
Freed Eismann Radio Corporation.....	500	2,037.50	None.	None.

Schedule A—Continued

Name of security	Bonds or shares	Book value	Market value	Annual income
United Stores Corporation class A voting trust certificates.....	87½	\$15,594.65	\$645	None.
Florida Improvement Corporation.....	7,500	225.00	221	None.
R. M. Catts Corporation.....	312½	962.50	1	None.
Russo Asiatic Corporation.....	450	116.64	24	None.
Mining Trust, Ltd.....	562½	175.33	90	None.
National Bellas Hess Co.....	127.5	11,249.88	1,036	None.
Consolidated Automatic Merchandising Corporation.....	1,312½	10,001.11	246	None.
Corstak Product Co., Inc.....	1,000	20,500.00	1	None.
Punta Alegre Sugar Co. certificate of deposit.....	1,000	30,025.00	1,500	None.
Burdines, Inc.:				
Preferred.....	750	15,937.50	6,750	None.
Common.....	750		750	
Tuhlize Chatillon Corporation (B).....	600	2,250.00	4,800	None.
Ohio Copper Co. of Utah.....	5,000	4,825.00	1,875	None.
Quincy Mining Co.....	250	11,727.19	2,000	None.
Big Missouri Mining Co. Ltd.....	5,000	7,546.50	2,400	None.
Chicago, Milwaukee, St. Paul & Pacific R.R. series A, 5 percent.....	2,000	9,416.98	5,000	None.
Cheeka Corporation.....	250	1,372,811.19	1,352,866	None.
Mogmar Art Foundation Incorporated.....	50	5,000.00	649,063	None.
Little Cinema Theatres Incorporated.....	100	100.00	None.	None.
Gallahad Corporation.....	50	13,500.00	6,871	None.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, what was the consideration, if any, that you paid to your daughter for this assignment of securities?

Mr. KAHN. None, so far as I know.

Mr. PECORA. None?

Mr. KAHN. No.

Mr. PECORA. Were these securities transferred to you as a gift?

Mr. KAHN. There was no consideration as I understand it, but that is really a legal question. I canceled an existing trust, and upon the advice of her lawyers the thing was rearranged.

Mr. PECORA. Well, did you actually pay her anything for the securities which she transferred to you by this assignment, which has been identified by being marked "Committee Exhibit No. 17" as of this date?

Mr. KAHN. You are going into legal matters as to which I am very unfamiliar, and especially after this length of time; but my recollection is that these securities were used for the purpose of setting up trusts for her benefit.

Mr. PECORA. Well, now, the instrument of assignment, which is very brief, reads as follows: (And counsel read the assignment as shown above.) And there is a certificate of acknowledgment attached thereto by a notary public indicating that on the 30th day of March 1931, I. B. Levine, the subscribing witness, appeared before such notary and deposed that Maud E. Marriott executed the instrument; but does not set forth the date in the certificate of the acknowledgment when the subscribing witness acknowledged that Maud E. Marriott had executed it.

Mr. KAHN. To the best of my knowledge, it was executed on the 30th of March.

Mr. PECORA. Why was it dated on December 31, 1930?

Mr. KAHN. To the best of my recollection, it was so dated on the advice of her lawyer, and I believe this statement which was handed in this morning so sets forth; but there were really two lawyers dealing with one another who prearranged certain matters which

only concerned my daughter and myself and, to the best of my knowledge, concerned nobody else; and I accepted their advice exactly as she accepted their advice. One lawyer was acting for me; another lawyer was acting for her. But to the best of my knowledge neither of us derived any benefit from the transaction except a different legal set-up for her.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know personally of any reason why this instrument, which you say was not signed by your daughter until March 30, 1931, was dated and made effective the 31st of December 1930?

Mr. KAHN. The only reason that I know of was that she was so advised by her lawyer. What, precisely, actuated him and his English correspondent I could not possibly tell you.

Mr. PECORA. Were you such a stranger to this transaction that you do not know any reason why an instrument which actually was executed and signed on March 30, 1931, should have in terms been dated and made effective December 31, 1930?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, Mr. Pecora, I was such a stranger to that transaction. I had nothing to gain from it and nothing to lose by it, as far as I knew. I did what the respective lawyers advised, and as far as I knew it involved no one but my daughter and myself.

Mr. PECORA. Did it not involve the Government of the United States in connection with its rights to collect income taxes from you?

Mr. KAHN. Not to my knowledge, because the securities which I sold were sold on the 30th of December, in fact. This was signed late in March 1931, in fact. I understand, also, from my lawyer, that this very point which you raise, whether the Government of the United States was in any way detrimented by this, was brought up at the time, was argued before the authorities in Washington, and was decided in my favor. I did not even sign the protest myself. It was signed, in my absence in Europe, by some people who were my attorneys in fact. It was done on the advice of my lawyer. I certainly had no intention of doing anything, and had not the remotest knowledge that it involved doing anything, which could be a detriment to the United States Government.

Mr. PECORA. Now, the instrument, exhibit 17, which I shall call the assignment by your daughter to you, specifically says:

“Know all men by these presents, that I, the undersigned”, and so forth, “herewith assign, convey and transfer to my father as of the date of this instrument”—and the date of the instrument is December 31, 1930. Why was this instrument executed on March 30, 1931, by specific language made effective as of December 31, 1930?

Mr. KAHN. To the best of my knowledge, it was under the advice of her English and American lawyers.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know when the instrument itself was drafted?

Mr. KAHN. I do not.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know who drafted it?

Mr. KAHN. I presume it must have been drafted either by Messrs. Stroock & Stroock or by her lawyer; I do not know which.

Mr. PECORA. Her lawyer, you say, was an English solicitor?

Mr. KAHN. Her principal lawyer was an English solicitor with whom she conferred on the other side.

Mr. PECORA. Was her English solicitor in this country at the time this instrument was signed?

Mr. KAHN. I do not believe so.

Mr. PECORA. Does that suggest to you that the instrument was drawn by counsel here in this country or in New York, instead of by the English counsel or solicitor?

Mr. KAHN. I believe so.

Mr. PECORA. Who was the counsel in New York?

Mr. KAHN. Her counsel here was Mr. McIlvane, of the firm of Parsons, Parsons & McIlvane, who had been her grandfather's attorneys many years ago.

Mr. PECORA. I notice on the title page of the exhibit, which is the assignment, the printed name of Stroock & Stroock, counselors at law, 141 Broadway, New York City. Does that suggest that this instrument was drawn in that office?

Mr. KAHN. Mr. Levine tells me it was drawn in their office.

Mr. PECORA. By Stroock & Stroock or one of their attorneys?

Mr. KAHN. He told me before that it was drawn in pursuance of telephonic conversation between him and Mr. McIlvane.

Mr. PECORA. Stroock & Stroock are your personal attorneys in many matters, are they not?

Mr. KAHN. In tax matters; yes. May I say—I do not wish to give the impression of diminishing my relations with Stroock & Stroock, who are not only my counsel but my personal friends. In personal matters and in tax matters they are my lawyers.

Mr. PECORA. You have said something about the Internal Revenue Department having overruled the field agent who sought to assess a tax upon you by disallowing the deduction of the loss you claim, amounting to \$117,584, from your taxable income for the year 1930, because of this sale to your daughter. Have you ever seen the decision that the Internal Revenue Bureau rendered on its review?

Mr. KAHN. Not to the best of my knowledge.

Mr. PECORA. Well, do you know when it was rendered?

Mr. KAHN. I am afraid I do not.

Mr. PECORA. I understand it was rendered on April 28, 1933, which was just about 2 months ago.

Mr. KAHN. Mr. Levine says he has the record and the letter.

Mr. PECORA. What was the name of the Internal Revenue Department's agent in this matter?

Mr. KAHN. I do not know, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. Perhaps your counsel can tell you.

Mr. LEVINE. R. T. Mott.

Mr. PECORA. Was it not N. C. Shields?

Mr. LEVINE. He was in it, too. Shields was the field agent.

Mr. PECORA. The field agent, N. C. Shields, sought to assess an income tax upon you for the year 1930 of \$16,000 or more, did he not, upon the belief expressed by him that this sale of December 30, 1930, to your daughter was a wash sale?

Mr. KAHN. So I was informed this morning.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know that Mr. Shields in a report submitted by him under date of April 28, 1933, to the internal-revenue agent in charge of the second New York division said as follows:

Relative to loss sustained by the above-named taxpayer of \$117,584, it can be stated that this loss resulted from an ordinary sale on the New York Stock

Exchange of securities owned by taxpayer. Taxpayer's daughter, Maud Merriott, also had a substantial sum invested in securities which for personal reasons she gave to her father, Mr. Kahn, by assignment dated March 31, 1930—

That should be 1931—

which included shares of stocks in four companies of which companies Mr. Kahn had sold his holdings on December 31, 1930.

From the above it will be noted that there were no direct dealings between the taxpayer and his daughter with the exception of a mere transfer by gift of the securities owned by the daughter to the father.

Are you familiar with that report or memorandum?

Mr. KAHN. No; I am not.

Mr. PECORA. Was not the field agent in error when he said that the loss resulted from an ordinary sale made by you on the New York Stock Exchange?

Mr. KAHN. I really do not know.

Mr. PECORA. Have you not testified here this morning that you made the sale not through the medium of the exchange, but directly to your daughter?

Mr. KAHN. So I was informed by Mr. Levine.

Mr. PECORA. What was the fact?

Mr. KAHN. I do not know the fact. I presume that he knows it, because he was in my office yesterday.

Mr. PECORA. His information to you was that the sale was made not through the stock exchange, but directly between you and your daughter?

Mr. KAHN. So I understood.

Mr. PECORA. Have you any reason to doubt the accuracy of that information?

Mr. KAHN. His or the agent's?

Mr. PECORA. The accuracy of the information which your counsel gave to you.

Mr. KAHN. Oh, I have complete confidence in my counsel's information.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know also that the field agent states in this memorandum or report by him of April 28, 1933—

There were no direct dealings between the taxpayer and his daughter with the exception of a mere transfer by gift of the securities owned by the daughter to the father.

Does it now seem that that also was an erroneous statement of fact made by the field agent?

Mr. KAHN. It was an erroneous statement, evidently, either by the field agent, or it was an error on the part of my counsel. I am inclined to give my counsel the benefit of the doubt.

Mr. PECORA. You are inclined to feel that your counsel's information to you was accurate?

Mr. KAHN. So I would feel, unless evidence was produced to me to the contrary.

Mr. PECORA. Can you suggest any means by which the field agent acquired this misinformation concerning the transaction in question?

Mr. KAHN. I have no knowledge; but inasmuch as I am informed that all my books and all my family's books and records were open to the inspection of the field agent and that he spent days and days

in my office going over them, I have not any suggestion to make why any such error, if it was an error, occurred.

Mr. PECORA. Now, when your attorneys protested to the Internal Revenue Department against the original action of this same field agent seeking to assess an income tax of over \$16,000 upon you, is it not a fact that the primary basis of the protest was that you were a dealer in securities rather than an investor?

Mr. KAHN. That is a technical matter on which I am utterly devoid of knowledge.

Mr. PECORA. The protest was made in your behalf, was it not?

Mr. KAHN. In my absence.

Mr. PECORA. In your absence and without communication beforehand with you?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. You mean to say that your attorneys would assume a factual basis concerning a transaction involving yourself without first getting in touch with you?

Mr. KAHN. Oh, they would know it better than I did.

Mr. PECORA. You mean, your attorneys, from the inception, knew more about this sale by you to your daughter than you did?

Mr. KAHN. They knew about this transaction between my daughter and myself much better than I did, and presumably they posted themselves fully as to all the facts before they sent in this protest of which I know nothing and as to the details of which I am to this day without knowledge.

Mr. PECORA. You said something in the course of your testimony earlier in this session about the sale of this stock by you to your daughter having been entered on somebody's books. Whose books was the sale entered on?

Mr. KAHN. That would presumably, if my counsel is correct, be the books of Kuhn, Loeb & Co.; likewise, of course, my books and her books.

Mr. PECORA. As of what date was this transfer of the securities under this instrument of assignment by your daughter to you entered?

Mr. KAHN. That, again, would be a technical matter between the two lawyers that I would not know.

Mr. PECORA. In this typewritten statement which you read into the record this morning in the early part of your testimony on this subject, I observe the following statement:

Counsel reports to me that in December 1930 these securities were sold by myself for cash at the regular market price on that day and the amount received therefor duly credited to me.

Were they actually sold for cash, Mr. Kahn?

Mr. KAHN. To the extent that I understand "cash"; yes.

Mr. PECORA. That is, did you actually receive any cash or payment of any kind, or token of payment from your daughter on the occasion of this sale?

Mr. KAHN. If by cash you understand greenbacks or yellowbacks; no. If by cash you understand what everybody in New York does understand, a transfer of value from one party to another party through a book entry or through a check, I did actually receive cash; yes.

Mr. PECORA. You mean you received a credit on a book account?

Mr. KAHN. I received a credit on a book account; yes.

Mr. PECORA. Do you call that a cash transaction?

Mr. KAHN. I call that 95 percent of the cash transactions which are consummated in this country.

Mr. PECORA. That was the kind of cash transaction referred to by you, was it?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Your statement further proceeds in this fashion:

In March 1931 my daughter arrived in this country, and about that time I discussed her affairs with counsel acquainted with English law who called in English solicitors in order to devise and carry out a plan by which trusts could be set up for her and my son-in-law, Major Merriott.

What was that plan?

Mr. KAHN. That was the plan which was worked out between Mr. McIlvane and Mr. Levine under the instructions of the English counsel.

Mr. PECORA. What was the plan? You told us they worked it out; but what was the substance of it?

Mr. KAHN. The substance of it was various trusts set up for my daughter; and I suppose that is all that I can state on the subject with any accuracy.

Mr. PECORA. What property went into the trust?

Mr. KAHN. The property which she turned over to me.

Mr. PECORA. That is, the property consisting of the securities that are set forth in the schedule attached to the assignment, exhibit no. 17?

Mr. KAHN. Not necessarily all of them; presumably the bulk of it.

Mr. PECORA. Did your daughter have the sole beneficial title to these securities that are enumerated in this assignment?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And your daughter was turning over a very considerable amount of property to you for the purpose of your setting up a trust for her benefit; that is, property that she already owned?

Mr. KAHN. I beg your pardon?

Mr. PECORA. Do you want us to understand that your daughter turned over to you property consisting of these securities as set forth in this assignment, which she already owned, in order that you might set up a trust for her benefit?

Mr. KAHN. That question presupposes legal knowledge and detailed knowledge which I do not possess. I hate to tax your patience, Mr. Pecora, by repeating that, as to the details, they were left to the respective lawyers, Mr. McIlvane, primarily; and whatever I might say would be a guess as to those details with which I certainly am not familiar.

The CHAIRMAN. Were those securities actually delivered to you in trust for your daughter?

Mr. KAHN. They were delivered to me to be dealt with as my daughter, under the instructions of her lawyer, would advise me and as I saw fit. Of course, I saw fit to deal with her and with those securities in the way that I thought was best, under legal advice, for her interests.

Mr. PECORA. I observe in going over this instrument of assignment and hurriedly scanning the schedule of securities attached to it, or

shown upon it, rather, that there is one block of securities shown to have a value of \$1,352,866, the security in question being designated as Oheka Corporation. Did your daughter have actual beneficial title and ownership of that block of securities which she turned over to you?

Mr. KAHN. She did, Mr. Pecora; but the figure is, again, one of those things to which I have referred before, where optimism and reality clash. They were worth nothing like that. They consisted mainly of real estate; and some of that real estate, you know, even at that time—real estate was not worth the price that our hopes dictated.

Mr. PECORA. In addition to this schedule indicating a market value of \$1,352,866 for that security, the schedule indicates a book value for that security of \$1,372,811.19. So, apparently, the fact that there was a difference between market value and book value was recognized in this instrument of assignment?

Mr. KAHN. The book value was equally under the influence of that conflict between optimism and reality.

Mr. PECORA. Who arrived at those estimates of market value?

Mr. KAHN. They were no doubt got up from the figures in which they appeared in the books. Who determined those figures I do not really know. They did not have any significance to speak of.

Mr. PECORA. Had you previously to the making of this assignment delivered to your daughter all of the securities that are listed in schedule A attached to the assignment?

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. That whole thing, you mean?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. KAHN (after conferring with associates). I have been trying to get information all around and have been unsuccessful.

Mr. PECORA. What is your best recollection?

Mr. KAHN. Her books would show—in England, presumably.

Mr. PECORA. But what is your own best recollection?

Mr. KAHN. Oh, my recollection is simply that over a term of years I used to make gifts to her, and sometimes she would buy things, and presumably that is the explanation. I do not know it of my own knowledge, but her books would show.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recognize on the schedule of securities attached to this assignment, exhibit no. 17, any securities that you had previously delivered to your daughter, either as a gift or by virtue of any sale?

Mr. KAHN. No, Mr. Pecora. I recognize, of course, the five which were sold to her in December; but as to the rest I would be guessing, and I can do nothing better than guess. I refer you to the fact that her books would show.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, can you supply the committee with a list of names of the securities that you sold to your daughter at the end of any other tax year?

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. We will look it up. We cannot get it today, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, did you for any of the years 1930, 1931, or 1932 pay any income tax to any other jurisdiction than the United States—to any foreign jurisdiction?

Mr. KAHN. What years are those?

Mr. PECORA. 1930, 1931, and 1932.

Mr. MOORE. I will read it from the return, Mr. Pecora. In 1930 he paid \$4,480.26, item 54, income tax paid to a foreign country or United States possession.

Mr. PECORA. What country was that?

Mr. KAHN. I assume it must have been England, because I assume that these items are income deducted at the source on English securities which I own. I cannot imagine what else they could be. They must be that.

Senator TOWNSEND. It was not a property tax?

Mr. KAHN. No.

Mr. PECORA. Was there any other tax paid to any other foreign jurisdiction?

Mr. MOORE. In 1931 there is no such tax entered here. In 1932 there is apparently no such item.

The CHAIRMAN. We will take a recess now until 2 o'clock.

(Whereupon, at 12:30 p.m., a recess was taken until 2 p.m.)

AFTERNOON SESSION

Upon the expiration of the noon recess the hearing was resumed at 2 o'clock p.m.

The CHAIRMAN. The committee will come to order, and you may proceed, Mr. Pecora.

TESTIMONY OF OTTO H. KAHN, A PARTNER OF KUHN, LOEB & CO.—Resumed

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, before we pass on from the subject of the sales of securities on December 30, 1930, which was the subject of your examination this morning, let me ask if you have any further statement on that subject you wish to make to the committee without the necessity of being asked any questions concerning it.

Mr. KAHN. None that I know of, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. In the questionnaire that was submitted to your firm by counsel for the committee several weeks ago you were asked to give us the names of all other participants and the extent of their respective participation in syndicates handling issues which your firm managed.

Mr. KAHN. I believe we have done so, haven't we?

Mr. PECORA. Yes; you have. And in response to that request your firm furnished us with various lists, which we have caused to be consolidated into one list, which I will now show you, which I believe has been already examined by your firm and checked by them and found to be a correct consolidation of such lists. Will you look at it and tell us if you can identify it as such?

Mr. STEWART. We have never seen it in this form, Mr. Pecora, but I presume it is correct, because I gave them the facts.

Mr. KAHN. We have not seen it in this form, but I have no doubt of its correctness.

Mr. PECORA. Then, subject to any correction that you might want to make on it, I offer it in evidence and ask that it be spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted and put in the record.

(Consolidated list of participations was thereupon marked "Committee Exhibit 18, June 29, 1933." See p. 1262.)

Mr. STEWART. I have no doubt it is all right, Mr. Pecora, because I gave them the facts.

Mr. PECORA. The lists which we obtained from you in answer to that request in our questionnaire did not include all of the affiliations of the various individuals shown on the lists. The consolidated list just received in evidence purports to give those corporate affiliations?

Mr. STEWART. That is right.

Mr. PECORA. They were prepared from authorized lists of boards of directors and other authentic information. You may check against them in any way you want to and advise us of any correction you wish to make.

Mr. STEWART. Surely.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, who selected the gentlemen whose names appear on exhibit 18 as persons who were invited or were to be invited to participate in these various syndicate operations of your firm?

Mr. KAHN. That would be a conglomerate invitation, Mr. Pecora. In the first instance the name would be set down by the gentleman who manages our syndicates, which is Mr. Bovenizer, Mr. George Bovenizer. Then my partners and I would go over it and see whether we wanted anything added or taken away.

Mr. PECORA. Is it the fact that various gentlemen whose names appear on this list were invited and permitted to participate in these various syndicate operations under circumstances which did not require them to actually put up any money?

Mr. KAHN. I do not think that is a fact, Mr. Pecora. They were treated exactly like any other syndicate participant was treated. Ordinarily, I am glad to say, our batting average is that we succeeded in selling our bonds fairly quickly, and there was usually no need to call for money to be put up. Sometimes there is, I am sorry to say.

Mr. PECORA. Those instances where there is such need are very, very few, aren't they?

Mr. KAHN. Perhaps not as few as for peace of my nights I would like them to be, but they are few, and these people whom you refer to are treated exactly as every syndicate participant is treated. It does happen that some bonds or securities remain and that we are willing in their case, as we would be willing in other cases if we have available cash, to carry them under security of the particular bond to which that syndicate relates, but ordinarily that is not the case. Ordinarily it is not the case. Many of them when there are amounts to be taken up because the syndicate has not been wholly successful, take up those amounts and pay for them. I should say a majority of them, a great majority of them.

Mr. PECORA. A great majority of them did what?

Mr. KAHN. A great majority of them, I should say, of those whom you mentioned on that list, if there are bonds to be taken up because the syndicate has not been wholly successful, the majority of them would take them up and pay for them. Some of them would say, "Are you willing to carry them?" And if we have the money available, why, we are quite willing to accommodate them, just as we would accommodate any other syndicate participant.

Mr. PECORA. Would it be possible for you, Mr. Kahn, in going over this list with reference to the various issues in the syndicates in which these gentlemen were invited to participate to tell this com-

mittee in which issues the need arose for calling upon any of these participants to actually put up any of their money?

Mr. KAHN. I think I can. Perhaps I can abbreviate my answer by saying a considerable number of those participants were relatives who kept their account in our office and about whose financial standing we are constantly advised. Mr. Stewart says they are not on that list. I thought they were. I beg your pardon.

Mr. PECORA. I would say in casually glancing over this list that a large number if not a majority of the names appearing thereon are the names of men who were executive officers of various railroad corporations.

Mr. KAHN. Railroad and other corporations; yes.

Mr. PECORA. And most of the railroad corporations with which these men were affiliated are railroad corporations for which your firm did financing, are they not?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Did your firm handle issues that found their way into the portfolio of large insurance companies?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. I notice among the names on this list that of Mr. F. H. Ecker, president and director of the Metropolitan Life Insurance Co.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. That is one of the largest insurance companies in the country, isn't it?

Mr. KAHN. It is; yes.

Mr. PECORA. If not in the world?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And has perhaps the largest cash resources of the entire country?

Mr. KAHN. I think so.

Mr. PECORA. And hence is the largest potential buyer of railroad bonds?

Mr. KAHN. I think so.

Mr. PECORA. Now, there are instances where the Metropolitan Life Insurance Co. purchased an entire issue of bonds put out by your firm?

(Mr. Kahn conferred with Mr. Stewart and Mr. de Gersdorff.)

Mr. PECORA. By that I meant the participation of your firm in such issues.

Mr. KAHN. There may be one or two very small issues not amounting to anything; no large issue.

And possibly, Mr. Pecora, before we leave Mr. Ecker I should say in justice to him that he never had a syndicate participation in any bond issue which his corporation would legally be permitted to invest in, and that the total profit realized on his participations in the course of 5 years amounted to less than \$7,000. That is, he got altogether an average in his participations over the 5 years of \$1,400 a year. He was never in any syndicate in which his company bought bonds.

Mr. PECORA. Then his participation, I assume from your statement, in these issues was on a very small scale?

Mr. KAHN. On a very small scale; yes.

Mr. PECORA. Was his participation invited as a courtesy to him or because you felt that you needed his financial assistance in any way with respect to those issues in which he was invited to participate?

Mr. KAHN. Perhaps once more, all saving your time, I can answer to the viewpoint which actuated us in offering this kind of participation to a very small list of men. By no means are those all with whom we did business or with whose company we did business. These men, all of them, are men known for their outstanding ability and for their wide information on particular fields, either a field of life insurance and investment, field of railroading, field of industry. It was of very great value to us—they are all old friends of ours—to be able to go to them and get their judgment. We would not hesitate, for instance, in the case of Mr. Ecker, to telephone him and say, "In your opinion do you think that this is a useful and favorable time for bringing out a large bond issue, or do you think that the market in general is not now favorably disposed toward it?" He would give us the benefit of his opinion. We would not hesitate in going to every other one on that small list and say, "Please give us the benefit of your opinion. What do things in the country look like?"

For instance, let us say it is Newcomb Carlton, of the Western Union. We would go and we would say to him, "Now, you get information all over the country as to how industrial conditions are. It would be very helpful if you would give us the benefit of your view of what things are looking like." They would be good enough to permit us to get that opinion.

In return for that the only thing we could do to show our gratitude and our appreciation and our recognition, and not to feel that we are absolutely sponging upon them, is to give them a little token of courtesy and good will when the opportunity presented itself, amounting to insignificant sums; not with the idea that these sums could possibly have any effect upon them, but with the idea that we felt if we could we ought to make a gesture of courtesy and good will.

That was really in all cases the actuating motive why we offered these men these small participations, and that was true of Mr. Ecker, and it held good of everybody else on that list.

Mr. PECORA. Most of the corporations with which many of the men whose names appear on this list were affiliated and are affiliated are corporation clients of your firm, are they not?

Mr. KAHN. A client of our firm? Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. In other words, they are corporations who maintain deposit accounts with you, as well as corporations that engage your firms to do financing for them?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Were these participations which were accorded to them by your firm in the nature of reciprocity by your firm to these gentlemen for any service they rendered or any usefulness that they were to your firm?

Mr. KAHN. In the way, if I understand the implication of the question, of inducing them to do business with us, most positively not. You must realize that those men, being in important positions, if we had wanted to induce them, could not possibly be induced by relatively trifling participations. They were, as I have said before, tokens of good will and an attempt to give some little recognition

for the liberty which we took in asking their opinions on important matters. We haven't very many close affiliations, as some other bankers have. We largely depend upon our own judgment. And it is of great value to us to be permitted to go and ask other people who have a country-wide knowledge of things.

Mr. PECORA. Well now, along that line, the National City Co. was an investment or security selling company which competed to a certain extent with your firm, wasn't it?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; except that we were not a retail organization and they were.

Mr. PECORA. But in bringing out issues they competed with your firm?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. In addition to issuing securities they also sold them through a selling force that they maintained?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. I notice the name of a gentleman who was the chairman of that company appears on this list.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. A man named Charles E. Mitchell.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Was he permitted to participate—or rather invited to participate—in these various syndicate operations of yours because from time to time you found it necessary to seek his opinion or advice on whether or not a given time was a good time to bring out an issue of bonds?

Mr. KAHN. The participation profits of Mr. Mitchell in those 5 years aggregate about \$2,600 a year.

Mr. PECORA. Whatever it was, was the invitation to him to participate in your syndicate operations extended as a token of your appreciation for any assistance you got from him by way of advice as to whether or not a given time was a propitious time to bring out an issue?

Mr. KAHN. Decidedly so. We would not hesitate to go to Mr. Mitchell and compare views with him.

Mr. PECORA. Would you go to a competitor for such advice and opinions?

Mr. KAHN. Yes. Yes; because the case where we would go to him would not be a case where he and we would be in direct and immediate competition. It would be a case where we were considering certain business, and we would say, "Mr. Mitchell, what do you think of the present situation?" We might even tell him what it was about. He would not hesitate to give us his opinion. That would not prevent him from competing with us if he felt like it.

Mr. PECORA. That leads me to the observation that the competition between banking houses was rather of a friendly nature. Is that observation an unsound or an unwarranted one?

Mr. KAHN. I hope that competition is of a friendly nature, and ought to be. I have said before that I know of nothing more damaging than cutthroat, ruthless competition.

Mr. PECORA. In view of the fact that you testified that these invitations to participate in your syndicates were extended in appreciation of aid or assistance that you got from these various gentlemen, or to establish or maintain good will and friendly relations, would

that further lead to the observation that the competition is of a character which was founded upon mutual good will?

Mr. KAHN. May I be allowed to slightly amend the query? I did not say appreciation. I said we felt it incumbent upon us, having taken the liberty of inviting the opinion of these gentlemen from time to time, as it seemed valuable to us—we felt it incumbent upon us, not as a reciprocity, not as a token of appreciation, but as a matter of ordinary courtesy and good will, to invite them to small syndicate participations if the occasion arose on exactly the same terms as everybody else, at exactly the same risks that everybody else took.

Mr. PECORA. Did other competing firms or other banking houses extend similar invitations to your firm?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Is this a sort of a common occurrence?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; quite a common occurrence.

Mr. PECORA. Now, the Chase Securities Corporation, which is the investment affiliate of the Chase National Bank, is also a competitor of your house in the issuance and promotion of securities?

Mr. KAHN. The First National Bank?

Mr. PECORA. The Chase.

Mr. KAHN. The Chase, yes.

Mr. PECORA. I notice the name of Mr. Wiggin, the former head of that company, also on these lists. I assume from your testimony that he was invited to participate on these various occasions from the same motive you have already given expression to?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Senator BARKLEY. Where in a given case you would call on Mr. Mitchell or anybody else for his suggestions or advice about the condition of the market, or the propriety of the occasion with reference to one of these issues, and his advice was negative, or his suggestion was that it was not a good time, in the event that you went ahead with it anyway would you take him in in the investment, regardless of his advice?

Mr. KAHN. Oh, quite regardless of his advice. We would take him in, as I say, annually a couple of times, over a period of 5 years. Quite irrespective of whether his advice was good, bad, or indifferent. We felt it was no more than reasonable to—

Senator BARKLEY. Your invitation was not based on their advice in any particular case then?

Mr. KAHN. No.

Senator BARKLEY. But just as a sort of a continuing courtesy?

Mr. KAHN. A continuing courtesy; yes.

Mr. PECORA. And to maintain this spirit of good-will that you referred to; is that right?

Mr. KAHN. Right.

Senator BARKLEY. The amount of profit so far named here was apparently not sufficient to warp anybody's judgment as to the wisdom or un wisdom of any issue?

Mr. KAHN. I am quite sure, Senator, knowing the salaries, compensations, and opportunities of these men, that \$1,500 or \$2,000 or \$2,500 a year could not possibly tempt them one way or another. But they would say: "Well, these people are trying to be decent when the opportunity arises. They have not got much to give which is very

profitable." Because our business was mainly in bonds, and bonds usually do not permit of large profits.

Mr. PECORA. Would one be guilty of giving expression to a violent or wild imagination if he were to assume from these acts of courtesy and mutual goodwill that an effort was made to obtain some utopian state of business?

Mr. KAHN. I do not believe that we will ever come any nearer to that, Mr. Pecora, than we are with the present attempt of the industries bill. I hope very much it will lead to something quite different from what existed in the past.

Senator BARKLEY. You are in sympathy with the Industrial Recovery Act then, I gather?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; I am in sympathy with the purpose of it entirely.

Senator BARKLEY. That is what I mean.

Mr. KAHN. Entirely. As I said this morning, I believe we will have to find by test and trial what, if any, changes are required. I am wholly in sympathy equally with the purpose of the securities bill. In fact, I made what I tried to render an eloquent speech 15 years ago on this very subject, urging this very thing. But if you ask me whether I believe that as it is now drawn it will not require certain modifications, not in the interest of bankers but in the interest of those services which bankers ought to render to industry and to the economy of the country, then I am afraid I will have to say I think there are a few points in there which experience will show will need to be changed.

Senator BARKLEY. That was true of the Federal Reserve Act and is true of practically every new great step in legislation?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; I agree. I just wanted to make my answer plain.

Senator ADAMS. That is rather a compliment to the law, that you think it needs only a few corrections.

Mr. KAHN. I think it needs a few corrections; yes.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, you have already testified in substance to the effect that most of the corporation financing done by your firm throughout its history has been for railroad corporations?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Now, in undertaking financing operations involving the issuance of bonds for and on behalf of a railroad corporation whose interests particularly do you deem it proper for your firm to serve?

Mr. KAHN. We attempt to the best of our ability and our conscience to serve equally the public and the corporation. Not, as I said yesterday, because we are more altruistic than others, but from enlightened self-interest. We know if we sell at an unjustifiable price to the public the public will leave us. We know if we buy at too low a price from the railroads, the railroads will go to somebody else, or the Interstate Commerce Commission will turn us down, which is always a black mark. So, not because we are virtuous but because I hope we have a correct appreciation of enlightened self-interest, we try to put them on an equal footing and agree with the railroads at a price that we feel we can justly defend both toward the public and toward the railroad.

Mr. PECORA. In your testimony previously at these hearings you have likened the relationship of the banker to the railroad corpora-

tions to the relationship existing between an attorney and client, as well as to the relationship existing between a doctor and a patient.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Now, in the case of the attorney, he, of course, recognizes that the interests that he is charged with serving, assuming a relationship for the client, are the interests of the client. And in the case of the doctor, he naturally assumes that the interests he is to serve are the interests of his patient. Now, in the case of the banker for the railroad corporation, the banker regards the railroad corporation essentially as his client, whose interest he should serve, does he not?

Mr. KAHN. If he is a stupid banker; yes. If he has got sense he will realize that for his purposes the interests of the public are just as important as the interests of the railroad, and that neither of the two will thank him ultimately except if he serves both of them well. And when I compared our method of doing business with that of a lawyer or of a doctor, it did not mean—and if I conveyed that impression I expressed myself badly—it did not mean to go right through from beginning to end. It meant only that I said that we stand on our reputation. Our asset is our reputation. We do not go out and seek clients any more than a lawyer or a doctor does. But we hope we have established a reputation for integrity and thoroughness and good treatment comparable to what a doctor or a lawyer does. But it did not mean to go any further than that.

Mr. PECORA. Now there is also another interest to be served or which arises in the relationship between the banker and the railroad corporation, and that is the interest of the banker himself, is there not?

Mr. KAHN. I consider that identical with the other two interests I have mentioned.

Mr. PECORA. Are they all merged?

Mr. KAHN. I consider that all three are merged in rendering service which is acceptable both to the railroads or the industrial corporations and to the public, and which is reasonably profitable to the banker.

Mr. PECORA. The banker, you feel, is justified in having some regard for his own interests, do you not?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; I do.

Mr. PECORA. And you feel that the circumstances warrant his giving some special consideration to the peculiar interests of the client, which is the railroad corporation, do you not?

Mr. KAHN. I am afraid in this general sense I cannot vary my answers that I believe the interests of the public and of the railroad corporation, of the buyer and of the seller, are precisely identical.

Mr. PECORA. Well, is it not the interest of the railroad corporation to get as big a price for its bonds as it can?

Mr. KAHN. In my judgment, no. I think it is to the interest of the railroads to build up a regular investment clientele through the bankers, which investment clientele feels that they are being fairly dealt with by the railroad, and if the railroad in any one particular instance attempts to gouge the public and gets more out of it than its securities are worth in my opinion it is a very short-sighted policy.

Mr. PECORA. Do you not recognize that there is a distinction between the interests of the investor who buys the bond and the interests of the issuer who sells them?

Mr. KAHN. In my opinion they ought to be, and by any enlightened conception of the matter they are identical.

Mr. PECORA. You recognize no distinction between them?

Mr. KAHN. I do not; no. I think they are identical interests. The one wants to offer at a fair price and the other wants to buy at a fair price. And if either of them is unfair it reacts against him ultimately.

The CHAIRMAN. You cannot usually get both sides to see that, can you?

Mr. KAHN. Well, we have been fairly successful, Senator, in persuading our clients equally to the effect which I have just tried to express to Mr. Pecora. We frequently argue that very point. We have not always succeeded, but we are always endeavoring to succeed.

Mr. PECORA. In the general method by which bankers bring out issues for railroad corporations and sell them to the public the price at which the bonds are purchased by the banker is one that is determined in negotiations between the banker and his client, the railroad corporation, is it not?

Mr. KAHN. Between himself and his client, the railroad corporation; yes.

Mr. PECORA. Yes. The investor has nothing to do with those negotiations and has no participation therein, has he?

Mr. KAHN. The investor directly, no; except to the extent that he looks to the banker to have a decent regard for his interests.

Mr. PECORA. But anyway, the investor is not consulted and has no part in the negotiations leading to the fixation of the price at which the issue is taken over by the banker?

Mr. KAHN. He is not, except in the case of the railroads to the extent that the Interstate Commerce Commission represents the investor inasmuch as it represents the community as a whole. It is a Government body which has no favors to give and no favors to ask.

Mr. PECORA. But the fact is the investor has no part in those negotiations which result in the fixation of the price at which the banker takes over the issue from the railroad corporation?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Has the investor any participation in the conferences or negotiations which result in the fixation of the price at which the banker offers those bonds to the investing public?

Mr. KAHN. None. No.

Senator BARKLEY. Is the same true of the municipal and county and State and Government bonds, too?

Mr. KAHN. That is true of all bonds. The market fixes the price.

Mr. PECORA. Well, is it not a fact that in the issuance of municipal bonds, bonds falling within that classification, the public offering is frequently on a competitive bidding basis?

Mr. KAHN. Competitive bidding basis—

Mr. PECORA. So that the investor is free to bid at whatever price his judgment dictated?

Mr. KAHN. But he does not, Mr. Pecora. Experience has shown that the investor does not bid, and you cannot make him do it. He

will not come out of his shell and say, "Here is a chance to buy something cheap. I will put in a bid." He will not do it. He will leave it to a group, and then he buys from that group a point or two points higher. He is built that way.

Mr. PECORA. Do you not know of many instances where municipal issues have been offered to the public on a competitive bidding basis and the public has responded by subscribing for the whole issue? Do you not know of many instances of that sort?

Mr. KAHN. I do not know of any such instances, but I know of many instances where the public offerings have resulted in a dismal failure, and where the municipalities have come to the banks or the bankers and said, "Please help us out of a hole. We did not get the money we counted on, and we need it. We need it to pay our school teachers and our employees, and the public did not give it to us. Please give it to us as a patriotic duty, as a community service." And it has always been done. But I know very few instances where the public absorbed an issue offered for public subscription.

Mr. PECORA. My recollection may be at fault, but I recall, I think, having read sometime ago a book called "Other People's Money", written by an eminent jurist, in which are recorded instances of the kind that I referred to.

Mr. KAHN. I know the eminent jurist, and have the utmost respect for him, and admiration. I would like to write a book in reply, if I had the time for it. In any event, I am quite sure that I can bring forth many more instances to the contrary than he has brought forth in the affirmative.

Mr. PECORA. Would you say that the bankers, either consciously or unconsciously, have helped to educate the public to believe that the public cannot formulate its own judgment and make its own bids for securities, but should rely upon the judgment of the banker?

Mr. KAHN. I am quite sure that the bankers have not; and if they attempted it with the reputation that now adheres to bankers, and has long adhered to them, it would be quite futile. The public would not listen to them. If the public believed that it wanted to invest upon its own direct judgment, it would do so. The public does not. The public is a queer animal, and it has got certain traits, and one of the traits is that it will not come out of its shell and submit a direct individual bid.

Mr. PECORA. The public has adopted the habit of just buying bonds at the offering price that has been fixed by bankers or the issuer, is that what you mean to say?

Mr. KAHN. Not necessarily. Sometimes they do not. Sometimes they do. Sometimes they think the price is too high, and they will stay away, and they think, "We will get them better and cheaper if we wait longer." But the public has learned that it is a convenience to it to utilize the services of a banker, and purely of its own accord it sticks to that habit.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know a corporation called the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. KAHN. I beg your pardon?

Mr. PECORA. Do you know a corporation called the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. KAHN. Very well.

Mr. PECORA. Did your firm have anything to do with the organization of that corporation?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. When was it incorporated?

Mr. KAHN. If you will permit me I will refer to a few notes which I have here.

Mr. PECORA. Surely.

Mr. KAHN. I know it in a general way. It was incorporated in April, 1929.

Mr. PECORA. At whose instance was it incorporated?

Mr. KAHN. I referred yesterday to the reason why the Pennsylvania Railroad felt it incumbent to attempt to create an instrument of defense against the threatened and apprehended aggressions on the part of competing railroads in its own territory, an instrument which could be used swiftly and which could act as the necessity arose.

General Atterbury, the president of the Pennsylvania Railroad, in the circular which was issued when the first issue of Pennroad stock was offered to the public, went into that quite at length and, I think, set forth the reasons which justified that action much more forcefully than I could. I do not know whether you have that circular, but if not I would like to submit it. I believe you have it, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. No.

Mr. KAHN. The only reason why I am not setting it forth is I do not want to take your time unnecessarily.

Mr. PECORA. Well, if you have it I would like to offer it for the record.

Mr. KAHN. Yes. Here is the typewritten copy.

Mr. PECORA. Thank you, sir.

The CHAIRMAN. It may be received in evidence and spread upon the record.

(Circular dated Philadelphia, Pa., April 24, 1929, of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., by W. W. Atterbury, president, containing also circular of the Pennroad Corporation, dated Wilmington, Del., April 24, 1929, signed by Henry H. Lee, president, was received in evidence, marked "Committee Exhibit 19" of June 29, 1933, and is here printed in the record in full, as follows:)

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT 19 OF JUNE 29, 1933

(Please read carefully and retain for future reference)

THE PENNSYLVANIA RAILROAD CO.,
Philadelphia, Pa., April 24, 1929.

To the stockholders:

Your directors have given earnest consideration to recent developments in the field of transportation, and have reached the conclusion that it will be of material advantage to this company and its stockholders for the stockholders to unite in establishing a corporation so organized that it may make investments and take advantage of opportunities on a much broader basis than is possible under the limited powers of a railroad company. Your directors are of the opinion that such an independent instrumentality is needed to protect your interests and those of your company.

Accordingly there has been incorporated under the laws of the State of Delaware the Pennroad Corporation (hereinafter called the corporation), with broad powers, among others, to invest its funds in securities of any corporation

or other agency, including those engaged in transportation of any description on land or water or by air, but without power to operate railroads.

In order that the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. should have the first opportunity to purchase the stock of the corporation, arrangements have been made that there be offered to said stockholders at \$15 per share the 5,800,000 shares of common stock, without par value, of the corporation presently to be issued.

The outstanding capital stock of your company, including stock allotted to employees on the installment plan, consists of 11,583,479 shares of the par value of \$50 each, a total of \$579,173,950 par value. There are approximately 157,000 registered holders of stock of your company, of whom over 80 percent own 100 shares or less, and in addition there are close to 100,000 employee subscribers.

The wide diversification of the ownership of your company's stock, not only in this country but abroad, indicates that there will be a correspondingly wide distribution of the stock of the new corporation. Accordingly, in furtherance of the purpose for which the corporation has been organized and in order to insure continuity of management, all the stock now being issued will be placed in a voting trust under which Messrs. W. W. Atterbury, Effingham B. Morris, and Jay Cooke have consented to act as voting trustees. The voting trust will be for a period of 10 years and will vest in the voting trustee the entire voting power in respect of the stock deposited thereunder. Voting-trust certificates will be delivered in respect of all stock purchased pursuant to the present offering.

Reference is made to the accompanying circular of the Pennroad Corporation for further and full details of the offer.

THE PENNSYLVANIA RAILROAD CO.,
By W. W. ATTERBURY, *President*.

THE PENNROAD CORPORATION,
Wilmington, Del., April 24, 1929.

To the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.:

The Pennroad Corporation hereby offers to the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., including employees now subscribing to its stock, the opportunity to purchase, at \$15 per share, voting trust certificates for 5,800,000 shares of common stock of the corporation, without par value. The detailed terms of the offering are set out below.

The corporation reserves the right to sell to others, at such times and at such prices as the board of directors may determine, any of such stock not purchased by stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., or their assigns, and to sell the stock purchased pursuant to said offering irrespective of the aggregate amount thus sold.

The certificate of incorporation provides for an authorized issue of 10,000,000 shares of common stock without par value, of which, as above stated, 5,800,000 are now being offered. The balance is reserved for future issue, including shares reserved against options which have been granted, in connection with the organization of the corporation, to purchase additional common stock of the corporation on or before July 1, 1932, as follows: 125,000 shares at \$16 per share, 125,000 shares at \$17 per share, 125,000 shares at \$18 per share, and 125,000 shares at \$19 per share. No officers or directors of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. participate in such options.

Holder of common stock will have the right to subscribe pro rata to future additional issues of common stock sold for cash, except stock issued upon exercise of options or option warrants as more fully set out in the certificate of incorporation, copies of which may be obtained from the corporation on request. The common stock has no other preemptive right, except as may be granted by the board of directors, in respect of any particular issue of stock or securities.

Of the proceeds of the common stock to be issued as herein provided, \$10 per share is to be capital and the remainder paid-in surplus not available for dividends on the common stock.

The first board of directors of the corporation consists of W. W. Atterbury, Effingham B. Morris, Charles E. Ingersoll, Levi L. Rue, Jay Cooke, R. B. Mellon, and A. J. County, all of whom are members of the board of directors of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., and Henry H. Lee, the president of the corporation.

TERMS OF OFFERING

Stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. are hereby offered the privilege of purchasing at \$15 per share, upon the terms and conditions herein-after stated, on or before June 14, 1929, a number of shares of the common stock of the corporation equal to one half of the number of shares of stock of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., registered in their respective names on its books at the close of business on May 10, 1929.

Full share and fractional warrants, specifying the amount of stock which may be purchased, will be issued by the corporation and mailed to each stockholder. These warrants will be mailed as soon as possible after May 10, 1929, to the addresses for dividends recorded on the books of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., unless other instructions are received prior to that date.

In order to purchase stock the purchase form on the back of the warrant should be signed by the stockholders, but holders of fractional warrants desiring to purchase stock must present such warrants in amounts calling in the aggregate for one or more full shares, as no payments will be accepted for a fraction of a share. Fractional warrants desired by stockholders to complete full shares or fractional warrants which the stockholders desire to dispose of must be bought or sold in the market, as such fractions will not be sold or purchased by the corporation. The corporation will, however, on request, endeavor to aid stockholders to purchase or sell fractional warrants.

Payment for stock purchased must be made in full at the time of surrender of the warrants on or before June 14, 1929.

Checks or drafts should be drawn in favor of the Pennroad Corporation for the exact amount of the payment required.

Unless the warrants, accompanied by payment in full for the stock purchased, are returned to one of the offices named below on or before June 14, 1929, the right to purchase will be void and the warrants of no value.

For the convenience of stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., payment will be accepted by the corporation at any of the following offices: Room 169 Broad Street Station, Philadelphia, Pa.; no. 380 Seventh Avenue, New York City, N.Y.; Wilmington Trust Co., Wilmington, Del.; Midland Bank, Ltd., London, England.

The purchase privilege may be sold and transferred by assignment of the full share warrant, or by delivery of the fractional warrant in bearer form. On the back of the full-share warrant will be found an assignment to be filled in and signed by the registered holder and witnessed, if it is desired to transfer or dispose of the purchase right. Signatures to assignment of stockholders must be satisfactorily guaranteed.

If fractional warrants representing in the aggregate the right to purchase one full share are surrendered at any of the above-named offices before June 14, 1929, a full-share warrant for one share will be issued in exchange.

Stockholders who may wish to purchase a portion of the stock covered by a warrant and dispose of the balance, or who may wish to dispose of a portion to one person and the balance to another, should return their warrants before June 14, 1929, to one of the offices named herein to be exchanged for other warrants, specifying the number of warrants desired in exchange and the number of shares to be covered by such warrants.

No stockholder shall be entitled to purchase any stock under this offer unless the terms of purchase are fully complied with and payments made as herein specified, and no purchase or assignment of the right to purchase will be recognized unless made on the forms furnished by the corporation.

In furtherance of the purposes of the corporation, all its common stock is being placed in a voting trust, remaining in effect for 10 years, under which Messrs. W. W. Atterbury, Effingham B. Morris, and Jay Cooke have consented to act as voting trustees.

Voting trust certificates representing common stock of the corporation will be delivered in respect of all stock purchased pursuant to this offering. Such voting trust certificates will be sent to the purchasers thereof by registered mail as soon as possible after June 14, 1929. All references to stock herein shall be deemed to mean and to include voting trust certificates therefor.

All communications in relation to the foregoing should be addressed to the Pennroad Corporation, room 169, Broad Street Station, Philadelphia, Pa.

THE PENNROAD CORPORATION,
By HENRY H. LEE, *President*.

FOREIGN STOCKHOLDERS

Warrants for stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. residing in Great Britain or on the Continent of Europe will be sent to the recorded addresses for dividends as promptly as possible. The warrants, accompanied by payment in full of the purchase price, may be sent to the Midland Bank, Ltd., Poultry, London, E.C. 2, provided they are received by that bank on or before June 14, 1929. Payment of such purchase price may be made in sterling by check drawn to the order of the Midland Bank, Ltd., at the rate of 49½ pence sterling for each dollar.

Mr. KAHN. My attention is called to the fact that I said "when the stock was offered to the public." It was not offered to the public. It was offered to the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad.

Mr. PECORA. It was offered to that section of the public that constitutes the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad, was it not?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Now, is it fair to say, then, from your answer that the Pennroad Corporation was organized in April 1929 at the instance of the Pennsylvania Railroad?

Mr. KAHN. At the instance of the Pennsylvania Railroad; yes.

Mr. PECORA. And was your firm the bankers of the Pennsylvania at that time?

Mr. KAHN. We were.

Mr. PECORA. And had been for a great many years prior thereto?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Now, you said in the course of your testimony day before yesterday that railroad corporations for which you do the financing are also advised by your firm on financial matters.

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And on no other matters specifically?

Mr. KAHN. Generally speaking, I should say on no other matters, except if they choose of their own accord to ask our opinion on another matter. But while I have more than once been asked about matters of railroad strategy, I have no very high opinion as to the value of my own advice on railroad strategy or on running any other business than my own. I know my own business, but I do not know railroad strategy or any other business.

Mr. PECORA. Well, what are the instances or occasions in which railroad corporations seek advice on financial matters from their bankers?

Mr. KAHN. Constantly, Mr. Pecora, when they feel that a transaction of a certain magnitude is impending. They would particularly seek advice on two subjects. What kind of a security is the best to sell under the prevailing circumstances? What should be in fairness to the railroad and in fairness to the salability of the bond—what should be the provisions of the mortgage or the indenture or the trust deed? And above all things, what is the best time for making the sale? Shall we hurry? Is this a good time? Or had we better wait? Had we better finance this thing temporarily through short term loans from the banks, or had we better come out at once? In other words, to the extent that our advice as bankers, as observers of the financial trend is of any use, to the extent that our experience in drawing mortgages—or rather, we do not draw them ourselves, but in judging of the provisions which ought to go into mortgages

is of any use, to the extent that we know what the public likes and does not like, what maturity, what kind of bond, they come to us.

Mr. PECORA. How frequently does the average railroad require advice or service of that kind from its banker? It certainly does not require it every day or every week or every month or every year?

Mr. KAHN. Oh, certainly, I should say more nearly every couple of weeks than every year, because they do not necessarily wait until the emergency is upon them. The man in their organization, in the railroad organization, or in the industrial organization, who is particularly charged with looking after its financial affairs, wants to be intelligently advised by people in whom he has confidence. Matters of that nature may come up at any time in his board of directors or in the business meetings. It is perfectly natural that he should say, "I want the best advice that I can get and I want to get it constantly. Things may change. I may be a week too late, but no harm if I am a week too early. But there will be a great deal of harm if I am a week too late."

Mr. PECORA. In the light of your extensive experience as a banker for railroad corporations, how frequently does the average railroad corporation, would you say, bring out issues through its bankers?

Mr. KAHN. I can give you a schedule, Mr. Pecora, which probably would be more useful than a mere guess. It depends upon the times. At the present, and ever since 1929, I am sorry to say, that they have starved their bankers completely, they have brought out practically nothing. It depends upon—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). Of course they themselves have been starved.

Mr. KAHN. Yes; they themselves have been starved. It depends upon how active they are, and how active they are depends upon their judgment of prevailing conditions. It depends upon how well they keep up their property. It depends upon their plans, their ambitions; and it is very difficult to give you an accurate answer. But I could easily get up a statement showing how many issues have been made, in the course of the last 10 years if you like, by the railroads whose regular financial advisers we are.

Mr. PECORA. Would you say that the average railroad company whose financial advisers you are—and of course when I say "you" I mean your firm—brings out as many as one issue a year?

Mr. KAHN. I should think at an average that would be true, or more. You have a schedule, I believe, which shows what transactions were made with railroads; and that, I believe, will show you how many transactions were made over the last 5 years.

Mr. PECORA. Now, do you know a corporation called the Pennsylvania Co.?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Was that a subsidiary or affiliate of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. KAHN. I do not know whether affiliate is the correct term or not. What is the correct term, Mr. de Gersdorff?

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. I would say it is a subsidiary. The Pennsylvania Railroad Co. owns all of its stock, I believe.

Mr. KAHN. I am told that the correct legal term is subsidiary.

MR. DE GERSDORFF. Mr. Pecora knows whether that is the correct term or not. The Pennsylvania Railroad Co. owns all of the stock of the Pennsylvania Co.

MR. PECORA. I am a neophyte, Mr. de Gersdorff.

MR. DE GERSDORFF. Maybe so.

MR. PECORA. When was the Pennsylvania Co. organized, Mr. Kahn?

MR. KAHN. Oh, it was organized years ago, and I could not tell you the exact time.

MR. PECORA. What was the purpose of its incorporation?

MR. KAHN. I was told only recently, but again my repetition of what is being said and what I understand to be the case is in no way binding upon the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. or the Pennsylvania Co.—but to rehearse, as I have had occasion recently to go over the growth of the Pennsylvania system, I will say that I was told some years ago it became manifest that for the Pennsylvania Railroad to become a cohesive and effective system it was necessary for it to take in certain other properties.

THE CHAIRMAN. Was the Pennsylvania Co. a holding company?

MR. KAHN. Yes, Senator Fletcher.

MR. PECORA. Go ahead with your answer, Mr. Kahn.

MR. KAHN. On April 7, 1870, the Pennsylvania Co. was formed. And it was, as I understood it, a very effective instrument for the purpose of drawing the Pennsylvania system together into the powerful and far-flung system which it now is.

MR. PECORA. And that company was functioning in April of 1929, when the Pennroad Corporation was formed, was it not?

MR. KAHN. Yes, sir.

MR. PECORA. What was the special purpose of the formation or incorporation of the Pennroad Corporation in 1929?

MR. KAHN. The circular sets it forth fairly fully.

MR. PECORA. Well, the circular sets it forth in this language, in part, and I am reading from the circular, a copy of which you have handed to me, and which is entitled or captioned [reading]:

PENNSYLVANIA RAILROAD CO.,
Philadelphia, Pa., April 24, 1929.

And it is addressed to the stockholders and is as follows:

Your directors have given earnest consideration to recent developments in the field of transportation, and have reached the conclusion that it will be of material advantage to this company and its stockholders for the stockholders to unite in establishing a corporation so organized that it may make investments and take advantage of opportunities on a much broader basis than is possible under the limited powers of a railroad company.

Were you a director of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., Mr. Kahn?

MR. KAHN. No.

MR. PECORA. Were any of your partners a director of that company?

MR. KAHN. Never.

MR. PECORA. Well, your firm were the financial advisers and bankers of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

MR. KAHN. Yes.

MR. PECORA. And was its opinion sought by the directors of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. on the subject of organizing a new company, which subsequently was organized and called the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir; it formed the subject of many conversations, of many discussions.

Mr. PECORA. Now, the statement of this circular, which is signed by W. W. Atterbury, president of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., and which I have just read, is that the directors of that railroad company reached the conclusion that it would be of material advantage "to this company and its stockholders to unite in establishing a corporation so organized that it may make investments and take advantage of opportunities on a much broader basis than is possible under the limited powers of a railroad company." What was the material advantage that was sought to be served by the incorporation of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. KAHN. As a separate company?

Mr. PECORA. Whatever it was.

Mr. KAHN. Well, whatever it was is a matter of railroad strategy on which my opinion isn't of much value, except, as I have stated before, that they were apprehensive that their territory was being threatened by other corporations, who found it perhaps a little easier to act than the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., having no large combined stockholders such as some other railroads have, could have acted. They felt very strongly that at that time, when everybody thought whatever he bought was going to be worth more tomorrow and was certainly worth buying, that they should not permit invading forces to come in and buy up properties that they believed to be of strategic need for their own purposes and the purpose of serving their great system for the benefit of their 100,000 or more stockholders.

Mr. PECORA. Which were those invading forces that they had in mind?

Mr. KAHN. All the forces in the territory. Primarily I should say the Alleghany.

Mr. PECORA. Do you mean the Alleghany Corporation?

Mr. KAHN. Primarily the Alleghany Corporation. But there were others. The Baltimore & Ohio went in and bought certain things. The Erie Railroad went in and bought certain things. And they were apprehensive that certain properties which they believed essential to them would be snatched away from them. An additional reason why the Pennroad Corporation was formed rather than have the Pennsylvania Co. act, was that we urgently advised our Pennsylvania Railroad friends that when they came to raise that money which they needed for their acquisitions, that not one dollar of fixed charges should be created. We stated that we did not believe that for this purpose they should create fixed charges, or that any subsidiary of theirs should create fixed charges. We told them that we did not then believe that they should create a preferred-stock charge. We told them: We believe you should go to your own stockholders and tell them frankly what the facts are, what you propose, what is being done, and say to them: Now, here will be formed a separate company, which will be owned by you as stockholders. If you choose to take any stock, take it. If you do not choose to take any stock, why, we will have to try to find some other means of raising the money.

But we urged as strongly as we could on them that there should be no fixed charges, no preferred stock. We also urged upon them

that they should pay no underwriting fee. It is very much against our general habit to make such a recommendation, because we generally believe that if you issue a very large amount of new stock it must be underwritten for the protection of the issue, otherwise it is a standing invitation for bear raids, a standing invitation for short selling, or even for legitimate selling by persons who think they better get out, that there is a lot of stock coming on the market.

But in this case we told them: No fixed charge, no preferred stock, no underwriting. And we also stated: Usually we would not give you the latter advice, but we do give you that advice now—and that was in April of 1929—and in our opinion you can and you ought to take the risk of disposing of that security to your stockholders without having it underwritten. We can not take the responsibility of advising you to incur a heavy charge for underwriting when we are convinced that your issue will succeed without an underwriting. It was in April of 1929 and we felt convinced that they could go ahead along that line.

The CHAIRMAN. The primary purpose was to raise more capital, wasn't it?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; to raise more capital and to raise it without incurring either an underwriting expense or a fixed charge.

The CHAIRMAN. I understand. But what amount of capital did they contemplate raising at that time?

Mr. KAHN. They offered in round figures 6,000,000 shares of stock, or to be exact, 5,800,000 shares of stock at \$15 a share, which would be, roughly speaking, \$85,000,000, or to be more nearly correct, I would say \$87,000,000.

Senator TOWNSEND. That stock was sold and the money was raised for an express purpose, was it not?

Mr. KAHN. The stock was sold for purposes some of which they had definitely in mind at that time, and some of which they believed would arise in the early future and for which they wanted to be prepared.

The CHAIRMAN. You say they had how many stockholders?

Mr. KAHN. They had over 100,000 stockholders.

The CHAIRMAN. And the stock of the Pennroad Corporation was to be offered first to their stockholders?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. To the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Senator TOWNSEND. Do you know what percent of the stock the stockholders took up themselves?

Mr. KAHN. About 97 percent.

Senator TOWNSEND. Ninety-seven percent of this stock was sold to the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. I want to offer for the record and ask to have spread on the record a copy of the circular which the witness has produced.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted and made a part of the record. I believe this is another copy of the paper which Mr. Pecora already had and perhaps had offered.

Mr. PECORA. Wasn't the Pennsylvania Co., as distinguished from the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., empowered to function in the way

that it was proposed to have this new corporation, subsequently called the Pennroad Corporation, function?

Mr. KAHN. It was; but that would have required the issuance—well, my friend sitting here at my side asks me, “How do you know?” Well, I think I know or I wouldn’t take an oath to it. I believe that the Pennsylvania Co. could have functioned for that purpose, but it would have made heavy inroads upon the capital structure of the Pennsylvania Co., and would have probably necessitated the Pennsylvania Railroad giving up a part of its stock control of the Pennsylvania Co., which it did not want to do. It wanted to keep the Pennsylvania Co. as a separate unit, all the stock of which it owned. It did not want any part of the stock offered around in the market. It wanted to continue to own it.

Mr. PECORA. The Pennsylvania Co. could have, under proper authority, increased its capital stock for the purpose of raising additional capital that was deemed to be necessary in order to carry out the purposes which the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. then had in mind, couldn’t it?

Mr. KAHN. Yes. But it could only have sold that capital stock in the market. Otherwise where should they have got the \$87,000,000 which they needed?

Mr. PECORA. Well, where did the Pennroad Corporation get it?

Mr. KAHN. From the Pennsylvania Railroad stockholders in exchange for the offer of its own stock. Now, the Pennsylvania Railroad, as I understood, was not willing that the Pennsylvania Co.’s stock should get out of its possession. It was perfectly willing that the stock of the Pennroad Corporation should be owned widely, but it wanted to keep permanently, as I understood it, the control and not merely the control but the actual ownership of the Pennsylvania Co., which had been formed nearly 50 years ago and which had come to be looked upon as an integral part of the railroad company.

Mr. PECORA. You mentioned before the Alleghany Corporation, which as I recall was organized in January or February of 1929.

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir; I think so.

Mr. PECORA. Is it fair to say that the Pennroad Corporation was organized by the Pennsylvania Railroad interest in order to combat the Alleghany Corporation?

Mr. KAHN. You are asking me to pass upon the motives of the Pennsylvania Railroad.

Mr. PECORA. Well, I assumed that you know something of its motives in view of the fact that you sat around the council table of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. in its deliberations that resulted in a decision to organize the Pennroad Corporation.

Mr. KAHN. Well, the motives, as I understood them, were of a general character. They did not envisage merely the Alleghany Corporation. They envisaged what they believed, rightly or wrongly, a menace to the integrity and the effectiveness and the necessary expansion of the whole Pennsylvania Railroad system.

Mr. PECORA. How was the integrity of the Pennsylvania Railroad system threatened or menaced at that time, and by what interests?

Mr. KAHN. Well, perhaps the best answer to that is to show you a list of some of the securities which the Pennroad Corporation bought, a great majority of them being properties which they believed to be of essential value to the Pennsylvania Railroad system.

Senator TOWNSEND. Have you such a list of stocks or properties that the Pennroad Corporation purchased?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Senator TOWNSEND. May I see it?

Mr. KAHN. Here it is.

Senator TOWNSEND. Were these stocks or bonds purchased on the stock exchange?

Mr. STEWART. They were purchased at various places, some on the stock exchange and some direct.

Senator TOWNSEND. Through private sale?

Mr. STEWART. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, if I understand you correctly, one of the purposes of organizing and incorporating the Pennroad Corporation was to protect the integrity of the Pennsylvania Railroad system from aggression by other and combating railroad interests.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Can you tell the committee the railroad lines that the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. sought to acquire, or to acquire a substantial interest in, through the medium of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. KAHN. If Senator Townsend will let me have that paper back for a minute. I am not sure that you have a copy of this, Mr. Pecora. I can tell you some of the principal acquisitions which they made and which at that time they considered of essential value to them. The first which they had in mind and which the Pennroad Corporation bought, not the Pennsylvania Railroad, of course, was the Detroit, Toledo & Ironton Railroad stock, 245,327 shares, which I believe, if my memory serves me right, were owned by Mr. Henry Ford, at a total cost of \$23,917,017.

Senator TOWNSEND. Owned by whom?

Mr. KAHN. By Mr. Henry Ford.

Mr. PECORA. Go ahead.

Mr. KAHN. They then acquired 99 percent of the Canton Co. of Baltimore common stock.

Mr. PECORA. Ninety-nine percent of the common stock of what company?

Mr. KAHN. Of the C-a-n-t-o-n Co. of Baltimore common stock, which was a great and a very valuable terminal company in Baltimore and its neighborhood. For that they paid \$13,432,817.

Senator TOWNSEND. Through whom did they purchase that stock?

Mr. KAHN. That is the one concern, the one company which they bought, not from us but through us. That is, we brought the opportunity, my firm brought the opportunity to acquire that property to their attention. And that is the only thing which they did buy through my firm except minor or trifling things.

Senator TOWNSEND. Who was the owner of the Canton Co.?

Mr. KAHN. The principal owner, as far as I can recall, was Mr. Colgate. You have his initials. It was an old family holding, mainly in the hands of Baltimore people. There were other railroads that wanted it. We had the opportunity of getting the first chance of offering it to the Pennroad Corporation, and they were very glad to buy it, and they are very glad to have it now.

Senator TOWNSEND. You purchased it and in turn turned it over to the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. KAHN. Oh, no. They purchased it direct.

Senator TOWNSEND. Through your firm?

Mr. KAHN. They purchased it direct but purchased it through our good offices. We acted as brokers in making the purchase.

Mr. PECORA. Go ahead.

Mr. KAHN. Then the Pennroad Corporation bought—and in saying “then” I am merely mentioning the large purchases as they come along—223,230 shares of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railroad Co. common stock, for which they paid \$37,910,145. They bought that direct from the owner.

Senator TOWNSEND. And who was the owner?

Mr. KAHN. Taplin.

Mr. PECORA. Was that Frank E. Taplin?

Mr. KAHN. I do not recall his initials. I suppose that is the gentleman.

Senator TOWNSEND. It was purchased from Mr. Taplin?

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. Yes; and associates of theirs.

Mr. PECORA. Go ahead, Mr. Kahn, and complete your answer.

Mr. KAHN. Then they bought—and when I say “then”, of course, I do not mean the precise order in which they made the purchases but am merely going down the list in a general way—then they bought simultaneously with having purchased the Detroit, Toledo & Ironton common stock, \$2,918,000 of Detroit, Toledo & Ironton first mortgage bonds, for which they paid \$2,693,171; and they bought \$10,626,000 of Detroit, Toledo & Ironton Railroad Co. first and refunding mortgage 5-percent bonds, for which they paid \$9,983,820. And they bought a very small issue of equipment notes and notes secured by collateral, for which they paid a few hundred thousand dollars.

Senator TOWNSEND. Have you any knowledge of what the stocks were worth on the stock exchange that were purchased from Mr. Taplin at the time when they were purchased?

Mr. KAHN. I do not know. They were very closely held. I do not know the stock-exchange quotations on them.

Senator TOWNSEND. Were they listed?

Mr. KAHN. I believe they were listed. Weren't they? [Inquiring of an associate.] Yes; they were listed.

Mr. PECORA. This purchase from Taplin was at the rate of \$170 a share, wasn't it.

Mr. KAHN. Well, this statement would show it.

Mr. PECORA. Does that appear in that statement, that the purchase from Taplin was at the rate of \$170 per share?

Mr. KAHN. I am trying to figure it out. That must be about right. As I stated before—and my associate wonders if I made that answer—that was bought direct, and we had nothing to do with it.

Mr. PECORA. That transaction was made in October of 1929, wasn't it, or, to be more specific, on October 16, 1929, or thereabouts.

Mr. KAHN. I do not really know, except as the records may show.

The CHAIRMAN. Was it all purchased at one time?

Mr. KAHN. They are all matters which the Pennroad Corporation did, and we have no record, except to the extent that anything that was purchased through us we would know about, and this was not purchased through us.

Mr. PECORA. Is it your recollection that the public market quotations for the stock of this Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railroad Co. in the month of September 1929 ran from a low of 135 to a high of 142 $\frac{3}{8}$, and that in the month of October of that year the range was from a low of 110 to a high of 145 $\frac{1}{2}$?

Mr. KAHN. I have no recollection, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. Wasn't your advice as the banker of the railroad company sought with regard to this particular transaction with Mr. Taplin?

Mr. KAHN. Our advice would not be sought in matters involving railroad strategy and the decision of the officers as to what they wanted to do. Our advice would be sought on financial matters.

Mr. PECORA. Wasn't this a financial transaction, this purchase of two hundred and twenty-two thousand nine hundred and odd shares of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railroad Co. from Mr. Taplin?

Mr. KAHN. No; because they had the money on hand. They did not need our services.

Senator TOWNSEND. Weren't they obliged to borrow some money in connection with all of these purchases?

Mr. KAHN. They had \$87,000,000 on hand from their first issue of stock.

Senator TOWNSEND. And these purchases amount to about what?

Mr. PECORA. This Taplin transaction amounted to \$37,898,100.

Mr. KAHN. Yes; I realize that.

Mr. PECORA. Did you as the banker for the railroad company have any voice at all in the determination of the question of what price the Pennroad Corporation should pay for these railroad stocks?

Mr. KAHN. We were not consulted and we should have been very much embarrassed if we had been consulted, because to the extent—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). Well, was your advice that they sought as their banker limited only to such matters as to what kind of security to issue at a given time?

Mr. KAHN. Oh, no. In this case I think the most valuable piece of advice we ever gave almost was that they should—shall I go on with my answer?

Mr. PECORA. Yes; go ahead.

Mr. KAHN. That almost the most valuable piece of advice we ever gave them was that we urged upon them to provide for these acquisitions, as to the value of which, as to the permanent desirability of which we could not possibly form a judgment of our own—we urged upon them not to create a fixed charge, not to create any preferred stock, not to create anything which could cause them embarrassment, not to pay an underwriting commission, but to go to their own stockholders and get the money. And I say now that if we ever gave good advice that was good advice.

The CHAIRMAN. What did they sell the stock at; do you know?

Mr. KAHN. \$15 a share, to their own stockholders; \$15 a share net. They did not pay a dollar commission to anybody.

The CHAIRMAN. Do you know what it was at that time?

Mr. KAHN. I knew what it was when I left New York—about 3 $\frac{1}{2}$ or 3 $\frac{3}{4}$; but it of course had been very much higher.

Senator TOWNSEND. It had been lower, too, had it not?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; it had been lower.

The CHAIRMAN. How high did it go; do you remember?

Mr. KAHN. It went close to 30. It may even have touched 30; I do not know; but I know it went close to 30.

Mr. PECORA. What other large blocks of stock of other railroad companies were purchased by the Pennroad Corporation in pursuance of this plan to protect the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. from aggression on the part of competing lines?

Mr. KAHN. Mr. Pecora, the other large blocks which they bought were Boston & Maine Railroad—I will give to you or to the reporter a list, so that I will not have to take your time to read them all. They bought a large block of Boston & Maine Railroad; they bought a large block of New York, New Haven & Hartford Railroad common and a small block of preferred; they bought 402,119 shares of Seaboard Air Line Railway common stock.

Mr. PECORA. Have you a printed pamphlet or list of its acquisitions?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Will you kindly produce it for the record?

(The witness handed a paper to Mr. Pecora.)

I offer it in evidence and ask that it be spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. It may be received and spread on the record.

(The pamphlet referred to, entitled "The Pennroad Corporation, Statement for Year Ended December 31, 1932," was received in evidence, marked "Committee's Exhibit No. 20", see p. 1268.)

Mr. PECORA. Was the New York, New Haven & Hartford Railroad Co. a line competing with the Pennsylvania Railroad?

Mr. KAHN. I hesitate to speak on their behalf, because, of course, they are infinitely more competent to answer than I am; but they believed that in the general shuffling in the entire trunk line situation which was then under consideration and which was being prepared for—they believed that a substantial holding on their part, if not an important holding of the leading New England lines, was of great importance to them from the traffic point of view.

Mr. PECORA. The Pennsylvania Railroad did not have any line operating through New England, did it?

Mr. KAHN. Not direct; no.

Mr. PECORA. Did it consider the Boston & Maine Railroad as a competing line?

Mr. KAHN. The Boston & Maine Railroad, I assume, became of importance when they reached the conclusion that the New Haven was of importance; but all these questions you are asking of a rather ignorant man.

The CHAIRMAN. Were those purchases made before October 1929, do you think, or most of them?

Mr. KAHN. The record we have does not show it, Senator.

The CHAIRMAN. I did not know whether you knew that they bought these stocks before the collapse in October.

Mr. KAHN. Our record does not show; but no doubt they bought a number of them, a large proportion of them, before the collapse. I make this deduction because after the first transaction by which they raised \$87,000,000 a second transaction was undertaken to raise additional money; so they must have needed additional money.

Mr. PECORA. In your answer a few moments back you made some reference to a shuffle. What was the shuffle that you had reference to?

Mr. KAHN. Again I speak as an outsider and I speak from hearsay and I speak with no competence. The Alleghany people, the Pennsylvania Railroad people, the New York Central people, the Erie people, the Baltimore & Ohio people can tell you of that without any if's or but's. I can only speak with great reservations and subject to correction. But at that time, as you will recall, the question was a very active one, and, in my opinion, a very immediate one, as to how many trunkline systems there should be. The Interstate Commerce Commission had provided for four. The systems as set up originally by the Interstate Commerce Commission were not in all respects satisfactory to the great railroads concerned, and there ensued something like a—

Mr. PECORA. A scramble?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; which I call a shuffle, but "scramble" is a much better word—a scramble to put themselves in a position where possession was nine points of the law, and they tried, each one of them, that kind of competition which I have referred to as unwise and detrimental competition. They tried to put themselves in a position where, if anything was determined unsatisfactory to them, they could as nearly as possible bedevil it, or they could say, "We own that. You can't take that away from us; we have already bought it." And it was, as you rightly term it, a scramble preparatory to a decision which was going to be made ultimately by the Interstate Commerce Commission.

The CHAIRMAN. In reference to possible mergers?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; in reference to possible more or less enforced mergers.

Mr. PECORA. Or groupings of railroad lines in a system?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. The Interstate Commerce Commission, as you probably know, has no jurisdiction or control over holding companies?

Mr. KAHN. No.

Mr. PECORA. Was the Pennroad Corporation organized as a holding company in order to enable the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. to avoid the jurisdiction of the Interstate Commerce Commission?

Mr. KAHN. That I cannot possibly answer except to the extent that General Atterbury's circular may throw light upon the subject.

Mr. PECORA. General Atterbury's circular on that point merely says that—

Your directors have given earnest consideration to recent developments in the field of transportation and have reached the conclusion that it will be of material advantage to this company and its stockholders for the stockholders to unite in establishing a corporation so organized that it may make investments and take advantage of opportunities on a much broader basis than is possible under the limited powers of a railroad company.

Would you say that is a polite way of saying, "We want to do something that the Interstate Commerce Commission can't tell us not to do"?

Mr. KAHN. Nothing is more difficult than for a man to say what thoughts were behind other people at the time they committed an act, praiseworthy or otherwise. I may possibly help in answering your question if I give you a statement here which says for what purpose the Pennroad Corporation was incorporated. I do not know whether it answers your question, but if it is any help to you I offer it to you.

Mr. PECORA. What are you reading from—from the Splawn financial report?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. If you want to read a portion of that which has caught your eye, I think it would be enlightening.

Mr. KAHN. This particular portion?

Mr. PECORA. The portion that you were about to call my attention to.

Mr. KAHN. It starts—

The Pennroad Corporation was incorporated on April 24, 1929, under the laws of the State of Delaware, to have perpetual existence and with powers to engage in business as follows: First, to acquire without restriction all kinds of securities issued by corporations or other agencies engaged in transportation of persons or property on land or water or by air, or in any other business, to exercise all rights of such ownership, to aid by loan, subsidy, guarantee, or otherwise, those issuing such securities, and to underwrite or subscribe for such securities with a view to investment or for resale—

Mr. PECORA. I do not think you need to read all that follows after that, because it is largely repetitious matter.

Now, Mr. Kahn, you have already said that at its inception the Pennroad Corporation issued and sold 5,800,000 shares of common stock.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. That was stock of no par value, was it not?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And that stock was offered first to stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. at \$15 a share?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. In the ratio of 1 share of Pennroad Corporation stock for every 2 shares of Pennsylvania Railroad Co.'s stock?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. As a matter of fact, Mr. Kahn, did the Pennroad Corporation issue to the subscribers certificates of stock, or were they voting trust certificates?

Mr. KAHN. A voting trust certificate was created.

Mr. PECORA. And under those voting-trust certificates the voting power was placed in a board of three trustees?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Who were those three trustees at the outset?

Mr. KAHN. I have got them here—Gen. W. W. Atterbury, Mr. Effingham B. Morris, and Mr. Jay Cooke.

Mr. PECORA. They were, of course, trustees that were selected with an eye to the interests of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., were they not?

Mr. KAHN. Is there not a provision of law, Mr. Counsellor, that people must be presumed to know the natural consequences of their actions?

Mr. PECORA. There is such a principle of equity; yes.

Mr. KAHN. Is not that my best answer, that in selecting these people—

Mr. PECORA. That is giving us an answer in legal circumlocution. You are not very familiar with legal terms, so far as I have been able to understand your testimony heretofore; so I suggest that perhaps you might give us an answer in your own language and let legal verbiage alone.

Mr. KAHN. After this rather unfortunate attempt to act as a lawyer or to use legal parlance, I will read to you, with your permission, exactly what General Atterbury says on that subject in a circular addressed to the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad. He says:

Accordingly, in furtherance of the purpose for which the corporation has been organized, and in order to insure continuity of management, all of the stock issued will be placed in a voting trust under which Messrs. W. W. Atterbury, Effingham B. Morris, and Jay Cooke have consented to act as voting trustees.

That seems to set forth very plainly what was in their minds in taking the action they did.

Mr. PECORA. What rights did the purchasers of these voting trust certificates of the Pennroad Corporation have in the operation or management of the Pennroad Corporation? Did they have any at all?

Mr. KAHN. Having given their consent to the election of voting trustees, I presume that by that very act they conferred the rights of management, direct or indirect, upon those voting trustees.

Mr. PECORA. You say that the stockholders "having given their consent." As a matter of fact, did the stockholders give their consent to the establishment of this voting trust?

Mr. KAHN. Oh, yes. Otherwise they would not have bought the stock. The very fact that they bought the stock proved that they were in accord with the method of setting it up.

Mr. PECORA. You do not mean to say that they affirmatively gave their consent at the outset to the creation of this voting trust, do you?

Mr. KAHN. Affirmatively, no; by implication, yes.

Mr. PECORA. The implication flowing from the fact that they purchased the stock that was subject to this voting trust, more or less?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Now, as a matter of fact, the purchasers of these voting-trust certificates paid something like \$130,000,000 in the aggregate, did they not, for those certificates?

Mr. KAHN. They did; yes.

Mr. PECORA. And they bought them under circumstances, terms, and conditions which deprived them of any voice even in the election of officers or directors, did they not?

Mr. KAHN. It would seem so; yes.

Mr. PECORA. On principle do you approve of that method of financing a corporation?

Mr. KAHN. On principle, Mr. Pecora, I have the utmost faith in the working of public opinion. I have relatively little faith in supervision, and I do not generally approve any paternalistic attitude on the part of corporation managers or anybody else. I do think, speaking now as a principle, that when you ask people to go into a concern with you and you take their money, I do generally think as a principle that nothing ought to be done to interfere with the right to exercise their vote, and I also say that occasions may arise where the continuity of management is of such importance that for the time being, and with the knowledge of the people who put up their money, a voting trust is justifiable. When you get into a situation having a definite, well-defined purpose, requiring continuity of management,

it may be right to have a voting trust. Ordinarily speaking, I do not believe in depriving people of the right to have their say.

Mr. PECORA. Am I correct in my understanding that the directors and voting trustees of the Pennroad Corporation were not even required to be stockholders in order to qualify them?

Mr. KAHN. I could not tell you, but I should not be at all surprised if it were so. I do not know it.

Mr. PECORA. So this was a case where a corporation was set up under forms that enabled it to get over \$130,000,000 from the investing public for the purposes of the corporation, without giving to the investing public who contributed that large sum of money any voice whatsoever in the management or operation of the business of the company or in the selection of its officers?

Mr. KAHN (after conferring with associates). I am getting advice.

Mr. PECORA. As to how to answer that question?

Mr. KAHN. I am getting advice which I shall probably disregard.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is what he thinks of his mentors.

Mr. KAHN. My answer to your question, of course, is that I would like to point out that this was done in 1929; and I think anything that was done in 1929 should be judged by a different standard from that which prevailed before, which is prevailing now, and which I hope will always prevail after our experience. But the instances, the things for which 1929 and the spirit of 1929 were responsible are legion; and in the light of hindsight they are simply inexplicable.

Mr. PECORA. Would you go so far as to say, in the light of this hindsight, that such things should be made impossible by law, if necessary?

Mr. KAHN. Unless there is a really good, sound, legitimate, and generally useful reason why a certain transaction should be carried to its destined and logical end by a continuity of management—unless that is so I think all things of that kind ought to be eliminated. I think affiliates, investment trusts—by which common voting power is given to a small class of stock—are inventions of the devil and ought to be done away with.

Mr. PECORA. Those devils have come from around the vicinity of Wall Street, have they not?

Mr. KAHN. All over the country. They are not only created in Wall Street. I have got quite some painful experience of the same kind of thing that was done outside of Wall Street. But I do think, and I think it is one of the things which I venture the hope will come from the deliberations of your committee, that all these things will be eliminated and not be permitted to occur again, unless good reason can be shown to you why in specific instances the continuity of management should be secured.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, reference has been made in your examination this afternoon to the scramble that was engaged in by the Alleghany Corporation, and railroad interests which it represented or for which it acted, and the Pennroad Corporation, and the railroad interests for which it acted, to acquire an ownership interest through the purchase of stock in various railroad lines that might have been tributary to the main system.

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And reference has also been made to the fact that that scramble was induced more or less by desire to circumvent the decisions and the judgment of the Interstate Commerce Commission.

Mr. KAHN. Is not that perhaps putting it rather more strongly than I made it?

Mr. PECORA. Is it too strong a statement?

Mr. KAHN. I think it is too strong a statement.

Mr. PECORA. In view of the facts?

Mr. KAHN. I venture to think it is too strong a statement, because I said that possession is nine points of the law. But there is a tenth point; and the Interstate Commerce Commission is a pretty potent body, and so are the courts, and even if I have nine points of the law and the Interstate Commerce Commission and the courts of the country will not let me have the tenth point, my nine points do not do me much good.

Mr. PECORA. I did not know that I was using too strong a characterization. I doubt whether it is any stronger than your own term of "bedevilment", but perhaps it is. The fact is that the Interstate Commerce Commission prior to 1929, shortly prior to it had publicly indicated in a general fashion its opinion as to how the railroad systems of the country should be grouped, had it not?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And the Interstate Commerce Commission has no authority over a holding company, has it?

Mr. KAHN. I understand, no.

Mr. PECORA. You understand that the Alleghany Corporation is a holding company for certain railroad lines?

Mr. KAHN. I do; yes.

Mr. PECORA. And the Pennroad Corporation was organized in the form of a holding company to act for the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.'s interests?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. You have referred to a scramble participated in by those competing railroad systems to acquire a measure of control or influence, if you please, over tributary lines that might not be given to them or might be given to a competing system under the indicated groupings of the Interstate Commerce Commission?

Mr. KAHN. But may I say that as I understand it, or understood at the time, without being formally consulted, that the purpose was not merely a defensive or acquisitive one, perhaps. To what extent that was the purpose I am not competent to say. But the purpose was also very largely that of legitimate expansion. Getting systems that had not yet been allocated, for the expansion of the railroad concerned, was considered to be of great value. So it was not merely a scramble; it was not merely bedevilment; it was not merely acquisitiveness or defense. It was to a large extent—to what extent I cannot define—a purpose to acquire properties which were eminently desirable in the judgment of the officers for the purpose of expanding the system in desirable directions.

Mr. PECORA. Let us see if General Atterbury in his circular marked "Exhibit 19" in evidence does not very strongly suggest the implication of the question that you thought was phrased in language that was a bit too strong, where he said:

The directors of the Pennsylvania Railroad have reached the conclusion that it would be of material advantage to this company and its stockholders for the stockholders to unite in establishing a corporation so organized that it may make investments and take advantage of opportunities on a much broader basis than is possible under the limited powers of a railroad company.

Does he not disguise in those words that the purpose of the organization of the Pennroad Corporation was, among other things, to enable the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. to circumvent the position taken or announced by the Interstate Commerce Commission with regard to its groupings of railroad lines?

Mr. KAHN. Mr. Pecora, am I the man who can and should answer the question of what was the purpose behind another man's mental processes?

Mr. PECORA. The purpose of the incorporation is supposed to be set forth in this circular, is it not?

Mr. KAHN. But what this circular means is set forth in, I believe, very clear language, which I hesitate to further define or interpret. I think it says very plainly what it was meant to do. If in the opinion of yourself or of the legislature or your committee any such statement of purpose ought in future to be supplemented, that is a different chapter as to which in a general way I have expressed my opinion.

Unless there is good reason—I have known cases where there was a really good reason for a voting trust to be created, lest the property which depended for its welfare upon continuity of management should fall into evil hands; and I have known of my own knowledge of a case years ago when my firm believed, in pursuance of what we thought was our duty toward security holders, that there should be substituted a different management in place of the George Gould management of the Missouri Pacific Railroad, because we were afraid of what would happen to that property unless new management came in. We went to the stockholders and told them, just as General Atterbury says here, plainly why we believed that a new management, a new deal, was required, and we asked for their mandate to give us a sufficient length of stable management to protect the property, not in our hands, but in the hands of people whom they trusted. There was good reason for doing that, because if we had not done it, that property very likely might have gone back, and we did not believe it should go back, into the same hands from which it had been rescued.

In that way I can conceive of good reasons for doing that. I do not know whether public policy should or will permit a continuance of similar practices, but I can conceive of very good reasons, in a few instances, not in very many, why it should be done and why the public good is served by having it done. Under what restraints, under what restrictions, under what supervision, I am not now prepared to say. I believe I said before that I have much more faith in the power of public opinion than in the power of supervision.

The CHAIRMAN. These trustees were all quite large stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. KAHN. I have assumed so, Senator. I know so. I know that Jay Cooke was. In fact, I know all three gentlemen were; yes. I know they all were.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, was the advice or judgment of your firm as the bankers for the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. sought as to the form of security, the kind of security that the Pennroad Corporation should issue?

Mr. KAHN. As to the form of security; yes, no doubt.

Mr. PECORA. Then was it your judgment that voting-trust certificates, instead of common-stock certificates, should be issued?

Mr. KAHN. At that time very probably it was. I cannot say of my own knowledge. I do not know which member of my firm I placed that particular faith in. We are a family affair, and one speaks for all and all speak for one. I cannot say whether my particular advice was sought on that subject, but I have very little doubt that our firm, to the extent that its opinion was sought, approved that set-up.

Mr. PECORA. Was your personal approval given to that set-up?

Mr. KAHN. That I do not really recall. In fact, I recall no—no; it was not. I do not mean to say that it would not have been given. I am not throwing that on other people, but it so happened that at that time I was not in America.

Mr. PECORA. Now, these voting trust certificates of the Pennroad Corporation eventually became listed on public exchanges?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Which exchange?

Mr. KAHN. On the New York Curb and on the Philadelphia Stock Exchange.

Mr. PECORA. And they were purchased freely by the investing public who were not stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., weren't they, after they became listed?

Mr. KAHN. I do not know who bought them. I know they were purchased very freely.

Mr. PECORA. At least their sale was not listed or restricted merely to stockholders in the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. KAHN. No. The original offer was restricted, but anybody was free to sell.

Mr. PECORA. And to buy in the open market?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Now the purpose of this incorporation, that is, the Pennroad Co., was to serve the interests of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. and its stockholders, wasn't it?

Mr. KAHN. I would rather put it the other way around; to serve the purpose of the stockholders and the Pennroad, which was owned by those stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad.

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. KAHN. I know how much importance was attached by the Pennsylvania Railroad people and how frequently they emphasized the fact that they have no large stockholders; they cannot go to any one or half a dozen very large stockholders, as the New York Central can do, as the Alleghany people can do, as the Erie people can do, as the Delaware, Lackawanna & Western can do. They have got over a hundred thousand little people to protect, and they felt that responsibility very keenly, and very frequently in discussions with us referred to it.

Mr. PECORA. Now the purchasers of the stock or voting trust certificates of the Pennroad Co. who were not stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. were placed in the position of having their moneys used primarily for the benefit not of themselves but of the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., weren't they?

Mr. KAHN. Well, isn't that implied, without giving a yes or no answer as yet; but isn't that implied in the fact that with their eyes open they bought voting-trust certificates? They did not buy stock; they bought voting-trust certificates, which voting trust was in the name of three of the Pennsylvania officials.

Mr. PECORA. Well, it is the fact equally, isn't it, that every person who buys securities in the open market does so with his eyes open if he wants to have open eyes?

Mr. KAHN. That is correct; but here——

Mr. PECORA (interposing). You would not say that all transactions in which persons buy securities in the open or public market involve purchases by persons who have intelligent judgment?

Mr. KAHN. Not as yet. I hope that will be by and by. I hope they will be educated to it.

Mr. PECORA. So that when you say that these voting-trust certificates were bought with their eyes open you are using a phrase rather than stating a fact, aren't you?

Mr. KAHN. Not quite, Mr. Pecora, because here was plain warning—plain warning printed on the face of the certificates and printed on the curb quotation lists, "Pennroad stock V.T.C." Anyone who bought them had plain warning that he was buying, a warning which he could hardly disregard or overlook, that he was buying voting-trust certificates.

Mr. PECORA. Do you mean to say that the general body of the public that bought these certificates realized or knew, even at the time they bought them, that they were buying or making investments in a corporation under circumstances which deprived them of any voice whatsoever in the management, control, or operation of that corporation?

Mr. KAHN. Any even halfway careful man would know it; yes. It was made very plain.

Mr. PECORA. Do you really think, Mr. Kahn, that persons who bought these certificates, in the main, actually were aware of the fact that they were making their investment in a company that denied them any voice whatsoever in the management or operation of the company or even the selection of its officers?

Mr. KAHN. Not in 1929, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. And that is when these certificates were issued, in 1929?

Mr. KAHN. I believe so. But at that time they bought any quantity of so-called "investment-trust stocks" which deliberately deprived them of any kind of voting power.

Senator BARKLEY. Would it be a fair assumption that those who purchased these voting trust certificates on the curb were not so much interested in control, or having a voice in control of the company, as they were in getting a profit out of the purchases of that stock?

Mr. KAHN. That is quite true, Senator, quite true.

The CHAIRMAN. I think it would probably be best that we discontinue now and be in recess until 10 o'clock tomorrow morning.

(Accordingly, at 4:14 o'clock p.m. a recess was taken until 10 o'clock a.m. of the next day, Friday, June 30, 1933.)

EXHIBIT No. 18

QUESTION 16.—*Syndicate list (consolidated) Kuhn, Loeb & Co.*

	Issue								
	Missouri Pacific R.R. Co. 5's-1977	Pennsylvania, Ohio & Detroit R.R. 4½'s-1977	Illinois Central R.R. & Chicago, St. Louis & New Orleans R.R. 4½'s-1963	Union Pacific R.R. 4½'s-1967	North German Lloyd 6's-1947	Southern Pacific Co. Oregon Lines 4½'s-1977	Hudson Coal Co. 5's-1962	Baltimore & Ohio R.R. common stock	Paramount Famous Lasky Corporation 6's-1947
Cost price.....	Percent 98¾	Percent 93½	Percent 96	Percent 95¾	Percent 91½	Percent 99	Percent 96½	\$108.25	Percent 96½
Selling price.....	99	94	96¾	96½	92¾	99¾	97¾	107.50	97½
J. S. Alexander, former president National Bank of Commerce (deceased)	\$50,000	\$50,000		\$50,000		\$50,000	\$50,000	Shares 500	
Newcomb Carlton, president and director Western Union Telegraph Co.	25,000	25,000				25,000	25,000	250	
Cosmopolis Securities Corporation			100,000				100,000		
A. J. County, vice president in charge of finance and corporate relations and director the Pennsylvania R.R. Co.	50,000								
Henry W. De Forest, member of the executive committee and director Guaranty Trust Co., chairman of Board Southern Pacific R.R.	100,000	100,000		100,000			100,000	1,000	
G. H. Ecker, president and director, Metropolitan Life Insurance Co.				75,000				750	
C. W. Galloway, vice president in charge of operations and maintenance, Baltimore & Ohio R.R. Co.								500	
Hanstra Corporation								1,000	
Henry H. Lee, president, Pennroad Corporation	25,000								
Jas. Loeb & Co.	50,000	50,000		50,000		50,000	50,000	500	
L. F. Loree, president member of board of managers and chairman of executive committee, Delaware & Hudson Co.	50,000	50,000		50,000		50,000		500	
R. S. Lovett, former, Union Pacific R.R. (deceased)	50,000	50,000				50,000	50,000	500	
Chas. E. Mitchell, former chairman of the board National City Bank								2,000	
Chas. A. Peabody, former, Illinois Central (deceased)								1,000	
Samuel Rea, former president, Pennsylvania R.R. Co. (deceased)	50,000			50,000		50,000	50,000	500	
Percy A. Rockefeller, member of executive committee and director, New York Edison Co., Consolidated Gas Co.	250,000	250,000		150,000			150,000	2,500	

Mrs. A. G. Schiff (deceased)-----								2,000	
C. B. Seger, chairman of the executive committee and director, Union Pacific R.R. Co.-----		50,000				50,000	50,000	500	
Henry Tatnall, director Philadelphia, Baltimore & Washington Railway-----	50,000			50,000		50,000	50,000	500	
Guy E. Tripp, former, Westinghouse Electric (deceased)-----	50,000	50,000		50,000		50,000	50,000	500	
Paul M. Warburg (deceased)-----	100,000								
Paul M. Warburg, president (deceased)-----		100,000				100,000			
Jas. Paul Warburg, president and director of International Ac- ceptance Bank, Inc.-----				100,000				1,000	
Wellington Finance Corporation-----									1,000,000
Albert E. Wiggin, chairman of governing board the Chase Na- tional Bank-----	100,000	75,000		75,000		75,000	75,000	1,000	
W. H. Williams (deceased), formerly with Wabash R.R. Co.-----		50,000		50,000		50,000		500	
Sir Wm. Wiseman, firm of Kuhn, Loeb & Co.-----	100,000	100,000	50,000	50,000		75,000	50,000	750	100,000
Miscellaneous foreign banks and companies-----	1,150,000		225,000	450,000	1,550,000	600,000	600,000	52,750	575,000
Total-----	2,250,000	1,000,000	375,000	1,350,000	1,550,000	1,325,000	1,450,000	71,000	1,675,000

QUESTION 16.—*Syndicate list (consolidated) Kuhn, Loeb & Co.—Continued*

	Issue								
	Youngs- town Sheet & Tube Co. 5's-1978	Inland Steel Co. 4½'s-1978	Pennsyl- vania Co. 4¼'s-1963	U.S. Rub- ber Co. common stock	Mid Con- tinent Petroleum Corporation common stock	Westing- house Elec- tric Manu- facturing Co. com- mon stock	Southern Pacific Co. 4½'s-1969	Southern Pacific Co. 4½'s-1968	Missouri Pacific R.R. Co. 5½'s-1949
Cost price.....	Percent 99	Percent 93	Percent 97½	\$33.00	\$29.50	\$103.50	Percent 92½	Percent 98¼	Percent 96
Selling price.....	99¾	93¾	97¾	35.00	31.00	105.00	94	99	97½
J. S. Alexander, former president National Bank of Commerce (de- ceased).....	\$50,000	\$50,000	\$50,000	Shares	Shares 500	Shares 500	\$50,000	-----	\$50,000
Jas. C. Bennett, vice president of Westinghouse Electric & Manu- facturing Co.....	-----	-----	-----	2,500	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
Newcomb Carlton, president and director Western Union Tele- graph Co.....	50,000	50,000	50,000	500	500	500	50,000	-----	50,000
Cosmopolis Securities Corporation.....	100,000	100,000	-----	1,000	1,000	1,000	100,000	-----	100,000
Henry W. De Forest, member of the executive committee and di- rector Guaranty Trust Co., chairman of board—Southern Pacific R. R.....	100,000	100,000	100,000	1,500	1,000	1,000	-----	-----	-----
F. H. Ecker, president and director Metropolitan Life Insurance Co.....	-----	-----	-----	1,000	1,000	1,000	-----	-----	-----
Hanstra Corporation.....	-----	-----	-----	1,000	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
Mrs. A. Hellman—J. J. Hanauer for a/c of.....	-----	-----	-----	-----	1,500	-----	-----	-----	-----
Mrs. A. W. Kahn, wife of Otto Kahn.....	-----	-----	-----	2,500	2,000	-----	-----	-----	-----
Jas. Loeb & Co.....	50,000	50,000	50,000	500	500	500	50,000	-----	50,000
L. F. Loree, president, member of board of managers, and chairman of executive committee Delaware & Hudson Co.....	50,000	50,000	100,000	1,000	1,000	1,000	100,000	-----	100,000
R. S. Lovett, former Union Pacific R.R. (deceased).....	50,000	50,000	100,000	1,000	500	500	100,000	-----	100,000
Chas. E. Mitchell, former chairman of the board, National City Bank.....	-----	-----	-----	2,000	1,000	1,000	100,000	-----	100,000
Chas. A. Peabody, former Illinois Central (deceased).....	-----	100,000	100,000	1,000	1,000	1,000	100,000	-----	100,000
Samuel Rea, former president, Pennsylvania R.R. Co. (deceased).....	50,000	50,000	-----	500	500	500	-----	-----	-----
Percy A. Rockefeller, member of executive committee and director, New York Edison Co., Consolidated Gas Co.....	300,000	-----	-----	2,500	-----	2,000	250,000	-----	250,000
Mrs. A. G. Schiff (deceased).....	-----	-----	-----	5,000	2,500	-----	-----	-----	-----
C. B. Seger, chairman of the executive committee and director Union Pacific R.R. Co.....	50,000	100,000	100,000	-----	2,500	1,000	100,000	-----	100,000
Henry Tatnall, director Philadelphia, Baltimore & Washington Ry.....	50,000	50,000	-----	500	-----	-----	50,000	-----	50,000
Paul F. Warburg Do.....	-----	-----	100,000	250	250	-----	-----	-----	-----

Frederick M. Warburg, firm of Kuhn-Loeb & Co.....				250	250				
Edw. M. M. Warburg.....				250	250				
Gerald F. Warburg.....				250	250				
Albert H. Wiggin, chairman of governing board, the Chase National Bank.....	100,000		100,000	2,000	1,000		100,000		100,000
W. H. Williams (deceased), formerly with Wabash R.R. Co.....	50,000	50,000	100,000	1,000	1,000	1,000	100,000		
A. Wolff, estate of.....						1,250			
Miscellaneous foreign banks and companies.....	1,150,000	475,000	1,150,000	39,000	28,600	15,500	3,800,000	875,000	2,700,000
Total.....	2,200,000	1,275,000	2,100,000	67,000	48,600	29,250	5,050,000	875,000	3,950,000

QUESTION 16.—*Syndicate list (consolidated) Kuhn, Loeb & Co.—Continued*

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	Issue								
	Chicago & North Western Ry. Co. 4½'s, 1949	Pennroad Corporation common stock	Baltimore & Ohio R.R. Co. 4½'s, 1960	Western Union Telegraph Co. 5's, 1960	Pennsylvania R.R. 4½'s, 1970	Southern Pacific R.R. 4½'s, 1977	Paramount Publix Corporation 5½'s, 1950	Pennsylvania R.R. Co. 4½'s, 1981	Southern Pacific R.R. 4½'s, 1981
Cost price.....	Percent 98½	\$15.50	Percent 93½	Percent 98¼	Percent 93	Percent 96	Percent 91½	Percent 95	Percent 95¼
Selling price.....	100	16.50	95	99	93½	96½	92½	95½	95¾
		<i>Shares</i>							
J. S. Alexander former president National Bank of Commerce (deceased).....	\$50,000	2,000	\$50,000	\$50,000	\$50,000				
Lewis W. Baldwin, president and director Missouri Pacific.....	100,000		100,000	100,000	100,000	\$100,000			
Newcomb Carlton, president and director Western Union Telegraph Co.....	50,000	2,000	50,000		50,000	50,000			
Cosmopolis Securities Corporation.....	100,000	5,000			100,000	100,000			
Henry W. De Forest, member of the executive committee and director Guaranty Trust Co.; chairman of board, Southern Pacific R.R.....	100,000	5,000	100,000		100,000				
Henry H. Lee, president Pennroad Corporation.....	150,000		150,000	150,000	75,000	150,000			
Jas. Loeb & Co.....	50,000	2,000	50,000	50,000	50,000	50,000			
L. F. Loree, president, member of board of managers and chairman of executive committee, Delaware & Hudson Co.....	100,000		100,000	100,000	100,000	100,000			
R. S. Lovett, former Union Pacific R.R. (deceased).....	100,000		50,000		100,000	100,000			
Chas. E. Mitchell, former chairman of the board, National City Bank.....		5,000							
Chas. A. Peabody, former Illinois Central (deceased).....	100,000		100,000	100,000	100,000	100,000			
A. W. Robertson, chairman of the board, Westinghouse Electric & Manufacturing Co. and subsidiaries.....			100,000	100,000	100,000	100,000			
Percy A. Rockefeller, member of executive committee and director New York Edison Co., Consolidated Gas Co.....	250,000	10,000	250,000						
Fred W. Sargent, president and director Chicago Northwestern R.R.....			100,000	100,000	100,000	100,000			
Mrs. J. H. Schiff.....	200,000								
Mrs. A. G. Schiff (deceased).....	200,000								

STOCK EXCHANGE PRACTICES

C. R. Seger, chairman of the executive committee and director Union Pacific R.R. Co.	100,000		50,000		100,000	100,000		
Henry Tatnall, director, Philadelphia, Baltimore & Washington Ry.	50,000		50,000		50,000	50,000		
Jas. Paul Warburg, president and director of International Accept- ance Bank, Inc.			100,000	100,000				
Albert H. Wiggin, chairman of governing board the Chase National bank.	100,000	5,000	100,000		100,000	100,000		
W. H. Williams (deceased) formerly with Wabash R.R. Co.	100,000	5,000	100,000	100,000	100,000	100,000		
A. Wolf, estate of	200,000							
Miscellaneous foreign banks and companies	3,025,000	112,000	3,850,000	825,000	1,250,000		1,050,000	100,000
Total	5,125,000	153,000	5,450,000	1,775,000	2,625,000	1,300,000	1,050,000	100,000
								675,000

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 20

THE PENNROAD CORPORATION

STATEMENT FOR YEAR ENDED DECEMBER 31, 1932

Directors: W. W. Atterbury, George W. Bovenizer, A. J. County, William M. Elkins, Rodman E. Griscom, R. B. Mellon, Effingham B. Morris, A. H. S. Post, Joseph Wayne, Jr., and H. H. Lee, president.

Voting trustees under voting trust agreement of May 1, 1929: Effingham B. Morris, Joseph Wayne, Jr., and William M. Potts.

Agent and depository of voting trustees: The Philadelphia National Bank.

Registrars of voting trust certificates: Chemical Bank & Trust Co., New York, and Girard Trust Co., Philadelphia.

THE PENNROAD CORPORATION,
Philadelphia, Pa., March 14, 1933.

To the Stockholders of The Pennroad Corporation:

There is submitted herewith an income statement of the corporation for the calendar year 1932, together with statement of earned surplus and general balance sheet as of December 31, 1932.

There is also appended a list of the securities owned by the corporation with their cost and approximate market value as of December 31, 1932, where listed on stock exchanges and where the corporation owns less than a majority of such securities. In the case of stocks, bonds, notes, and advances having no stock exchange quotations or where this corporation owns at least a majority of such securities, no attempt is made to estimate their value or the value of the control represented thereby.

The net income for the year 1932 was \$793,897.65, a decrease of \$3,701,148.46 as compared with that for the year 1931. The decrease in net income is due primarily to reductions in dividends received. It indicates the greatly reduced gross and net earnings of enterprises in which this corporation is interested in a year of business curtailment. Any improvement in general business will be reflected in increased earnings of the companies in which this corporation has stock holdings, although the prospect of increased dividend receipts by reason thereof is not encouraging for the near future.

Notes payable were reduced by \$1,125,000 during the year to \$400,000.

There was no change in the stock of the corporation during the year 1932, voting trust certificates for which are in the hands of 156,418 holders.

During the year 1932 the corporation suffered a loss through the death of two members of the board of directors, James S. Alexander and Jay Cooke. George W. Bovenizer, of New York City, was elected to fill the vacancy in the board caused by the death of Mr. Alexander, and William M. Potts, of Philadelphia, succeeded him as a voting trustee.

By order of the board of directors.

HENRY H. LEE, *President.*

Income statement for period Jan. 1 to Dec. 31, 1932

		Increase (+) or decrease (-) compared with 1931
Income:		
Dividends.....	\$226, 438. 80	-\$3, 327, 186. 67
Interest from bonds.....	688, 461. 00	-391, 261. 66
Interest from other accounts.....	93, 342. 22	-12, 526. 86
Total income.....	1, 008, 242. 02	-3, 730, 975. 19
Deductions:		
Interest paid.....	45, 374. 99	+12, 595. 75
Taxes.....	25, 244. 38	+20. 66
General expenses.....	143, 725. 00	-42, 443. 14
Total deductions.....	214, 344. 37	-29, 826. 73
Net income credited to earned surplus..	793, 897. 65	-3, 701, 148. 46

Statement of earned surplus

Credit balance Dec. 31, 1931	\$8, 266, 213. 59
Net income for 1932	793, 897. 65
Credit balance Dec. 31, 1932	9, 060, 111. 24

General balance sheet Dec. 31, 1932

ASSETS	
Cash	\$347, 755. 04
Investment securities at cost	145, 679, 920. 50
Accrued income	80, 426. 69
Other assets	40, 300. 10
Total assets	146, 148, 402. 33
LIABILITIES	
Notes payable	\$400, 000. 00
Taxes accrued	545, 549. 11
Interest and accounts payable	916. 66
Capital stock (9,090,000 shares without par value)	90, 900, 000. 00
Surplus:	
Capital surplus	45, 241, 825. 32
Earned surplus	9, 060, 111. 24
Total liabilities	146, 148, 402. 33

SECURITIES OWNED DEC. 31, 1932

Securities for which stock exchange quotations are available

	Shares	Cost	Stock exchange price Dec. 31, 1932
Atlantic Coast Line R.R. Co., common	8, 000	\$1, 480, 000. 00	\$142, 000
Baltimore & Ohio R.R. Co., common	500	59, 125. 00	4, 375
Boston & Maine R.R.:			
Prior preference, 7 percent cumulative dividend	44, 304	5, 077, 871. 45	974, 688
First preferred:			
A, 5 percent cumulative dividend	50, 547	4, 575, 494. 69	404, 376
B, 8 percent cumulative dividend	24, 979	3, 602, 038. 91	256, 034
C, 7 percent cumulative dividend	24, 337	3, 064, 630. 87	237, 285
D, 10 percent cumulative dividend	14, 668	2, 663, 104. 99	176, 016
E, 4½ percent cumulative dividend	19	1, 628. 25	95
Preferred (old), 6 percent noncumulative dividend	14, 968	1, 704, 645. 82	104, 775
Common	27, 565	2, 948, 292. 40	172, 281
Chicago & Northwestern Ry. Co., common	1, 000	85, 175. 00	3, 750
Delaware & Hudson Co., common	2, 000	354, 400. 00	100, 000
Kansas City Southern Ry. Co., common	1, 000	80, 825. 00	7, 375
Lehigh Valley R.R. Co., common	10, 000	650, 000. 00	110, 000
Missouri-Kansas-Texas R.R. Co., 7 percent preferred	4, 500	484, 062. 50	51, 187
New York, New Haven & Hartford R.R. Co.:			
Common	148, 800	17, 301, 851. 25	2, 027, 400
Preferred	1, 200	149, 300. 00	30, 000
Pennroad Corporation voting trust certificates	152, 284	969, 828. 60	209, 390
Seaboard Air Line Ry. Co., common	402, 119	4, 523, 838. 75	100, 529
Southern Pacific Co., common	500	60, 125. 00	8, 000
Southern Ry. Co., common	10, 000	1, 415, 244. 32	50, 000
Baltimore & Ohio R.R. Co., convertible 4½ percent bonds, 1960, par value \$174,000		180, 612. 00	50, 460
		51, 432, 095. 80	5, 220, 017

Stocks having no stock-exchange quotations or where corporation owns at least a majority of the stock

	Shares	Cost
Over 99 percent, Canton Co. of Baltimore, common.....	21, 975	\$13, 432, 817. 90
Over 99 percent, Detroit, Toledo & Ironton R. R. Co.:		
Common.....	245, 327	23, 917, 017. 74
Scrip.....		53. 05
100 percent, National Freight Co., common.....	120, 000	2, 400, 000. 00
74 percent, Pittsburgh & West Virginia Ry. Co., common.....	223, 230	37, 910, 145. 00
100 percent, Springfield Suburban R. R. Co., common.....	5, 100	200, 500. 00
		77, 860, 533. 70

Bonds, notes, and advances having no stock-exchange quotations

	Par value	Cost
Detroit, Toledo & Ironton R.R. Co., first mortgage 5 percent (total issue \$4,323,000).....	\$2, 918, 000	\$2, 693, 171
Detroit, Toledo & Ironton R. R. Co., first and refunding mortgage 5 percent (total issue).....	10, 626, 000	9, 983, 820
Detroit, Toledo & Ironton R. R. Co., 6 percent equipment notes (total issue \$168,900).....	56, 400	56, 400
Notes secured by collateral.....	325, 000	325, 000
Advances to subsidiary companies.....	3, 328, 900	3, 328, 900
		16, 387, 291

We report that on January 5, 1933, we examined, or received confirmations from the depositaries of, the securities owned by the Pennroad Corporation at December 31, 1932, as recited in the foregoing statement and have found them to be recorded on the books of the corporation.

LYBRAND, ROSS BROS. & MONTGOMERY,
Accountants and Auditors, Philadelphia, Pa.

STOCK EXCHANGE PRACTICES

FRIDAY, JUNE 30, 1933

UNITED STATES SENATE,
SUBCOMMITTEE OF THE
COMMITTEE ON BANKING AND CURRENCY,
Washington, D.C.

The subcommittee met, pursuant to adjournment on yesterday, at 10 a.m., in the caucus room of the Senate Office Building, Senator Duncan U. Fletcher presiding.

Present: Senators Fletcher (chairman), Barkley, Costigan, Goldsborough, Townsend, and Steiwer.

Present also: Senator Adams.

Present also: Ferdinand Pecora, counsel to the committee; Julius Silver and David Saperstein, associate counsel to the committee; Frank J. Meehan, chief statistician to the committee; and Carl A. de Gersdorff, Robert T. Swaine, and M. T. Moore, counsel for Kuhn, Loeb & Co.

The CHAIRMAN. The subcommittee will come to order, please. We will resume our hearing. I might add that everyone is at liberty to remove his coat and make himself comfortable as far as he can.

Mr. Pecora, you may proceed, as Mr. Kahn is here at the committee table.

TESTIMONY OF OTTO H. KAHN, A MEMBER OF THE FIRM OF KUHN, LOEB & CO.—Resumed

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, at the outset the Pennroad Corporation issued and sold 5,800,000 shares of stock?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. To stockholders, or offered them to stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. At the price of \$15 per share?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. At or about the same time was any agreement entered into by the Pennroad Corporation with your firm involving the purchase of any part of those shares by your firm?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir. We were given the right and assumed the obligation under certain conditions to purchase up to 250,000 shares at precisely the same price at which the stockholders purchased.

Mr. PECORA. Was the exercise of that right dependent upon any condition?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir. It was dependent upon the condition that the stockholders would take not less than 85 percent of the total issue.

Mr. PECORA. Have you a copy of that agreement?

Mr. KAHN. I have no doubt we have.

Mr. PECORA. Will you be good enough to produce it for the purposes of the record?

Mr. KAHN. Here it is. This is not a very good copy, and we may have a better one here.

Mr. PECORA. I offer this in evidence and ask that it be spread upon the record of the subcommittee's hearings.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted, and the committee reporter will spread it upon the record of our hearings.

(The paper was marked "Committee Exhibit No. 21, June 30, 1933", and is as follows:)

THE PENNROAD CORPORATION,
Philadelphia, Pa., April 24, 1929.

MESSRS. KUHN, LOEB & Co.,
New York, N.Y.

DEAR SIRs: In order to facilitate the sale of its common stock, this corporation desires to make arrangements for the sale of a substantial amount thereof, in case the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. (including employees now subscribing to its stock) or their assigns, do not purchase the entire amount of 5,800,000 shares offered to them at \$15 per share, pursuant to the terms of the enclosed circular, dated April 24, 1929.

Accordingly this corporation requests you to purchase 250,000 shares of such common stock, or such part thereof as may be available for sale after the termination of said offer to the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., it being understood that there shall be no obligation on your part to make such purchase unless said stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., or their assigns, purchase at least 85 percent (4,930,000 shares) of said stock, pursuant to the terms of said offer. The corporation reserves the right, however, prior to June 14, 1929, to sell not to exceed 100,000 shares of said common stock at \$15 per share to others than said stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. or their assigns or yourselves, and to include such sales in determining whether said 85 percent (4,930,000 shares) of said common stock have been purchased pursuant to the terms of said offer, if thereby the amount of said common stock to be purchased by you hereunder is not reduced below 250,000 shares. In consideration of your agreeing to make such purchase, this corporation agrees to sell and deliver said stock to you upon the terms above stated, and also hereby gives and grants to you an option to purchase, at the same price, at any time or from time to time on or before August 31, 1929, any of said 5,800,000 shares of such common stock which may not be purchased by you hereunder or by said stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., or their assigns, or by others, pursuant to said offering, whether or not said stockholders or their assigns, or others, have purchased 85 percent of said stock.

Within 10 days after June 14, 1929, this corporation will notify you of the amount of stock purchased upon such offering, and any stock which you may be obligated to purchase hereunder is to be delivered to you and paid for by you within 10 days thereafter.

Any stock which you may have an option to purchase hereunder you shall take up and pay for in lots of not less than 50,000 shares upon 5 days' notice from you to us of your election to purchase the same.

Please confirm the agreement and option hereinabove stated upon the terms hereof.

The term common stock, or stock, wherever used herein, shall mean and include voting trust certificates for common stock.

There is attached hereto and made a part hereof a certified copy of a resolution of the board of directors of the corporation authorizing the agreement herein contained, and fixing and stating, in accordance with this letter, the terms upon which, the time within which, and the price at which, the shares of common stock covered by the option herein granted may be purchased from the corporation pursuant to such option.

Very truly yours,

H. H. LEE, *President.*

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, did your firm exercise any of the rights conferred upon it under this agreement as to the purchase of stock of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; Mr. Pecora. We found that the stockholders had exercised their right to subscribe, at \$15 a share, to all but 242,000 shares. Those 242,000 shares we were obligated to purchase, and we did purchase them. A little later on, at the request of the Pennroad Corporation, we let them have back 25,000 shares out of those 242,000 shares, so that the whole amount which remained in our possession was 217,000 shares.

Mr. PECORA. When was that option exercised by your firm?

Mr. KAHN. It was not an option.

Mr. PECORA. Well, that right.

Mr. KAHN. Immediately. As soon as the Pennroad Corporation, saw to what extent the stockholders had availed themselves of their offering, immediately thereafter we exercised the obligation which was resting upon us to purchase whatever the stockholders had not purchased.

The CHAIRMAN. At \$15 a share?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; at the same price at which the stockholders took theirs, \$15 a share.

Mr. PECORA. Now, this agreement also gave to your firm an option to purchase at the same price, namely, \$15 per share, at any time up to August 31, 1929, any of the original issue of 5,800,000 shares which might not have been purchased up to that time by your firm or by the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.

Mr. KAHN. It did, Mr. Pecora. But it was purely an academic thing. I could not tell you now for what reason that was put in, and, in my opinion, for no good reason whatever. In fact, it amounted to nothing. It was purely academic.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, subsequently to your firm entering into this agreement did your firm enter into another agreement with the Pennroad Corporation under which you were given options to purchase up to 500,000 shares?

Mr. KAHN. Not subsequently, but at the same time.

Mr. PECORA. And was that covered by a separate agreement?

Mr. KAHN. It was covered by a separate agreement.

Mr. PECORA. Have you that agreement, or a copy of it?

Mr. KAHN. I am quite sure we have.

Mr. PECORA. Will you be good enough to produce it for the record?

Mr. KAHN. That was considered to be our compensation for the work done, the advice given. It was a purely contingent compensation, because it was at prices higher than at which the stock was offered to stockholders. The option was at prices of \$16, \$17, \$18, and \$19, respectively.

Mr. PECORA. For blocks of 125,000 shares each?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. If you will produce a copy of the agreement, I should like to have it for the record.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Mr. Pecora, that letter is spread out on page 676 of the Splawn report.

Mr. PECORA. I know. But have you a copy of it here?

Mr. KAHN. We are looking for it. I am sure we have it here.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. In the meantime, if you want to use this copy spread on the Splawn report, you might have it.

Mr. PECORA. Well, I can read it into the record from that. The option agreement as it referred to your firm, Mr. Kahn, was in the form of a letter addressed to the firm of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. by the Pennroad Corporation, under date of April 24, 1929, was it not?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir. And here we have found a copy of that agreement.

Mr. PECORA. I offer this in evidence and ask that it may be spread upon the record, the original option agreement which has been produced by the witness.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted, and the committee reporter will make it a part of the record.

(The option agreement referred to was marked "Committee Exhibit No. 22, June 30, 1933", and is as follows:)

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 22

THE PENNROAD CORPORATION,
Philadelphia, Pa., April 24, 1929.

MESSRS. KUHN, LOEB & Co.,
52 William Street, New York, N.Y.

DEAR SIR: In consideration of your having acted in an advisory capacity and having given the organizers of this corporation the benefit of your experience and judgment in connection with the organization of this corporation, you are hereby accorded the right to purchase on or before July 1, 1932, all or any part of 125,000 shares of common stock of this corporation at \$16 per share, 125,000 shares of such common stock at \$17 per share, 125,000 shares of such common stock at \$18 per share, and 125,000 shares of such common stock at \$19 per share.

The stock covered by this option is in addition to the 5,800,000 shares offered at \$15 per share to the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. (including employees now subscribing to its stock), or their assigns, or to others. Transferable warrants, in such denominations as you may designate, evidencing your right to purchase the above-mentioned stock will be delivered to you at any time at your request.

The term "common stock" or "stock", wherever used herein, shall mean and include voting trust certificates for common stock.

There is attached hereto and made a part hereof a certified copy of a resolution of the board of directors of the corporation fixing and stating, in accordance with this letter, the terms upon which, the time within which, and the prices at which the shares of common stock above referred to may be purchased from the corporation pursuant hereto.

Very truly yours,

H. H. LEE, *President.*

On motion, duly made and seconded, it was unanimously

Resolved, That this corporation grant to Messrs. Kuhn, Loeb & Co. the right to purchase the voting trust certificates for 500,000 shares of the common stock of this corporation on the terms hereinafter specified.

Resolved, That the terms upon which, the time within which, and the prices at which such shares of common stock, or voting trust certificates therefor, may be purchased from this corporation are as follows:

All or any part of 125,000 shares of said common stock at \$16 per share at any time on or before July 1, 1932;

All or any part of 125,000 shares thereof at \$17 per share on or before said date;

All or any part of 125,000 shares thereof at \$18 per share on or before said date; and

All or any part of 125,000 shares thereof at \$19 per share on or before said date.

Resolved, That the form of letter to Messrs. Kuhn, Loeb & Co. which has been submitted to this meeting be, and it hereby is, in all things approved

and that the proper officers of this corporation be, and they hereby are, authorized and directed to execute and deliver to Messrs. Kuhn, Loeb & Co. a letter substantially in said form; and

Resolved, That there be executed and delivered to Messrs. Kuhn, Loeb & Co. at any time at their request transferable warrants in such denominations as Messrs. Kuhn, Loeb & Co. may request, evidencing their right to purchase such voting trust certificates for common stock on the terms above set out, such warrants to be in such form as the president of this corporation may approve; and

Resolved, That upon exercise of said right to purchase said common stock this corporation, upon payment to it for the stock as to which such right is exercised at the prices aforesaid, and upon surrender of the appropriate warrants, if any, at the time outstanding, issue to the voting trustees under the voting trust agreement hereinbefore authorized certificates for such stock, and request said voting trustees to issue voting trust certificates therefor to or upon the order of the person or persons so exercising such right.

Resolved, That of the consideration received by this corporation in respect of the issue of said 500,000 shares of common stock, or any thereof, \$10 per share shall be capital.

The president stated that in connection with the offering of voting trust certificates for common stock of this corporation to the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. it was proposed that an agreement should be made with Messrs. Kuhn, Loeb & Co. whereby this corporation would agree to sell to Messrs. Kuhn, Loeb & Co., at \$15 per share, voting trust certificates for 250,000 shares of common stock, or such smaller amount as might not be purchased on said offering, and Messrs. Kuhn, Loeb & Co. would agree to purchase such voting trust certificates at said price, provided 85 percent of the total amount of voting trust certificates so offered were purchased by the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. or their assigns, the corporation reserving the right, however, prior to June 14, 1929, to sell not to exceed 100,000 shares of said common stock at \$15 per share to others than stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. or their assigns or Messrs. Kuhn, Loeb & Co. and to include such shares in determining whether said 85 percent of common stock had been purchased pursuant to the terms of said offer, if thereby the amount of common stock to be purchased by Messrs. Kuhn, Loeb & Co. thereunder was not reduced below 250,000 shares; and whereby Messrs. Kuhn, Loeb & Co. would be granted an option to purchase at any time on or before August 31, 1929, at \$15 per share, any part of such voting trust certificates not purchased by the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. or their assigns, or by others. He submitted a form of letter proposed to be written to Messrs. Kuhn, Loeb & Co. setting forth the agreement outlined above.

Mr. PECORA. The agreement is in a letter form and reads as follows. (Counsel then read the letter of Apr. 24, 1929, which is a part of the above exhibit.) You have stated, Mr. Kahn, with reference to this agreement, and the letter itself states, that this right to purchase these 500,000 shares, at prices ranging from \$16 to \$19 per share, in blocks of 125,000 shares, was intended as some compensation or means of paying your firm compensation for services rendered by your firm in connection with the organization of the Pennroad Corporation.

Mr. KAHN. Contingent compensation; yes.

Mr. PECORA. Well, when you say "contingent compensation", what do you mean?

Mr. KAHN. I mean the question of whether these options were of any value or not depended entirely upon the development of the market. If the market had not gone above \$16 there would have been no value whatever. And I might also mention that the fact that such options had been granted was stated publicly in the prospectus addressed to the shareholders themselves.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, this agreement was entered into on the same date that the Pennroad Corporation itself was organized, I notice.

Mr. KAHN. Was it organized on the same date? (The witness addressing an associate.)

Mr. PECORA. Well, this letter is dated April 24, 1929, and it is my recollection that that was the date on which the Pennroad Corporation was incorporated.

Mr. KAHN. Well, I accept your recollection, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. Now, what were the services that your firm rendered as bankers to the Pennroad Corporation in connection with its organization?

Mr. KAHN. I tried to set forth yesterday what were our services. They extended over a number of weeks, during which the nature of the financial instrument and the financial methods for raising the large amount of money were to be defined, were under discussion and consideration. I stated on yesterday that that, in our opinion, was the best advice we ever gave—and, of course, we hope to give more than one piece of sound advice, but it was perhaps the best advice we ever gave, as things turned out, because we said to them: We urge you, first, to do these things without creating any fixed charge. The original idea was that something would be done which would have involved a fixed charge, just as the Alleghany financing involved a fixed charge. We said, In view of the character of this transaction, you ought not to burden yourself with the obligation of any fixed charge whatsoever. We said, You ought not even to burden yourself with the obligation of preferred stock, which involves a moral obligation to strain yourself to the utmost that you reasonably can to pay a dividend if it is at all possible, and which might create in the minds of the people to whom you offer the security the impression that you are offering them an investment security. We said to them, You are offering something the result of which, the outcome of which, depends entirely upon the future, and therefore, in our judgment, you ought to offer nothing but an equity. You ought to offer it to the people most directly concerned, namely, the Pennsylvania stockholders, in the first instance and not go directly to the public, but go first to the Pennsylvania stockholders.

Mr. PECORA. You mean the Pennsylvania Railroad stockholders as distinguished from the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Co.?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir; that is what I mean. We said to them "furthermore, you realize that we are taking a great responsibility in advising you to offer so large a block of stock without protecting yourself by underwriting. Our deliberate judgment is that you can afford to take that chance, that the issue will be taken, and it will prove a great success." We said to them "if you had an underwriting, the cost involved would be so great that we could not justly advise you to incur such expense." And I am vain enough to say that all those items of advice turned out to be sound.

Mr. PECORA. Were there any other services that you rendered in connection with the organization of the Pennroad Corporation for which you received this form of contingent compensation, consisting of this option agreement?

Mr. KAHN. None except that which is covered by the general statement I have made.

Mr. PECORA. In other words, the financial advice that you gave the organizers of the Pennroad Corporation simply was to issue common stock instead of bonds or preferred stock? That is what it boils down to, doesn't it?

Mr. KAHN. No. What it boils down to, and what was a great saving to the Pennroad, was that we told them to go ahead and take the chance of offering that issue of stock without an underwriting. An underwriting in untried and novel securities would inevitably have cost them millions of dollars. We told them "go ahead and take the chance and do not pay anybody anything."

Mr. PECORA. Then do you think that an underwriting expense in the flotation of an issue is a burdensome thing?

Mr. KAHN. I beg your pardon, but I was interrupted right there.

Mr. PECORA. I say, an underwriting charge in the flotation of an issue, in the issuance of a security, is a rather burdensome charge, and you thought that charge ought to be avoided in this particular instance?

Mr. KAHN. "Burdensome" is not the word I would use. Inevitably there are considerable items of cost for underwriting, it means that someone, some syndicate, has got to stand in the breach from 4 to 6 weeks, has got to insure the corporation in question that they will get that money whatever may happen. For instance, the *Lusitania* sinking might have happened, or many other things which did happen in some cases, might have happened, and the underwriting syndicate stands there and says, "Go ahead." We say to them, "Go ahead and offer it to your stockholders, and we will give you our assurance that if your stockholders do not take it we shall." That is a service of the greatest importance, and from the point of view of conservative financing in most cases an inevitable service. For instance, the Pennsylvania Railroad itself had that experience, in that a few years earlier it offered a large amount of its stock to its shareholders which, if I recall correctly, was at \$120 at a time when the market price was about \$150, or thereabouts, and had been for a long time. They did it without an underwriting.

They thought the spread was sufficient to make the offering safe. The result was that within a very few weeks the market price of the stock went from around \$150 or \$145, whatever it may have been, to \$125, and the offering, on which the Pennsylvania Railroad had relied for the purpose of securing money for important contracts which it had entered into, the offering was on the point of being a complete failure. And when a thing is a complete failure in the financial community it is a case of soiled goods. You cannot use them any more for a long time. People won't touch them. If a thing has failed, it is soiled goods. They do not want them. And at the last minute they came to us and they said, "Is it still time to get an underwriting, because we are very apprehensive, much more than apprehensive; we are certain that if something is not done it will prove a failure, a damage to our credit, and a great damage to our financial situation." We said, "We will try." And we did at the last minute form an underwriting, and we did at the last minute save that situation. Now, that is why an underwriting, when it is a question of offering a considerable amount of stock, in my opinion is an essential instrument of financial service. And if in this case

we departed from that it was because we felt the cost of an underwriting, with so large an amount involved, would have incurred a great expense, which is inevitable with a new security, which was an untried instrument; so we said, "Go ahead and take your chances; morally we give you the assurance that you are not going to get stuck."

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, how long prior to April 24, 1929, were conferences held among the organizers of the Pennroad Corporation with respect to the proposed organization?

Mr. KAHN. For weeks.

Mr. PECORA. For weeks?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; for weeks.

Mr. PECORA. And your firm participated in all those conferences through one or more of its members or representatives?

Mr. KAHN. To the extent that they related to financial matters; yes.

Mr. PECORA. Only to that extent did they participate?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. They did not participate to the extent of determining the purposes for which the corporation was to be organized?

Mr. KAHN. They did not to the extent of determining the purposes. That would have been beyond our province. They did participate, I have no doubt, even though I have no precise recollection, but they did participate no doubt as to the propriety, the value, and the usefulness of having such an instrument available provided that the Pennsylvania was right in its views as to the necessity of having such an instrument.

Mr. PECORA. Can you tell this committee who participated in those preliminary conferences?

Mr. KAHN. In my firm?

Mr. PECORA. Generally. Not alone representatives for your firm but the conferees representing other interests.

Mr. KAHN. Oh, in my firm, in the first instance, there would have been my late partner, Mr. Mortimer Schiff, who was very active in this particular thing. There was myself. There was my former partner, Mr. Jerome Hanauer. There was, on the part of the Pennsylvania interests, as I recall, General Atterbury, Mr. County, who was the financial vice president of the Pennsylvania Railroad. There might have been and probably was—but that I recall with less distinctness—there might have been Mr. Harry Lee, who was then treasurer of the Pennsylvania Railroad, who later became president of the Pennroad.

Mr. PECORA. Were there any other attorneys?

Mr. KAHN. I beg your pardon?

Mr. PECORA. Were there any other attorneys in those conferences?

Mr. KAHN. I should not think in the conferences between us at that stage. There doubtless—

Mr. PECORA. Well, I mean at any stage up to the actual incorporation and organization of the company.

Mr. KAHN. Not on our part, as far as that is concerned.

Mr. PECORA. Well, on anybody's part?

Mr. KAHN. Anybody's part—I could not say whether the Pennsylvania Railroad at any time brought their attorneys along. I

really do not recollect. Our attorneys, I presume, would not come in until the matter had reached the point where an instrument had to be drawn up setting forth a definite transaction between the Pennsylvania Railroad and ourselves, or the Pennroad and ourselves.

Mr. PECORA. What was said in those conferences that led to its incorporation about the need and the necessity for such a corporation?

Mr. KAHN. You ask me to go back a good many years.

Mr. PECORA. It is only 4 years.

Mr. KAHN. And they were pretty strenuous years. And they were more, in fact, than 4 years; I should rank them equal to about 12 years. What was said in these conferences other than the financial aspect of it, as far as we were concerned, was probably of relatively little significance, as I explained—

Mr. PECORA. Well, do you mean to say that the objects and purposes of the incorporation or proposed incorporation were matters of little or trifling significance?

Mr. KAHN. Oh, by no means, but I say to the extent that they were discussed with us they were probably of relatively little significance, because the determination to form such a corporation—a corporation the purpose of which was not within our province to determine and was hardly in our province to advise upon, except that, as I said yesterday, the Pennsylvania Railroad emphasized the fact that there were certain properties which in their opinion were necessary or eminently desirable for their expansion, for the rounding out of their system, for their strategic purposes, that they wanted to be sure that such properties would not fall into hands which could damage the legitimate interests, the legitimate development, the logical strategy of the Pennsylvania Railroad. And in order to accomplish that they ought to have an instrument available not merely for defense—least of all for attack—but an instrument similar, perhaps, to what they created in 1870 when they first started out to round out their system, to get such properties as in their best judgment were—I will not say vital, but were desirable for their legitimate, logical, strategic development.

Mr. PECORA. Then it was stated in these preliminary conferences that the essential purpose for organizing the Penroad Corporation was to create an instrument, using your terminology, that would enable the Pennsylvania Co. through the purchase of stock of other railroad companies to protect its interests and integrity as a railroad system?

Mr. KAHN. I hate, Mr. Pecora, to fence, but I cannot possibly express that in any way having the same degree of authority and competence as the Pennsylvania Railroad officials and board of directors expressed it in the circular signed by General Atterbury which is before you. They stated very definitely, very precisely, without any concealment, what was their purpose. Anything that I might add to it would be taken from a slightly hazy recollection and would be an interpretation that I put upon it possibly without any justification whatever.

You have before you the actual record of why this was done. You also have before you the Splawn report in which this whole transaction, its purposes and motives and methods, were gone into

and set forth in the fullest detail before the Interstate Commerce Committee of the House of Representatives. I really do not feel that I could add anything to it which would help you.

Mr. PECORA. Was it set forth by any one in any of these conferences that it was advisable or would be advisable to create an instrument to do the various things that the Pennroad Corporation accomplished or sought to accomplish, which instrument could be used without the supervision or right of interference, if you please, of the Interstate Commerce Commission under the laws creating that Commission?

Mr. KAHN. That I could not say, but I assume that the facts speak for themselves. As a matter of fact, that instrument was available, and under the laws as they then were I believe that instrument was free from supervision.

I should also add, searching my memory, that one of the things which were brought out—mentioned in those conferences—was that the Pennroad would be very careful when it once came into operation to buy such securities as would not only be of value to the strategic purposes of the Pennsylvania Railroad, but would in themselves be desirable purchases which at that time—1929, mark you—they believed to be fully worth the price that they were paying for them and ultimately probably worth more.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, in these preliminary conferences was there any discussion of a definitive character with respect to the railroad lines that the proposed corporation would buy into for the protection of the Pennsylvania Railroad interests?

Mr. KAHN. To the best of my recollection the only one which was definitely mentioned at the time was the Detroit, Toledo & Ironton, which they were very anxious to possess.

Mr. PECORA. Was that the only railroad company the purchase of whose shares was discussed at any time up to the actual incorporation of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. KAHN. At any time would undoubtedly be saying more than I could answer for, but it is the one that sticks in my memory as being very definitely discussed as a purchase that ought by no means to be missed. Now, it is quite possible that various other lines were mentioned at that time. I really have no definite recollection on that subject which would justify me to express an opinion before this committee.

Mr. PECORA. Well, now, the purchase of the Detroit, Toledo & Ironton road was a purchase which it was then known would involve only around \$30,000,000?

Mr. KAHN. It would involve a good deal more than that, Mr. Pecora. I think it would involve about \$50,000,000, if I remember rightly.

Mr. PECORA. Well, about \$50,000,000. The original set-up of the Pennroad Corporation provided for the issuance and sale of its securities in an amount that would yield the corporation around \$85,000,000 or \$90,000,000?

Mr. KAHN. \$87,000,000, to be exact.

Mr. PECORA. Yes. And there was also provision for issuing shares additional to the original 5,800,000 shares?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Now, up to April 24, 1929, when the Pennroad Corporation was organized, did not the organizers of that corporation indicate in these conferences rather definitely just what railroad lines it was deemed necessary to buy into for the protection of the interests of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. KAHN. To the best of my recollection the only one which was mentioned definitely, or rather definitely, was the Detroit, Toledo & Ironton.

Mr. PECORA. Would it not be essential for you as the banker and financial adviser of these interests to know just what their scope and plan was, so that you might the more intelligently advise them on financial matters?

Mr. KAHN. Would it have enabled us, Mr. Pecora—I am wrong in answering your question with another question—I ought to put it as my answer, and not as my question—and my answer is I do not believe it would. Their judgment as to the value of the thing which they contemplated buying was necessarily more competent than ours. Moreover, they were buying something which did not involve a fixed charge, and that made a vital difference in our conception. It involved something where they exchanged equities really, and in that case—whilst if a bond had been involved we doubtless would have been quite cantankerous in looking into values and seeing that that bond was as fully protected as in our judgment it ought to be, and would have made representations to them to that effect; where it was a question of exchanging equities, they buying an equity and offering it to the public in exchange for another equity, and only an equity, no bonds, no preferred stock, I do not believe we were called upon to go into the thing with the same thoroughness as we would have been with a bond issue.

Mr. PECORA. But Mr. Kahn, would it not have been preferable to you when called upon to give advice as to financial matters to know rather definitely the extent of the necessary financing, that is, the amount that would be involved, and also the purposes for which the money to be raised was to be used?

Mr. KAHN. If any responsibility toward the public attaches to us, any substantial moral responsibility, my answer is decidedly "yes." You may have observed, Mr. Pecora, that in this instance, in the first offering to the stockholders of 5,800,000 shares aggregating \$87,000,000 in value, our name does not appear on the circular. And it did not appear on the circular deliberately, because we did not want in any way by the sponsorship of our name to influence the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad, whether they desired or did not desire, to put up that money. We deliberately requested that our name be left out.

Mr. PECORA. Were you not willing to assume the responsibility for that particular issue or form of financing to the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. KAHN. We did not think that it was a matter in which in the first instance our name should appear, because that would have put upon us a responsibility that we should have had to exercise immediately, and we preferred that the stockholders should determine of their own choice whether it appealed to them to exchange equities for equities.

Mr. PECORA. Now, this corporation was organized as was testified to yesterday, essentially for the benefit of the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., was it not?

Mr. KAHN. It was organized as the circular of the Pennsylvania Railroad indicates, and nothing that I could add would explain it further than they have explained it. I can only add my guess.

Mr. PECORA. Well, you do not hesitate to say that it was organized or designed to be organized for the benefit of the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., do you?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; but you can, and I believe one should expand the definition of benefit not merely from the point of view of railroad purchases but also from the point of view of benefiting the stockholders of the Pennroad financially if that was possible. In other words, to make their choice of what they wanted to buy not solely from the point of view of the Pennsylvania Railroad but also from the point of view of the advantage to their stockholders.

The CHAIRMAN. May I ask, do you remember the mileage of the Detroit, Toledo & Ironton Railroad?

Mr. KAHN. The mileage—I do not remember; no. I believe that the amount involved, Senator, was about \$50,000,000, including stocks and bonds.

The CHAIRMAN. I do not remember the terminals of that road, or the length of it, or what branches it had, if any. Do you remember?

Mr. KAHN. I do not really remember now without having refreshed my memory. Possibly we may have some details here on the subject.

Mr. PECORA. Under its certificate of incorporation the Pennroad Corporation was authorized to issue up to 10,000,000 shares of stock?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Now, you said yesterday, if I recall correctly your testimony, that the Pennsylvania Company, which was a sort of a holding company and a subsidiary of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., was not considered by the organizers of the Pennroad Corporation to be the kind of instrument which they wanted with which to effectuate their railroad purposes?

Mr. KAHN. It was considered, Mr. Pecora, but the opinion was reached that it was not the right kind of instrument. That, moreover, if I recall correctly, the Pennsylvania Railroad, which owned all the stock of the Pennsylvania Co., was unwilling to give up any of that stock or to create preferred stocks. Therefore, if the Pennsylvania Co. had been used, it could only have been used by means of issuing bonds. And that we were unalterably opposed to.

Mr. PECORA. Why could it not have issued additional stock?

Mr. KAHN. Because the Pennsylvania Railroad was unwilling to give up any part of the stock which it owned. It owned all of the stock of the Pennsylvania Co., and it did not wish to give up any part of that stock.

Mr. PECORA. Was that the only factual basis for that conclusion or judgment with respect to the inadvisability of using the Pennsylvania Co.?

Mr. KAHN. To the best of my recollection, that is the only factual basis. We opposed the issue of bonds unalterably, and I do not know today, and I did not know then, in what way the Pennsyl-

vania Co. could have been used except by the issued of bonds involving a fixed charge.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recall that during the year preceding the incorporation of the Pennroad Co., the Pennsylvania Co. was virtually required to sell certain railroad-stock holdings in roads other than the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. KAHN. I am afraid I do not. Perhaps you can help me by telling me what those were.

Mr. PECORA. How about the Lehigh Valley Road and the Wabash Road?

Mr. KAHN. The Lehigh Valley Road and the Wabash Road were acquired by the Pennsylvania Co., and quite recently—I believe within the last 4 weeks those acquisitions were ratified by judgment of the circuit court—was it?

Mr. PECORA. The circuit court of appeals.

Mr. KAHN (continuing). By the circuit court of appeals, and were held to be proper and right. The precise circumstances under which at that time they were bought by the Pennsylvania Co. I do not now recall without searching my memory. But the mere fact that they were bought made it doubly desirable that this company should not be burdened any further if it could be helped.

Mr. PECORA. What was the litigation in which the circuit court of appeals recently rendered that decision?

Mr. KAHN. I am afraid I do not know the exact points which were involved. I only know that the purchase was ratified and held valid.

Mr. PECORA. Cannot some of your associates or counsel tell you?

The CHAIRMAN. Give the title of the case.

Mr. PECORA. Perhaps Mr. de Gersdorff can.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. I thought I had a copy of that opinion here, but I looked at my papers last night and could not find that. Shall I state my understanding of it?

Mr. PECORA. Yes; if you will.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. My understanding is that a suit was brought by the Interstate Commerce Commission to compel the Pennsylvania Co. to dispossess itself of the shares which it had acquired of the Lehigh Valley and the Wabash.

Mr. PECORA. What was the claim or contention of the Interstate Commerce Commission?

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. That it was in violation of the Clayton Act.

Mr. PECORA. All right.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. And the Pennsylvania Co. took an appeal from that decision of the Interstate Commerce Commission to the circuit court of appeals, and the Interstate Commerce Commission's decision was reversed, and the acquisition of those stocks by the Pennsylvania was held to be valid. And that was about 2 weeks ago, I think.

Mr. PECORA. The question is on its way to the United States Supreme Court?

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. I haven't any idea. I was not concerned in the case, and I do not know.

Mr. PECORA. Now, when was that action brought?

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. Originally?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. Oh, quite a few years ago.

Mr. PECORA. Back in 1928, was it not?

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. I should say so; yes.

Mr. PECORA. Yes; in June 1928? Thereabouts?

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. Thereabouts.

Mr. PECORA. So that some time during the year preceding the incorporation of the Pennroad Co. or Pennroad Corporation the Interstate Commerce Commission had by bringing that action which Mr. de Gersdorff has stated something about, indicated to the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. interests that it looked with disfavor upon those interests acquiring certain railroad lines, did it not?

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. Mr. Pecora, may I say that if that question is to be brought into this examination I think we ought to be accurate about that date. If not, why all right. I do not know whether it was '28 or '29 or '27.

Mr. PECORA. Well, I understand it was 1928. That is subject to correction.

Mr. KAHN. Well, that attributes to me more knowledge of the tangled legal structure of that period than I possess.

The CHAIRMAN. In other words, the point, as I understand, is that the acquiring of the stocks of other railroad companies by the Pennsylvania was questioned by the Interstate Commerce Commission?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

The CHAIRMAN. And in order to escape that sort of contingency or objection the Pennsylvania Co. proceeds to organize this corporation we are talking about to accomplish the same result that they were trying to accomplish, and which was questioned by the Interstate Commerce Commission, is that right?

Mr. KAHN. Senator Fletcher, you may be entirely right in attributing these motives; but I do not know that. Whether they existed or whether they did not exist, as far as we are concerned, we would not consent to give our name to any financing of the proposed transaction of acquiring railroad stocks of as yet undefined type except of the Detroit, Toledo & Ironton, if it involved any fixed charge, and therefore, whatever the attitude of the Interstate Commerce Commission would have been, if the Pennsylvania had come to us and said, "We want to finance these as yet undefined acquisitions by asking you to offer to the public a bond", with the utmost respect and affection for the Pennsylvania we would have said, "We are sorry, we cannot do that for you." And our advice would have been, as it was, "We are at your disposal to the utmost of our capacity, but if you have no other way of doing that, and you feel that it has got to be done, then you must offer to your stockholders something which represents nothing but equity, and tell them the true facts, and tell them, 'We are going to do that. You can come in or you can stay out. If you stay out, we cannot do it.'" But as far as we are concerned, we would not have offered a bond. We would not even have offered a preferred stock.

Mr. PECORA. Well, what, if anything, was said at the conferences that were held and which looked toward the incorporation of the Pennroad Corporation about the contention of the Interstate Commerce Commission with respect to the right of the Pennsylvania Co. to continue to hold certain railroad shares which it then owned?

MR. KAHN. On searching my memory, one thing which stuck in my memory as to these particular discussions is that the Pennsylvania Co. were advised by their counsel, to the best of my knowledge, that they were engaged in a perfectly legal thing and it would ultimately be so determined. His advise has been vindicated, and, to the best of my knowledge, they never doubted that they had that right, and, to the best of my knowledge, the fact that they never doubted it was mentioned repeatedly.

MR. PECORA. Is it your belief or the belief as stated to you by that counsel that the last word has been said and written with regard to that litigation against the Pennsylvania Co. merely because the circuit court of appeals made its ruling a few weeks ago?

MR. KAHN. I would like to know that, but you can tell me better than I can tell you.

MR. PECORA. I do not sit on the United States Supreme Court.

MR. KAHN. Yes; but you are a very distinguished lawyer and I am not.

MR. PECORA. Did counsel say anything about that?

MR. KAHN. Not to my recollection.

MR. PECORA. Did the fact that the Interstate Commerce Commission brought that action against the Pennsylvania Co. have any part in the judgment eventually arrived at by the organizers of the Pennroad Corporation to create that corporation as an instrument to be used for the purchase of stock of other railroad companies instead of using the Pennsylvania Co.?

MR. KAHN. I should not think so, because I do not know, as I said before, what was that purpose. They could not use any instrument except the new instrument involving no fixed charge.

MR. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, can you tell us approximately the total amount of fees, compensations, or profits that were paid or accrued to your firm as a result of its identification with the Pennroad Corporation enterprise?

MR. KAHN. The only fee which was paid to us was the fee for forming an underwriting syndicate for the second issue. It was when the second issue of Pennroad stock came along and when, contrary to our expectation and without really any preliminary notice, the Pennroad people came to us and said, "We want \$45,000,000 more money." We said to them, our answer was, as it was before, "We will not, as far as we are concerned, issue any bonds."

MR. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, my question calls for just an answer which could be expressed in figures—dollars and cents.

MR. KAHN. Yes; I am coming to the figures. I am trying to define how these figures are arrived at.

MR. PECORA. You see, I asked you for the total of fees, commissions, or profits or any other form of compensation which was paid to or accrued to your firm as a result of its identification with the Pennroad Corporation enterprise.

MR. KAHN. I am trying to answer it in the way in which the thing arose.

MR. PECORA. Well, if you could give us the total amount, then we will break it down.

MR. KAHN. I will be glad to give you the total amount, with the understanding that it will be broken down, because I do not like to create a wrong impression.

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. KAHN. The only fee which we received in connection with this transaction was when the second issue of 3,025,000 shares were issued, in connection with which an underwriting syndicate was formed, and in our opinion necessarily performed, for which we got a half a dollar a share commission, namely, \$1,512,500. That is the only fee we received.

Mr. PECORA. Well now, how about profits through the sale of stock that you acquired under your options?

Mr. KAHN. The third and fourth options were never exercised. They lapsed. All options lapsed except the first and second, which were at 16 and at 17, respectively. On these two options in 1929, when everything went up far beyond our expectations, we realized a profit of more than \$10 a share, namely, \$2,701,000.

Mr. PECORA. What profit did you derive from your acquiring the original block of 242,000 shares at \$15 a share?

Mr. KAHN. Of the 242,000 shares we gave back to the Pennsylvania Railroad at their request 25,000 shares at \$15 per share, even though at that time the market price was much higher.

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. KAHN. We gave them back to them. And on the remaining 217,000 shares our profit on selling and trading in the market was \$797,000.

Here, Mr. Pecora, I see you are shaking your head. You have got the figures, and I am not trying to withhold anything.

Mr. PECORA. No; I know you are not.

Mr. KAHN. In addition to the \$797,000 we received from the group which we formed to join the risk with us a commission—not a commission, a share in their profit, a share in the profit which they had realized, which aggregated \$391,000, and which represents what is called our management fee.

Mr. PECORA. So that from your operations with respect of that first block of 217,000 shares you received profits aggregating \$1,188,000 and odd?

Mr. KAHN. Including the management fee which we received not from the corporation but from the syndicate group.

Mr. PECORA. You received a profit of \$2,701,000 plus from exercising your options on 250,000 shares?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. That was the option referred to in this letter in evidence marked exhibit no. 22?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And you received profit of \$1,512,500 in December 1929, didn't you?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. In connection with underwriting 3,025,000 shares of Pennroad Corporation stock—that is, you received I think 50 cents a share on that?

Mr. KAHN. I should not like to call that a profit.

Mr. PECORA. Well, a compensation?

Mr. KAHN. Not from the Pennroad.

Mr. PECORA. Well, it certainly was not a gratuity, was it?

Mr. KAHN. Not from the Pennroad. We formed a syndicate. The figure is right.

Mr. PECORA. That was the profit accruing to your firm?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Whether it accrued from the sale of stock which you got at one price and sold at a higher price or whether it came from commissions or fees paid to you for managing underwriting syndicates, and so forth?

Mr. KAHN. Not only managing but being responsible.

Mr. PECORA. Assuming a responsibility?

Mr. KAHN. Assuming a complete obligation for 6 weeks, during which 6 weeks the panic of October 25 occurred, and during that panic we stood responsible for \$45,000,000.

Mr. PECORA. That responsibility was assumed by you and discharged by you in a fashion that returned a profit to you, didn't it?

Mr. KAHN. It might have returned a very heavy loss.

Mr. PECORA. I know, but I am speaking of what happened, not of what might have happened.

Mr. KAHN. Well, by the grace of God we got a profit when we stood the risk of a very heavy loss.

Mr. PECORA. Then didn't your firm make a profit of \$69,924.08 on or about December 11, 1929, in connection with a participation in an underwriting syndicate?

Mr. KAHN. Yes; we had a share in the underwriting syndicate on which we made that compensation; that is correct.

Mr. PECORA. Now, my calculation shows that these items total \$5,472,245.55, which your firm got as compensation, commission, or profit in connection with the sale of stock of the Pennroad Corporation between July 22, 1929, and December 11, 1929. Is that calculation correct, would you say?

Mr. KAHN. The facts are correct. I would like, if you will grant me an opportunity a little later on, to explain the facts, but your figure is correct.

Mr. PECORA. In addition to these sums your firm received certain commissions in connection with its purchase for the Pennroad Corporation of certain shares of the New York, New Haven & Hartford Railroad and shares of the Canton Co., which you referred to yesterday, didn't it?

Mr. KAHN. From the Pennroad Co. I believe you said the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.

Mr. PECORA. I meant from the Pennroad Co.

Mr. KAHN. From the Pennroad Co. we received no commission for the sale of the Canton Railroad. We received a commission from the vendor, which was known to the Pennroad Co., but I am just now advised that as a matter of fact we did receive certain commission from the Pennroad Co. for bringing this business to their attention and succeeding in obtaining it for them in spite of competition on the part of other people.

Mr. PECORA. What was the amount of that commission that your firm received in connection with the acquisition by the Pennroad Corporation of the stock of the Canton Co.?

Mr. KAHN. \$327,397.

Mr. PECORA. And what was the amount of the commission that your firm received in connection with its services in acquiring for the Pennroad Corporation certain stock of the New York, New Haven & Hartford Railroad?

Mr. KAHN. A trifling commission, Mr. Pecora. We were simply acting as brokers in buying things for them on the stock exchange.

Mr. PECORA. Well, as brokers you got commission?

Mr. KAHN. As brokers we got commissions. I should say roughly, being given the amount involved, that would amount to about \$40,000.

Mr. PECORA. That would make, with the commissions you received from the purchase for the Pennroad Corporation of the Canton Co. shares and the New York, New Haven & Hartford Co. shares, a total of about—

Mr. KAHN. \$5,840,000, approximately.

Mr. PECORA. Which your firm received in the year 1929?

Mr. KAHN. That is approximately correct; yes.

Mr. PECORA. What was the total amount raised by the Pennroad Corporation from the investing public from its sale of its stock to the public?

Mr. KAHN. Roughly speaking, \$133,000,000.

Mr. PECORA. So is it fair to say that the loss to those investors, measured by the depreciation in market value of those shares, is a little over \$100,000,000.

Mr. KAHN. I do not believe that that would be quite a correct description. A great many of those investors did sell. It is impossible to say whether the man who, for instance, holds the shares now at three and a half dollars has a loss or profit on them. I think all one can say is that if someone bought them at 15, which was the original issuing price, and later on 16½, and held them to the present day, there would be such loss.

Mr. PECORA. That is, there would be a loss of a little over a hundred million dollars, or to make it more accurate, about \$106,000,000, representing shrinkage in the market value of the stock of Pennroad Corporation, basing its present value on a figure of about 3½?

Mr. KAHN. If you do not want me to take the case of any one individual stockholder but collectively, yes.

Mr. PECORA. Now, may I ask, not by way of dropping the subject of Pennroad Corporation but merely in order that I may not overlook it, if you have now your balance sheet as of December 31, 1932.

(Mr. Kahn produced the document requested.)

Mr. PECORA. I offer in evidence a statement produced by the witness purporting to constitute the balance sheet of Kuhn, Loeb & Co., as of December 31, 1932, and ask that it be spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted and entered on the record.

(Kuhn, Loeb & Co. balance sheet as of December 31, 1932, was thereupon designated "Committee exhibit 23, June 30, 1933," and the same appears in the words and figures following:)

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 23, JUNE 30, 1933

Kuhn, Loeb & Co., balance sheet, Dec. 31, 1932

Cash-----	\$3, 600, 996. 62
Call loans secured by U.S. Government bonds-----	1, 000, 000. 00
All other loans-----	2, 279, 772. 85
Accounts receivable-----	1, 076, 009. 17
U.S. Treasury bills, certificates, and notes-----	18, 739, 404. 34
State and municipal bonds-----	3, 945, 804. 93
Other bonds and stocks-----	3, 624, 417. 19
Total-----	34, 266, 405. 10
Capital-----	17, 500, 000. 00
Deposits-----	15, 210, 248. 09
Accounts payable-----	1, 556, 157. 01
Total-----	34, 266, 405. 10

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, to what extent did your firm exercise the option granted to it by this letter of April 24, 1929, which is marked "Exhibit no. 22" in evidence?

Mr. KAHN. We only exercised the first and second option, that is, 125,000 shares at 16 and 125,000 shares at 17.

Mr. PECORA. When was the option exercised with respect to the 125,000 shares at 16?

Mr. KAHN. July 23, 1929.

Mr. PECORA. And what was the market value of the stock on that date?

Mr. KAHN. At that date I find that the market price was about 28¾.

Mr. PECORA. When did you exercise the option for the second block of 125,000 shares at \$17 a share under this option agreement?

Mr. KAHN. The following day.

Mr. PECORA. What was the market quotation for the stock on that day?

Mr. KAHN. The opening price on that day was 29¾.

Mr. PECORA. Now, prior to the date when you exercised your option rights with respect to those two blocks each of 125,000 shares had your firm gone short of this stock?

Mr. KAHN. We had what you might call traded in the stock and we had sold a portion of the 125,000 shares; yes.

Mr. PECORA. Sold it short—or sold it against the option?

Mr. KAHN. Sold it against the option; yes.

Mr. PECORA. I notice that the option gave you the right to buy that stock at any time up to—

Mr. KAHN. December 31, 1932.

Mr. PECORA. July 1, 1932, wasn't it? I am reading from the option itself, exhibit no. 22.

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir; that is quite right.

Mr. PECORA. So you got an option for a period of about 3¼ years?

Mr. KAHN. We got an option for a period—

Mr. PECORA. April 24, 1929, to July 1, 1932?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And that was the contingent compensation which your firm received for its services in advising as to the form of security that the Pennroad Corporation should issue?

Mr. KAHN. Mr. Pecora, we saved the company a great deal more than that. If the company had formed an underwriting for the original issue of 5,800,000 shares, it could not possibly have been consummated at that time without very considerable cost. It was a new security, the future of which no one could possibly guess. It could not possibly have been consummated for a compensation of less than a dollar and a half being given—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). When you say you gave the company all that advice you gave them, you mean you advised the company to issue an equity security like common stock instead of a fixed charge security like a bond or preferred stock?

Mr. KAHN. Not only that, but we advised them to do without underwriting.

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. KAHN. If they had formed an underwriting the cost of that underwriting would have been a great deal more than this thing is. We urged them to accept our advice, which was a very heavy responsibility that it took, and not to form an underwriting syndicate, and by the acceptance of that advice they saved a great deal more than the figure which you have mentioned.

Mr. PECORA. But it was for giving that advice that you received a form of contingent compensation under which you actually realized within 6 or 8 months time profits of over \$5,000,000 didn't you?

Mr. KAHN. No one was more surprised than we were.

Mr. PECORA. You mean at the smallness of the profit you received or the magnitude of it?

Mr. KAHN. At the size which this contingent compensation assumed, solely through the action of the market and solely through the fact that at that time, which as I said before, was a time of mania, people would buy securities at utterly unreasonable prices. We could not know that and we could not know how soon it would stop. We believed that it would last for a certain length of time to enable the Pennsylvania to make that issue at 15.

Mr. PECORA. Well, didn't you know from the operations of the market prior to April 1929 that by reason of this "perfect mania" that you referred to in those terms on Tuesday equity securities would sell more freely than senior securities, such as bonds or preferred stocks?

Mr. KAHN. My attention is called to the fact—which perhaps is as good an answer as I can give—that no possible knowledge, no possible estimate, was thinkable at that time. The best proof of that is that the second syndicate started at a time when the market price was 24, and within a few weeks the market price was 15.

Mr. PECORA. Well, you are speaking now of a time subsequent to October 24, 1929, aren't you?

Mr. KAHN. No; I am speaking of the time now—the second syndicate, if I recall correctly, was formed in September, wasn't it?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. October 8.

Mr. KAHN. October the 8th, and within a very short period we had—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). You had noticed the course in the market of the common stock of the Alleghany Corporation prior to April 1929, had you not?

Mr. KAHN. No doubt.

Mr. PECORA. You know that that stock was issued to the organizers or the bankers at \$20 a share?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. On the very date of issue—

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. It was traded in in the market at \$35 a share, or thereabouts, and continued to rise?

Mr. KAHN. Quite true, but—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). Throughout the spring of 1929?

Mr. KAHN. But how could we possibly have known that that would continue? How could we possibly have known that our options at 16 and 17 would prove profitable and our options at 18 and 19 were utterly waste?

Mr. PECORA. But there was no obligation on your part by this option agreement of April 24, 1929, to exercise your option unless you wanted to?

Mr. KAHN. That is quite true.

Mr. PECORA. And you had until July 1, 1932, within which to exercise the option?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. So that you were taking absolutely no risk in accepting compensation in this form, were you?

Mr. KAHN. We were taking no risk, but we got no compensation. We got no compensation which was worth at that time any tangible amount whatsoever.

Mr. PECORA. Let us see about that. At what quotations were the first trades made on the open market of Pennroad Corporation stock?

Mr. KAHN. April 25. The first trade was made at 25.

Mr. PECORA. You received this option on April 24 to buy 125,000 shares at any time thereafter, up to July 1, 1932, at \$16 a share; 125,000 at \$17; 125,000 at \$18; and 125,000 at \$19, did you not?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. So that within 24 hours after this option was granted to you as a contingent compensation for your services you knew that you had a form of agreement for compensation from which you could have netted immediately several million dollars?

Mr. KAHN. I do not believe we could, Mr. Pecora. The market was very thin, very small. If we had attempted to sell at anything like that figure, we would have gotten nowhere.

Mr. PECORA. You knew on April 25 that you were, under this option agreement, in a position to receive not a contingent compensation but a contingent compensation that would run into several millions of dollars?

Mr. KAHN. We had no such idea, and no one was more surprised than we were. The fact is—I have the figures here before me—that in May the stock on which was based that contingent compensation which you appraise at several millions of dollars was worth in the market 16¼ percent. That is just about what it would have cost us. They were given to us at 16, 17, 18, and 19. Our contingent compensation at 18 or 19 was never worth anything; Our contingent compensation at 16 was worth practically nothing in May, which was 1 month after we got it. Our contingent compensation at 17 was worth nothing in May.

Mr. PECORA. Your contingent compensation under this agreement was worth over \$5,000,000, as it turned out, within 6 or 8 months?

Mr. KAHN. Not merely the contingent compensation. Our compensation on the options plus the fee which we got from the syndicate for underwriting the second issue and for managing.

May I add one more answer? You have permitted me to make a few remarks. They will be very short. It is simply this, that during the existence of the group which with us had about 217,000 shares, until that group had disposed of its shares we did not sell one share of stock against our option. We did not think it would be decent to do so. During the time that we stood there waiting for the group to sell these 217,000 shares our option might very well have gone up the flue. It didn't, but that was not our knowledge, our fore knowledge.

I also want to say that as to the Canton transaction about which you have inquired, we succeeded in getting it at a very materially lower price than the Pennroad would have been willing to pay for it.

Mr. PECORA. Will you describe that negotiation for us, the negotiation by which the Pennroad Corporation, through your firm, purchased these shares of the Canton Co.?

Mr. KAHN. I doubt whether I am capable to speak to you on that, of my own knowledge. Heretofore I have spoken of my own knowledge. At that time I was not here, and I am speaking from hearsay. Maybe somebody else can speak from the actual facts. [Addressing Mr. Buttenwieser:] Can you speak from the actual facts?

All I know is that when I came back, and during the time I was away I was informed that they had called the attention of the Pennroad to the opportunity of buying an exceedingly important and desirable terminal property in Baltimore; that others were after it, and by negotiating skill or by good luck we obtained it at a price materially below the price at which the Pennroad was willing to buy it. We immediately offered it at the price at which we were able to obtain it. We brought it to their attention before we spoke to any other competitor—we never did speak to any other competitor, even though we knew there were competitors in the field, but we offered it to the Pennroad.

[After conferring with associates.] I am trying to get the story from someone who knows it of his own knowledge. I cannot get any more definite knowledge than I have already imparted to you. We succeeded in obtaining it at the lowest price that the Pennroad was willing to pay for it. We got it for them at that price plus a commission of which both the seller and the purchaser had knowledge.

Mr. PECORA. What agreement was made between your firm and the Pennroad Corporation with respect to your purchasing for the Pennroad Corporation these shares of the Canton Co.?

Mr. KAHN. What agreement was made?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. KAHN. We acted as brokers.

Mr. PECORA. Was any resolution adopted by the board of directors of the Pennroad Corporation authorizing you to go and acquire for that corporation the shares of the Canton Co.?

Mr. KAHN. I have no doubt there is such a resolution. We are trying to look it up.

[After searching records.] I do not know, Mr. Pecora, whether you are waiting for an answer to the question with regard to the Canton resolution?

Mr. PECORA. Yes, sir.

Mr. KAHN. That is the only thing which we can find [handing a book to Mr. Pecora]. I have marked it in pencil.

The CHAIRMAN. While Mr. Pecora is looking at that, may I ask one or two questions?

Mr. Gilbert H. Kahn is your son?

Mr. KAHN. Is Gilbert Kahn my son?

The CHAIRMAN. Yes.

Mr. KAHN. Yes, Senator.

The CHAIRMAN. He is one of your partners now?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

The CHAIRMAN. Your firm, or at least Kuhn, Loeb & Co., have been for some sixty-odd years engaged in banking?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, Senator.

The CHAIRMAN. And during that time you have maintained relations with foreign countries? I think you recite that in your articles of incorporation.

Mr. KAHN. We have maintained relations with foreign countries; not very actively. It would be perhaps more correct to say that we have for many years maintained friendly relations with the leading concerns in foreign countries, but we have never been very active. We maintain a slight, small balance with them and they maintain a small balance with us. We exchange friendly letters. We send one another cables of congratulations at the end of the year; but we have never been very active in European affairs.

The CHAIRMAN. With what foreign countries do you now maintain these business relations?

Mr. KAHN. I do not believe we are very welcome in Germany amongst the Nazis. So to a large extent close relations have ceased there. We still have relations with several banks in England, several banks in France, several banks in the Scandinavian countries, and in Holland; and when I say "banks" I include, of course, private bankers equally. I think, sir, that probably exhausts the list. We have no particular relations in South American or Central American countries. Our activities are mainly confined to those which I have mentioned.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. I might say, Mr. Chairman, that the particular reason why that phrase is used is that it was one of the requirements under the laws of the State of New York. Partnerships having relations with foreign countries are permitted to continue the firm name after the death of the partners.

The CHAIRMAN. I am not quite sure that it is important, perhaps, in this connection, but I might inquire about these partners. For instance, Mr. Felix Warburg—is he still alive?

Mr. KAHN. He is still alive. He is not very active in the firm. He is giving most of his time to charitable affairs, and has for a number of years. But he is still alive and still a partner.

The CHAIRMAN. And Mr. Schiff?

Mr. KAHN. Mr. Mortimer Schiff died a few years ago. His son John Schiff is a partner.

The CHAIRMAN. How about Mr. Elisha Walker?

Mr. KAHN. Mr. Elisha Walker became a partner at the first of the year, the first of 1933, January of 1933.

The CHAIRMAN. He is still active, is he?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

The CHAIRMAN. That is all.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know Frank E. Taplin?

Mr. KAHN. I have met him a few times.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Chairman, the reason I ask that is that we are in receipt of a telegram this morning from Mr. Taplin addressed to the Sergeant at Arms of the Senate, reading as follows:

Your subpoena requesting me to appear Washington 10 o'clock this morning was not delivered to me New York until 11 o'clock today, making it impossible to appear as requested. If you will advise me care Union Trust Building, Cleveland, Ohio, tomorrow, will be glad to appear next week.

It is signed "F. E. Taplin."

The CHAIRMAN. I thought he was here yesterday.

Mr. PECORA. We subpoenaed him or, rather, had a subpoena out for him, calling for his attendance here yesterday. We first sought to subpoena him in Cleveland, where, as I understand it, he has his home as well as his place of business, but the United States marshal, when the subpoena was given for service, learned that he was then in New York. Upon communicating that fact to me I caused a subpoena to be issued and delivered to the United States marshal in New York for service on Mr. Taplin. That subpoena was served on Mr. Taplin, apparently, according to this telegram, yesterday morning in New York, and it called for his attendance here in Washington yesterday morning. Mr. Taplin, instead of coming on here anyway, sends this telegram, thinking to appear next week. I think the testimony would be of some importance, because, according to the testimony heretofore given, Mr. Taplin was used by the Pennroad Corporation for the acquisition in its behalf of a large block of stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railroad Co. at \$170 a share, and I understand the public quotation for the stock was around \$110 to \$145.

This telegram appears to have been filed for forwarding at 5:57 p.m. June 29, 1933.

The CHAIRMAN. It looks as if he could have been here today.

Mr. PECORA. He could have been here yesterday. It was served at 11 o'clock, New York time, which is 10 o'clock Washington time. He could have taken any one of several trains yesterday afternoon.

The CHAIRMAN. Plainly, he cannot get here now before our recess comes.

Mr. PECORA. I imagine that Mr. Taplin reads the newspapers, and probably learned that this committee was still in session, holding hearings daily.

Senator STEIWER. Do you contemplate holding a session tomorrow?

The CHAIRMAN. We were in hopes of finishing today.

Senator STEIWER. If we were assured that he could be here tomorrow, we might remain in session.

Mr. KAHN. I would like to make it very emphatic that to the best of my knowledge I did not know Mr. Taplin at that time. I did not have the faintest idea of the transaction.

The CHAIRMAN. I think we ought to have him here tomorrow or Wednesday.

Senator BARKLEY. I think we would probably receive a similar telegram if we tried to get him back here tomorrow.

Mr. PECORA. He is apparently on his way to Cleveland, because he said to telephone him or wire him at Cleveland; but he does not send us that telegram until 7 hours after he was subpoenaed.

The CHAIRMAN. Without objection, we will ask Mr. Taplin to be here on next Wednesday, and when we recess we will recess until Wednesday. Have him subpoenaed for Wednesday at 10 o'clock.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, in answer to my question as to the adoption of any resolution by the directors of the Pennroad Corporation authorizing you to acquire in behalf of that corporation stock of the Canton Co. you call my attention to a resolution adopted at the meeting of the board of directors on June 12, 1929?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. At which were present Messrs. Atterbury, Morris, Ingersoll, Rue, Cooke, Mellon, County, and Lee. The resolution reads as follows, with its preamble:

The question of the acquisition of the stock of the Canton Co. of Baltimore, Md., was presented, whereupon, after discussion, the following resolution was adopted:

Resolved, That the president is hereby authorized to proceed with the acquisition of the whole or any part, not less, however, than 51 percent, of the outstanding stock or voting-trust certificates representing stock of the said company, at a price of \$596 per share plus costs and commission incident to the transaction."

Mr. Kahn, when did your firm acquire this stock of the Canton Co. on behalf of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. KAHN. As I said, Mr. Pecora, I am now speaking from information furnished me by others; and I say that because heretofore I have testified about matters of my own knowledge. But this is information supplied to me. And I understand that as far as any physical connection on our part is concerned it did not pass through our office. We brought these people into contact with the Pennroad people, and to the best of my knowledge and belief the transaction was consummated between them. I might, when I go back to my office, find some papers bearing on the subject; but I haven't got anything here now except this resolution.

Mr. PECORA. Which member of your firm, or which representative of your firm, actually brought the owner of the Canton Co. stock to the attention of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. KAHN. Well, presumably it was Mr. Mortimer Schiff who, after my departure for a vacation, became the principal active element in all these matters. Presumably he did. But I could not tell you definitely. I shall try to find out if you wish me to.

Mr. PECORA. When was the sale of the Canton Co. stock to the Pennroad Corporation effected?

Mr. KAHN. I believe the resolution states it, does it not? (Addressing an associate.) There is circumstantial evidence, Mr. Pecora, that it was effective on July 23, 1929, but it is circumstantial evidence only. I shall be glad to look through my files and find any item that may bear upon this matter, and furnish it to you if you wish it done.

Mr. PECORA. Who was the gentleman who owned the stock of the Canton Co. which was sold to the Pennroad Corporation? Was that Mr. Colgate?

Mr. KAHN. Mr. Colgate was one of them. It was owned by an old family estate or combination of people in Baltimore who had had it, as I understand it, for many years. Mr. Colgate, to the best of my knowledge, was the principal manager in the handling of the transaction on behalf of a number of Baltimore people.

Mr. PECORA. Was that stock a listed stock?

Mr. KAHN. Not in New York. There may have been a nominal quotation in Baltimore, but it is very unlikely.

Mr. PECORA. When did your firm first learn that the Pennroad Corporation desired to enter into any negotiations leading to the acquisition by it of 51 percent or more of the stock of the Canton Co.?

Mr. KAHN. Presumably when we brought it to their attention—and there again I say, presumably; it must have been a few weeks before they reached the conclusion that they wanted to buy it.

Mr. PECORA. Who took the initiative in any negotiations that culminated in the purchase of the Canton Co. stock at \$596 a share plus costs and so forth?

Mr. KAHN. In all likelihood it was Mr. Mortimer Schiff.

Mr. PECORA. Had there been any previous request or expression of desire on the part of the directors of the Pennroad Corporation to acquire that holding?

Mr. KAHN (after conferring with associates). None of us know of our own knowledge, and I am afraid I cannot give you any definite information on that.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, Mr. Mortimer Schiff is now dead, is he not?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Is there any other member of your firm who has any personal knowledge of this transaction?

Mr. KAHN. I am trying to find out now by inquiring among my associates whether they knew anything definite and tangible which they could testify about.

Mr. PECORA. All right. Tell me if you can learn about it.

Mr. KAHN. I assume, and they suggest to me, that no doubt Mr. Harry Lee, the president of the Pennroad Corporation, could give you all the details that you want on the subject.

Mr. PECORA. Does Mr. Hanauer, a former member of your firm and whom I see is here present, know anything about it?

Mr. KAHN. He says he attended no conference in the matter; attended no negotiations in the matter. He has some general knowledge of it. But I cannot tell you more than we have none of our knowledge. If there is anything we can find in our office bearing on the subject, you shall have it when we get back.

Mr. PECORA. All right. This is a transaction in which your firm received a commission of some three hundred and odd thousand dollars?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. By whom was that commission paid?

Mr. KAHN. By the Pennroad Corporation.

Mr. PECORA. What was the rate of that commission?

Mr. KAHN. Two and a half percent on the purchase price.

Mr. PECORA. That was far in excess of the usual commission allowed for the purchase of securities, wasn't it, by exchanges?

Mr. KAHN. Oh, it was not an exchange contract.

Mr. PECORA. I know it was not, but it was far in excess of that rate, wasn't it?

Mr. KAHN. It was not at all in excess of what was the usual rate for that kind of transaction, where you do not deal through the exchange but deal through your own skill, through your own negotiating capacity, through your own search for an opportunity. It is, I believe, less than is allowed a real-estate broker for effecting a sale of a country estate. And that was surely a country estate.

Mr. PECORA. Do you say that this terminal property was a country estate?

Mr. KAHN. In the sense in which I use the term; yes. It had no readily available stock market. And in the sense I use the comparison I think it might be fairly compared to a country estate for which you are to find a customer, because there is no ready market for it. There is no quoted market for it.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, I notice at page 638 of the Splawn report in regard to the Pennroad Corporation, that as of April 30, 1930, the investments which the Pennroad Corporation had made in pursuance of its general plan or purpose to protect the integrity of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., included the investment in one share of Bloomfield Hills Country Club stock. Do you know anything about that? [Laughter.]

Mr. KAHN. Not a thing. No; I do not know.

Mr. PECORA. I understand from this report that the share of stock in that country club, which is located at Detroit, Mich., carried membership privileges for the use of Mr. Frank, the president of the Detroit, Toledo & Ironton Railway Co. And I understand that \$5,000 was paid for that one share of stock. Do you know how essential the acquisition of that share of stock was to the protection of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.'s interests and integrity?

Mr. KAHN. May I say that I did not merely refer to protection. I referred to the defense, to the expansion, and to the strategic desirability of acquisitions in the first instance of the Pennsylvania Railroad, and to the benefit also eventually of the Pennroad Corporation stockholders. I cannot conceive now in what way this particular purchase falls into any of those categories.

Senator BARKLEY. Well, it might have been necessary to develop one's physical stamina in order that he might protect himself and his associates, I suppose. [Laughter.] In that way it might have been beneficial.

Mr. KAHN. I do not know about that.

The CHAIRMAN. When did Mr. Hanauer cease to be a partner in the firm of Kuhn, Loeb & Co., Mr. Kahn?

Mr. KAHN. At the end of last year.

The CHAIRMAN. On December 31, 1932?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

The CHAIRMAN. He was a partner and had to do with the handling of the Chicago, Milwaukee & St. Paul Railroad reorganization and receivership and so forth, didn't he?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

The CHAIRMAN. Representing the firm?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Senator BARKLEY. Mr. Pecora, this has no bearing upon the subject you are investigating at this moment, but I should like to ask a question.

Mr. PECORA. Certainly, Senator Barkley.

Senator BARKLEY. Mr. Kahn, has your firm taken any part in the selection of receivers appointed by Federal courts for railroads now in receivership?

Mr. KAHN. I always understood that that was up to the judge.

Senator BARKLEY. Of course it is, but has your firm either by objection or by recommendation played any part in the appointment of receivers, or sought to take any part in the appointment of receivers of railroads now in receivership?

Mr. KAHN. It is conceivable, Senator Barkley—and you will understand that I have to answer that question in a general way—it is conceivable that we might have been asked whether so-and-so is competent and a well-informed man for the position, whether in our judgment Mr. Smith or Mr. Brown would be capable from our knowledge of him to accomplish the difficult and complicated functions of a receiver. It is probable that in such case we would answer yes or no as the case might be. Beyond that I know of no instance, and I know of no part which we ever played in attempting to exercise any function relating to the appointment of particular receivers.

Senator BARKLEY. Do you know whether your firm has recently objected to the inclusion of a certain man on the panel for receiverships in connection with the Frisco Railroad?

Mr. KAHN. Oh, I am sure that we did not. We have nothing to do with the Frisco in any way whatever.

Senator BARKLEY. You have not had?

Mr. KAHN. Surely not.

Senator BARKLEY. Is there any financial relationship existing at all between your firm and the Frisco Railroad?

Mr. KAHN. No, sir.

Senator BARKLEY. Or the Missouri Pacific?

Mr. KAHN. I should say that the Missouri Pacific, under its present management at least, is, as I understand, under the control of the Van Sweringen interests. They would not be likely to ask us. In fact, they did not.

Senator BARKLEY. So that your answer is “no” to both of those questions?

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

The CHAIRMAN. You are called on, aren't you, for advice at times in reference to whether receivers should be appointed or not in connection with some railroad corporation?

Mr. KAHN. Oh, that does happen in a very general way. That is, as financial advisers it is more than likely that we would be asked: Now, do you see any way in which this thing can be financed? Do you see any way in which this thing can be saved? Is there any method that you can propose by which a security the public will take and which you are justified in offering to the public could be created in order to help the property out of its difficult situation? And it would depend upon the circumstances of the case as to what our answer would be. If we did not feel that we could honestly take

the responsibility for inviting the public to come in, and that is a great risk, merely in order to avoid the nuisance, and perhaps the disgrace, of a receivership, we would say: No; we know of no such way. On the other hand, if there was a possibility by which, by suggesting a new financial scheme, we could be helpful in saving a difficult situation we would attempt to save it.

The CHAIRMAN. Well, worse things can happen to a railroad than being put in the hands of receivers, can't they?

Mr. KAHN. Yes and no. It might be to the immediate advantage of a railroad to be placed in the hands of receivers. But, after all, the railroads are a part of our general industrial and credit system. If you shake the confidence of any part of that system you are not rendering any service to the community at large. And as long as it is possible to avoid receiverships of importance which would be adjudged both here and in Europe as reflecting the situation in America, whereby really important and weighty elements of American financial structure go down, it is better to avoid them if it can consistently be done without damage to the railroad.

The CHAIRMAN. Sometimes a receiver can operate a property, increase its earnings and reduce its expenses, to the advantage both of the public and of the railroad, isn't that true sometimes?

Mr. KAHN. It is true sometimes. But generally speaking I doubt whether a receiver can operate more cheaply or more advantageously in the interest of the public or of the railroad than can be done by a competent manager. If a manager is incompetent get rid of him.

The CHAIRMAN. Well, of course if that is more desirable it can be done. But occasionally a receiver will reduce some very exorbitant salaries of certain officers in the management of a railroad.

Mr. KAHN. Yes. I know that has occurred. But the term "exorbitant salaries", if I may say so, is a somewhat relative term. The rare thing is to find a man of outstanding ability. And the best investment I have always said that one can make is to find a man who has outstanding ability and attach him to you. If you want to get such men and if you want to keep them, you have to pay them the going rate or they won't stay but will go somewhere else. And I know of many instances of that kind, where people thought the salary paid to them was inadequate and that they could improve themselves by going elsewhere, and so they quit. So it is a matter of adjusting the situation to the going market rate, how cheap can you get a good man and keep him.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, in the circular letter addressed to the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. under date of April 24, 1929, offering them the right to subscribe at \$15 a share for 5,800,000 shares originally issued by the Pennroad Corporation, which was put in evidence on yesterday, and which appears at page 629 of the stenographic record of this hearing, mention is made in the following language, and I am reading from page 630 of the minutes, of the option rights that were granted to your firm by the Pennroad Corporation:

The certificate of incorporation provides for an authorized issue of 10,000,000 shares of common stock without par value, of which, as above stated, 5,800,000 are now being offered. The balance is reserved for future use, including shares reserved against options which have been granted in connection with the organization of the corporation to purchase additional common stock of the

corporation on or before July 1, 1932, as follows: 125,000 shares at \$16 per share, 125,000 shares at \$17 per share, 125,000 shares at \$18 per share, and 125,000 shares at \$19 per share. No officers or directors of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. participate in such options.

Do you know of any reason why in this circular letter making this offer to the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. the officers of the Pennroad Corporation did not include mention of the fact that those options had been granted to your firm?

Mr. KAHN. I have mentioned that before, Mr. Pecora. At that particular time, when this entirely new and untried issue was offered, not to the public but to the shareholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., we did not wish to bring any influence whatsoever upon the judgment of the shareholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. whether they should or should not avail themselves of that right. And we believed that if we had permitted it to be said that we accepted those options as our sole compensation it would exercise a certain influence on those stockholders, and so we deliberately did not wish to exercise any such influence.

Mr. PECORA. Did your firm retain all the profits it made from the resale of the stock it purchased under this option, or did it distribute any of those profits to any other persons?

Mr. KAHN. We retained all of them.

Mr. PECORA. Now, do you recall that in the fall of 1929 application was made to list this Pennroad Corporation stock to the stock-listing committee of the Philadelphia Stock Exchange?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Are you familiar with the correspondence that passed between the president of the Pennroad Corporation and your firm in connection with such application?

Mr. KAHN. Not with my firm, but—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). Well, with a member of your firm, Mr. Bovenizer.

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Have you here the letter or any copy thereof that was sent to Mr. Bovenizer, who was a member of your firm, by Mr. H. H. Lee, president of the Pennroad Corporation, under date of October 19, 1929?

Mr. KAHN. I think we have it here. Yes; we have it.

Mr. PECORA. Will you produce it for the record, please?

Mr. KAHN. Is it a letter dated the 19th of October 1929?

Mr. PECORA. Yes, sir.

Mr. KAHN. Here it is.

Mr. PECORA. I offer this letter in evidence and ask that it may be spread on the record of the hearings.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted, and the committee reporter will make it a part of the hearings.

(The letter was marked "Committee Exhibit No. 24, June 30, 1933," and is as follows:)

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 24

THE PENNROAD CORPORATION,
Philadelphia, Pa., October 19, 1929.

MR. GEORGE W. BOVENIZER,
c/o MESSRS. KUHN, LOEB & Co.,
New York City.

DEAR GEORGE: Enclosed herewith is a draft of application to the stock list committee of the Philadelphia Stock Exchange covering the new issue of voting-trust certificates for common stock of this corporation.

You will notice that we have included in the application, request for authority to list the 125,000 shares which you may take on option warrants. The fact that these additional optional warrants are included is pretty well hidden and only a careful analysis of the present application with the previous one would disclose the fact that they have been included. I feel that probably this is the best way to handle it because if you should exercise your option we would have to make a special application for the listing of 125,000 more shares.

Will you please let me have the benefit of your criticism of this application, returning the draft to me?

Very truly yours,

H. H. LEE, *President.*

MR. PECORA. The letter reads as follows: (Thereupon counsel read the letter above recorded.) Now, Mr. Kahn, do you know of any reason why this stock-listing application should have been so drafted as to hide the fact of the first option granted to your firm for the purchase of 125,000 shares of the Pennroad Corporation referred to in this letter?

MR. KAHN. Mr. Pecora, I have the stock-listing application here before me in its final form. It sets forth in two conspicuous places that that option had been granted to us. It not only so sets forth but it furthermore is accompanied by a letter, which I shall be glad to show you, showing that our attorneys insisted in their advice that it must be so phrased.

MR. PECORA. But what I am asking you now is: Do you know of any reason why Mr. Lee should have wanted to draft an application for listing in a fashion that would hide, or has he put this, "is pretty well hidden", referring to the fact of the inclusion of these additional option warrants?

MR. KAHN. There was no such reason whatsoever, and the moment it came to our attention we insisted that our option must be fully disclosed. And it is disclosed. What motive, or what imp of mischief guided Mr. Lee's pen when he drafted or dictated this letter, I could not possibly imagine. I only know that the moment it came to our notice we said: Of course it must contain a full disclosure of that option. And it does.

MR. PECORA. Have you a copy of the letter that you sent to Mr. Lee in reply to this one dated October 19, 1929?

MR. KAHN. We sent no letter to Mr. Lee. I asked Mr. Bovenizer about it, and he says the whole thing was handled by the lawyers thereafter. What particular expressions the lawyer used in speaking to Mr. Lee about this particular phrase—which, as I say, an imp of mischief must have dictated—I do not know. I only know that here is a letter which was sent by the vice president of the Pennroad Corporation enclosing to us for our information the application to the Philadelphia Stock Exchange, and which application does contain in two conspicuous places a disclosure of that option.

MR. PECORA. Yes; I understand that—

The CHAIRMAN (interposing). Mr. Kahn, did you dispose of your Pennroad Corporation stock in 1929?

Mr. KAHN. We disposed of the first two options in 1929, yes, Senator Fletcher. And we disposed of the 217,000 shares which were bought by us together with that group.

The CHAIRMAN. At about what price, do you remember?

Mr. KAHN. I have the prices here, no doubt.

The CHAIRMAN. Do I understand that it has already appeared that you made a profit on that stock of something like \$5,000,000?

Mr. KAHN. We made a profit not merely on that stock but on that stock together with a fee which we received for this issue of 3,025,000 shares made subsequent to the first issue, which aggregated about \$5,100,000. Mr. Pecora has brought that out.

The CHAIRMAN. And that did not include the commission or brokerage fee on the Baltimore property?

Mr. PECORA. On the Canton Co. property.

Mr. KAHN. No; it did not.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Mr. Pecora, might I substitute a copy for that original letter, Committee exhibit no. 24, which was furnished to you and which you made a part of the record?

Mr. PECORA. Certainly.

Mr. PECORA. I offer in evidence the letter of October 31, 1929, from S. H. Ogden, vice president of the Pennroad Corporation, addressed to Mr. P. M. Stewart, care of Kuhn, Loeb & Co., enclosing copy of the application to list additional voting-trust certificates on the Philadelphia Stock Exchange.

The CHAIRMAN. It may be received and spread upon the record.

(Letter of October 31, 1929, from S. H. Ogden, vice president, the Pennroad Corporation, addressed to Mr. P. M. Stewart, care of Kuhn, Loeb & Co., enclosing application to list, was received in evidence, marked "Committee Exhibit 25, of June 30, 1933", and is printed in full in the record, as follows:)

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT 25, JUNE 30, 1933

THE PENNROAD CORPORATION,
Philadelphia, Pa., October 31, 1929.

Mr. P. M. STEWART,
*% Messrs. Kuhn, Loeb & Co.,
New York.*

DEAR MR. STEWART: Enclosed is a copy of the application to list additional voting-trust certificates on the Philadelphia Stock Exchange. This application was prepared in the form suggested after my conference with Mr. Adkins last week and is satisfactory to the Philadelphia Stock Exchange. You will note that no balance sheet has been inserted.

Will you please let me know as promptly as possible if this is satisfactory to you?

Very truly yours,

S. H. OGDEN, *Vice President.*

THE PENNROAD CORPORATION

(Incorporated under the laws of the State of Delaware)

VOTING TRUST CERTIFICATES FOR COMMON STOCK

922 COMMERCIAL TRUST BUILDING,
Philadelphia, Pa., October 28, 1929.*To the Stock List Committee, Philadelphia Stock Exchange:*

Referring to the previous application, dated August 21, 1929, W. W. Atterbury, Effingham B. Morris, and Jay Cooke—voting trustees under a certain agreement dated May 1, 1929, between the Pennroad Corporation, owners of common stock of the Pennroad Corporation, and the said W. W. Atterbury, Effingham B. Morris, and Jay Cooke (hereinafter referred to as voting trustees)—hereby make application for the listing on the Philadelphia Stock Exchange, upon official notice of issuance, of an additional issue of temporary voting trust certificates for common stock, without par value, of the Pennroad Corporation, a Delaware corporation (hereinafter referred to as the corporation) as follows: 3,025,000 shares offered to holders of voting trust certificates for common stock of the Pennroad Corporation; and 125,000 shares on the exercise of an option as hereinafter described; making the total number of shares now applied for and those previously listed 9,450,000, with authority to admit to the list, upon official notice of issuance, and in exchange for such temporary voting trust certificates, permanent engraved voting trust certificates for common stock.

All of the shares represented by the said voting trust certificates are, or will be when issued, fully paid and nonassessable, and no personal liability attaches to the stockholders.

DESCRIPTION OF ISSUE

The present voting trust certificates are in temporary form, but are exchangeable for permanent engraved certificates when ready for delivery. Voting trust certificates are issued in pursuance of the aforementioned agreement dated May 1, 1929, in respect of shares of common stock, without par value, of the corporation deposited with the voting trustees as specified therein. The holders of such voting trust certificates are entitled to receive on May 1, 1930, or upon the earlier termination of such agreement, as therein provided, a certificate or certificates, expressed to be fully paid, for the specified number of shares of the common stock, without par value, of the corporation, and in the meantime to receive payments equal to the amount of dividends, if any, received by the voting trustees under said agreement upon a like number of shares of such stock, less any taxes, except as provided in said agreement, imposed thereon which the voting trustees may be required or permitted to pay thereon, or to withhold therefrom under any present or future law of the United States of America, or any State, county, municipality, or other taxing authority therein. Until the actual delivery of the certificates for the stock called for by voting trust certificates, the voting trustees possess, and are entitled to exercise, all rights and powers of absolute owners of such stock, including the right to vote for every purpose and to consent to any corporate act of the corporation, it being expressly stipulated that no voting right in respect of such stock passes by or under the voting trust certificates or by or under said agreement to the holders of voting trust certificates by implication or otherwise.

Three million twenty-five thousand shares of the additional common stock, as represented by voting trust certificates, now applied for, was authorized by the action of the board of directors of September 25, 1929, and was offered to the holders of voting trust certificates of record at the close of business on October 18, 1929, at \$16.50 per share, to the extent of 50 percent of their holdings.

One hundred and twenty-five thousand shares of such additional common stock, represented by voting trust certificates, are subject to an option to purchase such stock at \$16.50 per share, on or before December 31, 1929.

The corporation sent a circular on October 8, 1929, to the holders of voting trust certificates representing common stock, a certified copy of which is attached, marked "Exhibit A."

THE CORPORATION

The corporation was incorporated under the laws of the State of Delaware on April 24, 1929, with a perpetual charter. It is possessed of broad powers, among others, to invest its funds in securities of any corporation or other agency, including those engaged in transportation of any description on land, on water, or by air, but without power to operate railroads.

The certificate of incorporation provides for an authorized issue of 10,000,000 shares of common stock without par value, of which 6,050,000 shares have been issued and voting trust certificates for 3,025,000 have been offered to stockholders of record as aforesaid, the balance being reserved for future issue, including shares reserved against options which have been granted to purchase additional common stock of the corporation.

Holders of the common stock will have the right to subscribe pro rata to future additional issues of common stock sold for cash, except stock issued upon exercise of options or option warrants as more fully set out in the certificate of incorporation. The common stock has no other preemptive right, except as may be granted by the board of directors, in respect of any particular issue of stock or securities. Of the proceeds of the common stock to be issued, as above provided, \$10 per share is to be capital, and the remainder paid-in surplus not available for dividends on the common stock. Under the terms of the offering the entire issue of common stock now authorized will be deposited with the voting trustees under the said agreement of May 1, 1929, and the subscribers will receive voting trust certificates for common stock in respect thereof.

MANAGEMENT

The management of the Pennroad Corporation is vested solely in its board of directors. The present directors are:

W. W. Atterbury, Effingham B. Morris, Charles E. Ingersoll, Levi L. Rue, Jay Cooke, A. J. County, and Henry H. Lee, Philadelphia, Pa.; and R. B. Mellon, Pittsburgh, Pa.

OFFICERS

Henry H. Lee, president; Samuel H. Ogden, vice president and treasurer; W. U. Moyer, vice president, secretary, and assistant treasurer; C. Bidlingmeyer, assistant secretary and assistant treasurer; R. P. Andrews, auditor.

VOTING TRUSTEES

W. W. Atterbury, Broad Street Station, Philadelphia, Pa.; Effingham B. Morris, Broad and Chestnut Sts., Philadelphia, Pa.; Jay Cooke, 1428 Walnut Street, Philadelphia, Pa.

The agent of the voting trustees is the Philadelphia National Bank.

The transfer agents of the voting trustees are C. Bidlingmeyer, room 1021, Commercial Trust Building, Philadelphia, Pa.; W. U. Moyer, 1434 Hudson Terminal Building, 30 Church Street, New York, N.Y.

The registrars of the voting trust certificates are Girard Trust Co., Broad and Chestnut Streets, Philadelphia, Pa.; Chemical Bank & Trust Co., New York City, N.Y.

FINANCIAL STATEMENT

As the corporation was organized on April 24, 1929, no earning statement is as yet available, nor has any balance sheet been published or furnished to us; nor have any dividends been paid on the stock.

GENERAL

The voting trustees agree with the Philadelphia Stock Exchange as follows: Not to make any change of a transfer agency or of a registrar of their stock, nor of a trustee of their bonds, or other securities, without previous notice to the stock-list committee.

To notify the stock exchange in the event of the issuance of any rights or subscriptions to or allotments of securities and afford the holders of listed securities a proper period within which to record their interests, and when possible, all rights, subscriptions, or allotments shall be transferable, payable, and deliverable in the city of Philadelphia.

To notify the stock exchange of the issuance of additional amounts of listed securities and make immediate application for the listing thereof.

To give at least 10 days' notice in advance of the closing of the books or the taking of a record of holders for any purpose.

To have on hand at all times a sufficient supply of certificates to meet the demands for transfer.

The fiscal year of the corporation ends on December 31.

The annual meeting of the stockholders of the corporation is held at the principal office of the company in Wilmington, Del., on the fourth Thursday in March.

The directors are W. W. Atterbury, Effingham B. Morris, Charles E. Ingersoll, Levi L. Rue, Jay Cooke, A. J. County, Henry H. Lee, Philadelphia, Pa.; R. B. Mellon, Pittsburgh, Pa.

The officers are Henry H. Lee, president; Samuel H. Ogden, vice president and treasurer; W. U. Moyer, vice president, secretary, and assistant treasurer; C. Bidlingmeyer, assistant secretary and assistant treasurer; R. P. Andrews, auditor.

Voting trust certificates may be transferred at the offices of the voting trustees, 1021 Commercial Trust Building, Philadelphia, Pa., and 1434 Hudson Terminal Building, 30 Church Street, New York, N.Y.

W. W. ATTERBURY,
EFFINGHAM B. MORRIS,
JAY COOKE,
Voting Trustees.

By _____,
Assistant Secretary.

The CHAIRMAN. We will now recess until 2 o'clock this afternoon.

(Thereupon, at 12:33 p.m. Friday, June 30, 1933, a recess was taken until 2 p.m. the same day.)

AFTERNOON SESSION

Upon the expiration of the noon recess the hearing was resumed at 2 p.m.

The CHAIRMAN. The committee will come to order. Proceed, Mr. Pecora.

TESTIMONY OF OTTO H. KAHN, A MEMBER OF THE FIRM OF KUHN, LOEB & CO.—Resumed

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, are you familiar with the transaction that involved the acquisition by the Pennroad Corporation of 402,119 shares of the Seaboard Airline Railway for \$4,529,838.75?

Mr. KAHN. No, Mr. Pecora; I knew nothing about that.

Mr. PECORA. Your firm was not consulted in any way by the officers or directors of the Pennroad Corporation with regard to this purchase?

Mr. KAHN. In no way, to the best of my knowledge.

Mr. PECORA. Did your firm handle any other transactions in behalf of the Pennroad Corporation, or did it have any other transactions with the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. KAHN. The only other transactions we handled were purchases in the market, for which we got the regular broker's commission, amounting to approximately the figure which I gave you this morning, in the way of brokerages; but we suggested nothing; we had a hand in nothing, except the Canton transaction.

Mr. PECORA. Was the transaction to which you have just referred one involving the acquisition of shares of the New York, New Haven & Hartford Railroad?

Mr. KAHN. Yes. That was one of them.

Mr. PECORA. And how many shares of that road were acquired by the Pennroad Corporation through your firm?

Mr. KAHN. One hundred and forty-eight thousand eight hundred shares of common stock and 1,200 shares of preferred stock.

Mr. PECORA. Were those purchases made in the open market by your firm?

Mr. KAHN. To the best of my knowledge, yes. I do not know of any other way in which they could have been made by us. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. That is, they were not made in the way that the Canton Co. stock was acquired?

Mr. KAHN. Oh, no.

Mr. PECORA. And over what period of time were the market operations?

Mr. KAHN. That was between July 31, 1929, and June 15, 1930.

Mr. PECORA. That was found to be a convenient method for the Pennroad Corporation in acquiring this stock of the New Haven road, wasn't it?

Mr. KAHN. I do not know of any other way in which they could have done it.

Mr. PECORA. In your testimony this forenoon reference was made to the fact that the stock of the Pennroad Corporation was offered on the date of its incorporation, namely, April 24, 1929, to the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. at \$15 a share.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And reference also was made, as I recall it, to the fact that the following day, April 25, the stock was traded in in the open market, I suppose, on a when-issued basis?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. At something like \$25 or \$26; was that the figure you mentioned this morning?

Mr. KAHN. A few hundred shares, as I recall it; yes.

Mr. PECORA. There was a considerable variance between the offering price and the price at which the opening trades were made?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. At practically the same time?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know who made that market on the open trades?

Mr. KAHN. To the best of my knowledge the people who are buying and selling. I know of no one who instigated the buying and selling.

Mr. PECORA. Could you tell this committee, out of your experience, how these markets are made under similar circumstances?

(Mr. Kahn conferred with Mr. Stewart.)

Mr. PECORA. Let us rehearse briefly the circumstances.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. On April 24, 1929, the Pennroad Corporation was organized.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Certificate of incorporation was filed. And on the same date its stock, or rather 5,800,000 shares of its total authorized issue of 10,000,000 shares, was offered by letter.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Sent by General Atterbury, head of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., to the shareholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. At \$15 a share.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. The only other persons that had any interest or right to subscribe for the stock or were given the opportunity at that time were Kuhn, Loeb & Co.—

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Which had agreed to purchase up to 250,000 shares, any shares of the original allotment of 5,800,000 that were not subscribed for by the shareholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Now, no business had been transacted by the Penn-road Corporation which gave any value to its stock between April 24 and April 25?

Mr. KAHN. I suppose not.

Mr. PECORA. What were the circumstances that you could point to that tended to make the opening price for this stock in the public trading on April 25 something like \$25 a share?

Mr. KAHN. 1929, Mr. Pecora—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). Or, in other words, 66⅔ percent in excess of the price at which it was offered to the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad?

Mr. KAHN. I put the responsibility of all these things—and I can give you much more striking examples than this one—I put the responsibility for that upon 1929 in the first instance. People were wild to buy pieces of paper, and they were sure that the next day they would be worth more and the second day still more, and so on, and so on.

I do not mean to say—I am not as innocent as that—I do not mean to say that that is always the fact. Occasions do occur—I suppose legitimate occasions do occur—where a market is made in the sense that stocks are offered, stocks are bought perfectly innocently, simply for the purpose of establishing a market. A market has usually got to have some kind of trading activity in order to be a market.

I said yesterday usually stocks spring up like weeds as compared with bonds, which have to be carefully nursed, and I used the word “watered.” But quite normally it may be a perfectly legitimate and innocent thing to provide material out of which a legitimate market can be made, but it is not always, Mr. Pecora, a legitimate and innocent thing. I say I am not as innocent in saying that, and I know you are not as innocent in believing me if I did say it.

There are activities which are made for the deliberate purpose of agitating the market. I believe the exchange is doing all that it can to discourage that, to control it, and to stop it. But it is a difficult thing to stop. I know that of late there has been enormous activity in silver mines and in gold mines that were introduced in the market perhaps quite legitimately. The enormous profits which have been made in that connection—and they were huge profits—are due to the change in our governmental policy. To what extent the people who bought these bonds in the market acted in perfect good faith—

because they believed that they would be worth more—to what extent they took advantage of the gullibility of the public is very difficult to say. But if I had to draw a line it would vary between innocence, between legitimacy, and between taking advantage of the gullibility of the public. I think all three elements enter.

Mr. PECORA. Well, you have observed, and doubtless soundly, that in many instances opening trades in a new issue of common stock were made at prices that are excessive. In saying “excessive” I am using my own term as defining what I believe you had in mind.

Mr. KAHN. Yes; I have seen such cases.

Mr. PECORA. How could that be stopped, in your opinion?

Mr. KAHN. I said before, and I repeat it, that I have the utmost confidence in public opinion being guided so as to assert itself in what would be an irresistible way. If a thing by public opinion is condemned as something which no decent person ought to do, ultimately no decent person will do it. It requires education. It requires a very definite guidance and expression of public opinion. But I believe the greatest guardian and the greatest educator against things which ought to be prevented is public opinion under suitable guidance.

I also believe that the watchfulness of the stock exchange ought to be most carefully concentrated against any attempt to take advantage of the one function for which it exists, namely, to offer a fair and free market for securities, and that anything which tends artificially to interfere with that market ought to be punished not merely by the stock exchange but otherwise. It ought not to be permitted. The only legitimate function of the stock exchange is to be a fair and free market. If they cannot control it themselves—I believe so far, of late particularly, they have made a very great effort to control it; I think they are doing everything now that I could think of if I were a Mussolini of the stock exchange, to prevent these artificial, anti-social, illegitimate practices which thrive on the gullibility of the public.

But if it should be found that they are not capable of handling that situation, then some other means, I think, should be found to deal with it.

Mr. PECORA. What means have been adopted or devised by the stock exchange, say, since last February, along those lines?

Mr. KAHN. As far as I know, they are exceedingly watchful as far as it is possible, and they have introduced such regulations as their wisdom dictated to prevent pool activities of an illegitimate or of an artificial character. I do not claim that they have wholly succeeded. I know that the activities in the New York market in the last 3 or 4 months have been somewhat comparable to the activities in 1929. Buy—buy—buy—you will make money.

Mr. PECORA. Do you suspect that the activities of the present market or market within recent months contain any evidences or signs that you would interpret as evidences of pool operations?

Mr. KAHN. I ought not give an opinion on something which I have not investigated.

Mr. PECORA. Still your opinion would be valuable, I think.

Mr. KAHN (after conferring with Mr. Battenwieser). My partner calls my attention to the fact that the stock exchange has made short

selling something as to which you have got to give to the stock exchange public notice and mark your sales "short sales." They have also regulated the activities of the specialists, which in the past have given ground for complaint and objection.

It is something as to which I suppose I ought not to express myself without having had much access to the facts as to whether in this particular year since the month of March pool activities of an illegitimate character have been in evidence. But if, as appears to my knowledge this year, a number of people reach the conclusion simultaneously that people ought to buy gold-mining shares, so they are safe against inflation, or they ought to buy silver-mining shares because silver will form part of the Nation's official currency, I do not suppose that is a pool activity in the sense in which I mean it.

I think, perhaps, I can best define my conception of a pool activity by saying that it is an activity which is based upon a definite purpose to affect the market, irrespective of the opinions of the people concerned as to intrinsic value or nonvalue of the security they are dealing with. I believe in this year most people that display an active part in the market did believe that buying shares—the kind of shares which they had to offer, pretty nearly any kind of shares—was a wise and legitimate thing to do. In 1929 our guide was greed.

At the end of 1929 our guide was fear. I think they are the two worst guides in the world, greed and fear. I think at this time our guide was a desire for self-protection to a large extent, and if that is so, if my analysis is correct, then it is very difficult, in fact for me impossible, to determine in what instance those who were seeking self-protection were right, were justified, in commending their goods to the public. They were wrong, unquestionably wrong, in 1929, because greed was their guide. I think they were frequently wrong in 1931, because they had been made by fear incapable of judging, or permitted their own fear to affect their judgment and to act upon the judgment of others.

I am not prepared at this time to say in what way this at times undoubted evil can be dealt with. If you would like me to I will give it some further thought, especially in the light of the securities bill, which ought to help a good deal—I think in some respects, as I said yesterday, it is unworkable. In some respects I think it defeats its own purpose. But the effect of it, even with its existing shortcomings, ought to be good, and I think some of the things which have been done with impunity heretofore cannot be done any longer, and to that extent they ought also to have a beneficial effect upon the activities inside of the stock exchange.

Mr. PECORA. Now, do you recognize that the activities or operations of pools in the stock market gave that artificial stimulation to the market?

Mr. KAHN. Frequently; yes.

Mr. PECORA. And such artificial stimulation is misleading and deceptive to the average investor, isn't it?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And to that extent such pool activities should be restrained or curbed, some way found for eliminating them, on account of their baneful influences?

Mr. KAHN. Yes. I would like—no; I think you are absolutely right. “Restraint” I think is the right word. Precisely in what way, I am not prepared to say.

Mr. PECORA. You are anticipating my next question now.

Mr. KAHN. But I agree with you that these things which in my opinion are antisocial activities and which deal with what I think is one of the most solemn obligations, to indicate to people how they ought to invest their savings. What is the right and the desirable and the responsible way so to indicate I think is a very great responsibility; and if you see that that responsibility is not properly fulfilled, it ought to be guided by some agency in some way. I agree with you. But I also say that I have not found the way yet; and whether regulation is the way I do not know yet.

Mr. PECORA. Are you prepared to say whether or not such restraint should be applied by governmental agencies or by the application of governmental power and authority, or should it be left to the governing authorities of the stock exchange?

Mr. KAHN. I should hope it could safely be left to regulation which, under the spur of public opinion and with the fear of government in the offing, I think is the best kind of regulation.

Mr. PECORA. There has been agitation now over a period of many years for some kind of Government or State regulation of the stock exchange, and yet that fear has not yet been strong enough to bring about the necessary reformative, corrective measures by the authorities of the exchange. Is not that true?

Mr. KAHN. Mr. Pecora, I think that a great many corrective and wise and effective measures have been brought about by that assertion of public opinion and by that agitation.

Mr. PECORA. You may or may not be familiar with the fact, but last February before this committee Mr. Richard Whitney, then and still the president of the New York Stock Exchange, appeared as a witness and testified that the New York Stock Exchange did not then and never had considered itself as having any right to evaluate securities traded in on its floor. If that attitude be persisted in or that opinion be maintained consistently by the officials of the exchange, what reasonable hope is there that they will apply the necessary corrective measures to those conditions?

Mr. KAHN. You say “devalue”?

Mr. PECORA. Evaluate.

Mr. KAHN. Can there be more than a fair and free market, with every possible precaution taken that no advantage is taken of the forum which is given to the public to buy and to sell?

Mr. PECORA. Should they not be alert to see to it that that forum is not used in a manner that deceives or misleads the investing public?

Mr. KAHN. Decidedly.

Mr. PECORA. That you regard as their moral duty, do you not?

Mr. KAHN. I do, yes; their moral and their social duty, and their self interest; but above all, their moral duty.

Mr. PECORA. Do you think that in the fulfillment of that duty they might make some attempt, based upon an evaluation of the listed securities, so as to see to it that the investing public is kept currently posted as to real values as distinguished from those values that result from artificial stimulation of the market through pool activities?

Mr. KAHN. The duty to keep the public posted is primarily upon the corporations whose stock is being traded in. To the extent that the stock exchange can see to it that that information is fully given without any concealment of any kind whatsoever, and to the extent that they can say to the corporations, "If we catch you in the act of deceiving the public, out you go", I think they ought to do it by all means; but I do not see what more they can do than to insist upon those who have the privilege of supporting the exchange getting the fullest and fairest information; and if they recognize that, plus the action of the securities bill, I should hope that your purpose, with which I am in the fullest sympathy, will be accomplished. If it is not, then I think it is up to you to apply severer measures.

But, after all, this is a democracy. It is supposed to work by education, by enlightenment, by the decisive action of public opinion; and I hope and believe that there is no agency in this country which can evade that influence, and I hope that there is none which will seek to evade that influence.

Senator BARKLEY. Speaking of pools, to what extent, if at all, do pools which may be interested in the rise in prices on the stock market exceed those that may be interested in the decline of values?

Mr. KAHN. Sometimes one way and sometimes another. Of course, in 1930 and 1931, particularly in 1931, I think the pools that were working for a decline were much more potent than those working for the rise; but they had to have public sentiment with them.

Senator BARKLEY. They had to capitalize fear?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Senator BARKLEY. In order to bring about a decline which would result in profit to them?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Senator BARKLEY. Have you expressed or do you hold any opinion as to the propriety of what we know as short selling on the stock market?

Mr. KAHN. Again going into motives, if short selling is based not upon a cooperative movement deliberately intended to scare people, to spread rumors, to depress prices, to make somebody else's holdings less valuable, to cause him to throw his securities upon the market—if it is not based upon that, but is based upon a man's honest conviction that he can just as well invest, as some one has said, in being short of stocks as invest in being long of stocks—if that is his motive, I think it is quite legitimate; and I think if short selling takes the form of deliberately depressing prices it is even more wrong than the practice of artificially boosting prices. Both practices are wrong, but I think the practice of the short seller, of the combined short seller and short raider, is even more wrong, because it does harm to somebody else. It depreciates somebody else's property.

Senator BARKLEY. It has been testified here early in these hearings which really started out on the investigation of short selling in the stock market, but have taken a very much wider range, that it is customary among large commodity purchasers, like those who have to buy large quantities of cotton in advance of their needs, to order a certain amount of cotton at a given price and then they sell

the same or any particular amount of cotton at a figure probably a little above what they had to pay for it, in order to protect themselves against inordinate rises in the future. They call it "hedging", I believe. The same process is indulged in among millers with reference to wheat.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Senator BARKLEY. It is defended on the ground that it is necessary to protect them against future contingencies, and I can well understand that.

Mr. KAHN. I think it is.

Senator BARKLEY. But do you recognize any difference between that sort of a procedure and the deliberate sales by one person or by a group of persons of that which they do not possess, purely upon the theory that it will go down and they can purchase it at a lower rate and thereby reap a profit out of the fact that they have sold something to somebody that they did not possess, and afterward buy it back and nobody gets possession of it, and in that transaction make a considerable profit and thereby exercise a considerable influence in the artificial depression of the price either of the commodity or of a stock? What is your view with reference to the comparative morality of the two kinds of transactions that I have described?

Mr. KAHN. I know, as you know, that it is the stock argument in favor of short sales that they provide a cushion for the market and that the man who has sold short has got to buy back, and therefore it provides in times of storm and stress a cushion, a resiliency to the market which would otherwise not exist; and that whenever it has been attempted, as it has been attempted as far back, I believe, as the time of Napoleon in France, to stop short selling by edict, it has had to be repealed ultimately because it was found that it weakened the resisting power of the market. I am prepared to attribute a good deal of weight to that argument, and yet my moral sense tells me that there is something inherently repellent to a right-thinking man about short-selling activities to the extent that they can depreciate another man's property or that they will induce fear or produce alarm to harm normal activities. The line is most difficult to draw, as you will readily see, Senator.

I will come back to my old favorite doctrine from which I have learned much, particularly since 1929. What was done then none of us would think of doing, law or no law, because public opinion has changed and we have all learned from public opinion. I come back to that, that public opinion ought to be watchful, and if it finds that there are activities on the short-selling side or otherwise which are socially harmful, some means ought to be found to supervise them and to exercise the weight of public opinion. By what kind of a mentor you can do that I don't know; nor do I know at present, without having as yet the opportunity of seeing how the various new laws which have been enacted will work in operation—nor do I know now what I would suggest; but the activities of some moral force which in England is defined by the Governor of the Bank of England; in France it is largely defined, though not to the same extent, by the Governor of the Bank of France; in Germany it is most definitely defined by Dr. Schacht, of the Reichsbank. The guiding by such a man, the calling attention by such a man or a body

of men to activities which are socially or economically undesirable is the only thing which at present I could suggest, but I hope by next autumn I may possibly have evolved some theory more helpful than this one.

Senator BARKLEY. On yesterday you undertook to define the difference between gambling and speculation.

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Senator BARKLEY. It is true, is it not, that short selling more numerous partakes of the qualities of gambling than long buying? Would that be your judgment?

Mr. KAHN. I know of a man who made a lot of money in 1929, and he said, "I have invested all my savings in short selling." And I think he was perfectly bona fide. That shows how much depends upon the psychology of the public at the time. These are times when the public actually thinks that the best way in which they can invest their money is in short selling. Personally it is most repellant to me. Personally I have never sold a share of stock short in my life, and I do not believe I ever shall—I know I never shall. But I must recognize that short selling does exercise a certain function and that it is probably impossible to stop the public from being guided by its impulses if it feels sufficiently strongly like investing in short selling. I do not like it, and I wish I could do away with it. I think all kinds of gambling are economically detrimental to the country. Speculation is different, but all kinds of gambling are economically detrimental to the country.

Senator GOLDSBOROUGH. Would you differentiate between the "short sale" and the sale "against the box"?

Mr. KAHN. There is of course a distinct difference, in that a sale against the box is simply a deferred sale. It is a sale which is deferred. It is distinctly different from a short sale where the man has not got the securities that he sells and can only get them from some other man and where he hopes to get them at some other man's detriment. There is a distinct difference.

Mr. PECORA. Having in mind the distinction between gambling and speculation in stock-market operations, would you say that trading in puts and calls is a form of trading that partakes more of the nature of gambling than it does of speculation?

Mr. KAHN. Puts and calls are a mixture of the two. I think it is an attempt on the part of a man to avoid gambling and yet to do something which comes pretty close to it, but it is not direct gambling.

Mr. PECORA. Would you say it is an attempt on the part of the man to gamble, but with some limitation upon the losses he will sustain if the gamble goes against him?

Mr. KAHN. And also to save his own conscience. He would probably not like to think of himself as a gambler. Consequently he says, "Well, if I put and call I am not a gambler, because I can get my stock and deliver my stock." I think to a large extent he puts a salve of good intentions upon something which comes pretty close to gambling, but which is not exactly gambling, and he does protect himself.

Mr. PECORA. Would you put any form of restriction upon or even eliminate trading on puts and calls?

Mr. KAHN. "Elimination" is to me a very disagreeable term, because I hope that these things which are inherently undesirable will be corrected by public opinion, and I am convinced that they will be, especially when the public's attention is called to these things as your committee and you are calling them to their attention. What is happening here? The tales which are being recited here, the matters which you are bringing to public knowledge, the recommendations which you will make ultimately are bound to have a very important effect upon public opinion.

Mr. PECORA. Do you think they will have a beneficial effect?

Mr. KAHN. I think it is bound to have a very important and very beneficial effect upon public opinion. I think the kind of thing which is being done and looked into and brought to the surface here, even though in some respects sometimes, according to the editor of the Evening Post and others, it may go a little further than the occasion necessitates, is a matter of the greatest statesmanlike importance and value, because I think nothing is more important for the welfare and for the satisfaction and for the absence of irritation and resentment and bitterness on the part of the people than to have pointed out to them in what way they ought to deal with that which is their all, upon which they and their family depend, and which they now think is frequently abstracted out of their pockets. If you can give them a guide, a code, and a protection, I think you will perform a public service not merely of economic importance but of great social importance.

Mr. PECORA. You recognize, don't you, that the vast majority of stock-market transactions participated in by the public are on a so-called "margin" basis?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And in your dissertation or discussion of your views before this committee within the last 2 or 3 days on the differences between speculation and gambling in the stock market, at one point you made some observations that indicated to me that you felt that when trading was indulged in by the man of limited means to an extent that threatened his own complete financial ruin, it was a social evil?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Would you say that marginal transactions in the stock market savor more of gambling as those transactions are permitted on a larger margin, as the margin basis is greater?

Mr. KAHN. I am not sure that I understand you correctly. I should have said it the other way.

Mr. PECORA. I meant, as the margin is smaller.

Mr. KAHN. Yes. There should be a very ample margin required from anyone who wants to gamble—no; I do not want to use that word—anyone who wants to invest on a marginal basis, because it is a legitimate form of investment. There is no reason why only the rich should be able to take advantage of their judgment as to the rise or fall, especially the rise, of securities.

There is every reason why everyone within his means should have that same opportunity, and within his means and within prudence he should not be confined to 4 percent for the rest of his life. If he believes he can do better and does not jeopardize his welfare and that of his family, I say it is in the public interest that the interest

in securities of our corporations should be spread all over the country and that the benefit from their prosperity should be shared by the whole country as far as possible.

Mr. PECORA. If you cared to express an opinion, assuming that you have one at this moment on it, what would you say in the public interest would be a safe and proper marginal minimum?

Mr. KAHN. That varies according to circumstances. When there has been a violent upward movement, the margin ought to be increased. People ought not to be induced, as too many of our banks were induced, to make loans at a time when everything was booming. On the contrary, during such a time they ought to be particularly prudent and they ought to require a liberal and ample margin partly as a warning and partly for their protection and partly for the protection of their client.

On the other hand, as was the case in 1931, our securities were selling at prices which were manifestly absurd, considering the recuperative power of this country, the intrinsic wealth and the history of this country, then I think the public can be encouraged by somewhat more liberal terms to induce them to buy securities. When, for instance, the Union Pacific in June of last year, or early July, was paying a 6 percent dividend on its stock, with a magnificent record of performance behind it, located in one of the greatest parts of the United States, was selling below 30, the small man could legitimately be encouraged by liberal margin facilities to put some of his money into that stock. But when there has been a big boom, then I think the marginal requirements ought to be increased and ought to be increasingly stringent as the danger point is approached.

Mr. PECORA. To whose judgment should that determination be left, in your opinion?

Mr. KAHN. In the case of loans it should be left by the banks to our clearing houses which, under the Glass bill, are perhaps more strictly supervised than heretofore, and the Federal Reserve Board and the Controller of the Currency who are given pretty direct supervisory power and even responsibility to see that sane, wise, and conservative practices are performed; and in the case of our banks I think it is pretty safe to leave it as it is now.

Mr. PECORA. But it was not found safe to leave it to the judgment of the banks in 1928 and 1929, was it, speaking from the vantage point of hindsight that we now have?

Mr. KAHN. We were all sinners during that time, Mr. Pecora, or, if not sinners, we were all grossly mistaken or affected beyond our powers to resist by the then prevailing mania or greed. Put any blame you like upon all those who then had charge of the affairs of the country. I hope and believe they have all learned, and I hope and believe that those things will not in our generation occur again. But I do not mean to say that the policeman should not be around the corner, and that if we indulge again in practices that are socially, economically, and, from the point of view of the country, undesirable, I think the policeman ought to be ready to step in. I think he is, now, under the laws as they are.

In the case of the stock exchange itself, I think it is, as things are now, always subject to the possible interference of the policeman or to the watchdog who, not not only can bark, but can also bite if

necessary. I think it is safe to leave to the stock exchange what margin should be fixed for margin trading.

Mr. PECORA. Is the name of that policeman you have in mind the Congress of the United States?

Mr. KAHN. Of course, it is a superpoliceman who appoints all the subordinate policemen. It is that power of the United States and those to whom it delegates the power; and I think the power should always be latent and we should be always conscious of the fact that it is latent.

Senator BARKLEY. You also have a rather healthy pup in the New York Legislature that operates now and then?

Mr. KAHN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. I would say that while an attempt has been made to brandish that club, to my personal knowledge, somehow or other the stock exchange seemed to either ward off the blow or dodge it.

Senator BARKLEY. You misunderstood my statement.

Senator GOLDSBOROUGH. You did not even get a bark out of it, let alone bite.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, would you care to make any recommendations to this committee with regard to action which the Congress might take in respect of bringing about any improvement in the existing methods of investment banking?

Mr. KAHN. I have got to be particularly careful about what I say, because it affects me. [Laughter.]

Mr. PECORA. That is why I am asking you.

Mr. KAHN. And when I say "particularly careful", I hope it means that I have got to be leaning over backward in order not to claim something for us to which we are not justly entitled.

Mr. PECORA. All right.

Mr. KAHN. The test and the only justification which exists for the private banker is: What services can he render better than others to the industries of the country? To what extent is he better able by reason of his acquired knowledge, by reason of the fact that there is a kind of close-knit relationship between him and his clients, because a partner in a private banking house is necessarily different from a vice president in a bank and has necessarily a somewhat different spirit. The fact that there is necessarily something like a family spirit and a family preservation spirit prevailing in a private bank among private bankers, to what extent is that helpful in enabling him to render services to American industry in providing its long-range needs better than somebody else?

To what extent can he serve the public better? To what extent does his self-interest see to it that his client, the investment public, is given a fair deal, over that of the corporate entity, which necessarily does not feel these things as strongly as the private banker does, not by reason of virtue but because it is his self-interest. To what extent in this country, which is a democracy, based upon the education of public opinion, and by public opinion I mean submission to public opinion as it expresses itself; to what extent should this, in this country, encourage private enterprise rather than encourage a system which makes everybody a hired man? If you do want to encourage private enterprise, to what extent can you afford to regiment things rather than to give a reasonable degree, consistent with public safety, of latitude, and of freedom to the indi-

vidual? All these things enter into this question, and I believe my questions have really given my answer. For if the private banker does render, as I believe he does, services which are necessarily better rendered by him than by a corporate entity, then I say let him go ahead. But impose upon him the strictest requirements of disclosure as to what he offers. Impose upon him the strictest requirements as to the profits he is to make. By that you will ipso facto limit those profits and prevent them from becoming exorbitant. The danger of exorbitant profits is always there with the temptation of making exorbitant profits.

But if you compel a man to disclose everything he is doing, and if you penalize him for anything which he deliberately or knowingly withholds; if you force him to disclose his profits in every transaction, then that, together with the workings of public opinion in staying away from the man who deals badly with it and going to the man who deals well with it, and together with the action of corporations in necessarily going to the man who gives them sound advice and a fair price rather than to the man who simply tries to gouge them, and who says, "I have made a lot out of them this time and that will do." I think that will pretty nearly accomplish your purpose.

MR. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, in the questionnaire that was sent to your firm in behalf of this committee—

The CHAIRMAN (interposing). Mr. Pecora, before you branch off on that, let me ask Mr. Kahn a question or two.

MR. PECORA. Certainly, Mr. Chairman.

The CHAIRMAN. Mr. Kahn, you are familiar with the operations and practices of what are known as "investment trusts", I take it?

MR. KAHN. Yes, sir.

The CHAIRMAN. Have you any observations to make with regard to any of their practices and operations, and whether or not some of them ought not to be corrected?

MR. KAHN. A great many sins have been committed there, Senator Fletcher. Many things have been done which ought not to have been permitted; and I think, speaking generally, I would say that investment trusts, first of all, must not be controlled by a small group of people who happen to own one particular issue to which the voting power has been confided. Investment trusts must be controlled by their own people.

Secondly, investment trusts must deal at arm's length with every comer, including those that created it. They must not play favorites with those who are its originators. They are not children in the sense that I am my father's child. They are the public's child; and the public has provided the origination, and the public has provided the wherewithal that gave them their education. I think if you will make it the general rule that investment trusts must deal at arm's length with everybody, and must not be controlled by some small stock issue created for the purpose of providing control but must deal under the direction of their stockholders, and if you subject them, as you will subject them, to the same rule of profit disclosure, facts disclosure, to which the private banker is subjected, I think you will have done about all that can now be done or that should now be done.

The CHAIRMAN. All right. I thank you, Mr. Kahn.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, in the questionnaire which was sent to your firm in behalf of this committee several weeks ago, we asked, among other things, for the names of all banks and trust companies of which any partner or representative of your firm is a director or officer, and that was during the period 1927 to 1931, both inclusive. In response to that question I received from your firm this statement. Will you kindly look at it; and if you can identify it as a correct and complete answer to that question, will you do so?

Mr. KAHN. This is correct.

Mr. PECORA. I offer that in evidence and ask that it may be spread on the record of the hearing.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted, and the committee reporter will make it a part of the record.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Mr. Pecora, there is a very slight change in connection with that paper. Shall it be made later?

Mr. PECORA. If it can be made now, all right.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. In our letter to you of June 6 we told you that on this list we had Mr. Felix M. Warburg down as a director of the Manhattan Co. and that that name should be taken from list no. 2 and placed on list no. 3, because list no. 2 refers to banks and trust companies, while list no. 3 refers to corporations. It is merely for the sake of regularity.

Mr. PECORA. I am glad that you have noted that correction. With that correction I offer that typewritten statement in evidence and ask that it may be spread on the record of our hearing.

The CHAIRMAN. It will be admitted, and the committee reporter will make it a part of the hearing.

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 26, JUNE 30, 1933.

Question 2. Names of all banks and trust companies of which any partner or representative was a director or officer during the period 1927 to 1931, inclusive:

The Manhattan Co., Felix M. Warburg, 1930-31.

Chase National Bank of New York, Otto H. Kahn,¹ 1930-31.

Chemical Bank & Trust Co., Mortimer L. Schiff, 1930-31; John M. Schiff, 1931.

Equitable Trust Co. of New York, Otto H. Kahn,¹ 1927, 1928, 1929, 1930, 1931.

International Acceptance Bank, Felix M. Warburg, 1927-31.

U.S. Mortgage & Trust Co., Mortimer L. Schiff, 1927-29.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, question no. 3 in our questionnaire called for the names of all corporations in which any partner or representative of your firm or any of its agencies was a director or officer. That is, for the 5-year period embracing the years 1927 to 1931, both inclusive. I show you this list and ask you if this is a complete and correct answer to that question?

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. Mr. Pecora, this is also correct with one slight addition, if we may crave your indulgence. As we wrote you in a letter of June 22 there was an error on our part, which we again apologize for, in that we omitted to mention that Mr. Mortimer M. Schiff was a director of the Electric Overseas Investment Co. from 1929 to his death in 1931, and subsequent to his demise Mr. Frederick M. Warburg became a director.

¹ Resigned Aug. 5, 1931.

Mr. PECORA. With that omission supplied by your oral statement, I offer the list in evidence and ask that it may be spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted, and the committee reporter will make it a part of the proceedings.

(The paper referred to was marked "Committee Exhibit No. 27, June 30, 1933," and is as follows:)

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 27, JUNE 30, 1933

Question no. 3. Names of all corporations of which any partner or representative was a director or officer during the period 1927 to 1931, inclusive:

American & Continental Corporation, Mortimer L. Schiff	1927-29
American International Corporation, Otto H. Kahn	1927
American Railway Express Co., Mortimer L. Schiff	1927-28
Bond & Mortgage Guarantee Co., Felix M. Warburg	1927-31
Central Leather Co., Lewis L. Strauss	1927
Chemical National Associates, Mortimer L. Schiff	1929-30
Chemical National Co., Inc., later Chemical Securities Corporation, John M. Schiff	1929-31
Chemical Safe Deposit Co., Mortimer L. Schiff	1930-31
Chicago Pneumatic Tool Co., Lewis L. Strauss	1930-31
Equitable Corporation of New York, Otto H. Kahn	1927-30
Famous Players Canadian Corporation, Sir William Wiseman	1927-31
Fleischman Morris & Co., Lewis L. Strauss	1927-31
Hanstra Corporation:	
Jerome J. Hanauer, president	1927-31
Lewis L. Strauss	1927-31
George W. Bovenizer	1927-31
Hudson & Manhattan Railroad Co., Jerome J. Hanauer	1927-31
Indiana & Illinois Coal Corporation, Jerome J. Hanauer	1927-31
International Gear Co., Lewis L. Strauss	1927-29
James Loeb & Co., Geo. W. Bovenizer	1927-31
Los Angeles & Salt Lake R.R.:	
Mortimer L. Schiff	1927-31
Otto H. Kahn	1927-31
Frederick M. Warburg	1931
Mexican Central Rys. Co., Ltd.:	
Jerome J. Hanauer	1929-31
Sir William Wiseman	1927-31
Mexican National Construction Co.:	
Jerome J. Hanauer	1929-31
Sir William Wiseman	1927-31
Mid-Continent Petroleum Corporation, Jerome J. Hanauer	1930-31
Missouri-Kansas-Texas R.R. Co., Sir William Wiseman	1927-28
The Manhattan Co., Felix M. Warburg	1930-31
National R.R. Co. of Mexico:	
Jerome J. Hanauer	1929-31
Sir William Wiseman	1927-31
National Rys. of Mexico:	
Jerome J. Hanauer	1927-31
Sir William Wiseman	1927-31
Northwood Finance & Realty Corporation:	
Mortimer L. Schiff, president	1927-31
John M. Schiff (president 1931)	1929-31
Felix M. Warburg	1927-31
George W. Bovenizer	1927-31
Frederick M. Warburg	1931
Pacific Oil Co., Mortimer L. Schiff	1927-30
Paramount Publix Corporation:	
Sir William Wiseman	1927-31
Gilbert W. Kahn	1928-31
Provident Loan Society:	
Mortimer L. Schiff, president and trustee (executive committee)	1927-31
John M. Schiff, trustee	1931

Railway Express Agency, Inc., Mortimer L. Schiff	1927-29
Staten Island Rapid Transit Ry. Co., Felix M. Warburg	1929-31
Susquehanna & New York R.R., Lewis L. Strauss	1927-31
Transportation Indemnity Co., George W. Bovenizer	1931
Transportation Insurance Co. of New York, George W. Bovenizer	1931
United States Leather Co., Lewis L. Strauss	1928-31
United States Rubber Co.:	
Lewis L. Strauss	1929-31
Sir William Wiseman	1927-31
United States Safe Deposit Co., Mortimer L. Schiff	1927-29
Western Union Telegraph Co.:	
Mortimer L. Schiff (executive committee)	1927-31
John M. Schiff (executive committee)	1931
Westinghouse Acceptance Corporation, Jerome J. Hanauer	1929-31
Westinghouse Electric International Co., Jerome J. Hanauer	1927-31
Westinghouse Electric & Manufacturing Co., Jerome J. Hanauer	1927-31
Yazoo & Mississippi Valley R.R. Co., Jerome J. Hanauer	1927-31

LONDON, ENGLAND

European Merchant Banking Co., Ltd.:	
Sir William Wiseman	1927-30
Gordon Leith	1927-30
American Investment & General Trust Co., Ltd., Gordon Leith	1927-30
English & Caledonian Investment Co., Ltd., Gordon Leith	1927-30
Foreign, American & General Investments Trust Co., Ltd., Gordon Leith	1927-30
Foreign & Colonial Investment Trust Co., Ltd., Gordon Leith	1927-30
London Border & General Trust, Ltd., Gordon Leith	1927-30
London Prudential Investment Trust, Ltd., Gordon Leith	1927-30
National Mutual Life Assurance Society, Gordon Leith	1927-30
Scottish Stockholders Investment Trust, Ltd., Gordon Leith	1927-30
Southern Stockholders Investment Trust, Ltd., Gordon Leith	1927-30
Stockholders Investment Trust, Ltd., Gordon Leith	1927-30
Underground Electric Rys. Co. of London, Ltd., Gordon Leith	1927-30

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, questions 5 and 6 in our questionnaire to your firm called for, first, the names of all officers and directors of any banks or trust companies to whom your firm made any personal loan or advance in that same 5-year period; and also for the names of all officers and directors of any corporations to whom your firm or any of its agencies had made any personal loan or advance in that 5-year period. I show you this typewritten statement or list and ask you if that is a correct and complete answer to both of those questions.

Mr. KAHN. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. I offer that in evidence and ask that it may be spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted, and the committee reporter will make it a part of the proceedings.

(The paper referred to was marked "Committee Exhibit No. 28, June 30, 1933", and is as follows:)

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 28, JUNE 30, 1933

Questions 5 and 6.—Loans made during period from 1927 to 1931, inclusive, to directors and officers of banks or corporations. (Answers have been grouped, inasmuch as most of these men were directors of both banks and corporations.)

HENRY H. LEE

Banks.—Director Pennsylvania Co. for Insurances on Lives and Granting Annuities, Philadelphia. Beneficial Savings Fund Society, Philadelphia North-trn Trust Co., Philadelphia.

Corporations.—President and director the Pennroad Corporation, Philadelphia. Director, Detroit, Toledo & Ironton Railroad Co., Canton Co., Baltimore Mail & Steamship Co., National Freight Co., New York Federal International Corporation, and other minor corporations.

WILLIAM J. MORRIS

Corporations.—Vice president Youngstown Sheet & Tube Co.

JOHN W. PLATTEN

Banks.—President and director United States Mortgage & Trust Co., New York. Director, Commercial Trust Co. of New Jersey.

Corporations.—Chairman of the board and director Gulf, Mobile & Northern Railroad Co., Gulf State Steel Co. Director, Hudson & Manhattan Railroad Co., Missouri-Kansas-Texas Railroad Co., and other minor corporations.

H. HOBART PORTER

Banks.—Director United States Mortgage & Trust Co., New York.

Corporations.—Director Missouri Pacific Railroad Co., Texas & Pacific Railroad Co., National Surety Co., and other minor corporations.

SAMUEL REA

Banks.—Director Bank of North America & Trust Co., Philadelphia, Philadelphia National Bank.

Corporations.—Director Pennsylvania Railroad Co., Long Island Railroad Co., New York Connecting Railroad, Norfolk & Western Railroad, Richmond Washington Co., the Washington Terminal Co., Bell Telephone Co. of Pennsylvania, Northern Central Railway Co., Pennsylvania Tunnel & Terminal Railroad Co., Philadelphia, Baltimore & Washington Railroad Co., Pittsburgh, Fort Wayne & Chicago Railway Co., West Shore & Jersey Railroad Co., Philadelphia & Camden Ferry Co., Pennsylvania Co., Pittsburgh, Cincinnati, Chicago & St. Louis Railroad Co., Equitable Life Assurance Society of United States, Philadelphia Saving Fund Co.

WALTER N. ROTHSCHILD

Banks.—Director Title Guaranty & Trust Co. of New York, trustee.

Corporations.—Director American Merchandising Corporation, Associated Merchandising Corporation (member executive committee), North American Inter-Insurers Co., Retail Research Association, Abraham & Straus, Inc.

CHARLES B. SEGER

Banks.—Director National Bank of Commerce in New York, International Acceptance Bank, Inc., New York.

Corporations.—President and chairman of the board United States Rubber Co., Dominion Rubber Co., Ltd., General Rubber Co., United States Tire Co. Director Los Angeles & Salt Lake Railroad Co., Cleveland, Cincinnati, Chicago & St. Louis Railway Co., Detroit River Tunnel Co., Michigan Central Railroad Co., New Jersey Junction Railroad Co., New York & Harlem Railroad Co., Oregon Short Line Railroad Co., Oregon-Washington Railroad & Navigation Co., Pittsburgh & Lake Erie Railroad Co., Union Pacific Railroad Co., West Shore Railroad Co., National Surety Co., Pacific Oil Co., Western Union Telegraph Co., and other minor corporations.

E. R. TATNALL

Corporations.—Director Franklin Fuel Co., Philadelphia.

WILLIAM H. WILLIAMS

Banks.—Director United States Mortgage & Trust Co.

Corporations.—Chairman of the executive committee and chairman of the board of directors of the following: Missouri Pacific Railroad Co., Texas & Pacific Railway Co., International Great Northern Railway Co., Ann Arbor

Railroad Co. Director Hudson & Manhattan Railroad Co., American Refrigerator Transit Co., Warren Pipe & Foundry Co., and other minor corporations.

ADOLPH ZUKOR

Corporations.—President and director Paramount Famous Lasky Corporation. Director Motion Pictures Producers and Distributors of America, Inc.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, question 7 in our so-called "questionnaire" called for the names of all exchanges on which your firm or any of its agencies had a representative or member and the number of seats or memberships held in any of such exchanges during that 5-year period. And question 8 called for the names of all brokerage firms, security houses, or trading companies in which your firm or any of its agencies had any financial interest or management during that 5-year period.

Mr. KAHN. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. I now show you this typewritten statement and ask you if it constitutes a correct and complete answer to both of those questions.

Mr. KAHN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. I offer that in evidence and ask that it may be spread on the record of the committee's proceedings.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted, and the committee reporter will make it a part of the hearing.

(The paper referred to was marked "Committee Exhibit No. 29, June 30, 1933", and is as follows:)

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 29

Question 7. Names of all exchanges on which this firm or any of its agencies had a representative or member and the number of seats or memberships held in any of the said exchanges during the years 1927 to 1931, inclusive:

One membership in the New York Stock Exchange.

One associate membership in the New York Curb Exchange.

Question 8. Names of all brokerage firms, security houses, or trading companies in which this firm or any of its agencies had any financial interest or management representation during the years 1927 to 1931, inclusive:

European Merchant Banking Co., Ltd., London, England.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Kahn, question 9 (A) of our so-called "questionnaire" called for a list of all stock and bond issues in which your firm or any of its agencies has participated to the extent of not less than \$250,000, together with the following details: Whether such participation was in the originating terms group, the bankers, the wholesale distributors, or any other group. We received from you in answer to that question this typewritten document which I now show you. Please look at it and tell us if it constitutes a correct and complete answer to that question.

Mr. KAHN. Mr. Pecora, I take it for granted, of course, that this is a correct copy of the data we furnished you, and as such we accept it and testify to its correctness.

Mr. PECORA. Then it may be received, subject to any correction that you may want to make upon any subsequent confirmation of it.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. I think a correction has been made to it.

Mr. PECORA. That is the reason why I made that statement.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted, and the committee reporter will make it a part of the record.

(The answer to question 9 (A) was marked "Committee Exhibit No. 30, June 30, 1933." See p. 1360.)

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Chairman, with respect to the answer to question 9(A) just offered in evidence, we have made a recapitulation of all stock and bond issues of over \$250,000, by years, in which companies or concerns other than Kuhn, Loeb & Co. acted as managers during that 5-year period, and I want to offer it in evidence subject to any correction that the witness or any member of his firm or representative may find it necessary to make in that recapitulation.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. Do you mean in which they participated?

Mr. PECORA. In which they participated but in which they were not the managers.

The CHAIRMAN. It may be admitted, and the committee reporter will make it a part of the record.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. I do not suppose that we could compare it here now.

Mr. PECORA. No; but we will have it made available to you.

Mr. DE GERSDORFF. Will it be in New York?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. KAHN. Again we will say that inasmuch as it was prepared by you from data furnished by us, we of course accept it as correct.

Mr. PECORA. Well, that is our own recapitulation, and I won't even ask you to authenticate it. But I am offering it in evidence and calling attention to the circumstances under which it was prepared, and by whom it was prepared, and we will furnish you with a copy of it so that, if you care to call our attention to any errors in it, you will have ample opportunity for so doing.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted and made a part of the record.

(The recapitulation of all stocks and bond issues of over \$250,000 by years from 1927 to 1931 in which other companies acted as managers, was marked "Committee Exhibit No. 31, June 30, 1933." See p. 1369.)

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, question 9 (B) in our so-called "questionnaire" called for a list of all stock and bond issues in which your firm or any of its agencies participated to the extent of not less than \$250,000, together with the following details: Date of offer, amount of issue, rate, maturity, cost price, offering price, manager, spread, profit, and amount of participation in each group. In reply thereto we received the following typewritten statement or document, which I will show you and ask you kindly to look at it and see if you can identify it as a correct and complete answer to that question.

Mr. KAHN. We make the same answer, that we accept it as being correct.

Mr. PECORA. I offer it in evidence and ask that it may be spread on the record of the proceedings of the committee.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted, and the committee reporter will make it a part of the record.

(The answer to question 9 (B) was marked "Committee Exhibit No. 32, June 30, 1933." See p. 1375.)

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, or rather, Mr. Chairman, we have made a recapitulation of the data shown in the exhibit last offered in evidence, and I wish to offer it in evidence and ask that it may be spread

on the record. This is a recapitulation of all stock and bond issues of over \$250,000, by class, which Kuhn, Loeb & Co. originated and managed in the 5-year period from 1927 to 1931, both inclusive. Mr. Chairman, I wish to offer this in evidence and ask that it may be spread on the record of the hearings, and we will be glad to furnish the witness with a copy thereof for his examination and any correction that he may desire to make.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted, and the committee reporter will make it a part of the record.

(The recapitulation of all stock and bond issues of over \$250,000 which Kuhn, Loeb & Co. originated and managed from 1927 to 1931, was marked "Committee Exhibit No. 33, June 30, 1933." See p. 1380.)

Mr. STEWART. Mr. Pecora, we will have a copy of that to look over, will we?

Mr. PECORA. Certainly, and you may call our attention to any corrections that you may desire made.

Mr. STEWART. Thank you.

Mr. PECORA. Question no. 10 of our questionnaire called for a list of all stock pools, joint accounts, and—or syndicates in which your firm or any of its agencies or representatives participated, with the name of the security involved, names of all participants, and all details with respect to the amount of participation, and profits and losses therein. In response thereto we received this typewritten statement which I now show you. Kindly look at it and tell us if you can identify it as a correct and complete answer to that question.

Mr. KAHN. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. I offer it in evidence and ask that it may be spread on the record of the committee's hearings.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted, and the committee reporter will see that it is made a part of the record.

(The answer to question 10 was marked "Committee Exhibit No. 34, June 30, 1933." See p. 1392.)

Mr. PECORA. Question no. 11 of our questionnaire called for the names of all Governments, States, municipalities, and corporations in connection with which your firm or any of its agents has acted as fiscal agent during that 5-year period, together with a statement of the services rendered for each of the same. In reply thereto we received this typewritten document which I now show you, and I will ask you to look at it and tell us if you can identify it as a correct and complete answer to that question.

Mr. KAHN. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. I offer that in evidence, and ask that it may be spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted, and the committee reporter will make it a part of the record.

(The answer to question 11 was marked "Committee Exhibit No. 35, June 30, 1933." See p. 1396.)

Mr. PECORA. Question no. 12 of our questionnaire called for a list of all bond or debenture issues, foreign or domestic, of which Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or any of its agencies was the syndicate manager and which issues have been or are now in default; and any issues floated prior to 1927 which were in default at any time during the period

of 1927 to 1931, both inclusive. In response thereto we have received the following typewritten statement, which I show you and ask you if you can identify as a correct and complete answer to that question.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct, subject to the change mentioned in our letter of May 25, which requested a transfer of one item from list 15 to this list 12.

Mr. PECORA. With that statement I offer it in evidence and ask that it may be made a part of the record.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted, and the committee reporter will make it a part of the hearings.

(The answer to question 12 was marked "Committee Exhibit No. 36, June 30, 1933." See p. 1398.)

Mr. PECORA. Question no. 13 called for the names of all issues on which a member or representative of your firm or any of the agencies connected therewith acted as a member of a protective or reorganization committee during the period 1927 to 1931, both inclusive. In reply thereto we received a typewritten statement, a copy of which I now show you, and I ask you if you recognize it as being a complete and correct answer to that question.

Mr. KAHN. That is all right.

Mr. PECORA. I offer it in evidence and ask that it may be spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted, and the committee reporter will make it a part of the record.

(The answer to question 13 was marked "Committee Exhibit No. 37, June 30, 1933." See p. 1399.)

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn, question no. 15 of our questionnaire called for the names of all issues in which your firm or any of its agencies had any participation of not less than \$250,000, which are now or have been at any time during this 5-year period already mentioned in default, such information to include the date of default, present market value of the security, amount outstanding, and names and addresses of secretaries of committees formed to protect the interests of investors or for reorganization purposes. In reply thereto we have received the typewritten statement which I now hand over to you, or it is a copy of that paper, and I ask you if that is a correct and complete answer.

Mr. BUTTENWIESER. That is correct, with the reciprocal change due to the fact that one issue has been shifted from the answer to question 12 to the answer to question 15.

Mr. PECORA. With that correction I ask that it may be spread on the record of the committee's proceedings.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted, and the committee reporter will make it a part of the hearings.

(The answer to question 15 was marked "Committee Exhibit No. 38, June 30, 1933." See p. 1400.)

Mr. PECORA. Question 19 of our questionnaire called for the details of all stock issues in which your firm or any of its agencies participated, or in which a trading account is maintained, showing in the first classification the number of shares sold, the cost of such shares, the price to the public, and the net profit on each issue, and in the latter classification the period during which the account was carried,

the total number of shares bought and sold, and the net accruing profit or loss.

In reply thereto we received a typewritten statement, of which the paper which I now show you purports to be a copy. Will you look at that and tell us whether you can identify that as a complete and correct answer to that question?

Mr. STEWART. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. I offer that in evidence and ask that it be spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted in evidence and spread upon the record.

(The answer to question 19 was received in evidence, marked "Committee Exhibit 39 of June 30, 1933." See p. 140.)

Mr. PECORA. Question no. 20 of our questionnaire called for a transcript of all loan accounts in the names of any other persons, firms, or corporations in which the collateral pledged consisted of securities, and in which your firm or any of its agencies participated as a member of the original terms group, banking group, or wholesale group or distributors, or otherwise, and in reply thereto we received the typewritten statement of which the paper which I now show you purports to be a copy. Will you kindly look at it and see if you can identify it as a complete and correct answer to that question?

Mr. STEWART. That is correct, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. I offer it in evidence and ask that it be spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted and spread on the record.

(Answer to question no. 20 was received in evidence, marked "Committee Exhibit 40 of June 30, 1933." See p. 140.)

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Chairman, I think that is all we want to ask of the witness at this time, or at this present series of hearings.

If the witness has any statement he would like to make to the committee before leaving the stand, I think an opportunity will be given to you now, Mr. Kahn.

Mr. KAHN. Thank you very much, Mr. Pecora and Senators, but I am afraid I have troubled you long enough with statements on my part and at undue length, and there is nothing left for me except on behalf of my associates and myself to thank you for your patience and your consideration, which has been greatly appreciated, and to wish every possible success to the labors of your committee.

The CHAIRMAN. We are obliged to you, Mr. Kahn. You have been very kind and generous in your cooperation, and we are indebted to you.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Chairman, I also desire to say on the record at this time that the counsel for the committee and the investigating staff of the committee want to express publicly our thanks to the witness and his firm for the cooperation they have uniformly accorded us from the beginning of our investigation into their activities.

(At this point there was some informal conversation off the record, after which the following occurred:)

Mr. KAHN. I think I ought to say one more word to express our great appreciation of the extraordinary diligence and accuracy with which the committee's stenographers have accomplished their

purpose. They have been a marvel to us, both as to the speed with which we got the record and as to the accuracy with which they understood my quaint French-Canadian accent, as an English newspaper termed it.

Mr. PECORA. Now, I will ask if Mr. H. H. Lee is present.

Mr. LEE. Yes.

Mr. KAHN. Then we may be excused?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. KAHN. Thank you.

(Thereupon Mr. Kahn and his associates withdrew.)

Mr. PECORA. Will you come forward, Mr. Lee.

(Thereupon Mr. Henry H. Lee, president of the Pennroad Corporation; Mr. C. B. Heiserman, counsel for the Pennroad Corporation; and S. H. Ogden, vice president and treasurer of the Pennroad Corporation, took their places at the committee hearing table.)

Mr. PECORA. Have you been sworn, Mr. Lee?

Mr. LEE. No; I have not.

The CHAIRMAN. Mr. Lee, you solemnly swear that you will tell the truth, the whole truth, and nothing but the truth, regarding the matters now under investigation by the committee. So help you God.

Mr. LEE. I do.

TESTIMONY OF HENRY H. LEE, PRESIDENT OF THE PENNROAD CORPORATION—BUSINESS ADDRESS: ROOM 1264, 1617 PENNSYLVANIA BOULEVARD, PHILADELPHIA, PA.—RESIDENCE: MOYLAN, PA.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Lee, will you give your full name, business or occupation, and residence and office address to the stenographer?

Mr. LEE. Henry H. Lee. I am president of the Pennroad Corporation. My business address is room 1264, 1617 Pennsylvania Boulevard, Philadelphia, Pa., and my residence is Moylan, Pa.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Lee, how long have you been president of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. LEE. Since the organization of the corporation.

Mr. PECORA. That was on April 24, 1929?

Mr. LEE. Correct, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Prior to that time were you connected in any way with the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir; I was. I was treasurer of the Pennsylvania Railroad.

Mr. PECORA. For what period of time?

Mr. LEE. I think from some time in 1924 to the time of my resignation.

Mr. PECORA. Did you resign as treasurer of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. in order to become the president of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Did you have any part in the organization or in the conferences or negotiations that led to the organization and incorporation of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. LEE. Only from the time that I was invited to become the president of the Pennroad Corporation, which was about a week or so before its actual date of incorporation.

Mr. PECORA. Are you familiar with the substance of the conferences or the negotiations that resulted in the incorporation of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. LEE. No; I am not, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. Can you tell this committee from any knowledge in your possession what the purposes were for the incorporation of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. LEE. If I may say so, I think that I cannot state them as well as I believe they are stated in the letter of Mr. W. W. Atterbury, which has been filed with the committee.

Mr. PECORA. Well, the letter of General Atterbury, which is in evidence here, describes those purposes in rather general terms. Can you not elaborate on them in your own language?

Mr. LEE. From my own standpoint, I think, as the president of the corporation—and I think the directors agree with me—that our purpose, while it was stated as set forth in that letter, is a broader thing than that, because we look upon what we have purchased in the first place as being purchased in the interest of the corporation itself.

Mr. PECORA. Which corporation?

Mr. LEE. Pennroad Corporation I am talking about. Of the Pennroad Corporation itself. And we considered them in the light of investments at the time they were made.

Mr. PECORA. You are speaking now of the investments that were made by the Pennroad Corporation after its incorporation?

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. What I am trying to get at is a statement from you in your own language of the purposes for which the Pennroad Corporation was created.

Mr. LEE. It was created in the interest of the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. to make investments that the directors of Pennroad see fit to make.

Mr. PECORA. Well, were the investments to be made by the Pennroad Corporation of a character that would serve the interests of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. and its stockholders?

Mr. LEE. I think so.

Mr. PECORA. What was the object, or, rather, what kind of investments was it proposed or intended to make through the medium of the Pennroad Corporation, and to make which the Pennroad Corporation was created?

Mr. LEE. Do you mean what was the idea in the minds of the persons who brought about the formation of the Pennroad?

Mr. PECORA. Yes, sir.

Mr. LEE. Prior to the formation?

Mr. PECORA. Yes, sir.

Mr. LEE. I can not answer that question myself, sir.

The CHAIRMAN. Who were the original officers, the first officers of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. LEE. Myself as president, a gentleman named W. U. Moyer, as vice president and secretary; Mr. Samuel H. Ogden, as vice president and treasurer; Robert P. Andrews, auditor, and Charles Bidlingmeyer as assistant secretary and assistant treasurer.

Mr. PECORA. Do you mean to say, Mr. Lee, that you became president of the Pennroad Corporation upon its creation on April 24, 1929, and have been its president ever since, and are still unable to tell this committee what the purposes were for which the corporation was created?

Mr. LEE. Well, Mr. Pecora, I have tried to answer that question by my previous testimony.

Mr. PECORA. Well, the answer you made to my question was that you could not tell us; you did not know. I was just wondering if you meant that literally?

Mr. LEE. Please pardon me if I seemed confused about it, but I thought that my answer to your particular question was that the purposes for which the corporation was formed were set forth, I thought admirably, in Mr. Atterbury's letter, to which I referred, and that, to my own knowledge, the corporation was formed to protect the interests of the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad, to make investments, and so forth.

Mr. PECORA. What protection was it contemplated to give to the interests of the Pennsylvania Railroad and its stockholders through the medium of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. LEE. By the acquisition of securities of railroad companies principally which might be valuable from a strategic standpoint in connection with the railroad question generally in the United States.

Senator BARKLEY. And which might be bought by other roads, and you formed this corporation for that purpose?

Mr. LEE. They might be, sir.

Mr. PECORA. In connection with that purpose was it in contemplation by the acquisition of the stock of such other railroads that a grouping of railroad lines by the Interstate Commerce Commission might be circumvented in any way?

Mr. LEE. Well, of course, it is perfectly true that any acquisition of a railroad stock, or a railroad property, by the Pennroad Corporation was one which would not have to be passed upon by the Interstate Commerce Commission. At the same time, sir, it does seem to me that the investments that were made in certain railroads were just as good in our hands as in the hands of others. And further, nobody can buy them from us—no other railroad can buy them from us, without going to the Interstate Commerce Commission.

Mr. PECORA. Well, another holding company could buy them from you without going to the Interstate Commerce Commission, could it not?

Mr. LEE. I do not think it could now under recent legislation.

Mr. PECORA. I mean at that time when this company was created?

Mr. LEE. At that time; yes.

Mr. PECORA. At that time it could?

Mr. LEE. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. At that time you did not know what legislation was subsequently going to be enacted?

The CHAIRMAN. Were all the officers of the Pennroad Corporation stockholders in the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. LEE. I do not know, Senator. I was myself, and I am.

Senator BARKLEY. What had been your occupation prior to the time when you became president of this company?

Mr. LEE. I was treasurer of the Pennsylvania Railroad, sir.

Senator BARKLEY. You say you were asked to take the presidency about a week before you took it?

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

Senator BARKLEY. Who made that request?

Mr. LEE. As I recall, I was asked by Mr. A. J. County.

Senator BARKLEY. Who is he?

Mr. LEE. Mr. A. J. County is financial vice president of the Pennsylvania Railroad.

Senator BARKLEY. He was acting for the authorities of the Pennsylvania Railroad?

Mr. LEE. I assume so.

Senator BARKLEY. You understood that?

Mr. LEE. Sir?

Senator BARKLEY. You understood that?

Mr. LEE. Well, yes; he must have been.

Senator BARKLEY. Of course. You did not go into the thing like going up a blind alley. You knew what you were doing, and you knew why.

Mr. LEE. I beg your pardon; I did not hear you.

Senator BARKLEY. I say, you knew what you were doing, and you knew the reason why you were doing it, did you not, when you became president of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. LEE. Well, Senator, I knew nothing about it prior to my being officially invited to become its president.

Senator BARKLEY. I know, but you knew what you were doing when you accepted its invitation?

Mr. LEE. Yes.

Senator BARKLEY. And you have as president of it since learned what its objects were?

Mr. LEE. Yes.

Mr. BARKLEY. And those objects you have stated to be the purchase of the stocks of railroad companies in which the Pennsylvania Railroad might be interested from the standpoint of acquiring them, and also in which it might have an indirect interest by preventing others from acquiring them?

Mr. LEE. Well, I think that is correct.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Lee, do you know Mr. Frank E. Taplin?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. When did you last see him?

Mr. LEE. Wednesday night of this week.

Mr. PECORA. That is the day before yesterday?

Mr. LEE. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Where?

Mr. LEE. In the lobby of the Carlton Hotel.

Mr. PECORA. Here in Washington?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Did you have any discussion with him with respect to your appearing as a witness before this committee?

Mr. LEE. Not any discussion, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Well, did you allude to the fact when you saw him last Wednesday evening that you were under subpoena to appear before this committee?

Mr. LEE. I did.

Mr. PECORA. And did he say anything about any efforts that had been made to place him similarly under such a subpoena?

Mr. LEE. Well, he said he had not been subpoenaed.

Mr. PECORA. Did he say that he had been advised by his office in Cleveland that efforts had been made to subpoena him there?

Mr. LEE. Yes; I do recall his saying something about it.

Mr. PECORA. What did he say about it?

Mr. LEE. All he said was that he understood they were trying to subpoena him, but he had not been subpoenaed.

Mr. PECORA. And so being in Washington where the hearings of this committee were being held this week, he left on Wednesday night, did he?

Mr. LEE. He said he was going to New York Wednesday night. May I add, Mr. Pecora, that the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co., of which I am a director, was holding a regular meeting in New York on Thursday. My meeting with Mr. Taplin was entirely accidental. I had no knowledge he was around at all. And when I saw him I said that I could not attend the board meeting because I was subpoenaed to appear here, and then followed the conversation I referred to.

Senator BARKLEY. Is he a member of that board?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Did you tell him in that conversation Wednesday night that you had been subpoenaed to produce here records and documents bearing upon a certain transaction which the Pennroad Corporation had through or with Taplin?

Mr. LEE. I do not recall that I did, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know whether anyone else gave him any such information about your having been subpoenaed to produce such records?

Mr. LEE. Mr. Heiserman here tells me that he did make such a remark to him.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Heiserman is this gentleman sitting alongside of you here?

Mr. LEE. Yes.

Mr. HEISERMAN. C. B. Heiserman.

Mr. PECORA. Counsel for whom?

Mr. LEE. Pennroad Corporation.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know the reason, Mr. Lee, for the Pennroad Corporation at its inception issuing voting trust certificates instead of common stock having the usual voting rights?

Mr. LEE. Well, it was set forth, as I recall it, in the circulars that the stock would be carried in a voting to assure continuity of management.

Mr. PECORA. And under the voting-trust agreement the purchasers of those certificates were deprived for a period of 10 years of any and all voice in the management and operation of the company, were they not?

Mr. LEE. That is correct, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And that management was vested in three trustees?

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. Who were named in the voting-trust agreement and certificates?

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. Now, at the time of the incorporation of the Pennroad Corporation there was in existence and actually functioning as a going concern another company called the Pennsylvania Co., was there not?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And that was a subsidiary of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., which owned all of the stock of the Pennsylvania Co., was it not?

Mr. LEE. To my recollection that is correct.

Mr. PECORA. Were you an officer of the Pennsylvania Co.?

Mr. LEE. Yes; I was treasurer of the Pennsylvania Co.

Mr. PECORA. Now, the Pennsylvania Co. was organized for the purpose of acquiring and holding securities, was it not?

Mr. LEE. That was the purpose.

Mr. PECORA. Including the securities of railroad companies?

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know any reason why that vehicle, namely, the Pennsylvania Co., could not have been used to effectuate the purposes for which the Pennroad Corporation was created?

Mr. LEE. Mr. Pecora, I have no knowledge about that, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Have you no opinion on it, either?

Mr. LEE. I do not know whether my opinion would be of value.

Mr. PECORA. Well, let us have it.

Mr. LEE. I should assume the Pennsylvania Co. being a wholly owned subsidiary of the Pennsylvania Railroad—which is my recollection, and I believe it is correct—could not, it was felt, make the investments of the sort that the Pennroad could. But I ask you not to forget that I only got into this situation about a week before the corporation was formed and have no knowledge of what conversations may have been held which led up to the formation of Pennroad.

Mr. PECORA. Why was it considered, or why, in your opinion, do you think that the Pennsylvania Co. could not have been used to make the investments for the benefit of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. that the Pennroad Corporation was created for?

Mr. LEE. Well, the Pennroad was created as an independent instrumentality, if you will recall the words of our original circulars.

Mr. PECORA. Why could not the Pennsylvania Co. have been used to carry out those purposes? Why could it not have been used as an instrumentality already in existence?

Mr. LEE. Well, it was wholly owned by the Pennsylvania Railroad.

Mr. PECORA. What of that?

The CHAIRMAN. It could issue and sell stock to the public, could it not?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir; I think it would have every right to do that.

Mr. PECORA. And that is what the Pennroad Corporation did, is it not?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir. That is what the Pennroad Corporation did.

Mr. PECORA. Well, can you tell us any reason why the existing corporation called the "Pennsylvania Co." was not used in preference to the Pennroad Corporation, which had to be specially created for accomplishing or obtaining the purposes that the organizers had in mind?

Mr. LEE. Not of my own knowledge, Mr. Pecora.

Senator STEIWER. I wish to leave, Mr. Pecora, and I would like to ask a few questions, if you will permit me to interrupt you.

Mr. PECORA. Certainly.

Senator STEIWER. Mr. Lee, I want to ask who determined the stocks that were to be included in the investment portfolio of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. LEE. The board of directors of the Pennroad Corporation.

Senator STEIWER. Were they all identified with the Pennsylvania Railroad?

Mr. LEE. The first board was; yes.

Senator STEIWER. Has that already been covered?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Senator STEIWER. And who made the suggestions to them? Where did the inspiration come from to buy the stock of any particular railroad?

Mr. LEE. Well, from the directors themselves, I should say.

Senator STEIWER. Acting independently on their own judgment?

Mr. LEE. Acting independently on their own judgment.

Senator STEIWER. Had the other members of the board of directors more independent information than you had as to the nature and purpose and objects of this corporation?

Mr. LEE. I think so.

Senator STEIWER. Can you name the persons on the board who seemed to have inside information as to what the corporation was organized for?

Mr. LEE. On the Pennroad board?

Senator STEIWER. Yes.

Mr. LEE. This is the first board of directors of the Pennroad Corporation.

The CHAIRMAN. What is?

Mr. LEE. I am reading now from the report: W. W. Atterbury, Effingham B. Morris, Charles E. Ingersoll, Levi L. Rue, Jay Cooke, R. B. Mellon, A. J. County, and Henry H. Lee.

Senator STEIWER. And the suggestion to purchase certain stocks came from some of those gentlemen?

Mr. LEE. Yes; I should say so.

Senator STEIWER. Was there a chairman of the board?

Mr. LEE. No; the president presides.

Senator STEIWER. You, in your capacity as president, presided at the board?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Senator STEIWER. And you are nominally the head of the board?

Mr. LEE. That is right.

Senator STEIWER. And yet you did not initiate or suggest the purchase of this property?

Mr. LEE. Not necessarily. Now—

Senator STEIWER (interposing). Well, did you at all?

Mr. LEE. I have in some instances.

Senator STEIWER. Subsequently you mean?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir. As soon as I was elected and assumed office as president, then I think I was qualified to function. Prior to that time is the time I have spoken of, when I was not familiar with the conferences that went on that resulted in the formation of the company.

Senator STEIWER. What properties had been acquired prior to the time that you assumed the presidency of the company?

Mr. LEE. None, sir.

Senator STEIWER. Then, after you assumed the presidency of the company, did you immediately suggest or initiate the purchase of property?

Mr. LEE. No. The directors among themselves then began to cast around for investments.

Senator STEIWER. Were you a director?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Senator STEIWER. In those matters?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Senator STEIWER. Who suggested the purchase of the various properties that were actually acquired?

Mr. LEE. The first one to be suggested, to my remembrance, was the Detroit, Toledo & Ironton Railroad. I am not able to answer the question at present as to who suggested this purchase.

Senator STEIWER. You did not?

Mr. LEE. I did not.

Senator STEIWER. What was the next property acquired?

Mr. LEE. I have very little data here. My subpoena was in connection with Pittsburgh & West Virginia. So, if I may, I would like you to give me a little time to see what my records are that I have here.

(Mr. Lee conferred with Mr. Ogden.)

The CHAIRMAN. The board of directors that you have just read off, I presume, elected at that first meeting the officers?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir. The first purchase, as I recall it—now I am speaking mostly from memory—was Detroit, Toledo & Ironton. Probably the second one was the Canton Co.

Senator STEIWER. Did you suggest the purchase of that property?

Mr. LEE. No, sir.

Senator STEIWER. Do you know who did?

Mr. LEE. In that particular case my remembrance is that negotiations with the people who owned the stock of the Canton were initiated with Mr. A. J. County, a director of the Pennroad Corporation.

Senator STEIWER. You think he suggested it to the board; suggested the purchase to the board of directors?

Mr. LEE. He took up the negotiations with the people who owned the stock, and I don't remember whether he suggested it to the board or not. The probabilities are that the negotiations went on and then the matter was set up formally and reported for action.

Senator STEIWER. You have no definite recollection of that?

Mr. LEE. I have no definite recollection.

Senator BARKLEY. In all these cases who started the negotiations, the purchaser or the seller?

Mr. LEE. I think both ways. In one case it might have been the purchaser and the other case the seller.

Senator BARKLEY. You did not organize the Pennroad Co. to buy up stocks of certain railroads and then just sit down in your office waiting for them to come in to see you about it, did you? Didn't you go out after them? Didn't you negotiate or start to negotiate with the roads you wanted to buy?

Mr. LEE. After the formation of the company.

Senator BARKLEY. Well, that is what I am talking about.

Mr. LEE. Yes.

Senator BARKLEY. Of course, you didn't do it before you organized it. That is a fact, isn't it?

Mr. LEE. With respect to two of them only. That is Detroit, Toledo & Ironton and the Canton Co.

Senator BARKLEY. Then you bought stocks of other railroads besides those two?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Senator BARKLEY. Were they in contemplation as possible objects of purchase at the time the Pennroad Corporation was organized?

Mr. LEE. Not to my knowledge.

Senator BARKLEY. How soon after it was organized before they were discussed?

Mr. LEE. Well, we rapidly got into the purchase of an interest in a small road called "the Raritan River Railroad", stock of the Boston & Maine Railroad, stock of the New York, New Haven & Hartford Railroad. I think it was in about that order, and again I am testifying from memory.

Senator BARKLEY. How many railroads are there whose stock you purchased or part of whose stock you purchased for the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. LEE. There are 15 railroads on this list, which is the company's last annual report.

Senator BARKLEY. You say you have been the active head of this organization?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Senator BARKLEY. Since its incorporation?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Senator BARKLEY. Are the board of directors of the Pennroad Co. all on the board of the Pennsylvania Co.?

Mr. LEE. Of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Senator BARKLEY. Railroad Co.

Mr. LEE. Not now.

Senator BARKLEY. Were they at the beginning?

Mr. LEE. They were, except myself.

Senator BARKLEY. You were the treasurer of the company, though, at that time?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir; until I resigned on the day I became president of the Pennroad.

Senator BARKLEY. Yes. You have been the active head, then, of the Pennroad Co. since you took the presidency?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Senator BARKLEY. Have you determined its policy?

Mr. LEE. No, sir.

Senator BARKLEY. Who have?

Mr. LEE. The board of directors.

Senator BARKLEY. Have you been the real president or—I don't like to use this word—

Mr. LEE. I understand it.

Senator BARKLEY. Or the figurehead? Which have you been?

Mr. LEE. I have never considered myself a figurehead, but I think I am well disciplined enough to say that my acts must be supervised and directed by the board of directors of the corporation.

Senator BARKLEY. You resigned as treasurer of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. in order to devote all your time to this company?

Mr. LEE. That is correct, sir.

Senator BARKLEY. I do not mean by my question to imply that you were not in good faith the operating head of the company, but I am trying to find out what the facts are. That is all I will ask right now.

Mr. PECORA. Since you have been president of the Pennroad Corporation—of course that means throughout its entire life up to the present time—have you sought any guidance, assistance of any kind, from the executive officers of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. with respect to the investments that your company made or was to make in the securities of other railroads?

Mr. LEE. Only those officers of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. who at the same time were directors of my company.

Mr. PECORA. How many of the directors of your company were officers of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. and who are they?

Mr. LEE. You mean at the present time, Mr. Pecora?

Mr. PECORA. At the beginning; and then you can tell us at the present time.

Mr. LEE. All of them?

Mr. PECORA. All of them.

Mr. LEE. All of them were either officers or directors of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. except myself.

Mr. PECORA. How long did those men continue as the officers and directors of the Pennroad Corporation before any substantial change was made in the personnel of your corporation?

Mr. LEE. Will you excuse me a moment, sir? [After examining documents and conferring with Mr. Ogden:] Mr. Pecora, the original directors of the Pennroad Corporation are still directors of the corporation except Jay Cooke, who died a short time ago; Charles E. Ingersoll, who died some time ago; and Levi L. Rue, who also died perhaps 2 years ago.

The CHAIRMAN. Who have taken their places?

Mr. LEE. I am not sure, Mr. Chairman, just who took somebody's place. If I may go on with this.

The CHAIRMAN. Yes.

Mr. LEE. James S. Alexander was elected a director of our corporation on March 12, 1930. A. H. S. Post was elected March 12, 1930, and Philip Stockton was elected the same date.

Mr. PECORA. So that the only change made in the personnel of the officers and board of the Pennroad Corporation from its inception were those changes that were occasioned by deaths?

Mr. LEE. No, Mr. Pecora. We added three directors to our board when we elected the three last-named gentlemen on March 12, 1930. The directors who have died, whose places have been filled, were filled by Joseph Wayne, Jr., Rodman E. Griscom, William M. Elkins, and George W. Bovenizer.

Mr. PECORA. George W. Bovenizer is one of the partners of Kuhn, Loeb & Co.?

Mr. LEE. That is correct, sir.

Senator BARKLEY. You now have seven new men, then, who were not on at the beginning?

Mr. OGDEN. I make it five.

Senator BARKLEY. Well, there were three then, and you said you added three. That would have been six. This last list you read four.

Mr. LEE. We have one vacancy in the board, Senator—Mr. Cooke.

Senator BARKLEY. You have one now.

The CHAIRMAN. How many directors have you now?

Mr. LEE. We have an authorized board of 11. There are 10 on the board. We have not filled the vacancy caused by Mr. Cooke's death.

The CHAIRMAN. How many shares of stock did you have in the Pennroad Co. at the beginning and how many now, Mr. Lee?

Mr. LEE. I do not recollect, sir. I will be glad to furnish the information, but I haven't it in mind at the present time.

Senator BARKLEY. You are a stockholder?

Mr. LEE. I am a holder of voting trust certificates, if you please, Senator.

The CHAIRMAN. Let us have that data.

Senator BARKLEY. These men who have been added are also connected with the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. LEE. No; not at the time they were added to the board.

Senator BARKLEY. Are they now?

Mr. LEE. Only one of them—Mr. Joseph Wayne. He was a director of Pennroad before he was elected to the Pennsylvania Railroad board.

Senator BARKLEY. What connection have the others with the Pennsylvania Railroad?

Mr. LEE. They have none, sir.

Senator BARKLEY. Are they connected with any of the railroads whose stock was bought by the Pennroad Co.?

Mr. LEE. No; I don't believe they are.

Senator BARKLEY. Are they connected with any other railroad?

Mr. LEE. I don't know at this time.

Senator GOLDSBOROUGH. Mr. A. H. S. Post is president of the Mercantile Trust of Baltimore City, isn't he?

Mr. LEE. Yes. Now, Mr. Post is a director of the Canton Co.

Mr. PECORA. The three voting trustees are the only persons authorized and empowered to use the offices of the directors of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Who were the three original voting trustees of your corporation?

Mr. LEE. W. W. Atterbury, Jay Cooke, and Effingham B. Morris.

Mr. PECORA. Now those three men at that time were all directors of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. General Atterbury was the president of the railroad company?

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. Still is?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Do you keep in close touch with him regarding the affairs of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. LEE. I consult him from time to time from his standpoint as a director of Pennroad Corporation.

Mr. PECORA. Also from his standpoint as president and a director of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. LEE. Not as far as I am concerned, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Well, don't you understand and haven't you stated already that the Pennroad Corporation was organized for the purpose of protecting the interests of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. and its stockholders?

Mr. LEE. I stated that when we were organized.

Mr. PECORA. Then that is still the purpose, isn't it?

Mr. LEE. Mr. Pecora, I look at it otherwise; that while the corporation is formed for that purpose, bought securities, it bought them as its own investments on the direction of its own board of directors.

Mr. PECORA. Who selected the successors to any of the three original voting trustees?

Mr. LEE. The remaining voting trustees have the right to do it.

Mr. PECORA. So that the original board of trustees is virtually a self-perpetuating body with their successors?

Mr. LEE. I suppose that is correct.

Mr. PECORA. And the original voting trustees were all directors or officers of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. Who took the place of Mr. Cooke as a voting trustee? (Mr. Lee started to confer with Mr. Ogden.)

Mr. PECORA. Can't you tell us without reference to any records?

Mr. LEE. No, I cannot, Mr. Pecora. I want to be entirely correct about it if I can. James S. Alexander, I think, took Mr. Cooke's place, to the best of my recollection.

Mr. PECORA. Who took Mr. Morris' place?

Mr. LEE. Mr. Morris is still one.

Mr. PECORA. He is still a voting trustee?

Mr. LEE. That is right.

Mr. PECORA. And is General Atterbury one of the three voting trustees?

Mr. LEE. No, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Who took his place?

Mr. LEE. To the best of my recollection Mr. Joseph Wayne, Jr.

The CHAIRMAN. About when?

Mr. LEE. In June 1930.

Senator BARKLEY. Those three that are now trustees are officers or directors of the Pennsylvania Railroad?

Mr. LEE. Two of them.

Senator BARKLEY. Which two?

Mr. LEE. Mr. Effingham B. Morris and Mr. Joseph B. Wayne.

Senator BARKLEY. And what is the other man's business now? Alexander—what is his business?

Mr. LEE. Mr. Alexander is dead.

Senator BARKLEY. Who took his place?

Mr. LEE. William M. Potts.

Senator BARKLEY. So that Potts is now a member in place of Alexander? Is he a director of the Pennsylvania?

Mr. LEE. No, sir.

Senator BARKLEY. What is his business?

Mr. LEE. He is practically a retired man.

Mr. PECORA. What was his business?

Senator BARKLEY. What was it before?

Mr. LEE. The only connection I have known him in, in Philadelphia, was as director of the Philadelphia National Bank and president of the Enterprise Transit Co.

Mr. PECORA. Is that a local traction company?

Mr. LEE. I don't think it is. I don't know what it is. Mr. Pecora, I would like to add if I may that Mr. Potts, the latest member of the voting trustees, is a very heavy holder of voting-trust certificates.

Mr. PECORA. How many certificates does he hold?

Mr. LEE. Over 20,000.

Mr. PECORA. Out of a total of over 9,000,000 that are outstanding.

Senator BARKLEY. Is he a stockholder of the Pennsylvania Railroad?

Mr. LEE. I don't know.

Mr. PECORA. As president of the Pennroad Corporation has it been your intention and purpose to carry out the purposes for which the corporation was created?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir; to make investments.

Mr. PECORA. For the benefit or the protection of the interests of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., and its stockholders?

Mr. LEE. If at the same time we considered them to be for the benefit of the Pennroad Corporation itself.

Mr. PECORA. Well now, in that connection, did you favor the acquisition by the corporation of 402,119 shares of the Seaboard Air Line Railway in October 1929?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir. I presume I presided at the meeting.

Mr. PECORA. And did you think that that acquisition was intended for the benefit of the certificate holders of the Pennroad Corporation at the time it was made?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. As a matter of fact, what had been the financial history of the Seaboard Air Line Railway for some time immediately prior to the acquisition of those four hundred thousand and odd shares of its stock by your corporation?

Mr. LEE. Mr. Pecora, I am not prepared to testify, because I think my memory would be faulty on that. Remember, it was several years ago and I haven't the records here.

Mr. PECORA. Well, that was a transaction involving the acquisition of over 400,000 shares of another railroad company.

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. And that purchase involved several millions of dollars, didn't it?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Have you forgotten the details of that?

Mr. LEE. The details of the financial history of the Seaboard is what I am speaking of.

Mr. PECORA. Do you now recall whether or not at the time you advised, as president and director of the Pennroad Corporation, the purchase of these four hundred thousand odd shares of Seaboard Air Line Railway—

If the gentleman sitting alongside of you will not interrupt by whispering while I am phrasing the question I think we can make progress.

Mr. LEE. We beg your pardon, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Reporter, if you will read.

The SHORTHAND REPORTER (Mr. Randolph) (reading):

Do you now recall whether or not at the time you advised, as president and director of the Pennroad Corporation, the purchase of these four hundred thousand odd shares of Seaboard Air Line Railway—

Mr. PECORA (continuing). —Any attention or consideration had been given by you to the financial history of that railroad company?

Mr. LEE. Yes, Mr. Pecora; we have made an examination of the reports of the company and particularly of a report of Coverdale & Colpitts.

Mr. PECORA. Particularly a what report?

Mr. LEE. A report by Coverdale & Colpitts, as I recollect.

Mr. PECORA. They are engineers that make surveys and reports?

Mr. LEE. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. For railroad companies, aren't they, and investment companies?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. They are the ones that made the report and survey for the St. Paul Railroad prior to its going into a receivership?

Mr. LEE. I don't recall.

Mr. PECORA. And afterward?

Mr. LEE. I don't recall, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. Well, now, how long after the acquisition of these four hundred thousand and odd shares of Seaboard Air Line Railway by your corporation did that company go into a receivership?

Mr. LEE. Testifying from memory purely on the question; yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And do you recall that for a period of about 4 or 5 years prior to the time when your road acquired these four hundred thousand and odd shares of the Seaboard the earnings of that road had steadily and appreciably declined?

Mr. LEE. That is true, I think, but they had a short time prior to our acquisition completed a change—again I am testifying from memory—completed a change in their proposed set-up, which included an allotment of stock which in due course had the approval of the Interstate Commerce Commission. It was felt that that particular change in their financial set-up would improve their situation very materially.

Mr. PECORA. And you bought four hundred thousand-odd shares of its stock in anticipation of what might happen after a history of several years of declining earnings?

Mr. LEE. Mr. Pecora, we did not mean to buy four hundred-odd thousand shares of stock.

Mr. PECORA. Whether you meant to or not, that is what you did do, isn't it?

Mr. LEE. Unfortunately; yes.

Mr. PECORA. And that is the amount of money paid by the Pennroad Corporation to those from whom it purchased securities?

Mr. LEE. That is perfectly true.

Mr. PECORA. What did you mean to buy if you did not mean to buy four hundred thousand-odd shares of its stock?

Mr. LEE. About 125,000.

Mr. PECORA. What did you buy 400,000 for, then?

Mr. LEE. If you recall—well, that is a bad way to put it—we wanted to buy 125,000 shares to have about a million and a quarter investment in the Seaboard Air Line. We arranged and negotiated to make that purchase from the syndicate which was underwriting the forthcoming allotment of the Seaboard Air Line.

Mr. PECORA. Who managed that syndicate?

Mr. LEE. Dillon, Read & Co., I think. There may have been someone else associated with them.

Mr. PECORA. Yes; but Dillon, Read & Co. managed it?

Mr. LEE. That is right.

Mr. PECORA. Now go ahead.

Mr. LEE. And our arrangement was to take 125,000 shares. What we did do was arrange with the syndicate that we would take 25 percent of the stock that they might be required to take, hoping that it would be 125,000 shares. As I recall it, the break in the market put in the hands of the syndicate all of the stock that was offered under the allotment; practically all of it.

Mr. PECORA. In other words, the syndicate was unable to dispose of the holdings that it had in the Seaboard Air Line because of the break in the market; is that what you mean?

Mr. LEE. No. I mean that the company was not able to sell its stock to the stockholders because of the break in the market.

Mr. PECORA. Had the syndicate shown an inability to dispose of its holdings, this syndicate managed by Dillon, Read & Co.?

Mr. LEE. That would be after the event, I mean after the record date on which the stock was to be taken by the stockholders of the Seaboard.

Mr. PECORA. The first big break in the market to which you allude came on October 24, 1929, didn't it?

Mr. LEE. I don't remember the exact date.

Mr. PECORA. And this acquisition of four hundred and two thousand-odd shares of the Seaboard Air Line was made by your company on October 29, 1929, wasn't it?

Mr. LEE. I don't remember the date.

Mr. PECORA. Have you anything which would refresh your recollection on that? It is rather important.

Mr. LEE (after conferring with Mr. Ogden). My assistant tells me he thinks the settlement was made the first part of 1930.

Mr. PECORA. As of what date was the sale made?

Mr. LEE. I don't recall, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Chairman, we could make more progress if this witness came back next Thursday with sufficient data to enable him to answer questions with respect to his company's acquisition of various securities that it acquired.

Mr. HEISERMAN. Pardon me, Mr. Pecora. He came in obedience to the subpoena duces tecum which related only to the Pittsburgh & West Virginia.

Mr. PECORA. Well, I thought in view of the fact that he has been the president of this company since its inception that he would be able to testify from memory concerning these transactions.

The CHAIRMAN. He said he was prepared to go on with the Canton Co. Can you take that up now?

Mr. PECORA. Can you?

Mr. LEE. Mr. Chairman, if you don't mind, I am willing to answer questions, but I would like to refresh my mind with my own data, because these transactions took place in 1929, a great many of them, and without knowing just what information you want I would really prefer not to answer the questions for the record until I have the data.

Mr. PECORA. Can you tell us at this time from memory what the occasion was for your company acquiring that share of that Bloomfield Country Club?

Mr. LEE. Mr. Walter Franklin was president of the Detroit, Toledo & Ironton. He was made president after we bought the company. The share of stock happened to be one in his name, and we acquired it so that he could continue from a business standpoint his membership in that country club.

Mr. PECORA. He had the benefits of the membership and the company paid for it, is that it?

Mr. LEE. That is right.

Mr. PECORA. He lived in the vicinity of the Country Club, did he; near Detroit, Mich.?

Mr. LEE. I don't recall where he lived in Detroit.

Senator BARKLEY. What did you pay him for it?

Mr. LEE. \$5,000.

Senator BARKLEY. He had all the privileges of the club and his \$5,000, too?

Mr. LEE. No. I didn't understand you, Senator. He didn't own it himself. It stood in his name.

Senator BARKLEY. Did he get the \$5,000?

Mr. LEE. No, sir.

Mr. PECORA. He had all the beneficial use of that membership?

Mr. LEE. That is right.

Senator BARKLEY. Couldn't he keep that without—I don't quite see the significance of having to take over a share of stock in the country club in order that he might become president of this railroad company.

Mr. LEE. I didn't mean it that way, sir. The certificate had been bought for him for his interest by his former employer. Then when he went with the Detroit, Toledo & Ironton we bought the certificate from his former employer.

Senator BARKLEY. Who was his former employer?

Mr. LEE. At that time the Pennsylvania Railroad.

Senator BARKLEY. So that the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. owned this share of country-club stock for his benefit, and when he went with the Detroit, Toledo & Ironton they substituted for the—that is, the Pennroad Co. substituted for the Pennsylvania Co.

The CHAIRMAN. You say you made investments for the Pennroad Co. in the interest of the certificate holders. Did the Pennroad Co. make an investment in Seaboard Air Line shares?

Mr. LEE. It turned out not to be, Senator, but we were dealing with it in 1929.

Mr. PECORA. You said this custom of a corporation providing an officer or employee with a country club membership was a usual custom?

Mr. LEE. Oh, yes; I think it is quite usual, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know of any other instance than this instance of Mr. Franklin in which the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. has done that?

Mr. LEE. I don't recall any. I would like to amend my answer by saying that I didn't mean country clubs alone, but other clubs as well.

Senator BARKLEY. Is that charged up as a part of the fixed charges of the railroad company for which railroad rates are paid by the public?

Mr. LEE. You mean, in the event that a railroad company has bought such a membership?

Senator BARKLEY. Yes.

Mr. LEE. I don't know, Senator.

Mr. PECORA. Can you tell us anything about a transaction which the Pennroad Corporation had, through Mr. Frank E. Taplin, which involved the purchase of 222,930 shares of the stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. for \$37,898,100?

Mr. LEE. Did I understand you to say, Mr. Pecora, a transaction we had through Mr. Taplin?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. LEE. We did not have it through Mr. Taplin.

Mr. PECORA. Did Mr. Taplin have any part in that transaction?

Mr. LEE. We bought the Pittsburgh & West Virginia shares we own from Mr. Taplin and his associates.

Mr. PECORA. Who were his associates?

Mr. LEE. I don't know, sir.

Mr. PECORA. What proportion of the total outstanding stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. did these 222,930 shares represent?

Mr. LEE. As I recall it, 73 percent.

Mr. PECORA. At what price per share was this large block of stock purchased from Mr. Taplin and his associates?

Mr. LEE. \$170 per share.

Mr. PECORA. What was the market price of those shares at that time?

Mr. LEE. I don't recall, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. Can you not tell us by reference to any data that you may have with you?

Mr. LEE. We have no data here that covers that, but my recollection is that it was somewhere in the 140's—maybe \$140 a share.

Mr. PECORA. Did you give your consent, as president and director of the Pennroad Corporation, to that transaction?

Mr. LEE. Yes; I approved of it, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. What advantages did you see accruing to the Pennroad Corporation from that transaction?

Mr. LEE. We considered it an investment in a whole property. We were buying control.

Mr. PECORA. You could have bought control by buying 51 percent instead of 73 percent of its outstanding stock, could you not?

Mr. LEE. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Could you not?

Mr. LEE. Yes. I thought you heard my answer.

Mr. PECORA. If that was your purpose, why didn't you confine your purchase to 51 percent of the outstanding stock, instead of 73 percent, at a price around \$30 above the market?

Mr. LEE. My recollection is that the parties selling could deliver about 220,000 shares and we were willing to buy it.

Mr. PECORA. Why were you willing to buy 73 percent in order to get control, instead of only 51 percent, in view of the fact that you were paying something like \$30 above the market?

Mr. LEE. The property was in good shape; it was paying dividends and occupied a very fine strategic position in the coal and steel center of Pennsylvania.

Mr. PECORA. Were not all those elements reflected in the market price around \$140 a share?

Mr. LEE. I don't know.

The CHAIRMAN. Why should you pay that when it was offered on the market at \$140?

Mr. LEE. I do not think, Mr. Chairman, that we could possibly have bought even 51 percent on the market without a great rise in price.

Mr. PECORA. Do you think that Mr. Taplin and his associates would have sold anything like 73 percent without a great drop in the price if they attempted to sell in the open market?

Mr. LEE. I assume that would be so.

Mr. PECORA. When were the negotiations commenced that culminated in the purchase of these 222,930 shares?

Mr. LEE. I believe, during the summer of 1929.

Mr. PECORA. When were the negotiations concluded by the actual purchase?

Mr. LEE. October 16, 1929. That was the first settlement date—October 16, 1929.

Mr. PECORA. When was delivery of the 222,930 shares made to your company?

Mr. LEE. It was completed on January 7, 1930.

Mr. PECORA. Delivery was made as late as January 1930?

Mr. LEE. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. When did you say the negotiations were commenced?

Mr. LEE. October 16, 1929.

Mr. PECORA. Was any firm contract made in October 1929 with Mr. Taplin and his associates?

Mr. LEE. No; but we had an understanding with them, an oral agreement with them, prior to that time.

Mr. PECORA. When was that oral agreement entered into?

Mr. LEE. I don't recollect the date.

Mr. PECORA. How long prior to October 16, about?

Mr. LEE. Will you excuse me a moment?

Mr. PECORA. Surely.

Mr. LEE (after conferring with an associate). I assume that the negotiations with Mr. Taplin had approached a point where we were pretty well in agreement, because the board of directors of Pennroad on September 5 authorized the purchase of approximately 220,000 shares of the common stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. at a price not exceeding \$175 per share.

Mr. PECORA. When did you say that was—in September?

Mr. LEE. September 5, 1929.

Mr. PECORA. What was the market price of those shares on that date?

Mr. LEE. That I do not recall.

Mr. PECORA. Was it much less than \$140?

Mr. LEE. I don't recall.

Mr. PECORA. I wish you would look that up.

Mr. LEE. We will.

Mr. PECORA. As a matter of fact, were not the negotiations commenced prior to September 5?

Mr. LEE. Oh, I think so; yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. When did they commence?

Mr. LEE. I think, Mr. Pecora, that they commenced shortly after a transaction we had with Mr. Taplin where we loaned him \$1,950,000 on his note.

Mr. PECORA. What was that loan made to him for?

Mr. LEE. To the best of my knowledge, it was to purchase some more Wheeling & Lake Erie stock. I say "more"——

Mr. PECORA. Wheeling & Lake Erie stock?

Mr. LEE. Yes.

The CHAIRMAN. When was that?

Mr. LEE (after conferring with an associate). About June 20, 1929.

Mr. PECORA. To whom did your company make that loan directly, this loan of \$1,950,000?

Mr. LEE. To Frank E. Taplin.

Mr. PECORA. Did you not make it to Brown Bros. & Co., and did they not, in turn, make it to Frank E. Taplin?

Mr. LEE. No, sir. That loan was made direct to Mr. Taplin. It may have been made through Brown Brothers; I mean, Brown Brothers may have received it for his credit.

Mr. PECORA. Whose note did your company receive for that loan?

Mr. LEE. Mr. Taplin's note.

Mr. PECORA. What part did Brown Bros. Co. have in the loan transaction?

Mr. LEE. I always thought they simply acted as Mr. Taplin's agent.

Mr. PECORA. What actually did they do in connection with that loan transaction? How did they come into it?

Mr. LEE. I think Mr. Taplin had done business with them before, and selected them as the firm through which he could deliver his collateral.

Mr. PECORA. And the purpose for the making of that loan by your company of nearly \$2,000,000 to Mr. Taplin was to enable him to buy some shares of the Wheeling & Lake Erie Railway Co.?

Mr. LEE. I believe that is so; but, of course, I cannot answer for Mr. Taplin.

Mr. PECORA. But was it not also made to him for the purpose of enabling him to acquire 8,500 shares of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co.?

Mr. LEE. Mr. Pecora, I have here a memorandum on my file dated June 20, 1929, in which reference is made to the fact that Mr. Taplin advised that the loan should be for \$1,950,000 because there would be 32,500 shares of Wheeling & Lake Erie Railroad common and

preferred to be purchased. The memorandum also refers to the collateral we were to get, and that included 8,500 shares of Pittsburgh & West Virginia stock.

The CHAIRMAN. What collateral? Name the collateral.

Mr. LEE. Twelve thousand five hundred shares of Wheeling & Lake Erie Railroad common and preferred stocks and 8,500 shares of Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. stock.

Mr. PECORA. When I asked you a few moments ago to give us as closely as you could the date of the actual commencement of the negotiations which your corporation undertook with Mr. Taplin you said that on June 20, 1929, your company made this loan of \$1,950,000 to Mr. Taplin?

Mr. LEE. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Was that date mentioned by you for the purpose of informing us or telling us that that was the date on which the negotiations were commenced with Mr. Taplin to acquire from him and his associates these 220,000 shares of Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway stock?

Mr. LEE. No, Mr. Pecora. I mentioned that as being the first negotiations we had with Frank Taplin, with the thought in my own mind, to the best of my remembrance, following that—maybe not immediately following it, but some some short time after that date during the summer, negotiations took place with him for the acquisition of his stock.

Mr. PECORA. Did your company acquire from Mr. Taplin or anyone else any shares of Wheeling & Lake Erie Railroad stock?

Mr. LEE. In our purchase of the control of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway we also stipulated that 74,000 shares, about, of Wheeling & Lake Erie stock that was in the treasury of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia should be there after we had made our acquisition.

Mr. PECORA. Then you acquired that interest in Wheeling & Lake Erie Railroad through your acquisition of 73 percent of the outstanding stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia; is that right?

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. The Alleghany Corporation had purchased extensively shares of the Wheeling & Lake Erie road, had it not, up to that time?

Mr. LEE. I do not know of my own knowledge, but from public comment, and so forth, yes.

Mr. PECORA. The Wheeling & Lake Erie road is one of the so-called Van Sweringen group of railroads, is it not?

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. And the Alleghany Corporation was a holding company for the Van Sweringen railroad interests, was it not?

Mr. LEE. So I understand.

Mr. PECORA. The Alleghany Corporation came into existence in January 1929, didn't it?

Mr. LEE. I don't remember the date.

Mr. PECORA. It was only a matter of 2 or 3 months prior to the creation of the Pennroad Corporation, was it not?

Mr. LEE. I think that is correct; yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Would you say that the Pennroad Corporation was formed, among other reasons, for the purpose of combating the

Alleghany Corporation because that corporation was a holding company for rival railroad interests, that is, rivals of the Pennsylvania Railroad System?

Mr. LEE. I had never looked on it as being formed just because the Alleghany Corporation had been formed.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Kahn yesterday in his testimony here made some mention of the Alleghany Corporation in connection with the Pennroad Corporation. Did you hear his testimony to that effect?

Mr. LEE. I could not hear it very well.

Mr. PECORA. You did not hear it very well?

Mr. LEE. I am speaking of all his testimony; I could only hear parts of it.

Mr. PECORA. Did you read any part of it either in the record or in the newspapers?

Mr. LEE. Not yet, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Can you now fix even approximately the date of the inception of the negotiations of your company with Mr. Taplin and his associates?

Mr. LEE. No; I cannot, Mr. Pecora. I can only repeat what I said before.

Mr. HEISERMAN. Do you want, now, the whole history of the thing, how the money was paid and everything?

Mr. PECORA. I would like to get the history. I thought that the president of the corporation would be the officer or individual who could best give us that information. If I am mistaken in that I welcome any suggestion as to who is better qualified to give us that history.

Mr. HEISERMAN. He has all the information. I just asked him if he would not tell about the making of the loan and how the money was advanced and how the loan was paid off and the purchase of the stock, and so forth.

Mr. PECORA. Won't you do that, Mr. Lee?

Mr. LEE. Mr. Pecora, please absolve me from any intention of not answering, because I thought I was doing that thing. The loan to Mr. Taplin was made on June 20, 1929, of \$1,950,000. It was paid off October 16, 1929, in connection with the transaction where we purchased our first installment of Pittsburgh & West Virginia stock.

Mr. PECORA. On October 16, 1929, your company made its first payment to Mr. Taplin and his associates in connection with your company's acquisition from them of the 222,000 shares of Pittsburgh & West Virginia?

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. And that first payment was a payment of over \$28,000,000, was it not?

Mr. LEE. \$28,501,600.

Mr. PECORA. Out of that payment Mr. Taplin repaid this loan of \$1,950,000?

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

The CHAIRMAN. And you took over the collateral that he had pledged?

Mr. LEE. We held the collateral that he had pledged, Senator, during the time we held the note, and then we turned it back to him when the note was paid.

The CHAIRMAN. You bought it when you made your first payment?

Mr. LEE. We bought the collateral?

The CHAIRMAN. Yes.

Mr. LEE. No, sir; that collateral simply was assigned to us as collateral for his note when we made the loan to him.

The CHAIRMAN. I understand that, but you subsequently bought additional shares——

Mr. LEE. In the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway?

The CHAIRMAN. Yes.

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

The CHAIRMAN. That was some of the collateral. Eight thousand five hundred shares had been pledged as collateral.

Mr. LEE. Oh, I see what you mean.

The CHAIRMAN. When he paid the note, the collateral was released, and then you bought shares of the railroad company including the same shares that he had put up as collateral?

Mr. LEE. Very likely, sir.

Mr. PECORA. You said that the first agreement with Mr. Taplin and his associates was an oral one?

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. How many shares of stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia did it involve?

Mr. LEE. About 220,000.

Mr. PECORA. Do you mean to say that at the very outset your company concluded to purchase two hundred and twenty-two thousand one hundred and odd shares of Pittsburgh & West Virginia which represented 73 percent of its outstanding stock?

Mr. LEE. Not that exact number, and probably not at the outset; but the culmination of negotiations resulted in our agreeing to purchase 220,000 shares approximately at \$170 a share.

Mr. PECORA. Will you give us the best you can a résumé of the entire negotiations that your company had with Mr. Taplin and his associates which culminated in the purchase of 222,930 shares of Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. stock from them at \$170 a share?

Mr. LEE. I am sorry I cannot, Mr. Pecora, because I did not conduct the negotiations.

Mr. PECORA. Who did?

Mr. LEE. To the best of my knowledge and belief, Mr. A. J. County.

Mr. PECORA. He is one of the directors of your company?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. You as president and director and the executive head of the company gave your approval to it?

Mr. LEE. I was in the negotiations from time to time, and when it had been submitted to and approved by our board as a matter of purchase, of course, then I carried out the transaction.

Mr. HEISERMAN. I don't believe he understands, Mr. Pecora. As I understand it, you want a complete history of the making of the loan and the money that was advanced to Frank Taplin, where it went, how he got it, when it was paid off, when he turned over the Pittsburgh & West Virginia stock, and when he was paid for it?

Mr. PECORA. What I want is just exactly what my question called for—a résumé of the complete history of all of the negotiations, from their inception to their conclusion, that the Pennroad Corporation had with Frank E. Taplin and his associates and which culminated in the purchase from them by the Pennroad Corporation of these two hundred and twenty-two thousand and odd shares of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railroad.

Mr. HEISERMAN. I personally know that it all started with the borrowing of the money and the giving of the note.

Mr. PECORA. Does the president of the company know that too?

Mr. HEISERMAN. I would think so. He has all the material right here to tell the story.

Mr. LEE. I thought I had so answered the question. I suppose I am dumb about it, but I thought I had answered the question by saying that the acquisition of Pittsburgh & West Virginia started after or about the time of this particular negotiation of the loan.

Mr. PECORA. That is what I asked you before. I asked you before if when you mentioned the date of June 20, 1929, which happened to be the date of the making of this loan of \$1,950,000 to Mr. Taplin by your company, you gave us that date for the purpose of stating that that date marked the commencement of the negotiations with Taplin that led to the buying of the two hundred and twenty-two thousand and odd shares, and you said it did not. You said you did not mention that date for that purpose.

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. A moment ago you said that the negotiations commenced with the date of the making of that loan. Which is right?

Mr. LEE. Mr. Pecora, I do not know of my own knowledge whether negotiations started at this time or not. I mentioned the negotiation of the loan for the purpose of establishing some date after which, in all probability, the negotiations for the acquisition of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia stock started, sir. I mentioned that as an approximation of the time after which these negotiations for the purchase of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia were carried through.

Mr. PECORA. What was Mr. Taplin's business in June and July of 1929?

Mr. LEE. As I recall, he was president of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway.

Mr. PECORA. I believe I asked you before who Mr. Taplin's associates were, and you were not able to tell us?

Mr. LEE. No, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Are you now able to tell us?

Mr. LEE. No, sir. The only associate of his that I know of in connection with the Pittsburgh & West Virginia transaction was his brother, C. F. Taplin.

Mr. PECORA. Is he also an officer of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railroad?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir. He is general counsel of it.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know how many associates he had in the deal?

Mr. LEE. I do not.

Mr. PECORA. Did you know at the time that this loan of \$1,950,000 was made by your company to Mr. Taplin that Mr. Taplin and his associates owned anything like 220,000 shares of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co.?

Mr. LEE. Do I know it?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. LEE. Personally I do not, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know that they did not own at that time anything like that amount of stock?

Mr. LEE. I have no opinion about it at all.

Mr. PECORA. Who initiated these negotiations?

Mr. LEE. I said before, Mr. Pecora, that Mr. A. J. County did, probably.

Mr. PECORA. When for the first time was there presented for discussion or consideration to the board of the Pennroad Corporation anything about buying any stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co.?

Mr. LEE. I can only identify one date, and that is the date of September 5, 1929, when the board took action.

Mr. PECORA. That is some two and a half months after the making of this loan to Taplin, is it not?

Mr. LEE. Yes. Of my knowledge I do not know, but I assume that between the date of making this loan and September 5, 1929, negotiations were carried forward which resulted in an offer to purchase the stock from Taplin.

Mr. PECORA. And those negotiations were carried forward orally?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. No letters or correspondence or writings of any kind to evidence the nature of these negotiations?

Mr. LEE. Not to my remembrance. We have got our file here.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know when for the first time the matter of your company buying shares of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Road was first brought up for discussion at your board meetings?

Mr. LEE. No, sir; I don't recall.

Mr. PECORA. Was it some time prior to September 5, 1929?

Mr. LEE. I think it must have been.

Mr. PECORA. Why was not the matter then placed on the record of the board meeting?

Mr. LEE. When I referred to discussions at board meetings I referred to informal discussions where no vote would be taken.

Mr. PECORA. Have you got the minute book here of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. LEE. No, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Will you have it here on Thursday of next week?

Mr. LEE. I will. Excuse me. We brought down a certified copy of the resolution which formally placed this matter on our books.

Mr. PECORA. When was that resolution adopted?

Mr. LEE. September 5, 1929.

Mr. PECORA. Was it Mr. County, one of your directors, who first brought up, even in an informal fashion, at a meeting of your board the question of your company buying extensively into the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway?

Mr. LEE. I am not able to recall whether it was Mr. County or not. I think there was probably an informal talk among the directors.

The CHAIRMAN. Who offered the resolution?

Mr. LEE. We have no record of that.

Mr. PECORA. Is Mr. County a stockholder of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co.?

Mr. LEE. I do not know.

Mr. PECORA. What is Mr. County's address, do you know?

Mr. LEE. Broad Street Station, Suburban Building, Philadelphia.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Chairman, I should like to ask that a subpoena be issued for the attendance of Mr. County before this subcommittee at its next hearing.

The CHAIRMAN. What are his initials?

Mr. PECORA. It is A. J. County, isn't it, Mr. Lee?

Mr. LEE. A. J. County; yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Was Mr. County at that time an officer or director of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. What office did he hold?

Mr. LEE. Financial vice president.

Mr. PECORA. And also director?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Were all the other negotiations that were undertaken and concluded by your company for the purchase of the stock of other railroad companies negotiated in the same informal manner that you have described in connection with these particular negotiations?

Mr. LEE. I would not be able to answer that question without a study of whatever records I may have or trying to refresh my recollection by a study of each particular situation.

Mr. PECORA. Cannot you tell us that generally from your memory, Mr. Lee?

Mr. LEE. I think some of them were informally started, and some were formally started.

Mr. PECORA. Then some were informally started and others were formally started. What was the reason for making formal entries with regard to some of these negotiations and leaving the informal negotiations off the record in part?

Mr. LEE. I wasn't speaking of the negotiations so much as the discussions.

Mr. PECORA. Well, then, what was the reason for making some discussions formal and others informal?

Mr. LEE. Well, I have no reason to offer except that I suppose they just happened that way.

Mr. PECORA. Now, what other loans were made by your company to Taplin or any of his associates?

Mr. LEE. None others that I recall.

Mr. PECORA. Was this loan of \$1,950,000 made to him specifically to enable him to acquire the stock of other railroad companies, which were in turn to be acquired by your company?

Mr. LEE. I do not know of my own knowledge, Mr. Pecora. As I have told you—well, I think I answered that question before by saying I had a memorandum which indicated that when the proceeds of this loan were made available he proposed to buy Wheeling & Lake Erie common and preferred stock. But I do not know it of my own knowledge.

Mr. PECORA. The making of this loan by your company to Mr. Taplin was evidenced by the adoption of a resolution, wasn't it?

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. And had there been discussions of the resolution before the adoption of it?

Mr. LEE. I do not recall that there had been.

Mr. PECORA. What was that answer?

Mr. LEE. I do not recall that there had been.

Mr. PECORA. Was it customary for your board to adopt without previous discussion resolutions authorizing the making of loans of nearly \$2,000,000 to an individual?

Mr. LEE. Well, it is conceivable it would be done if the person who presented the project, the suggestion of the loan, was able to convince the board it was a proper loan to make.

Mr. PECORA. Well, now, do you recall any discussion by which the board was convinced by anyone that this was a proper loan to make?

Mr. LEE. No; I do not remember any discussion.

Senator BARKLEY. Is your company, the Pennroad Corporation, in the money-lending business?

Mr. LEE. We have a charter right to lend money.

Senator BARKLEY. I know, but were you making loans?

Mr. LEE. No, sir.

Senator BARKLEY. Do you remember any other loan of this character?

Mr. LEE. That is the only one I recall.

Senator BARKLEY. That is the only loan you ever made as a company?

Mr. LEE. To an individual.

Mr. PECORA. Did you make any such loan to a corporation or a syndicate?

Mr. LEE. I would have to refresh my memory on that.

Senator BARKLEY. When you made this loan for the purpose of Mr. Taplin buying this stock, was it known that The Pennroad Corporation was going to buy it back from him when he accumulated a certain number of shares?

Mr. LEE. Certainly I didn't know it.

Mr. PECORA. Well, if you didn't know it, and you were the president and a director of the company, who would be expected to know it?

Mr. LEE. I mean by that answer, Mr. Pecora, that when that loan was made personally I had no recollection of anyone having said a word about buying the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway stock.

Mr. PECORA. Have you any recollection of anyone advancing any reasons why it was a good thing for your company to make this loan of \$1,900,000 to Taplin?

Mr. LEE. I have nothing here, but the fact that I do not remember at this time, when this transaction took place 4 years ago, what preceded that loan, is not strange, and I have no record so far as I know.

Senator BARKLEY. The fact that your concern loaned this money to Taplin in order to enable him to buy this stock which your company was to buy back from him when he had accumulated it, didn't you know that?

Mr. LEE. No; I didn't know that.

Senator BARKLEY. Isn't that what happened?

Mr. LEE. I am not sure that it did.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know what happened in connection with that loan?

Mr. LEE. I only have this record here.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recall any statement made by anybody at any meeting of your board in connection with this loan that convinced you or satisfied your mind it was a good thing for your company to make this loan?

Mr. LEE. No; I do not recall it.

The CHAIRMAN. Did you acquire the Wheeling & Lake Erie stock?

Mr. LEE. We did not, Senator Fletcher. But after the acquisition of control of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia, they had some in their treasury.

The CHAIRMAN. How much did they have?

Mr. LEE. Seventy-four thousand shares.

Mr. PECORA. It was understood and agreed at the outset of those negotiations with Taplin and his associates that they would see to it that there was in the treasury or, rather, that there would be in the treasury of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. 74,000 shares of the Wheeling & Lake Erie Railway Co. at the time when your company bought 220,000 shares of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia stock, wasn't it?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Senator BARKLEY. Was that 74,000 shares in the portfolio of the company at the time when this loan was made, or were they purchased afterward and put into their portfolio?

Mr. LEE. At the time when the loan was made or at the time when we purchased the company?

Senator BARKLEY. I am talking about the time when the loan was made.

Mr. LEE. As to that I do not know.

The CHAIRMAN. He had 12,500 shares in his possession then.

Mr. LEE. Well, I don't know whether he did or not.

The CHAIRMAN. Well, that was put up as collateral and he must have had it.

Mr. LEE. Well, probably that wasn't corporation stock; that is, stock owned by the Pittsburgh & West Virginia.

Mr. PECORA. No; that was stock owned by Taplin. He put it up as collateral for the personal note with your company.

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Senator BARKLEY. Did the 74,000 shares appear in the portfolio when you bought the 220,000 shares?

Mr. LEE. When we bought control of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia the 74,000 shares of Wheeling & Lake Erie preferred and common stock was in the Pittsburgh & West Virginia's possession.

Senator BARKLEY. What proportion of the whole was the 74,000 shares?

Mr. LEE. I can not recall at the moment. I have not the papers here.

Senator BARKLEY. Was that a controlling interest?

Mr. LEE. Oh, no.

Mr. PECORA. When was there for the first time any written agreement or writing of any kind between your company and Mr. Taplin and his associates with respect to this transaction?

Mr. LEE. We have no written agreement about it whatever.

Mr. PECORA. And the whole thing was under an oral agreement or understanding?

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. A transaction involving something like \$38,000,000 was undertaken on an oral basis?

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. And that was done, although the fact is that the transaction was one which was spread over a period of several months?

Mr. LEE. Well, we did not pay any money until we got the stock in exchange for it.

Mr. PECORA. Who functioned as counsel or the legal adviser of your company at that time?

Mr. LEE. Judge Heiserman.

Mr. PECORA. Was the opinion of your counsel sought at any time during the pendency of these negotiations with regard to this transaction?

Mr. LEE. Judge Heiserman and I completed the transaction. I mean by that that we made the final agreement that we would buy 220,000 shares.

Mr. PECORA. I did not ask you that. I asked if you sought the advice of counsel for your company during the entire period of the pendency of those negotiations, and your answer is that at the completion of them you sought his assistance, I suppose with regard to the drafting of the papers. What is your answer to my question?

Mr. LEE. I did not consult Judge Heiserman, so far as I remember, during the pendency of these negotiations.

Mr. PECORA. Did you as president of the company delegate that duty or responsibility to any other officer or member of the board?

Mr. LEE. I said before, Mr. Pecora, that these negotiations were conducted, as far as I remember, primarily by Mr. County from the beginning.

Mr. PECORA. Well, when for the first time did your company or board authorize Mr. County to enter into any such negotiations in behalf of your company?

Mr. LEE. I do not recall.

Mr. PECORA. Is there any written record in any minutes of your board meetings that would show that?

Mr. LEE. I do not recall any, but I will have a search made.

Mr. PECORA. Is it a fair statement to make that those negotiations were conducted in a delightfully informal fashion?

Mr. LEE. Well, perhaps without the word "delightfully."

Mr. PECORA. They were not painfully informal, were they?

Mr. LEE. Hardly.

Mr. PECORA. It might have been to the shareholders.

Senator BARKLEY. The pain was suffered after the thing was over.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Lee, before we adjourn I want to ask you about a letter that I understand you wrote as the president of your company to Mr. George W. Bovenizer, of Messrs. Kuhn, Loeb & Co., under date of June 29, 1929. Do you recall that letter?

Mr. LEE. Will you be good enough to let me look at it?

Mr. PECORA. I only have a copy of it. See if it refreshes your recollection.

Mr. LEE (after reading the letter). Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recall that letter?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Is the copy of the letter which I have shown you a true and correct copy thereof, would you say?

Mr. LEE. I am not able to say that, but I recognize the terms of the letter.

Mr. PECORA. Well, now, I will offer this copy in evidence subject to any corrections that you may find it necessary to make, if you find it necessary to make any correction of this copy, at your next appearance before the subcommittee.

Mr. HEISERMAN. That is the letter you inquired of Mr. Kahn concerning?

Mr. PECORA. Yes, sir.

Mr. HEISERMAN. That is, as to some hidden matter?

Mr. PECORA. No, sir. This is an entirely different letter, about some subscriptions to stock.

Mr. HEISERMAN. All right.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted and spread on the record by the committee reporter.

(The letter was marked "Committee Exhibit No. 41, June 30, 1933," and is as follows:)

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 41, JUNE 30, 1933

(Personal.)

PHILADELPHIA, PA., *June 29, 1929.*

Mr. GEORGE W. BOVENIZER,

*c/o Messrs. Kuhn, Loeb & Co., 52 William Street,
New York, N.Y.*

DEAR GEORGE: As you know, we offered to the persons on our special list a little less than 24,000 shares as an allotment on a subscription of 92,788.

The majority on the list from whom we have heard have accepted our allotment. There are probably 10 objectors, 1 of whom threatens suit; 1 or 2 others indicate that they sold the stock in anticipation of receiving it, and, of course, will lose money in fulfilling their contracts. Most of the others who have made any comment at all say the situation has caused them embarrassment, which may mean that they too have sold in anticipation of receipt of their full subscription.

Mr. County has said he has received comments from several people, who are supposed to be friends of ours, on the list, which leads him to believe that if we do not fulfill our original contract with these people we will never hear the last of it. For that reason he is suggesting that we endeavor to ascertain whether there is any way in which we can issue, say, roughly, an additional 100,000 shares to be represented by Voting-Trust Certificates. Under the Charter, if we sell stock for cash, we are obligated to allot it to the stockholders. It appears to both of us, however, that under other conditions, such as the issuance of stock in exchange for property, which I assume could include securities of some other concern, we might be able to issue additional stock without offering it first to the stockholders whose stock is now represented by voting-trust certificates. The question would be whether we can get such additional stock into the Voting-Trust Agreement, and also what other security we might issue it for; for instance, I have in mind the National Freight Company which we have recently formed, where quite possibly we could subscribe for their stock and offer to pay for it in stock represented by Voting-Trust Certificates of The Pennroad Corporation. The Freight Company could authorize us to sell such stock for them to furnish cash, and we could discharge our commitment to the people on this special list in full and your concern would get its full allotment under our commitment with you.

I am having our lawyers give this consideration, with the thought that I will talk to them Monday morning to see if they have found a method of doing it. Will you consider it, and after I have talked with them Monday I will call you, and also probably see you either Monday or Tuesday.

If we find we can do it and you are willing to agree, we may ask you to let us utilize a part of your 250,000 shares to get rid of the situation that exists with these people under obligation to substitute as soon as we get authority. See P.S.

Of course, the question in my mind is whether a thing like this would disturb the market unduly, having in mind that possibly one half of these people may sell their stock, although I doubt if this would be quite true. Further, in view of your letter just received, stating that you will accept delivery of the balance of stock due under your commitment on July 3d, would we be disturbing your plans by asking what in effect would amount to a postponement of the physical fulfillment of our commitment; i.e., the delivery of 250,000 shares to you?

Will you think it over?

Sincerely yours,

H. H. LEE.

P.S.—If our plan should turn out to be agreeable to you, would you be willing to have us divert, say, 100,000 shares from delivery, under our commitment in order to close up the situation with those on our special list, on our undertaking to supply such number of shares to you as soon as we could have Board action and go through the formalities of issuing additional stock, which might be 2 or 3 days?

H. H. LEE.

Mr. PECORA. The letter reads as follows:

(And the letter was read as above spread on the record.)

Now, Mr. Lee, what was that special list referred to in this letter?

Mr. LEE. It was a list of persons to whom I had offered stock in the event that it was not taken by the stockholders in the offer to purchase.

Mr. PECORA. In the original offering of 5,800,000 shares?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. I show you this list and ask you if that is a correct and complete list of such persons and the number of shares respectively allotted to them?

Mr. LEE. If that is the copy that was handed to your people this morning I believe it to be correct.

Mr. PECORA. I offer it in evidence and ask that it may be spread on the record of the committee hearing.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted, and the committee reporter will make it a part of the transcript.

(The list was marked "Committee Exhibit No. 42, June 30, 1933", and is as follows:)

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 42, JUNE 30, 1933

Leslie G. Knapp.....	50	John M. Gross.....	250
Milton D. Reinhold.....	38	Quincy Bent.....	250
Thomas S. Hopkins.....	50	Robert E. McMath.....	250
George H. Stewart, Jr.....	75	H. E. Lewis.....	1, 200
R. R. Steele.....	200	Eugene G. Grace.....	1, 200
Arthur C. Dorrance.....	150	F. A. Schick.....	250
Drexel & Co.....	6, 000	Mary E. Conner.....	50
Frank K. Houston.....	250	Felix P. Eysmans.....	50
Mark Willcox.....	75	L. H. Wheeler.....	50
J. Wm. Hardt.....	50	Thomas J. Purcell.....	50
Philadelphia National Co.....	3, 000	Albert H. Heckel.....	50
Charles Francis Clement.....	400	Oliver P. Merriman.....	50
Douglas R. Warfield.....	50	Patrick J. Hyland.....	50
Frank A. Bedford.....	75	DeWaldt J. Hicks.....	600
Evan Randolph.....	150	George G. Asplund.....	75
John L. Burns.....	100	Roy F. Buchman.....	50
Harry Frank.....	500	Alan M. Scaife.....	500
C. M. Keys.....	250	Edward B. Clarke.....	50
Bernard F. Weadock.....	500	Howard M. Johnson.....	75
John T. Dorrance.....	6, 000	Paul Henderson.....	100
Joseph Wayne, Jr.....	300		
William I. Schaffer.....	250	Total.....	23, 963
C. A. Buck.....	250		

Mr. PECORA. Now, when was this offer made to the persons shown on this list to sell to them stock of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. LEE. I am speaking from memory, but some time soon after our offer of stock was made to the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.

Mr. PECORA. That offer was made to the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. on April 24, 1929, as appears from the record here.

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. How long after that date did you in behalf of your company offer to the persons named on that list their respective allotments, as shown on that list of the stock of your company?

Mr. LEE. Mr. Pecora, will you be good enough to let me bring my record with me on Thursday?

Mr. PECORA. Certainly, if you cannot tell us now from memory.

Mr. LEE. No; I cannot. I think it was some time about the first part of May.

Mr. PECORA. At what price was it offered to the persons shown on that list?

Mr. LEE. At the same price.

Mr. PECORA. That is, at \$15 a share?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. What was the reason for doing that, Mr. Lee?

Mr. LEE. Our reason was that in case there was any stock left that the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. did not subscribe for, that we would have an outlet, so to speak, where we might offer a number of shares, say 100,000 shares, to persons who might be interested in purchasing it who were not already stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.

Mr. PECORA. Hadn't you given to Kuhn, Loeb & Co. such right originally?

Mr. LEE. Yes; as to 250,000 shares.

Mr. PECORA. And you found it necessary to obtain from them about 25,000 shares from their allotment of 250,000 shares in order to enable you to fulfill your offer to the persons shown on that list?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. What was the benefit to your company from that, or what did you conceive would be the benefit accruing to your company from that?

Mr. LEE. Well, that we might sell that much more stock. I mean, if it were not taken by stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., by putting it into the hands of persons not stockholders but who, at least, would be willing to take it.

Mr. PECORA. Well, what led to the selection of these particular persons on this list for that purpose?

Mr. LEE. I wrote a letter to the directors of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. as individuals and asked them if they could suggest the names of persons who were not stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad and who, in the event we had the stock to offer, they thought would take it.

Mr. PECORA. And then these names were suggested to you by the Pennsylvania Railroad?

Mr. LEE. By some of the directors of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.

Mr. PECORA. It was not intended to establish good will with those persons named on that list for some reason or other, was it, or was it so intended?

Mr. LEE. I think so.

Mr. PECORA. It was done for that purpose?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

The CHAIRMAN. Speaking about some threatened suits, what were the suits you apprehended might give you trouble?

Mr. LEE. I did not hear that, Senator Fletcher.

The CHAIRMAN. You spoke in this letter about some threatened suits. What suits were about to give you trouble?

Mr. LEE. From some of these persons to whom I had made the offer of stock contingent on its not being taken by the stockholders of the railroad company. And some of them were kind enough to come back and say if I could not fulfill my promise to deliver to them the shares they had subscribed for they might sue us. That was all.

Mr. PECORA. Had you made a formal commitment in behalf of your company to these persons before you knew whether or not you would have the stock available?

Mr. LEE. Well, I would not call it a formal commitment. But I had agreed if they would subscribe I would accept their subscriptions.

Mr. PECORA. Was it such a commitment that you feared you might be brought into the courts for enforcement against you?

Mr. LEE. It might amount to that, I think.

Mr. PECORA. Why did you commit your corporation to these persons before you knew whether or not you could fulfill your obligation?

Mr. LEE. To the best of my remembrance our issue of stock and its offer of sale to the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad was not proceeding at that time with very great celerity. We were pretty sure, at that time, I mean, according to our best estimates, that we would not probably exceed the amount of subscription, 85 percent, that we, if you will recall, had agreed with Kuhn, Loeb & Co. about, that if we got 85 percent of the subscription from the Pennsylvania Railroad stockholders they would take 250,000 shares; and we were not sure that we would get the 85 percent.

Mr. PECORA. The offer to the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. at \$15 went out on the date of April 24, 1929, it was testified here to us by Mr. Kahn, and that the stock was traded in on the public market the following day, April 25, 1929, on a when-issued basis around 25.

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir; I recall hearing him say that.

Mr. PECORA. Did you know what the opening trades were in your stock, and I mean the stock of your company, on April 25, 1929?

Mr. LEE. Only when we saw them in the papers.

Mr. PECORA. Of course.

The CHAIRMAN. Some of the people to whom you had offered the stock were then anxious to get it, and you did not have the stock; is that the idea?

Mr. LEE. Yes. Are you speaking of this special list?

The CHAIRMAN. Yes.

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

The CHAIRMAN. That was why they threatened suit, because the price had gone up?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And some of them even informed you that they had already sold the stock since it was offered to them by you and before they had received it from you?

Mr. LEE. On a when-issued basis; yes.

Mr. PECORA. And probably had sold it at the price of 25 or more?

Mr. LEE. Well, I have no way of telling about that.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know who made the market on April 25, 1929, for the stock?

Mr. LEE. I have no idea in the world, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Did this opening price at 25 surprise you?

Mr. LEE. Very much.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know how those prices were reached?

Mr. LEE. I have no idea.

Mr. PECORA. You could not give this committee any enlightenment at all about that?

Mr. LEE. None at all, sir. I don't know.

Mr. PECORA. You haven't even any suspicions about it?

Mr. LEE. I have none at all.

The CHAIRMAN. Did you actually have any suits brought against you?

Mr. LEE. No, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Chairman, would it be convenient to you for the subcommittee to stand in recess until Thursday of next week?

The CHAIRMAN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And will it be understood that Mr. Lee will be on hand then for further interrogation?

Mr. LEE. Do you want us here at 10 o'clock?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. LEE. Oh. I was going to ask you a question about the time, but that was when I understood you would probably adjourn until Wednesday, but you are now adjourning until Thursday of next week.

The CHAIRMAN. Yes. You will be here at 10 o'clock on Thursday of next week. The subcommittee will now stand adjourned until 10 a.m. on Thursday, July 6, 1933.

(Whereupon, at 5:30 p.m., Friday, June 30, 1933, the subcommittee adjourned to meet at 10 a.m. on the following Thursday, July 6, 1933.)

COMMITTEE EXHIBITS

Committee exhibits nos. 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, and 40 are here printed in full in the record, as follows:

EXHIBIT No. 30

[Excerpt from letter of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. to Ferdinand Pecora, May 25, 1933]

We find that in the following issues we acted as joint syndicate managers, although the accounts and actual administration of the syndicates were handled by the managers stated in our reply to this question and this accounts for our error in having originally omitted to state that we were such cosyndicate managers. The issues in question are as follows:

On page 1: \$20,640,000 principal amount city of Tokyo external loan of 1927 sinking fund 5½ percent gold bonds, due October 1, 1961; \$20,000,000 par value United Cigar Stores Co. 6 percent cumulative preferred stock.

On page 3: \$10,000,000 principal amount Cigar Stores Realty Holdings, Inc., 20-year 5½ percent sinking fund gold debentures, series A, due January 1, 1949; \$32,000,000 principal amount Railway Express Agency, Inc., 5 percent serial gold bonds, series A, due serially until March 1, 1949.

On page 5: \$22,800,000 principal amount Taiwan Electric Power Co., Ltd., 40-year sinking fund 5½ percent gold bonds, due July 1, 1971.

The fact that we were cosyndicate managers of the Cigar Stores Realty Holdings, Inc., issue referred to above would require that we transfer this issue from the list submitted to you in answer to your question no. 15 to the list submitted in reply to your question no. 12.

Question 9A. List of all stock and bond participations of not less than \$250,000

Name	Date	Amount	Description of issue	Public offering price	Syndicate managers	Amount of our participation	Gross amount of commission	Net profit received	
Government of the Argentine Nation.	Jan. 13, 1927	\$27,000,000	External sinking fund 6-percent gold bonds, issue of Feb. 1, 1927; due Feb. 1, 1961.	Percent 98 $\frac{3}{4}$	J. P. Morgan & Co.....	Distributing syndicate, \$400,000.....	Percent 1	\$3,316.00	
					National City Co.....	Public offering, \$200,000.....	1	2,000.00	
California Petroleum Corporation.	Jan. 19, 1927	8,000,000	12-year convertible 5-percent sinking-fund gold debentures, due Nov. 1, 1938.	96 $\frac{1}{2}$	Blair & Co., Inc.....	Original account, \$1,000,000.....	13 $\frac{1}{4}$	11,250.00	
Consolidated Gas Co. of New York.do.....	1 1,200,000	\$5 cumulative preferred stock.	91	National City Co.....	Hallgarten & Co.....	Special group, \$731,250.....	3 $\frac{1}{4}$	3,656.25
						Banking group, 30,000 shares. Underwriting syndicate, 20,000 shares.	2 $\frac{1}{2}$	15,000.00	
Hocking Valley Ry. Co.....	Feb. 28, 1927	5,000,000	6-month 4 $\frac{1}{2}$ -percent secured gold notes, due Sept. 1, 1927.	99 $\frac{7}{8}$	J. P. Morgan & Co.....	Original account, \$875,000.....	1 $\frac{5}{8}$	38,983.26	
City of Tokyo.....	Mar. 19, 1927	20,640,000	External loan of 1927, sinking fund 5 $\frac{1}{2}$ -percent gold bonds, due Oct. 1, 1961.	89 $\frac{1}{2}$	J. P. Morgan & Co. and associates.	Original account, \$4,910,000.....	1	40,507.50	
						Offering group, \$3,975,000.....	1 $\frac{1}{2}$	19,875.00	
City of Rome.....	Mar. 28, 1927	30,000,000	External loan of 1927 sinking fund 6 $\frac{1}{2}$ -percent gold bonds, due Apr. 1, 1952.	91	J. P. Morgan & Co.....	Distributing syndicate, \$409,000.....	1	3,288.36	
						Public offering, \$250,000.....	1	2,470.00	
						Offering group, \$600,000.....	1	5,000.00	
Kingdom of the Serbs, Croats and Slovenes.	Apr. 4, 1927	30,000,000	7-percent secured external gold bonds, series B, due 1962.	92 $\frac{1}{2}$	Blair & Co., Inc.....	Distributing syndicate, \$200,000.....	1	1,600.00	
						Public offering, \$150,000.....	1	1,500.00	
Federal Land Bank.....	Apr. 2, 1927	100,000,000	4 $\frac{1}{4}$ -percent, due May 1, 1957.	101 $\frac{1}{4}$	Chase Securities Corporation and associates.	Original account, \$3,000,000.....	3 $\frac{1}{4}$	14,400.26	
						Special group, \$1,630,000.....	1	12,169.16	
Shell Union Oil Corporation...	Apr. 15, 1927	50,000,000	20-year 5-percent sinking-fund gold debentures, due May 1, 1947.	99 $\frac{1}{2}$	Alex. Brown & Sons and associates.	Bankers group, \$589,100.....	1	2,969.60	
						Public offering, \$265,000.....	3 $\frac{1}{4}$	1,891.15	
United Cigar Stores Co.....do.....	2 20,000,000	6-percent cumulative preferred stock.	109	Lee, Higginson & Co.....	Original account, \$11,500,000.....	1	109,064.48	
						Banking group, \$5,787,500.....	1 $\frac{1}{2}$	28,937.50	
						Selling group, \$250,000.....	1 $\frac{1}{2}$	3,125.00	
						Purchase group.....	40	17,369.21	
Argentine Government.....	Apr. 27, 1927	21,200,000	Loan of 1927 external sinking fund 6-percent gold bonds of May 1, 1927, due May 1, 1961.	90	J. P. Morgan & Co., National City Co.	Original account.....	40	82,635.20	
						Banking group, \$2,020,000 par value.	-----	18,150.37	
						Selling group, \$260,000 par value.	13 $\frac{1}{4}$	4,375.00	
						Syndicate, \$300,000.....	1	\$2,214.00	

¹ Shares.

¹ Par value.

Question 9A. List of all stock and bond participations of not less than \$250,000—Continued

Name	Date	Amount	Description of issue	Public offering price	Syndicate managers	Amount of our participation	Gross amount of commission	Net profit received
Erie Railroad Co.....	May 7, 1927	\$50,000,000	Refunding and improvement mortgage 5-percent gold bonds of 1927, due May 1, 1967.	Percent 94½	J. P. Morgan & Co.....	Syndicate, \$250,000.....	Percent 1	\$2,117.50
The Chesapeake Corporation.	May 10, 1927	48,000,000	20-year 5-percent convertible collateral trust bonds due May 15, 1947.	94	J. P. Morgan & Co..... Guaranty Co. of New York.....	Offering group \$2,000,000.... Distributing syndicate, \$250,000.	½ 1	10,000.00 2,095.00
United Electric Service Co..	May 13, 1927	6,000,000	External first-mortgage sinking fund gold bonds series A, 7 percent, due 1956.	92½	J. A. Sisto & Co.....	Buying group.....		4,738.95
Republic of Cuba.....	June 30, 1927	9,000,000	Serial 5½-percent gold bonds, due July 1, 1928, to July 1, 1937.	101.122	J. P. Morgan & Co.....	Original account \$1,800,000..	1.122	2,940.00
United Steel Works Corporation.	July 27, 1927	30,000,000	20-year 6½-percent sinking fund debentures series A, due July 1, 1947.	98½	International Acceptance Bank, Inc.	Purchase group, \$250,000.....		2,990.50
Boston & Maine R.R. Co....	Aug. 27, 1927	30,942,000	First-mortgage gold bonds, series A.C., 5 percent, due Sept. 1, 1967.	93¼	Kidder, Peabody & Co. and associates.	Original account \$2,867,000.... Syndicate, \$1,275,000.....	1 1	28,670.00 11,232.50 224.65
Tide Water Associated Transport Corporation.	Sept. 15, 1927	1,800,000	First-lien 10-year marine equipment 5-percent sinking fund gold bonds.	98¼	Blair & Co., Inc., Chase Securities Corporation.	Original account \$375,000....	15%	5,854.87
Do.....	Oct. 11, 1927	1,300,000	First-lien 10-year marine equipment 5-percent sinking fund gold bonds, due Sept. 15, 1937.	98	do.....	Original account \$270,833.... Bankers group \$145,000.....	½ ½	1,354.16 639.11
Republic of Poland.....	Oct. 14, 1927	62,000,000 £2,000,000	Stabilization loan 1927 7-percent external sinking fund gold bonds due Oct. 15, 1947.	92	Bankers Trust Co. and associates.	Original account 20 percent, Banking group \$1,995,000..	2 1	166,842.41 14,498.68
Edison Electric Illuminating Co. of Boston.	Oct. 18, 1927	30,000,000	3-year 4½-percent gold notes, due Nov. 1, 1930.	100	Lee, Higginson & Co. and associates.	Selling group, \$500,000.....	½	2,500.00
Shell Pipe Line Corporation..	Oct. 26, 1927	30,000,000	25-year 5-percent sinking fund gold debentures, due Nov. 1, 1952.	98	Lee, Higginson & Co.....	Original account \$6,900,000.... Banking group, \$2,325,000.... Syndicate, \$250,000..... Selling group \$250,000.....	½ ½ ¾ ¼	34,500.00 11,625.00 1,678.03 625.00
Paramount Famous Lasky Corporation.	Nov. 14, 1927	198,263	Common stock.....	98½	Hallgarten & Co.....	Original account.....	1¼	122,828.75
Republic of Chile Ry.....	Jan. 23, 1928	45,912,000	Refunding sinking fund 6-percent gold external bonds due Jan. 1, 1961.	93½	E. F. Hutton & Co..... National City Co.....	Syndicate account \$10,689,000. Distributing group \$1,000,000.	2½ 1	28,272.40 7,931.97

Brooklyn-Manhattan Trans- it Corporation	Aug. 15, 1928	10,000,000	1-year 6-percent secured gold notes, due Aug. 15, 1929.	100	Chase Securities Corpora- tion and associates.	Original account, \$4,848,300.....	$\frac{3}{4}$	7,784.87
Republic of Chile.....	Aug. 31, 1928	16,000,000	External loan sinking-fund 6 percent gold bonds, due Sept. 1, 1961.	94	National City Co.....	Selling group, \$1,212,000..... Original account \$1,600,000..... Distributing group \$884,500.....	1 1 1	10,605.00 14,000.00 5,796.35
Abraham & Straus.....	Oct. 1, 1928	5,150,000	15-year 5½ percent gold de- bentures, due Oct. 1, 1943.	101	Lehman Bros.....	Original account, 25 percent.....		22,498.41
The Oriental Development Co., Ltd.	Oct. 30, 1928	19,900,000	External loan 30-year 5½ percent gold debentures, due Nov. 1, 1968.	90	National City Co.....	Original account \$3,980,000..... Distributing group \$1,000,000..... Selling group, \$100,000.....	$\frac{3}{4}$ $\frac{1}{4}$ $2\frac{1}{4}$	22,387.50 5,025.83 2,125.00
Republic of Estonia.....	June 16, 1927	4,000,000	Banking currency reform 7 percent loan of 1927, due July 1, 1967.	94½	Hallgarten & Co.....	Original account \$2,000,000.....		30,474.62
Nathan Straus, Inc.....	Nov. 7, 1928	1,000,000	10-year sinking fund 6 per- cent convertible bonds, due 1938 and stock options.	99½	J. A. Sisto & Co.....	Original account 10 percent.....		125,939.50
Cigar Stores Realty Holdings, Inc.	Jan. 2, 1929	10,000,000	20-year 5½ percent sinking- fund gold debentures, series A, due Jan. 1, 1949.	99¾	Guaranty Co. of New York..	Original account \$3,500,000..... Banking group \$1,074,500.....	1 $\frac{3}{4}$	33,081.30 5,372.50
The Chesapeake & Ohio Ry. Co.	Jan. 26, 1929	24,784,000	Refunding and improvement mortgage 4½ percent gold bonds, series A, due Oct. 1, 1993.	95	J. P. Morgan & Co.....	Original account \$4,337,200.....	1	34,697.60
Railway Express Agency, Inc.	Jan. 28, 1929	32,000,000	5 percent serial gold bonds, series A, due serially until Mar. 1, 1949.	100	do.....	Original account \$12,000,000..... Selling group \$2,184,000.....	1 $1\frac{1}{4}$	121,560.00 24,750.00
Alleghany Corporation.....	Jan. 30, 1929	35,000,000	15-year collateral trust con- vertible 5 percent bonds, due Feb. 1, 1944.	100	do.....	Selling group \$3,160,000..... Syndicate \$250,000..... Selling group \$250,000.....	$1\frac{1}{4}$ $\frac{3}{4}$ $\frac{3}{4}$	35,550.00 3,325.00
Republic of Chile.....	Mar. 11, 1929	10,000,000	External loan sinking fund 6 percent gold bonds, due Mar. 1, 1962.	93½	National City Co.....	Original account \$1,000,000..... Distributing group \$250,000.....	1 1	8,750.00 1,653.60
Shell Union Oil Corporation.	Sept. 13, 1929	50,000,000	5 percent sinking-fund gold debentures (with war- rants), due Oct. 1, 1949.	100	Lee Higginson & Co.....	Original account \$11,500,000..... Banking group \$4,966,250.....	$\frac{3}{4}$ 1	86,250.00 48,118.81
Hotel Waldorf-Astoria Cor- poration.	Aug. 29, 1929	11,000,000	First mortgage leasehold 7 percent sinking-fund gold bonds (with warrants), due Sept. 1, 1954.	103	Hallgarten & Co..... Hayden, Stone & Co.....	Selling group \$1,000,000..... Purchase account \$625,000..... Carrying account \$107,000..... bonds.	$1\frac{3}{4}$ 2	7,250.00
Southern Bell Telephone & Telegraph Co.	Oct. 17, 1929	32,000,000	First mortgage sinking-fund gold bonds, due Jan. 1, 1941.	100	Kissel, Kinnicutt Co.....			433,536.90
American Telephone & Tele- graph Co.	Jan. 11, 1930	150,000,000	35-year 5 percent gold de- bentures, due Feb. 1, 1965.	99½	J. P. Morgan & Co.....	Original account \$3,440,000..... Banking group \$911,000.....	1 $1\frac{3}{4}$	6,366.15 29,670.00 14,266.26
						Original account, \$16,125,000..... Distributing syndicate, \$4,145,000..... Selling group, \$4,000,000.....	1 $\frac{3}{4}$ $1\frac{1}{4}$	137,062.50 78,351.80

¹ Plus 1,100 shares common.

² And 100 stock warrants.

³ Loss.

⁴ Bonds, loss.

Question 9A. List of all stock and bond participations of not less than \$250,000—Continued

Name	Date	Amount	Description of issue	Public offering price	Syndicate managers	Amount of our participation	Gross amount of commission	Net profit received
The Chesapeake & Ohio Ry. Co.	Jan. 14, 1930	\$35,088,000	Refunding and improvement mortgage 4½ percent gold bonds, series B due Jan. 1, 1935.	Percent 94	J. P. Morgan & Co.-----	Original account, \$6,140,400 Distributing syndicate, \$250,000.	Percent 1 ½	\$49,123.20 5,900.00
Republic Steel Corporation..	Jan. 27, 1930	1,558,311	New 6 percent preferred stock, underwriting syndicate.	95	Otis & Co.-----	Selling group, \$500,000 Underwriting group, 12 percent.	1	130,615.17
The Pure Oil Co.-----	Mar. 17, 1930	20,000,000	10-year 5½ percent sinking-fund gold notes, due Mar. 1, 1940.	97½	Guaranty Co. of New York.	Banking group, \$335,400 Selling group, \$475,000	-----	2,934.75 9,500.00
Boston & Maine R.R. Co.---	Mar. 21, 1930	15,000,000	First mortgage gold bonds, series II, 5 percent, due May 1, 1955.	100½	Kidder, Peabody & Co.---	Banking group, \$250,000	1	1,930.31
Pennsylvania Tank Line.---	Mar. 25, 1930	900,000	5 percent equipment trust certificates, series BB, basis due Oct. 1, 1930, to 1940.	5-5.35	Freeman & Co.-----	Original account	1	9,000.00
B. F. Goodrich & Co.-----	Apr. 21, 1930	30,000,000	15-year 6 percent convertible gold debentures due underwriting syndicate.	98	Otis & Co. and associates---	Syndicate account, \$1,000,000 Took down \$732,000 bonds	-----	16,470.00 8,750.00
Republic of Chile.-----	Apr. 23, 1930	25,000,000	External loan sinking fund 6-percent gold bonds, due May 1, 1933.	91½	National City Co.-----	Original account, \$2,500,000 Special buying account, \$1,500,000.	1 1	21,875.00 750.00
Van Sweringen Corporation..	-----do-----	30,000,000	5-year 6 percent gold notes (with warrants), due May 1, 1935.	100	Guaranty Co. of New York.	Banking group, \$250,000 Selling group, \$250,000	1 1½	1,562.50 3,437.50
Imperial Japanese Government.	May 9, 1930	71,000,000	External loan of 1930; 35-year sinking fund, 5½ percent gold bonds, due May 1, 1965.	90	J. P. Morgan & Co. and associates.	Original account, \$17,000,000 Intermediate group, \$5,044,000.	1 ½	197,056.34 25,220.00
German Government.-----	June 11, 1930	98,250,000	International 5½ percent loan, 1930, 35-year gold bonds.	90	J. P. Morgan & Co.-----	Syndicate account, \$1,196,000 Selling group, \$1,000,000	1 1½	23,671.00
Austrian Government.-----	July 14, 1930	25,000,000	International loan, 1930, sinking fund 7 percent gold bonds, American tranche.	95	-----do-----	Original account, \$9,333,750 Group account, \$2,500,000 Syndicate account, \$1,500,000 Selling group, \$1,500,000	1 1½ 1¼ 1¼	74,670.00 12,500.00 31,612.50
						Original account, \$2,375,000 Purchasing syndicate, \$1,000,000.	1 1	19,000.00 7,900.00

The Cincinnati Union Terminal Co.	Sept. 24, 1930	12,000,000	First mortgage 4½-percent gold bonds, series A, due July 1, 2020.	102¼	do.	Original account, \$4,000,000.	1	42,250.00
					Kuhn, Loeb & Co.	Selling group, \$2,500,000.	1¼	26,750.00
Texas & Pacific Ry. Co.	Jan. 8, 1931	13,000,000	General and refunding mortgage 5-percent gold bonds, series D, due Dec. 1, 1980.	98½	J. P. Morgan & Co.	Original account, \$2,730,000.	½	10,237.50
						Selling group, \$1,500,000.	¾	14,625.00
Missouri Pacific R.R. Co.	Jan. 26, 1931	61,200,000	First and refunding mortgage 5-percent gold bonds, series I, due Feb. 1, 1981.	95	do.	Bond selling group \$600,000.	1¼	6,240.00
						Original account, \$12,582,000.	½	48,195.00
						Purchasing group, \$9,180,000.	½	45,900.00
						Syndicate, \$1,000,000.	½	12,700.00
						Selling group, \$1,000,000.	1	12,608.81
Boston & Maine R.R. Co.	Mar. 11, 1931	13,943,000	First mortgage gold bonds, series JJ, 4¾-percent, due Apr. 1, 1961.	99¼	Lee, Higginson & Co.	Original account, \$1,220,000.	1	
Taiwan Electric Power Co., Ltd.	June 25, 1931	22,800,000	40-year sinking fund 5½-percent gold bonds, due July 1, 1971.	93½	J. P. Morgan & Co. and associates.	Original account, \$5,200,000.	1	42,900.00
						Intermediate group, \$3,800,000	½	17,499.00
						Syndicate, \$955,000.	1	12,162.50
						Selling group, \$500,000.	1	42,500.00
The Cincinnati Union Terminal Co.	Nov. 18, 1931	12,000,000	First mortgage 5-percent gold bonds, series B, due July 1, 2020.	97½	J. P. Morgan & Co.	Original account, \$4,000,000.	1	42,500.00
					Kuhn, Loeb & Co.	Selling group, \$1,210,000.	1½	15,367.00

¹ Shares.² Applied against cost of bonds.

Recapitulation of all stocks and bond issues of over \$250,000 in which other companies acted as managers, 1927-31

BY YEARS

Classification and year	Number of issues	Amount of issue	Amount of participation			Net profit			Total net profit
			Original group	Intermediate group	Selling group	Original group	Intermediate group	Selling group	
1927									
Foreign bonds	10	\$239,840,000	\$24,110,000	\$10,248,100	\$600,000	\$194,215.55	\$70,660.15	\$5,970.00	\$270,845.70
Do		(£2,000,000)	(£400,000)						
Domestic bonds	8	269,100,000	20,045,833	11,488,750	1,265,000	162,023.51	59,226.52	8,141.15	229,391.18
Railroad bonds	3	85,942,000	3,742,000	1,525,000		29,577.81	13,574.65		43,152.46
Domestic stocks	21	594,882,000	47,897,833	23,261,850	1,865,000	385,816.87	143,461.32	14,111.15	543,389.34
		(£2,000,000)	(£400,000)						
	2	\$1,400,000	\$100,000	\$50,200	\$2,500	138,987.67	33,150.37	4,375.00	176,513.04
1928									
Foreign bonds	3	81,812,000	5,598,000	2,884,500	100,000	36,387.50	18,754.15	2,125.00	57,266.65
Domestic bonds	2	6,150,000	1,387,500			48,437.91			\$48,437.91
Railroad bonds	1	10,000,000	4,848,300		1,212,000	7,784.87		10,605.00	18,389.87
	6	97,962,000	11,815,800	2,884,500	1,312,000	92,610.28	18,754.15	12,730.00	124,094.43
1929									
Foreign bonds	1	10,000,000	1,000,000	250,000		8,750.00	1,653.60		10,403.60
Domestic bonds	5	138,000,000	18,440,000	7,933,750	1,250,000	155,367.45	35,883.17	8,912.50	200,163.12
Railroads	2	56,784,000	16,337,200		5,334,000	156,257.60		60,300.00	216,557.60
	8	204,784,000	35,777,200	8,183,750	6,584,000	320,375.05	37,536.77	69,212.50	427,124.32
1930									
Foreign bonds	4	219,250,000	31,208,750	10,044,000	5,296,000	312,601.34	46,370.00	55,283.50	414,254.84
Domestic bonds	4	230,000,000	16,125,000	5,645,000	4,982,000	137,062.50	49,682.46	60,819.65	247,564.61
Railroad bonds	4	62,988,000	12,352,500	250,000	3,786,000	113,187.27	1,180.00	42,277.50	156,644.77
	12	512,238,000	59,686,250	15,939,000	14,064,000	562,851.11	97,232.46	158,380.65	818,464.22
Domestic stocks	1	\$558,311	\$70,000	335,400	475,000	130,615.17	2,934.75	9,500.00	143,049.92
1931									
Foreign bonds	1	22,800,000	5,200,000	3,800,000	1,455,000	42,900.00	17,499.00	12,162.50	72,561.50
Railroad bonds	4	100,143,000	20,532,000	10,180,000	4,310,000	113,541.31	52,250.00	42,582.00	208,373.31
	5	122,943,000	25,732,000	13,980,000	5,765,000	156,441.31	69,749.00	54,744.50	280,934.81

SUMMARY—BONDS

1927-----	21	\$594,882,000 £2,000,000	\$47,897,833 £400,000	\$23,261,850	\$1,865,000	\$385,816.87	\$143,461.32	\$14,111.15	\$543,389.34
1928-----	6	\$97,962,000	\$11,815,800	2,884,500	1,312,000	92,610.28	18,754.15	12,730.00	124,094.43
1929-----	8	204,784,000	35,777,200	8,183,750	6,584,000	320,375.05	37,536.77	69,212.50	427,124.32
1930-----	12	502,238,000	59,689,250	15,939,000	14,064,000	562,851.11	97,232.46	158,380.65	818,464.22
1931-----	5	122,943,000	25,732,000	13,980,000	5,765,000	156,441.31	69,749.00	54,744.50	280,934.81
	52	1,534,809,000 £2,000,000	180,909,083 £400,000	64,249,100	29,590,000	1,518,094.62	366,733.70	309,178.80	2,194,007.12

SUMMARY—STOCKS

1927-----	2	\$1,400,000	\$100,000	\$50,200	\$2,500	\$138,987.67	\$33,150.37	\$4,375.00	\$176,513.04
1930-----	1	\$558,311	\$70,000	335,400	475,000	130,615.17	2,934.75	9,500.00	143,049.92
	3	\$1,958,311	\$170,000	385,600	477,500	269,602.84	36,085.12	13,875.00	319,562.96

BY CLASS

Foreign bonds, 1927-----	10	\$239,840,000 (£2,000,000)	\$24,110,000 (£400,000)	\$10,248,100	\$600,000	\$194,215.55	\$70,660.15	\$5,970.00	\$270,845.70
1928-----	3	81,812,000	5,580,000	2,884,500	100,000	36,387.50	18,754.15	2,125.00	57,286.65
1929-----	1	10,000,000	1,000,000	250,000		8,750.00	1,653.60		10,403.60
1930-----	4	219,250,000	31,208,750	10,044,000	5,296,000	312,601.34	46,370.00	55,283.50	414,254.84
1931-----	1	22,800,000	5,200,000	3,800,000	1,455,000	42,900.00	17,499.00	12,162.50	72,561.50
Total-----	19	573,702,000 (£2,000,000)	57,098,750 (£400,000)	27,226,600	7,451,000	594,854.39	154,936.90	75,541.00	825,332.29
Domestic bonds, 1927-----	8	269,100,000	20,045,833	11,488,750	1,265,000	162,023.51	59,226.52	8,141.15	229,391.18
1928-----	2	6,150,000	1,387,500			48,437.91			\$ 48,437.91
1929-----	5	138,000,000	18,440,000	7,933,750	1,250,000	155,387.45	35,883.17	8,912.50	200,163.12
1930-----	4	230,000,000	16,125,000	5,645,000	4,982,000	137,062.50	49,682.46	60,819.65	247,564.61
Total-----	19	643,250,000	55,998,333	25,067,500	7,497,000	502,891.37	144,792.15	77,873.30	725,556.82
Railroad bonds, 1927-----	3	85,942,000	3,742,000	1,525,000		29,577.81	13,574.65		43,152.46
1928-----	1	10,000,000	4,848,300		1,212,000	7,784.87		10,605.00	18,389.87
1929-----	2	56,784,000	16,337,200		5,334,000	156,257.60		60,300.00	216,557.60
1930-----	4	62,988,000	12,352,500	250,000	3,786,000	\$ 113,187.27	1,180.00	42,277.50	\$ 156,644.77
1931-----	4	100,143,000	20,532,000	10,180,000	4,310,000	113,541.31	52,250.00	42,582.00	208,373.31
Total-----	14	315,857,000	57,812,000	11,955,000	14,642,000	420,348.86	67,004.65	155,764.50	643,118.01
Domestic stock, 1927-----	2	\$1,400,000	\$100,000	\$50,200	\$2,500	\$138,987.67	\$33,150.37	\$4,375.00	\$176,513.04
1930-----	1	\$558,311	\$70,000	335,400	475,000	130,615.17	2,934.75	9,500.00	143,049.92
Total-----	3	\$1,958,311	\$170,000	385,600	477,500	269,602.84	36,085.12	13,875.00	319,562.96

¹ Plus 100 stock warrants.

² Shares.

³ And 1,100 common stock.

Recapitulation of all stocks and bond issues of over \$250,000 in which other companies acted as managers, 1927-31—Continued

SUMMARY—BONDS

Classification and year	Number of issues	Amount of issue	Amount of participation			Net profit			Total net profit
			Original group	Intermediate group	Selling group	Original group	Intermediate group	Selling group	
Foreign bonds, 1927-31.....	19	\$573,702,000 (£2,000,000)	\$57,098,750 (£400,000)	\$27,226,600	\$7,451,000	\$594,854.39	\$154,936.90	\$75,541.00	\$825,332.29
Domestic bonds, 1927-31.....	19	643,250,000	55,998,333	25,067,500	7,497,000	502,891.37	144,792.15	77,873.30	725,556.82
Railroad bonds, 1927-31.....	14	315,857,000	57,812,000	11,955,000	14,642,000	420,348.86	67,004.65	155,764.50	643,118.01
Total bonds.....	52	1,532,809,000 (£2,000,000)	170,909,083 £400,000	64,249,100	29,590,000	1,518,094.62	366,733.70	309,178.80	2,194,007.12

SUMMARY—STOCKS

Domestic stocks, 1927-31.....	3	¹ \$1,958,311	¹ 170,000	\$385,600	\$477,500	\$269,602.84	\$36,085.12	\$13,875.00	\$319,562.96
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¹ Shares.

EXHIBIT NO. 31

Participations of over \$250,000 in which other companies acted as managers

FOREIGN BONDS

No.	Date of participation	Name of issue	Description	Due date	Amount of issue	Syndicate managers	Amount of participation			Net profit			Total profit	
							Original group	Intermediate group	Selling group	Original group	Intermediate group	Selling group		
1	1927 Jan. 13	Government of the Argentine Nation.	External sinking-fund 6 percent gold bond issue of Feb. 1, 1927.	Feb. 1, 1961	\$27,000,000	J. P. Morgan & Co., National City Co.	-----	\$400,000	\$200,000	-----	\$3,316.00	\$2,000.00	\$5,316.00	
2	Mar. 19	City of Tokyo	External loan of 1927 sinking-fund, 5½ percent gold bonds.	Oct. 1, 1961	20,640,000	J. P. Morgan and associates.	\$4,910,000	4,384,000	250,000	\$40,507.50	23,163.36	2,470.00	66,140.86	
3	Mar. 28	City of Rome	External loan of 1927 sinking-fund 6½ percent gold bonds.	Apr. 1, 1952	30,000,000	J. P. Morgan & Co., National City Co.	-----	700,000	150,000	-----	6,600.00	1,500.00	8,100.00	
4	Apr. 4	Kingdom of the Serbs, Croats and Slovenes.	7 percent secured external gold bonds, series B.	Nov. 1, 1962	30,000,000	Blair & Co., Inc., Chase Securities Corporation and associates.	3,000,000	2,219,100	-----	14,400.26	15,138.66	-----	29,538.92	
5	Apr. 27	Argentine Government.	1927 external sinking-fund 6 percent gold bonds May 1, 1927.	May 1, 1961	21,200,000	J. P. Morgan & Co., National City Co.	-----	300,000	-----	-----	2,214.00	-----	2,214.00	
6	June 30	Republic of Cuba.	Serial 5½ percent gold bonds.	July 1, 1928 to July 1, 1937.	9,000,000	J. P. Morgan & Co.	1,800,000	-----	-----	2,940.00	-----	-----	2,940.00	
7	Oct. 14	Republic of Poland.	Stabilization loan 1927 7 percent external sinking-fund gold bonds.	Oct. 15, 1947	62,000,000 £2,000,000	Bankers Trust Co. and associates.	12,400,000 £400,000	1,995,000	-----	166,842.41	14,498.68	-----	181,341.09	
8	June 16	Republic of Estonia.	Banking currency reform 7 percent loan of 1927.	July 1, 1967	4,000,000	Hallgarten & Co.	2,000,000	-----	-----	*30,474.62	-----	-----	*30,474.62	
9	May 13	United Electric Service Co.	External first mortgage sinking-fund gold bonds 7 percent series A.	----- 1956	6,000,000	J. A. Sisto & Co.	-----	-----	-----	-----	2,738.95	-----	2,738.95	
10	July 27	United Steel Works Corporation.	20-year 6½ percent sinking-fund debentures, series A.	July 1, 1947	30,000,000	International Acceptance Bank, Inc.	-----	250,000	-----	-----	2,990.50	-----	2,990.50	
					239,840,000 £2,000,000	-----		24,110,000 £400,000	10,243,100	600,000	194,215.55	70,660.15	5,970.00	270,845.70

¹ Plus 100 stock warrants.

* Loss.

175841-38-PT 3-27

STOCK EXCHANGE PRACTICES

1369

Participations of over \$250,000 in which other companies acted as managers—Continued

FOREIGN BONDS—Continued

No.	Date of participation	Name of issue	Description	Due date	Amount of issue	Syndicate managers	Amount of participation			Net profit			Total profit
							Original group	Intermediate group	Selling group	Original group	Intermediate group	Selling group	
1	1928 Jan. 23	Republic of Chile Ry.	Refunding sinking-fund 6-percent gold external bonds.	Jan. 1, 1961	\$45,912,000	National City Co.	-----	\$1,000,000	-----	-----	\$7,931.97	-----	\$7,931.97
2	Aug. 31	Republic of Chile.	External loan sinking-fund 6-percent gold bonds.	Sept. 1, 1961	16,000,000do.....	\$1,600,000	884,500	-----	\$14,000	5,796.35	-----	19,796.35
3	Oct. 30	The Oriental Development Co., Ltd.	External loan 30-year 5½-percent gold debentures.	Nov. 1, 1958	19,900,000do.....	3,980,000	1,000,000	\$100,000	22,387.50	5,025.83	\$2,125	29,538.33
					81,812,000		5,598,000	2,884,500	100,000	36,387.50	18,754.15	2,125	57,266.65
1	1929 Mar. 11	Republic of Chile.	External loan sinking-fund 6-percent gold bonds.	Mar. 1, 1962	10,000,000do.....	1,000,000	250,000	-----	8,750.00	1,653.60	-----	10,403.60
1	1930 Apr. 23	Republic of Chile.	External 6 percent gold bonds.	May 1, 1963	25,000,000	National City Co.	2,500,000	1,500,000	-----	21,875.00	750.00	-----	22,625.00
2	May 9	Imperial Japanese Government.	External loan of 1930 35-year sinking-fund 5½-percent gold bonds.	May 1, 1965	71,000,000	J. P. Morgan & Co. and associates.	17,000,000	5,044,000	2,296,000	197,056.34	25,220.00	23,671.00	245,947.34
3	June 11	German Government.	International 5½-percent loan, 1930, 35-year gold bonds.	June 1, 1965	98,250,000	J. P. Morgan & Co.	9,333,750	2,500,000	3,000,000	74,670.00	12,500.00	31,612.50	118,782.50
4	July 14	Austrian Government.	International Loan, 1930, sinking-fund 7-percent gold bonds American Tranche.	July 1, 1957	25,000,000do.....	2,375,000	1,000,000	-----	19,000.00	7,900.00	-----	26,900.00
					219,250,000		31,208,750	10,044,000	5,296,000	312,601.34	46,370.00	55,283.50	414,254.84
1	1931 June 25	Taiwan Electric Power Co., Ltd.	40-year sinking-fund 5½-percent gold bonds.	July 1, 1971	22,800,000	J. P. Morgan & Co. and associates.	5,200,000	3,800,000	1,455,000	42,900.00	17,499.00	12,162.50	72,561.50

DOMESTIC BONDS

1	1927 Jan. 19	California Petroleum Corporation.	12-year convertible 5s S. F. gold debentures.	Nov. 1, 1938	\$8,000,000	Blair & Co., Inc., Hallgarten & Co.	\$1,000,000	\$731,250		\$11,250.00	\$4,251.88		\$15,501.88
	Apr. 2	Federal Land Bank.	4¼ percent	May 1, 1957	100,000,000	Alexander Brown & Sons and associates.			\$265,000			\$1,891.15	1,891.15
	Apr. 15	Shell Union Oil Corporation.	20-year 5 percent sinking-fund gold debentures.	May 1, 1947	60,000,000	Lee Higginson & Co.	11,500,000	5,787,500	260,000	109,064.48	28,937.50	3,125.00	141,126.98
4	May 10	The Chesapeake Corporation.	20-year 5 percent collateral trust bonds, convertible.	May 15, 1947	48,000,000	J. P. Morgan & Co., Guaranty Co. of New York.		2,250,000			12,095.00		12,095.00
5	Sept. 15	Tidewater Associated Transport Corporation.	First lien 10-year Marine Equipment 5 percent sinking-fund gold bonds.	1937	1,800,000	Blair & Co., Inc., Chase Securities Corporation.	375,000			5,854.87			5,854.87
6	Oct. 11	do	do	1937	1,300,000	Blair & Co., Chase Securities Corporation.	270,833	145,000		1,354.16	630.11		1,993.27
7	Oct. 18	Edison Electric Illuminating Co. (Boston).	3-year 4½ percent gold notes.	Nov. 1, 1930	30,000,000	Lee Higginson & Co. and associates.			500,000			2,500.00	2,500.00
8	Oct. 26	Shell Pipe Line Corporation.	25-year 5 percent sinking-fund gold debentures.	Nov. 1, 1952	30,000,000	Lee Higginson & Co.	6,900,000	2,575,000	250,000	34,500.00	13,303.03	625.00	48,428.03
		Total			269,100,000		20,045,833	11,483,750	1,265,000	162,023.51	59,226.52	8,141.15	229,391.18
1	1928 Oct. 1	Abraham & Straus.	15-year 5½ percent gold debentures.	Oct. 1, 1943	5,150,000	Lehman Bros.	1,287,500			22,498.41			22,498.41
2	Nov. 7	Nathan Straus, Inc.	10-year sinking fund 6-percent convertible bonds.	1938	1,000,000	J. A. Sisto & Co.	100,000			25,939.50			25,939.50
		Total			6,150,000		1,387,500			48,437.91			48,437.91
1	1929 Jan. 2	Cigar Stores Realty Holdings, Inc.	20-year 5½ percent sinking fund gold debentures, series A.	Jan. 1, 1949	10,000,000	Guaranty Co. of New York.	3,500,000	1,074,500		33,081.30	5,372.50		38,453.80
2	Sept. 13	Shell Union Oil Corporation.	5-percent sinking fund gold debentures with warrants.	Oct. 1, 1949	50,000,000	Lee Higginson & Co.	11,500,000	4,966,250	1,000,000	86,250.00	48,118.81	7,250.00	141,618.81

* Plus 1,100 shares of common stock.

Participations of over \$250,000 in which other companies acted as managers—Continued

FOREIGN BONDS

No.	Date of participation	Name of issue	Description	Due date	Amount of issue	Syndicate managers	Amount of participation			Net profit			Total profit
							Original group	Intermediate group	Selling group	Original group	Intermediate group	Selling group	
3	1929 Aug. 29	Hotel Waldorf-Astoria Corporation.	First mortgage leasehold 7-percent sinking fund gold bonds with warrants.	Sept. 1, 1954	\$11,000,000	Hayden, Stone & Co., Hallgarten & Co., Kissel Kinnicutt & Co.	-----	732,000	-----	-----	*\$33,536.90	-----	*\$33,536.90
4	Oct. 17	Southern Bell Telephone & Telegraph.	First mortgage sinking fund gold bonds.	Jan. 1, 1941	32,000,000	J. P. Morgan & Co.	\$3,440,000	911,000	-----	\$36,036.15	14,266.26	-----	50,302.41
5	Jan. 30	Allegheny Corporation.	15-year collateral trust convertible 5 percent.	Feb. 1, 1944	35,000,000	do	-----	250,000	\$250,000	-----	1,662.50	\$1,662.50	3,325.00
		Total	-----	-----	138,000,000	-----	18,440,000	7,933,750	1,250,000	155,367.45	35,883.17	8,912.50	200,163.12
1	1930 Jan. 11	American Telephone & Telegraph.	35-year 5-percent gold debentures.	Feb. 1, 1965	150,000,000	J. P. Morgan & Co.	16,125,000	4,145,000	4,000,000	137,062.50	29,719.65	48,632.15	215,414.30
2	Mar. 17	Pure Oil Co.	10-year 5½-percent sinking fund gold notes.	Mar. 1, 1940	20,000,000	Guaranty Co. of New York.	-----	250,000	-----	-----	1,930.31	-----	1,930.31
3	Apr. 21	B. F. Goodrich & Co.	15-year convertible 6-percent gold debentures.	June 1, 1945	30,000,000	Otis & Co. and Associates.	-----	1,000,000	732,000	-----	16,470.00	8,750.00	25,220.00
4	Apr. 23	Van Sweringen Corporation.	5-year 6-percent gold notes with warrants.	May 1, 1935	30,000,000	Guaranty Co. of New York.	-----	250,000	250,000	-----	1,562.50	3,437.50	5,000.00
		Total	-----	-----	230,000,000	-----	16,125,000	5,645,000	4,982,000	137,062.50	49,682.46	60,819.65	247,564.61

RAILROAD BONDS

1	1927 Feb. 23	Hocking Valley Ry. Co.	4½-percent secured gold notes.	Sept. 1, 1927	\$5,000,000	J. P. Morgan & Co.	\$875,000	-----	-----	-----	\$907.81	-----	\$907.81
2	May 7	Erie R.R. Co.	Refunding and improvement mortgage 5-percent gold notes.	May 1, 1967	50,000,000	do	-----	250,000	-----	-----	2,117.50	-----	2,117.50

3	Aug. 27	Boston & Maine R.R. Co.	First mortgage gold bonds series AC, 5 percent.	Sept. 1, 1967	30,942,000	Kidder, Peabody & Co. and associates.	2,867,000	1,275,000	28,670.00	11,457.15	40,127.15		
			Total		85,942,000		3,742,000	1,525,000	29,577.81	13,574.65	43,152.46		
1	1928 Aug. 15	Brooklyn Manhattan Transit Corporation.	1-year 6-percent secured gold notes.	Aug. 15, 1929	10,000,000	Chase Securities Corporation and associates.	4,848,300		1,212,000	07,784.87	10,605	18,389.87	
1	1929 Jan. 26	Chesapeake & Ohio Ry. Co.	Refunding and improvement mortgage 4½-percent gold bonds series A.	Oct. 1, 1993	24,784,000	J. P. Morgan & Co.	4,337,200			34,697.60		34,697.60	
2	Jan. 28	Railway Express Agency, Inc.	5 percent serial gold bonds, series A.	(*)	32,000,000	do.	12,000,000		5,334,000	121,560.00	60,300.00	181,860.00	
			Total		56,784,000		16,337,200		5,334,000	156,257.60	60,300.00	216,557.60	
1	1930 Mar. 21	Boston & Maine Railroad Co.	First mortgage gold bonds series II 5 percent.	May 1, 1955	15,000,000	Kidder, Peabody & Co.	1,312,500		786,000	12,814.07	10,807.50	23,621.57	
2	Mar. 25	Pennsylvania Tank Line.	5 percent equipment trust certificates series BB.	(*)	900,000	Freeman & Co.	900,000			9,000.00		9,000.00	
3	Sept. 24	Cincinnati Union Terminal Co.	First mortgage 4½-percent gold bonds series A.	July 1, 2020	12,000,000	J. P. Morgan & Co., Kuhn, Loeb & Co.	4,000,000		2,500,000	42,250.00	26,750.00	69,000.00	
4	Jan. 14	Chesapeake & Ohio Railway Co.	Refunding and improvement mortgage 4½-percent gold bonds series B.	Jan. 1, 1935	35,088,000	J. P. Morgan & Co.	6,140,000	250,000	500,000	49,123.20	1,180.00	4,720.00	55,023.20
			Total		62,988,000		12,352,500	250,000	3,786,000	113,187.27	1,180.00	42,277.50	156,644.77
1	1931 Jan. 8	Texas & Pacific Ry. Co.	General and refunding gold bonds, 5-percent series D.	Dec. 1, 1980	13,000,000	J.P. Morgan & Co.	2,730,000		2,100,000	10,237.50	20,865	31,102.50	
2	Jan. 26	Missouri Pacific R.R. Co.	First and refunding mortgage 5-percent gold bonds, series I.	Feb. 1, 1981	61,200,000	do.	12,582,000	10,180,000	1,000,000	48,195.00	52,250	6,350	106,795.00
3	Mar. 11	Boston & Maine R.R. Co.	First mortgage gold bonds, series J, 4¾%	Apr. 1, 1961	13,943,000	Lee Higginson & Co.	1,220,000			12,608.81		12,608.81	
4	Nov. 18	Cincinnati Union Terminal Co.	First mortgage 5-percent gold bonds, series B.	July 1, 2020	12,000,000	J. P. Morgan & Co.; Kuhn Loeb & Co.	4,000,000		1,210,000	42,500.00	15,367	57,867	
			Total		100,143,000		20,532,000	10,180,000	4,310,000	113,541.31	52,250	42,582	208,373.31

* Loss.

* Due serially to Mar. 1, 1949.

* Oct. 1, 1930/40.

Participations of over \$250,000 in which other companies acted as managers—Continued

DOMESTIC STOCK

No.	Date of participation	Name of issue	Description	Due date	Amount of issue	Syndicate managers	Amount of participation			Net profit			Total profit
							Original group	Inter-mediate group	Selling group	Original group	Inter-mediate group	Selling group	
1	1927 Jan. 19	Consolidated Gas Co. of New York.	5 percent cumulative preferred.	-----	\$ 1,200,000	National City Co.	\$ 20,000	\$ 30,000	-----	\$38,983.26	\$15,000.00	-----	\$53,983.26
2	Apr. 15	United Cigar Stores Co.	6 percent preferred	-----	\$ 200,000	Guaranty Co. of New York.	\$ 80,000	\$ 20,200	\$ 2,500	100,004.41	18,150.37	\$4,375.00	122,529.78
		Total	-----	-----	\$ 1,400,000	-----	\$ 100,000	\$ 50,200	\$ 2,500	138,987.67	33,150.37	4,375.00	176,513.04
1	1930 Jan. 27	Republic Steel Corporation.	6 percent preferred	-----	558,311	Otis & Co.	\$ 70,000	335,400	475,000	130,615.17	2,934.75	9,500.00	143,049.92

¹ Shares.

EXHIBIT NO. 32

QUESTION 9B.—List of all stock and bond issues originated and managed by us and in which we participated to the extent of not less than \$250,000

No.	Name	Date	Amount	Description of issue	Cost price	Public offering price	Gross spread	Our participations	Net profit realized
1	Pacific Fruit Express.....	Jan. 14, 1927	\$5,783,000	5-percent equipment trust certificates, series D, due Apr. 1, 1927, to 1941.	Percent 100%	Percent 101½	Percent 1%	Original account, \$5,783,000..... Selling group \$386,000.....	\$60,716.25 482.50
2	Gulf, Mobile & Northern R. R. Co.	Jan. 26, 1927	3,000,000	First mortgage 5-percent gold bonds, series C, due Oct. 1, 1950.	97¼	99¾	2½	Original account \$3,000,000..... Purchase group, \$850,000.....	30,000.00 5,169.55
3	Missouri Pacific R.R. Co.....	Jan. 31, 1927	95,000,000	First and refunding mortgage 5-percent gold bonds, series F, due Mar. 1, 1977.	97¼	100	2¾	Original account \$80,750,000..... Syndicate account, \$3,415,000..... Selling group, \$2,000,000.....	807,500.00 22,532.10 8,425.50
4	Chicago & North Western Ry. Co.	Feb. 9, 1927	20,572,000	First and refunding mortgage 4½-percent gold bonds, due May 1, 2037.	92½	95	2½	Original account, \$16,457,600..... Selling group, \$1,000,000.....	220,746.38 7,500.00
5	The Texas & Pacific Ry. Co.	Mar. 2, 1927	16,000,000	General and refunding mortgage 5-percent gold bonds, series B, due Apr. 1, 1977.	97	99½	2½	Original account \$16,000,000..... Selling group, \$750,000.....	163,261.99 7,500.00
6	The Pennsylvania, Ohio & Detroit R.R. Co.	Mar. 7, 1927	22,000,000	First and refunding mortgage 4½-percent gold bonds series A due Apr. 1, 1977.	92½	95	2½	Original account \$18,500,000..... Purchase group \$3,050,000..... Selling group \$4,000,000.....	189,375.00 9,425.52 30,000.00
7	The Northern Central Ry. Co.	Mar. 10, 1927	5,231,000	General and refunding mortgage 4½-percent gold bonds series A due Mar. 1, 1974.	94¼	96¼	2	Original account \$4,231,000..... Selling group \$2,750,000.....	41,081.28 20,625.00
8	Illinois Central R.R. Co. and Chicago, St. Louis & New Orleans R.R. Co.	Apr. 26, 1927	17,350,000	Joint first refunding mortgage 4½-percent bonds series C due Dec. 1, 1963.	95	97½	2½	Original account \$15,050,000..... Purchase group \$2,050,000..... Selling group \$2,974,000.....	153,375.00 14,933.75 11,455.44
9	Union Pacific R.R. Co.....	May 19, 1927	26,835,000	40-year 4½-percent gold bonds due July 1, 1967.	94¼	97¼	2½	Original account \$26,835,000..... Purchase group \$2,660,000..... Selling group \$256,000.....	268,350.00 17,011.17 1,721.25
10	Southern Pacific Co. Oregon lines.	June 3, 1927	20,000,000	First mortgage 4½-percent bonds series A, due Mar. 1, 1977.	98	100½	2½	Original account \$18,250,000..... Purchase group \$4,525,000..... Selling group \$5,055,000.....	184,687.50 27,913.54 26,325.50
11	The Hudson Coal Co.....	June 7, 1927	35,000,000	First mortgage sinking-fund 5-percent gold bonds series A due June 1, 1962.	95½	98½	3	Original account \$28,000,000..... Syndicate \$3,515,000..... Selling group \$1,000,000.....	290,500.00 22,787.41 10,000.00
12	City of Copenhagen.....	June 9, 1927	15,000,000	25-year 5-percent gold bonds due June 1, 1952.	94.29	97¼	2.71	Original account \$10,000,000.....	112,372.93
13	The Baltimore & Ohio R.R. Co.	---do-----	1,632,425	Common stock syndicate underwriting.	105¼	107½	2.25	Original account 252,970 shares..... Syndicate 48,870 shares.....	252,970.00 69,684.90
14	Western Maryland Ry. Co..	June, 1927	12,000,000	First and refunding mortgage 5½-percent gold bonds, series A, due July 1, 1977.	96½	99½	3	Original account \$4,300,000..... Purchase group \$1,265,000.....	48,000.00 6,691.05

1 Shares.

STOCK EXCHANGE PRACTICES

1375

QUESTION 9B.—List of all stock and bond issues originated and managed by us and in which we participated to the extent of not less than \$250,000—
Continued

No.	Name	Date	Amount	Description of issue	Cost price	Public offering price	Gross spread	Our participations	Net profit realized
15	North German Lloyd.....	Oct. 22, 1927	\$20,000,000	20-year 6-percent sinking-fund gold bonds due Nov. 1, 1947.	Percent 90	Percent 94	Percent 4	Purchase group \$1,925,000..... Original account \$10,000,000..... Selling group \$277,000.....	\$6,305.20 96,875.00 2,866.25
16	Paramount Famous Lasky Corporation.	Nov. 14, 1927	16,000,000	20-year 6-percent sinking-fund gold bonds due Dec. 1, 1947.	95	99½	4½	Original account \$10,000,000..... Purchase group \$1,875,000.....	180,000.00 14,581.78
17	The Youngstown Sheet & Tube Co.	Nov. 21, 1927	75,000,000	First mortgage sinking-fund 5-percent gold bonds series A, due Jan. 1, 1978.	98	101	3	Original account \$67,500,000..... Syndicate account \$2,235,000..... Selling group \$8,100,000.....	686,250.00 11,713.47 81,000.00
18	Missouri, Kansas & Texas R.R. Co.	Dec. 1, 1927	13,600,000	Prior lien mortgage 4½-percent gold bonds series D, due Jan. 1, 1978.	97¼	99¾	2½	Original account \$3,740,000..... Selling group \$2,125,000.....	49,980.80 48,467.01
19	International Great Northern R.R. Co.	Dec. 22, 1927	5,500,000	First mortgage 5-percent gold bonds, series C, due July 1, 1956.	99½	101¾	2¼	Original account \$5,200,000..... Selling group \$1,865,000.....	56,978.61 13,987.50
20	New Orleans, Texas & Mexico Ry. Co.do.....	5,900,000	First mortgage 4½-percent gold bonds, series D, due Aug. 1, 1956.	95¾	98	2¼	Original account \$4,220,000..... Selling group \$100,000.....	44,780.43 875.00
21	Texarkana Union Station....	Dec. 22, 1927	1,500,000	5-percent trust certificates series A, due Dec. 1, 1957.	100	101¾	1¾	Original account \$1,500,000.....	\$21,000.00
22	Southern Pacific Co.....	Jan. 30, 1928	29,400,000	40-year 4½-percent gold bonds due Mar. 1, 1968.	97¾	99¾	2½	Original account \$26,800,000..... Purchase group, \$1,675,000.....	271,250.00 9,804.19
23	The Denver & Rio Grande Western Railroad Co.	Mar. 2, 1928	12,000,000	Refunding and improvement mortgage 5-percent gold bonds series B due Apr. 1, 1978.	98½	96	2½	Original account, \$9,000,000.....	91,303.56
24	American & Continental Corporation.	Mar. 7, 1928	7,500,000	15-year 5-percent gold debentures due Apr. 1, 1943.	95¼	97½	2¼	Original account, \$3,500,000.....	45,000.96
25	Inland Steel Co.....	Mar. 17, 1928	30,000,000	First mortgage sinking fund 4½-percent gold bonds due Apr. 1, 1978.	92	95	3	Original account, \$24,000,000..... Purchase group, \$1,225,000..... Selling group, \$6,700,000.....	249,000.00 7,022.50 37,500.00
26	Wabash Railway Co.....	Mar. 21, 1928	17,867,000	Refunding and general mortgage 4½-percent gold bonds series C due Apr. 1, 1978.	93	95½	2½	Original account, \$17,867,000..... Selling group, \$1,800,000.....	199,767.23 18,000.00
27	City of Copenhagen.....	Apr. 24, 1928	12,000,000	25-year 4½-percent gold bonds due May 1, 1953.	92.077	94½	2.423	Original account, \$8,000,000.....	66,019.85
28	Chicago, Milwaukee & St. Paul Ry. Co.	Apr. 25, 1928	24,000,000	General mortgage 4½-percent gold bonds, series E, due May 1, 1989.	100	102½	2½	Original account, \$12,000,000..... Purchase group, \$3,600,000..... Selling group, \$2,500,000.....	120,000.00 13,252.06 18,750.00
29	Mortgage Bank of Chile.....	Apr. 30, 1928	20,000,000	Guaranteed sinking fund 6-percent gold bonds of 1928, due Apr. 30, 1961.	91¾	96¼	4+-565	Original account, \$6,000,000.....	59,868.86
30	Union Pacific R.R. Co.....	May 2, 1928	20,000,000	40-year 4-percent gold bonds due June 1, 1968.	90½	92¼	2¼	Original account, \$20,000,000.....	175,685.80

31	Southern Pacific Co.....	July 25, 1928	4,815,000	4½ percent equipment trust certificates, series K due Aug. 1, 1929 to 1943.	98¼	98¼	½	Original account, \$4,365,000.....	12,037.50
32	Missouri Pacific R.R. Co.....	Oct. 4, 1928	25,000,000	First and refunding mortgage, 5 percent gold bonds series G due Nov. 1, 1978.	96½	99¼	2¼	Original account, \$21,250,000..... Selling group, \$850,000.....	193,934.17 10,625.00
33	North German Lloyd.....	Oct. 26, 1928	1 175,000	American shares for common stock.	63.532	69	5.468	Original account, 70,000 shares.....	140,167.70
34	Pennsylvania Co.....	Nov. 7, 1923	50,000,000	35-year 4½ percent secured gold bonds, due Nov. 1, 1963.	96½	99	27½	Original account, \$4,950,000..... Selling group, \$6,615,000.....	461,468.75 66,031.04
35	United States Rubber Co.....	Dec. 11, 1923	1 728,412	Common stock underwriting syndicate.	32	35	3	Original account, 582,730 shares..... Syndicate account, 51,512 shares.....	105,927.77 223,956.00
36	Mid Continent Petroleum Corporation.	Dec. 21, 1923	1 447,912	do.....	28½	31	2½	Original account, 223,956 shares..... Syndicate account, 25,606 shares.....	38,379.81 197,501.33
37	Westinghouse Electric Manufacturing Co.	Dec. 27, 1923	1 296,252	do.....	102½	105	2½	Original account, 197,502 shares..... Syndicate account, 24,502 shares.....	43,866.71 28,616.00
39	Chicago & North Western Ry. Co.	Jan. 8, 1929	3,577,000	General mortgage gold 4½ percent bonds, due Nov. 1, 1987.	98	99	1	Original account, \$3,506,000.....	30,500.00
40	American Refrigerator Transit Co.	Feb. 6, 1929	2,100,000	Equipment trust 5 percent certificates. Series G, due Feb. 1, 1930 to 1944.	97¼	98¼	1½	Original account, \$2,100,000.....	190,295.92 7,500.00
41	The Texas & Pacific Ry. Co.	Mar. 5, 1929	20,000,000	General refunding mortgage 5 percent gold bonds series C, due Apr. 1, 1979.	96¼	99½	2¼	Original account, \$15,000,000..... Selling group, \$500,000.....	607,910.00 23,616.19
42	Southern Pacific Co.....	Mar. 11, 1929	65,166,000	40-year 4½ percent gold bonds of 1929, due May 1, 1969 underwriting syndicate.	91½	94	2½	Original account, \$60,166,000..... Syndicate account, \$1,611,000.....	403,030.50 6,653.42
43	Missouri Pacific R.R. Co....	Mar. 14, 1929	46,392,000	20-year 5½ percent convertible gold bonds series A due May 1, 1949, underwriting syndicate.	95	97½	2½	Original account, \$39,433,000..... Syndicate account, \$417,000.....	90,815.93 6,250.00
44	Central of Georgia Ry. Co..	May 2, 1929	10,000,000	Refunding and general mortgage 5 percent gold bonds, series C, due Apr. 1, 1959.	95½	98¼	2¼	Original account \$8,500,000..... Selling group \$500,000.....	----- -----
45	The City of New York.....	May 7, 1929	52,000,000	5½ percent gold corporate stock, due Dec. 15, 1932.	101.412	(²)	-----	-----	-----
46	Chicago & North Western Ry.	June 7, 1929	3,971,000	4½ percent equipment trust certificates, series Q, due Oct. 1, 1930 to 1940.	97	97	-----	-----	-----
47	Mortgage Bank of Chile.....	June 26, 1929	20,000,000	Guarantee sinking-fund 6 percent gold bonds of 1929, due May 1, 1962.	89½	92	2½	Original account \$6,000,000.....	4 24,288.91
48	Chicago & North Western Ry. Co.	Oct. 10, 1929	72,335,000	20-year 4¼ percent convertible gold bonds, series A, due Nov. 1, 1949, underwriting.	97½	100	-----	Original account \$57,868,000..... Syndicate account \$6,025,000.....	578,680.00 38,569.86
49	The Pennroad Corporation..	Oct. 8, 1929	1 3,025,000	Voting trust certificates for common stock.	\$15-14.50	\$16.50	5 1½	Original account 3,025,000 shares..... Syndicate account 57,000 shares (syndicate distribution to apply against cost of shares taken up from syndicate).	1,512,812.50 69,924.08

¹ Shares.² Not offered for sale.³ Plus 1¼ percent interest gain.⁴ Loss.⁵ 2 percent as to shares taken up by syndicate.

QUESTION 9B.—List of all stock and bond issues originated and managed by us and in which we participated to the extent of not less than \$250,000—Continued

No.	Name	Date	Amount	Description of issue	Cost price XXX	Public offering price	Gross spread	Our participations	Net profit realized
50	The Baltimore & Ohio R.R. Co.	Jan. 23, 1930	\$63,031,000	30-year 4½ percent convertible gold bonds, due Feb. 1, 1960, underwriting syndicate.	Percent 92½	Percent 95	Percent 2½	Original account, \$25,212,400..... Syndicate account, \$3,736,000.....	\$252,124.00 56,723.04
51	The Western Union Telegraph Co.	Feb. 11, 1930	35,000,000	30-year 5-percent gold bonds, due Mar. 1, 1960.	97¼	100	2¾	Original account, \$26,250,000..... Purchase group account, \$5,150,000..... Selling group, \$2,275,000.....	284,375.00 13,443.72 17,062.50
52	Chicago & Eastern Illinois Ry. Co.	Feb. 19, 1930	2,500,000	2-year 5-percent secured gold notes, due Mar. 1, 1932.	98.18	98.70 99.07	.89	Original account, \$2,500,000.....	18,550.00
53	The Pennsylvania R.R. Co.	Mar. 12, 1930	60,000,000	40-year 4½-percent gold debenture bonds, due Apr. 1, 1970.	92	94½	2½	Original account, \$55,000,000..... Syndicate account, \$4,000,000..... Selling group account, \$4,405,000.....	556,250.00 14,955.94 30,937.50
54	Missouri Pacific R.R. Co.	Mar. 13, 1930	25,000,000	First and refunding mortgage 5-percent gold bonds, series H, due Apr. 1, 1980.	97¾	100¼	2½	Original account, \$17,250,000..... Selling group account, \$2,845,000.....	193,286.88 28,450.00
55	Wabash Ry. Co.	Mar. 14, 1930	15,000,000	Refunding and general mortgage 5-percent gold bonds, series D, due Apr. 1, 1980.	98	100½	2½	Original account, \$15,000,000..... Selling group \$1,975,000.....	164,172.24 19,750.00
56	Chicago, Milwaukee & St. Paul Ry. Co.	Mar. 20, 1930	15,000,000	General mortgage 4¾-percent gold bonds series F due May 1, 1939.	98	100½	2½	Original account \$7,500,000..... Selling group, \$3,271,000.....	74,492.60 32,710.00
57	Southern Pacific Co.	Apr. 15, 1930	41,294,000	Oregon Lines first mortgage 4½-percent bonds, series A due Mar. 1, 1977.	95	97½	2½	Original account, \$37,794,000..... Syndicate account, \$444,000.....	382,315.00 1,526.21
58	Chicago & North Western Ry. Co.	Apr. 15, 1930	5,031,000	General mortgage gold 4¾-percent bonds, due Nov. 1, 1937.	100½	103	2½	Original account, \$4,025,000..... Selling group, \$3,125,000.....	55,315.77 23,437.50
59	The Delaware & Hudson Co.	Apr. 22, 1930	10,000,000	First and refunding mortgage 4-percent gold bonds, due May 1, 1943.	90½	93	2½	Original account, \$8,000,000..... Selling group, \$500,000.....	85,651.22 5,000.00
60	Chicago & Western Indiana R.R. Co.	Apr. 23, 1930	917,000	Consolidated mortgage 4-percent gold bonds, due 1952.	87¾	87¾	½	Original account, \$917,000.....	4,585.00
61	U.S. Rubber Co.	Apr. 30, 1930	15,000,000	6-percent 3-year secured gold notes, due June 1, 1933.	97	99	2	Original account, \$9,600,000.....	76,700.42
62	Vicksburg, Shreveport & Pacific Ry. Co.	May 27, 1930	1,845,000	Refunding & improvement mortgage 5-percent bonds, series B due Nov. 1, 1973.	100½	102½	2	Original account, \$1,845,000.....	27,675.00
63	Gulf, Mobile & Northern R.R. Co.	June 9, 1930	3,000,000	First mortgage, 5-percent gold bonds, series C, due Oct. 1, 1950.	97	99½	2½	Original account, \$3,000,000.....	31,446.10
64	Paramount Publix Corporation.	July 31, 1930	15,000,000	20 year 5½ percent sinking fund gold bonds due Aug. 1, 1950.	90	94½	4½	Original account \$9,375,000..... Purchase group \$1,200,000.....	168,750.00 6,292.39
65	Chicago & North Western Ry. Co.	Sept. 9, 1930	12,000,000	First and Refunding Mortgage, series C 4½ percent gold bonds due May 1, 2037.	97½	99¾	2¼	Original account, \$9,600,000..... Selling group, \$500,000.....	\$ 92,808.00 3,750.00

66	The Pittsburgh, Cincinnati, Chicago & St. Louis R.R. Co.	Sept. 16, 1930	23,735,000	General mortgage 4½ percent gold bonds, series C due July 1, 1977.	98¾	100½	2¼	Original account, \$21,735,000..... Selling group, \$2,555,000.....	240,591.98 30,127.50
67	The Cleveland & Pittsburgh R.R. Co.do.....	7,182,000	General and refunding mortgage 4¼ percent gold bonds series A due Feb. 1, 1977.	98¾	100½	2¼	Original account, \$6,582,000..... Selling group, \$3,507,000.....	74,914.14 38,723.75
68	Chicago Heights Terminal Transfer R.R. Co.	Dec. 5, 1930	562,000	First mortgage 6 percent gold bonds, series A due Jan. 1, 1951.	98	100	2	Original account, \$562,000.....	8,835.00
69	The Philadelphia Baltimore & Washington R.R. Co.	Jan. 22, 1931	11,301,000	General mortgage 4½ percent gold bonds, series C due July 1, 1977.	100	102	2	Original account, \$16,284,000..... Selling group, \$3,030,000.....	160,325.49 18,937.50
70	The Pennsylvania Ohio & Detroit R.R. Co.do.....	6,483,000	First and refunding mortgage 4½ percent gold bonds, series A due Apr. 1, 1977.	98	100	2	Selling group, \$175,000.....	1,093.75
71	The United New Jersey R.R. & Canal Co.do.....	6,020,000	General (now first) mortgage 4½ percent gold bonds due Sept. 1, 1979.	100	102	2	Original account, \$5,520,000..... Selling group, \$5,120,000.....	67,577.63 38,400.00
72	The Pittsburgh, Youngstown & Ashtabula Ry. Co.do.....	1,485,000	First general mortgage 4½ percent gold bonds, series D, due June 1, 1977.	98½	100½	2	Original account \$1,485,000.....	25,655.10
74	The Connecting Railway Co.do.....	2,032,000	First mortgage 4½ percent gold bonds, due Mar. 15, 1951.	99	101	2	Original account \$2,032,000.....	35,560.00
75	Inland Steel Co.....	Jan. 23, 1931	15,000,000	First mortgage sinking fund 4½ percent gold bonds, series B, due Feb. 1, 1981.	94	96½	2½	Original account \$12,500,000..... Selling group \$1,985,000.....	132,436.67 19,850.09
76	The Baltimore & Ohio R.R. Co.	Feb. 2, 1931	35,000,000	4 percent gold notes, due Aug. 10, 1932.	99½	99.85	.35	Original account \$14,000,000.....	48,207.65
77	The City of New York.....	Mar. 4, 1931	100,000,000	4¼ percent gold corporate stock and gold serial bonds.	101.977	2.25-4.08	-----	Original account \$29,000,000.....	220,535.51
78	The Pennsylvania R.R. Co.	Mar. 9, 1931	50,000,000	General mortgage 4¼ percent gold bonds, series D, due Apr. 1, 1981.	94	96½	2½	Original account \$46,000,000..... Syndicate account \$5,175,000..... Selling group \$4,140,000.....	465,000.00 18,908.49 34,470.00
79	General American Transportation System.	Mar. 10, 1931	9,690,000	4½ percent equipment trust certificates, series A, due Mar. 1, 1932 to 1946.	95¾	97.98	2.23	Original account \$7,752,000..... Selling group \$510,000.....	87,506.93 3,825.00
80	Southern Pacific Co.....	Mar. 25, 1931	50,000,000	50-year 4½ percent gold bonds, due May 1, 1981.	94¼	96¾	2½	Original account \$46,000,000..... Syndicate account \$5,920,000..... Selling group \$4,110,000.....	465,000.00 12,220.00 30,287.50
81	Illinois Central R.R. Co.....	May 5, 1931	20,000,000	3-year 4½ percent gold notes, due June 1, 1934.	98½	99½	½	Original account \$17,500,000.....	86,541.71

* Applied against cost of bonds taken up from syndicate.

EXHIBIT NO. 33

Recapitulation of all stock and bond issues of over \$250,000 which Kuhn, Loeb & Co. originated and managed 1927-31

BY CLASS

Classification	Year	Number of issues	Amount of issue	Amount of participation			Net profits			Total net profits	
				Original group	Intermediate group	Selling group	Original group	Intermediate group	Selling group		
Foreign bonds.....	1927	2	\$35,000,000	\$20,000,000	\$1,925,000	\$277,000	\$209,247.93	\$6,305.20	\$2,866.25	\$218,419.38	
	1928	2	32,000,000	14,000,000			125,888.71			125,888.71	
	1929	1	20,000,000	6,000,000			24,288.91			24,288.91	
			5	87,000,000	40,000,000	1,925,000	277,000	310,847.73	6,305.20	2,866.25	320,019.18
Railroad bonds.....	1927	14	264,488,000	218,533,600	17,815,000	22,875,000	2,279,116.99	103,676.68	176,882.20	2,559,675.87	
	1928	8	183,082,000	156,782,000	10,225,000	11,765,000	1,525,447.01	56,632.46	113,406.04	1,695,485.51	
	1929	7	221,441,000	184,473,000	8,053,000	1,000,000	1,899,348.35	68,829.47	13,750.00	1,981,927.82	
	1930	16	286,097,000	216,522,400	8,180,000	22,683,000	2,263,012.93	73,205.19	212,886.25	2,549,104.37	
	1931	9	182,321,000	148,821,000	11,095,000	16,575,000	1,353,867.68	31,128.49	123,188.75	1,508,184.82	
			54	1,137,429,000	925,132,000	55,368,000	74,898,000	9,320,792.86	333,472.29	640,113.24	10,294,378.39
Domestic bonds.....	1927	4	131,783,000	111,283,000	7,625,000	9,486,000	1,217,466.25	49,082.66	91,482.50	1,358,031.41	
	1928	2	37,500,000	27,500,000	1,225,000	6,700,000	294,000.96	7,022.50	37,500.00	338,523.46	
	1929	2	54,100,000	2,100,000			30,500.00			30,500.00	
	1930	3	65,000,000	45,225,000	6,350,000	2,275,000	529,825.42	24,736.11	17,062.50	571,624.03	
	1931	3	124,690,000	49,252,000		2,495,000	440,479.11		23,675.00	464,154.11	
			14	413,073,000	235,360,000	15,200,000	20,956,000	2,512,271.74	80,841.27	169,720.00	2,762,833.01
Foreign stock.....	1928	1	175,000	170,000			140,167.70			140,167.70	
Railroad stock.....	1927	1	632,425	252,970	148,870		252,970.00	69,684.90		322,654.90	
Domestic stock.....	1928	3	1,472,576	1,004,188	1,101,620		1,026,039.29	188,384.29		1,214,423.58	
	1929	1	3,025,000	3,025,000	57,000		1,512,812.50	69,924.08		1,682,736.68	
		4	4,497,576	4,029,188	1,158,620		2,538,851.79	258,308.37		2,797,160.16	

SUMMARY

Foreign bonds	1927-1929	5	\$87,000,000	\$40,000,000	\$1,925,000	\$277,000	\$310,847.73	\$6,305.20	\$2,866.25	\$320,019.18
Railroad bonds	1927-1931	54	1,137,429,000	925,132,000	55,368,000	74,898,000	9,320,792.86	333,472.29	640,113.24	10,294,378.39
Domestic bonds	1927-1931	14	413,073,000	235,360,000	15,200,000	20,956,000	2,512,271.74	80,841.37	169,720.00	2,762,833.01
Total bonds		73	1,637,502,000	1,200,492,000	72,493,000	96,131,000	12,143,912.33	420,618.76	812,699.49	13,377,230.58
Foreign stocks	1928	1	175,000	170,000			140,167.70			140,167.70
Railroad stocks	1927	1	632,425	252,970	48,870		252,970.00	69,684.90		322,654.90
Domestic stocks	1928-1929	4	4,497,576	4,029,188	158,620		2,538,851.79	258,308.37		2,797,160.16
		6	5,305,001	4,352,158	207,490		2,931,989.49	327,993.27		3,259,982.76

BY YEAR

Foreign bonds	1927	2	\$35,000,000	\$20,000,000	\$1,925,000	\$277,000	\$209,247.93	\$6,305.20	\$2,866.25	\$218,419.38
Railroad bonds		14	264,488,000	218,533,600	17,815,000	22,875,000	2,279,116.99	103,676.68	176,882.20	2,559,675.87
Domestic bonds		4	131,783,000	111,283,000	7,625,000	9,486,000	1,217,466.25	49,082.66	91,482.50	1,358,031.41
		20	431,271,000	349,816,600	27,365,000	32,638,000	3,705,831.17	159,064.54	271,230.95	4,136,126.66
Railroad stock		1	632,425	252,970	48,870		252,970.00	69,684.90		322,654.90
Foreign bonds	1928	2	32,000,000	14,000,000			125,888.71			125,888.71
Railroad bonds		8	183,082,000	156,782,000	10,225,000	11,765,000	1,525,447.01	56,632.46	113,406.04	1,695,485.61
Domestic bonds		2	37,500,000	27,500,000	1,225,000	6,700,000	294,000.96	7,022.50	37,500.00	338,523.46
		12	252,582,000	198,282,000	11,450,000	18,465,000	1,945,336.68	63,654.96	150,906.04	2,159,897.68
Foreign stocks		1	175,000	170,000			140,167.70			140,167.70
Domestic stocks		3	1,472,576	1,004,188	101,620		1,026,039.29	188,384.29		1,214,423.58
		4	1,647,576	1,074,188	101,620		1,166,206.99	188,384.29		1,354,591.28
Foreign bonds	1929	1	20,000,000	6,000,000			24,288.91			24,288.91
Railroad bonds		7	221,441,000	184,473,000	8,053,000	1,000,000	1,899,348.35	68,829.47	13,750.00	1,981,927.82
Domestic bonds		2	54,100,000	2,100,000			30,500.00			30,500.00
		10	295,541,000	192,573,000	8,053,000	1,000,000	1,905,559.44	68,829.47	13,750.00	1,988,138.91
Domestic stock		1	3,025,000	3,025,000	57,000		1,512,812.50	69,924.08		1,582,736.58
Railroad bond	1930	16	286,097,000	216,522,400	8,180,000	22,683,000	2,263,012.93	73,205.19	212,886.25	2,549,104.37
Domestic bonds		3	65,000,000	45,225,000	6,350,000	2,275,000	529,825.42	24,736.11	17,062.50	571,624.03
		19	351,097,000	261,747,400	14,530,000	24,958,000	2,792,838.35	97,941.30	229,948.75	3,120,728.40

1 Shares.

* Loss.

Recapitulation of all stock and bond issues of over \$250,000 which Kuhn, Loeb & Co. originated and managed 1927-31—Continued

BY CLASS

Classification	Year	Number of issues	Amount of issue	Amount of participation			Net profits			Total net profits
				Original group	Intermediate group	Selling group	Original group	Intermediate group	Selling group	
Railroad bonds.....	1931	9	\$182,321,000	\$148,821,000	\$11,095,000	\$16,575,000	\$1,353,867.58	\$31,128.49	\$123,188.75	\$1,508,184.82
Domestic bonds.....		3	124,690,000	49,252,000	-----	2,495,000	440,479.11	-----	23,675.00	464,154.11
		12	307,011,000	198,073,000	11,095,000	19,070,000	1,794,346.69	31,128.49	146,863.75	1,972,338.93
SUMMARY—BONDS										
	1927	20	\$431,271,000	\$349,816,600	\$27,365,000	\$32,638,000	\$3,705,831.17	\$159,064.54	\$271,230.95	\$4,136,126.66
		12	252,582,000	198,282,000	11,450,000	18,465,000	1,945,336.68	63,654.96	150,906.04	2,159,897.68
		10	206,541,000	192,573,000	8,053,000	1,000,000	1,905,559.44	68,829.47	13,750.00	1,988,138.91
		19	351,097,000	261,747,400	14,530,000	24,958,000	2,792,838.35	97,941.30	229,948.75	3,120,728.40
		12	307,011,000	198,073,000	11,095,000	19,070,000	1,794,346.69	31,128.49	146,863.75	1,972,338.93
			73	1,638,502,000	1,200,492,000	72,493,000	96,131,000	12,143,912.33	420,618.76	812,699.49
SUMMARY—STOCKS										
	1927	1	1 632,425	1 252,970	1 48,870	-----	\$252,970.00	\$69,684.90	-----	\$322,654.90
		4	1 1,647,576	1 1,074,188	1 101,620	-----	1,166,206.99	188,384.29	-----	1,354,591.28
		1	1 3,025,000	1 3,025,000	1 57,000	-----	1,512,812.50	69,924.08	-----	1,582,736.58
			6	1 5,305,001	1 4,352,158	1 207,490	-----	2,931,989.49	327,993.27	-----

1 Shares.

Participations of over \$250,000 which Kuhn, Loeb & Co. originated and managed

DOMESTIC BONDS

No.	Date of issue	Name of issue	Description of issue	Due date	Amount of issue	Amount of participation			Net profit			Total profit
						Original group	Inter-mediate group	Selling group	Original group	Inter-mediate group	Selling group	
	1927 June 7	Hudson Coal Co.....	First mortgage sinking fund 5 percent gold bonds, series A.	June 1, 1962	\$35,000,000	\$28,000,000	\$3,515,000	\$1,000,000	\$290,500.00	\$22,787.41	\$10,000.00	\$323,287.41
2	Jan. 14	Pacific Fruit Express.....	5 percent equipment trust certificates, series D.	Apr. 1, 1927 to 1941.	5,783,000	5,783,000	-----	386,000	60,716.25	-----	482.50	61,198.75
3	Nov. 14	Paramount Famous Lasky	20-year 6 percent sinking fund gold bonds.	Dec. 1, 1947	16,000,000	10,000,000	1,875,000	-----	180,000.00	14,581.78	-----	194,581.78
4	Nov. 21	The Youngstown Sheet & Tube Co.	First mortgage sinking 5 percent gold bonds series A.	Jan. 1, 1978	75,000,000	67,500,000	2,235,000	8,100,000	686,250.00	11,713.47	81,000.00	778,963.47
		Total.....	-----	-----	131,783,000	111,283,000	7,625,000	9,486,000	1,217,466.25	49,082.66	91,482.50	1,358,031.41
	1928											
1	Mar. 7	American & Continental Corp.	15-year 5 percent gold debentures.	Apr. 1, 1943	7,500,000	3,500,000	-----	-----	45,000.96	-----	-----	45,000.96
2	Mar. 17	Inland Steel Co.....	First mortgage sinking fund 4½ percent gold bonds.	Apr. 1, 1978	30,000,000	24,000,000	1,225,000	6,700,000	249,000.00	7,022.50	37,500.00	293,522.50
		Total.....	-----	-----	37,500,000	27,500,000	1,225,000	6,700,000	294,000.96	7,022.50	37,500.00	338,523.46
	1929											
1	Feb. 6	American Refrigerator Transit Co.	Equipment trust 5 percent certificates, series G.	Feb. 1, 1930 to 1944.	2,100,000	2,100,000	-----	-----	30,500.00	-----	-----	30,500.00
2	May 7	The City of New York.....	5¼ percent gold corporate stock.	Dec. 15, 1932 ¹	52,000,000	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----
		Total.....	-----	-----	54,100,000	2,100,000	-----	-----	30,500.00	-----	-----	30,500.00

¹ Not offered for sale.

Participations of over \$250,000 which Kuhn, Loeb & Co. originated and managed—Continued

No.	Date of issue	Name of issue	Description of issue	Due date	Amount of issue	Amount of participation			Net profit			Total profit
						Original group	Inter-mediate group	Selling group	Original group	Inter-mediate group	Selling group	
1	1930 Feb. 11	The Western Union Telegraph Co.	30-year 5-percent gold bonds.	Mar. 1, 1960	\$35,000,000	\$26,250,000	\$5,150,000	\$2,275,000	\$284,375.00	\$18,443.72	\$17,062.50	\$319,881.22
2	Apr. 30	U.S. Rubber Co.	6-percent 3-year secured gold notes.	June 1, 1933	15,000,000	9,600,000	-----	-----	76,700.42	-----	-----	76,700.42
3	July 31	Paramount Publix Corporation.	20-year 5½-percent sinking fund gold bonds.	Aug. 1, 1950	15,000,000	9,375,000	1,200,000	-----	168,750.00	6,292.39	-----	175,042.39
		Total.....	-----	-----	65,000,000	45,225,000	6,350,000	2,275,000	529,825.42	24,736.11	17,062.50	571,624.03
1	1931 Jan. 23	Inland Steel Co.	First mortgage sinking-fund 4½-percent gold bonds B.	Feb. 1, 1981	15,000,000	12,500,000	-----	1,985,000	132,436.67	-----	19,850	152,286.67
2	Mar. 4	City of New York	4¼-percent gold corporate stock and gold serial bonds.	-----	100,000,000	29,000,000	-----	-----	220,535.51	-----	-----	220,535.51
3	Mar. 10	General American Transportation System.	4½-percent equipment trust certificates A.	(1)	9,690,000	7,752,000	-----	510,000	87,506.93	-----	3,825	91,331.93
		Total.....	-----	-----	124,690,000	49,252,000	-----	2,495,000	440,479.11	-----	23,675	464,154.11

FOREIGN BONDS

1	1927 June 9	City of Copenhagen	25-year 5 percent gold bonds.	June 1, 1952	\$15,000,000	\$10,000,000	-----	-----	\$112,372.93	-----	-----	\$112,372.93
2	Oct. 22	North German Lloyd	20-year 6 percent sinking fund gold bonds.	Nov. 1, 1947	20,000,000	10,000,000	\$1,925,000	\$277,000	96,875.00	\$6,305.20	\$2,866.25	106,046.45
		Total.....	-----	-----	35,000,000	20,000,000	1,925,000	277,000	209,247.93	6,305.20	2,866.25	218,419.38
1	1928 Apr. 24	City of Copenhagen	25-year 4½ percent gold bonds.	May 1, 1953	12,000,000	8,000,000	-----	-----	66,019.85	-----	-----	66,019.85
2	Apr. 30	Mortgage Bank of Chile	Guaranteed sinking fund 6 percent gold bonds of 1928.	Apr. 30, 1961	20,000,000	6,000,000	-----	-----	59,868.86	-----	-----	59,868.86
		Total.....	-----	-----	32,000,000	14,000,000	-----	-----	125,888.71	-----	-----	125,888.71

1	1929 June 26	Mortgage Bank of Chile...	Guaranteed sinking fund 6 per cent gold bonds of 1929.	May 1, 1962	20,000,000	6,000,000	-----	-----	4 24,288.91	-----	-----	4 24,288.91
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RAILROAD BONDS

1	1927 Jan. 26	Gulf Mobile & Northern R.R. Co.	First mortgage 5-percent gold bonds, series C.	Oct. 1, 1950	\$3,000,000	\$3,000,000	\$850,000	-----	\$30,000.00	\$5,169.55	-----	\$35,169.55
2	Jan. 31	Missouri Pacific R.R. Co...	First and refunding mortgage 5-percent gold bonds, series F.	Mar. 1, 1977	95,000,000	80,750,000	3,415,000	\$2,000,000	807,500.00	22,532.10	\$8,425.50	838,457.60
3	Feb. 9	Chicago & North Western Ry. Co.	First and refunding mortgage 4½-percent gold bonds.	May 1, 2037	20,572,000	16,457,600	-----	1,000,000	220,746.38	-----	7,500.00	228,246.38
4	Mar. 2	Texas & Pacific Ry. Co.....	General and refunding mortgage 5-percent gold bonds, series B.	Apr. 1, 1977	16,000,000	16,000,000	-----	750,000	163,261.99	-----	7,500.00	170,761.99
5	Mar. 7	Penna Ohio & Detroit R.R. Co.	First and refunding mortgage 4½-percent gold bonds, series A.	-----do-----	22,000,000	18,500,000	3,050,000	4,000,000	189,375.00	9,425.52	30,000.00	228,800.52
6	Mar. 10	Northern Central Ry. Co..	General and refunding mortgage 4½-percent gold bonds, series A.	Mar. 1, 1974	5,231,000	4,231,000	-----	2,750,000	41,081.28	-----	20,625.00	61,706.28
7	Apr. 26	Illinois Central R.R. Co. and Chicago, St. Louis & New Orleans R.R. Co.	Joint first refunding mortgage 4½ percent gold bonds, series C.	Dec. 1, 1963	17,350,000	15,050,000	2,050,000	2,974,000	153,375.00	14,933.75	11,455.44	179,764.19
8	May 19	Union Pacific R.R. Co.....	40-year 4½-percent gold bonds.	July 1, 1967	26,835,000	26,835,000	2,660,000	256,000	268,350.00	17,011.17	1,721.25	287,082.42
9	June 3	Southern Pacific Co., Oregon Lines.	First-mortgage 4½-percent series A bond.	Mar. 1, 1977	20,000,000	18,250,000	4,525,000	5,055,000	184,687.50	27,913.54	26,325.50	238,926.54
10	June -	Western Maryland Ry. Co.	First and refunding mortgage 5½-percent gold bonds, series A.	July 1, 1977	12,000,000	4,800,000	1,265,000	-----	48,000.00	6,691.05	-----	54,691.05
11	Dec. 1	Missouri, Kansas & Texas R.R.	Prior lien mortgage 4½-percent gold bonds, series D.	Jan. 1, 1978	13,600,000	3,740,000	-----	2,125,000	49,980.80	-----	48,467.01	98,447.81
12	Dec. 22	International Great Northern R.R. Co.	First-mortgage 5-percent gold bonds, series C.	July 1, 1956	5,500,000	5,200,000	-----	1,865,000	56,978.61	-----	13,987.50	70,966.11
13	...do....	New Orleans Texas & Mexico Ry. Co.	First-mortgage 4½-percent gold bonds, series D.	Aug. 1, 1956	5,900,000	4,220,000	-----	100,000	44,780.43	-----	875.00	45,655.43
14	...do....	Texarkana Union Station...	5-percent trust certificates, series A.	Dec. 1, 1957	1,500,000	1,500,000	-----	-----	21,000.00	-----	-----	21,000.00
Total.....					264,488,000	218,533,600	17,815,000	22,875,000	2,279,116.99	103,676.68	176,882.20	2,559,675.87

¹ Mar. 1, 1932 to Mar. 1, 1946.

⁴ Loss.

Participations of over \$250,000 which Kuhn, Loeb & Co. originated and managed—Continued

1386

STOCK EXCHANGE PRACTICES

No.	Date of issue	Name of issue	Description of issue	Due date	Amount of issue	Amount of participation			Net profit			Total profit
						Original group	Inter-mediate group	Selling group	Original group	Inter-mediate group	Selling group	
	1928											
1	Jan. 30	Southern Pacific Co.....	40-year 4½-percent gold bonds.	Mar. 1, 1968	\$29,400,000	\$26,800,000	\$1,675,000	-----	\$271,250.00	\$9,804.19	-----	\$281,054.19
2	Mar. 2	Denver & Rio Grande Western R.R. Co.	Refunding and improvement mortgage 5-percent gold bonds B.	Apr. 1, 1978	12,000,000	9,000,000	-----	-----	91,303.56	-----	-----	91,303.56
3	Mar. 21	Wabash Ry. Co.....	Refunding and general mortgage 4½-percent gold bonds C.	-----do-----	17,867,000	17,867,000	-----	\$1,800,000	199,767.23	-----	\$18,000.00	217,767.23
4	Apr. 25	Chicago, Milwaukee & St. Paul Ry. Co.	General mortgage 4½ percent gold bonds series E.	May 1, 1989	24,000,000	12,000,000	3,800,000	2,500,000	120,000.00	13,252.06	18,750.00	152,002.06
5	May 2	Union Pacific R.R. Co.....	40-year 4-percent gold bonds.	June 1, 1968	20,000,000	20,000,000	-----	-----	175,685.80	-----	-----	175,685.80
6	July 25	Southern Pacific Co.....	4½-percent equipment trust certificates series K.	(?)	4,815,000	4,365,000	-----	-----	12,037.50	-----	-----	12,037.50
7	Oct. 4	Missouri Pacific R.R. Co..	First and refunding mortgage 5-percent gold bonds G.	Nov. 1, 1978	25,000,000	21,250,000	-----	850,000	193,934.17	-----	10,625.00	204,559.17
8	Nov. 7	Pennsylvania Co.....	35-year 4¾ secured gold bonds.	Nov. 1, 1963	50,000,000	45,500,000	4,950,000	6,615,000	461,468.75	33,576.21	66,031.04	561,076.00
		Total.....			133,082,000	156,782,000	10,225,000	11,765,000	1,525,447.01	56,632.46	113,406.04	1,695,485.51
	1929											
1	Jan. 8	Chicago & North Western Ry. Co.	General mortgage gold 4½ percent bonds.	Nov. 1, 1987	3,577,000	3,506,000	-----	-----	28,616.00	-----	-----	28,616.00
2	Mar. 5	Texas & Pacific Ry. Co....	General refunding mortgage 5 percent gold bonds C.	Apr. 1, 1979	20,000,000	15,000,000	-----	500,000	190,295.92	-----	7,500.00	197,795.92
3	Mar. 11	Southern Pacific Co.....	40-year 4½-percent gold bonds.	May 1, 1969	65,166,000	60,166,000	1,611,000	-----	607,910.00	23,616.19	-----	631,526.19
4	Mar. 14	Missouri Pacific R.R. Co..	20-year 5½-percent convertible gold bonds A.	May 1, 1949	46,392,000	39,433,000	417,000	-----	403,030.50	6,653.42	-----	409,683.92
5	May 2	Central of Georgia Ry. Co..	Refunding and general mortgage 5-percent gold bonds, C.	Apr. 1, 1959	10,000,000	8,500,000	-----	500,000	90,815.93	-----	6,250.00	97,065.93
46	June 7	Chicago & Northwestern Ry. Co.	4½-percent equipment trust certificates, series Q.	(3)	3,971,000	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----

7	Oct. 10	do	20-year 4½-percent convertible gold bonds, series A.	Nov. 1, 1949	72,335,000	57,868,000	6,025,000		578,680.00	38,559.86		617,239.86
		Total			221,441,000	184,473,000	8,053,000	1,000,000	1,899,348.35	68,829.47	13,750.00	1,981,927.82
	1930											
1	Jan. 23	Baltimore & Ohio R.R. Co.	30-year 4½ percent convertible gold bonds.	Feb. 1, 1960	63,031,000	25,212,400	3,736,000		252,124.00	56,723.04		308,847.04
2	Feb. 19	Chicago & Eastern Ry. Co.	2-year 5-percent gold notes.	Mar. 1, 1932	2,500,000	2,500,000			18,550.00			18,550.00
3	Mar. 12	Pennsylvania R.R. Co.	40-year 4½-percent gold debenture bonds.	Apr. 1, 1970	60,000,000	55,000,000	4,000,000	4,405,000	556,250.00	14,955.94	30,937.50	602,143.44
4	Mar. 13	Missouri Pacific R.R. Co.	First and refunding mortgage 5-percent gold bonds, H.	Apr. 1, 1980	25,000,000	17,250,000		2,845,000	193,286.88		28,450.00	221,736.88
5	Mar. 14	Wabash Ry. Co.	Refunding and general mortgage 5-percent gold bonds, D.	do	15,000,000	15,000,000		1,975,000	164,172.24		19,750.00	183,922.24
6	Mar. 20	Chicgo, Milwaukee & St. Paul Ry. Co.	General mortgage 4¾-percent gold bonds, F.	May 1, 1989	15,000,000	7,500,000		3,271,000	74,492.60		32,710.00	107,202.60
7	Apr. 15	Southern Pacific Co., Oregon lines.	First mortgage 4½-percent bonds, A.	Mar. 1, 1977	41,294,000	37,794,000	444,000		382,315.00	1,526.21		383,841.21
8	do	Chicago & North Western Ry. Co.	General mortgage gold 4¾ percent bonds.	Nov. 1, 1987	5,031,000	4,025,000		3,125,000	55,315.77		23,437.50	78,753.27
9	Apr. 22	Delaware Hudson Co.	First and refunding mortgage 4-percent gold bonds.	May 1, 1943	10,000,000	8,000,000		500,000	85,651.22		5,000.00	90,651.22
10	Apr. 23	Chicago & Western Indiana R.R. Co.	Consolidated mortgage 4-percent gold bonds.	1952	917,000	917,000			4,585.00			4,585.00
11	May 27	Vioksburg, Shreveport & Pacific Ry. Co.	Refunding and improvement 5 percent bonds B.	Nov. 1, 1973	1,845,000	1,845,000			27,675.00			27,675.00
12	June 9	Gulf, Mobile & Northern R.R. Co.	First mortgage 5-percent gold bonds, C.	Oct. 1, 1950	3,000,000	3,000,000			31,446.10			31,446.10
13	Sept. 9	Chicago & North Western Ry. Co.	First and refunding mortgage 4½-percent gold bonds, C.	May 1, 2037	12,000,000	9,600,000		650,000	92,808.00		3,750	96,558.00
14	Sept. 16	Pittsburgh, Cincinnati, Chicago & St. Louis R.R. Co.	General mortgage 4½-percent gold bonds, C.	July 1, 1977	23,735,000	21,735,000		2,555,000	240,591.98		30,127.50	270,719.48
15	do	Cleveland & Pittsburgh R.R. Co.	General and refunding mortgage 4½-percent gold bonds, A.	Feb. 1, 1977	7,182,000	6,582,000		3,507,000	74,914.14		38,723.75	113,637.89
16	Dec. 5	Chicago Heights Terminal Transfer R.R. Co.	First mortgage 6-percent gold bonds, A.	Jan. 1, 1951	562,000	562,000			8,835.00			8,835.00
		Total			286,097,000	216,522,400	8,180,000	22,683,000	2,263,012.93	73,205.19	212,886.25	2,549,104.37

² Due date Aug. 1, 1929-43.

³ Due date Oct. 1, 1930-40.

⁴ Resold at cost price, no profit shown.

⁶ Applied against cost of bonds taken up from syndicate.

Participation of over \$250,000 which Kuhn, Loeb & Co. originated and managed—Continued

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No.	Date of issue	Name of issue	Description of issue	Due date	Amount of issue	Amount of participation			Net profit			Total profit
						Original group	Inter-mediate group	Selling group	Original group	Inter-mediate group	Selling group	
1	1931 Jan. 22	Philadelphia, Baltimore & Washington R.R. Co.	General mortgage 4½ percent gold bonds, series C.	July 1, 1977	\$11,301,000	\$16,284,000	{	\$3,030,000	\$160,325.49	{	\$18,937.50	\$180,356.74
2	---do---	Pennsylvania, Ohio & Detroit R.R. Co.	First and refunding mortgage 4½ percent gold bonds, series A.	Apr. 1, 1977	6,483,000							
3	---do---	United New Jersey R.R. & Canal Co.	General (now first) 4½ percent gold bonds.	Sept. 1, 1979	6,020,000	5,520,000	-----	5,120,000	67,577.63	-----	38,400.00	105,977.63
4	---do---	Pittsburgh, Youngstown, Ashtabula Ry. Co.	First general mortgage 4½ percent gold bonds, series D.	June 1, 1977	1,485,000	1,485,000	-----	-----	25,655.10	-----	-----	25,655.10
5	---do---	The Connecting Ry. Co.	First mortgage 4½ percent gold bonds.	Mar. 15, 1951	2,032,000	2,032,000	-----	-----	35,560.00	-----	-----	35,560.00
6	Feb. 2	Baltimore & Ohio R.R. Co.	4 percent gold notes	Aug. 10, 1932	35,000,000	14,000,000	-----	-----	48,207.65	-----	-----	48,207.65
7	Mar. 9	Pennsylvania R.R. Co.	General mortgage 4½ percent gold bonds D.	Apr. 1, 1981	50,000,000	46,000,000	\$5,175,000	4,140,000	465,000.00	\$18,908.49	34,470.00	518,378.49
8	Mar. 25	Southern Pacific Co.	50-year 4¼ percent gold bonds.	May 1, 1981	50,000,000	46,000,000	5,920,000	4,110,000	465,000.00	12,220.00	30,287.50	507,507.50
9	May 5	Illinois Central R.R. Co.	3-year 4½ percent gold notes.	June 1, 1934	20,000,000	17,500,000	-----	-----	86,541.71	-----	-----	86,541.71
Total					182,321,000	148,821,000	11,095,000	16,575,000	1,353,867.58	31,128.49	123,188.75	1,508,184.82

DOMESTIC STOCKS

1	1928 Dec. 11	United States Rubber Co.	Common stock	-----	1 728,412	1 682,730	1 51,512	-----	604,581.96	105,937.77	-----	710,519.73
2	Dec. 21	Mid Continent Petroleum Corporation.	do	-----	1 447,912	1 223,956	1 25,606	-----	223,956.00	38,579.81	-----	262,535.81
3	Dec. 27	Westinghouse Electric & Manufacturing Co.	do	-----	1 296,252	1 197,502	1 24,502	-----	197,501.33	43,866.71	-----	241,368.04
					1 1,472,576	1 1,004,188	1 101,620	-----	1,026,039.29	188,384.29	-----	1,214,423.58
1	1929 Oct. 8	The Pennroad Corporation.	Voting trust certificates for common stock.	-----	1 3,025,000	1 3,025,000	1 57,000	-----	1,512,812.50	69,924.08	-----	1,582,736.58

STOCK EXCHANGE PRACTICES

RAILROAD STOCK

1	1927 June 9	Baltimore & Ohio R.R.....	Common stock.....		¹ 632,425	¹ 252,970	¹ 48,870		252,970.00	69,684.90		322,654.90
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FOREIGN STOCK

1	1928 Oct. 26	North German Lloyd.....	American shares for com- mon stock.		¹ 175,000	¹ 70,000			140,167.70			140,167.70
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¹ Shares.

Revised schedule of railroad stocks and bonds and domestic stocks after deducting underwriting for the period 1927-31

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STOCK EXCHANGE PRACTICES

Number of issues	Classification	Year	Amount of issue	Amount of participation			Net profits			Total net profit
				Original group	Intermediate group	Selling group	Original group	Intermediate group	Selling group	
1	Railroad stock	1927	1 632,425	1 252,970	1 48,870		252,970.00	69,684.90		322,654.90
1	Deduct		1 632,425	1 252,970	1 48,870		252,970.00	69,684.90		322,654.90
54	Railroad bonds	1927-31	1,137,429,000	925,132,000	55,368,000	\$74,898,000	9,320,792.86	333,472.29	\$640,113.24	10,294,378.39
3	Deduct	1929	183,893,000	157,467,000	8,053,000		1,589,620.50	68,829.47		1,658,449.97
1	Do	1930	63,031,000	25,212,400	3,736,000		252,124.00	56,723.04		308,847.04
4	Total deductions, 1929-30		246,924,000	182,679,400	11,789,000		1,841,744.50	125,552.51		1,967,297.01
50			890,505,000	742,452,600	43,579,000	74,898,000	7,479,048.36	207,919.78	676,113.24	8,327,081.38
6	Total stocks		1 5,305,001	1 4,352,158	1 207,490		2,931,989.49	327,993.27		3,259,982.76
1	Deduct	1927	1 632,425	1 252,970	1 48,870		252,970.00	69,684.90		322,654.90
1	do	1929	1 3,025,000	1 3,025,000	1 57,000		1,512,812.50	69,924.08		1,582,736.58
2			1 3,657,425	1 3,277,970	1 105,870		1,765,782.50	139,608.98		1,905,391.48
4			1 1,647,576	1 1,074,188	1 101,620		1,166,206.99	188,384.29		1,354,591.28
7	Railroad bonds	1929	221,441,000	184,473,000	8,053,000	1,000,000	1,899,348.35	68,829.47	13,750.00	1,981,927.82
1	Deduct:									
1	Southern Pacific 4½ percent, 1969		65,166,000	60,166,000	1,611,000		607,910.00	23,616.19		631,526.19
1	Missouri Pacific 5½ percent, 1949		46,392,000	39,453,000	417,000		403,030.50	6,653.42		409,683.92
1	Chicago & North Western 4¾ percent, 1949		72,335,000	57,868,000	6,025,000		578,680.00	38,559.86		617,239.86
3			183,893,000	157,467,000	8,053,000		1,589,620.50	68,829.47		1,658,449.97
4			37,548,000	27,006,000		1,000,000	309,727.85		13,750.00	323,477.85
1	Domestic stock	1929	1 3,025,000	1 3,025,000	1 57,000		1,512,812.50	69,924.08		1,582,736.58
1	Deduct		1 3,025,000	1 3,025,000	1 57,000		1,512,812.50	69,924.08		1,582,736.58

1 Shares.

SUMMARY—BONDS

73	Total bonds.....		\$1,638,502,000	\$1,200,492,000	\$72,493,000	\$96,131,000	\$12,143,912.33	\$420,618.76	\$812,699.49	\$13,377,230.58
3	Deduct.....	1929	183,893,000	187,467,000	8,053,000	-----	1,589,620.50	68,829.47	-----	1,658,449.97
1	Do.....	1930	63,031,000	25,212,400	3,736,000	-----	252,124.00	56,723.04	-----	308,847.04
4	Total deductions.....		246,924,000	182,679,400	11,789,000	-----	1,841,744.50	125,552.51	-----	1,967,297.01
69	-----		1,491,578,000	1,017,812,600	60,704,000	96,131,000	10,302,167.83	295,066.25	812,699.49	11,409,933.57
16	Railroad bonds.....	1930	286,097,000	216,522,400	8,180,000	22,683,000	2,263,012.93	73,205.19	212,886.25	2,549,104.37
1	Deduct: Baltimore & Ohio 4½ percent, 1960.	-----	63,031,000	25,212,400	3,736,000	-----	252,124.00	56,723.04	-----	308,847.04
15	-----		223,066,000	191,310,000	4,444,000	22,683,000	2,010,888.93	16,482.15	212,886.25	2,240,257.33

EXHIBIT No. 34

SUPPLEMENTARY NOTATIONS IN CONNECTION WITH QUESTION 10

1. *Patino Mines and Enterprises, capital stock.*—We were allotted 7,500 shares at \$25 per share, for which we paid \$187,500 against which we credited the commission of \$13,125, making a net cost for the 7,500 shares of \$174,375. The shares were subsequently sold at a net profit of \$1,755.40.
2. *Auto-Strop Safety Razor, Inc., convertible class A stock.*—We were allotted 3,000 shares which were sold to clients at cost.
3. *Youngstown Sheet & Tube Co. 5½ per cent preferred stock.*—We were allotted 1,000 shares which were sold to clients at cost.
4. *Shell Union Oil Corporation common stock.*—We took up 241 shares against payment of \$2,410. The shares were subsequently sold and a net profit of \$4,172.61 realized. We also received from the syndicate managers additional profit of \$70.46.
5. *United Dry Docks, Inc., common stock.*—We were allotted 10,000 shares at a cost of \$220,000, against which were credited profit and commission received, totalling \$26,465. The shares are still held.
6. *Tri Continental Corporation preferred and common stock.*—We were allotted 2,000 shares preferred stock at a cost of \$208,000, against which we credited banking and selling group commissions of \$5,500. The shares were subsequently sold at a loss of \$4,965.36. We were also allotted 3,000 shares common stock at a cost of \$81,000, against which we credited banking and selling commissions totalling \$4,500. These shares were subsequently sold and a net profit of \$19,305 realized.
7. *Allegheny Corporation 5½ percent preferred stock series A.*—We were allotted 1,000 shares at a cost of \$100,000, against which we credited banking and selling commissions totaling \$3,037.75. The shares were subsequently sold and a net profit of \$4,097.75 realized.
8. *Shell Union Oil Co., 5½ percent preferred stock.*—We were allotted 11,000 shares of which 10,300 were sold to clients at cost, and the remaining 700 shares were subsequently resold and a profit of \$4,163.25 realized.
9. *Bethlehem Steel Corporation common stock underwriting.*—We took up 6,967 shares at a cost of \$766,370, against which we credited Underwriting Profit of \$21,895.29. We subsequently purchased additional 7,300 shares in the market and eventually sold the entire amount of stock at a net loss of \$35,848.68.
10. *American Cyanamid Co. common stock underwriting.*—We took up 3,631 shares against payment of \$108,930, against which we credited Syndicate Profit of \$8,587.05. The shares were subsequently sold and a net profit of \$5,637.56 realized.
11. *Northwest Bancorporation common stock underwriting.*—We took up 4,850 shares against payment of \$361,325 against which we credited \$2,820.23 Commissions Received; 2,850 shares were subsequently sold at a loss of \$128,000 and the balance was still held December 31, 1931.
12. *Monsanto Chemical Works common stock underwriting.*—We took up 2,250 shares against payment of \$152,500, against which we credited \$2,943.23 commissions received. Part of these shares have been sold and part are still held.
13. *Allegheny Corporation 5½ percent preferred stock.*—We were allotted 1,000 shares, for which we paid \$98,500. We received Banking Group profit and selling commission, totaling \$2,906.73, which were credited against the cost of the shares. The shares were still held on December 31, 1931.
14. *American Smelting & Refining 6 percent second preferred stock.*—We took up 23,000 shares, for which we paid \$2,369,042.82. Against this we credited profits and commission received, totaling \$77,012.92, making a net cost of \$2,292,029.90. The shares were subsequently sold and a net profit of \$2,246.73 realized.
15. *Hotel Waldorf Astoria common stock.*—We took up 8,500 shares at a net cost of \$395,250. The shares were still held on December 31, 1931.

List of all stock pools, joint accounts and/or syndicates in which Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or any of its agencies or representatives participated, with the name of security involved, etc.

Name	Date	Amount offered	Public offering price	Managers	Our participation	Gross commission	Received	Profit, compensation, or commission received
Patino Mines & Enterprises Consolidated, Inc. (Capital stock selling group).	Dec. 21, 1926	200,000 shares-----	<i>Per share</i> \$25.00	Lehman Bros-----	Selling group----- We took up 7,500 shares.	<i>Per share</i> \$2.00	Feb. 3, 1927	\$13,125.
Stanley Co. of America Capital Stock Syndicate.	Feb. 28, 1927	125,000 shares-----	65.00	E. B. Smith & Co and associates.	Underwriting----- Syndicate 2,000 shares.	1.50	Apr. 29, 1927	2,836.30.
Auto-Strop Safety Razor Inc. Convertible class A stock.	July 12, 1927	87,500 shares-----	43.00	A. G. Becker & Co-----	Special group 2,000 shares-- Took up in selling group 3,000 shares.	.50 2.00	Sept. 13, 1927 do-----	1,000. 5,250.
Fox Film Corporation class A common stock underwriting syndicate.	Jan. 26, 1928	125,000 shares-----	75.00	Hayden, Stone & Co-----	Underwriting syndicate 5,000 shares.	2.00	Mar. 6, 1928	10,000.
Youngtown Sheet & Tube Co. series A 5½ percent preferred selling group.	June 18, 1928	\$15,000,000-----	100.00	Cleveland Trust Co-----	Took up in selling group 1,000 shares.	1.00	Sept. 20, 1928	937.50.
Fox Film Corporation class A common stock underwriting syndicate.	Sept. 19, 1928	153,444 shares-----	85.00	Hayden, Stone & Co-----	Underwriting syndicate 10,000 shares.	3.00	Oct. 29, 1928	30,000.
Checker Cab Manufacturing Corporation common stock underwriting syndicate.	Nov. 8, 1928	125,000 shares-----	80.00	J. A. Sisto & Co-----	Underwriting syndicate 10,000 shares.	1.50	Dec. 17, 1928	15,159.49.
Shell Union Oil Corporation common stock underwriting.	Nov. 9, 1928	3,000,000 shares----	10.00	Lee, Higginson & Co-----	Underwriting syndicate \$2,000 shares. Syndicate takes unsubscribed shares at \$10 per share.	-----	Feb. 2, 1929 July 20, 1929	Took up 241 shares at \$10 per share. \$70.46 additional profit.
Republic Iron & Steel Co. common stock underwriting.	Dec. 11, 1928	-----	65.00	Otis & Co-----	Our interest 10 percent----	1.50	Jan. 22, 1929	\$20,149.89.
Hahn Department Stores preferred and common stock syndicate.	Dec. 13, 1928	{ \$22,700,000 preferred 454,000 shares common.	{ 103.00 38.00	Lehman Bros. and Prince & Whitely.	{ Preferred selling group---- Common selling group 500. Underwriting Syndicate 500 shares.	2.00 1.50 .50	{ Feb. 16, 1929 Feb. 16, 1929	750. 250.
United Dry Docks common stock	Jan. 14, 1929	450,000 shares-----	22.00	{ Hayden, Stone & Co., Minsch, Monell & Co., and Fynchon & Co.	{ Banking syndicate 20,000-- Selling group 10,000 shares.	.50 1.25	May -- 1929 Apr. 22, 1929	14,590. 11,875.

List of all stock pools, joint accounts and/or syndicates in which Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or any of its agencies or representatives participated, with the name of security involved, etc.—Continued

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STOCK EXCHANGE PRACTICES

Name	Date	Amount offered	Public offering price	Managers	Our participation	Gross commission	Received	Profit, compensation, or commission received
			<i>Per share</i>			<i>Per share</i>		
Tri Continental Corporation 6 percent preferred and common stock.	Jan. 18, 1929	250,000 shares preferred. 1,000,000 shares common.	\$104.00 27.00	J. & W. Seligman & Co.	Preferred stock banking group 2,000 shares.	\$0.50	Feb. 6, 1929	\$1,000.
					Preferred selling group 2,000 shares.	2.50	Feb. 6, 1929	4,500.
					Common stock special group 3,000 shares.	.25	Feb. 6, 1929	750.
					Common stock banking group 3,000 shares.	.25	Feb. 6, 1929	750.
Gulf States Steel Co. common stock underwriting syndicate.	Jan. 22, 1929	72,500 shares	60.00	Hallgarten & Co.	Common stock selling group 3,000 shares.	1.00	Feb. 6, 1929	3,000.
					Participation 10,000 shares	2.25	Apr. 4, 1929	22,848.
Petroleum Corporation of America capital stock underwriting syndicate and option warrants	Jan. 21, 1929	3,250,000 shares	34.00	Blair & Co.	Purchase group 1 percent	.625	July 27, 1929	19,243.53.
					Banking group 3,750 shares	.625		Loss charged to purchase group.
					Selling group	1.75		\$2,396.67 proceeds warrants.
Allegheny Corporation cumulative 5½ percent preferred stock series A.	Jan. 31, 1929	\$25,000,000	100.00	Guaranty Co. of New York and associates.	Interest in purchase group		Nov. 9, 1931	Received 5,971 optional warrants.
					Carried interest in warrants.		Nov. 23, 1932	
Atlantic Refining Co. common stock underwriting syndicate.	Mar. 16, 1929	666,667 shares	40.00	Guaranty Co. of New York.	Banking group 2,500 shares.	.75	Apr. 29, 1929	\$1,600.25.
					Selling group 1,000 shares	1.50	Mar. 8, 1929	1,437.50.
Bethlehem Steel Corporation common stock underwriting syndicate.	Apr. 26, 1929	600,000 shares	85.00	Guaranty Co. and associates.	Syndicate 80,000 shares	.25	May 17, 1929	24,512.69.
					Syndicate 10,000 shares	1.00	July 17, 1929	12,736.33.
Allegheny Corporation 5½ percent preferred stock, with warrants.	May 13, 1929	\$25,000,000	100.00	do.	Selling group 2,000 shares	1.50		
					Took up 2,000 shares at 100. Resold to them at 99		Aug. 2, 1929	750.000.
Shell Union Oil Corporation 5½ percent preferred.	June 24, 1929	\$40,000,000	98.00	Lee Higginson & Co.	Original business \$9,200,000	.50	Nov. 13, 1929	46,000.00.
					Banking group \$3,375,000	1.00	do.	14,029.28.
Commercial Credit Co. \$3 class A convertible stock.	July 9, 1929	300,000 shares	50.00	Kidder Peabody & Co. and associates.	Selling group	2.00	Aug. 28, 1929	22,000.00.
					We took up 11,000 shares. Original business 5 percent.		Nov. 19, 1929	25,070.05.
Tri Continental Allied Co. preferred and common.	Aug. 17, 1929	500,000 preferred 750,000 common	1101.50	J. & W. Seligman & Co.		<i>Per unit</i>		
					Special group, 500 units	\$0.50	Oct. 2, 1929	250.
					Banking group, 500 units	.50	do.	250.
					Selling group, 500 units	2.50	do.	1,250.

Chemical National Associates, Inc., common stock.	Aug. 30, 1929	1,500,000 shares.....	27.00	Chemical National Co., Inc.	Our interest, 20 percent, with interest in option warrants.		Dec. 31, 1929	566,409.00; rec'd. \$30,000 option warrants.
Chicago Pneumatic Tool Co. common stock.	} Sept. 4, 1929	50,000 shares.....	43.00	J. A. Sisto and A. G. Becker & Co.	{ Original business, 33 1/2 percent. Selling group.....		Sept. 16, 1929	216,666.67.
							Dec. 28, 1929	18,532.50.
Northwest Bancorporation common-stock underwriting syndicate.	July 22, 1929	90,000 shares.....	62.00	A. G. Becker & Co.....	Participation, 3,000 shares.	<i>Per share</i> \$1	Sept. 5, 1929	3,000.
Bethlehem Steel Corporation common-stock underwriting syndicate.	Sept. 11, 1929	800,000 shares.....	110.00	Guaranty Co. and associates.	Participation, 14,000 shares	1	Dec. 12, 1929	21,895.29.
American Cyanamid Co. "B" common underwriting syndicate.	Oct. 1, 1929	823,984 shares.....	30.00	Guaranty Co.....	Participation, 20,000 shares	.50	Dec. 9, 1929	8,587.05.
Northwest Bancorporation common-stock underwriting syndicate.	} Oct. 10, 1929	175,000 shares.....	72.50	A. G. Becker & Co.....	{ Participation, 5,000 shares. Plus on shares taken up.....	1 1	} Mar. 13, 1930	2,820.23.
Firestone Tire & Rubber Co. 6 percent preferred stock.	} Oct. 16, 1929	\$80,000,000.....	99.00	Otis & Co. and associates..	{ Special banking group, \$1,000,000. Banking group, \$1,000,000. Participation, 2,000,000.....	<i>Per share</i> \$1.00 3.00	Dec. 18, 1929	5,000.00.
							Dec. 19, 1929	8,450.00.
Manhattan Co. stock underwriting.	Nov. 19, 1929	185,366 shares.....	120.00	W. A. Harriman & Co. and Field, Gore & Co.			Dec. 6, 1929	49,430.93.
Allegheny Coporation 5 1/2 percent preferred stock.	} Mar. 10, 1930	\$12,500,000.....	98.50	{ Guaranty Co. and associates. do.....	{ Banking group, 2,500 shares Selling group, 1,000 shares. Purchase group, 22 percent. Banking group, 26,782 shares. Selling group, 23,000 shares. Participation, 50,000 shares.	.75 1.50 .75 .75 1.50 1.00	June 28, 1930	1,531.73.
							June 13, 1930	1,375.00.
American Smelting & Refining Co. 6 percent second preferred stock.	} May 21, 1930	175,000 shares.....	103.00	do.....			Oct. 16, 1930	28,875.00.
							Oct. 15, 1930	13,687.92.
Warner Bros. Pictures, Inc., common stock underwriting syndicate.	Aug. 14, 1930	755,000 shares.....	20.00	Goldman Sachs & Co. and Hayden Stone & Co.			Sept. 2, 1930	34,500.00.
Hotel Waldorf-Astoria common stock.	} Aug. 29, 1929	149,000 shares.....	50.00	{ Halgarten & Co., Hayden, Stone & Co., and Kissel, Kinnicutt & Co. J. A. Sisto & Co. and A. G. Becker & Co.	{ Purchase group, 8,500 shares. Selling group..... Original group, one third. Selling group.....	1.00 2.50 2.50 2.50	Sept. 29, 1930	52,121.55.
							Oct. 28, 1929	{ Took up 8,500 shares at \$46.50 per share.
Chicago Pneumatic Tool Co. preferred stock.	Dec. 1928	100,000 shares.....	55.00	J. A. Sisto & Co. and A. G. Becker & Co.			July 8, 1929	\$17,116.61.

For units of 1 preferred and 1 1/2 common.

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 35, JUNE 30, 1933

Question 11: Issues of Governments, States, municipalities, and corporations in connection with which we have acted as fiscal or paying agents in the period January 1, 1927, to December 31, 1931.

NAME AND ISSUE	SERVICES RENDERED
Government of the Argentine Nation: \$40,000,000 external sinking fund 6-percent gold bonds of 1923 series A, due 1957.	Depository for interest and redemption funds pending transfer to paying agent. ¹
Czechoslovak Republic: \$14,000,000 secured external sinking fund gold loan of 1922, due 1951.	Payment of interest; payment of principal of called bonds. ²
\$9,250,000 secured external sinking fund gold loan, series B, due 1952.	Do.
Kingdom of the Netherlands: \$40,000,000 30-year 6-percent external sinking fund gold bonds.	Payment of interest and principal. ³
Department of the Seine (France): \$25,000,000 20-year 7-percent external gold loan bonds of 1922.	Payment of interest and principal.
Cities of Bordeaux, Lyons, and Marseilles (France): \$15,000,000 (each) municipal external loan of 1919 15-year 6-percent gold bonds.	Payment of interest.
City of Oslo (Norway): \$2,000,000 municipal external loan of 1924 30-year 6-percent sinking fund gold bonds.	Payment of interest; payment of principal of bonds called for sinking fund; purchase of bonds for sinking fund.
\$8,000,000 municipal external loan of 1925 30-year 6-percent sinking fund gold bonds.	Do.
\$4,000,000 municipal external loan of 1926 20-year 5½-percent sinking fund gold bonds.	Payment of interest and principal; payment of principal of bonds called for sinking fund; purchase of bonds for sinking fund.
City of Greater Prague (Czechoslovakia): \$7,500,000 7½-percent mortgage loan of 1922, due 1952.	Payment of interest; payment of principal of bonds called for sinking fund; purchase of bonds for sinking fund.
Mortgage Bank of Chile (Caja de Crédito Hipotecario): Guaranteed sinking fund gold bonds.) \$20,000,000 6½-percent due 1957.) \$20,000,000 6¼-percent of 1926, due 1961.) \$20,000,000 6-percent of 1928, due 1961.) \$20,000,000 6-percent of 1929, due 1962.) \$10,000,000 guaranteed 5-year 6-percent agricultural gold notes of 1926.	Payment of interest; payment of principal of bonds called for sinking fund. ⁴
North German Lloyd (Bremen): \$20,000,000 20-year 6-percent sinking fund gold bonds, due 1947.	Payment of interest. ⁴
Paris-Lyons-Mediterranean Railroad Company: \$40,000,000 6-percent external sinking fund gold bonds, due 1958.	Payment of interest; receipt of bonds for sinking fund. ⁴
	Payment of interest and principal; payment of principal of bonds called for sinking fund; purchase of bonds for sinking fund. ⁵

¹ Jointly with Chase National Bank and Blair & Co.

² Jointly with Kidder, Peabody & Co. and National City Bank.

³ Jointly with National City Bank.

⁴ Jointly with Guaranty Trust Co. of New York.

⁵ Payment also made by National City Bank.

United Steel Works of Burbach-Eich-Dudelange (Arbed) (Luxemburg): \$10,000,000 25-year sinking fund 7-percent gold bonds, due 1951.	Paying agents for coupons and bonds called for sinking fund. ⁴
The Cincinnati Union Terminal Co.: \$12,000,000 first mortgage 4½ percent gold bonds, series A, due 2020.	Paying agents for coupons. ⁵
\$12,000,000 first mortgage 4½-percent gold bonds, series B, due 2020.	Do.
Mid-Continent Petroleum Corporation: \$12,500,000 first mortgage 15-year 6½ percent sinking fund gold bonds.	Purchase of bonds for sinking fund, as sinking fund agents.

⁴ Jointly with Guaranty Trust Co. of New York.

⁵ Jointly with J. P. Morgan & Co.

EXHIBIT No. 36

Question no. 12.—List of all bond or debenture issues, foreign or domestic, of which Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or any of its agencies was the syndicate manager and which issues have been or are now in default; and any issues floated prior to 1927 which were in default at any time during the period of 1927-31

Date of issue	Amount issued	Issue	Date of default	Remarks
Mar. 1911.....	\$26,175,000	Chicago, Milwaukee & Puget Sound Railway Co. 1st gold 4 percent due Jan. 1, 1949.	July 1, 1925	Chicago, Milwaukee & St. Paul Railway Co. entered receivership Mar. 18, 1925. Reorganization approved, Jan. 19, 1927. Receivership ended, Jan. 13, 1928, when Chicago, Milwaukee, St. Paul & Pacific Railroad took over properties of old railway company. New securities issued Feb. 1928.
June 1914, \$30,000,000.....	} 43,089,000	{ Chicago, Milwaukee & St. Paul Railway general and refunding 4½-percent "A" due Jan. 1, 2014.	Apr. 1, 1925	
Jan. 1917, \$25,000,000.....				
Jan. 1916.....				
June 3, 1909.....	24,000,000	National Railways of Mexico Prior Lien 4½-percent sinking fund gold bonds, due July 1, 1957.	July 1, 1914	
June 4, 1913.....	26,730,000	National Railways of Mexico 2-year 6-percent secured gold bonds due June 1, 1915.	Dec. 1, 1914	
June 25, 1925.....	20,000,000	Mortgage Bank of Chile guaranteed sinking fund 6½-percent gold bonds due June 30, 1957.	Dec. 31, 1931	
July 30, 1926.....	18,330,000	Mortgage Bank of Chile guaranteed sinking fund 6¾-percent gold bonds of 1926 due June 30, 1961.	Dec. 31, 1931	
Dec. 23, 1926.....	10,000,000	Mortgage Bank of Chile guaranteed 5-year 6-percent agricultural gold notes of 1926 due Dec. 31, 1931.	Dec. 31, 1931 ¹	
May 1, 1928.....	20,000,000	Mortgage Bank of Chile guaranteed sinking fund 6-percent gold bonds of 1928, due Apr. 30, 1961.	Dec. 31, 1931	
June 27, 1929.....	20,000,000	Mortgage Bank of Chile guaranteed sinking fund 6-percent gold bonds of 1929 due May 1, 1962.	Nov. 1, 1931	
Nov. 14, 1927.....	16,000,000	Paramount Famous Lasky Corporation 20-year 6-percent sinking fund gold bonds—Dec. 1, 1947.	-----	Coupons due June 1, 1933, attached. Bonds being traded in "and interest."
Aug. 4, 1930.....	15,000,000	Paramount Publix Corporation 20-year 5½-percent sinking fund gold bonds due Aug. 1, 1950.	Feb. 1, 1933	
Mar. 21, 1928.....	17,867,000	Wabash Railway Co. refunding and general mortgage 4½-percent gold bonds, series "C" due Apr. 1, 1978.	Apr. 1, 1932	There have been subsequent defaults on various other bonds of this company.
Mar. 15, 1930.....	15,000,000	Wabash Railway Co. refunding and general mortgage 5-percent gold bonds "D" due Apr. 1, 1980.	..do.....	Do.
May 2, 1929.....	10,000,000	Central of Georgia Ry. Co. refunding and general mortgage 5-percent gold bonds "C" due Apr. 1, 1959.	Apr. 1, 1933	Do.
Mar. 14, 1930.....	25,000,000	Missouri Pacific R. R. Co. first and refunding mortgage 5-percent gold bonds, series "H", due Apr. 1, 1980.	..do.....	Do.

¹ Principal and interest.

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 37, JUNE 30, 1933

Question no. 13: * * * Names of all issues on which a member or representative of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or any of its agencies acted as a member of a protective or reorganization committee during the period 1927 to 1931, inclusive:

Chicago, Milwaukee & St. Paul Railway Co.: 4 percent gold bonds of 1925; 4 percent 15-year European loan bonds of 1910; 4½ percent convertible gold bonds, due 1932; 25-year 4 percent gold bonds of 1909, due 1934; general and refunding mortgage gold bonds, series A and B, due 2014.

Chicago, Milwaukee & Puget Sound first mortgage 4 percent gold bonds, due 1949: Jerome J. Hanauer was a member of the protective committee; Kuhn, Loeb & Co. were comanagers of the reorganization of the above company.

United States of Mexico readjustment of debt: Mortimer L. Schiff, from 1927 until his death on June 4, 1931, was a member of the International Committee of Bankers on Mexico, which handled the above.

After Mr. Schiff's death, Sir William Wiseman became a member of the committee.

Central Leather Co.: Kuhn, Loeb & Co. were comanagers of the readjustment of the above company.

EXHIBIT No. 38

Question 15: Names of all issues in which Kuhn, Loeb & Co., or any of its agencies had any participation, of not less than \$250,000, which are now or have been at any time during the period of 1927-31 in default; including date of default, market value of securities as of Mar. 31, 1933, amount outstanding, and names and addresses of the secretaries of committees formed to protect the interests of investors or for reorganization purposes

Name of issue	Amount issued	Our participation	Date of default	Market value March 31, 1933	Amount outstanding	Date of issue	Names and addresses of protective committees' secretaries
Republic of Chile 6 percent External Loan Sinking Fund Gold Bonds: Due May 1, 1963.....	\$25,000,000	\$2,500,000	Nov. 1, 1931	5½-6¼	\$24,745,000	Apr. 25, 1930	The National City Co., Hallgarten & Co. and Kissel, Kinnicutt & Co. of New York City published a statement on Oct. 8, 1931, in which they stated that they are keeping in close touch with the Chilean situation but at that time saw no need for holders to deposit their bonds.
Due Mar. 1, 1962.....	10,000,000	1,000,000	Sept. 1, 1931	5½-6½	9,892,000	Mar. 12, 1929	
Republic of Chile 6 percent External Loan Sinking Fund Gold Bonds due Sept. 1, 1961.	16,000,000	1,600,000	do.....	5½	15,823,000	Aug. 8, 1928	Do.
Republic of Chile Railway Refunding Sinking Fund 6 percent Gold External Bonds due Jan. 1, 1961.	45,912,000	In distributing group \$1,000,000	Jan. 1, 1932	6	44,152,000	Jan. 23, 1928	Do.
Cigar Stores Realty Holdings, Inc. 20-year 5½ percent Sinking Fund Gold Debentures "A", due Jan. 1, 1949.	10,000,000		1,074,500	Jan. 1, 1933	34 bid	8,701,000	Jan. 3, 1929
Kingdom of the Serbs, Croats & Slovenes 7 percent Secured External Gold Bonds "B" due Nov. 1, 1962.	30,000,000	1,630,000	Nov. 1, 1932	14	30,000,000	Apr. 4, 1927	E. G. Burland, secretary, 44 Wall Street, New York City.
Hotel Waldorf Astoria Corporation First Mortgage Leasehold 7 percent Sinking Fund Gold Bonds due Sept. 1, 1954.	11,000,000	625,000	Sept. 1, 1932	Bonds, 5 Certificates, 3½ as of March 23, 1933.	11,000,000	Aug. 29, 1929	(According to the deposit agreement each of the following was authorized to accept deposit of bonds under plan: Hallgarten & Co., 44 Pine St., Hayden Stone & Co., 25 Broad St., G. H. Kinnicutt, 17 Wall Street, S. L. Fuller, 14 Wall Street, Hornblower & Weeks, 42 Broadway, Cassatt & Co., Commercial Trust Building, Philadelphia, Pa., Greenebaum Sons Investment Company, La Salle Street and Madison, Chicago, Ill.

EXHIBIT No 39.

SUPPLEMENTARY NOTATIONS IN CONNECTION WITH QUESTION 19

1. *Mid-Continent Petroleum*.—The 4,366 shares which were taken up against payment of \$155,842.08 were subsequently sold, realizing a profit of \$13,748.53.

2. *French Line Common Stock*.—We took up 964 shares against payment of \$58,804, against which was credited profits received \$55,610.85 making a net cost of 964 shares \$3,193.15. The shares were subsequently sold, and a net profit of \$30,860.64 realized.

3. *H. R. Mallinson Co., Inc.*—We took up 11,750 shares against payment of \$408,427; 1,750 shares were subsequently sold at a loss of \$40,037.50, and the balance of shares were still held on December 31, 1931.

4. *Mid-Continent Petroleum Corporation*.—We took up 18,539 shares against payment of \$665,202.74. The shares are still held.

5. *North German Lloyd American Shares*.—We took up 8,404 shares against payment of \$489,298.17. The shares were subsequently sold at a loss of \$187,142.66.

6. *Electric Boat Co.*—We took up 25,000 shares against payment of \$428,032.20. The shares were still held December 31, 1931.

7. *Chicago Pneumatic Tool Co., common stock*.—We took up 520 shares against payment of \$15,204.15. The shares were subsequently sold at a loss of \$2,239.95.

8. *Chicago, Milwaukee, St. Paul & Pacific Railroad Co., preferred stock*.—We took up 18,400 shares against payment of \$999,766.17. The shares were still held December 31, 1931.

9. *McCrorry Stores, common stock*.—We took up 25,000 shares against payment of \$1,000,000. The shares were still held December 31, 1931.

Question 19.—Details of all stock issues in which Kuhn, Loeb & Co. or any of its agencies participated or in which a trading account was maintained, etc.

Date and name	Managers	Maximum commitment	Our share	Our profit or loss	Remarks
Dec. 30, 1926. Mid Continent Petroleum common stock trading account.	Hallgarten & Co.-----	60,000 shares.	20,000 shares.-----	July 1, 1927.-----	} We took up 4,366 shares against payment of \$155,842.08.
Feb. 14, 1928. Wesco Corporation and/or Fox Film Corporation class A stock account.	Haystone Securities Corporation.	\$7,000,000.-----	\$1,000,000.-----	Sept. 10, 1928. Received \$174,481.41.-----	
Mar. 12, 1928. Compagnie Generale Transatlantique (French Line) common stock.	J. A. Sisto & Co. and Equitable Trust Co.	} 87,500 shares.	} 7½ percent original also second group. Original 36¼ percent.	June 27, 1928. Received \$22,500.-----	} Took up 964 shares for \$58,804.
May 22, 1928. Missouri, Kansas & Texas Ry. common stock.	} Ladenburg, Thalmann & Co. and National City Co.			} 287,616 shares.	
		Aug. 22, 1928. Received \$108,720.35.-----			
Sept. 10, 1928. Republic Iron & Steel Co., common stock trading account.	Otis & Co.-----	60,000 shares.	5,000 shares.-----	Aug. 16, 1928. Received \$63,772.37.-----	} Took up 11,750 shares for \$408,427.
Oct. 19, 1928. H. R. Mallinson Co., Inc., common stock joint account.	J. A. Sisto & Co.	30,000 shares.	50 percent.-----	Sept. 27, 1928. Received \$17,376.52.-----	
Oct. 30, 1928. United States Leather Co., class A stock joint account.	Bankers Co. of New York.		50 percent.-----	Oct. 19, 1929.-----	} Took up total of 18,539 shares, \$665,202.74.
Nov. 21, 1928. Liquid Carbonic Corporation, common stock trad. account.	W. E. Hutten & Co.	100,000 shs.	10 percent.-----	Feb. 13, 1929. Received \$8,504.68.-----	
Nov. 21, 1928. Mid Continent Petroleum Corporation, common stock trad. account.	Hallgarten & Co.	100,000 shs.	20,000 shs.-----	Dec. 13, 1928. Received \$40,914.54.-----	
Dec. 1928. Chicago Pneumatic Tool Co., common stock joint account.	J. A. Sisto & Co.		50 percent.-----	Nov. 22, 1929.-----	
Jan. 21, 1929. North German Lloyd (American shares) account.	Kuhn, Loeb & Co.	25,000 shs. ¹	40 percent.-----	Dec. 20, 1928. Received \$12,555.95.-----	} We took up 8,404 shares, \$489,298.17.
Feb. 21, 1929. American Sugar Refining Co., common stock joint account.	J. & W. Seligman Co.	3,000 shs.	50 percent.-----	June 11, 1930.-----	
Feb. 25, 1929. National Sugar Refining Co., common stock joint account.	Kuhn, Loeb & Co.	5,000 shs. ²	50 percent.-----	Oct. 16, 1929. Loss \$12,618.26.-----	
Mar. 14, 1929. Electric Boat Co., capital stock account.	J. A. Sisto & Co.	130,000 shs.	25,000 shs.-----	Oct. 16, 1929. Loss \$32,568.75.-----	} We took up 25,000 shares, \$428,032.20.
Oct. 18, 1928. Kansas City Southern Ry. Co., common stock account.	Ladenburg, Thalmann & Co.		25,000 shs.-----	Dec. 20, 1929.-----	
Sept. 5, 1929. Chicago Pneumatic Tool Co., common stock trading account.	A. G. Becker & Co.	10,000 shs.	¼.-----	July 22, 1929. Received \$333,819.76.-----	} We took up 520 shares, \$15,204.15.
Aug. 26, 1929. Chicago, Milwaukee, St. Paul & Pacific Railroad Co. preferred stock trading account.	Clark, Dodge, & Co.	50,000 shs.	20,000 shs.-----	Jan. 7, 1930.-----	
Sept. 12, 1929. General Refractories Co., common stock account.	Ladenburg, Thalmann & Co.	100,000 shs.	10,000 shs.-----	Dec. 30, 1929.-----	} We took up 18,400 shares, \$999,766.17.
				Sept. 12, 1930. Received \$11,159.70.-----	

Nov. 7, 1929. Chicago Pneumatic Tool Co., common stock trading account.	A. G. Becker & Co.-----	5,000 shs.-----	1/8-----	Apr. 16, 1930. Received \$16,600.-----	
Dec. 30, 1929. Chemical National Associates, Inc., common stock trading account.	Chemical National Co., Inc.	50,000 shs.-----	20 percent.-----	July 21, 1930. Received \$21,626.28.-----	
Jan. 3, 1930. McCrory Stores common stock purchase.	Merrill, Lynch & Co.-----	250,000 shs.-----	\$1,000,000.-----	Jan. 1, 1933.-----	We took up 25,000 shares, \$1,000,000.
Apr. 30, 1929. Pennroad Corporation common stock account.	Kuhn, Loeb & Co.-----	500,000 shs. ² -----			
				Participants:	<i>Profit</i>
				Bank of North America & Trust Co., Philadelphia 4 percent, July 22, 1929.-----	\$62,546.47
				Chas. D. Barney & Co., New York, 10 percent.-----	156,366.18
				Blair & Co., New York, 2 1/2 percent.-----	39,091.55
				Cassatt & Co., Philadelphia, 4 percent.-----	62,546.47
				Chemical National Co., Inc., New York, 3 percent.-----	46,909.86
				Jas. B. Colgate & Co., New York, 6 1/2 percent.-----	101,638.02
				Fidelity Philadelphia Trust Co., Philadelphia, 4 percent.-----	62,546.47
				Girard Trust Co., Philadelphia, 6 percent.-----	93,819.71
				International Manhattan Co., Inc., New York, 3 percent.-----	46,909.86
				Union Trust Co., Pittsburgh, 6 percent.-----	93,819.71
				Kuhn, Loeb & Co., 51 percent, including managers compensation.-----	1,188,382.97

¹ Total shares bought 22,409, sold 1,400, distributed to participants 21,009. Participants, Kuhn, Loeb & Co. 40 percent took up 8,404 shares for \$489,298.17; Lee, Higginson & Co. 40 percent took up 8,404 shares for \$489,298.17; German Banks 20 percent took up 4,201 shares for \$244,590.86; total 21,009 shares \$1,223,187.20. Distributed June 11, 1930.

² A total of 5,000 shares were bought and sold. Participants, Kuhn, Loeb & Co. 50 percent Oct. 16, 1929 net loss \$32,568.75; J. & W. Seligman & Co. 50 percent Oct. 16, 1929, net loss \$32,568.75.

³ A total of 358,900 shares were bought and sold.

Exhibit No. 40

QUESTION No. 20—SUMMARY

I. Names of all brokers to whom loans amounting to \$500,000 in the aggregate or over were made during the period 1927-31, inclusive.

II. Transcript of all loan accounts during the period 1927-31, inclusive, in which the collateral pledged consisted of securities in the issuance of which we participated:

- (a) Fujimoto Securities Corporation.
- (b) United States Rubber Company.
- (c) Pennsylvania Company.
- (d) Delaware and Hudson Company.
- (e) Lenox Corporation.
- (f) Wellington Finance Corporation.
- (g) Wellington Finance Corporation.
- (h) Wellington Finance Corporation.
- (i) Adolph Zukor.

List of loans to stock exchange firms amounting to \$500,000 and over

Abraham & Co.	Fenner, Beane & Ungerleider
Anderson & Fox	Fenner & Beane
Asiel & Co.	Farnum, Winter & Co.
Ardis, Smith & Warwick	Francis Bro. & Co.
Abbott, Hoppin & Co.	
Bamberger Bros.	Gray & Wilmerding
Benjamin Block & Co.	Gruntal, Lillienthal & Co.
Block, Maloney & Co.	Greer, Crane & Webb
Babcock, Rushton & Co.	Gilchrist, Bliss & Co.
Baruch (Sailing W.) & Co.	Gude, Winmill & Co.
Belden & Co.	W. H. Goadby & Co.
Bennett, Smith & Co.	Goodbody & Co.
Branch, Cabell & Co.	Green, Ellis & Anderson
Berg, Eyer & Kerr	
Battell, Ludwig & Co.	Harris, Upham & Co.
J. S. Bache & Co.	E. F. Hutton & Co.
Bear, Stearns & Co.	Hornblower & Weeks
H. & B. Beer	Hirsch, Lillienthal & Co.
W. E. Burnett & Co.	Hilson & Neuburger
Chas. D. Barney & Co.	J. H. Holmes & Co.
Benj. D. Bartlett & Co.	W. E. Hutton & Co.
Clark, Childs & Co.	Herzfeld & Stern
Campbell, Starring & Co.	Ira Haupt & Co.
Carleton & Mott	Henderson & Co.
Chauncey & Co.	Harriman & Co.
E. W. Clucas & Co.	Hallgarten & Co.
Henry Clews & Co.	Harris, Winthrop & Co.
F. B. Cahn & Co.	Hemphill, Noyes & Co.
S. B. Chapin & Co.	Hayden, Stone & Co.
P. F. Cusick & Co.	Henry Hentz & Co.
P. F. Cusick, Kent & Co.	Halle & Stieglitz
Carter & Co.	C. D. Halsey & Co.
A. H. Caspary & Co.	Hoge, Underhill & Co.
Carlisle, Mellick & Co.	Hammerslag, Borg & Co.
Clark, Dodge & Co.	Hendrickson & Co.
Dominick & Dominick	
J. W. Davis & Co.	Jesup & Lamont
DeCoppett & Doremus	Jackson Bros., Boesel & Co.
Dyer, Hudson & Co.	Johnson & Wood
Davenport & Co.	Frazier, Jelke & Co.
	Jacquelin & DeCoppet
	Josephthal & Co.
Eastman, Dillon & Co.	Jenks, Gwynne & Co.
Emanuel & Co.	
Evans, Stillman & Co.	Kean, Taylor & Co.
Engel & Co.	F. B. Keech & Co.
Eric & Dryfoos	Kay, Richards & Co.
Eric & Drevers	Kissell, Kinnicutt & Co.
Ehrich & Co.	

Logan & Bryan
 Livingston & Co.
 Laidlaw & Co.
 Laird, Bissell & Meeds
 Lindley & Co.
 Lamson Bros. & Co.
 W. G. Langley & Co.
 Lage & Co.
 H. C. Lapham & Co.
 Louchheim, Minton & Co.
 Arthur Lipper & Co.
 Libaire & Co.
 Loew & Co.
 Lober Bros. & Plaut
 E. Lowitz & Co.

Mabon & Co.
 G. M. P. Murphy & Co.
 A. E. Masten & Co.
 Mackay & Co.
 McDonnell & Co.
 Peter J. Maloney & Co.
 Munds & Winslow
 McGlenn & Co.
 M. J. Meehan & Co.
 Moore, Leonard & Lynch
 J. D. Merriman & Co.
 Maxwell & Co.
 Morrison & Townsend
 Monteith & Co.

Newborg & Co.
 Newburger, Henderson & Loeb
 Newman Bros. & Worms

Otis & Co.
 Orvis Bros. & Co.

Paine, Webber & Co.
 Post & Flagg
 Pouch & Co.
 Pyne, Kendall & Hollister
 Prince & Whitely
 Pearl & Co.
 E. A. Pierce & Co.
 Prentice & Slepach

Pyncheon & Co.
 Palmer & Co.
 Parrish & Co.
 Redmond & Co.
 L. F. Rothschild & Co.
 A. J. Rosenthal & Co.
 Roosevelt & Son
 E. B. Smith & Co.
 Stein, Bros. & Boyce
 Scholle Bros.
 Springs & Co.
 D. H. Silberberg & Co.
 Sutro Bros. & Co.
 Stern, Kempner & Co.
 Steven & Co.
 A. F. Schiff & Co.
 Salomon Bros. & Hutzler
 Stafford & Co.
 deSaint-Phalle & Co.
 Stephens & Co.
 Steiner, Rouse & Stroock
 Shearson, Hammill & Co.

Tameling, Keen & Co.
 Spencer Trask & Co.
 Toerge & Schiffer
 Thomson & McKinnon
 Tefft & Co.
 Tucker, Anthony & Co.

S. Ungerleider & Co.

Walker Bros.
 Winthrop, Mitchell & Co.
 Wright, Slade & Co.
 Wheeler & Kinley.
 Whitehouse & Co.
 White, Weld & Co.
 Edwin Weisl & Co.
 Wrenn Bros. & Co.
 T. L. Watson & Co.
 W. J. Wollman & Co.
 J. R. Williston & Co.
 C. E. Welles & Co.
 West & Co.

Loan to Fujimoto Securities Corporation (Japan)

Date loaned	Amount	Date paid	Amount
Jan. 6, 1927	\$1,000,000	Apr. 12, 1927	\$100,000
		Apr. 13, 1927	500,000
		Apr. 14, 1927	400,000

COLLATERAL

£40,000 City of Tokyo 5-percent bonds of 1926.
 £3,700 Imperial Japanese Government 4-percent bonds due 1931.
 \$25,000 City of Tokyo, Japan, 5½-percent bonds of 1927 due Oct. 1, 1961.
 \$28,000 Province of Buenos Aires 7-percent bonds due 1957.
 \$31,000 United States of Brazil 6½-percent bonds due 1957.
 \$63,000 Great Consolidated Electric Power 7-percent bonds due 1944.
 \$53,000 Kingdom of Italy 7-percent bonds due 1951.
 \$843,000 Imperial Japanese Government 6½-percent external loan due Feb. 1, 1954.
 \$22,000 Oriental Development Company, Ltd., 6-percent external debentures due Mar. 15, 1953.
 \$16,000 Toho Electric Company 6-percent bonds of 1929.

STOCK EXCHANGE PRACTICES

Loan to United States Rubber Co.

Date loaned	Amount	Date paid	Amount
July 2, 1928.....	\$1,400,000	Dec. 28, 1928	\$1,400,000

COLLATERAL

\$2,000,000 United States Rubber Co. first and refunding mortgage 5-percent bonds due Jan. 1, 1947.

Loan to Pennsylvania Co., Philadelphia, Pa.

Date loaned	Amount	Date paid	Amount
Apr. 26, 1928.....	\$62,500,000	{Apr. 30, 1928 {May 1, 1928	{\$56,000,000 {6,500,000

COLLATERAL

61,271 shares Pittsburgh, Fort Wayne & Chicago common stock.
 21,000 shares Pittsburgh, Youngstown & Ashtabula common stock.
 57,743 shares Pittsburgh, Youngstown & Ashtabula preferred stock.
 288,000 shares Norfolk & Western Railroad Co. common stock.
 \$3,311,000 Pennsylvania Co. gold loan 4-percent bonds due 1931.
 \$2,370,000 Pennsylvania Co. collateral 7-percent bonds due 1930.

Loan to Delaware & Hudson Co.

1930:	Nov. 18 paid for 171M Hudson Coal Co. 5-percent first mortgage sinking fund bonds.....	\$111,547.84	1930:	Dec. 1 received cou- pon from 171M bonds.....	\$4,275.00
1931:	Feb. 9 interest to date at 4 percent..	2,195.44	1931:	Feb. 9 received check from Delaware & Hudson Co.....	109,468.28
		<u>113,743.28</u>			<u>113,743.28</u>

COLLATERAL

\$171,000 Hudson Coal Co. first mortgage sinking fund 5-percent bonds due 1962.

Lenox Corporation loan

Date		Debit	Date		Credit
1928			1928		
Sept. 19	900 Paramount Famous Lasky common.....	\$125,375.00	Sept. 25	Check.....	\$25,000.00
20	100 Paramount Famous Lasky common.....	13,875.00	Oct. 1	do.....	20,000.00
26	400 Paramount Famous Lasky common.....	57,850.00	Nov. 1	do.....	40,000.00
27	400 Paramount Famous Lasky common.....	58,250.00	Dec. 31	Dividend, 11,600 shares.....	8,700.00
Oct. 15	Exchanged 1,800 old for 5,400 new.....		1929		
31	2,600 Paramount Famous Lasky common.....	130,065.00	Mar. 30	do.....	8,700.00
Nov. 1	1,100 Paramount Famous Lasky common.....	54,027.50	June 29	Dividend, 13,300 shares.....	9,975.00
2	500 Paramount Famous Lasky common.....	24,450.00	Aug. 23	Delivered 2,200 shares Paramount Famous Lasky common.....	153,485.00
7	2,000 Paramount Famous Lasky common.....	100,350.00	29	Delivered 11,600 shares Paramount Famous Lasky common.....	477,182.48
1929			30	Check.....	7,802.72
Jan. 2	Interest to Dec. 31, 1928....	6,134.72	29	Transfer from Lenox Corporation credit.....	90,354.62
Mar. 11	Value Dec. 31, 1928, transfer to Lenox Corporation credit.....	86,107.50			
22	1,700 Paramount Famous Lasky common.....	117,347.50			
Apr. 1	Interest to Mar. 31, 1929....	9,334.37			
July 11	Interest to June 30, 1929....	12,904.13			
Aug. 19	500 Paramount Famous Lasky common.....	36,137.50			
29	Interest to date.....	8,991.60			
		841,199.82			841,199.82

Lenox Corporation

1929		1929	
Aug. 29, transfer.....	\$90,354.62	Mar. 11, value Dec. 31, 1928, transfer.....	\$86,107.50
		Apr. 1, interest to Mar. 31..	1,399.25
		July 11, interest to June 30..	1,658.99
		Aug. 29, interest to date..	1,188.88
	<u>90,354.62</u>		<u>90,354.62</u>

Question No. 20. Wellington Finance Corporation Loan

Date	Shares	Debit	Date		Credit
1928			1928		
Feb. 10	600 Paramount Famous Lasky	\$69,150.00	Feb. 9	Check	\$300,000.00
14	200 Paramount Famous Lasky	22,950.00	10	do	200,000.00
17	600 Paramount Famous Lasky	68,850.00	Mar. 13	8,700 shares Paramount Famous Lasky delivered	508,200.00
20	3,200 Paramount Famous Lasky	364,825.00	27	500 shares Paramount Famous Lasky delivered	59,952.66
21	600 Paramount Famous Lasky	68,900.00			
24	200 Paramount Famous Lasky	23,050.00			
28	400 Paramount Famous Lasky	46,100.00			
29	300 Paramount Famous Lasky	34,500.00			
Mar. 6	300 Paramount Famous Lasky	35,287.50			
7	500 Paramount Famous Lasky	59,675.00			
8	300 Paramount Famous Lasky	35,587.50			
	400 Paramount Famous Lasky	47,600.00			
12	1,100 Paramount Famous Lasky	131,725.00			
13	500 Paramount Famous Lasky	59,737.50			
14	Interest	118.09			
27	do	97.07			
		1,068,152.66			1,068,152.66

Wellington Finance Corporation

		Debit			Credit
Apr. 4	1,000 Paramount Famous Lasky Common	\$116,250.00	Apr. 3	Check	\$250,000.00
May 8	2,000 Paramount Famous Lasky Common	260,500.00	11	1,000 Paramount Famous Lasky Common delivered	116,250.00
June 13	1,600 Paramount Famous Lasky Common	193,400.00	July 2	Dividend on 2,000 shares	4,000.00
20	1,400 Paramount Famous Lasky Common	172,150.00	9	Interest to June 30	64.40
Sept. 6	Interest to date	4,217.17	Sept. 6	Delivered 5,000 shares	376,202.77
		746,517.17			746,517.17

Wellington Finance Corporation loan

Date		Debit	Date		Credit
1929			1929		
Mar. 4	2,000 Paramount Famous Lasky, common	\$132,075.00	Mar. 30	Dividend 19,100 shares	\$14,325.00
Mar. 5	5,700 Paramount Famous Lasky, common	372,097.50	June 5	Delivered 600 shares Paramount Famous Lasky	41,533.50
Mar. 6	3,000 Paramount Famous Lasky, common	194,850.00	June 29	Dividend 35,000 shares	26,250.00
Mar. 7	5,400 Paramount Famous Lasky, common	347,745.00	July 13	Check	7,631.51
Mar. 8	3,000 Paramount Famous Lasky, common	191,637.50	Sept. 28	Dividend 35,000 shares	26,250.00
	Received 25,000 Bethlehem Steel 5s, series C, June 15, 1931.		Nov. 22	Delivered 4,000 East Chester 4 1/4's, Dec. 1, 1929	
	Received 5,000 Cleveland, Ohio, 4 1/2's, Oct. 1, 1944.		Dec. 28	Dividend 41,900 shares	31,425.00
	Received 10,000 Idaho 5's, Jan. 1, 1941.		Dec. 30	Delivered 5,000 Chicago 4's, Jan. 1, 1930.	
	Received 117,000 New York City 4 1/2's, May 1, 1957.		1930		
	Received 33,000 New York City 4 1/2's, Nov. 1, 1957.		Jan. 6	Check for interest	50,531.21
	Received 20,000 New York City 4 1/2's, April 1, 1966.			Check	500,000.00
	Received 10,000 Tennessee 4's, July 1, 1938.		Jan. 23	Delivered 75,000 Paramount Famous Lasky 6s, Dec. 1, 1947.	
	Received 100,000 Paramount Famous Lasky's, 6's, Dec. 1, 1947.		Feb. 4	Delivered 500 shares Paramount Famous Lasky	
	Received 5,000 Mount Vernon 4 1/4's, May 1, 1932.		Feb. 11	Check	100,000.00
	Received 25,000 New York City 4 1/2's, June 1, 1933.		Feb. 20	Delivered 1,000 shares.	
	Received 25,000 New York City 4 1/2's, Mar. 1, 1960.		Feb. 21	Check	100,000.00
	Received 140,000 New York City 4 1/2's, Mar. 1, 1962.		Feb. 27	Delivered 800 shares.	
	Received 159,000 New York City 4 1/2's, Mar. 1, 1964.		Mar. 1	Check	100,000.00
	Received 20,000 Philadelphia, Pa., 3 1/2's, July 1, 1934.		Mar. 3	Check	300,000.00
	Received 40,000 Rochester, N.Y., 4 1/2's, Jan. 15, 1933.			Delivered 25,000 Paramount Famous Lasky 6's, Dec. 4, 1947.	
	Received 10,000 Detroit, Mich., 4 1/2's, June 1, 1931.		Mar. 4	Delivered 4,400 shares.	
	Received 20,000 Detroit, Mich., 4 1/2's, June 1, 1930.		Mar. 5	Delivered 41,432 shares.	
	Received 20,000 Cambridge, Mass., 3's, Feb. 1, 1941.		Mar. 6	Check	14,000.00
	Received 10,000 Iowa 4 1/2's, Dec. 1, 1931.			Delivered 200 shares.	
	Received 35,000 Jersey City, N.J., 4 1/2's, Aug. 1, 1930.		Mar. 13	Delivered 8,400 shares.	
	Received 25,000 Kansas City, Mo., 4's, Sept. 1, 1930.			Check	600,000.00
	Received 15,000 Maine 4's, Dec. 1, 1932.		Mar. 18	Delivered 5,000 Massachusetts 3 1/2's, July 1, 1935.	
	Received 25,000 New York City 4's, May 1, 1934.			Delivered 3,000 Akron, Ohio, 4 1/2's, May 15, 1933.	
	Received 33,000 New York City 3 1/2's, Nov. 1, 1954.			Delivered 8,000 Allegheny 4's, June 1, 1933.	
	Received 17,000 New York City 3 1/2's, May 1, 1954.			Delivered 20,000 Cambridge 3's, Feb. 1, 1941.	
	Received 30,000 New York City 4 1/2's, July 1, 1967.			Delivered 4,000 East Chester 4 1/2's, Dec. 1, 1930.	
	Received 25,000 Port of New York Authority 4's, B, Dec. 1, 1937.			Delivered 2,000 Harrison, N.Y., 4 1/2's, Dec. 1, 1930.	
Mar. 11	6,600 Paramount Famous Lasky, common	427,067.50		Delivered 2,000 Harrison, N.Y., 4 1/2's, Dec. 1, 1933.	
Mar. 12	500 Paramount Famous Lasky, common	33,087.50		Delivered 5,000 Mamaronock 4 1/2's, June 1, 1931.	
Mar. 13	2,300 Paramount Famous Lasky, common	152,127.50		Delivered 5,000 Mobile, Ala., 5's, Nov. 2, 1935.	
Mar. 25	1,600 Paramount Famous Lasky, common	105,755.00		Delivered 10,000 New York City 4 1/2's, Sept. 1, 1960.	
Mar. 26	3,200 Paramount Famous Lasky, common	201,760.00		Delivered 30,000 New York City 4 1/2's, July 1, 1967.	
Mar. 27	2,300 Paramount Famous Lasky, common	130,302.50		Delivered 5,000 Philadelphia, Pa., 3 1/2's, July 1, 1934.	
Apr. 1	Interest on \$699,022.50	1,331.51	Mar. 21	Check	450,000.00
June 4	Check	14,325.00		Delivered 6,100 shares.	
July 11	Interest to June 30	50,656.50	Mar. 26	Delivered 50,000 Paramount Famous Lasky, 6's, Dec. 1, 1947.	
Oct. 1	Interest to Sept. 30	43,596.23		Delivered 10,000 Iowa 4 1/2's, Dec. 1, 1931.	
				Delivered 15,000 Maine 4's, Dec. 1, 1932.	
				Delivered 20,000 West Virginia, 3 1/2's, Jan. 1, 1939.	
				Delivered 33,000 New York City 3 1/2's, Nov. 1, 1954.	

Wellington Finance Corporation loan—Continued

Date		Debit	Date		Credit
Oct. 26	6,900 Paramount Famous Lasky, common.....	\$446,523.03	Mar. 26	Delivered 25,000 Port of N. Y. Auth. 4's, B, Dec. 1, 1937.	
28	Received 10,000 San. Dist. Chicago 5's, July 1, 1934.		29	Dividend, 35,000 shares....	\$35,000
	Received 20,000 Massachusetts 3½'s, Jan. 1, 1938.		31	Check.....	750,000
	Received 5,000 Massachusetts 3½'s, July 1, 1935.		Apr. 1, 1930	Delivered 10,000 shares.	
	Received 20,000 West Virginia 3½'s, Jan. 1, 1939.			Delivered 25,000 Bethlehem Steel 5's, June 15, 1931.	
	Received 10,000 West Virginia 5's, July 1, 1934.			Delivered 5,000 Cleveland, Ohio, 4½'s, Oct. 1, 1944.	
	Received 10,000 Atlantic City 4½'s, July 1, 1933.			Delivered 10,000 Idaho 5's, Jan. 1, 1941.	
	Received 10,000 New York City 3½'s, Nov. 1, 1955.			Delivered 117,000 New York City 4½'s, May 1, 1957.	
	Received 50,000 New York City 4½'s, Sept. 1, 1960.			Delivered 33,000 New York City 4½'s, Nov. 1, 1957.	
	Received 5,000 San Francisco 4½'s, July 1, 1939.			Delivered 20,000 New York City 4½'s, Apr. 1, 1966.	
	Received 10,000 Illinois 4's, May 1, 1932.			Delivered 25,000 New York City 4½'s, June 1, 1933.	
29	Received 20,232 Paramount Famous Lasky, common.	500,000.00		Delivered 25,000 New York City 4½'s, Mar. 1, 1960.	
30	Received 21,200 Paramount Famous Lasky, common.	500,000.00		Delivered 140,000 New York City 4½'s, Mar. 1, 1962.	
	Received 304,000 Paramount Famous Lasky 6's, Dec. 1, 1947.			Delivered 159,000 New York City 4½'s, Mar. 1, 1964.	
	Received 3,000 Akron, Ohio, 4½'s, May 15, 1933.			Delivered 25,000 New York City 4's, May 1, 1934.	
	Received 5,000 Philadelphia, Pa., 3½'s, July 1, 1934.			Delivered 17,000 New York City 3½'s, May 1, 1954.	
	Received 5,000 Chicago, Ill., 4's, Jan. 1, 1930.			Delivered 10,000 New York City 3½'s, Nov. 1, 1955.	
	Received 8,000 Alleghany City 4's, June 1, 1933.			Delivered 40,000 New York City 4½'s, Sept. 1, 1960.	
	Received 5,000 Massachusetts 3½'s, July 1, 1935.			Delivered 10,000 Tennessee 4's, July 1, 1938.	
	Received 2,000 Harrison, N. Y., 4½'s, Dec. 1, 1930.			Delivered 5,000 Mount Vernon 4½'s, May 1, 1932.	
	Received 2,000 Harrison, N. Y., 4½'s, Dec. 1, 1933.			Delivered 40,000 Rochester N. Y., 4½'s, Jan. 15, 1933.	
	Received 5,000 Mamaronock, N. Y., 4½'s, June 1, 1931.			Delivered 10,000 Detroit, Ohio, 4½'s, June 1, 1931.	
	Received 5,000 Mobile, Ala., 5's, Nov. 2, 1935.			Delivered 20,000 Detroit, Ohio, 4½'s, June 1, 1930.	
	Received 4,000 East Chester, N. Y., 4½'s, Dec. 1, 1929.			Delivered 35,000 Jersey City 4½'s, Aug. 1, 1930.	
	Received 4,000 East Chester, N. Y., 4½'s, Dec. 1, 1930.			Delivered 25,000 Kansas City 4's, Sept. 1, 1930.	
Dec. 31	Interest to date.....	50,531.21		Delivered 10,000 San. District Chicago 5's, July 1, 1934.	
Apr. 1, 1930do.....	35,684.40		Delivered 20,000 Massachusetts 3½'s, Jan. 1, 1938.	
				Delivered 10,000 West Virginia 5's, July 1, 1934.	
				Delivered 10,000 Atlantic City 4½'s, July 1, 1933.	
				Delivered 5,000 San Francisco 4½'s, July 1, 1939.	
				Delivered 10,000 Illinois 4's, May 1, 1932.	
				Delivered 254,000 Paramount Famous Lasky 6's, Dec. 1, 1947.	
				Delivered 20,000 Philadelphia, Pa., 3½'s, July 1, 1934.	
				Delivered 5,000 Massachusetts 3½'s, July 1, 1935.	
			1	Delivered 10,500 shares....	793,206.66
		3,940,152.88			3,940,152.88

Loan to Adolph Zukor

1930	Debit	1930	Credit	
Apr. 1	27,000 Paramount Famous Lasky common..... Federal and State transfer stamps..... Received 25,000 Bethlehem Steel 5's C June 15, 1931. Received 5,000 Cleveland, Ohio, 4½'s Oct. 1, 1944. Received 10,000 Idaho 5's Jan. 1, 1941. Received 117,000 New York City 4½'s May 1, 1957. Received 33,000 New York City 4½ percent Nov. 1, 1957. Received 20,000 New York City 4¼ percent Apr. 1, 1966. Received 25,000 New York City 4¼ percent June 1, 1933. Received 25,000 New York City 4¼ percent Mar. 1, 1960. Received 140,000 New York City 4¼ percent Mar. 1, 1962. Received 159,000 New York City 4¼ percent Mar. 1, 1964. Received 25,000 New York City 4's May 1, 1934. Received 17,000 New York City 3½ percent May 1, 1954. Received 10,000 New York City 3½ percent Nov. 1, 1955. Received 40,000 New York City 4¼ percent Sept. 1, 1960. Received 10,000 Tennessee 4's July 1, 1938. Received 5,000 Mount Vernon 4½'s May 1, 1932. Received 40,000 Rochester 4½'s Jan. 15, 1933. Received 10,000 Detroit 4¼'s June 1, 1931. Received 20,000 Detroit 4¼'s June 1, 1930. Received 35,000 Jersey City 4¼'s Aug. 1, 1930. Received 25,000 Kansas City, Mo. 4's Sept. 1, 1930. Received 10,000 San. District, Chicago 5's July 1, 1934. Received 20,000 Massachusetts 3½'s Jan. 1, 1938. Received 10,000 West Virginia 5's July 1, 1934. Received 10,000 Atlantic City 4½'s July 1, 1933. Received 5,000 San Francisco 4½'s July 1, 1939. Received 10,000 Illinois 4's Apr. 1, 1932. Received 254,000 Paramount Famous Lasky 6's Dec. 1, 1947. Received 20,000 Philadelphia, Pa. 3½'s July 1, 1934. Received 5,000 Massachusetts 3½'s July 1, 1935.	\$1,404,000.00 1,080.00	Apr. 16 Delivered 54,000 Paramount Famous Lasky 6's Dec. 1, 1947. 17 Delivered 1,000 shares Paramount Famous Lasky common..... 25 Delivered 20,000 Detroit 4¼'s June 1, 1930. 30 Delivered 50,000 Paramount Famous Lasky 6's Dec. 1, 1947. May 22 Delivered 50,000 Paramount Famous Lasky 6's. Delivered 1,500 shares Paramount Publix Corporation common..... June 3 Delivered 50,000 Paramount Famous Lasky 6's Dec. 1, 1947. 6 Delivered 25,000 Bethlehem Steel 5's "c" June 15, 1931. 28 Dividend 24,500 shares.... 30 Delivered 1,000 shares Paramount Publix Corporation common..... July 29 Delivered 600 shares Paramount Publix Corporation common..... Delivered 25,000 Paramount Famous Lasky 6's Dec. 1, 1947. Aug. 1 Due 35,000 Jersey City 4¼'s Aug. 1, 1930..... Sept. 2 Due 25,000 Kansas City, Mo., 4's Sept. 1, 1930..... Coupons 40,000 New York City 4¼'s..... Coupons 140,000 New York City 4¼'s..... Coupons 159,000 New York City 4¼'s..... Coupons 25,000 New York City 4¼'s..... 27 Dividend 23,000 Paramount Publix Corporation common..... Oct. 1 Coupons 5,000 Cleveland 4½'s..... Coupons 20,000 New York City 4¼'s..... Nov. 1 Coupons 5,000 Mount Vernon 4½'s..... Coupons 33,000 New York City 4¼'s..... Coupons 117,000 New York City 4½'s..... Coupons 17,000 New York City 3½'s..... Coupons 25,000 New York City 4's..... Coupons 10,000 New York City 3½'s..... 6 Value Nov. 1..... 12 Check..... Dec. 1 Coupons 10,000 Detroit 4½'s..... Coupons 25,000 Paramount Famous Lasky 6's..... 17 Delivered 10,000 Idaho 5's Jan. 1, 1941. 27 Dividend 43,000 shares Paramount Publix Corporation common.....	\$52,000.00 78,000.00 24,500.00 52,000.00 26,000.00 35,000.00 25,500.00 850.00 2,975.00 3,378.75 531.25 23,000.00 112.50 425.00 106.25 742.50 2,632.50 297.50 500.00 175.00 4,453.75 150,000.00 212.50 750.00 43,000.00

Loan to Adolph Zukor—Continued

1930		Debit	1932		Credit
Mar. 15	Recd. 1,500 Par. Publix Com.—Continued		Jan. 8	10,000 New York City 4½'s, Mar. 1, 1960.	\$8,249.93
				10,000 Illinois 4's, May 1, 1932.	10,161.94
				10,000 Paramount Famous Lasky 6's, Dec. 1, 1947.	4,886.67
			11	17,000 New York City 3½'s, May 1, 1954.	12,504.44
			13	10,000 New York City 3½'s, Nov. 1, 1955.	7,332.50
			14	10,000 Tennessee 4's, July 1, 1933.	8,739.44
			15	5,000 New York City 4's, May 1, 1934.	4,816.86
			16	Interest 40,000 Rochester 4½'s.	900.00
			25	10,000 New York City 4's, May 1, 1934.	9,637.08
			Feb. 1	5,000 Mount Vernon 4¼'s, May 1, 1932.	4,950.00
			9	R. C. Montgomery & Co., value, Feb. 8, 1932.	25,000.00
			11	Check, A. Zukor ----- Delivered to National City Bank, Forty-first Street Branch:	4,577.35 225,000.00
				25,000 New York City 4½'s, June 1, 1933.	
				10,000 New York City 4's, May 1, 1934.	
				10,000 Sanitary District Chicago 5's, July 1, 1934.	
				10,000 Atlantic City, N.J., 4½'s, July 1, 1933.	
				25,664.375 Paramount Publix common. ⁴	
		\$2,423,022.30			2,423,022.30

STOCK EXCHANGE PRACTICES

THURSDAY, JULY 6, 1933

UNITED STATES SENATE,
SUBCOMMITTEE OF THE COMMITTEE
ON BANKING AND CURRENCY,
Washington, D.C.

The subcommittee met, pursuant to adjournment on Friday, June 30, 1933, at 10 o'clock a.m., in the caucus room of the Senate Office Building, Senator Duncan U. Fletcher presiding.

Present: Senators Fletcher (chairman), Barkley, Goldsborough, Townsend, and Steiwer.

Present also: Ferdinand Pecora, counsel to the committee; Frank J. Meehan, chief statistician to the committee.

The CHAIRMAN. The subcommittee will come to order. Mr. Pecora, you may proceed.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Taplin.

The CHAIRMAN. Mr. Taplin will come forward to the committee table, stand, and hold up his right hand, to be sworn: You solemnly swear that you will tell the truth, the whole truth, and nothing but the truth, regarding the matters now under investigation by the committee. So help you God.

Mr. TAPLIN. I do.

TESTIMONY OF FRANK E. TAPLIN, PRESIDENT OF THE PITTSBURGH & WEST VIRGINIA RAILWAY CO., CLEVELAND, OHIO

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Taplin, will you kindly give your full name, business, and address to the committee reporter for the record?

Mr. TAPLIN. Frank E. Taplin, president of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co.; residence, Cleveland, Ohio.

Mr. PECORA. What is the street number of your residence?

Mr. TAPLIN. 3090 Fairmont Boulevard.

Mr. PECORA. How long have you been president of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co.?

Mr. TAPLIN. Since 1923.

Mr. PECORA. Prior to that time were you connected with that railroad corporation in any other capacity?

Mr. TAPLIN. No. I had nothing to do with it prior to 1923.

Mr. PECORA. When were you first served with a subpoena to appear before this committee?

Mr. TAPLIN. On Thursday morning of last week at 3 minutes after 11 in New York City, and it is so noted on the subpoena by my secretary.

Mr. PECORA. When did you first learn that a subpoena had been issued by this committee for your attendance?

Mr. TAPLIN. At that time. When I got it.

Mr. PECORA. Didn't you know before that?

Mr. TAPLIN. No, sir.

Mr. PECORA. On the evening before the service of that subpoena upon you were you in Washington, D.C.?

Mr. TAPLIN. I was in Washington on that day.

Mr. PECORA. Did you have any conversation on that day with Mr. Henry H. Lee?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir. I think about 10 o'clock in the evening. I did not know that he was in the city until I saw him get into a taxicab at the Carlton Hotel, and I stopped him and talked to him for about a minute. There was a very important matter to be taken care of the next day in New York, at a board meeting, which I spent most of the minute trying to discuss with him, as he was hurrying to the cab. Judge Heiserman was with him, and he said that he had been subpoenaed to appear down here before the Senate Banking and Currency Committee in regard to the Pittsburgh & West Virginia-Pennroad case. I said:

I heard this evening that somebody at Washington was trying to get hold of me today. I guess maybe they wanted to subpoena me before that committee.

At that he got into the cab, and that was the only conversation I had with him.

Mr. PECORA. Well, had you heard that someone had tried to subpoena you?

Mr. TAPLIN. No. I heard that someone that evening—well, my secretary told me that someone in Washington was trying to get hold of me. And I will say that when I got back to Cleveland then I found that the sheriff had delivered another subpoena—I mean another from the one I received in New York, at the residence. They told the office about it, and I learned when I got home that the office had told the party trying to serve it that I was in Washington and they could undoubtedly locate me either at the Mayflower, the Carlton, or the Washington Hotel. But I never heard of anybody that day when I was in Washington.

Mr. PECORA. After you were subpoenaed last Thursday morning what did you do in connection with the services of the subpoena upon you?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I was in the board meeting, Mr. Pecora, called for 11 o'clock, and the subpoena called on me to be in Washington at 10 o'clock. Of course, I could not be in Washington at 10 o'clock, so I wrote on the subpoena a memorandum that "this notice was served on me at New York at 11:03 p.m."—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). Did you say "p.m."?

Mr. TAPLIN. Or a.m., which is on here, and to which my secretary signed his name. I was in the board meeting, and I took the subpoena and put it over with some other papers. I was in that meeting until 1 o'clock as chairman of the board of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co., and there were some very important matters that had to be taken care of that day. And I had another meeting at 1 o'clock, at 120 Broadway, in a different building, at the Eastern Railroad Presidents' Conference, and I was a little bit late. And I rushed up

to that meeting, and I was there until about 3 o'clock, and I made a couple of calls down town, and at one of them I was detained a little time waiting for a gentleman longer than I had expected, and when I got up to the hotel it was about 5 o'clock, and I took my papers out, and when I took them out I looked them over, and then I found this subpoena which had been handed me in the morning, and I asked my secretary to take a telegram, a copy of which I have here, and to send it to you, and to advise you that I received the subpoena too late, and would be glad to appear this week any day you wanted me.

Mr. PECORA. Couldn't you have appeared the following day, namely, on last Friday?

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, yes. But, you see, I will have to plead a little bit of ignorance, and am sorry if I discommoded you, but when I got the subpoena for Thursday it never occurred to me that there was any reason to be here on Friday. I mean when I got the subpoena for Thursday. But I will tell you that if I had got this subpoena—and I guess you call it a subpoena duces tecum, for it was asking for a lot of papers—I could not possibly have had the papers, because the gentleman, Mr. Larson, who is here with me, is the only gentleman who is in possession of the papers in Cleveland, and he was in Boston. So I would have been here without any papers to support any evidence you wanted.

Mr. PECORA. Have you the documents and records the subpoena calls for?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir; all of them today. And I could just as well have had them with me on last Wednesday, when I was in Washington, if you had wired me, without subpoena. I did not need to have any subpoena. I was here then, and if I had known that I was wanted, without any subpoena, I could have had all the papers I have today, with everything complete, if I had known what you wanted.

Mr. PECORA. Testimony introduced before this committee, Mr. Taplin, is to the effect that when you met Mr. Lee last Wednesday night at the hotel in Washington you stated, in words or substance, that you knew the committee was seeking to serve a subpoena upon you.

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, Mr. Pecora, I will say—

Mr. PECORA (continuing). And that you went to New York the following morning, or rather that Wednesday night.

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I don't know about that. I didn't testify to that.

Mr. PECORA. I know you did not; of course not—

Mr. TAPLIN (interposing). I did afterwards read that statement in a newspaper, and a couple of other statements that were not exactly accurate either, and so if a man could make a mistake in one case he could make a mistake in another. I have told you just what I said to Mr. Lee.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Taplin, are you familiar with the transaction whereby 222,930 shares of the capital stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. were sold to the Pennroad Corporation in 1929?

Mr. TAPLIN. Thoroughly. I sold it to them.

Mr. PECORA. When you say you sold it to the Pennroad Corporation, do you mean that it was your stock that you sold to that corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. It was under my control. A part of it was mine and the rest of it was under my control by agreements.

Mr. PECORA. How much of it was yours?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I think about one-half of it. That is, when I say mine I will have to include the members of my family as mine, a small amount that was mine personally, and my wife had some of it, and my children had some of it, and a company had some of it, but I include that as mine because I spoke for it.

Mr. PECORA. And you said about one-half of it?

Mr. TAPLIN. About one-half.

Mr. PECORA. Was yours, meaning by that that it was more or less under your control, being owned by you or members of your family?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; and a company I controlled.

Mr. PECORA. How much of it was yours individually?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I have all the figures here, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. Well, so long as you have all the figures, will you tell the committee who the owners were of the 222,930 shares immediately prior to the sale of that stock to the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. Do you mean, shall I read the names?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. All the names?

Mr. PECORA. And their holdings; yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. I will read them all to you.

Mr. PECORA. All right.

Mr. TAPLIN. They are as follows:

	<i>Shares</i>		<i>Shares</i>
William C. Atwater-----	13, 650	Charles D. Hebard-----	1, 100
R. B. Brown-----	549	Feran & Co-----	10, 370
E. W. Backus-----	4, 740	A. P. King-----	878
L. P. Cretilius-----	50	E. J. Kules-----	1, 097
T. B. Davis-----	3, 000	J. R. Kraus-----	4, 200
E. M. Ford-----	500	E. S. Kandrick-----	4, 100
A. H. Ferbert-----	219	E. P. Lenahan-----	3, 097
Adam Gross-----	549	Charles D. Little-----	164
F. H. Ginn-----	1, 097	O. J. Lange-----	219
C. P. Hutchins-----	5, 564	R. S. McVeigh-----	21, 085

Then the next is McDonnell & Co., in three separate lots, and I will bulk them together.

Mr. PECORA. What do they amount to?

Mr. TAPLIN. McDonnell & Co. amount to 9,350 shares.

Mr. PECORA. Is that the total of the three lots of the stock that they had?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Senator TOWNSEND. What company is that?

Mr. TAPLIN. Some stockbrokers in New York.

Mr. PECORA. All right, you may proceed.

Mr. TAPLIN (reading) :

	<i>Shares</i>		<i>Shares</i>
North American Coal Corporation.....	30,720	C. F. Taplin.....	5,090
R. H. Munan.....	2,000	F. E. Taplin.....	16,601
L. C. Percival.....	1,200	Clara Louise Taplin.....	14,516
Samuel Pursglove.....	1,694	F. E. Taplin, Jr.....	25,166
Thomas Pursglove.....	500	Thomas Ely Taplin.....	2,900
C. A. Paul.....	1,097	Edith S. Taplin.....	2,960
Joseph Pursglove.....	279	W. P. Todd.....	1,097
E. P. Peters.....	65	Isabel Thompson.....	4,266
F. W. Paine.....	2,194	A. B. Uhrig.....	14,000
George M. Rogers.....	1,097	Thomas Warfield.....	700
Arthur Rand.....	1,000	J. S. Wood.....	1,179
John L. Steinbugler.....	3,450	Thomas H. Wilson.....	1,000
F. B. Stearns.....	1,358	Charles E. Williams.....	134
A. E. R. Schneider.....	439		
		Total.....	222,930

The CHAIRMAN. What was the total issue of the railroad corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. Approximately 302,000 shares.

Mr. PECORA. Who conducted the negotiations in behalf of the sellers of this stock to the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. I did.

Mr. PECORA. When were those negotiations commenced?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, there had been discussions of the purchase of the stock I would say for a period of at least 2 and maybe 3 years prior to the time that this stock was actually sold.

Mr. PECORA. Well, with whom did you have those discussions for 2 or 3 years before the sale?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, in the earlier part of that time, which would be, maybe, 1926 or 1927, I think I discussed the matter with General Atterbury and A. J. County.

Mr. PECORA. Was General Atterbury then the president of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. TAPLIN. He was.

Mr. PECORA. Was Mr. County then the vice president of that railroad company?

Mr. TAPLIN. He was.

Mr. PECORA. Do they still hold those offices in that company?

Mr. TAPLIN. I think they do.

Mr. PECORA. Who took the initiative in 1926 in negotiating the proceedings that culminated in the sale of this stock? Was it you, or the sellers of the stock, or General Atterbury, or Mr. County?

Mr. TAPLIN. I do not believe I could answer that, because I saw them every month or so, and we were always discussing different railroad problems, and there was a great desire at that time on the part of two or three railroads, I believe, to own the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. on account of the strategic position which it occupied in the city of Pittsburgh, which is a heavy-tonnage district, and I cannot say just who initiated it because the talk was more or less continual.

Mr. PECORA. That is, beginning with some time in 1926, you had many conversations with General Atterbury and Mr. County with respect to the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.—

Mr. TAPLIN (interposing). Yes. The Pennroad Corporation at that time was not interested, you understand, and I do not believe it was even organized at that time.

Mr. PECORA. You want me to understand, then, to resume the question before you interrupted it, that some time in 1926 there were a series of conferences initiated between you and General Atterbury and Mr. County?

Mr. TAPLIN. I do not think I ever talked with them together. They were not conferences. The talk was with each one of them separately when I would see them.

Mr. PECORA. In those talks was the subject of the acquisition by the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. of a substantial stock interest in the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. discussed?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And you cannot tell who initiated those discussions?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; I cannot.

Mr. PECORA. Whether you or whether General Atterbury or Mr. County?

Mr. TAPLIN. I am inclined to think I probably did, but I wouldn't want to say who initiated them.

Mr. PECORA. At that time, Mr. Taplin, how many shares of stock of your company did you have either in your ownership or in the ownership of members of your family or under control?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I always had—at that time I had probably 200,000 shares.

Mr. PECORA. Did they represent the shares that were sold—

Mr. TAPLIN (interposing). Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA (continuing). And which were owned and held by the persons whose names you have given us this morning?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir. I had an agreement that took in the most of these holders beginning with 1923, I believe.

Mr. PECORA. That is from the time you became the president of the road?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; from the time I bought the stock.

Mr. PECORA. What was the nature of these agreements you had with these stockholders of your company?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, now, I had this in two ways, Mr. Pecora. Here is an agreement that is a syndicate agreement that a great many of these people put money into in which they did not have a specific number of shares, but they had a certificate of interest in the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway syndicate.

Mr. PECORA. Have you that syndicate agreement with you?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; I have.

Mr. PECORA. Will you produce it, please?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir. I think that is the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway syndicate agreement dated July 20, 1923 [handing same to Mr. Pecora].

Mr. PECORA. Is this a duplicate original of such agreement?

Mr. TAPLIN. I did not look at that when I handed it to you. That is an original copy. Here is another one though, Mr. Pecora [handing same to Mr. Pecora]. If you will look at this you will notice it was for a specific period of time, and then it was renewed, and it seems that the copy I handed you did not have all of the names of the syndicate on it, but this one seems to have all of them on it.

Mr. PECORA. Well, let me have the first one also. Now the one you first handed me is captioned "Pittsburgh & West Virginia

Railway Syndicate Agreement." It bears date July 20, 1923. That, you say, is a duplicate original?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, it is signed by those people, so it must be an original. But it has not got all of the names of the syndicate members on it. I can see that by glancing at it, because they are all here in these copies.

Mr. PECORA. I offer it in evidence and ask that it be spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. It will be received in evidence and will be spread on the record. Have you got a copy of that, Mr. Taplin?

Mr. TAPLIN. I do not think I have any other copy of that, no; unless I have one at home.

The CHAIRMAN. You want that one returned to you, then?

Mr. TAPLIN. Pardon me. Mr. Larson explains to me, Mr. Pecora, why all of the names were not on that one. He says that there were three copies, and some were on one copy and some on another and some on a third, and therefore I think these three here ought to go together. I think those three are of the same syndicate—the original, you see—with all of the names on them.

The CHAIRMAN. The body of the agreement is the same?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; the body of the agreement is the same, only I used three copies to get all the signatures. Only some would have one copy, others would have another.

Mr. PECORA. Yes. I offer in evidence all three copies, and ask that they be spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. They will be admitted in evidence and spread on the record. You want these returned to you, do you, Mr. Taplin?

Mr. TAPLIN. I certainly do. They are the only ones I have, Senator.

The CHAIRMAN. Let the reporters know that you want the originals returned.

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; I want them returned to me.

(Three copies of Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Syndicate Agreement dated July 20th, 1923, each copy containing different signatures and different amounts, were received in evidence, marked "Committee Exhibits 43, 44 and 45, of July 6, 1933", and are here printed in the record in full, as follows:)

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT 43

PITTSBURGH & WEST VIRGINIA RAILWAY SYNDICATE AGREEMENT, JULY 20, 1923— SYNDICATE AGREEMENT

This agreement made at Cleveland, Ohio, as of July 20, 1923, is to witness:

1. The subscribers hereto shall constitute a syndicate for the purpose of buying, selling, and trading in the securities of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. and/or any subsidiary or affiliated company and/or property of whatever nature which the syndicate managers deem appropriate in connection with the first stated purposes.

2. The subscribers hereto shall be participants in the syndicate in the amounts set opposite their respective signatures to this agreement, which amounts they agree to pay as hereinafter set forth. Participants shall elect at the time of signature to either pay their participation in full or to pay 50 percent thereof on the initial call and the balance on 30-day call or calls of the syndicate managers, and shall stand obligated according to such election either to pay the full participation on the initial call or to pay 50 percent on the initial call and 50 percent on such further 30-day call or calls by the syndicate managers.

Participants who do not pay in full on their initial call shall be from time to time charged with interest on their deferred payments from the date hereof at the rate of 6 percent per annum. All participations and calls are payable at the principal office of The Union Trust Co., Cleveland, Ohio, and/or at such other place or places as the syndicate managers shall designate.

3. The syndicate managers will issue to participants certificates of participation in the syndicate to the extent of their subscriptions and providing for endorsement of payments beyond 50 percent. Such certificates of participation shall be registered by The Union Trust Co., Cleveland, Ohio, which the syndicate managers have named as registrar of such certificates. Certificates of participation shall be in such form as the syndicate managers shall determine and shall be transferable only with the prior consent of the syndicate managers, unless fully paid, in which case they shall be freely transferable.

4. F. E. Taplin and J. R. Kraus are constituted "syndicate managers" under this agreement with the power to add one or more managers to their number at any time during the life of the syndicate. Upon resignation or death of a syndicate manager or managers, the successor or successors shall be named by the survivor or survivors of the syndicate managers. The syndicate managers assume no personal obligation or liability in the management of the syndicate and shall be liable only for willful bad faith in the conduct of the syndicate. If there shall at any time be more than two syndicate managers, the action of two shall control.

5. The syndicate managers are empowered with the entire and sole management and conduct of the syndicate and without limitation upon such general power, shall have the right to purchase, sell, repurchase and resell any securities and/or other property hereinbefore referred to; to borrow for the account of the syndicate at such interest rate or rates and upon such terms as they may determine; to pledge or otherwise charge, as security for such borrowings, the assets of the syndicate in whole or part and including obligations of the participants; to employ and pay such depositories, agents, counsel, and others in whatever capacity, as they may deem proper; all for the account of the syndicate and at its expense. The syndicate managers shall act without compensation.

6. This syndicate is organized for the term of 1 year from its date and shall expire at the close of business July 19, 1924; subject, however, to the right of the syndicate managers to extend the same for a further period of 1 year from that date by written notice to participants mailed on or before July 1, 1924. The syndicate managers may, however, terminate this syndicate at any time within the period or periods above specified.

7. On expiration or termination of the syndicate, any property then held shall be distributed to participants pro rata upon or after payment of syndicate obligations.

The syndicate managers may from time to time distribute any profits from the syndicate operations and the same shall be distributed pro rata to participants according to the full amount of their participation whether full or part paid.

8. The syndicate managers shall have the right to cancel and forfeit to the syndicate any participation on failure of the participant to make payment of all or part of his participation when called in accordance with this agreement. The failure of any participant to perform any part of his obligations hereunder shall not relieve any other participant.

9. From time to time during the life of the syndicate the syndicate managers in their discretion may accept further subscriptions to and participations in the syndicate, from then members or others, upon such terms as to participation in previous profits, losses, expenses, and otherwise as the syndicate managers may determine.

10. All calls and notices upon or to participants shall be made or given by the syndicate managers or their nominee or nominees and shall be sufficient if mailed registered to the participants at their addresses of record with the syndicate managers or the registrar of certificates.

11. This agreement shall bind the parties signing and their respective successors, assigns, and personal representatives. It may be made and signed in several counterparts but all such shall be taken as one original instrument.

In witness whereof the various parties hereto have subscribed their names and addresses and the amounts of their subscriptions as of the day and year first above written, and the syndicate managers have signed as such in acceptance of their obligations hereunder.

The Mid-Continent Securities Co.

Jno. Sherwin, vice president, Cleveland.....	\$300, 000
A. H. Scoville, Cleveland.....	25, 000
F. W. Lovell, 2041 East Ninety-third Street, Cleveland, Ohio.....	25, 000
W. M. Baldwin, Cleveland.....	5, 000
J. R. Kraus, Cleveland.....	50, 000
Frank H. Ginn, Williamson Building.....	50, 000
R. V. Mitchell, care United Security, Canton, Ohio.....	35, 000
E. J. Kulas, 1104 Union National Bank Building.....	50, 000
Thomas H. Wilson, 406 Caxton Building.....	30, 000
Chas. A. Paul, Norwalk, Ohio.....	50, 000

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT 44

PITTSBURGH & WEST VIRGINIA RAILWAY SYNDICATE AGREEMENT, JULY 20, 1923—
SYNDICATE AGREEMENT

This agreement made at Cleveland, Ohio, as of July 20, 1923, is to witness:

1. The subscribers hereto shall constitute a syndicate for the purpose of buying, selling, and trading in the securities of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. and/or any subsidiary or affiliated company and/or property of whatever nature which the syndicate managers deem appropriate in connection with the first-stated purposes.

2. The subscribers hereto shall be participants in the syndicate in the amounts set opposite their respective signatures to this agreement, which amounts they agree to pay as hereinafter set forth. Participants shall elect at the time of signature to either pay their participation in full or to pay 50 percent thereof on the initial call and the balance on 30-day call or calls of the syndicate managers, and shall stand obligated according to such election either to pay the full participation on the initial call or to pay 50 percent on the initial call and 50 percent on such further 30-day call or calls by the syndicate managers. Participants who do not pay in full on the initial call shall be from time to time charged with interest on their deferred payments from the date hereof at the rate of 6 percent per annum. All participations and calls are payable at the principal office of the Union Trust Co., Cleveland, Ohio, and/or at such other place or places as the syndicate managers shall designate.

3. The syndicate managers will issue to participants certificates of participation in the syndicate to the extent of their subscriptions and providing for endorsement of payments beyond 50 percent. Such certificates of participation shall be registered by the Union Trust Co., Cleveland, Ohio, which the syndicate managers have named as registrar of such certificates. Certificates of participation shall be in such form as the syndicate managers shall determine and shall be transferable only with the prior consent of the syndicate managers, unless fully paid, in which case they shall be freely transferable.

4. F. E. Taplin and J. R. Kraus are constituted "syndicate managers" under this agreement, with the power to add one or more managers to their number at any time during the life of the syndicate. Upon resignation or death of a syndicate manager or managers, the successor or successors shall be named by the survivor or survivors of the syndicate managers. The syndicate managers assume no personal obligation or liability in the management of the syndicate and shall be liable only for willful bad faith in the conduct of the syndicate. If there shall at any time be more than two syndicate managers, the action of two shall control.

5. The syndicate managers are empowered with the entire and sole management and conduct of the syndicate and, without limitation upon such general power, shall have the right to purchase, sell, repurchase, and resell any securities and/or other property hereinbefore referred to; to borrow for the account of the syndicate at such interest rate or rates and upon such terms as they may determine; to pledge or otherwise charge, as security for such borrowings, the assets of the syndicate in whole or part and including obligations of the participants; to employ and pay such depositories, agents, counsel, and others in whatever capacity as they may deem proper; all for the account of the syndicate and at its expense. The syndicate managers shall act without compensation.

6. This syndicate is organized for the term of 1 year from its date, and shall expire at the close of business July 19, 1924, subject, however, to the right of the syndicate managers to extend the same for a further period of 1 year from that date by written notice to participants mailed on or before July 1, 1924. The syndicate managers may, however, terminate this syndicate at any time within the period or periods above specified.

7. On expiration or termination of the syndicate any property then held shall be distributed to participants pro rata upon or after payment of syndicate obligations.

The syndicate managers may from time to time distribute any profits from the syndicate operations, and the same shall be distributed pro rata to participants according to the full amount of their participations, whether full or part paid.

8. The syndicate managers shall have the right to cancel and forfeit to the syndicate any participation on failure of the participant to make payment of all or part of his participation when called in accordance with this agreement. The failure of any participant to perform any part of his obligations hereunder shall not relieve any other participant.

9. From time to time during the life of the syndicate the syndicate managers, in their discretion, may accept further subscriptions to and participations in the syndicate from then members or others upon such terms as to participation in previous profits, losses, expenses, and otherwise as the syndicate managers may determine.

10. All calls and notices upon or to participants shall be made or given by the syndicate managers, or their nominee or nominees, and shall be sufficient if mailed registered to the participants at their addresses of record with the syndicate managers or the registrar of certificates.

11. This agreement shall bind the parties signing and their respective successors, assigns, and personal representatives. It may be made and signed in several counterparts, but all such shall be taken as one original instrument.

In witness whereof the various parties hereto have subscribed their names and addresses and the amounts of their subscriptions as of the day and year first above written, and the syndicate managers have signed as such in acceptance of their obligations hereunder.

William C. Atwater, 1 Broadway, New York.....	\$350, 000
Thomas H. Wilson.....	25, 000
Charles S. Hebard.....	50, 000
Thomas W. Pursglove.....	25, 000
J. S. Wood.....	13, 000
C. F. Taylor.....	10, 000
G. M. Jones.....	10, 000
Transferred to A. H. Ferbert.	
J. S. Wood, trustee.....	10, 000
R. C. Hyatt.....	20, 000
A. H. Ferbert.....	10, 000
The Mid-Continent Securities Co., John Sherwin, vice president.....	50, 000

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 45

PITTSBURGH & WEST VIRGINIA SYNDICATE AGREEMENT, JULY 20, 1923—SYNDICATE AGREEMENT

This agreement made at Cleveland, Ohio, as of July 20, 1923, is to witness:

1. The subscribers hereto shall constitute a syndicate for the purpose of buying, selling, and trading in the securities of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. and/or any subsidiary company and/or property of whatever nature which the syndicate managers deem appropriate in connection with the first-stated purposes.

2. The subscribers hereto shall be participants in the syndicate in the amounts set opposite their respective signatures to this agreement, which amounts they agree to pay as hereinafter set forth. Participants shall elect at the time of signature to either pay their participation in full or to pay 50 percent thereof on the initial call and the balance on 30-day call or calls of the syndicate managers, and shall stand obligated according to such election

either to pay the full participation on the initial call or to pay 50 percent on the initial call and 50 percent on such further 30-day call or calls by the syndicate managers. Participants who do not pay in full on the initial call shall be from time to time charged with interest on their deferred payments from the date hereof at the rate of 6 percent per annum. All participations and calls are payable at the principal office of the Union Trust Co., Cleveland, Ohio, and/or at such other place or places as the syndicate managers shall designate.

3. The syndicate managers will issue to participants certificates of participation in the syndicate to the extent of their subscriptions and providing for endorsement of payments beyond 50 percent. Such certificates of participation shall be registered by the Union Trust Co., Cleveland, Ohio, which the syndicate managers have named as registrar of such certificates. Certificates of participation shall be in such form as the syndicate managers shall determine and shall be transferable only with the prior consent of the syndicate managers, unless fully paid, in which case they shall be freely transferable.

4. F. E. Taplin and J. R. Kraus are constituted "syndicate managers" under this agreement with the power to add one or more managers to their number at any time during the life of the syndicate. Upon resignation or death of a syndicate manager or managers the successor or successors shall be named by the survivor or survivors of the syndicate managers. The syndicate managers assume no personal obligation or liability in the management of the syndicate, and shall be liable only for willful bad faith in the conduct of the syndicate. If there shall at any time be more than two syndicate managers, the action of two shall control.

5. The syndicate managers are empowered with the entire and sole management and conduct of the syndicate, and without limitation upon such general power shall have the right to purchase, sell, repurchase, and resell any securities and/or other property hereinbefore referred to; to borrow for the account of the syndicate at such interest rate or rates and upon such terms as they may determine; to pledge or otherwise charge, as security for such borrowings, the assets of the syndicate in whole or part and including organization of the participants; to employ and pay such depositories, agents, counsel, and others in whatever capacity, as they may deem proper; all for the account of the syndicate and at its expense. The syndicate managers shall act without compensation.

6. This syndicate is organized for the term of 1 year from its date and shall expire at the close of business July 19, 1924; subject, however, to the right of the syndicate managers to extend the same for a further period of 1 year from that date by written notice to participants mailed on or before July 1, 1924. The syndicate managers may, however, terminate this syndicate at any time within the period or periods above specified.

7. On expiration or termination of the syndicate any property then held shall be distributed to participants pro rata upon or after payment of syndicate obligations.

The syndicate managers may, from time to time, distribute any profits from the syndicate operations, and the same shall be distributed pro rata to participants according to the full amount of their participations, whether full or part paid.

8. The syndicate managers shall have the right to cancel and forfeit to the syndicate any participation on failure of the participant to make payment of all or part of his participation when called in accordance with this agreement. The failure of any participant to perform any part of his obligations hereunder shall not relieve any other participant.

9. From time to time during the life of the syndicate the syndicate managers in their discretion may accept further subscriptions to and participations in the syndicate from then members or others, upon such terms as to participation in previous profits, losses, expenses, and otherwise, as the syndicate managers may determine.

10. All calls and notices upon or to participants shall be made or given by the syndicate managers or their nominees, and shall be sufficient if mailed registered to the participants at their addresses of record with the syndicate managers or the registrar of certificates.

11. This agreement shall bind the parties signing and their respective successors, assigns, and personal representatives. It may be made and signed in several counterparts, but such shall be taken as one original instrument.

In witness whereof the various parties hereto have subscribed their names and addresses and the amounts of their subscriptions as of the day and year

first above written, and the syndicate managers have signed as such in acceptance of their obligations hereunder.

	Amount
The Cleveland & Western Coal Co., F. E. Taplin, president, Cleveland, Ohio	\$2, 000, 000
F. E. Taplin, trustee, Cleveland, Ohio	600, 000
Ernest O. Lenihan, Cleveland, Ohio	50, 000
Charles P. Hutchins, Boston	200, 000
F. W. Paine, Boston	100, 000
W. P. Todd, New York	50, 000
Frank B. Stearns, Cleveland	30, 000
Charles H. Little, Cleveland, nothing paid (?)	
Oscar J. Lange, Cleveland	10, 000
A. W. Thompson, Cleveland	100, 000
R. S. Wood, Cleveland	20, 000
A. E. R. Schneider, Cleveland	20, 000
Crecelius & Phillips, Cleveland	40, 000
Do	30, 000
Alex. B. Uhrig, Milwaukee	100, 000
Samuel Pursglove, Cleveland	50, 000
C. F. Taplin, Cleveland	100, 000
George M. Rogers, Cleveland, Ohio	50, 000
Joseph Pursglove, Cleveland, Ohio	25, 000
R. H. Pigott, Cleveland, Ohio	10, 000
A. P. King, Cleveland, Ohio	40, 000
Adam Gross, Milwaukee	25, 000
Thomas W. Pursglove, Cleveland, Ohio	25, 000
H. W. Nethken, Pittsburgh	100, 000
William C. Atwater, New York	350, 000

F. E. TAPLIN,
J. R. KRAUS,
Syndicate Managers.

Mr. TAPLIN. These (indicating some other papers) are all extensions of the original agreement.

The CHAIRMAN. Is that syndicate any longer in existence now?

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, no. That is closed out.

The CHAIRMAN. That is all closed out?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes. That was all closed out when the stock was sold.

Mr. PECORA. Now the syndicate agreement bearing date July 20, 1923, describes the syndicate constituted by this agreement as being constituted for the purpose of buying, selling, and trading in the securities of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. and/or any subsidiary or affiliated company, and/or property of whatever nature which the syndicate managers deem appropriate in connection with the first stated purposes. Did all the subscribers to the three original syndicate agreements all bearing date July 20, 1923, fulfill their subscriptions?

Mr. TAPLIN. They all fulfilled their subscriptions, but some of them drew out of later renewals, Mr. Pecora. Now I gave you renewal I think of—

Mr. PECORA. I am coming to that.

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; they all paid in and fulfilled their subscriptions.

Mr. PECORA. Who organized this syndicate back on July 20, 1923?

Mr. TAPLIN. I did.

Mr. PECORA. At that time did you have any stock interest in the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co.?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; I had bought some stock. I bought this stock on the market. I did not buy it from any individual.

[After reading this testimony I find I was in error when I testified that I bought all of this stock on the market and did not buy it from any individual. I overlooked the fact that I did purchase approximately 25,000 shares direct from the Metropolitan Life Insurance Co. I am very sorry that this did not occur to me at the time I testified.]

Mr. PECORA. What was your business at the time of the organization of this syndicate?

Mr. TAPLIN. I was in the coal business.

Mr. PECORA. In the coal business?

Mr. TAPLIN. Coal mining.

Mr. PECORA. You had no connection with the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. until you became its president?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I was a stockholder before I became president.

Mr. PECORA. I mean you were not an officer or a director?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; I had nothing to do with it. I picked the stock up on the market with the money that I got from the people that I got to come into this syndicate.

Mr. PECORA. And was this syndicate organized for the purposes set forth in the first paragraph of the syndicate agreement dated July 20, 1923?

Mr. TAPLIN. The syndicate was organized to furnish money for the purposes of buying this stock.

Mr. PECORA. Well, what was it—a stock-trading syndicate?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; I would not say it was a stock-trading syndicate, because we wanted to get hold of the control of the railroad. We thought it was a valuable piece of railroad and we could sell it at a profit. At least we thought we could.

Mr. PECORA. Were any of the subscribers persons who were connected as directors or officers with any railroad company at that time?

Mr. TAPLIN. With any railroad company?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I will have to look over the list. I would say that Mr. Frank Ginn is a director, I know, in one railroad and an attorney for some railroad people.

Mr. PECORA. Is he a director in one of the Van Sweringen roads?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And also an attorney for the Van Sweringen interests?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; and he is an attorney for them, yes. But he is a personal friend of mine. It had nothing to do with this other railroad connection with them. Now, I will have to look over the rest of the list, Mr. Pecora, if you will pardon me just a minute.

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. There is not another man on there that has any connection that I know of with any railroad in the country.

The CHAIRMAN. What did the stock originally cost you, Mr. Taplin?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, our books are here. I had them all brought down, Senator Fletcher. I could not say positively, but it is all in the syndicate books which our treasurer here brought with him. There is a complete record of every transaction. I would not want to guess at what it cost, Senator Fletcher.

Mr. PECORA. Now, this syndicate as originally organized was to expire at the close of business on July 19, 1924. In other words, the syndicate was organized to operate for 1 year?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Upon the expiration of that year was the life of the syndicate extended by agreement among its various members?

Mr. TAPLIN. My recollection is that it was extended for 1 year without signing up a new agreement. Is there a provision in there about that? The reason I think—

Mr. PECORA. Yes; there is a provision. Paragraph no. 6 of the agreement in evidence reads as follows:

This syndicate is organized for the term of 1 year from its date and shall expire at the close of business July 19, 1924—

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA (continuing reading):

subject, however, to the right of the syndicate managers to extend the same for a further period of 1 year from that date by written notice to participants mailed on or before July 1, 1924.

Mr. TAPLIN. Now, that 1 year accounts for the reason that the next agreement you have is dated '25 and not '24.

Mr. PECORA. Well, was it extended by means of such written notice for a year?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. From July 20, 1924?

Mr. TAPLIN. It was.

Mr. PECORA. And then upon the expiration of that second year what happened?

Mr. TAPLIN. We had to write a new agreement up.

Mr. PECORA. Then it was extended by a written agreement for a further term of one year?

Mr. TAPLIN. I do not know what that one says, Mr. Pecora—how long a term. I think one year, is my recollection.

Mr. PECORA. Well, is this the extension agreement that was entered into in the year 1924, extending the life of the syndicate for one more year? [Handing paper to the witness.]

Mr. TAPLIN. It says here "That whereas under date of June 21, 1924, notice" to the subscribers was given as stated—then this was a new agreement, that it was to be extended until the 19th day of July, 1925. Signed by the syndicate managers.

Mr. PECORA. Is that the original extension agreement?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; that is the original extension agreement by the syndicate managers.

Mr. PECORA. I offer that in evidence.

Mr. TAPLIN. Now is this 1 of the 3 original copies, Mr. Pecora?

Mr. PECORA. Let me see that.

Mr. TAPLIN. I think it is 1 of the 3 that I had.

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. You want that.

Mr. PECORA. I have one before me.

Mr. TAPLIN. No; there were three parts to that.

Mr. PECORA. I know, but they all contain the same thing.

Mr. TAPLIN. You want only one?

Mr. PECORA. No. All three of them are in evidence.

Mr. TAPLIN. Don't you want that with them, too? That is one of the three.

Mr. PECORA. They are all in evidence. They have all been marked, and here they are before me, exhibits 43, 44, and 45, with the respective exhibit numbers on them.

Mr. TAPLIN. This is the extension agreement [handing same to Mr. Pecora].

Mr. PECORA. All right. I offer that in evidence and ask to have it spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted in evidence and entered on the record, and return the original thereof to the witness.

Mr. PECORA. This will also be returned to the witness.

(Original extension agreement of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Syndicate was received in evidence, marked "Committee exhibit 46 of July 6, 1933", and is here printed in the record in full, as follows:)

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 46

THE PITTSBURGH & WEST VIRGINIA SYNDICATE—EXTENSION AGREEMENT—
JUNE —, 1925

Whereas under date of July 20, 1923, a certain syndicate agreement was executed by the undersigned for the purpose of buying, selling, and trading in the securities of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. and/or any subsidiary or affiliated company and/or property of whatever nature which the syndicate managers deem appropriate in connection with the first stated purposes; and

Whereas under date of June 21, 1924, notice to all of the subscribers to said syndicate was given by the syndicate managers that they had elected to extend said agreement for a further period of 1 year from and after the 19th day of July 1924; and

Whereas it now is apparent that it is not to the advantage of the subscribers to said syndicate that the syndicate be liquidated and closed on July 20, but, rather, that said syndicate agreement should be extended for a further period of 1 year from said date.

Now, therefore, it is agreed by the undersigned, being the subscribers to said syndicate agreement, that said agreement be extended in full operation for a period of 1 year from and after the 19th day of July 1925, and be in full force and of the same effect during said extended period as during the preceding period.

In witness whereof the various parties hereto have subscribed their names the day and year first above written, and the syndicate managers have signed as such in acceptance of their obligations hereunder.

(Signed) F. E. TAPLIN,

(Signed) J. R. KBAUS,

Syndicate Managers.

THE PITTSBURGH & WEST VIRGINIA SYNDICATE EXTENSION AGREEMENT

Whereas under date of July 20, 1923, a certain syndicate agreement was executed by the undersigned for the purpose of buying, selling, and trading in the securities of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. and/or any subsidiary or affiliated company and/or property of whatever nature which the syndicate managers deem appropriate in connection with the first-stated purposes; and

Whereas under date of June 21, 1924, notice to all of the subscribers to said syndicate was given by the syndicate managers that they had elected to extend said agreement for a further period of 1 year from and after the 19th day of July 1924; and

Whereas it is not apparent that it is not to the advantage of the subscribers to said syndicate that the syndicate be liquidated and closed on July 20, 1925, but rather that said syndicate agreement should be extended for a further period of 1 year from said date:

Now, therefore, it is agreed by the undersigned, being the subscribers to said syndicate agreement, that said agreement be extended in full operation for a period of 1 year from and after the 19th day of July 1925 and be in full force and of the same effect during said extended period as during the preceding period.

In witness whereof the various parties hereto have subscribed their names the day and year first above written, and the syndicate managers have signed as such in acceptance of their obligations hereunder,

(Signed) CHAS. D. HEBARD.

CHARLES P. HUTCHINS.

C. F. TAPLIN

F. E. TAPLIN, *Trustee for F. E. Taplin,*
Jr.

F. E. TAPLIN, *Trustee for Clara L.*
Taplin

SAMUEL PURSGLOVE

THOS. W. PURSGLOVE

A. E. R. SCHNEIDER

A. W. THOMSON

R. C. HYATT

J. C. KRAUS

CHAS. A. PAUL

JOSEPH PURSGLOVE

A. P. KING

J. S. WOOD

J. S. WOOD, *trustee*

R. H. PIGOTT

C. F. TAYLOR

A. H. FERBERT

GEO. M. JAMES

WM. C. ATWATER

T. H. WILSON

W. PARSONS TODD

FRANK H. SMITH

R. C. MITCHELL

W. M. BALDWIN

R. B. BROWN

ADAM GROSS

ALEX B. UHRIG

GEO. M. ROGERS

FRANK B. STEARNS

THE CLEVELAND & WESTERN COAL Co.,
by P. LARSEN, *Secretary*

E. J. KULAS

H. W. NETHKEN

F. W. LOVELL

CRECELIUS & PHILLIPS L.P.C.

E. P. LENIHAN

THE MID-CONTINENT SECURITIES Co.,
JOHN A. SHERWIN, Jr., *President*

A. H. SCOVILLE

O. J. LANGE (and syndicate managers)

CHAS. D. HEBARD

F. W. PAINE

Mr. PECORA. The exhibit last offered in evidence, number 46, is the written agreement whereby this syndicate was extended for 1 year from and after the 19th of July 1925?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Upon the expiration of that year, namely, on or before July 19, 1926, was this syndicate account liquidated?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; it was continued year by year.

Mr. PECORA. By written agreement each time?

Mr. TAPLIN. By written agreements.

Mr. PECORA. Until when?

Mr. TAPLIN. Until the last written agreement is dated July 16, 1928, which I have here.

Mr. PECORA. Have you all the intermediate extension agreements between the one entered into in July 1925 and the last one, in 1928?

Mr. TAPLIN. I have one dated '28. I have one dated '27. I haven't any '26.

Mr. PECORA. Will you give me those that were entered into in 1927 and 1928, respectively?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes. [Producing same.]

Mr. PECORA. I offer them in evidence and ask that they be spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. Let them be admitted in evidence and spread upon the record, and the originals returned to the witness.

(Extension and release agreement re Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co., dated June 1, 1927, and extension agreement of same dated July 16, 1928, were received in evidence, marked, respectively, "Committee Exhibits 47 and 48 of July 6, 1933", and are here printed in the record in full as follows:)

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 47

EXTENSION AND RELEASE AGREEMENT RE THE PITTSBURGH & WEST VIRGINIA RAILWAY COMPANY, JUNE 1, 1927—EXTENSION AND RELEASE AGREEMENT

Whereas under date of July 20, 1923, a certain syndicate agreement was executed by the undersigned for the purpose of buying, selling, and trading in the securities of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. and/or any subsidiary or affiliated company and/or property of whatever nature which the syndicate managers deem appropriate in connection with the first stated purposes; and

Whereas under date of July 21, 1924, notice to all of the subscribers to said syndicate was given by the syndicate managers that they had elected to extend said agreement for a further period of 1 year from and after the 19th day of July 1924; and

Whereas in July 1925, and again in July 1926, extension agreements were executed by the syndicate managers and by all the subscribers to said original syndicate agreement, thereby extending said syndicate agreement in full operation for further periods of 1 year, the latter extension being for the period of 1 year from and after the 19th of July 1926; and

Whereas certain subscribers to said syndicate agreement hereinafter referred to as group A, have indicated that they desire to retire from said syndicate on July 31, 1927, upon receiving their proportion of the securities held by said syndicate managers, and upon payment by each of his or its share of the indebtedness of the syndicate; and

Whereas the other subscribers to said syndicate agreement, hereinafter referred to as group B, desire that said syndicate agreement be extended for a further period of 1 year from and after July 31, 1927; and

Whereas J. R. Kraus desires to retire as one of the syndicate managers, and the consensus of opinion of the subscribers included in group B is that there should be selected two additional syndicate managers to act with F. E. Taplin, the remaining syndicate manager, the names of E. P. Lenihan and C. F. Taplin being suggested in this connection;

Now, therefore, it is agreed by all of the undersigned, both in group A and in group B, that said syndicate agreement as heretofore extended shall be further extended in full operation until July 31, 1927, on which date an account shall be taken of the total indebtedness of the syndicate, and each subscriber's proportion of said indebtedness (after reducing same by the amount of funds on hand) shall be ascertained, and, upon payment to the syndicate managers of said amount so determined by each of the subscribers included in group A hereof, there shall be delivered to each of said subscribers his or its proportion of all securities held in the syndicate. Thereupon each of the subscribers included in group A hereof shall cease to have any further interest in said syndicate and shall stand released of all obligations in respect thereof. Furthermore, all acts of J. R. Kraus and F. E. Taplin, as syndicate managers, are hereby ratified and approved and they are hereby acquitted of all responsibility for acts done, as syndicate managers, up to and including said July 31, 1927.

It is agreed by all of the undersigned in group B that said syndicate agreement as heretofore and hereby extended shall be further extended in full operation for a period of one year from and after the 31st day of July 1927, and that it be in full force and of the same effect during said extended period as during the preceding period; and, further, that in the place of J. R. Kraus, resigning, Messrs. E. P. Lenihan and C. F. Taplin be, and they are hereby, appointed to act with F. E. Taplin as syndicate managers, such appointment to be effective from and after said July 31, 1927.

In witness whereof the various parties hereto have subscribed their names as of the 1st day of June 1927, and the syndicate managers have signed as such in acceptance of their obligations hereunder.

Group A subscribers:

A. H. SCOVILLE
THE MID-CONTINENT SECURITIES Co., by
R. C. HYATT, *Secretary*
J. R. KRAUS
R. C. MITCHELL

W. W. BALDWIN
R. C. HYATT
E. J. KULAS
FRANK H. SMITH
CHAS. P. HUTCHINS

Group B subscribers:
 A. W. THOMSON
 J. S. WOOD
 J. S. WOOD, *Trustee*
 R. H. PIGOTT

F. W. LOVELL
 CHAS. S. HEBARD
 CHAS. A. PAUL
 FRANK B. STEARNS

THOMAS H. WILSON.

Former syndicate manager:

J. R. KRAUSE

New syndicate manager:

E. P. LENIHAN.

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 48

EXTENSION AGREEMENT, PITTSBURGH & WEST VIRGINIA RAILWAY SYNDICATE, JULY 16, 1928—EXTENSION AGREEMENT

Whereas under date of July 20, 1923, a certain syndicate agreement was executed by the undersigned, and others, for the purpose of buying, selling, and trading in the securities of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co., and/or any subsidiary or affiliated company, and/or property of whatever nature which the syndicate managers should deem appropriate in connection with the first stated purposes; and

Whereas, under date of June 21, 1924, notice to all of the subscribers to said syndicate was given by the syndicate managers that they had elected to extend said agreement for a further period of 1 year from and after the 19th day of July 1924; and

Whereas in July 1925 and July 1926 extension agreements were executed by the syndicate managers, and by all of the subscribers to said original syndicate agreement, thereby extending said agreement in full operation for further periods of 1 year, the latter extension being for the period of 1 year from and after the 19th day of July 1926; and

Whereas in June 1927 an extension and release agreement was executed by virtue of which certain subscribers to said syndicate agreed to and thereafter did, on July 31, 1927, retire from said syndicate, receiving their proportion of the securities held by said syndicate managers and paying their shares of the indebtedness to said syndicate, the remaining subscribers to said syndicate agreement agreeing to the extension of said agreement for a further period of 1 year from and after July 31, 1927:

Now, therefore, it is agreed by the undersigned, being the remaining subscribers to said syndicate agreement, that said agreement be extended in full operation for the period of 1 year from and after the 31st day of July 1928, and be in full force and of the same effect during said extended period as during the preceding period.

It witness whereof the various parties hereto have subscribed their names as of the 16th day of July 1928, and the syndicate managers have signed, as such, in acceptance of their obligations hereunder.

North American Coal Corporation, by F. E. Taplin, president; F. E. Taplin, trustee for F. E. Taplin, Jr.; Frank B. Stearns; F. E. Taplin, trustee for Clara Louise Taplin; R. B. Brown; Geo. M. Rogers; A. E. R. Schneider, trustee for Clara B. Schneider, Cletus P. Schneider, Esther B. Schneider, Clare A. Schneider, and Ruth L. Burke; Oscar J. Lange; A. P. King; W. Parsons Todd; J. S. Wood; J. S. Wood, trustee; A. H. Ferbert; R. H. Piggott; Creelius & Phillips, by Victor B. Phillips; Samuel Pursglove; Thos. W. Pursglove; Chas. A. Paul; F. W. Paine; Wilclara Investment Co., J. W. Gross, treasurer; Alex. B. Uhrig; E. P. Lenihan; Thomas H. Wilson.

Mr. PECORA. What object did you have in organizing this syndicate in 1923?

Mr. TAPLIN. To make money on the purchase of the stock.

Mr. PECORA. Was it to make money by purchasing and reselling the stock in the market?

Mr. TAPLIN. No.

Mr. PECORA. Well, how did you expect to do it?

Mr. TAPLIN. I expected the railroad would be worth a lot more money and could be made to show lots bigger earnings than it had been showing. The stock was selling very cheap when we started to buy it. They hadn't been making much money.

Mr. PECORA. Was it your hope to hold the stock for an appreciation and then sell?

Mr. TAPLIN. It was.

Mr. PECORA. Now in 1926, during the life of this syndicate, you say you commenced having conferences with General Atterbury and Mr. County, both of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., looking toward the acquisition by the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. of stock interest of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co.?

Mr. TAPLIN. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. And you are unable to tell us whether those conferences were initiated by you or whether they were had on the initiation of General Atterbury or Mr. County?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; I would not say which started the conversation, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. What was the subject of the conversations?

Mr. TAPLIN. They wanted to buy the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co.—the control of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. I was willing to sell it. But apparently our minds did not meet as to the price. That seemed to be the only difficulty.

Mr. PECORA. Did those negotiations continue over a period of 3 years until the sale was consummated to the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. Off and on, but sometimes maybe it would not be discussed for 6 months.

Mr. PECORA. And each time you acted in behalf of the members of the syndicate whose names appear in these various agreements that have been offered in evidence?

Mr. TAPLIN. And others who had Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway stock.

Mr. PECORA. Well, when did the others come in? Did they come in by virtue of any written agreement?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Will you produce the written agreement in question?

Mr. TAPLIN. I had an agreement that if a man was not in the syndicate and he had stock, I permitted him to tie it up to me under an agreement—or a similar agreement which I will read to you.

Mr. PECORA. Just produce it and I will offer it.

Mr. TAPLIN. They are all alike, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. Just produce one of them then and I will have it spread on the record.

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes. [Handing same to Mr. Pecora.]

Mr. PECORA. I offer in evidence a document produced by the witness consisting of a letter addressed to Mr. John J. Atwater, under date of June 9, 1927, and I ask that it be spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted and placed in the record.

(Letter addressed to Mr. John J. Atwater, June 9, 1927, was received in evidence, marked "Committee exhibit no. 49 of July 6, 1933", and is here printed in the record in full, as follows:)

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT 49

FRANK E. TAPLIN,
Cleveland, Ohio, June 9, 1927.

Mr. JOHN J. ATWATER,
New York City.

DEAR SIR: Confirming our talk, it is understood that if you will agree not to dispose of your holdings of stock in the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. during the life of the syndicate, then such holdings of stock shall be treated the same as the stock in the syndicate; that is, upon any disposition of the stock held by the syndicate as a part of any transaction passing control of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. (a majority of the stock of said company being held by the syndicate and other parties with whom agreements similar to this are had), your stock shall be included in any such transaction, and you shall receive the same price for your stock as is received for the syndicate's holdings.

Will you kindly indicate your agreement with this method of holding and disposing of your stock in the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co., and oblige?

Yours very truly,

F. E. TAPLIN.

The above represents my understanding and I agree not to sell my holdings of stock in the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. except in accordance therewith.

JOHN J. ATWATER.

(1,100 shares.)

Mr. PECORA. Now, you sent letters similar in form to various other persons?

Mr. TAPLIN. On this list of sellers.

Mr. PECORA. On the list of sellers of this block of 222,930 shares?

Mr. TAPLIN. Who were not in the syndicate.

Mr. PECORA. Who were not members of the original syndicate?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; that is right.

Mr. PECORA. And all those letters were similar in form to this one that is marked "Exhibit No. 49"?

Mr. TAPLIN. Absolutely. They are all here. A bunch of them.

Mr. PECORA. For the benefit of the committee I will read Exhibit 49. Written on the letterhead of Frank E. Taplin, Cleveland, Ohio. [Reading:]

JUNE 9, 1927.

Mr. JOHN J. ATWATER,
New York City.

DEAR SIR: Confirming our talk, it is understood that if you will agree not to dispose of your holdings of stock in the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. during the life of the syndicate, then such holdings of stock shall be treated the same as the stock in the syndicate; that is, upon any disposition of the stock held by the syndicate as a part of any transaction passing control of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. (a majority of the stock of said company being held by the syndicate and other parties with whom agreements similar to this are had), your stock shall be included in any such transaction, and you shall receive the same price for your stock as is received for the syndicate's holdings.

Will you kindly indicate your agreement with this method of holding and disposing of your stock in the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co., and oblige.

Yours very truly,

F. E. TAPLIN.

(Description at the bottom of the letter, Exhibit 49, reads as follows:)

The above represents my understanding and I agree not to sell my holdings of stock in the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. except in accordance therewith.

JOHN J. ATWATER.

(1,100 shares.)

Mr. PECORA. Now were these letters sent out at about the time or date borne by Exhibit 49, namely, June 9, 1927?

Mr. TAPLIN. They are all here. June, '27. June, '27. December, '27. June, '27. June, '27. June 15, '27. Here is one that is dated June 29, but that is a transfer from the Willclare Investment Co. Here is one June, '27, signed by Mr. Hebard on stock which he had purchased and which was in the syndicate, and then he bought this afterwards. This was signed on January 14, 1929. And so it made no difference to me, Mr. Pecora, if they came in in June 1929 or May, or any month.

Mr. PECORA. No, I know that. I wanted to just get the history of the thing. Now, Mr. Taplin, the members of the syndicate as organized in 1923 acquired through the managers of the syndicate about what proportion of the total outstanding capital stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co.?

Mr. TAPLIN. Now Mr. Larson can you tell me? [After conferring.] He said the books will show 109,000 shares, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. Well, that was less than a majority, was it not?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. The total outstanding shares were a little over 300,000?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; but I had some that was not in the syndicate.

Mr. PECORA. At the time of the end of the first year of the life of this syndicate, namely, on July 19, 1924, after the syndicate had been in operation for 1 year, what proportion of the outstanding stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. was owned or had been acquired by the syndicate or its individual members?

Mr. TAPLIN. I think about one half, because I know from the very beginning I had control of half of the stock.

Mr. PECORA. That included the holdings of yourself and members of your family?

Mr. TAPLIN. And with the syndicate. It is stock that I had control of that nobody could get.

Mr. PECORA. Was it in 1927 that you commenced sending out letters similar to the one marked "Exhibit 49"?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, that seems to be the earliest date on any of these agreements, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. From that would you conclude that you did not do anything about tying up the stock of other holders who were not members of your syndicate or participants therein until on or about June 1927?

Mr. TAPLIN. I assume that is correct. I could not have had control of it unless I had the agreement signed.

Mr. PECORA. Yes. Now, as a result of entering into the agreements with these stockholders who were not members of the syndicate, which agreements are similar to Exhibit 49, what proportion of the

total outstanding capital stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. did you succeed in getting control of?

Mr. TAPLIN. Between 70 and 75 percent.

Mr. PECORA. According to Exhibit No. 49 it was intended by you as manager of this syndicate to acquire control of a majority of the stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. for the purpose of selling it to someone else who wanted to acquire control of that railway company?

Mr. TAPLIN. That is right.

Mr. PECORA. And that someone was the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, there were what we call four trunk lines in the country, in the eastern division, that is, the Pennsylvania, the New York Central, B. & O., and the Van Sweringen Co. And I think the property was—my idea was that the property was desirable to each one of those four systems.

Mr. PECORA. It would form a desirable part of any one of those four systems?

Mr. TAPLIN. Any one of the four.

Mr. PECORA. Which of those systems did you have any negotiations or conversations with at any time during the life of this syndicate?

Mr. TAPLIN. I had conversations with the New York Central.

Mr. PECORA. When?

Mr. TAPLIN. I cannot give you the date. I never made any—

Mr. PECORA. Was it before you commenced discussing the question with General Atterbury and Mr. County?

Mr. TAPLIN. I would not want to say whether it was before 1926 or about that time, but I know I had discussions with the New York Central. I have no record of the date.

Mr. PECORA. With what officer or officers of the New York Central Railroad Co. system did you have those conversations?

Mr. TAPLIN. With Mr. Crowley and Mr. Ingalls.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Crowley was the president?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Ingalls held one of them?

Mr. TAPLIN. He is vice president. The conversations with them, though, didn't amount to much. They were rather general in nature.

Mr. PECORA. Did they encourage you in the belief that you might eventually sell these holdings to that system?

Mr. TAPLIN. I would not say they ever encouraged me; no.

Mr. PECORA. With what other railroad officials did you discuss the matter of selling these holdings of your syndicate in the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co.?

Mr. TAPLIN. The Van Sweringen people had discussions with me at times.

Mr. PECORA. Were they of an encouraging nature to you?

Mr. TAPLIN. I would not say they were overly encouraging.

Mr. PECORA. In order to sell control of the railroad company it would only be necessary for you to sell 51 percent of its capital stock, wouldn't it?

Mr. TAPLIN. That is right.

Mr. PECORA. Well, why did you tie up stockholders in the form of agreements corresponding to Exhibit 49 to the extent of 75 percent of the total outstanding stock?

Mr. TAPLIN. To get as much stock as I could under control. The more I could get under control the better.

Mr. PECORA. The better for whom?

Mr. TAPLIN. Better for me.

Mr. PECORA. Why?

Mr. TAPLIN. There is less opportunity of anybody buying some of it on the market; less opportunity of those people throwing it around on the stock market. It is always bad for the stock.

Mr. PECORA. Then you wanted to buy the stock up so it would not be thrown on the market in a fashion that would depress the price of it?

Mr. TAPLIN. I think undoubtedly that had something to do with it.

Mr. PECORA. And you did succeed in tying up, not only through the holdings of your syndicate but through agreements in the form of Exhibit 49, something like three fourths of the outstanding stock?

Mr. TAPLIN. Almost three fourths.

The CHAIRMAN. How much did the members of the syndicate pay for the stock?

Mr. TAPLIN. How much did they pay, Senator Fletcher?

The CHAIRMAN. Yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. Mr. Pecora asked me, I think, or somebody, a few minutes ago, and I said I would not want to give the figures, because our treasurer has them all here in the books of the syndicate, all of the facts in regard to it, cost, and what became of it.

The CHAIRMAN. Did they pay different prices, or did they all pay the same price?

Mr. TAPLIN. He said the stock that the syndicate bought worked out about \$52.50 a share.

Mr. PECORA. That would be the average?

Mr. TAPLIN. That is the average.

Mr. PECORA. \$52.50 a share.

The CHAIRMAN. The syndicate members drew dividends on that stock, did they? Did it pay dividends?

Mr. TAPLIN. I think so. They didn't when we purchased it, Senator Fletcher. The road was not making any money when we purchased it in 1923, but we got it in shape where it was making good money and paying dividends.

[Addressing an associate:] What year did it commence to pay dividends? When? 1926, he says, we started to pay dividends, 6 percent dividends.

The CHAIRMAN. You were president of the road?

Mr. TAPLIN. In 1923. That was 3 years later. We started to pay dividends in 1926.

Mr. PECORA. Did you discuss terms back in 1926 with General Atterbury or Mr. County; that is, the terms on which your syndicate would sell its holdings of Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. stock?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; we were always discussing terms; and the people I talked with never talked high enough. They always thought I had too big ideas, and we never could quite get together.

Mr. PECORA. What prices did you discuss? At what price did you eventually offer the syndicate holdings to General Atterbury or Mr. County?

Mr. TAPLIN. The cheapest price I recollect that I ever talked about immediately preceding the time we made this deal was \$200 a share. That was the only price I ever talked prior to this time.

Mr. PECORA. You first mentioned that price at what time?

Mr. TAPLIN. Whenever I talked with anybody it was always \$200 a share or I was not interested.

Mr. PECORA. That is, beginning in 1926 you discussed and quoted a price of \$200 a share for the syndicate holdings. What was the price in the market in 1926?

Mr. TAPLIN. My recollection is that about the most it ever sold in the market was not much over \$170, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. No; in 1926.

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I think probably around \$170. That is my recollection now. I don't keep track of the stock market.

Senator TOWNSEND. It was listed on the stock exchange?

Mr. TAPLIN. It was listed on the market.

Mr. PECORA. Did the syndicate maintain a trading account in this stock during its lifetime?

Mr. TAPLIN. To a slight extent but not much; no.

Mr. PECORA. Who were the brokers that handled it?

Mr. TAPLIN. McDonnell & Co. bought stock for me, and in addition to McDonnell & Co., Hendrickson & Co. bought stock for me; and I think I probably did more trading personally than anybody else did.

Senator GOLDSBOROUGH. Wasn't McDonnell one of the syndicate?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes. No; I beg your pardon, Senator Goldsborough; I don't think he was a member of the syndicate.

Mr. PECORA. You gave us the name of McDonnell & Co. as owners of 9,350 shares.

Mr. TAPLIN. I do not think he was a member of that syndicate.

Mr. PECORA. He came in on some kind of an agreement something like Exhibit 49?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; he came in by agreement.

Mr. PECORA. Have you records of the trading that was done in the stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. on behalf of the syndicate or its members?

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, absolutely. It must be on their books.

Mr. PECORA. Will you produce it?

Mr. TAPLIN (addressing Mr. Larson). Doesn't this include the purchases of the 109,000 shares?

Mr. LARSON. Yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. These were not trading purchases. You understand, Mr. Pecora, this stock was all bought in the stock market; and, just as I thought, Mr. Larson has included that and mixed it up with what you call trading, buying, and selling for profit. These are the purchases of the stock for the syndicate account, and here are the two accounts he has. He has one with McDonnell & Co. and one with Paine-Weber & Co.

What is the date of this, Mr. Larson? It says November 29. What year? Here is 1924, 1923.

Mr. PECORA. 1923 goes right through 1924.

Senator TOWNSEND. Those were all purchases.

Mr. TAPLIN. 1924-1926. Now I think you will find, Mr. Pecora, that most all of these purchases were the original stock purchases and

not trading accounts, if you will check the dates. If they were trading accounts, there would have to be some sales slips there. Are they sales as well as purchase slips or are they all purchase slips?

Mr. PECORA. They are both purchases and sales. Both purchases and sales, according to the slips you have given me, Mr. Taplin.

Mr. TAPLIN. Are there any sales in all that big bulk of those entire transactions in 1923 or 1924, or are they all purchases?

Mr. PECORA. Let me see. Can't you tell us from your own memory as the syndicate manager?

Mr. TAPLIN. I could not say what we did. That is the reason I brought the books all here, so as to be sure.

Mr. PECORA. Can't you tell us whether or not this syndicate maintained more or less active trading account during its life?

Mr. TAPLIN. I think very little trading, Mr. Pecora. He said there was not any trading after 1926 at all in the account. Here are the Paine-Weber purchases [handing documents to Mr. Pecora].

Senator TOWNSEND. They were all purchases and no sales?

Mr. TAPLIN. It was not a trading account. It was a purchase made for the purpose of selling at a profit, not a trading account.

Senator GOLDSBOROUGH. You mean a purchase outright and then not a resale?

Mr. TAPLIN. No. It was not a trading account, buying and selling account, to make profit buying and selling stock. It was purchased with the idea of selling it at a profit all together in one lump, as was done.

The CHAIRMAN. Did you talk with the B. & O. people in connection with that?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; I never talked to the B. & O. people about it, Senator Fletcher.

Mr. PECORA. Did you talk with the Van Sweringens about it?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. About the same time that you were having the conversations with the Pennsylvania Railroad officers?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; off and on over 3 or 4 years.

Mr. PECORA. When for the first time did anyone connected with the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. tell you that his company was interested in buying these shares from you and your associates?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, at least as far back as 1925 or 1926.

Mr. PECORA. What did they say to you?

Mr. TAPLIN. Said they ought to own that railroad.

Mr. PECORA. And they were willing to buy the majority of its outstanding stock from you and your associates?

Mr. TAPLIN. We never could agree on a price.

Mr. PECORA. What price was discussed by you and what price by them?

Mr. TAPLIN. They never discussed any price. I discussed \$200, and they always said it was too high.

Mr. PECORA. They never quoted any price to you, never made any offer?

Mr. TAPLIN. No.

Mr. PECORA. When for the first time was any offer made to you?

Mr. TAPLIN. I guess the first definite time we ever got together was 1929 when I sold it.

Mr. PECORA. When did you sell it in 1929; as of what date was the sale effected?

Mr. TAPLIN. Sometime in September. I don't know the exact date.

Mr. PECORA. September 1929?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Did you have any written agreement?

Mr. TAPLIN. No.

Mr. PECORA. Covering that sale?

Mr. TAPLIN. No, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Who did you make the sale to?

Mr. TAPLIN. I talked to General Atterbury, and I believe Judge Heiserman, with Mr. Lee.

Mr. PECORA. Was General Atterbury at that time connected with the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, I was dealing with him as the trustee of the Pennroad Corporation, not as the president of the Pennsylvania Railroad.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Lee was then the president of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And what relationship did Judge Heiserman bear to the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. He was their counsel, I understood.

Mr. PECORA. When did you first take up negotiations with those gentlemen representing the Pennroad Corporation to sell to that corporation this stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia?

Mr. TAPLIN. Late in the spring; I would guess about May, possibly.

Mr. PECORA. Have you any written matter of any kind consisting of letters or agreements or memoranda that would throw any light on the course of these negotiations with the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. Not at all. None whatever, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. They were all conducted by word of mouth?

Mr. TAPLIN. All word of mouth.

Mr. PECORA. Who took the initiative in connection with the transaction with the Pennroad Corporation, you or the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. I think I did.

Mr. PECORA. Were you a stockholder of the Pennroad Corporation at any time?

Mr. TAPLIN. No.

Mr. PECORA. Were any of your associates in the syndicate stockholders of the Pennroad Corporation at any time prior to the making of this sale?

Mr. TAPLIN. Not that I ever heard of.

Mr. PECORA. What price did you discuss with these gentlemen representing the Pennroad Corporation at the inception of your dealings and negotiations with them?

Mr. TAPLIN. At the inception—do you mean in May 1929?

Mr. PECORA. In May 1929 if that was the date.

Mr. TAPLIN. That is, the negotiations that led up to the sale?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. What price did I—

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. I think I conceded that if I could not get \$200 I might take a little less.

Mr. PECORA. How much less?

Mr. TAPLIN. I don't think I said how much less until September 1929.

Mr. PECORA. What price did they quote to you?

Mr. TAPLIN. I don't think they ever made me an offer. I am very sure they never did.

Mr. PECORA. When did you finally agree with them on the price at which the stock was sold to the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. Sometime in September 1929.

Mr. PECORA. Have you a memorandum of the date?

Mr. TAPLIN. No, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Have you any recollection of the date?

Mr. TAPLIN. No. It did not make any particular impression on me as to the date in September. I know it was in September.

Mr. PECORA. How do you know it was in September?

Mr. TAPLIN. Because it was about a month or so prior to the time that the stock was delivered. I facilitated the delivery just as much as I reasonably could after I made the deal.

Mr. PECORA. Did you understand at the time you commenced these negotiations with the Pennroad Corporation that that corporation represented Pennsylvania Railroad Co. interests?

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, certainly.

Mr. PECORA. When did you first have any formal business transactions with the Pennroad Corporation of any kind whatsoever?

Mr. TAPLIN. I think about June 1929. I had better look that up. I believe in June 1929.

Mr. PECORA. What was the nature of that transaction?

Mr. TAPLIN. I borrowed some money from them.

Mr. PECORA. Was that the first business transaction you ever had with them?

Mr. TAPLIN. First I ever had with them.

Mr. PECORA. How much did you borrow from them?

Mr. TAPLIN. I borrowed \$1,950,000.

Mr. PECORA. Did you negotiate that loan yourself?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. You used no broker or other intermediary?

Mr. TAPLIN. No. I got it direct.

Mr. PECORA. Whom did you negotiate that loan with?

Mr. TAPLIN. Mr. John County.

Mr. PECORA. He was then a director of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. I think he was, as far as I know.

Mr. PECORA. And a friend of yours at that time?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Had you previously discussed with Mr. County, who, I believe, you testified earlier was also vice president and a director of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., the matter of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. buying this control stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co.?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; not in 1929, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. Had you at any time prior to this loan transaction—

Mr. TAPLIN (interposing). Yes; I think—

Mr. PECORA (continuing). Had any such discussion with Mr. County?

Mr. TAPLIN. After the purchase of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. I think I did in 1926 and 1927.

Mr. PECORA. 1926 and 1927. Did you understand that the Penn-road Corporation was a corporation engaged in the business, among other things, of lending money when you negotiated this loan in June 1929?

Mr. TAPLIN. They might if it was to their advantage to loan it for some purpose that was advantageous to them.

Mr. PECORA. How was this loan advantageous to them?

Mr. TAPLIN. That is quite a long story, Mr. Pecora; but I will endeavor to explain it.

Mr. PECORA. If you will, please.

Mr. TAPLIN. I also, in addition to the Pittsburgh & West Virginia, with some associates, owned a majority of the preferred and common stock of the Wheeling & Lake Erie Railroad.

Mr. PECORA. Were those associates the same individuals or were they represented among the individuals who constituted this syndicate?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; but to a much smaller extent.

Mr. PECORA. Have you their names?

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, yes.

Mr. PECORA. Have you a list of them?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; I have no list of them, because it has nothing to do with this transaction. You did not ask me to bring anything except these papers. I am just trying to relate now how they were interested.

Mr. PECORA. Go ahead then.

Mr. TAPLIN. With a few other friends I owned a majority of the preferred and common stock of the Wheeling & Lake Erie Railroad, and there had been a big scrap on to get the control of that road. It was very vital to me to keep—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). Who were the participants in that scrap?

Mr. TAPLIN. The Van Sweringen interests and myself. They got the prior lien stock and I got the majority of the preferred and common stock. I did not want that majority of preferred and common broken.

When I was buying the Wheeling & Lake Erie stock a man came to see me by the name of Reynolds from Louisville, and he said that he had 32,500 shares of Wheeling & Lake Erie stock—I believe that was it; it was approximately that—which they owned, and they would like to make an agreement to tie their stock up with what I had and it would make a majority.

Mr. PECORA. How much of the stock did you and your associates have in Wheeling & Lake Erie then?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, outside of this lot of 32,500 shares I had approximately 190 to 195 thousand shares.

Mr. PECORA. And that represented what proportion of the outstanding stock of that road?

Mr. TAPLIN. By adding these 32,500 it makes about 225,000 shares. There are 440,000 shares of common and preferred outstanding. So I figured it just gave me the edge by a few thousand shares by tying up his 32,500.

Mr. PECORA. That gave you control of more than 51 percent?

Mr. TAPLIN. Common and preferred stock only.

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. I made an agreement with Reynolds. There were two brothers. I don't know whether I have all of the agreements here, but it seems to be the whole file. I made an agreement in which they tied their stock up with mine.

Mr. PECORA. What was the date of that agreement with the Reynolds Bros.?

Mr. TAPLIN. February 1, 1927.

Mr. PECORA. Now go ahead with your narration.

Mr. TAPLIN. Along about May or June, I don't know the exact date, Reynolds Bros. came to me and said this agreement was running out and they thought that they would sell their stock to the Van Sweringens.

Mr. PECORA. Along about May or June of what year?

Mr. TAPLIN. 1929. They thought they would sell this stock to the Van Sweringens, and I told them I thought they would not; that I had an agreement with them. They said the agreement had expired. Well, I—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). Will you produce the agreement you had with Reynolds Brothers?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes. It is right here. Do you want that newspaper clipping that is attached to it [handing document to Mr. Pecora]?

Mr. PECORA. It is not part of the agreement, is it?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; it is not.

Mr. PECORA. We will see it, anyway.

Mr. TAPLIN. He does not want that. That is how they hooked me. I put that on for that reason. You don't want that clipping, Mr. Pecora.

(Mr. Pecora perused the document and handed the clipping back to Mr. Taplin.)

The CHAIRMAN. You were telling us they called on you and spoke about selling to the Van Sweringens, and you said you thought they would not. Now proceed with that.

Mr. TAPLIN. The result of it was that I had to buy their stock at their price to keep the control. Do you want me to continue, Mr. Pecora?

Mr. PECORA. I just want to read this for a moment. [After perusing document further.] Now, the agreement that you entered into with the Reynolds brothers is dated February 1, 1927. This is a copy of it?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir. Is it signed?

Mr. PECORA. Is this a true and correct copy? This is not signed at all. It is a blank copy.

Mr. TAPLIN. That is a true and correct copy or it would not be in my files.

Mr. PECORA. I offer it in evidence and ask that it be spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted and entered in the record.

Mr. TAPLIN. It is the only one I have. So I guess it is a copy.

(The agreement, dated February 1, 1927, between Frank E. Taplin and Clarence Reynolds, was received in evidence, and appears in the record in full, as follows:)

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT 50

Agreement made February 1, 1927, between Frank E. Taplin, of Cleveland, Ohio, hereinafter called the "buyer", party of the first part, and Clarence Reynolds, of Louisville, Ky., on behalf of himself and his associates, hereinafter called the "seller", party of the second part, witnesseth:

Whereas the buyer now owns and controls large amount of the common and preferred stocks of the Wheeling & Lake Erie Railway Co.; and

Whereas the seller and his said associates now own and control upwards of 30,000 shares of common stock and upwards of 5,000 shares of preferred stock of said Wheeling & Lake Erie Railway Co.; and

Whereas the buyer wishes to associate the seller and the seller's associates with himself in all matters involving action on the part of the buyer as a stockholder in said Wheeling & Lake Erie Railway Co.: Now, therefore, this agreement witnesseth:

1. The seller, on behalf of himself and his associates agrees to cooperate with the buyer and to support the plans of the buyer with respect to voting stock of the said Wheeling & Lake Erie Railway Co. to the extent of not less than 30,000 shares of common, nor less than 5,000 shares of preferred stock. It being the purpose of this clause that the seller and his associates shall make available to the buyer said minimum number of shares for all intents and purposes as if the buyer had the actual voting rights of said stock for the period of this agreement.

2. In consideration of the performance by the seller of the foregoing agreement, the buyer agrees that he will at the option of the seller and his associates purchase 30,000 shares of said common stock and 5,000 shares of said preferred stock at the price of \$50 per share on the 1st day of February 1928, provided the seller shall give notice in writing to the buyer of its election to exercise this option 60 days prior to said date.

3. In consideration of the foregoing agreement on the part of the seller, the buyer further agrees that, if he shall during the period of this contract consummate any plan of sale or reorganization involving the buyer's shares of said Wheeling & Lake Erie Railway Co. stock, he will offer to the seller the opportunity to participate in such sale or reorganization on the same terms as the buyer.

4. This contract shall cover the period of 12 months beginning February 1, 1927.

In witness whereof the parties hereto have signed this agreement in four counterparts at New York City, N.Y., this 1st day of February 1927.

In presence of:

Mr. PECORA. You may continue now.

Mr. TAPLIN. To make a long story short, I had to buy their stock for \$3,900,000 or let it go the other way. So I agreed to buy it.

Mr. PECORA. And did you buy it?

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, yes; I bought it.

Mr. PECORA. When?

Mr. TAPLIN. June 1929.

Mr. PECORA. That was the 30,000 shares?

Mr. TAPLIN. Thirty-two thousand five hundred.

Mr. PECORA. Of the common, and 5,000 shares of the preferred?

Mr. TAPLIN. I bought 32,500 shares.

Mr. PECORA. Of the common?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; some preferred and some common.

The CHAIRMAN. You bought it at how much a share?

Mr. TAPLIN. \$120 a share; 32,500 shares, \$3,900,000. I agreed to pay them, not having any money, one half cash and a note for the other half.

Mr. PECORA. When did you make that agreement with the Reynolds brothers to buy that stock?

Mr. TAPLIN. Here in an agreement signed by myself and Mr. Reynolds dated—no; that is an extension. June 20, is that correct? Nineteenth day of June 1929.

Mr. PECORA. Nineteenth day of June 1929. Have you got the agreement with you, or a copy of it?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Will you produce it, please, for the record?

(Mr. Taplin produced the document as requested.)

Mr. PECORA. I offer the agreement produced by the witness in evidence and ask it be spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted and entered in the record.

(The agreement dated June 19, 1929, between C. K. Reynolds and Frank E. Taplin, was received in evidence marked "Committee Exhibit No. 51", and is copied in the record in full as follows:)

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT 51

This agreement made this 19th day of June 1929, by and between C. K. Reynolds and Frank E. Taplin

Witnesseth: That for and in consideration of \$1, receipt of which is hereby acknowledged by each of the parties hereto, C. K. Reynolds hereby agrees to sell and Frank E. Taplin hereby agrees to purchase 11,550 shares, more or less, of 6 percent preferred stock of the Wheeling & Lake Erie Railway Co., and 20,950 shares, more or less, of common stock of the Wheeling & Lake Erie Railway, at the price of \$120 a share, payable as follows: One half of said amount to be paid in cash upon receipt of said stock and one half is to be evidenced by a negotiable promissory note of even date with this agreement made by Frank E. Taplin and guaranteed by the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co., payable to C. K. Reynolds 12 months after date, bearing interest at 6 percent, which said note is to be secured by the deposit by Frank E. Taplin with C. K. Reynolds of 20,000 shares of said stock sold to Frank E. Taplin under this agreement. It is understood that Frank E. Taplin may anticipate the payment of said note at any time and receive the stock held as collateral upon payment thereof.

Witness the following signatures and seals:

[SEAL]

(Signed) FRANK E. TAPLIN.

[SEAL]

(Signed) C. K. REYNOLDS.

Mr. PECORA. Now, with one hundred and ninety thousand and odd shares of the Wheeling & Lake Erie Railway Co. which you have referred to, owned at that time by you and the members of this syndicate—

Mr. TAPLIN (interposing.) No; owned by me and a few other individuals not in that syndicate.

Mr. PECORA. Were any of them in the syndicate?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, you understand it had nothing to do with the Pittsburgh & West Virginia.

Mr. PECORA. It was a separate transaction?

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, entirely separate. No connection. There may have been two or three that were syndicate members.

Mr. PECORA. Can you tell the committee the average cost to you and your associates of the acquisition of those one hundred and

ninety thousand and odd shares of Wheeling & Lake Erie Railway Co. stock?

Mr. TAPLIN. I could only guess at it.

Mr. PECORA. What is your best guess?

Mr. TAPLIN. \$65.

Mr. PECORA. Was it purchased in the open market from time to time?

Mr. TAPLIN. All of it.

Mr. PECORA. Through what brokers?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I guess McDonnell & Co. and Hendrickson & Co.

Mr. PECORA. All right. Now will you go ahead with your narrative?

Mr. TAPLIN. We made this agreement and I purchased their stock.

Mr. PECORA. Well.

Mr. TAPLIN. Agreeing to give them half in cash, half in a note for 1 year. I did not have any cash, so I had to borrow the cash.

Mr. PECORA. You borrowed it from the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. I knew the Pennsylvania and Pennroad people would not want the Van Sweringens to get the Wheeling & Lake Erie stock. I told them just what Reynolds was doing with me. It would be a big accommodation if they would loan me some money for a year, with which I would buy the stock.

Mr. PECORA. How was it going to be beneficial to the interests of the Pennroad Corporation to have you buy stock of the Wheeling & Lake Erie Railroad at the time this loan was made?

Mr. TAPLIN. I don't guess they wanted the Van Sweringen people to get control of the Wheeling—I imagine; I don't know. I would not, if I had been in their place.

Mr. PECORA. Up to that time, up to the time of the negotiation of this loan, you had not reached any agreement or understanding with the Pennroad Corporation that it would buy from you and your associates the stock that you owed in the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railroad?

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, no; it was an entirely separate deal; no connection between the two. That came later in the fall.

Mr. PECORA. I know that. Did you tell them, when you negotiated this loan of \$1,950,000, that you wanted the loan to enable you to buy these 30-odd thousand shares of Wheeling & Lake Erie stock from the Reynolds brothers?

Mr. TAPLIN. I told Mr. County all about what it was for, and he understood it explicitly.

Mr. PECORA. Did you have then any agreement, either expressed or implied, with the Pennroad Corporation that you and your associates who bought this Wheeling & Lake Erie Railroad Co. stock would turn it over to the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. No. I have it today. We never turned it over to the Pennroad. I own the stock. I paid this loan. I own the stock now.

[After reading this testimony, I want to straighten out what might leave an erroneous impression. When I paid the loan from the Pennroad Corporation, I did it as trustee for one of my children, which I considered the same thing on account of my power of attorney to act for them.]

Mr. PECORA. That was an interest-bearing loan, of course?

Mr. TAPLIN. Sure.

Mr. PECORA. Six percent per annum?

Mr. TAPLIN. Mr. County never loaned any money for less than 6 percent. I have a copy of the note here.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Lee, may I ask you if you will let me have the file covering this transaction that you had here last Friday and which you showed me after the hearing?

Mr. TAPLIN. It is 6 percent.

Mr. PECORA. Payable quarterly?

Mr. TAPLIN. Quarterly.

The CHAIRMAN. You borrowed the money from the Pennroad Corporation and gave them a note and put up as collateral this stock?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; I only paid Mr. Reynolds for half of this money. I bought the 32,500 shares, and he insisted on keeping 20,000 shares—not half of the stock he sold me, but 20,000 as the security for the other half of the loan. So I only had 12,500 shares which I could put up, and Mr. County would not take that, and I had to dig up some more stock as collateral and give him in addition to the 12,500. A record of the whole transaction is here. In addition I gave the Pennroad Corporation 8,500 shares belonging to the syndicate and 7,000 shares of this 8,500 which had been taken down from the Chase Bank, and we took down 2,000 shares from the Union Trust Co.; and that evidently is 10,500 shares of the 12,500, and I assume that he must have gotten almost 33,000 shares of stock as collateral; 12,500 shares of Wheeling & Lake Erie and 8,500 shares of Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway stock put up as collateral on my note to the Pennroad Corporation.

The CHAIRMAN. Then you gave the Reynolds brothers a note for the other half?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; I have a copy of the note here.

The CHAIRMAN. And as collateral to that went the 20,000 shares?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir. Here is a copy of the note I gave the Reynolds brothers [indicating].

Mr. PECORA. For 1 year?

Mr. TAPLIN. "One year after date, or before, I promise to pay"—here is a copy of it [handing a paper to the chairman].

Mr. PECORA. I offer this copy of the note produced by the witness in evidence and ask that it be spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. That may be done.

(Copy of note referred to and produced by the witness, dated New York, N.Y., June 20, 1929, was received in evidence, marked "Committee Exhibit No. 52", and is here printed in full as follows:)

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 52

Copy.

\$1,950,000

NEW YORK, N.Y., June 20, 1929.

One year after date, or before, I promise to pay to the order of C. K. Reynolds one million nine hundred and fifty thousand dollars and interest at 6 per cent per annum from date hereof, payable semiannually at Bankers Trust Co., 16 Wall St., New York City, N. Y.

This note is secured by the deposit of 20,000 shares of value received preferred and common stock of the Wheeling & Lake Erie Railway Co.

No. _____ Due _____

F. E. TAPLIN.

Mr. PECORA. Have you a copy of the collateral note you gave to the Pennroad Corporation for the \$1,950,000 loan?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Will you produce it, please?

Mr. TAPLIN. Here is a copy of the note I gave to the Pennroad [handing a paper to Mr. Pecora].

Mr. PECORA. I offer it in evidence and ask that it be spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted.

(The note referred to, dated New York, June 25, 1929, was received in evidence, marked "Committee Exhibit No. 53", and is here printed in full, as follows:)

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT No. 53

Stock note 278, \$1,950,000

NEW YORK, June 25, 1929.

On or before June 25, 1930, which is 1 year after date, for value received I promise to pay to the order of the Pennroad Corporation, at Philadelphia, Pa., \$1,950,000 with interest at 6 percent per annum, payable quarterly, having deposited with the holder hereof as collateral security for payment of this or any other liability or liabilities of mine to said corporation, due or to become due, or that may be hereafter contracted, the following property, viz, 12,500 shares common stock and preferred stock, amount of each class not specified, of the Wheeling & Lake Erie Railway Co., 8,500 shares common stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. The market value of which is now \$——, with the right on the part of said corporation from time to time to demand such additional collateral security as herein provided should the market value thereof decline, and upon my failure to comply with any such demand, this obligation shall forthwith become due, with full power and authority to said corporation or its assigns in case of such default or of the nonpayment of any of the liabilities above mentioned at maturity, to sell, assign, and deliver the whole, or any part of such securities or any substitutes therefor or additions thereto at any broker's board or at public or private sale, at their option, at any time or times thereafter without advertisement or notice to me and with the right on its part to become purchasers thereof at such sale or sales, freed and discharged of any equity of redemption.

And after deducting all legal or other costs and expenses for collection, sale, and delivery, to apply the residue of the proceeds of such sale or sales, so made, to pay any, either, or all of said liabilities, as said corporation shall deem proper, returning the overplus to the undersigned; and I will still remain liable for any amount so unpaid. It being understood that the Wheeling & Lake Erie stock is to be valued at \$120 per share at all times and that a sufficient number of shares of Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. is to be kept in the hands of the corporation to maintain the total market value of the collateral at 35 percent in excess of the amount of the loan.

The CHAIRMAN. Are they both dated the same?

Mr. TAPLIN. The note to Reynolds is dated June 20 and the date of the Pennroad note is June 25.

Mr. PECORA. 1929?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Did you pay the interest for the first quarter on this loan negotiated from the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. Absolutely. It says, "payable quarterly."

Mr. PECORA. Did you pay it when it fell due in September?

Mr. TAPLIN. I certainly did. I was afraid, if I didn't, they might call the note.

Mr. PECORA. Was there any understanding between you and the Pennroad Corporation with reference to the sale by you and your

syndicate of the stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. with respect to the Wheeling & Lake Erie Railroad?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; they had no connection.

Mr. PECORA. There was no connection at all between the two?

Mr. TAPLIN. No.

Mr. PECORA. Was there not some understanding at the time of the acquisition by the Pennroad Corporation of the syndicate shares of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. that there would be in the treasury of the latter company a certain amount of stock of the Wheeling & Lake Erie Railroad Co.?

Mr. TAPLIN. There was 75,000 shares of Wheeling & Lake Erie Railroad stock, and is today.

Mr. PECORA. Was there an understanding between you and the Pennroad Corporation to that effect?

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, yes; because they paid extra for that Wheeling stock that was in the treasury. It had to be there, because they paid extra money for that.

Mr. PECORA. Was there that amount of stock of the Wheeling & Lake Erie Railroad Co. in the treasury of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co.?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; 75,000 shares is my recollection. It had been there some time.

Maybe I have not clarified this. The one hundred and ninety and odd thousand shares of Wheeling & Lake Erie included the 75,000 which I controlled at that time. That was part of the one hundred and ninety and odd thousand shares.

Senator STEIWER. When you say they paid extra for it, do you mean over and above the price per share which they paid you?

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, no. I mean, in figuring out the value of the stock I always contended that this ownership of 75,000 shares of Wheeling & Lake Erie Railroad stock, which was worth considerably over \$100 a share, should be given consideration at the rate of so much a share for Pittsburgh & West Virginia stock. For instance, 75,000 shares at \$100 would be \$7,500,000. Three hundred thousand shares of P. & W. V. stock outstanding would make that equivalent to about \$25 a share extra for the Pittsburgh & West Virginia stock.

Senator STEIWER. In calculating the value of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia you just took this into account as you would any other asset of the corporation; is not that true?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. The fact that the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. had in its treasury 75,000 shares was reflected in the market value of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway stock, was it not?

Mr. TAPLIN. I don't know that the people that traded in the market ever knew that they had it, so I have no way of knowing whether it was reflected or not. But I always in my mind figured it was worth that additional amount through the ownership of the Wheeling stock.

Mr. PECORA. In annual reports made to its stockholders by the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co., was mention made of the ownership of this stock of the Wheeling & Lake Erie Railroad Co.?

Mr. TAPLIN. Certainly. It had to be. But I don't think that the average trader ever looks at an annual report.

Mr. PECORA. You think he buys stock without seeking to acquaint himself with the condition of the company?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. In other words, he buys blindly?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; that is true.

Mr. PECORA. It is the first time, to my knowledge, that any witness has admitted that to this committee.

Mr. TAPLIN. That is my personal opinion.

Mr. PECORA. I think you are right.

What was the immediate occasion for you and your associates selling 222,930 shares to the Pennroad Corporation in the fall of 1929? What factor or situation then existed which prompted you to make that sale?

Mr. TAPLIN. The general economic condition of affairs, which was not very satisfactory to me.

Mr. PECORA. What do you mean by that?

Mr. TAPLIN. If you had fellows, certain bankers, and other people gunning for you for about 5 years and you saw dark clouds coming up, you would get your sail down and get under cover. That is what I did.

Mr. PECORA. In other words, you saw financial clouds lowering in the skies?

Mr. TAPLIN. I don't claim I was any prophet, but I just would rather be in snug shape than to be carrying so much stock in the fall of 1929.

Mr. PECORA. Was that the sentiment also of your various syndicate participants?

Mr. TAPLIN. I didn't ask them. I was syndicate manager and they had to take what I got for the stock.

Mr. PECORA. Did you have full authority to act for the syndicate without their advice or consent?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. You made no report to the syndicate from time to time in the course of your negotiations for the sale of that stock?

Mr. TAPLIN. No, sir. It was never mentioned. Nobody in the syndicate even had a breath of what I was doing—nobody. Well, I will take that back—my counsel.

Mr. PECORA. Who was that?

Mr. TAPLIN. Mr. C. F. Taplin.

Mr. PECORA. Your brother?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes. When he came back from Europe in September; he was the first person I told.

Mr. PECORA. Is it a fact that only about in September of 1929 you became especially desirous of selling this Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. stock to the Pennroad Corporation because you saw an impending financial storm?

Mr. TAPLIN. I had a strong desire to want to sell it.

Mr. PECORA. For that reason?

Mr. TAPLIN. That had a lot to do with it.

Mr. PECORA. What else had anything to do with your decision?

Mr. TAPLIN. Getting the money, aside from the storm.

The CHAIRMAN. You had to get some money to take up this note?

Mr. TAPLIN. Pardon.

The CHAIRMAN. It was the necessity for getting money to take up that note?

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, that note was not due for a year. It wasn't due until the following year. But I was looking ahead.

Mr. PECORA. What was the market price of the stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway in September 1929? Give us the range.

Mr. TAPLIN. I never looked the range up. It was around \$140. I read that in the newspaper. That is all I know about it. I never took the trouble to look it up.

Mr. PECORA. That was the high?

Mr. TAPLIN. I think so—\$140.

Mr. PECORA. Was that discussed in any conversation you had with officials of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. No.

Mr. PECORA. How much did the Pennroad Corporation actually pay you for this stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co.?

Mr. TAPLIN. \$170 per share.

Mr. PECORA. With what officers did you have the final discussion at which that price was agreed upon?

Mr. TAPLIN. General Atterbury acted as trustee to the Pennroad.

Mr. PECORA. Anyone else?

Mr. TAPLIN. I don't think Judge Heiserman was there that day.

Mr. PECORA. Anyone else?

Mr. TAPLIN. No.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Lee?

Mr. TAPLIN. Not that day. You asked me as to the final negotiation.

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. He talked to Mr. Lee about it—I know that—that day.

Mr. PECORA. Was General Atterbury a director of the Pennroad Corporation at that time?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Lee was president of it?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Why did you have your conversations with General Atterbury instead of with Mr. Lee, the executive head of the corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. Because at railroad meetings I would see General Atterbury all the time, and didn't have occasion to come in contact with Mr. Lee.

Mr. PECORA. You were seeking to sell it to the Pennroad Corporation.

Mr. TAPLIN. I was not seeking to run after them about it.

Mr. PECORA. You did run after them for a period of about 3 years before the sale was actually consummated.

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, no.

Mr. PECORA. You went to see them for a period of 3 years.

Mr. TAPLIN. I saw them every month. I was always talking to General Atterbury, Mr. County, and all the officials of these roads, and this would come up. Sometimes it would and sometimes it would not.

Mr. PECORA. Did you ever tell General Atterbury or any other official of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. that you also were seeking to dispose of the stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. to the other three trunk systems?

Mr. TAPLIN. He knew that. I suppose he did. He keeps pretty well posted.

Mr. PECORA. Did you ever tell him?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; I don't think so.

Mr. PECORA. Did he ever indicate to you that he knew it?

Mr. TAPLIN. No.

Mr. PECORA. Was anything said to you at the time of the negotiation in June 1929 for this loan of \$1,950,000 by the Pennroad Corporation about your eventually selling the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. stock to the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. No, sir.

Mr. PECORA. At that time, for all that the Pennroad Corporation knew, you might have acquired this majority control of the Wheeling & Lake Erie Railroad with a view of selling it to some competitor of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I don't think I could have done that very ethically.

Mr. PECORA. What would have prevented you?

Mr. TAPLIN. I don't suppose anything would have prevented me, but I don't think I could have done that very ethically.

Mr. PECORA. You were willing to sell your Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railroad stock to any system other than the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. that would have paid you your price?

Mr. TAPLIN. No, sir; I didn't say that I was willing to. I was not.

Mr. PECORA. Why not?

Mr. TAPLIN. I say I could have gotten more money for the Pittsburgh & West Virginia than I did get from the Pennroad.

Mr. PECORA. Why were you not willing to sell to anyone but the Pennsylvania Railroad or interests favorable to it?

Mr. TAPLIN. It is pretty hard to tell sometime why you are willing to trade with some people and not with others.

Mr. PECORA. You had indicated a willingness to trade with the New York Central and the Baltimore & Ohio—

Mr. TAPLIN. I said, we discussed it.

Mr. PECORA. You discussed a possible sale to them of your stock?

Mr. TAPLIN. But we never made it.

Mr. PECORA. You didn't make any with the Pennroad Corporation until the fall of 1929, although your discussions commenced in 1926, with the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I will say to you frankly, when we got right down to getting control of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railroad I preferred to deal with the Pennsylvania Railroad.

Mr. PECORA. For what reasons?

Mr. TAPLIN. Personal reasons.

Mr. PECORA. What were they? You were not putting personal reasons ahead of the interests of your syndicate participants, were you?

Mr. TAPLIN. You can't help but let personal reasons control you to a certain extent.

Mr. PECORA. What were those personal reasons?

Mr. TAPLIN. Friendship with a great many officials of the Pennsylvania Railroad, of many years' standing.

Mr. PECORA. You were the manager of this syndicate which owned approximately two thirds or more of the total outstanding stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co., were you not?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. You had full power to act?

Mr. TAPLIN. That is right.

Mr. PECORA. Without their consent, to sell the stock on any terms agreeable to you in their behalf?

Mr. TAPLIN. That is right.

Mr. PECORA. Didn't you consider you owed the participants in your syndicate the duty of making as favorable a deal for the sale of their stock as you possibly could?

Mr. TAPLIN. I think they all thought that I made a very favorable deal.

Mr. PECORA. Didn't you consider that you owed them the duty of making as favorable a deal as you possibly could in the sale of their stock?

Mr. TAPLIN. I don't think you can measure your entire duty in terms of cash.

Mr. PECORA. No; but I was asking you whether you owed any such duty to them.

Mr. TAPLIN. I always lean over backward to see that my participants in any syndicate get a square deal, and I always see that they do get a square deal, and I consider they did in this case. My judgment was controlling that, that was the best thing to do. I didn't intend to say that I had a definite offer of more money. I said I thought I had reason to believe I could get more.

Mr. PECORA. From whom?

Mr. TAPLIN. Maybe the Van Sweringens who wanted to get an entrance into Pittsburgh very badly, and didn't have one.

Mr. PECORA. One of the syndicate participants was an attorney for the Van Sweringens, I believe you said?

Mr. TAPLIN. That was a personal relationship between Mr. Ginn and myself. I don't believe they ever knew that he had any interest in that. I question it very much. It is a personal matter between him and me; nothing about the relationship as their counsel. You can very readily see that his stock didn't amount to anything one way or the other. He only had a thousand shares of stock, and it didn't make any difference whether he kept it or did not keep it.

The CHAIRMAN. Have you still any stock in the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Ry. Co.?

Mr. TAPLIN. No, sir; I sold my stock.

The CHAIRMAN. You were not influenced by any possible advantage to the Wheeling road by reason of its connection with the Pennsylvania over its connection with any other road? In other words, was there any advantage coming to your road by reason of the connection with the Pennsylvania Railroad instead of by reason of a connection with the other?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; I wouldn't say there was any advantage.

But Mr. Pecora asked me one question that I didn't really have time to answer—about the Wheeling & Lake Erie Railroad. I didn't

think it would be quite ethical to sell the Pittsburgh & West Virginia to one crowd and then turn around with the Wheeling, connected right up with it, and sell that to a different crowd. It wouldn't taste just right.

Mr. PECORA. Did you make that attitude known to the officials of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. They didn't ask me to buy the Wheeling & Lake Erie Railroad.

Mr. PECORA. No; but did you make that attitude of yours known to the officials of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. Which attitude?

Mr. PECORA. With regard to the Wheeling & Lake Erie—the one you have just expressed.

Mr. TAPLIN. I think they understood that.

Mr. PECORA. Did you make it known to them?

Mr. TAPLIN. I think so.

Mr. PECORA. What were the terms of payment for this block of two hundred and twenty-two thousand and odd shares?

Mr. TAPLIN. Cash.

Mr. PECORA. When was payment to be made—at the time the firm agreement to buy the stock was entered into?

Mr. TAPLIN. The exact date was not specific, but it was understood it was to be paid as promptly as the stock could be delivered, within a reasonable time. No specific date was set. I think it was paid for, a big part of it, the latter part of October.

Mr. PECORA. 1929?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; about 30 days.

The CHAIRMAN. That money all came from the public, rising from the sale of the shares or trust certificates of the Pennroad?

Mr. TAPLIN. When I made the sale to them I wasn't really concerned with where they got the money from.

The CHAIRMAN. I understand that.

Mr. TAPLIN. I had my suspicions afterward where the money came from, which I believe were not far from the facts, by selling Pennroad stock. But I had no knowledge at that time how they were going to pay for it or where the money was coming from.

Mr. PECORA. Why was it that there never was a written agreement of any kind between you as the syndicate manager and the Pennroad Corporation, covering the terms and provisions of this purchase by the latter corporation of two hundred and twenty-two thousand and odd shares?

Mr. TAPLIN. I am not surprised that you ask me that question, Mr. Pecora, because a great many other people have expressed surprise and amazement that I would make a deal to sell something for that amount of money and not have an agreement signed. The only answer I can give you is what I have given them. I would not have done it with everybody, but I had absolute confidence in the integrity of the man that I made the deal with.

Mr. PECORA. Who was that?

Mr. TAPLIN. Gen. W. W. Atterbury.

Mr. PECORA. Is that the only reason why no writing was resorted to evidencing this transaction?

Mr. TAPLIN. I think if it had been with anybody else I would have wanted it in writing.

Mr. PECORA. Did he offer to put it in writing?

Mr. TAPLIN. I didn't ask him.

Mr. PECORA. And he never offered to?

Mr. TAPLIN. No. He took my word that I would give him the stock, and I took his word that he would give me the money.

Mr. PECORA. When was the first payment made? Do you remember the date?

Mr. TAPLIN. It was the very last few days of October.

Mr. PECORA. Was it before or after the 24th day of October 1929?

Mr. TAPLIN. My impression is it was the 28th or 29th, Mr. Pecora. I have no record of it here. I didn't get a payment made direct in cash, you see. I elected Mr. James McDonnell as pay-off man for me. Do you see what I mean? I didn't handle any money.

Mr. PECORA. Why did you do that?

Mr. TAPLIN. Because it was necessary to get this stock accumulated from various people at various places.

Mr. PECORA. Had not that been done some time prior to September or October of 1929?

Mr. TAPLIN. No. These people had this stock. The syndicate had some and it owed a little money on it, and other people had some. You can very readily appreciate that somebody had to accumulate this stock in a package and deliver it for the money, and it took quite a bit of money, ten to twelve million dollars cash, to pay for that stock and hold it until the Pennroad people paid me for it. In the interim it might have been 2 weeks, or some of it 2 days. You understand how that would be.

Mr. PECORA. Was the stock under option to you in the syndicate?

Mr. TAPLIN. Stock under option?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. Why, we owned it.

Mr. PECORA. You owned it?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; except those shares which were under agreements.

Mr. PECORA. You said it took 10 to 12 million dollars to pay for the stock.

Mr. TAPLIN. All right. Say this fellow is delivering his stock, and he owed money on it, then he had to get money enough to pay what he owed on it.

Mr. PECORA. When you say "owned" you mean controlled?

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, no.

Mr. PECORA. Owned but not fully paid for by the syndicate managers?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Not fully paid for?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. There was still something like 10 to 12 million dollars unpaid?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir. What the syndicate paid to the different people, it took 10 to 12 million dollars to use on this stock, and I could not find a banker who would have thought of trusting me for 10 to 12 million dollars. He might think that I would walk out on

him and leave the stock on his hands. James McDonnell took it and paid the money on it. When he delivered the stock he got the money.

Mr. PECORA. Is that the McDonnell of the firm of McDonnell & Co., stock brokers, of New York City?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir; he is the head of the firm. He got the money from the bank that they specified when they got the stock. I gave him a list of the stock to be delivered, by different names, showing it would take that much money to give to those people \$170 a share for their stock.

Mr. PECORA. What bank was used by Mr. McDonnell?

Mr. TAPLIN. He didn't use any bank. He went to the bank specified by the Pennroad Corporation to get the money when he delivered the stock.

Mr. PECORA. What bank was it?

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, I don't know. It was the Empire Trust Co. of New York, I think. You see, I kept in the background, so to speak.

Mr. PECORA. How much was paid on account of this purchase of two hundred and twenty-two thousand and odd shares of stock as an initial payment?

Mr. TAPLIN. On the initial payment?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, I cannot tell you how it was divided. First, he got one block in, and I think he must have got maybe 140,000 or 150,000 shares. Then in 2 or 3 or 4 weeks later, or maybe 2 or 3 weeks later, he got another 10,000 shares from the different people I specified. I think altogether there were four lots of stock that totaled this 222,980 shares.

Mr. PECORA. At any time in connection with this stock transaction did General Atterbury give you the reasons why he wanted the Pennroad Corporation, or why he was willing to have the Pennroad Corporation buy this large block of stock from you and your associates?

Mr. TAPLIN. No. I did not ask him why. He just said he would take it.

The CHAIRMAN. How much did you have to pay McDonnell for those services?

Mr. TAPLIN. I am happy to see that you asked me that question, because I did not pay him a nickel for all the risk he took, Senator Fletcher. He owned about 3,000 shares of the stock, on which he got the same profit, but he didn't charge me a 5-cent piece for putting all that money into it.

Mr. PECORA. Did this transaction involve any other consideration than the mere payment for the stock at \$170 a share by the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. Did it involve any other consideration?

Mr. PECORA. Yes; or conditions.

Mr. TAPLIN. On their part?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. Or on my part?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, it was pretty distinctly understood that I agreed to continue to run the property. That was the only stipulation in it.

Mr. PECORA. That is, you agreed to continue to run the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. as president?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. That was a specific understanding between you?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Was there any other understanding involved in the transaction or included in it?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes. I think there was another understanding.

Mr. PECORA. What was it?

Mr. TAPLIN. The understanding that I would not do anything with my Wheeling & Lake Erie stock individually outside of those 75,000 shares; or that the railway company could not do anything with theirs except by joint agreement.

Mr. PECORA. Except by joint agreement with whom?

Mr. TAPLIN. With each other.

Mr. PECORA. Who was the other party?

Mr. TAPLIN. The Pennroad.

Mr. PECORA. The Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir; they owned it.

Mr. PECORA. That was all the understanding you had with General Atterbury acting for the Pennroad Corporation, was it?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Now, when was delivery of those 222,930 shares of Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. stock completed to the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. I think about the 1st of January, or maybe the 2d of January of 1930. That is just a recollection, but I am not far wrong on it. It might have been the first week in January.

Mr. PECORA. And at that time final payment was made?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. The total purchase price amounted to over 37 million dollars, didn't it?

Mr. TAPLIN. It amounted to \$170 a share, which is about 38 million dollars, I believe.

Mr. PECORA. It amounted to around 38 million dollars?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir.

The CHAIRMAN. Was any agreement reached as to the salary or compensation that you would receive?

Mr. TAPLIN. None whatever.

Mr. PECORA. Did you continue to receive the salary as president of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. that you had received prior to the sale of this stock?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; because soon after I sold the stock business got bad and we cut everybody's salary 10 percent first, and then we cut 10 percent more, and so on. Nothing was said about salary at all.

The CHAIRMAN. How much salary do you get?

Mr. TAPLIN. Now?

The CHAIRMAN. Yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. I think—(and the witness confers with some associates).

Mr. PECORA. Don't you know what salary you get?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; I don't. I think it is \$17,000 now. I think it is.

Mr. PECORA. What was it just prior to the sale of the stock?

Mr. TAPLIN. It was \$30,000. I think it has been cut four times, 10 percent each time, which is cumulative, which would be about 35 percent off.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Taplin, in whose name did these 222,930 shares of Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. stock stand, or do they stand today, I mean?

Mr. TAPLIN. In my name?

Mr. PECORA. In your name?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And they have stood in your name ever since the making of the sale of this stock to the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. What is the reason for that?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, it has to stand in somebody's name.

Mr. PECORA. Why not in the name of the corporation which bought it and paid for it in full?

Mr. TAPLIN. I don't know.

Mr. PECORA. You say you don't know?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, they stand in my name, and I don't know exactly that there was any good reason for it. They have to stand in somebody's name, and might as well stand in my name. It is immaterial in whose name they stand, because it is a matter of public knowledge that they belong to the Pennroad Corporation.

Mr. PECORA. How was that knowledge communicated?

Mr. TAPLIN. I think everybody in the railroad business understands it.

Mr. PECORA. The legal title of the stock is in you today?

Mr. TAPLIN. I do not know about the legal title.

Mr. PECORA. Well, it is registered in your name?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; it is registered in my name. But I don't own it.

Mr. PECORA. Was it a part of the understanding that you had with the Pennroad Corporation that the stock was to continue to stand in your name?

Mr. TAPLIN. No, sir.

Mr. PECORA. How do you account for that situation, that the stock is still in your own name?

Mr. TAPLIN. I don't know. I think that Mr. Lee will have to answer that question. I think he is the only one who really knows the truth of why he wants it in my name.

Mr. PECORA. Didn't he ever tell you why he wanted it in your name?

Mr. TAPLIN. No, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Didn't General Atterbury ever tell you why?

Mr. TAPLIN. No, sir. He never mentioned it?

Mr. PECORA. Did anyone ever tell you?

Mr. TAPLIN. No, sir; because it is immaterial whether the stock is in my name or in whose name it stands.

Mr. PECORA. Who receives the dividends on the stock?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, nobody is receiving them now. They stopped.

Mr. PECORA. Who received the dividends, such dividends as were paid on and after the sale?

Mr. TAPLIN. The Pennroad Corporation.

Mr. PECORA. Did they?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir; by assignment to them.

Mr. PECORA. Was the dividend check made directly payable to the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know that to be a fact?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir. Or I know that I never got them.

Mr. PECORA. Now, this sale of 222,930 shares was an outright absolute sale, was it?

Mr. TAPLIN. Absolutely.

Mr. PECORA. With no strings of any kind tied to it?

Mr. TAPLIN. There was some talk at one time about my having the privilege of buying it back if I chose to when a fifth trunk-line system was recommended by the Interstate Commerce Commission. But that was afterward killed by the Commission.

Mr. PECORA. When did you have that talk with anybody?

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, sometime after the purchase was made.

Mr. PECORA. About how long afterward?

Mr. TAPLIN. I could not tell you the exact time, but it was probably within a year. No; it was less than a year.

Mr. PECORA. At the time the sale was made it was made as an absolute, unqualified, unconditional sale, with no strings attached to it, was it?

Mr. TAPLIN. That is right.

Mr. PECORA. Is that right?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Now, with whom did you have any discussion a year afterward, or thereabouts, concerning the possibility of your buying the stock back?

Mr. TAPLIN. I think that General Atterbury, Judge Heiserman, Mr. Lee, and I talked with regard to the inclusion of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia in a fifth trunk-line system, with the Wheeling & Lake Erie and the Western Maryland Railroads.

Mr. PECORA. Will you give us the substance of those conversations?

Mr. TAPLIN. It was a matter of general conversation.

Mr. PECORA. What was the substance of it or them?

Mr. TAPLIN. That if we could work out a plan to consolidate the Wabash Railroad, the Lehigh Valley, the Wheeling & Lake Erie, the Pittsburgh & West Virginia, and the Western Maryland Railroads, which plan was recommended about that time by the Interstate Commerce Commission, that if I could work out the financing of that plan it would be agreeable to let me buy back the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co.

The CHAIRMAN. What became of that?

Mr. TAPLIN. We didn't do anything about it, Senator Fletcher. Soon after that financial conditions became pretty much disturbed, and I do not or I did not want to assume such obligations. And then nobody did anything. And the Interstate Commerce Commission recalled their privilege of a fifth system and switched back to a fourth system. That was the end of that, because we could not do it today, for the reason that they withdrew their permission.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Taplin, did you think in September of 1929, when you finally agreed upon the terms of this sale, that a financial storm was brewing which would depreciate the value of that Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. stock substantially?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I thought conditions were getting a little top-heavy, Mr. Pecora. And I was in two or three other deals, and I did the same thing with them that I did with the Pittsburgh & West

Virginia Railway Co. So I must have had some idea in mind that I wanted to unload and lighten up a little bit. I hadn't any assurance as to how long things might continue the way they were going.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Taplin, you gave some testimony, didn't you, in a proceeding before the Interstate Commerce Commission during the year 1930 in relation to this transaction with the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. I recall, yes, that I did, or I am pretty sure that I did. I do not know what hearing that was—what case, I mean. If you have a reference to the docket number there, it might help.

Mr. PECORA. Yes. And I will give it to you in a moment. It is Finance Docket 6486, at the application of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. for the approval of acquisition and control by the Pittsburgh & West Virginia of the Wheeling & Lake Erie Railway Co. and its subsidiary the Lorain & West Virginia Railway Co.

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; I was on the stand then.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recall having been asked in those proceedings the following question with regard to this transaction with the Pennroad Corporation and your making thereto the following answer? And I believe this question was put to you by your brother, who was counsel for you in that application:

Question. Considerable has been said of late regarding the purchase of the P. & W. V. by the Pennroad Corporation. What are the facts?

Answer. The facts in regard to that are: In the fall of 1929 I saw a financial storm coming; and knowing that certain interests were out gunning for me and my associates, and that some of the latter were, maybe, not in as strong financial condition as they should be, I decided that we should not take any chance of losing control of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway. And therefore I went to the Pennroad Corporation, with which company I had had previous financial dealings, and upon whom I felt I could depend to protect me and the whole situation. As a result of this call upon the Pennroad Corporation I sold 222,930 shares of Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. stock to it. This sale of the stock was only a temporary one until such time as the financial skies cleared. At the time of the sale of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia stock it was absolutely agreed that the management and control were to remain with us, as at present, without interference of any kind in the absence of action on our part that would be detrimental to their investment in the company's stock.

Do you recall that?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes. And I think that is substantially what I testified to here this morning.

Mr. PECORA. And were you in the same proceeding and at the same hearing asked the following questions, and did you make the following answers thereto:

Question. When you speak of the financial storm that you saw coming or thought you saw coming, was not that the storm which resulted in the stock-market break?

Answer. Yes.

Do you recall that testimony given by you in that proceeding?

Mr. TAPLIN. I recall it now that you read it.

Mr. PECORA. Well, that testimony was the truth, wasn't it?

Mr. TAPLIN. I think I was getting a little yellow and I ran a little.

Mr. PECORA. Was the testimony as given the truth at that time?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir; absolutely.

Mr. PECORA. Now, was this the fact, that one of the reasons why you and your associates sold this large block of Pittsburgh & West Virginia stock to the Pennroad Corporation was because you saw a financial storm coming and because some of your associates owning this stock were not in as strong a financial condition as they should be?

Mr. TAPLIN. I don't think that I am competent enough to say that I can see trouble coming any quicker than anybody else can, Mr. Pecora. But I have found from past experience, especially during the past 4 years, that whenever there are any financial difficulties you put in a big part of your time bailing out your friends. I did not want to be bailing out too many. I was a little worried about that situation. It isn't only taking care of your own troubles, but taking care of friends in deals with you. You cannot keep your own house in order very well under such circumstances.

Mr. PECORA. In this particular case were your friends not in as strong a position as they should be, so that they had to be bailed out by you, or by the Pennroad Corporation through the medium of this sale?

Mr. TAPLIN. No one was bailed out. They were not in any trouble.

Mr. PECORA. You have said they were not in as strong a financial position as they should be, and you stated that as one of the facts that entered into this transaction.

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, if the unexpected should happen, if things got bad, I did not want to be bailing them out. The Pennroad Corporation did not bail anyone out. There was no one in difficulties when that stock was sold. It was afterward that trouble developed, which I was not willing to—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). Now, you made that answer in June of 1930 in this proceeding before the Interstate Commerce Commission when you were asked the question by your counsel, your brother, which question was couched in these words:

Question. Considerable has been said of late regarding the purchase of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia by the Pennroad Corporation. What are the facts?

Then you went on to say that in the fall of 1929 you saw a financial storm coming, and that some of your associates were not in as strong a financial condition as they should be, and so you decided that you should take no chance of losing control of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co.

Mr. TAPLIN. I do not see anything wrong with that testimony, or anything conflicting as between that and what I say here now, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. I asked you if one of the motives that prompted you to make this sale for the syndicate at \$170 a share was because you saw a financial storm coming, and that your associates were not in a financial condition to stand it, or not as strong as they should be, and that you wanted to protect them against the storm that you saw coming.

Mr. TAPLIN. I just wanted to unload and get out at a price that was satisfactory to me. That was the long and the short of it.

Mr. PECORA. One of the reasons why you wanted to get out was because you saw a storm coming, and that some of your associates were in a weak position financially, wasn't it?

Mr. TAPLIN. I did not have any particular associate in mind.

Mr. PECORA. Well, Mr. Taplin, I am simply questioning you on the basis of the testimony that you gave back in June of 1930 about this very transaction.

Mr. TAPLIN. Now, let me—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). I am not conjuring up any elements that entered into that transaction. I am simply questioning you about what you said in June of 1930 were some of the elements existing.

Mr. TAPLIN. I said that because it is in the testimony, and I must have said that.

Mr. PECORA. And it was the truth, wasn't it?

Mr. TAPLIN. It must have been the truth or I wouldn't have said it.

Mr. PECORA. Now, who were the interests that were out gunning for you and your associates at the time you entered into this transaction with the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. I prefer not to mention any names.

Mr. PECORA. Why not?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, of course, I cannot prove it about anybody else. I might make statements that I am not able to prove.

Mr. PECORA. You stated just a moment ago that this testimony you gave in June of 1930 was the truth or you wouldn't have said it. Now, tell us who it was you said that about.

Mr. TAPLIN. I didn't say who it was.

Mr. PECORA. Who were they?

Mr. TAPLIN. Different interests in railroad deals.

Mr. PECORA. What interests did they represent?

Mr. TAPLIN. We had a lot of legal difficulties, and we have been in a lot of court actions, had been for 3 or 4 years, over some of those acquisitions.

Mr. PECORA. Well, if you had had court actions with them, those actions were a matter of record.

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Then why don't you mention their names here?

Mr. TAPLIN. Because I cannot prove that they were out gunning for me. That was my idea. I know this, that one reason I went to the Pennroad Corporation—and I didn't hardly dare go to a bank to borrow money, because there was the possibility of the strings being pulled, because there is sometimes a connection with many New York and other bankers, and I did not want them to pull the strings on me.

Senator STEIWER. Do New York bankers do that?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, they haven't done it to me.

Senator STEIWER. But you have just said that you did not want it done.

Mr. TAPLIN. I have heard it said that they do.

Senator STEIWER. Do you know what interests they were?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; but I know how they work.

Mr. PECORA. How do they work?

Mr. TAPLIN. They loan you money, and then when some good friends come along and pull the strings on you they always ask you to pay the money when you haven't got it. And I didn't want to take any chance.

Mr. PECORA. They have never done that to you, you say?

Mr. TAPLIN. I am pretty careful not to go to banks. One reason I would rather go to the Pennroad Corporation than to a bank to borrow \$1,950,000 was that.

Mr. PECORA. Now, you said in answer to your brother's question back in June of 1930 in testimony you gave before the Interstate Commerce Commission that because of these elements, namely, that you foresaw this financial storm coming and that some of your associates were in a weak financial condition, you did not want to take any chance of losing control of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co., and therefore you went to the Pennroad Corporation, upon whom you thought you could depend, to protect you and the whole situation. Why did you have that feeling?

Mr. TAPLIN. I think I said before that my relations with the officials of the Pennsylvania Railroad for a great number of years had always been very friendly. That is, I do not know that they did me any favors, but I knew that they had always been fair and square and open and aboveboard with me. And that is more than you can say for some people.

Mr. PECORA. You thought the Pennroad Corporation would be fair and square with you in these dealings, did you?

Mr. TAPLIN. Absolutely.

Mr. PECORA. And was it for that reason that you sought to sell to the Pennroad Corporation, just before the financial storm broke, 222,930 shares of the stock of your railroad company, at \$170 a share, when the market at that time was a good deal less. You felt that it would be a good deal lower when the storm broke?

Mr. TAPLIN. I do not take any stock in the market for a few hundred shares. That does not mean anything to me, as to the value of one single block carrying control of 225,000 shares. And, as I have said as to that railroad, that market never did reflect, through lack of knowledge, the ownership of the Wheeling & Lake Erie stock in the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway treasury.

Mr. PECORA. That is an assumption on your part, isn't it?

Mr. TAPLIN. That is a pure assumption. So that I did not figure that the \$170 a share was a high price. In fact, I figured it was a cheap price, \$30 less than I had ever talked before, the price coming down \$30 over night.

Mr. PECORA. You didn't think the price you asked represented the actual value of the stock, did you?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, it occupied a very strategic position in Pittsburgh, and it was worth a lot of money to some railroads.

Mr. PECORA. Didn't you think the \$200 a share was the hold-up value for control?

Mr. TAPLIN. No, sir. I thought it was worth it. And I thought inasmuch as we had just finished a new line, a connecting link between Pittsburgh and Connellsville, with the Western Maryland Railroad, after a fight in the courts and the Commission for about 3 or 4 years, which would add a great deal of value to the railroad, and which connecting link was only finished in 1931; and you see it never had had any earnings; and you must not overlook the fact either that in establishing that link, which I could have attached to and made this fifth trunk line system possible; and I had had a long fight in the courts against all of the trunk line systems, the Baltimore &

Ohio, Pennsylvania, New York Central, and Van Sweringens, and I was on the other end——

Mr. PECORA (interposing). As I recall the testimony given here last Friday by Mr. Lee, president of the Pennroad Corporation, he said, in substance, that the negotiations in behalf of the Pennroad Corporation for the purchase of this large block of stock from you and your associates, of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co., were undertaken in behalf of the Pennroad Corporation by Mr. County, and that he knew nothing or practically little about them until his board of directors adopted a resolution some time in September of 1929.

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, Mr. Pecora, if you will recollect back at this morning's testimony, I think you will find that I stated that my negotiations early in 1926 or 1927 had been somewhat with Mr. A. J. County, and that my negotiations, I believe it states, at the time that this deal was consummated were not with Mr. County. And all I can say is I do not know whether Mr. Lee referred to the negotiations leading up to the sale of it those 2 or 3 years before. But if he thinks he was referring to the negotiations leading up to the 1929 deal, I don't believe I ever talked to Mr. John County about that.

Mr. PECORA. Did you ever talk to Mr. Lee about it?

Mr. TAPLIN. Certainly.

Mr. PECORA. Frequently?

Mr. TAPLIN. No.

Mr. PECORA. With whom did you conduct the most of the negotiations with the Pennroad Corporation, with what officer?

Mr. TAPLIN. I think with General Atterbury.

Mr. PECORA. Not with Mr. Lee?

Mr. TAPLIN. I discussed it with Mr. Lee, but I discussed the details more with General Atterbury. And I recollect distinctly that General Atterbury at a meeting one day with the Pennroad Corporation board of directors discussed the matter with him, or at least he told me he did.

Senator STEIWER. Do you know when the Pennroad Corporation was organized?

Mr. TAPLIN. I do not remember the date.

Senator STEIWER. I do not mean, do you know now, but did you know at the time. Were you close enough to the situation to know at the time of the organization of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. I do not think I knew it before it was done. I mean I didn't know it until it was accomplished.

Senator STEIWER. Do you know whether you were advised about it after it had been accomplished?

Mr. TAPLIN. I do not recall much about it. I think I knew it as soon as it was organized.

Senator STEIWER. In dealing with the Pennsylvania Railroad did you know that you would not deal with the parent corporation but that you would deal with this other institution?

Mr. TAPLIN. I did not know that I could not deal with the Pennsylvania Railroad if they wanted to buy the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railroad, but of course I had nothing to say as to who they designated, or whether it was the Pennsylvania Co. or the Pennroad. It was none of my concern.

Senator STEIWER. I do not suppose it was, but my question was: Did you know that you were to deal with this Pennroad Corporation rather than the parent company, the Pennsylvania Railroad?

Mr. TAPLIN. I knew it before the deal was consummated.

Senator STEIWER. Did you not know it long before the deal was consummated?

Mr. TAPLIN. I could not have known it very long. My recollection is pretty fairly clear that—this is just my recollection now—that General Atterbury went away that summer around the Fourth of July, and was gone until after Labor Day. Of course if he did not get back until after Labor Day I do not see how I could have known it very long before we made the deal in September. That is a very clear recollection that I have.

Senator STEIWER. Well, you borrowed the money in June, the \$1,900,000?

Mr. TAPLIN. You mean for the Wheeling & Lake Erie?

Senator STEIWER. Yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Senator STEIWER. But you had borrowed the money in June?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Senator STEIWER. And you borrowed it from the Pennroad Corporation, did you not?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Senator STEIWER. So you knew before June, or at that time, that the Pennroad Corporation was in existence?

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, I knew it was in existence. I think it was organized before June some time.

Senator STEIWER. You knew it immediately, did you not?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir.

Senator STEIWER. After the organization?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir.

Senator STEIWER. You knew that it was controlled by the same people that controlled the Pennsylvania Railroad?

Mr. TAPLIN. I knew their stockholders controlled it. The stock was issued pro rata to their stockholders, I was told.

Senator STEIWER. I was interested in your statement that there was no agreement between you and General Atterbury with respect to the time of making payment for the stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. Was there not anything said about the subject?

Mr. TAPLIN. We would get the stock together and make prompt delivery.

Senator STEIWER. And then was it agreed that they would pay upon delivery?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Senator STEIWER. So payment depended upon your delivery, then?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Senator STEIWER. It did not depend upon the whim or caprice of General Atterbury or someone else?

Mr. TAPLIN. No.

Senator STEIWER. Well then, we possibly misunderstood your earlier testimony. It is not true then, that there was no understanding about the time of payment?

Mr. TAPLIN. I do not recollect that I said there was no understanding about it. There was an understanding that it was to be delivered and paid for promptly, or within a reasonable time. And you know there was not anything in writing about it. It was just word of mouth. If it had been in writing you could have put your finger on just what was said. There was none.

Senator STEIWER. But in the word-of-mouth arrangement made between you and General Atterbury there was some discussion about the time of payment?

Mr. TAPLIN. I do not think there was very much discussion about how long it would take to deliver the stock—how quick—I do not think there was very much time put on that part of it, because it was stated that the stock would be delivered with reasonable promptness and paid for. Now, that was about all the understanding. And I want to make—well, let that go. You did not ask me.

Senator STEIWER. I would be glad to have your explanation if you want to make a further explanation.

(There was no reply.)

Senator STEIWER. Well, was there any time limit put upon the period that you might require in order to assemble and deliver the stock?

Mr. TAPLIN. I do not think there was when we made the deal. There may have been after—discussing the delivery with Mr. Lee afterwards, that it would, maybe, take 1 month or 2 months or—the biggest part of it, though, was delivered reasonably promptly.

Senator STEIWER. Was it understood that you would have to assemble certain amounts of stock, pay off some liens, and clean up some loans and things of that kind?

Mr. TAPLIN. It was understood between me and Mr. Lee afterwards.

Senator STEIWER. Was it understood between you and General Atterbury?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; he was not interested in what the broker paid up. He was not interested in that.

Senator STEIWER. General Atterbury was not interested in the time of the delivery?

Mr. TAPLIN. I suppose he wanted it promptly.

Senator STEIWER. Did he indicate that he was not ready with the cash?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; he did not say anything about it. I did not ask him about the cash.

Senator STEIWER. Suppose you had been able to deliver the whole thing in a week, did you have any reason to believe that he would have the cash ready?

Mr. TAPLIN. I certainly would have thought that his company would not have bought something that they could not have paid for. I assumed that.

Senator STEIWER. You relied on your own assumption?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Senator STEIWER. When did you find out that the cash would not be ready until they sold the stock of the Pennroad Corporation to the public?

Mr. TAPLIN. When did I find it out?

Senator STEIWER. Yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. I do not know. I maybe found it out that they were going to sell stock—well, I am guessing at this—maybe a couple of weeks afterward, that they were going to sell—

Senator STEIWER. After what?

Mr. TAPLIN. After we made the deal; agreed to deliver the stock for \$170 a share.

Senator STEIWER. That is, then, about 2 weeks, according to your recollection—

Mr. TAPLIN (interposing). That is my recollection.

Senator STEIWER (continuing). Two weeks after you and General Atterbury agreed upon the sales price and you had started out to assemble the stock you learned that they were selling stock in the Pennroad Corporation for the purpose of raising money to complete the transaction?

Mr. TAPLIN. That—I think I did hear of that.

Senator STEIWER. Did you know anything about the pace with which they proceeded with the sale of the stock?

Mr. TAPLIN. Not a thing.

Senator STEIWER. Was the money always ready by the time you got your installment ready?

Mr. TAPLIN. Absolutely. They never delayed our delivery. When we had the stock we delivered it and got our money.

Senator STEIWER. What determined about the size of the blocks of stock in which you made the successive deliveries?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, as I think I stated before, I think the first block was in the neighborhood—my recollection is—of 150,000 shares.

Senator STEIWER. Yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. And I am very sure there was another block of 10,000.

Senator STEIWER. Yes; you stated that, Mr. Taplin; but that does not answer my question.

Mr. TAPLIN. And maybe another.

Senator STEIWER. I ask you what determined the size of those blocks.

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, just the convenience of getting them together.

Senator STEIWER. The determination of the size of the blocks was not fixed in any way by the sale of the stock of the Pennroad Corporation to the public?

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, not at all. And, furthermore, if the delivery was delayed, it carried interest.

Senator STEIWER. And what provided that?

Mr. TAPLIN. It goes without saying that if on a given date I agree to sell you stock, and I can bring it in and do bring in a big block of it on October 29, and that was the first date, and I do not ask you to pay for all of it and deliver some of it 60 days later, I want interest for that 60 days.

Senator STEIWER. Had there been any discussion of the payment of interest between you and General Atterbury?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; there wasn't any discussion, because when by mutual agreement, if it is satisfactory to both parties to delay the delivery 60 days, it goes without saying, according to my way of doing business, that I want interest for that 60 days; and we got interest. There was never any question about paying the interest on the delayed time.

Senator STEIWER. Was interest paid on any of these obligations from the Pennroad Corporation to your syndicate?

Mr. TAPLIN. Do you mean these delayed deliveries?

Senator STEIWER. Yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. Certainly.

Senator STEIWER. Interest was paid?

Mr. TAPLIN. Certainly.

Senator STEIWER. Even though you had not been ready to deliver?

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, I don't know—maybe we were not ready to deliver, and then again maybe for one reason or another I did not prefer to deliver the stock for 30 or 60 days. I can see what you are driving at, but there are some people that you have got in this list, if you delivered too quickly they would know too much and they would have talked too much. I let them wait a little bit. Less conversation around the country about what I had done.

Senator STEIWER. And you deliberately—that is, you willfully held up delivery of the stock in some cases?

Mr. TAPLIN. Some of it; yes.

Senator STEIWER. But nevertheless collected interest?

Mr. TAPLIN. But they got interest on it where they were delayed.

Senator STEIWER. Who got interest?

Mr. TAPLIN. I cannot tell you. Mr. McDonnell can tell you.

Senator STEIWER. I do not mean the names, but what I am trying to get at is, did the owner of the stock—

Mr. TAPLIN (interposing). Oh, yes; certainly, the owner of the stock.

Senator STEIWER (continuing). Get interest?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes. Now this point ought to be made very clear if it is not. I do not know whether Mr. Pecora has brought this out, but you see here is a list of people that got \$170 a share for the Pittsburgh West Virginia Railway stock. Now in some cases where for some reason or another, regardless of what the reason is—maybe I was responsible—the delivery of their stock may have been held up 60 days; then they collected in addition to that, interest for the delayed time. Nothing was said to them at all. Now they got this money. Nobody else got any commissions or anything out of this price. There was no handout to anybody out of this \$170. And furthermore, I think Mr. Pecora will find if he will take this list and check it, that there is nobody in it that is any dummy for anybody, either. There is nothing in this that won't stand the closest scrutiny and inspection as far as anything wrong with it is concerned. There is nobody got a nickel.

Mr. PECORA. Is that the list that you read into the record in the early part of the hearing?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; that is the list that I read into the record. There are no dummies in that list. Everybody with that stock got the same price that I got. No commissions paid to anybody. No siphoning back or any pipe line to anybody else.

Senator STEIWER. There was not any intimation that there were any commissions paid or anything like that.

Mr. TAPLIN. I just wanted to make clear to Mr. Pecora that this was not any of those deals with a handout to somebody.

Mr. PECORA. What kind of deal do you refer to?

Mr. TAPLIN. I have seen a whole lot of deals—preferred lists and something of that kind. There was no preferred list.

Senator STEIWER. There was no preferred list?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; there was no preferred list. I was not on the preferred list of anybody else, either.

Senator STEIWER. You have not made it clear to me how it came you paid interest to some of these syndicate holders and not to others.

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I thought I had made that clear. But suppose that we find the first date—and I am only a day or two off, if I am that—that the first date of delivering 150,000 shares of stock was October 29.

Senator STEIWER. We will assume that as the correct date for the purpose of this explanation.

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes. Now we got \$170. Suppose Mr. Bronson here had 2,000 shares of stock, and I did not tell him anything about this, and he could not get his stock on October 29, and he did not get it until December 5, then I tell Mr. Bronson some day to send his stock in to McDonnell & Co. and on December 5 he will get \$170 plus interest from October 29 to December 5. It was not his fault I held him up. He got the interest. He was entitled to it.

Senator STEIWER. Were any dividends declared during that period?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, if they were they did not belong to me.

Senator STEIWER. Who did they belong to?

Mr. TAPLIN. They belonged to the owner of the stock.

Senator STEIWER. Did he get the dividends?

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, no; if there were any dividends after October 29—but I doubt that there were any after that—they would have gone to the rightful owners of the stock. He would not have got them. They would have got the dividends.

Senator STEIWER. Who are “they”?

Mr. TAPLIN. The owners of the stock.

Senator STEIWER. In this particular case—

Mr. TAPLIN (interposing). After October 29, the Pennroad.

Senator STEIWER. Oh, the Pennroad would have gotten the dividends if there were any?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes. Suppose his interest were only 60 cents and his dividend was \$1.50 a quarter, he would not have been entitled to keep the \$1.50 on top of his interest.

Senator STEIWER. Well, now, what justification was there for the Pennroad to pay you interest when it stood ready to buy, but you failed to make delivery?

Mr. TAPLIN. I do not know. We never had—I do not recollect any argument about it. I said, “For delayed deliveries there will be interest”, and they must have said, “O.K.”, because I am very sure interest was paid.

Senator STEIWER. I think it would have been easier to explain if there had been some argument about it. What I am trying to get at is why they were willing to pay, and without argument, interest upon these deferred deliveries when you failed to deliver the stock for reasons of your own?

Mr. TAPLIN. I cannot answer why. All I know is what I did. I do not know about why they did it.

Senator STEIWER. Now, let us see if I understand another feature. You said that you did not want to make delivery too soon with respect to some of that stock because——

Mr. TAPLIN (interposing). I said that might have been the reason.

Senator STEIWER (continuing). Because there are some of these holders that might have known too much, or words to that effect.

Mr. TAPLIN. That is about it; yes.

Senator STEIWER. I do not care about the identity of the holder.

Mr. TAPLIN. I was not going to tell you.

Senator STEIWER. Well, possibly I may ask you later.

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I would not tell you who they were, because I do not know.

Senator STEIWER. But what I am interested in is what could they know that was hurtful? What could they have known about a transaction in which you agreed with General Atterbury to sell him the stock at \$170 a share?

Mr. TAPLIN. If I make a deal, say, to sell Wheeling & Lake Erie stock, would it do me any good to go out and tell everybody in the country about it?

Senator STEIWER. I do not know whether it would do you any good. I did not ask you that.

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I just did not do it.

Senator STEIWER. I wondered if it would do any harm.

Mr. TAPLIN. I just let them find out when it comes around to it. I am not going to tell the world about it.

Senator STEIWER. You had control of the stock in the syndicate?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Senator STEIWER. You could deliver it?

Mr. TAPLIN. But maybe, you see, it is just an old custom of mine that I do not tell what I am doing.

Senator STEIWER. A Spanish custom? [Laughter.]

Mr. TAPLIN. A Spanish custom.

Senator STEIWER. That is all.

The CHAIRMAN. Did the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. ever borrow from the Reconstruction Finance Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. They are borrowers now. They are right now, Senator Fletcher. I will tell you why they are borrowing now, too. They built this new line that cost 17 million dollars. We got our bonds authorized by the Interstate Commerce Commission to sell at 94½, but by the time we got around to it we could not get 94½ on the market. With the last 5 million dollars' worth of bonds there wasn't any market, and there has never been any since.

Senator TOWNSEND. They are not yet sold?

Mr. TAPLIN. They are not yet sold. We put them up as collateral with the banks, and when the R.F.C. loaned us the money we paid off one half of what the banks had loaned us with those \$5,000,000 of bonds as collateral.

Senator GOLDSBOROUGH. The R.F.C. now has them?

Mr. TAPLIN. Half of them. The banks have half and now the R.F.C. has half. We had to pay off 50 percent of the bank loans, and they had to carry the other 50 percent for 3 years.

The CHAIRMAN. How much?

Senator GOLDSBOROUGH. Fifty percent.

The CHAIRMAN. No; what is the total loan?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I think we owe the R.F.C. \$3,900,000. Am I right?

Mr. BRONSON. A little more than that. About \$4,000,000.

Mr. TAPLIN. About \$4,000,000 we owe them.

The CHAIRMAN. And the banks got about one half of that?

Mr. TAPLIN. I would have to figure up what we owe the banks. I could tell you. We owe the banks about \$3,000,000. Between 2½ and 3 million dollars. But it is all well collateraled.

The CHAIRMAN. All right.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Taplin, with whom did you have the conversations specifically that led to the agreement between you in behalf of your associates, as well as yourself, and the Pennroad Corporation at which the price of \$170 a share for this stock was agreed upon?

Mr. TAPLIN. General Atterbury.

Mr. PECORA. Only General Atterbury?

Mr. TAPLIN. I think that this was after he conferred with his board at a meeting.

Mr. PECORA. Is it your recollection that you only discussed the price of \$170 a share, or reached an agreement at that figure—

Mr. TAPLIN (interposing). Reached the agreement with him.

Mr. PECORA (continuing). With General Atterbury, and no one else?

Mr. TAPLIN. I discussed it with others, but I reached the agreement with General Atterbury as trustee of the Pennroad Corporation.

Mr. PECORA. Now, when did you first take up any negotiations with General Atterbury in his capacity as a trustee of the Pennroad Corporation looking to the making of this—

Mr. TAPLIN (interposing). Mr. Pecora, I don't know when I discussed Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway with General Atterbury in the early months of 1929 whether he was talking for the Pennroad or whether he was not talking for the Pennroad. You see I did not know then. But I do know that at this time Pennroad had been organized and the Pennroad was mentioned. But I cannot tell you the dividing point as to when he began to discuss with me or who he was representing, because I did not ask him.

Mr. PECORA. Well, you learned of the organization of the Pennroad Corporation at about the time of its incorporation, did you not?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; but I do not know when—my recollection is not clear when the Pennroad came into existence.

Mr. PECORA. Well, it came into existence on April 24, 1929, according to the records.

Mr. TAPLIN. That was not known to me.

Mr. PECORA. Now, was it after that date that you resumed your discussions with General Atterbury for the sale of the 222,930 shares of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway stock?

Mr. TAPLIN. It was not after that date that I resumed with him. I had been continually with him, I think, off and on all the time, and I did discuss with him after April, and I know very distinctly I was discussing with him the question in the months of April or May, and it seems to me—my recollection is that it died out again. Nothing doing.

Mr. PECORA. Well, when you had these discussions with General Atterbury after April 24, 1929, that being the date of the incorpora-

tion of the Pennroad Corporation, did he indicate to you by anything he said that he was representing at that time in those discussions the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. Now, that is pretty hard for me to recollect whether he did or not, Mr. Pecora. I do not know, really.

Mr. PECORA. Did you have any conversations with any person connected with the Pennroad Corporation, other than General Atterbury, in respect of the price of \$170 a share which was agreed upon?

Mr. TAPLIN. I do not think so. I think with nobody else.

Mr. PECORA. Now according to the record of your testimony before the Interstate Commerce Commission in June 1930, when you were questioned about this transaction, the following questions were asked you, to which you made the following answers (the question was asked by a Mr. Martin):

Q. With whom did you negotiate as to the price? With Mr. Lee and Mr. Atterbury?

A. Yes, sir.

Q. Now, as to the agreement for the noninterference with the present management of the Pittsburg & West Virginia Railway, did you have that oral agreement with the same gentlemen?

A. Yes, sir.

Do you recall that testimony?

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, I only recall it as you read it. It must be right, and I think that is a fact.

Mr. PECORA. Well, does it refresh your recollection that in addition to discussing the price of \$170 a share which you took from the Pennroad Corporation for the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway stock you also discussed that price with Mr. Lee?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; after I discussed it with the General. Afterwards. But the price—you asked me who I made the agreement with. The agreement was with the General. I discussed it afterwards with Mr. Lee. Maybe the next day, maybe the same day. But the agreement was not made with Mr. Lee. That is what I am trying to convey to you, Mr. Pecora. The agreement was made with General Atterbury.

Mr. PECORA. Let me see if this testimony given by you before the Interstate Commerce Commission in June 1930 serves to refresh your recollection about that. I am reading again from the record of your testimony in that proceeding before the Interstate Commerce Commission:

Q. When did you begin to negotiate for the disposition of the block of 222,930 shares?

A. I don't remember.

Q. Well, approximately?

A. Oh, 1929.

Q. The fall of 1929?

A. Well, sometime in 1929.

Q. With whom did you open these negotiations?

A. Why, I talked to two different people about them. I do not know which one of the two I opened up with. I could not say whether it was Mr. Lee, the president, or not.

Q. You mean Mr. Henry H. Lee?

A. Yes.

Q. President of the Pennroad Corporation?

A. Yes, sir.

Q. He was one of the persons. And who was the other?

A. At times I talked to Mr. Atterbury, one of the trustees.

Q. Mr. W. W. Atterbury, who is also president of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

A. I believe so.

Q. And also the Pennsylvania Co.?

A. I believe he is.

Does that refresh your recollection, Mr. Taplin?

Mr. TAPLIN. Nothing in that is contradictory of what I said this morning.

Mr. PECORA. Except that in this testimony given in June 1930 you mentioned Mr. Lee first as being the person, or one of the two persons, with whom you opened and conducted the negotiations.

Mr. TAPLIN. Right. But I did not make the final agreement with Mr. Lee. I made it with General Atterbury. That is the one thing that is more distinct in my memory, as to who I made that deal with, you see, than the details who I talked with.

Mr. PECORA. Did you have a number of conversations with General Atterbury and Mr. Lee at different times?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Before you reached your final agreement with General Atterbury?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And when did you reach your final agreement with General Atterbury?

Mr. TAPLIN. Some time in September 1929. I do not remember the date.

Mr. PECORA. Did you ever discuss the price of \$170 a share with Mr. Lee before the final negotiations with General Atterbury?

Mr. TAPLIN. I do not believe I did. I do not think I had concluded to take \$170 before that final negotiation with General Atterbury.

Mr. PECORA. You understood at that time that the Pennroad Corporation was acting in the interests of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., did you not?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I understood that the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. owned the stock of the Pennroad Corporation.

Mr. PECORA. Well, did you not from that circumstance understand that the Pennroad Corporation was acting in the interests of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I do not know what you mean by "interests", but I, of course, knew that they were closely affiliated and that General Atterbury was a trustee, and that the Pennsylvania Railroad people were interested in the Pennroad, and the Pennroad was working in the interest of the Pennsylvania Railroad.

Mr. PECORA. Can you give the committee the substance of the conversations you had with General Atterbury from time to time, beginning with May or June 1929 and ending with the agreement as to the purchase price of \$170 a share in September 1929?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; I would not want to attempt to repeat the conversation—

Mr. PECORA. Not to repeat the conversation, but to give us the substance of those conversations.

Mr. TAPLIN. I wanted to sell the stock, and they wanted to buy the stock, and we just couldn't agree on the price. And I was speaking about a couple of hundred dollars, and I came down, I guess, a little

bit. I finally made up my mind that I would take \$170, and when I said I would take \$170 he said he would let me know—hold a meeting—let me know immediately. That was the close, and that was all there was to it.

Mr. PECORA. Well, did you point out to the Pennroad Corporation or any officer or person representing it any advantages that might accrue to the Pennroad Corporation from its purchase of this stock?

Mr. TAPLIN. No. I did not need to point them out. They knew them.

Mr. PECORA. They knew?

Mr. TAPLIN. They knew them better than I did.

Mr. PECORA. What did they say to you that caused you to believe that they knew?

Mr. TAPLIN. Nothing. I knew that they know the railroad game better than I do. They know the advantages better than I know them.

Mr. PECORA. Well, didn't that have something to do with the fixation of the price—your asking price of \$200 a share—that is, the fact that you knew that they knew the advantages that would accrue to them from purchasing this stock?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I do not know how I arrived at the \$200, Mr. Pecora. I just got that idea in my mind and it stuck there, and I couldn't get away with it.

Mr. PECORA. Just an arbitrary figure on your part?

Mr. TAPLIN. That is what some people thought it was, pretty arbitrary, but I did not get it.

Mr. PECORA. Well, what did anybody representing the Pennroad Corporation ever say to you concerning it which indicated the advantages that they felt would accrue to them from their purchase of this stock from you and your associates at \$170 a share?

Mr. TAPLIN. They never told me anything about the advantages. They were not boasting about them, I guess.

Mr. PECORA. How many conversations did you have with General Atterbury and Mr. Lee combined?

Mr. TAPLIN. With the two of them?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. Combined?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, I would imagine—you say the Pennroad was formed in April 1929?

Mr. PECORA. April 24, 1929.

Mr. TAPLIN. April 24, 1929. I never discussed it with Mr. Lee prior to April 1929. And then the General was away two months that summer. I would think a mere guess would be about a half a dozen conversations, anyway, from April to September, inclusive.

Mr. PECORA. In the aggregate of a half a dozen conversations?

Mr. TAPLIN. I should think so.

Mr. PECORA. Three with each, would you say?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; I think maybe—I think I must have talked with the General more than I talked with Mr. Lee, but I think everything has to be a guess.

Mr. PECORA. But you did discuss price with Mr. Lee, did you not?

Mr. TAPLIN. Not before the \$170. Not before I agreed upon it. I discussed the price, but I had then agreed with General Atterbury. The first time I ever mentioned \$170 was to General Atterbury. And he accepted it that same day, so I could not have discussed it with Mr. Lee in the interim.

Mr. PECORA. Did you make any notes at all of that conversation?

Mr. TAPLIN. No.

Mr. PECORA. So as to have a memorandum of it?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; because the same day he accepted it.

Mr. PECORA. Were you advised when the matter was presented for the consideration of the board of directors of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; that same day.

Mr. PECORA. The same day that you talked with General Atterbury the proposition was submitted to the board of directors of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. I think so. I do not know who he talked to.

Mr. PECORA. Well, that date appears to have been on September 5, 1929.

Mr. TAPLIN. September 5?

Mr. PECORA. According to the record; yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. I do not know who he talked to, but he was going to talk to somebody. I thought it was his board. He did not tell me it was his board.

Mr. PECORA. When were you first advised that the board had approved the plan to buy the stock at \$170 a share?

Mr. TAPLIN. I do not know that I was ever advised specifically that the board had approved it, but I do know that the General talked to some people, whether at a board meeting or a special meeting called for the purpose I cannot say, Mr. Pecora, but he said that they had agreed to take the stock. He didn't say the board. It might have been a special meeting. I would have said it was later than September 5. That would have been my guess.

Mr. PECORA. And was there ever a discussion between you and General Atterbury or Mr. Lee concerning the fact that the stock was to remain registered in your name after the sale?

Mr. TAPLIN. Not at that time. That was not discussed.

Mr. PECORA. When was it discussed after the sale?

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, it must have been some time after the stock was delivered and paid for, I guess, because I don't see that that was any pertinent part of the deal, as to what name the stock was in. It was not of any concern to me. I was more concerned in the money than I was in the name they carried the stock in.

Mr. PECORA. Was all of this stock at the time you turned it over to the Pennroad Corporation registered in your name?

Mr. TAPLIN. No.

Mr. PECORA. On the books of the transfer agent, or rather of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co.?

Mr. TAPLIN. No. Not before I delivered it.

Mr. PECORA. Was it at the time you delivered it to the Pennroad Corporation all registered in your name?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; I think it was endorsed in blank and delivered in the name it was then standing in on the books. I think they took that delivery.

Mr. PECORA. Well, but in whose name?

Senator GOLDSBOROUGH. On the back of the certificate or by power of attorney?

Mr. TAPLIN. That I cannot tell you, Senator Goldsborough, because my attorney, Mr. C. F. Taplin, handled all of those details, and it is not very clear to me. I think it probably was delivered to them endorsed in blank, turned over to them, and afterward transferred to me.

The CHAIRMAN. Do you vote the stock now all the time, elect a board of directors and all?

Mr. TAPLIN. Absolutely.

Mr. PECORA. Do you vote it in the exercise of your own judgment?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir. I have never had anybody in the Pennroad Co. dictate to me how to run the railroad since I have been president.

Mr. PECORA. How do you account for the fact that the Pennroad Corporation owns these two hundred and twenty-two thousand and odd shares and permits you to vote that stock?

Mr. TAPLIN. I don't know. I give it up. I guess they must think I am running it in the best interests of the railroad. I don't know.

Mr. PECORA. Did it just happen that way without any prearrangement or agreement?

Mr. TAPLIN. No, Mr. Pecora. I think they believe I know how to run that railroad better than a lot of other people.

Mr. PECORA. Do you believe that they think you can run that road better than they could run it?

Mr. TAPLIN. I believe they think so, or they would not let me run it for a minute.

Mr. PECORA. Did they ever ask you to continue the running of the road?

Mr. TAPLIN. Absolutely.

Mr. PECORA. Was it part of that understanding that the stock was to remain in your name so that you could vote it?

Mr. TAPLIN. No. The understanding that I would run the railroad was part of the deal when I sold the stock, and I think I so testified earlier in the day.

The CHAIRMAN. They do not even suggest who the directors shall be?

Mr. TAPLIN. No. Never have suggested anything to me since I have run the road.

Mr. PECORA. The Pennsylvania Railroad lines were competitors of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia, weren't they?

Mr. TAPLIN. You bet they are. They were and are.

Mr. PECORA. They were and are?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And is that why they continue to leave the management of this competing line in your hands?

Mr. TAPLIN. I don't know just what their reasons are, but they are certainly competitors, good ones.

Mr. PECORA. They must be if they let their competitor run their competing lines.

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, those are questions of fact, Mr. Pecora. They compete just about as hard against us as any other railroad there is,

and they do not give us a carload of business that we do not have to fight for.

Mr. PECORA. Are you a shareholder now of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co.?

Mr. TAPLIN. No.

Mr. PECORA. Not at all?

Mr. TAPLIN. No.

The CHAIRMAN. Are you interested in the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; not a share. I am only interested in making the best showing I can make for the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railroad Co.

Mr. PECORA. Of course, the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. and the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. are competing lines, and the Pennsylvania Railroad would not be permitted, under the rules of the Interstate Commerce Commission, to own the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co., would it?

Mr. TAPLIN. I do not believe they would, although I suppose the Pennsylvania Co. could own it, couldn't they?

Mr. PECORA. The Pennsylvania Co. is this subsidiary of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. of which you have already spoken?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Pardon me, Mr. Pecora. Mr. Larsen brings up the point that I may not have made clear to you, that this stock that I sold in my name is not in my possession. You certainly know that it is in the possession of the Pennroad Corporation, endorsed by me in blank. I haven't the stock.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recall testifying before the Interstate Commerce Commission in June 1930 as follows, in relation to this sale of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. stock to the Pennroad Corporation:

This sale of the stock was, I hoped, only a temporary one, until such time as the financial skies cleared.

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Was it a temporary one at the time you made it?

Mr. TAPLIN. I tried to explain to you, Mr. Pecora, that at the time the sale was made in 1929 I had hopes of getting through this fifth system, which required this piece of railroad as a connecting link; and I had thought that if I could get this fifth system approved by the Commission I could then make arrangements to get this piece of road back again, because of my interest in the Wheeling & Lake Erie, which I already discussed this morning, and my ownership of a lot of Western Maryland stock. Those three together made one straight line from the Great Lakes to the Atlantic Ocean, to Baltimore.

Mr. PECORA. At what price did you expect to get it back from the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I will tell you frankly I knew that I would never get it back unless I paid them whatever they paid me for it.

Mr. PECORA. You mean \$170?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Plus carrying charges?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes. Well, I knew they would not lose any money on the deal.

Mr. PECORA. What discussion did you have with General Atterbury, Mr. Lee, or anyone else representing the Pennroad Corporation respecting that?

Mr. TAPLIN. I had enough of discussion about the fifth system that led me to believe that there would be no objection to doing that if we would get the matter approved by the Commission.

Mr. PECORA. Well, what conversation did you have with these other gentlemen on that phase of the question?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I had general conversation with Judge Heiserman and a general conversation with Mr. Lee to the effect that if I could get the fifth system approved I would like to take this road back, and I had reasons to believe from replies that they made that that could be arranged undoubtedly.

Mr. PECORA. Well now, you are stating a conclusion. Tell us what they said to you upon which you base that conclusion?

Mr. TAPLIN. They said it might be possible to do that.

Mr. PECORA. Who said that to you?

Mr. TAPLIN. Mr. Lee. I think possibly Judge Heiserman, possibly General Atterbury. They all said it to me.

Mr. PECORA. Was that a reason why the stock was permitted to remain in your name?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; no, that has nothing to do with it. That did not have anything to do with it. That matter did not come up for definite discussion.

Mr. PECORA. Have you ever taken up with any of those gentlemen or anyone else representing the Pennroad Corporation the matter of your reacquiring that stock?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, as I stated previously, Mr. Pecora, the situation changed, and the Commission took that right away from me to put the fifth system through which I had and reverted again to the 4-system plan, which killed it, and I could not do it. I did not take advantage of it when I could on account of financial conditions and disturbances, and then afterward they removed my possibility of getting the fifth system through.

Senator STEIWER. Do I understand you refer to this proposal of consolidation as the fifth system?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes. What we call—there were four systems.

Senator STEIWER. Yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. And I was trying to get this system from the Lakes to the Atlantic Ocean, comprising these three roads, and I got authority from the Commission to do that, contrary to the expectation of the four trunk lines. I did not take advantage of it. And afterward the Commission withdrew that authority to put through the fifth line, so that I could not do it today. There is no way I can do it. It is contrary to the orders of the Interstate Commerce Commission.

Senator STEIWER. In your conversation with General Atterbury and these other gentlemen in which you say that they indicated they might let you take back this stock, was it also agreed that the Pennsylvania or its subsidiary companies would acquire an interest in the whole fifth system in case that were done?

Mr. TAPLIN. No. Nothing was said about that.

Senator STEIWER. They were not interested in the acquisition of the other system?

Mr. TAPLIN. I don't know. They never said anything to me about taking any interest in it.

Senator STEIWER. It was not in the conversation?

Mr. TAPLIN. I don't think they would have permitted it. I am sure the Commission would never have permitted them to have participated in the fifth system. I would not think they would.

Senator STEIWER. Was the Pennsylvania one of the lines that did not want the fifth system?

Mr. TAPLIN. No. They counted it out entirely. None of them wanted it. Why do they want any more systems?

Senator STEIWER. Why did the Pennsylvania officials agree to trade you back this stock in order to facilitate the organization of the fifth system when they did not want it organized?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I presume that if they do not want a thing organized, after I get permission they might prefer that I would have it than to have some other people have it. I mean a man can want something after a thing is perfected that he does not want before. That is very easy to see.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Taplin, I believe you said that the average price at which you and the members of your syndicate acquired these 222,930 shares was around 52½.

Mr. TAPLIN. No; I did not say that. Oh, no.

Mr. PECORA. Didn't you give that figure before?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; I said the stock, the price of 109,000 shares that the syndicate bought that is in this book here averaged 52½. Not the two hundred and twenty-two thousand-odd shares.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know the average price which the 222,930 shares cost the owners which they sold to the Pennroad?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; I do not know. I know I bought some of it as high as 160, \$165 a share, myself.

Mr. PECORA. In the open market?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. When?

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, probably bought it in 1926, 1927. Just kept it. I have very distinct recollection of one deal where I got some stock at \$160 and odd a share.

Mr. PECORA. Have you any data here or any account on behalf of the syndicate showing the profit to the syndicate from this transaction?

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, I think those books must show the profit, absolutely.

Mr. PECORA. Will you give the figure from the books?

Mr. TAPLIN. He has got the whole set there with all the figures in regard to it.

Mr. PECORA. Can you get that figure for us?

Mr. LARSEN. Each member in the syndicate withdrew his stock by paying in what he owed, and then the stock was returned to Mr. Taplin and turned in on this deal.

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; but you know, if you have a certain number of shares of stock, they cost you so much money, and if you sell at 170, you know how much money you made. He asked you how much the

syndicate made, not the outside stock. You certainly could estimate pretty close to what the syndicate made.

Mr. LARSEN. You can estimate it, and it would be on that basis about \$118 a share.

Mr. PECORA. Well, the syndicate paid an average of \$52.50?

Mr. TAPLIN. And sold it at 170. The difference is profit.

Mr. PECORA. And that profit was obtained on 109,000 shares?

Mr. TAPLIN. Approximately; yes, sir. It could not be otherwise than that, Mr. Pecora.

The CHAIRMAN. We will have to recess now till 2:30.

Mr. TAPLIN. Do you need me back after recess?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

The CHAIRMAN. It will be very brief.

(Thereupon, at 1:22 p.m., a recess was taken until 2:30 p.m. of the same day.)

AFTERNOON SESSION

The subcommittee resumed its session at the expiration of the recess.

The CHAIRMAN. The committee will come to order. Mr. Taplin will resume the stand.

TESTIMONY OF FRANK E. TAPLIN, PRESIDENT PITTSBURGH & WEST VIRGINIA RAILWAY CO., CLEVELAND, OHIO—Resumed

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Taplin, in the list that you read into the record this morning of the members of the syndicate and your other associates, in connection with this sale of stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway to the Pennroad Corporation, you included the name of F. E. Taplin, Jr.?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. As the owner of 25,166 shares?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Is he related to you?

Mr. TAPLIN. He is my son.

Mr. PECORA. Did he have title to that stock in his own individual name, or was it in a trust?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; a trust which I am trustee for and which he paid for with his own money.

Mr. PECORA. You are the trustee?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. When was that trust created?

Mr. TAPLIN. In 1918.

The CHAIRMAN. He is not a minor, is he?

Mr. TAPLIN. Oh, yes; he is a minor.

Mr. PECORA. He is still a minor?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And you are the sole trustee?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Who created the trust?

Mr. TAPLIN. I did.

Mr. PECORA. For his benefit?

Mr. TAPLIN. For his benefit; an irrevocable trust.

Mr. PECORA. The corpus of the trust originally consisted of 300 shares of the capital stock of the Yohogany, Ohio, Coal Co., did it?

Mr. TAPLIN. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. And as trustee you were given power to invest and reinvest the moneys coming into that trust estate?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. In the exercise of your own judgment and discretion?

Mr. TAPLIN. Absolutely.

Mr. PECORA. Did you as such trustee acquire these 25,166 shares of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co.?

Mr. TAPLIN. The Pittsburgh & West Virginia.

Mr. PECORA. As such trustee did you sell that stock at \$170 a share to the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. I presume that as trustee of that estate you filed an income-tax return in its behalf for the year 1929?

Mr. TAPLIN. I did.

Mr. PECORA. Did you in that return report profits accruing to the estate from the sale of those 25,166 shares?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. How much of a profit did you report?

Mr. TAPLIN. My treasurer keeps the books for each one of the children's trust accounts, and he will have to answer the question. I don't know the exact amount; but whatever the profit was, it was reported. He says he has not the books here.

Mr. PECORA. As I understand it, the profit reported in connection with that sale was one of \$2,559,132.72.

Mr. TAPLIN. How much?

Mr. PECORA. \$2,559,132.72; that the selling price in 1929 was \$4,278,220, and that the cost price to the estate was \$1,719,087.28, resulting in this profit of \$2,559,132.72. Do you recall when those 25,166 shares were acquired?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; I could not recall offhand.

Mr. PECORA. My information is that they were acquired in 1926. Would that be correct, do you think?

Mr. TAPLIN. I would not be surprised. Our treasurer says that some of that stock was acquired in 1923. He was a member of the syndicate, and some of the stock was acquired as a part of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway syndicate.

Mr. PECORA. I presume an income tax was paid by the estate?

Mr. TAPLIN. Obviously; by the trust.

Mr. PECORA. And you, as trustee, paid it?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. For the year 1929?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Do you remember how much it was?

Mr. TAPLIN. No.

Mr. PECORA. Did you as trustee for that trust estate qualify as a dealer in securities?

Mr. TAPLIN. I think so. I think my attorney brought that question up. I recall his mentioning the matter.

Mr. PECORA. When the return was made for the year 1929, was the tax which was levied one based upon the estate being a dealer in securities or being an investor?

Mr. TAPLIN. I could not answer that. Maybe our treasurer, who keeps their books, can answer. [Addressing Mr. Larson:] Do you know?

Mr. PECORA. See if you can find out, please.

Mr. TAPLIN. He says it was made on the basis of an ordinary individual that had that much profit.

Mr. PECORA. As an investor?

Mr. TAPLIN. I would think so.

Mr. PECORA. In previous years was the tax paid on the basis of the trust estate being a dealer in securities?

Mr. TAPLIN. I don't know that. He says not.

Mr. PECORA. How about the year 1926?

Mr. TAPLIN. I don't know.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recall having a controversy with the Internal Revenue Department in connection with the income-tax return filed by you for the year 1926 as trustee for that trust estate?

Mr. TAPLIN. I know there was a controversy when the Treasury Department, in 1923, tried to make out that those trusts for each member of my family, dated in 1918, were not bona fide trusts. That matter was taken right up through the Board of Review and Tax Appeals, and they, not having a leg to stand on, dropped the case. My treasurer thinks that you are referring to the 1926 return—

Mr. PECORA. I am referring to 1926.

Mr. TAPLIN. In which there was some question of some stock being sold, and they having taken the oldest stock—went back and corrected it in some way to the oldest stock prior to the stock that was reported.

Mr. PECORA. Was not the question really involved in connection with the 1926 return as to whether or not the taxpayer, who was yourself as trustee, was entitled to carry forward a loss as a dealer in securities?

Mr. TAPLIN. I don't know enough about the details, Mr. Pecora, to answer; but I know that my brother, who is my counsel, did mention to me at one time the question of the right to deal in securities.

Mr. PECORA. Yes. Did you qualify, as trustee for that trust estate, as a dealer in securities under the income tax law?

Mr. TAPLIN. Mr. Larsen here says that the account was all accepted and O.K.'d, and there was no controversy.

Mr. PECORA. I am asking you the question: Did you qualify as trustee for the estate of Frank E. Taplin, Jr., as a dealer in securities?

Mr. TAPLIN. That I don't know. I don't believe I understand the difference between an individual buying and selling stocks and qualifying as a dealer in securities. I don't appreciate what the difference is between them.

Mr. PECORA. You know that there are certain rights and privileges in the income tax law which are available only to a dealer in securities and not to an ordinary investor?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; I am not enough familiar with income-tax matters to know that, even. I don't know the distinction between the two.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recall the amount of tax paid by you as trustee for this trust estate for the year 1929, which was the year in which this profit of over two and a half million dollars was reported

in connection with the sale of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia stock to the Pennroad Corporation, amounting to about \$309,000 plus?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; I don't recall the amount of it.

Mr. PECORA. And that if that return had been made in behalf of the estate as a dealer in securities rather than as an investor, the tax would have been assessed at \$684,676.52?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; I don't know that.

Mr. PECORA. Didn't you take that question up with your attorney at all?

Mr. TAPLIN. No.

Mr. PECORA. At no time?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; because he tells me what the interpretation of the law is. I give him the profits in any transaction, and he and Mr. Larsen, the treasurer, figure out the return.

Mr. PECORA. Were you questioned in any way by the Internal Revenue Bureau about these returns?

Mr. TAPLIN. Not that I know of.

Mr. PECORA. Were you ever questioned by any representatives or officials of the Internal Revenue Bureau?

Mr. TAPLIN. About that return?

Mr. PECORA. About any of these returns.

Mr. TAPLIN. Not that I recall. They may have been, but I don't recall.

Mr. PECORA. When you say "they may have been", whom do you refer to?

Mr. TAPLIN. Mr. Larsen or my counsel, Mr. C. F. Taplin, who make up the returns.

Mr. PECORA. Will you ask them to inform you so that you may answer the question?

Mr. TAPLIN (addressing associates). Was there ever any controversy about the 1929 return that you know of?

He says not that he knows of.

Mr. PECORA. Can you not acquire the information from your counsel now to enable you to tell this committee whether or not this trust estate ever qualified as a dealer in securities for the purposes of the income-tax law?

Mr. TAPLIN. When I go to Cleveland I can get my counsel—

Mr. PECORA. Are they not present?

Mr. TAPLIN. No, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Are not the gentlemen who are associated with you here in position to give you that information?

Mr. TAPLIN. Mr. Larsen is the treasurer and makes up the report, but Mr. C. F. Taplin, my counsel, is not here.

Mr. PECORA. Does not Mr. Larsen know about that?

Mr. TAPLIN. He says he never heard of any. He says he doesn't think they are qualified as dealers in securities any more than I may be. Am I qualified as a dealer in securities?

Mr. PECORA. I don't know.

Mr. TAPLIN. I don't know that I am. I may be. I don't know that I am.

Mr. PECORA. Who made out your return—Mr. Larsen?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Before you leave the stand, let me ask you, for the record, this question: Among the associates, so-called, whom you named this morning in connection with the sale to the Pennroad Corporation of these 222,930 shares, you named the North American Coal Corporation. Are you connected with that corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. I am president of it.

Mr. PECORA. Are you its principal stockholder?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; I and my family.

Mr. PECORA. That is a close corporation, owned by your own family?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. I will examine Mr. Larsen now, Mr. Chairman.

The CHAIRMAN (addressing Mr. Larsen). Do you solemnly swear that what you will testify in this hearing will be the truth, the whole truth, and nothing but the truth, so help you God?

Mr. LARSEN. I do.

TESTIMONY OF OTTO C. LARSEN, SECRETARY-TREASURER NORTH AMERICAN COAL CORPORATION, CLEVELAND, OHIO

Mr. PECORA. What is your full name?

Mr. LARSEN. Otto C. Larsen.

Mr. PECORA. What is your business or occupation?

Mr. LARSEN. Secretary-treasurer North American Coal Corporation.

Mr. PECORA. Do you make up the income-tax returns filed by Mr. Frank E. Taplin as trustee for the estate of Frank E. Taplin, Jr.?

Mr. LARSEN. I do.

Mr. PECORA. For what period of years have you been doing that?

Mr. LARSEN. I believe since 1923.

Mr. PECORA. In any of the years since 1923 have the returns made out in behalf of that estate or taxpayer been made out as a dealer in securities?

Mr. LARSEN. I do not think so. I remember that question coming up in connection with the tax return for some particular year.

Mr. PECORA. Did it come up with respect to the return for 1926?

Mr. LARSEN. It seems to me that it was possibly the 1926 return.

Mr. PECORA. What disposition was made of that question?

Mr. LARSEN. I really don't know. That was handled by Mr. C. F. Taplin, and I was not advised of the ultimate outcome.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recall that in the return for that year you were permitted to carry forward certain losses that had accrued during that year, on the ground that the taxpayer was a dealer in securities?

Mr. LARSEN. I do not.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recall that that is not the fact?

Mr. LARSEN. I couldn't say whether it was or was not the fact.

Mr. PECORA. Did you make out a return for this estate in the year 1929?

Mr. LARSEN. I believe I did.

Mr. PECORA. Was it made out then as a dealer in securities or as an investor?

Mr. LARSEN. I think, as an investor.

Mr. PECORA. As an investor you were permitted to pay 12½ per cent capital profits?

Mr. LARSEN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And the tax apportioned or assessed for that year was on that basis?

Mr. LARSEN. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Had it been on the basis of a dealer in securities, the tax would have been much heavier?

Mr. LARSEN. I suppose we took it on a capital-investment basis as an investor.

Mr. PECORA. You took it on that basis in order to save on the tax?

Mr. LARSEN. That is right.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know how much was saved thereby?

Mr. LARSEN. No; I do not.

Mr. PECORA. Was it the difference between \$684,676.52 and the sum of \$309,755.43, which I understand was the tax that was assessed and paid?

Mr. LARSEN. Possibly it might have been.

Mr. PECORA. From whom did you get your instructions as to the basis upon which you make out these returns, Mr. Larsen?

Mr. LARSEN. From Mr. C. F. Taplin.

Mr. PECORA. Is he an attorney?

Mr. LARSEN. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. So that when it is profitable to make the return out as an investor, it is done in that way, and when it is profitable to make it out as a dealer in securities, it is done in that way?

Mr. LARSEN. I don't believe the returns have ever been made as a dealer in securities.

Mr. PECORA. You said you recalled the question having arisen one year.

Mr. LARSEN. Yes; it came up when there was some item at issue in connection with the audit of the tax return.

Mr. PECORA. What was the determination made when that question came up?

Mr. LARSEN. I don't recall the final determination.

Mr. PECORA. Was it not that the taxpayer, which was this estate, was a dealer in securities?

Mr. LARSEN. I would not be able to say.

The CHAIRMAN. A dealer in securities has to pay the normal tax and then a surtax, does he not, under the income-tax law, whereas the individual pays the regular tax?

Mr. LARSEN. The individual pays the normal tax and a surtax if his income is above a certain figure.

Mr. PECORA. But a dealer in securities is not entitled to the benefits of the capital loss and capital gain section of the law. You know that, don't you?

Mr. LARSEN. Is not anyone entitled to that privilege?

Mr. TAPLIN. What do you have to do to qualify?

Mr. PECORA. You have a brother who is an attorney and who can advise you. Suppose you ask him.

Mr. TAPLIN. I never discussed the question with him. Mr. Bronson, here, does not know anything about this case, but he has given me a little enlightenment. He says a dealer in securities buys securi-

ties for other people, and that an individual buys them for himself. Of course all I know is—

Mr. PECORA. No; that is not the law. Of course, one who buys for others may be also qualified as a dealer in securities; but in order to qualify as a dealer in securities one does not have to engage in the business of buying and selling for the account of others. He may confine his operations to his own account.

Mr. BRONSON. That is possible, of course. It is a distinction without a difference.

TESTIMONY OF FRANK E. TAPLIN, PRESIDENT OF THE PITTSBURGH & WEST VIRGINIA RAILWAY CO.—Resumed

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Taplin, did you ever make any contention before the Internal Revenue Bureau that this trust estate was acting as a dealer in securities?

Mr. TAPLIN. Not to my knowledge.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recall anything at all about any controversy raised with respect to the income-tax return for 1926 in behalf of the trust estate?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; I don't remember anything coming up. My counsel may know all about it, C. F. Taplin, but I would not.

Mr. PECORA. Well, Mr. Chairman, from the information which I have it seems for the year 1926 a question was raised as to whether this trust estate was entitled to carry forward a loss it claimed to have sustained in the year 1925, to deduct that loss from its taxable income for the year 1926, on the ground that its business was that of buying and selling securities. In other words, was a dealer. And the ruling of the Department was to the effect that the taxpayer was entitled to carry that forward, to carry it forward against the taxable income for the year 1926 as a loss sustained for the year 1925. It also appears that in 1929 a return made in behalf of this estate and the tax levied against the estate was levied, not on the basis of the estate being a dealer but being an investor, which made a difference to the taxpayer's advantage of \$374,921.09. In view of the fact that the witness, Mr. Frank E. Taplin, is not familiar with that controversy or those issues or the proceedings had with respect thereto, and in view of the absence of Mr. C. F. Taplin, I cannot proceed with this line of inquiry any further at this time. At some future time I will bring to the attention of the committee such additional evidence as is procurable.

The CHAIRMAN. Mr. Taplin, you do not recall those facts and circumstances, you say?

Mr. TAPLIN. I do not know.

The CHAIRMAN. Have you any recollection of having changed your attitude with reference to that question?

Mr. TAPLIN. No. I have no recollection of ever having changed it at all. I did not know that I was a dealer in securities.

The CHAIRMAN. You did not change your business between 1926 and 1929 as the trustee of that estate?

Mr. TAPLIN. No.

The CHAIRMAN. You continued in the same business as before?

Mr. TAPLIN. The same as before.

Senator BARKLEY. Have you turned over your affairs to your counsel and your associates to such a degree that they would be justified in putting you down in an income-tax report as a dealer in securities without consulting you?

Mr. TAPLIN. I wouldn't think so. I do not know what these lawyers do sometimes when they are looking after your tax returns, but I wouldn't think they could do it without I qualified or signed something. I did not know that I was a dealer in securities.

Mr. PECORA. Now, Mr. Taplin, with regard to the interest for the first quarter that you testified this morning you paid to the Pennroad Corporation in connection with the loan of \$1,950,000 that you obtained from it, in June of 1929, do you recall who made that interest payment?

Mr. TAPLIN. No. The only reason I say that it was paid was because if I have a note from a man paying interest quarterly it must have been due in September, and I would say it must have been paid. But I cannot say how.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recall having paid it yourself?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; I cannot say that I recall it. I have no recollection of having signed a check.

Mr. PECORA. Did you deal with that loan as though it was your personal and individual obligation, or did you deal with it as yourself being the manager of this syndicate?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I do not know that I could answer that, Mr. Pecora, very clearly.

Mr. PECORA. Well, can you tell me who could?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, it is possible that I made the loan for the account of the syndicate.

Mr. PECORA. Well, wasn't it important to you to know that you were dealing with that as a personal and individual obligation or as an obligation that you incurred in behalf of the syndicate?

Mr. TAPLIN. I cannot go back and recollect it now. But Mr. Larsen can tell you. If it was a syndicate loan, then the syndicate would have paid the interest on it.

Mr. PECORA. But I am trying to find out who paid the interest.

Mr. TAPLIN. He says it was not a syndicate obligation, and he is the one who ought to know, because he kept the books. He kept my accounts, and he says it was not a syndicate operation.

Mr. PECORA. Well, were you careful in making out your income-tax return to deduct from the amount of your income any interest items paid by you in the course of the tax year?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes; if I pay any interest, it will show on my check book. Or if the company paid it for my account, they would tell me and charge it up to me.

Mr. PECORA. My information is that you claimed no deduction for payment of interest to the Pennroad Corporation whatsoever for the year 1929.

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, Mr. Larsen says he doesn't think it was the syndicate account. Someone must have deducted interest, if it was paid, whose ever account it was for. Are you talking about my personal return now?

Mr. PECORA. Yes; your personal return.

Mr. TAPLIN. I can go back and get that for you. Mr. Larsen says he thinks that was my daughter's return.

Mr. PECORA. Who borrowed the money, your daughter or you? According to the evidence of this morning your note was the one given for the \$1,950,000.

Mr. TAPLIN. But I cannot tell you whether I signed that note as trustee or as an individual.

Mr. PECORA. Look at the note itself.

Mr. TAPLIN. Where is the note?

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Lee, you have the original note, haven't you?

Mr. LEE. I think there is a copy in your files.

Mr. PECORA. A copy was put in the record this morning, and my recollection is that it is your personal note, Mr. Taplin.

Mr. TAPLIN. We have it here, I think.

Mr. PECORA. Well, look at it, please.

Mr. TAPLIN. Here it is. I show it to you.

Mr. PECORA. Now, this copy that you show me has no signature on it at all.

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, Mr. Larsen says I borrowed it for the account of Clara Louise Taplin, my daughter.

Mr. PECORA. Does he know more about it than you?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir. He keeps the books for every one of them.

Mr. PECORA. What is your present recollection? Did you borrow this money for yourself or for your daughter?

Mr. TAPLIN. If he says I borrowed it for my daughter's account, then that is what it was borrowed for, and he ought to know because he keeps the books. And she owns the stock.

Mr. PECORA. Well, who negotiated the loan, you or Mr. Larsen.

Mr. TAPLIN. I negotiated it.

Mr. PECORA. Did you negotiate it for yourself or for your daughter?

Mr. TAPLIN. I don't recall. Mr. Larsen says he thinks it was her note. It was her stock.

Mr. PECORA. Was your daughter a minor?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir. Mr. Larsen says it was her note and that she paid it. He ought to know as he has the keeping of her books.

Mr. PECORA. What was your daughter, who was a minor, borrowing nearly \$2,000,000 for?

Mr. TAPLIN. To buy this stock. I think you will find that if she borrowed it she paid it off. Is that correct, Mr. Larsen?

Mr. LARSEN. Yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. Mr. Pecora, Mr. Larsen says she paid it off.

Senator BARKLEY. Mr. Taplin, is a transaction of nearly \$2,000,000 so small a matter that it passes out of your mind?

Mr. TAPLIN. It is not a small matter, but there were a great many transactions at that time, and if it was for her account and she paid the interest, and if she owns the stock and she paid off the loan, I would say that is the best evidence that it was borrowed for her account.

Mr. PECORA. Did your daughter ask you to borrow \$2,000,000?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; she is a minor.

Mr. PECORA. How old was she in 1929?

Mr. TAPLIN. About 11 years old, I think. I think under the trust agreement I never asked them anything about what I did with their money. This is their own money. Mr. Pecora, you started out to

say the trust agreements were where the money started from, that 300 shares of stock was the beginning of her trust fund, and I sold that stock, I remember, because of some arbitration proceeding, for \$1,150 a share, from which she must have realized about \$450,000 in 1918. That was invested and reinvested to her account, and my money has never been—and Mr. Larsen will tell you—mixed up with theirs; my accounts have never in any way been mixed up with her money.

Mr. PECORA. Were those trusts created for your daughters' benefit for income-tax purposes?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I will tell you why they were created.

Mr. PECORA. If you please.

Mr. TAPLIN. In 1918 I owned a considerable amount of this stock in this coal company that you spoke of, and I was going to sell the stock, and an attorney of mine, not my brother but another attorney, called my attention at that time to the fact as to what the tax would be. But the stock could be given away, in 1918, if absolutely given away and irrevocably given away, which I did, and distributed the stock to my family. It was theirs, and the books were kept for every dollar accumulated since then, every payment made for their account was kept separately and never mixed up with my account in any way, shape, form, or manner. There are three trust agreements, for each one of my three children. I will be very glad to furnish you with the books from 1918 up to date, showing every transaction made for their account. Their income-tax returns are made separately. Everything that they have is theirs. And you can have those books.

Mr. PECORA. What is your answer to my question: Were those trust estates created for income-tax purposes?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I would say that I was advised as to the income tax, that if I sold the stock it would be one thing, but if I wanted to give it away irrevocably, it would be another thing. And that is what I did, to avoid the heavy tax, which was possible in 1918. But afterwards we were not able to do that, because they changed the law; that if you gave it and the person sold it, as I understand the law, the cost is based upon cost to the giver. The department threshed that all out for a long term of years, because the instruments which I just gave you a copy of were decided to be bona fide in every way.

Senator BARKLEY. Then the answer to Mr. Pecora's question is yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I explained to him that I did it because the tax on the sale of that stock would be different, it was less this way.

Senator BARKLEY. Then you did create these trusts for income-tax purposes?

Mr. TAPLIN. I would say that that is a correct statement.

Mr. PECORA. That is all I wanted on that.

The CHAIRMAN. If it passed as a gift there would be no income tax at all, is that it?

Mr. TAPLIN. I believe at that time the law was that the cost was based upon the value when you gave it away, but it was afterward changed.

The CHAIRMAN. Then in regard to this note, your daughter, 11 years old, did not sign the note, did she?

Mr. TAPLIN. No; I signed every note, or any note or paper or check, as trustee, for one of my children, for every one of the three.

The CHAIRMAN. The note was probably signed by you as trustee for your daughter?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I suppose I have signed it probably for her account, and on their books immediately it would be placed. I never took any money from their accounts and used it for myself. Sometimes, though, I have, vice versa, let them have the use of my own money.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Taplin, when you negotiated this loan of \$1,950,000 with the Pennroad Corporation did you tell that corporation you were negotiating the loan as trustee for your 11-year-old daughter?

Mr. TAPLIN. Well, I wouldn't have told them that, because it would have been immaterial to them who I was negotiating it for so long as I gave them plenty of collateral on it. I do not think I would have told them. Even though I were giving it for my daughter I wouldn't have told them. I am very sure of that, that I wouldn't have told them.

Mr. PECORA. In whose name was the collateral registered at the time you turned it over to the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. TAPLIN. I think I borrowed some of the collateral put up at that time.

Mr. PECORA. From whom?

Mr. TAPLIN. I wouldn't want to say, but that is just my faint recollection, that I borrowed some. It may be that Mr. Larsen can tell you.

The CHAIRMAN. All the collateral is not your daughter's collateral, nor was it held in her name.

Mr. TAPLIN. I have a recollection that I borrowed some of the collateral in order to keep control of that stock.

Senator BARKLEY. Did you borrow it from her trust?

Mr. TAPLIN. No. I borrowed stock that did not belong to her, borrowed it for her account and put it up as collateral until the note was paid.

Mr. PECORA. My last question was: From whom did you borrow it?

Mr. TAPLIN. I think Mr. Larsen ought to be able to tell you. He says he thinks I borrowed some of it from the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway stock.

Mr. PECORA. Was that the syndicate you were the manager of?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir; although I would have to have authority.

Mr. PECORA. That is the syndicate referred to in the syndicate agreements put in evidence this morning?

Mr. TAPLIN. Yes, sir. I believe that Mr. Kraus was the syndicate manager with me at the time.

Mr. PECORA. Originally?

Mr. TAPLIN. And Mr. Kraus knew what the deal was for, that it was to protect this stock, and he O.K.'d the borrowing of the collateral.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Chairman, I think I will now resume the examination of Mr. Lee.

Mr. TAPLIN. Are you all through with me now, Mr. Pecora?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. TAPLIN. I thank you very much.

(Thereupon Mr. Taplin was excused.)

The CHAIRMAN. All right, Mr. Lee, will you come forward and resume the stand?

TESTIMONY OF HENRY H. LEE, PRESIDENT OF THE PENNROAD CORPORATION—Resumed

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Lee, did you hear the testimony that Mr. Frank E. Taplin gave here today?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Did it refresh your recollection in any way as to any participation you had in the year 1929 as president of the Pennroad Corporation in the transaction that resulted in the purchase by your corporation from Mr. Taplin and his associates of the 222,930 shares of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. stock?

Mr. LEE. Since my last appearance here I have refreshed my recollection somewhat from my own records and from talking to my associates.

Mr. PECORA. What associates did you talk to that served to refresh your recollection since last Friday?

Mr. LEE. My staff.

Mr. PECORA. Well, that is still very indefinite. Who are they?

Mr. LEE. Mr. Ogden here.

Mr. PECORA. Is Mr. Ogden an officer of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. What office does he hold?

Mr. LEE. Vice president and treasurer.

Mr. PECORA. Who else?

Mr. LEE. Judge Heiserman.

Mr. PECORA. He is attorney for the corporation?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Anyone else?

Mr. LEE. No.

Mr. PECORA. Do you now recall what part, if any, you had in the negotiations with Mr. Frank E. Taplin that led to the making of that sale?

Mr. LEE. This is my recollection, that my first knowledge of it, my first entrance into it, was in the fall of 1929.

Mr. PECORA. Give us, will you, your complete recollection of your part in the negotiations.

Mr. LEE. So far as I recall, Mr. Pecora, after the Pennroad Corporation board acted on September 5 of 1929, some time after that time was my first actual knowledge of the negotiations, the question of price, and so forth; that Judge Heiserman and I participated on the 26th of September, as I recall it, in a conference with Mr. C. F. Taplin, representing Mr. Frank E. Taplin, and his associates.

Mr. PECORA. Well, that was nearly 3 weeks after your board had adopted the resolution which was put in evidence last Friday. Do

you mean to say that that was the first time the thing was called to your attention?

Mr. LEE. Mr. Pecora, I wasn't at the board meeting on September 5. I was at the board meeting on September 11, when the minutes of the meeting of September 5 were, no doubt, read.

Mr. PECORA. Was that your first knowledge of the fact that any negotiations had been pending involving the purchase by your company of this large block of Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. stock?

Mr. LEE. To the best of my recollection, it was.

Mr. PECORA. It was?

Mr. LEE. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And you were the executive head of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. That was a deal that involved some 38 million dollars by your company, wasn't it?

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. And the first knowledge you had of it was after the preliminary negotiations had been concluded and an agreement arrived at?

Mr. LEE. I do not know whether they had been concluded or not, but that was my first knowledge of the fact that negotiations for the acquisition of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia stock had approached a point of completion.

Mr. PECORA. When did you first learn that any such negotiations were under way?

Mr. LEE. As far as I can recall that was it.

Mr. PECORA. Late in September of 1929?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And it was then brought to your attention, as you now recall it, through hearing read at the meeting of the board the minutes of the prior meeting, which was held on September 5, 1929?

Mr. LEE. That is the best of my recollection.

Mr. PECORA. The subject had never before been discussed at any meeting of your board?

Mr. LEE. I do not recall it, Mr. Pecora. I have no remembrance about it.

The CHAIRMAN. When was the first time you discussed it with Mr. Taplin, who has just left the stand?

Mr. LEE. I should say sometime between the 11th of September and the end of September or the first part of October. I haven't any definite recollection of that.

Mr. PECORA. Well, now, Mr. Taplin has testified that in June of 1930 he gave certain testimony with regard to this transaction when he appeared before the Interstate Commerce Commission, and that in the course of that testimony he stated that he had taken up the negotiations which culminated in this transaction with both you and General Atterbury. Have you any recollection of having any such negotiations with Mr. Taplin?

Mr. LEE. No, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Did General Atterbury ever report to you prior to September 11, 1929, that he was having any negotiations with Mr. Taplin covering that subject?

Mr. LEE. I do not recall.

Mr. PECORA. Were you the active executive head of the Pennroad Corporation in the year 1929?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Will you explain how it was possible for a 38-million-dollar transaction to be undertaken in behalf of your corporation and you not know anything about it until the arrangements had been concluded, if you were the active head of the corporation?

Mr. LEE. Well, I can only account for it by venturing this guess: That it was no doubt an informal negotiation until the time that the Pennroad board acted. Now, during that period, Mr. Pecora and gentlemen of the committee, we had formed the corporation and issued 5,800,000 voting-trust certificates, and we had acquired a number of issues, and I was extremely busy.

Mr. PECORA. Wasn't it the largest single deal that your corporation negotiated in its whole history?

Mr. LEE. I think so. That is right.

The CHAIRMAN. When did you first learn of the price of \$170 a share being fixed?

Mr. LEE. Our directors on September 5 authorized the acquisition of 220,000 shares at not more than \$175 per share. My knowledge of the price of \$170 a share was a little later than that, I assume, Senator Fletcher.

Mr. PECORA. You were available for the purpose of taking part in those negotiations between the time of your election as president of the Pennroad Corporation in April of 1929 and September of 1929, were you not?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir. Excuse me, except that I went on vacation prior to September 5.

Mr. PECORA. How long did that vacation last?

Mr. LEE. Well, it lasted until I was back for duty on the 11th of September.

Mr. PECORA. But how long did it last?

Mr. LEE. That would be from the 4th or probably the 3rd of September.

Mr. PECORA. For about a week?

Mr. LEE. A little more than a week.

Mr. PECORA. You were not so busy with other matters in behalf of the Pennroad Corporation that you could not take up this most important deal of all, were you?

Mr. LEE. No; not if I had been asked about it or advised of it.

Mr. PECORA. How do you account for the fact that you as president were not asked about it, or invited to take part in the negotiations that culminated in the transaction?

Mr. LEE. I do not account for it, except from the testimony here this morning that evidently Mr. Taplin negotiated with other people.

Mr. PECORA. Well, he also said that he negotiated it with you.

Mr. LEE. Well, I think that he was confused about that.

Mr. PECORA. It would not be an extraordinary thing for him to negotiate this deal with you as the head of the Pennroad Corporation, would it? Wouldn't it be rather the ordinary and logical thing for him to do?

Mr. LEE. I suppose it would be the thing under some circumstances. It is also not inconceivable that he would take it up with

a director of the Pennroad Corporation, whom he knew a great deal better than he knew me.

Mr. PECORA. Would a director of your corporation feel that he had authority to go ahead and enter into negotiations involving \$38,000,000 for your corporation without advising you about it?

Mr. LEE. He wouldn't have any authority. But he would have the right, I think, to engage in negotiations provided he made no commitments.

Mr. PECORA. How often did the board of directors of the Pennroad Corporation meet between April of 1929 and September of 1929?

Mr. LEE. A number of times; but irregularly.

Mr. PECORA. Well, at whose instance were those meetings called from time to time?

Mr. LEE. Well, I cannot recall that.

Mr. PECORA. Wasn't there any provision in the bylaws for such meetings of the board of directors at regular intervals?

Mr. LEE. I think on the order of the board. I do not recall whether in those early months, after the creation of the corporation, we had adopted any regular meeting day.

Mr. PECORA. Now, on last Friday your testimony, as I recall it was, in substance, to the effect that Mr. A. J. County, who was a director of the Pennroad Corporation, had conducted those negotiations with Mr. Taplin.

Mr. LEE. As I recollect, I said I had no part in the inception or continuance of the negotiations, and to the best of my remembrance, Mr. County was the person who did conduct them.

Mr. PECORA. Your recollection has been refreshed since last Friday, and you now say it was not Mr. County but General Atterbury.

Mr. LEE. My recollection on that subject was refreshed this morning.

Mr. PECORA. By whom?

Mr. LEE. By Mr. Taplin's testimony.

Mr. PECORA. But you disagree with Mr. Taplin's testimony of this morning insofar as he stated that he had conducted these negotiations with you as well as with General Atterbury.

Mr. LEE. No; I meant with regard to his negotiations with General Atterbury.

Mr. PECORA. You do disagree with Mr. Taplin's testimony of today with regard to his having negotiated this transaction with you?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. As well as with General Atterbury?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Why did you say on last Friday that Mr. County, a director of the Pennroad Corporation, had undertaken these negotiations in the first instance in behalf of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. LEE. Because I believed that to be so. If you will recall, I also testified, or tried to illustrate, that my idea about the beginning of those negotiations, started with the loan of \$1,950,000 to Mr. Taplin, and it was quite reasonable in my own mind, with a recollection starting with myself, that if Mr. Taplin had taken up negotiations of the loan with Mr. County, that he had taken up

the question of the sale of his Pittsburgh & West Virginia interests with Mr. County.

Mr. PECORA. Did you recognize on last Friday that there was a direct connection between the making of that loan and the negotiations which resulted in the purchase of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. stock by your company?

Mr. LEE. No; I cannot say that I did. But the connection of the gentlemen and the property made me feel that some time between there and the fall Mr. County had been the negotiator.

Mr. PECORA. What advantages did you see accruing to the Pennroad Corporation from the purchase of this large block of stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. at \$170 a share?

Mr. LEE. Well, its strategic value both from a commercial standpoint and from its location.

Mr. PECORA. Strategic value to whom?

Mr. LEE. Strategic value in the way of traffic.

Mr. PECORA. To whom?

Mr. LEE. Or I should say commercial value.

Mr. PECORA. To whom?

Mr. LEE. To the Pittsburgh & West Virginia, and consequently to its owner in the way of return.

Mr. PECORA. Well, what was that strategic value?

Mr. LEE. Well, it sat in the middle of the steel and coal industries of Pennsylvania. And it was earning good money.

Mr. PECORA. How much was it earning?

Mr. LEE. Let me see—

Mr. PECORA. Or let me put it in this way: What was it earning on the basis of \$170 a share; what percentage?

Mr. LEE. It was paying 6-percent dividends, and earning somewhat more than that.

Mr. PECORA. Paying 6 percent on its par value?

Mr. LEE. On its par value.

Mr. PECORA. And the par value was what?

Mr. LEE. \$100, as I recall.

Mr. PECORA. So that on a valuation of \$170 a share it was paying—

Mr. LEE. Something over 3½ percent.

Mr. PECORA. Something less than 4 percent?

Mr. LEE. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And you considered that a good investment for the Pennroad Corporation to make?

Mr. LEE. For that reason and for the possibilities of its future value in connection with the very evident desire of railroad companies to align themselves in one or more systems.

Mr. PECORA. Well, what systems did you have in mind at that time?

Mr. LEE. I cannot recall that I had any particular system in mind at that time, but perhaps some of this testimony refers to things I have learned—or I have thought of afterwards. One of the main things to my mind was the fact that Mr. Taplin wanted to include the Pittsburgh & West Virginia with the Wheeling & Lake Erie and Western Maryland in a small system running from Baltimore to the Great Lakes, and that seemed to me personally to be a very good

scheme, because it was a short route and ought to get a good deal of business.

Mr. PECORA. Was not the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. operating through this territory, too?

Mr. LEE. Well, its operation was farther north, as I recall it, from this little three party system that I am speaking of.

Mr. PECORA. Well, the stock of the Pennroad Corporation originally was offered to the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., was it not?

Mr. LEE. That is correct, sir.

Mr. PECORA. You were then the treasurer?

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. The treasurer of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And you resigned as such treasurer in order to become the president of the Pennroad Corporation on April 24, 1929?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Who asked you to become the president of the Pennroad Corporation, Mr. Lee?

Mr. LEE. Mr. A. J. County.

Mr. PECORA. Was he then a vice president and director of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Had you had any experience as an executive head of a holding company prior to that?

Mr. LEE. No, sir. I was a departmental officer of the Pennsylvania Railroad.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Lee, what services were rendered by Kuhn, Loeb & Co. to the Pennroad Corporation in consideration for which the Pennroad Corporation gave to Kuhn, Loeb & Co. the options on several hundred thousand shares of its stock at \$15 a share?

Mr. LEE. I cannot answer that of my own knowledge, because I did not attend those conferences, but I should say that they were given those options for their advice as to of the type of corporation that might be formed.

Mr. PECORA. To whom did they give that advice?

Mr. LEE. To whoever consulted them on the subject.

Mr. PECORA. Don't you know who they were?

Mr. LEE. Well, I think they were Mr. County and Mr. Atterbury, and possibly Mr. Jay Cooke and Mr. E. B. Morris.

Mr. PECORA. Those gentlemen were all connected with the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. at that time?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir; as directors or officers.

Mr. PECORA. They were the organizers, were they not, of the Pennroad Corporation? They took the leading part in the organization of the company?

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. Well, what services did Kuhn, Loeb & Co. render the Pennroad Corporation subsequent to April 24, 1929, while you were its president?

Mr. LEE. They brought to our attention the Canton Co.

Mr. PECORA. Well, they received a commission of 2½ percent on the purchase by the Pennroad Corporation of the capital stock of the Canton Co., did they not?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And that was a commission which resulted in a payment to them of over \$300,000, as I recall it?

Mr. LEE. That is correct, as far as my memory goes.

Mr. PECORA. What other services did they render the Pennroad Corporation since you have been the president?

Mr. LEE. We felt free to consult with them on any subject that might arise.

Mr. PECORA. Well, what subjects did you consult with them about? Did any arise from time to time?

Mr. LEE. I remember one particular one, which was probably in 1930, when I consulted Mr. Mortimer Schiff, now deceased, with reference to the investment of some money in a number of securities of different railroad companies in the country, and secured from him his recommendations as to what he considered we might buy.

Mr. PECORA. And what roads, or what securities, rather, did he advise you the Pennroad Corporation might buy at that time?

Mr. LEE. To my recollection they were The Chicago & North Western, Baltimore & Ohio stock, and some convertible bonds. The Delaware & Hudson Co. The Missouri, Kansas & Texas preferred stock and Southern Pacific, as I recall it.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know whether or not Kuhn, Loeb & Co. were bankers for any of these railroads at that time, or had done any financing for any of them?

Mr. LEE. I think for all of them, except I do not remember about the Missouri, Kansas & Texas—the Katy.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recall any other service Kuhn Loeb & Co. rendered to the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. LEE. In the organization of it, as I said before—not from my own knowledge, but from facts developed later, they were of very great service in determining the type of corporation that ought to be formed. They also helped us, of course, in connection with the allotment. I realize they got a fee for that, but their advice was valuable. And I think, too, there is a good deal of value to be attached to the fact that I feel free to go to them, to their partners, from time to time and ask advice about any situation we might be in. It is pretty hard to pin down the exact thing we may desire to ask advice about.

Mr. PECORA. Did the Pennroad Corporation ever enter into any agreement with Kuhn, Loeb & Co. whereby it would seek their advice?

Mr. LEE. No, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Why did you go to them for advice from time to time?

Mr. LEE. They are a very well known and conservative banking house. I think a good many of us in the Pennroad directorate had known them for a great many years.

Mr. PECORA. Was it because they had been bankers for the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. that you went to them?

Mr. LEE. I think that is a very natural conclusion.

Mr. PECORA. Now, it appears from the testimony of Mr. Otto H. Kahn of that firm given before this committee last week that his firm realized a total of some \$5,840,000.

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. From commissions paid to it by the Pennroad Corporation, fees paid to it, and profits they made from the sale of stock which they bought from the Pennroad Corporation under these option agreements you have referred to.

Mr. LEE. That is correct, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And that those profits and commissions were all realized within a period of a few months in the year 1929. Will you enumerate to this committee, if you can, the specific services they rendered for which they received nearly \$6,000,000 or were enabled to make nearly \$6,000,000?

Mr. LEE. I do not think I can, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. Do you think anybody can?

Mr. LEE. I doubt it very much. On the other hand, it seems to me, too, that they took a certain amount of risk in what they undertook for us, and the tables might have been turned and they might have lost money or at least made very much less.

Mr. PECORA. Do you think they took a risk when they bought the stock from your company at a fixed price under options that they need not have exercised except at a time when the stock was selling in the open market for more than the option price; do you think they were taking a risk in that?

Mr. LEE. Mr. Pecora, I thought myself at the time that as the issue went to the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad at 15, that if we could get options at 16, 17, 18, or 19 afterward, it was not such a bad thing for us.

Mr. PECORA. Do you realize that on April 25, 1929, the day after the incorporation of the Pennroad Corporation, its stock was selling at 25; not 15, 16, or 17 or 18, but at 25?

Mr. LEE. No one was more surprised than I was.

Mr. PECORA. But you know that is a fact?

Mr. LEE. That is true; yes. I have heard it testified to here.

Mr. PECORA. And in the light of that fact do you think they were taking any risk at all?

Mr. LEE. It would appear not. But, of course, later the price of the stock did recede considerably, even before it was actually issued.

Mr. PECORA. But it receded to a point where they were able to make only 5½ million dollars' profit on the stock they acquired under these options? That was quite a recession to them, was it not?

Mr. LEE. Not to them, but for the market.

Mr. PECORA. I am just asking you these questions, Mr. Lee, because you are the executive head of this big corporation that sold nearly \$140,000,000 worth of its securities to the investing public, to find out really what services are rendered by bankers for which they receive such compensation as has been testified to here in the present instance. And you cannot enlighten us any further than you have on that, can you?

Mr. LEE. I do not think I can do so well as Mr. Otto Kahn.

Mr. PECORA. Now, why was the stock purchased from Mr. Frank E. Taplin and his associates by your corporation permitted to remain in the name of Mr. Frank E. Taplin to this date?

Mr. LEE. Well, in the first place, our negotiation with him ended with the acquisition of the last block of stock he presented shortly

after the first of January 1930. We were preparing at once to have it transferred because the stock went of record for dividend on, I think, the 15th of January—that same month. We were not as yet desirous on our own part of making public our acquisition, and, to the best of my recollection, we put the stock in his name as the nominee for that purpose originally.

Mr. PECORA. Well, why has it continued to stand in his name for the last 3½ years?

Mr. LEE. I think it has continued to stand in his name, because we also had an understanding with him—arrived at after the settlement, as I recall it—that he could continue to operate and manage the property, provided he did so in a manner not adverse to our interests.

Mr. PECORA. Who was to determine whether or not his operation of that road was adverse to your interests?

Mr. LEE. That would be our organization, sir.

Mr. PECORA. By that do you mean the Pennroad Corporation or the Pennsylvania Railroad?

Mr. LEE. I mean the Pennroad Corporation.

Mr. PECORA. Well, what interests did the Pennroad Corporation have in the management of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. of any special character?

Mr. LEE. A great desire to see it make as much money as it could out of the transportation of traffic for the benefit of the stockholders.

Mr. PECORA. Well, was the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. regarded as a line competing with the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. LEE. Yes; I should say it would around the Pittsburgh district.

Mr. PECORA. And the original voting trustees of the Pennroad Corporation, who had full power to vote the stock for a period of 10 years from its incorporation, were all officers and directors of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., were they not?

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. And you heard the testimony of Mr. Taplin to the effect that his negotiations with your company were conducted by him in behalf of himself and his associates with General Atterbury on behalf of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Is it fair to assume from that that the interest which General Atterbury had in the Pennroad Corporation was an interest that was reflected or absorbed by the interest he had in the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., of which he was president?

Mr. LEE. I consider Mr. Atterbury a man of such character that if he is a trustee or a director of some other corporation, he is going to endeavor to give his trusteeship or directorship in behalf of the company whose interests are then being considered.

Mr. PECORA. Well, what was he doing then? Acting as trustee for the owners of 73 percent of the stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. and at the same time acting as president of a rival or competing line known as the "Pennsylvania Railroad Co."?

Mr. LEE. Well, the competition, if you do not mind, Mr. Pecora—the competition side of it rather makes me smile, because one is a great big corporation and the other one is a little one. They could only compete within a very limited territory.

Mr. PECORA. But within that limitation of territory they were strong competitors, were they not?

Mr. LEE. I assume that is so.

Mr. PECORA. Do you think General Atterbury when he acted for the Pennroad Corporation in these negotiations with Mr. Taplin was acting in the interests of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. or in the interests of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. Which?

Mr. LEE. I should think he was acting and negotiating under the terms of his own statement with reference to the reason for the organization of the Pennroad, for the protection of the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., and to my mind also trying to find investments for the Pennroad Corporation.

Mr. PECORA. Well, were the investors in the Pennroad Corporation always the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. LEE. Do you mean the people who purchased—

Mr. PECORA. The people who purchased the voting trust certificates; yes.

Mr. LEE. They were, I think, very considerably, in the first place.

Mr. PECORA. In the first instance, but subsequently was not that stock dealt in by the general public?

Mr. LEE. Very decidedly.

Mr. PECORA. Very decidedly. Well, now, when the general public who were not stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. became investors in the Pennroad Corporation, whose interests were the officers of the Pennroad Corporation seeking to serve, their own stockholders, or the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. LEE. I think the very fact that there must have been a substantial change in the ownership of voting-trust certificates from those first entitled to subscribe means just one thing—that the officers and directors of the Pennroad Corporation must consider whatever they do primarily from the standpoint of the investments of the Pennroad and the protection of the Pennroad's interest.

Mr. PECORA. Was it because they thought that in September 1929 it would be a good thing to buy 73 percent of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. at \$170 when the road was paying 6 percent dividends that they agreed to buy that stock at that figure and thereby return only 3½ percent on their investment?

Mr. LEE. Well, by the way business looked at that time, Mr. Pecora, there appeared to be no limit to where it might go and where the market might go.

Mr. PECORA. Have you any notion why there was never any written agreement entered into between the Pennroad Corporation or any of its officers or representatives acting for it and Mr. Taplin and his associates in connection with this stock purchase?

Mr. LEE. Well, no doubt there was confidence in Mr. Taplin. I think there is something to the fact that a good many negotiations of that sort would be undertaken, at least prior to their completion, without evidence in the way of formal agreements. And, of course, we did not pay out any money in that connection until we received securities for it at the price we had agreed upon.

Mr. PECORA. Was it customary for your road to enter into such negotiations or transactions purely by word of mouth?

Mr. LEE. I think it depends a good deal on the transaction.

Mr. PECORA. What is that?

Mr. LEE. It would depend a good deal on the nature of the transaction or the person.

Mr. PECORA. Well, did it have any transaction comparable to it in size or magnitude on a word-of-mouth basis, purely on the oral basis?

Mr. LEE. The Detroit, Toledo & Ironton was one, as I recall it.

Mr. PECORA. Any other?

Mr. LEE. I believe not. No others of any consequence. Whether there were formal agreements executed or not I do not know. I do not recall at this time.

Mr. PECORA. With regard to this loan of \$1,950,000 that your company made in June 1929 to Mr. Taplin, was that loan made to Mr. Taplin individually or to himself as trustee for the estate of his infant daughter?

Mr. LEE. My understanding has always been that it was made to him individually.

Mr. PECORA. And he signed the collateral note, did he not, individually?

Mr. LEE. That is my recollection, Mr. Pecora. May I ask: In that file of mine which you have before you is there a copy of the signature on the note? The one with the blue backer.

Mr. PECORA. Here is your file. I guess you are more familiar with it [handing same to Mr. Lee].

Mr. LEE. Thank you, sir. Of course, this is a copy of the note, because necessarily when the note was paid Mr. Taplin got his original back. It is signed, that is, bears the typed signature of F. E. Taplin.

Mr. PECORA. Individually?

Mr. LEE. Individually.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know whether interest was paid on that note for the first quarter?

Mr. LEE. I do not recollect, Mr. Pecora. I always thought that interest was paid at the time of settlement for the first installment of Pittsburgh & West Virginia stock.

Mr. PECORA. That was some time in October 1929, was it not?

Mr. LEE. That was the 16th of October 1929.

Mr. PECORA. 1929. Now, the first quarter's interest became due in September 1929, according to the terms of the note?

Mr. LEE. It would be September 25; yes.

Mr. PECORA. Now, was the interest paid at that time?

Mr. LEE. Will you excuse me a moment?

Mr. PECORA. Surely.

Mr. LEE (after conferring with Mr. Ogden). No; it was not paid at that time. It was included in——

Mr. PECORA. Did your company seek to enforce the payment of that interest?

Mr. LEE. I have no recollection about it, Mr. Pecora. It was quite a surprise to me when the question was asked this morning.

Mr. PECORA. Well, whose duty was it to attend to that little detail for your company?

Mr. LEE. That would be the duty of our treasurer.

Mr. PECORA. Do you know any reason why the interest was not paid in September?

Mr. LEE. I cannot recall.

Mr. PECORA. Did you learn for the first time today that the interest had not been paid in September of 1929 on this note?

Mr. LEE. Yes. I had no idea about it. I rather thought—if I thought anything about it—that this was a note where interest was payable semiannually.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recall Mr. Taplin asking for any forbearance from your corporation in the matter of this interest in September 1929?

Mr. LEE. No; I recall nothing about it at this time, Mr. Pecora. It raised a new question in my mind.

Mr. PECORA. It seems that all these negotiations with Mr. Taplin, including this former one of this loan of \$1,950,000, were conducted on a rather informal basis and in a rather informal way.

Mr. LEE. It looks so.

Mr. PECORA. Am I correct in that assumption?

Mr. LEE. I think you are, sir.

Mr. PECORA. What was the reason for that?

Mr. LEE. In this particular case I cannot say. I have no recollection about it whatever. I do know that we received interest in full on the 16th of October, together with the principal of the note.

Mr. PECORA. Well, when you received it in October you received payment in full of the principal of the note and all accrued interest out of the sum of money that your company then paid to Mr. Taplin and his associates for a large block of the stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia road, did you not?

Mr. LEE. That is correct, sir. It was an off-set in the original transaction.

Mr. PECORA. Now Mr. Lee, last Friday you gave me a printed copy of the statement for the year ended December 31, 1932, sent to the stockholders of the Pennroad Corporation, which I now show you [handing same to Mr. Lee]. Is that a correct copy of that statement?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir; that is correct. That is a printed copy.

Mr. PECORA. I offer it in evidence and ask that it be spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted and placed in the record.

(The Pennroad Corporation statement for year ended December 31, 1932, was received in evidence, marked "Committee Exhibit 54 of July 6, 1933", and is here printed in the record in full, as follows:)

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT 54

THE PENNROAD CORPORATION—STATEMENT FOR YEAR ENDED DECEMBER 31, 1932

Directors: W. W. Atterbury, George W. Bovenizer, A. J. County, William M. Elkins, Rodman E. Griscom, R. B. Mellon, Effingham B. Morris, A. H. S. Post, Joseph Wayne, Jr., H. H. Lee, president.

Voting trustees under voting trust agreement of May 1, 1929: Effingham B. Morris, Joseph Wayne, Jr., William M. Potts.

Agent and depository of voting trustees: The Philadelphia National Bank.

Registrars of voting trust certificates: Chemical Bank & Trust Co., New York; Girard Trust Co., Philadelphia.

THE PENNROAD CORPORATION,
Philadelphia, Pa., March 14, 1933.

To the Stockholders of the Pennroad Corporation:

There is submitted herewith an income statement of the corporation for the calendar year 1932, together with statement of earned surplus and general balance sheet as of December 31, 1932.

There is also appended a list of the securities owned by the corporation with their cost and approximate market value as of December 31, 1932, where listed on stock exchanges and where the corporation owns less than a majority of such securities. In the case of stocks, bonds, notes, and advances having no stock exchange quotations or where this corporation owns at least a majority of such securities, no attempt is made to estimate their value or the value of the control represented thereby.

The net income for the year 1932 was \$793,897.65, a decrease of \$3,701,148.46 as compared with that for the year 1931. The decrease in net income is due primarily to reductions in dividends received. It indicates the greatly reduced gross and net earnings of enterprises in which this corporation is interested in a year of business curtailment. Any improvement in general business will be reflected in increased earnings of the companies in which this corporation has stock holdings, although the prospect of increased dividend receipts by reason thereof is not encouraging for the near future.

Notes payable were reduced by \$1,125,000 during the year to \$400,000.

There was no change in the stock of the corporation during the year 1932, voting trust certificates for which are in the hands of 156,418 holders.

During the year 1932 the corporation suffered a loss through the death of two members of the board of directors, James S. Alexander and Jay Cooke. George W. Bevenizer, of New York City, was elected to fill the vacancy in the board caused by the death of Mr. Alexander, and William M. Potts, of Philadelphia, succeeded him as a voting trustee.

By order of the board of directors.

HENRY H. LEE, *President.*

The Pennroad Corporation income statement for period Jan. 1 to Dec. 31, 1932

		Increase or decrease compared with 1931
Income:		
Dividends	\$226,438.80	—\$3,327,186.67
Interest from bonds.....	688,461.00	—391,261.66
Interest from other accounts..	93,342.22	—12,526.86
Total income.....	\$1,008,242.02	—3,730,975.19
Deductions:		
Interest paid.....	45,374.99	+12,595.75
Taxes.....	25,244.38	+20.66
General expenses.....	143,725.00	—42,443.14
Total deductions.....	214,344.37	—29,826.73
Net income credited to earned surplus..	793,897.65	—3,701,148.46

Statement of earned surplus

Credit balance, Dec. 31, 1931.....	8,266,213.59
Net income for 1932.....	793,897.65
Credit balance, Dec. 31, 1932.....	9,060,111.24

General balance sheet, Dec. 31, 1932

ASSETS

Cash	\$347, 755. 04
Investment securities at cost.....	145, 679, 920. 50
Accrued income.....	80, 426. 69
Other assets.....	40, 300. 10
Total assets.....	146, 148, 402. 33

LIABILITIES

Notes payable.....	400, 000. 00
Taxes accrued.....	545, 549. 11
Interest and accounts payable.....	916. 66
Capital stock (9,090,000 shares without par value).....	90, 900, 000. 00
Surplus:	
Capital surplus.....	45, 241, 825. 32
Earned surplus.....	9, 060, 111. 24
Total liabilities.....	146, 148, 402. 33

Pennroad Corporation—Securities owned Dec. 31, 1932

	Shares	Cost	Stock exchange price, Dec. 31, 1932
SECURITIES FOR WHICH STOCK EXCHANGE QUOTATIONS ARE AVAILABLE			
Atlantic Coast Line R. R. Co., common.....	8, 000	\$1, 480, 000. 00	\$142, 000
Baltimore & Ohio R. R. Co., common.....	500	59, 125. 00	4, 375
Boston & Maine R. R.:			
Prior preference 7 percent cumulative dividend.....	44, 304	5, 077, 871. 45	974, 688
First preferred A 5 percent cumulative dividend.....	50, 547	4, 575, 494. 69	404, 376
First preferred B 8 percent cumulative dividend.....	24, 979	3, 602, 038. 91	256, 034
First preferred C 7 percent cumulative dividend.....	24, 337	3, 064, 630. 87	237, 285
First preferred D 10 percent cumulative dividend.....	14, 668	2, 663, 104. 99	176, 016
First preferred E 4½ percent cumulative dividend.....	19	1, 629. 25	95
Preferred old 6 percent noncumulative dividend.....	14, 968	1, 704, 645. 82	104, 776
Common.....	27, 565	2, 948, 292. 40	172, 281
Chicago & North Western Ry. Co. common.....	1, 000	85, 175. 00	3, 750
Delaware & Hudson Co. common.....	2, 000	354, 400. 00	100, 000
Kansas City Southern Ry. Co. common.....	1, 000	80, 825. 00	7, 375
Lehigh Valley R. R. Co. common.....	10, 000	650, 000. 00	110, 000
Missouri-Kansas-Texas R. R. Co. 7 percent preferred.....	4, 500	484, 062. 50	51, 187
New York, New Haven & Hartford R. R. Co. common.....	148, 800	17, 301, 851. 25	2, 027, 400
New York, New Haven & Hartford R. R. Co. preferred.....	1, 200	149, 300. 00	30, 000
Pennroad corporation voting trust certificates.....	152, 284	969, 828. 60	209, 390
Seaboard Air Line Ry. Co. common.....	402, 119	4, 523, 838. 75	100, 529
Southern Pacific Co. common.....	500	60, 125. 00	8, 000
Southern Ry. Co. common.....	10, 000	1, 415, 244. 32	50, 000
Baltimore & Ohio R. R. Co. convertible 4½ percent bonds, 1960.....	<i>Par value</i> \$174, 000	180, 612. 00	50, 460
		51, 432, 095. 80	5, 220, 017
STOCKS HAVING NO STOCK-EXCHANGE QUOTATIONS OR WHERE CORPORATION OWNS AT LEAST A MAJORITY OF THE STOCK			
	<i>Shares</i>		
(Over 99 percent) Canton Company of Baltimore common.....	21, 975	13, 432, 817. 90	-----
(Over 99 percent) Detroit, Toledo & Ironton R. R. Co. common.....	245, 327	23, 917, 017. 74	-----
Detroit, Toledo & Ironton R. R. Co. scrip.....	\$53. 06	53. 06	-----
(100 percent) National Freight Co. common.....	120, 000	2, 400, 000. 00	-----
(74 percent) Pittsburgh & West Virginia Rwy. Co. common.....	223, 230	37, 910, 145. 00	-----
(100 percent) Springfield Suburban R. R. Co. common.....	5, 100	200, 500. 00	-----
		77, 860, 533. 70	-----

Penroad Corporation—Securities owned Dec. 31, 1932—Continued

	Shares	Cost	Stock exchange price, Dec. 31, 1932
BONDS, NOTES, AND ADVANCES HAVING NO STOCK-EXCHANGE QUOTATIONS			
	<i>Par value</i>		
Detroit, Toledo & Ironton R.R. Co. first mortgage 5 percent (total issue, \$4,329,000).....	\$2,918,000	\$2,693,171.00	-----
Detroit, Toledo & Ironton R.R. Co. first and refunding mortgage 5 percent (total issue).....	10,626,000	9,983,820.00	-----
Detroit, Toledo & Ironton R.R. Co. 6 percent equipment notes (total issue, \$163,900).....	56,400	56,400.00	-----
Notes secured by collateral.....	325,000	325,000.00	-----
Advances to subsidiary companies.....	3,328,900	3,328,900.00	-----
		16,387,291.00	-----

We report that on January 5, 1933, we examined, or received confirmations from the depositaries of, the securities owned by the Penroad Corporation at December 31, 1932, as recited in the foregoing statement and have found them to be recorded on the books of the corporation.

LYBRAND, ROSS BROS. & MONTGOMERY
Accountants and Auditors, Philadelphia, Pa.

Mr. PECORA. Now, the purpose of sending out this annual statement to your stockholders is to inform them accurately of the financial condition of their company, is it not?

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. Do you consider that this statement operates to do that?

Mr. LEE. I think so, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Do you think a person reading that, studying it, and giving effect to all of its contents would thereby gain a complete and accurate knowledge of the financial condition of your corporation as of December 31, 1932?

Mr. LEE. I think so. We could not publish every detail.

Mr. PECORA. Well, now, let us see. This statement, which has been marked "Exhibit 54", in the general balance sheet under the caption of "Assets" carries an item of "Investment securities at cost," amounting to \$145,679,920.50. And also set forth the total assets of the company to be \$146,148,402.33. So that that item of investment securities of \$145,679,920.50 virtually shows all the assets, or nearly all the assets of the company?

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. Now, on December 31, 1932, were those securities worth \$145,679,920.50?

Mr. LEE. I think it would be pretty hard to tell what they were worth.

Mr. PECORA. Well, what were they worth at market prices on that date?

Mr. LEE. On the back sheet of the report we showed what we felt was the best thing we could do, and that is set forth the market prices as well as cost for the securities for which stock exchange quotations were available. Where the stocks had no stock exchange quotations, or at least where a majority of the stock is owned, we show the cost, because we ourselves, I think, are unable to say what they may be worth. To my mind, the control of the corporation is

of very great value from a bargaining standpoint when it comes to the time of the sale of our assets, and ours are for sale if we can get a price for them that we consider satisfactory.

Mr. PECORA. Now, on the back sheet or the last sheet of this printed financial statement there are various blocks of securities owned on December 31, 1932, by the Pennroad Corporation, which are itemized and to which a total cost price of \$51,432,095.80 is set forth.

Mr. LEE. That is right.

Mr. PECORA. And in an adjoining column those securities are shown at their market or public exchange price quotation as of December 31, 1932, to be worth \$5,220,017. Is that right?

Mr. LEE. That is right.

Mr. PECORA. That 51 million represents a little bit more than only one third of the total investment of securities which had been purchased for its portfolio by the Pennroad Corporation, doesn't it?

Mr. LEE. That is right.

Mr. PECORA. Why didn't you give the stock market or public quotation for those other securities as of December 31, 1932?

Mr. LEE. They either had none or the corporation owned at least a majority of the stock.

Mr. PECORA. Well now, the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. stock had a public quotation; it was listed on the stock market, wasn't it?

Mr. LEE. We own more than a majority.

Mr. PECORA. Is that any reason for not giving your stockholders in your annual report to them the market value of the securities as of December 31, 1932?

Mr. LEE. Mr. Pecora, I thought I answered that question before by saying that neither I nor any member of my board felt that we could assign a value to control. And, further than that, I think if we had attempted to make any estimate of the value of those assets that we hold we would be putting ourselves in a bad position for future trading if anybody comes along who wants to buy them.

Mr. PECORA. Why couldn't they consult the public market quotations without coming to you if they wanted to find out what they were worth?

Mr. LEE. But I don't think the public market quotation reflects the value of Pittsburgh & West Virginia stock.

Mr. PECORA. It reflected the value of the stock as of that date, didn't it, in the estimation of the company?

Mr. LEE. It reflected what public was willing to pay for it, I suppose.

Mr. PECORA. You said that the purpose of issuing these annual reports was to correctly and fully inform the stockholders of the financial condition of the company, didn't you?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Do you think it was fair to the stockholders to state that Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. common stock was worth \$37,910,145?

Mr. LEE. Mr. Pecora, we did not state that.

Mr. PECORA. Well, that is the only figure at which you carry that security.

Mr. LEE. That is correct.

Mr. PECORA. Among your assets.

Mr. LEE. And we state the reason why we are doing so.

Mr. PECORA. You do not state it here, do you, in this annual report?

Mr. LEE. That is the cost price. We head that particular portion of the report as stocks having no stock exchange quotations or where the corporation owns at least a majority of the stock.

I might say that that form and that method of set-up was adopted after a great deal of consideration by the directors of our corporation. Now, I call attention—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). You mean it was put out in this form advisedly and after considerable discussion by the board?

Mr. LEE. Considerable consideration. I would like to call your attention to the second paragraph of the first inner page of the report where we say that "There is also appended a list of the securities owned by the corporation with their cost and approximate market value as of December 28, 1932, where listed on stock exchanges and where the corporation owns less than a majority of such securities. In the cases of stocks, bonds, notes and advances having no stock-exchange quotations or where this corporation owns at least the majority of such securities, no attempt is made to estimate their value or the value of the control represented thereby."

I merely mention that, if you please, sir, to show that we were not trying to hide anything. We were merely stating to the public and to our voting trust-certificate holders the facts as we saw them.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recall that under date of April 21, 1933, a letter was sent by the Pennroad Corporation to Mr. Fred Horowitz of the Department of Justice in Washington, D.C.?

Mr. LEE. I don't remember the date, but I remember a letter being sent; yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. What was the occasion of the sending of that letter?

Mr. LEE. Mr. Horowitz came to us and asked us to give him some information in connection with inquiries he said had been made of the department with reference to our investments.

Mr. PECORA. Do you recall that in the letter that was sent to Mr. Horowitz in response to his request for such information the following statement was made in connection with the purchase of the two hundred and twenty thousand and odd shares of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co.:

Two hundred and twenty-two thousand nine hundred and thirty shares were purchased through Frank E. Taplin at \$170 per share, settlement being made for 166,480 shares on October 16, 1929; 10,000 shares on November 12, 1929; 22,035 shares on November 21, 1929; and 24,415 shares on January 7, 1930. Total cost of shares purchased through Frank E. Taplin, \$37,898,100.

Mr. LEE. If you are reading from a copy of the letter, I assume it is correct.

Mr. PECORA. Well, were these shares purchased by your company through Mr. Taplin, or were they purchased from Mr. Taplin and his associates?

Mr. LEE. Purchased from him and his associates.

Mr. PECORA. Why was the Department of Justice advised that the purchase was made by your corporation "through" Mr. Taplin instead of "from" him?

Mr. LEE. Mr. Pecora, as far as I can remember, I think that was just a mistake in the use of a word.

Mr. PECORA. Now, I want to ask you about a transaction through the medium of which your company acquired 402,119 shares of the common stock of the Seaboard Air Line Railway Co.

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. For a total consideration of \$4,523,838.75. Are you familiar with that transaction?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Did you take any part in the negotiations that terminated in that transaction?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. With whom did you have those negotiations?

Mr. LEE. With Mr. Bollard, of Dillon, Read & Co.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Pollard?

Mr. LEE. Mr. Bollard—B-o-double-l-a-r-d.

Mr. PECORA. Bollard. When did they commence?

Mr. LEE. Some time after the Seaboard announced its plan relating to the 5-percent adjustment mortgage bonds, which plan was dated May 27, 1929, and contemplated certain rearrangements, which I think I referred to last Friday, of its capital structure, and which included the provision of additional cash to be realized from the issue and sale of new stock. They culminated—

Mr. PECORA. Well, now, you say some time after that. That does not give us the date of the commencement of these negotiations.

Mr. LEE. I don't think we are able to state when they did start.

Mr. PECORA. How long did the negotiations last before they terminated in a sale?

Mr. LEE. My records do not show that, Mr. Pecora, at this time. I have got a copy of the agreement here.

Mr. PECORA. Will you produce it, please?

Mr. LEE. Dated October 9, 1929, formal agreement by which we agreed to take that stock [handing document to Mr. Pecora].

Mr. PECORA. Thank you. Is this a correct and true copy of the agreement in question?

Mr. LEE. We believe it to be true.

Mr. PECORA. We offer it in evidence and ask it be spread on the record.

The CHAIRMAN. Let it be admitted and entered on the record.

(Agreement dated October 9, 1929, between the Pennroad Corporation and Dillon, Reed & Co. was designated "Committee Exhibit 55", and appears in full in the words and figures following:)

COMMITTEE EXHIBIT 55

OCTOBER 9, 1929.

Seaboard Air Line Railway Co. proposes to change the par value of its common stock from \$100 per share to no-par value, to authorize an additional amount of common stock, and to offer to the holders of its preferred and common stocks, including holders of common stock to be received by depositing adjustment bondholders, the right to subscribe to two new shares of the no-par value common stock for each share of preferred and common stock now held (including stock to be received by depositing adjustment bondholders in exchange for adjustment bonds deposited).

The amount of new stock to be offered as above will vary somewhat dependent on the amount of adjustment bonds deposited, but it is expected that the amount will approximate 1,900,000 shares. The present syndicate owning

Seaboard securities (herein called the Securities Syndicate) now owns approximately 105,000 shares of Seaboard preferred and common stock and will receive approximately 25,000 shares of additional common stock in exchange for deposited adjustment bonds owned by this syndicate. This syndicate will subscribe for the amount of additional stock offered to it under the terms of the above offer—approximately 260,000 shares.

Dillon, Read & Co. and associates propose to form a new underwriting syndicate to underwrite the above-described offering of new stock by Seaboard Air Line Railway Co. It is expected that the price at which the new stock is to be offered to stockholders will be in the neighborhood of \$12 per share, but it may be somewhat above or below that price, as agreed upon by the company, the underwriting syndicate, and the Interstate Commerce Commission.

If the proposed additional offer of new stock is made and underwritten as above outlined, the Pennroad Corporation agrees, at such time as the underwriting syndicate takes up and pays for any stock not subscribed and paid for by stockholders, to purchase from the Securities Syndicate or from sellers designated by the Securities Syndicate an amount of new stock equivalent to 25 percent of all stock so purchased by the underwriting syndicate from the Seaboard Air Line Railway Co. (Said purchase not to include any part of the 260,000 shares referred to above to be subscribed for by the present syndicate owning Seaboard securities.) Should 25 percent of the stock purchased by the underwriting syndicate not aggregate 125,000 shares the stock to be so purchased by the Pennroad Corporation is to be increased to a total of 125,000 shares—such aggregate amount not exceeding, however, the full amount of the stock received by the underwriting syndicate upon its underwriting. The price to be paid by the Pennroad Corporation is to be the price per share at which the stock is offered to the stockholders of the Seaboard Air Line Railway less the net amount per share received by the underwriting syndicate as compensation for the underwriting. (It is understood that said amount to be received by the underwriting syndicate may be less than the total amount per share to be paid by Seaboard Air Line Railway Co. as underwriting compensation as Dillon, Read & Co. and associates propose to retain not to exceed 25 cents per share from the amount to be paid by the company as compensation for their services in forming the underwriting syndicate.)

It is understood that it is intended to form the proposed underwriting syndicate and make the proposed offering of new stock promptly (subject to market conditions and the approval of the Interstate Commerce Commission). The obligation of the Pennroad Corporation to complete above described purchase of Seaboard Air Line Railway Co. common stock is to be of no effect unless the above described stock offering is made and underwritten as above outlined within a period not longer than 6 months from date.

THE PENNROAD CORPORATION
By H. H. LEE, *President*
"SECURITIES SYNDICATE"
By DILLON, READ & Co.
(Signature illegible.)
COVERDALE & COLPITTS

To the extent that the stock to be purchased by the Pennroad Corporation does not aggregate 125,000 shares, the Pennroad Corporation is to receive a cash payment equivalent to the net amount per share received by the underwriting syndicate as compensation for the underwriting, computed on the total number of shares by which the number of shares purchased by the Pennroad Corporation falls short of 125,000.

H. H. L.
D. R. & Co.

The CHAIRMAN. Did you buy the stock from Dillon, Read & Co.?

Mr. LEE. We bought it from a syndicate.

Mr. PECORA. Of which they were the managers?

Mr. LEE. Of which they were the managers, according to my recollection. Mr. Pecora, may I add that that transaction was approved by our board on October 9, 1929?

Mr. PECORA. Yes; but when were the negotiations commenced?

Mr. LEE. Well, the best I can tell you about that is from this memorandum I have before me, and you asked us to bring data down here, and we have tried our best, and some of this was written by others of my staff. The best I can say is it started sometime after that Seaboard plan was announced in 1929. The plan was dated May 1929, and I haven't any certain recollection of when the negotiations began. They certainly, of course, began some time prior to that agreement.

Mr. PECORA. Did you enter upon these negotiations in behalf of the Pennroad Corporation in pursuance of any direction of the board of directors of that corporation?

Mr. LEE. We entered upon those negotiations with Messrs. Dillon, Read & Co. after consideration of the subject of some investment in the Seaboard by our directors, which was, as far as I recall, entirely an informal matter.

Mr. PECORA. Are there any entries in the minute book of your board showing the consideration that was given to this subject by the board?

Mr. LEE. Not that I recall, except the action taken approving the agreement and approving the transaction.

Mr. PECORA. In other words, the only official action taken by the board was one ratifying and approving this agreement of October 9, 1929?

Mr. LEE. That is correct. [After conferring with associates:] Mr. Pecora, if I may, my assistants here tell me that our action was an action which authorized the proper officers to take steps to negotiate that agreement, and it was not a ratifying and confirming action. It was an authority to us to go and do it.

Mr. PECORA. At what meeting was that authority given to you?

Mr. LEE. The same day, sir.

Mr. PECORA. On October 9, 1929?

Mr. LEE. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. The first official action taken by the board was at the end of the negotiations?

Mr. LEE. Yes. Mr. Pecora, they tell me, too, that that agreement in memorandum form was submitted to the board, so evidently the negotiations with Dillon, Read & Co. had proceeded up to the point of framing an agreement which we were satisfied to go into, and then we took it to our board and had them approve and authorize its execution.

Mr. PECORA. What were the reasons that prompted you as the head of the Pennroad Corporation to enter into this transaction with Dillon, Read & Co.?

Mr. LEE. Well, the Seaboard had its new plan. It included a provision for cash to be realized from the sale of common stock which was under consideration by the Commission and later approved by them.

Mr. PECORA. That is, the Seaboard was selling additional stock?

Mr. LEE. Was selling additional stock.

Mr. PECORA. To the public. Did it have any earnings, any net earnings, in 1929? Or was it operating at a deficit that year?

Mr. LEE. The statistical data relating to the company, I am advised here, for May 1929, 5 months to May 1929, compared with the corresponding month of the previous year, showed a substantial in-

crease in net income. I assume, therefore, it had net income. In September 1929 the president of the company stated a substantial part of the increase of \$1,900,000 of gross income for 8 months over the previous year would be reflected in net income, notwithstanding considerable maintenance expenditures.

Mr. PECORA. What are you reading that from?

Mr. LEE. I am just reading that from a memorandum prepared by my staff.

Mr. PECORA. Well, prepared by whom?

Mr. LEE. By Mr. Hebden of my staff.

Mr. PECORA. By whom?

Mr. LEE. By Mr. Hebden of my staff.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Hepburn?

Mr. LEE. Mr. Hebden—H-e-b-d-e-n.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Hebden. Does he hold any office in the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. LEE. Assistant secretary.

Mr. PECORA. Who conducted these negotiations in 1929—you or Mr. Hebden?

Mr. LEE. Oh, I did.

Mr. PECORA. Don't you recall the factors that entered into your decision it would be a good thing for your company to buy over 400,000 shares of the stock of the Seaboard Air Line?

Mr. LEE. I think I testified the other day, Mr. Pecora, we only wanted to buy 125,000.

Mr. PECORA. Yes. Well, what prompted you to buy 402,000 instead of 125,000?

Mr. LEE. We were under contract to take 25 percent, as I recall the figure, of the total amount of stock offered to the stockholders of the Seaboard which might have to be taken by an underwriting syndicate.

Mr. PECORA. You were in that contract because you willingly entered into that contract for your company?

Mr. LEE. That is true.

Mr. PECORA. What were the factors, the circumstances, that caused you to regard that contract as a good thing for the Pennroad Corporation to enter into?

Mr. LEE. Well, my remembrance of it is, in the first place, that Seaboard had begun apparently to pick up. It was about to adopt a financial plan which was believed would help its capital structure. At that time it appeared that the South was again coming forward in its business, and the price at which we were able to acquire the stock and proposed to acquire it was \$11.25 a share, and at the time of entering into that agreement it was selling from \$16.25 to \$17.25.

Mr. PECORA. Now, you are reading again from somebody else's prepared statement, aren't you?

Mr. LEE. I am reading this part only as to stock prices.

Mr. PECORA. I wish you would tell us from your own recollection, Mr. Lee. You were the gentleman who conducted these negotiations for your corporation?

Mr. LEE. I was one of them.

Mr. PECORA. Who were the others?

Mr. LEE. Mr. County was the other.

Mr. PECORA. Now, can you tell us from memory the reasons that prompted you, as the president of the Pennroad Corporation, to conclude it would be a good thing for the Pennroad Corporation to buy 402,000 shares of the Seaboard Air Line Co. stock?

Mr. LEE. Because we believed that there was a possibility that that particular railroad was becoming one which we could properly have an investment in and in time, if we chose to sell, make some money in, or, if we held, we might derive some benefit from. We had in mind and did desire to make investments in the three southern carriers; that is, the principal ones—Atlantic Coast Line, the Southern Railway, and the Seaboard Air Line—and we proposed to invest something over a million dollars in each of them.

Mr. PECORA. Now, you actually invested over 4½ million dollars in the Seaboard Air Line?

Mr. LEE. Unfortunately, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Why was that unfortunate?

Mr. LEE. Because I think that was entirely too much money for us to put into the Seaboard Air Line or any other such company.

Mr. PECORA. But why did you do it?

Mr. LEE. Because we could not help ourselves under the contract we had agreed to.

Mr. PECORA. But you made a contract voluntarily?

Mr. LEE. Yes; we did.

Mr. PECORA. And in the free exercise of your own judgment?

Mr. LEE. For 125,000.

Mr. PECORA. For 125,000 shares?

Mr. LEE. Which would have cost us about a little over a million and a quarter dollars.

Mr. PECORA. Why didn't you stick to that purpose instead of going far beyond it and buying four hundred and odd thousand shares?

Mr. LEE. We did not expect we would be called upon for more than the purchase of the 125,000 shares.

Mr. PECORA. Why didn't you make a contract in such terms that you could not be called upon to purchase more than that?

Mr. LEE. We thought we did, I believe.

Mr. PECORA. Who prepared this contract marked Exhibit No. 55?

Mr. LEE. As I recall it, that was a joint preparation between our side and Mr. Bollard of Dillon, Read & Co. What I mean is this, Mr. Pecora—125,000 shares we thought—we knew was the amount we wanted. We felt that we would not get any more because of the market condition, because of the fact that the stockholders would undoubtedly take a very fair percentage, and the best way of making investment in Seaboard was through the particular syndicate that we afterward made the arrangement with. It was unfortunate for us that the contract was signed and in effect, and that the financial plan approved by the Commission for the issue of stock was not promulgated until after the first market break, and as a consequence of that market break the stockholders of the Seaboard Air Line took a very small proportion, an insignificant proportion, of the stock that was offered to them, and the syndicate had to take practically all of it.

The CHAIRMAN. How much did you pay?

Mr. LEE. \$11.25 per share, Senator.

Senator GOLDSBOROUGH. What was the market at the time?

Mr. LEE. At the time of entering into that agreement the market was—I am now reading, Mr. Pecora— $16\frac{1}{4}$ to $17\frac{1}{4}$.

Mr. PECORA. Where is the provision in this contract of October 9, 1929, that obligated your company to buy four hundred and two thousand and odd shares?

Mr. LEE. May I read it? [Reading:]

If the proposed additional offer of new stock is made and underwritten as above outlined, the Pennroad Corporation agrees, at such time as the underwriting syndicate takes up and pays for any stock not subscribed and paid for by stockholders, to purchase from the Securities Syndicate or from sellers designated by the Securities Syndicate an amount of new stock equivalent to 25 percent of all stock so purchased by the underwriting syndicate from the Seaboard Air Line Railway Company.

Mr. PECORA. When was that issue made to the public or offered to the public?

Mr. LEE. As I recall it—may I refer to this memorandum? [After consulting memorandum:] The order of the Commission approving the issue was not issued until November 12, 1929.

Mr. PECORA. When was the offering made to the public of that new stock?

Mr. LEE. I assume it was made immediately, Mr. Pecora. I don't find anything—wait a minute; here it is. I beg your pardon. The offering of new stock was announced to the Seaboard security holders on November 26, 1929.

The CHAIRMAN. What is that stock worth now, Mr. Lee?

Mr. LEE. Well, the quotation for it is practically nominal. It has been down to a half, and I think it is a little over a dollar now, Senator.

The CHAIRMAN. The road is in receivership?

Mr. LEE. The road is in receivership.

Mr. PECORA. How long after January 1930, did the road go into receivership?

Mr. LEE. The receiver was appointed December 23, 1930.

Mr. PECORA. Was it considered by you that the agreement or rather the acquisition of these 400,000 and odd shares of the Seaboard Air Line would be beneficial to the stockholders of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. LEE. It was considered by me that the acquisition of 125,000 would be beneficial to the stockholders of the Pennroad Corporation. I am very sorry personally we got the 400,000, but, as I say, we were under contract, as I see it, to have to take it.

Mr. PECORA. Wasn't it a simple thing to have the contract limit you to the obligation to buy only 125,000 shares if in your judgment that is all that your company should have bought?

Mr. LEE. I didn't understand that question, Mr. Pecora.

Mr. PECORA. Wouldn't it have been a simple thing to have had the contract into which you entered in behalf of your corporation so worded that your obligation or the obligation of your company would be limited to the purchase of 125,000 shares of stock, if that number of shares was all that you thought your company should buy?

Mr. LEE. But as I tried to explain, we thought that we were limiting it, because we felt that 125,000 shares was even more than we

might get because of the incidence of this allotment; that is, the fact that the allotment was coming forward.

Mr. PECORA. Where is the original of that contract?

Mr. LEE. On our files, sir.

Mr. PECORA. What is that?

Mr. LEE. On our files.

Mr. PECORA. I would like to see the original, Mr. Lee.

Mr. LEE. I am sorry to say I haven't the file here. I will send you the original. That is the best I can do.

Mr. PECORA. Was it entered into upon the date borne by that copy, namely, October 9, 1929?

Mr. LEE. Yes, sir; that is correct.

Mr. PECORA. Let me see the entry in the minute book of your company with regard to this transaction, will you?

(An associate of Mr. Lee handed the minute book to Mr. Pecora.)

Mr. PECORA. Now, the entry, in part, which has been handed me reads as follows, and I am reading from minute book of the Pennroad Corporation:

Resolved, That the proper officers of this Corporation are hereby authorized to take any and all action and to execute any and all papers and instruments deemed by them proper to carry fully into effect arrangements with Messrs. Dillon, Read & Co. and associates, upon the general terms of a memorandum submitted to this meeting with respect to new stock proposed to be issued by the Seaboard Air Line Railway Company.

And that resolution appears to have been adopted at meeting of the board held on October 9, 1929, which is attended by you as president, Messrs. Atterbury, Morris, Ingersoll, Mellon, County, and Rue as directors.

Where is there anything in that resolution which indicates the number of shares of the Seaboard Air Line Railway Co. that you were authorized to contract to purchase in its behalf?

Mr. LEE. Well, I assume that the memorandum of agreement referred to—my recollection is that the memorandum of agreement referred to, is this memorandum the original of which is on our files, which probably was in final form. I believe it was, to the best of my recollection.

Mr. PECORA. Did you have it passed upon by attorneys for your company?

Mr. LEE. Oh, yes.

Mr. PECORA. Did they know that the purpose of your company was to acquire only 125,000 shares of this stock?

Mr. LEE. I should think so, sir.

Mr. PECORA. At this meeting of October 9, 1929, was that agreement that is in evidence here presented to the board for its consideration?

Mr. LEE. I am unable to testify whether it was this or a draft of agreement, as is frequently presented to board meetings, which resulted in the agreement being executed which is on our file and of which this is a true copy. In other words, Mr. Pecora, I think the agreement as we executed it was substantially in the form presented to the meeting.

Mr. PECORA. Did you present that agreement to the meeting on October 9, 1929?

Mr. LEE. I assume I did. I don't recollect particularly whether I actually presented it, but I believe I did.

Mr. PECORA. Well, did you explain to the board that it was the purpose of your company to acquire only 125,000 shares?

Mr. LEE. I am quite sure I did, sir, because that is all that is mentioned in this agreement.

The CHAIRMAN. Do you think the memorandum referred to in these minutes was substantially what is set out in this agreement?

Mr. LEE. I think so, Senator.

The CHAIRMAN. How long after that was the stock acquired, the transaction consummated?

Mr. LEE. January 14, 1930.

Mr. PECORA. At that time what was the market price of the stock?

Mr. LEE. January 14, 1930?

Mr. PECORA. Yes.

Mr. LEE. $9\frac{3}{4}$.

Mr. PECORA. And your company bought it at $11\frac{1}{2}$.

Mr. LEE. Eleven and one fourth.

The CHAIRMAN. That is all, Mr. Lee.

Mr. LEE. Senator Fletcher, excuse me, sir. You asked me a question the other day when I was here about my personal holdings of Pennroad. I desire to answer it, sir. I held 548 shares at the beginning of the corporation. I now hold 810.

The CHAIRMAN. Thank you.

Mr. LEE. Am I excused?

The CHAIRMAN. That is all; yes.

Mr. LEE. Thank you very much, gentlemen.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Chairman, in reliance upon the statement or testimony of Mr. Lee last Friday that the gentleman who conducted the negotiations in behalf of the Pennroad Corporation with Mr. Taplin was Mr. County, I asked that a subpoena be issued for Mr. County, who is in attendance here today. Mr. County is here now. But, in view of the testimony that has been given here today both by Mr. Taplin and Mr. Lee, I see no occasion to examine Mr. County, unless Mr. County has any statement to make which he desires to lay before the committee.

Mr. COUNTY. I am here at the service of the committee.

Mr. PECORA. Is there any information concerning the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway transaction that you want to lay before the committee?

Mr. COUNTY. Nothing special. It is a very old story with me, but I think there is no use going into that unless the committee sees fit to do so.

Mr. PECORA. Well, is there any information you could add to that which has been given to the committee by Mr. Taplin and Mr. Lee?

Mr. COUNTY. I don't think so. Every one of these investments were very carefully inquired into and decided to be for the benefit, sole benefit, of the stockholders of the Pennroad Corporation, of which I am one.

Mr. PECORA. I suggest—there are a few questions I want to ask Mr. County, if he will be sworn.

**TESTIMONY OF A. J. COUNTY, VICE PRESIDENT AND DIRECTOR
PENNSYLVANIA RAILROAD CO., PHILADELPHIA, PA.**

The CHAIRMAN. You will be sworn, Mr. County. Do you solemnly swear the evidence you will give in this hearing will be the truth, the whole truth, and nothing but the truth, so help you God?

Mr. COUNTY. I do.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. County, you just stated informally and before you were under oath that all of these investments that have been made by the Pennroad Corporation were made in the interests of the stockholders of the Pennroad Corporation.

Mr. COUNTY. Absolutely, sir.

Mr. PECORA. That is a correct statement, is it?

Mr. COUNTY. Absolutely.

Mr. PECORA. Now, in addition to being a director of the Pennroad Corporation you are an officer and director of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. COUNTY. I am, sir.

Mr. PECORA. How long have you been an officer and director of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. COUNTY. Well, for quite a number of years. I have been vice president of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. for about 13 years, and I suppose I have been a director for maybe half that time.

Mr. PECORA. And you have been a director of the Pennroad Corporation from its inception in April 1929?

Mr. COUNTY. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Up to the present time?

Mr. COUNTY. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. Were you one of the organizers of the Pennroad Corporation, Mr. County?

Mr. COUNTY. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Who were the other organizers of it?

Mr. COUNTY. Well, the organizers mentioned are the directors at that time, like Mr. Atterbury and Mr. Morris, Mr. Cooke, several other members of the board of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., as set forth in the announcement concerning the Pennroad Corporation.

Mr. PECORA. Well, as that announcement has been read into the record here it would appear that the Pennroad Corporation was organized originally to serve the interests of the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. Is that a correct assumption?

Mr. COUNTY. I don't think that you have carefully or fully read that statement. I say that with some diffidence.

Mr. PECORA. Well, Mr. County, will you tell us then what the purposes were of the organization of the new corporation, the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. COUNTY. The purpose of incorporating this investment corporation was to protect the interests of the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., and in addition to make such other investments as from time to time are deemed essential.

Mr. PECORA. Deemed essential to whose interests?

Mr. COUNTY. To the interests of the Pennroad stockholders.

Mr. PECORA. Well, as distinguished from the interests of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. stockholders?

Mr. COUNTY. Absolutely, because you will notice that in the first six lines submitting this proposition to the public as well as to the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., it is designated an independent instrumentality. I didn't hear that mentioned today, and that is the reason I am mentioning it now.

Mr. PECORA. Well, whether so designated or not, do you conceive that there was a point where the interests of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. might clash, or, rather, where the interests of the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. might clash, with the interests of the stockholders of the Pennroad Corporation who were not also stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. COUNTY. Yes; in the long future, with the broad powers of an investment corporation, that might arise.

Mr. PECORA. You as a director of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., as well as vice president of it, owed a duty to protect the interests of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., didn't you, at all times?

Mr. COUNTY. Yes; to the extent where they are affected.

Mr. PECORA. Yes. And as a director of the Pennroad Corporation you owed a duty to the stockholders of the Pennroad Corporation at all times to protect their interests?

Mr. COUNTY. Yes, sir; wherein they were affected.

Mr. PECORA. If conceivable, the interests of the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. might clash with the interests of the stockholders of the Pennroad Corporation, whose interests would you serve as a director in the one instance of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. and the other instance and at the same time of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. COUNTY. I would serve the interests of the company on whose board I sat and upon whose board I acted, because in this case there can be no apparent clash between them. This corporation, the Pennroad Corporation, made separate and independent investments of its own.

Mr. PECORA. Who determined the investments that were made by the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. COUNTY. The directors of the Pennroad Corporation and its executive committee.

Mr. PECORA. Who composed the executive committee in the year 1929?

Mr. COUNTY. The executive committee in 1929—I was a member myself, and I think that Mr. Cooke and Mr. Morris and Mr. Lee ex officio, the president of the company.

Mr. PECORA. Well, was Mr. Cooke a director at the same time of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. COUNTY. He was, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Was Mr. Morris?

Mr. COUNTY. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And you were, of course?

Mr. COUNTY. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. So that the executive committee of the Pennroad Corporation in the year 1929 was composed of three gentlemen who were also directors of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. COUNTY. Absolutely; and so set forth to the public before any investment was made in this stock or any stock was offered.

Mr. PECORA. Now, did you seek, as a director and a member of the executive committee of the Pennroad Corporation, in making investments of its funds, to serve the interests of the Pennroad Corporation as distinguished from the interests of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. or its stockholders?

Mr. COUNTY. As a director of the Pennroad Corporation, I sought primarily to protect its interests first of all, but in nothing that was done did I see any occasion to clash with the interests of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.

Mr. PECORA. Did those interests ever clash?

Mr. COUNTY. Not so far, but we are not at the end of them yet at all.

Mr. PECORA. I mean up to the present time.

Mr. COUNTY. Up to the present time.

Mr. PECORA. The interests have been harmonious?

Mr. COUNTY. Absolutely, so far.

Mr. PECORA. Now, in connection with the purchase of the 222,930 shares of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. stock by the Pennroad Corporation, did you have anything to do with the negotiations that led to that sale?

Mr. COUNTY. Yes, sir. I did, sir.

Mr. PECORA. What part did you have in that transaction?

Mr. COUNTY. It is a long story with me, this Pittsburgh & West Virginia. I think as far back as 1923 in my capacity as an officer of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., and especially one that deals with the corporate relations, that stock was offered to me. I think at that time it was offered through somebody connected with Sutro Bros. of New York. The answer I made after consulting our own people was, We are not interested.

Mr. PECORA. When you say "after consulting our own people"—

Mr. COUNTY. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. What people do you mean?

Mr. COUNTY. I went back and consulted the officers of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. and that would also reach the finance committee and be generally discussed.

Again, I think in about another year, it was offered to me through a man I think called Barker, who is a banker in the city of Philadelphia.

Mr. PECORA. When was that?

Mr. COUNTY. I think about 1923. And from time to time we had heard—it was common knowledge—that Pittsburgh & West Virginia stock was for sale.

Mr. PECORA. But the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. was not interested?

Mr. COUNTY. Not interested at the time, sir.

Mr. PECORA. When did it first become interested in the purchase?

Mr. COUNTY. Well, I think after that, because of the fact that the Pittsburgh & West Virginia—I assume Frank Taplin got into it, but I am not sure of that, and his associates, began to improve and extend the property. As a link of itself, from my conception of it, it ought to have been much farther or much longer to make it of essential interest to the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. There also may have been the question of the extraordinary value that these people attached to their stock at the time. They asked all kinds of ridiculous prices, and I never—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). What prices were asked for it when the matter was first brought to your notice by Sutro Bros.?

Mr. COUNTY. I think between \$400 or \$500 a share or something like that. It was perfectly ridiculous.

Mr. PECORA. And what price was mentioned by Barker?

Mr. COUNTY. Oh, we never got far enough, because a great many people and a great many properties of that kind were hawked around and we cannot pay attention to them. In my position as a financial officer loads of things are offered to me, from anything you can think of in the country, any kind of a corporate enterprise.

Mr. PECORA. Well, when for the first time did the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. become interested in the acquisition of large blocks of stock in the Pittsburgh & West Virginia?

Mr. COUNTY. I should think about 1926 it began to have some interest to us, because it had shown some real resources. It is a very valuable property. If my recollection is right, there are about a hundred million tons of unmined coal on that property. Now, Frank Taplin mentioned to me, or I mentioned to him several times when I met him, but Frank's figures were always too high, and as a financial officer I always let him do as much of the talking as he wants. I did not open it up, you know and say, "Well now, have you got that West Virginia stock for sale?" Because then I would be putting myself into a position of being a petitioner for the stock, and I didn't wish to be. A buyer usually never likes to get into that position.

Furthermore, we may not have had too much money at the time. Furthermore, the plans of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway looked to extensions that would connect it with other railroads at the time so that we would get a longer haul of its traffic. And all through this were the friendly relations with Frank Taplin, which were very friendly. It was a railroad from which we got a great deal of traffic on the Pennsylvania Railroad, and so long as it was in his hands I think it was pretty safe, and—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). You thought that while in his hands it was very friendly to the Pennsylvania Railroad?

Mr. COUNTY. Yes, sir; I did. I thought that his company, and its development, and the relations with him, as a valuable business man, and as a valuable man who knew really what he was doing, because he is a very well-informed man, and a very level-headed business man, I thought they were very desirable relations for us to cultivate, and while we did not buy the property or make an offer for the property, I did my best to keep those relations just as friendly as I could.

Mr. PECORA. Well, then, in April of 1929 the Pennroad Corporation was organized, and ultimately that corporation bought this Taplin stock.

Mr. COUNTY. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Now, what part did you take, if any, in those immediate negotiations?

Mr. COUNTY. Well, in those immediate negotiations I met Frank Taplin, and he discussed the proposition of getting a loan in connection with these properties. I must say that I had been treating the matter as a nonchalant and safe matter about the Pittsburgh & West

Virginia. Frank mentioned, when I asked what would be the security for such a loan, the Wheeling & Lake Erie stock. Now, about that time was announced the purchase, or at least we got information of—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). What did Taplin tell you about the purpose for which he was seeking the loan?

Mr. COUNTY. He was seeking a loan to get additional capital.

Mr. PECORA. To do what?

Mr. COUNTY. To hold onto his Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway shares and also to purchase Wheeling & Lake Erie shares.

Mr. PECORA. And also to prevent shares of the Wheeling & Lake Erie from falling into the hands of railroad interests hostile to the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.

Mr. COUNTY. I don't think we reached that stage. He probably left that to my intuition, because I had knowledge at that time that there had been extensive purchases by the New York Central, Baltimore & Ohio, and Van Sweringen interests of a number of lines, and either then or shortly thereafter we had acknowledgement that they had purchased the equivalent of or almost 50 or 51 percent of the Wheeling & Lake Erie. I therefore was interested, and I thought a loan to Frank Taplin would be all right, and that I would see that he got it if it was possible and his security was adequate.

Mr. PECORA. You were interested in what?

Mr. COUNTY. The Pennroad Corporation.

Mr. PECORA. What interest did the Pennroad Corporation have at that time in either of those two railroad properties, either the Wheeling & Lake Erie or the Pittsburgh & West Virginia?

Mr. COUNTY. It was a splendid investment is point no. 1, and—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). But it had not made any investment in either one of those railroads at that time.

Mr. COUNTY. No; but this was a valuable investment, is point no. 1, and then—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). Do you mean the loan was a valuable investment?

Mr. COUNTY. Yes, sir; because I was offered ample collateral. And in addition to that—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). How many times did you ask that that collateral be increased?

Mr. COUNTY. I think probably twice, and—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). So the original collateral was not adequate?

Mr. COUNTY. Well, not from my standpoint. You see, I was the person who was going to recommend that loan, and I wanted to be sure it was safe. Indeed, for an Irishman, I asked him a third time to increase that collateral. We attribute these attributes to Scotchmen, but I am an Irishman and I wanted that loan adequately secured, because a part of my money as well as the money of the stockholders of the Pennroad Corporation that I represented was going to be invested in that loan, and—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). All right. Now, that loan was made for the purpose of yielding a 6 percent return during the period of the loan to the Pennroad Corporation and not for the purpose of enabling Taplin to acquire stock of the Wheeling & Lake Erie Railroad.

Mr. COUNTY. Oh, yes. That was Mr. Taplin's end of it. In other words, I had an excellent loan to recommend to the Pennroad Corporation with collateral we would be very happy to have in the Pennroad Corporation treasury if anything should occur to Frank Taplin.

Mr. PECORA. That is, if the loan were not paid?

Mr. COUNTY. Absolutely.

Mr. PECORA. As a matter of fact, when September of 1929 came around the first quarter's interest installment on that loan fell due, and it now appears from the testimony of this afternoon given by Mr. Lee that that interest was not then paid.

Mr. COUNTY. I do not think that was quite the testimony. I think the testimony also went on to show that negotiations were pending for the purchase of a big lot of Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway stock and that the settlement was to be concluded just as soon thereafter as possible, and that was when the interest was paid.

Mr. PECORA. Well, the interest was paid in October of 1929.

Mr. COUNTY. That is right.

Mr. PECORA. When the Pennroad Corporation made the first payment upon its purchases of common stock in the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railroad to Taplin.

Mr. COUNTY. That is my recollection.

Mr. PECORA. Well, now, in buying those 222,930 shares of that stock from Taplin and his associates, you realized, didn't you, that you were buying an amount equivalent to about 73 percent of the total outstanding stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co.?

Mr. COUNTY. I did.

Mr. PECORA. And Mr. Taplin was permitted to retain the presidency of the railroad?

Mr. COUNTY. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And has continued in that office ever since?

Mr. COUNTY. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And he is operating a railroad company that is a competitor of the Pennsylvania Railroad?

Mr. COUNTY. Yes; in part.

Mr. PECORA. And do you mean in part otherwise?

Mr. COUNTY. When I say in part I mean in that particular mileage that corresponds to the Pennsylvania railroad mileage in that territory. But you must remember that when the traffic leaves the Pittsburgh & West Virginia tracks it comes, a great deal of it, to the Pennsylvania Railroad.

Mr. PECORA. Then to a certain extent it was favorable to the interests of the Pennsylvania Railroad to have Mr. Taplin operate the Pittsburgh & West Virginia?

Mr. COUNTY. It was fortunate, I think, for both, but I do not think that is quite the way it was left. The way it was left was this: Mr. Taplin has a great deal of pride in his work. He has a great deal of pride in the Pittsburgh & West Virginia. He has pretty headstrong qualities, but if you get to know him you find he has also very lovable qualities, and he asked that until the Pennroad Corporation had somebody to take charge of that property that he be permitted to continue there, and that the results would be all that we could ask for it. And

he has operated that property I think with marvelous skill, and we have the greatest faith in him. But I might say that we have not trusted solely to him, much as we like him, for we have monthly reports and from time to time reports of what is going on in the Pittsburgh & West Virginia.

Mr. PECORA. Who has them?

Mr. COUNTY. The Pennroad Corporation. And the Pennsylvania Railroad watches that matter, too. That is where we get some of our business. In addition to that, Mr. Lee, the president of the Pennroad Corporation, is a director of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co., and he has been over that property and personally inspected it and reported to the board, and the board of the Pennroad Corporation keeps in touch with what is going on every month, and also between times if they ask about it.

Mr. PECORA. Well, you feel that Mr. Taplin is operating the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway for the benefit of the stockholders of that railway company, do you?

Mr. COUNTY. Absolutely.

Mr. PECORA. And that railroad is a competitor within the limits of its mileage of the Pennsylvania Railroad?

Mr. COUNTY. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. And a strong competitor?

Mr. COUNTY. Yes, sir. And if he can make it any stronger he makes it stronger. He makes it as strong as he can. And on our part we make it as strong as we can.

Mr. PECORA. Do you consider, as a director of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., that you are serving the interests of the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. by permitting the operation of this competing line called the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. to remain in the control and management of as strong a competitor as Mr. Taplin?

Mr. COUNTY. Absolutely. The more coal he produces the more we are going to get, a part of it anyway. If he would get it entirely, we would get a part of the whole haul, but we will get our share anyway.

Mr. PECORA. Is there a community of interest?

Mr. COUNTY. I wouldn't say that. But there is no clash of interests. That is, within his limits, of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co., he is absolutely in control, and he works for the benefit of its property, just as in the case of our property we are working for our interest.

Mr. PECORA. Were all those elements in your mind when you, as a director of the Pennroad Corporation, advocated the purchase of those railroad shares?

Mr. COUNTY. Yes, sir; because we had not developed on the Pennroad an operating staff that we could put in charge of a railroad of that size. In addition to that, and I think it ought to go in as a part of the history here in justice to Frank Taplin, that Frank Taplin had the understanding, the clear understanding, although it is not a written understanding that I know of, that he was engaged in trying to form an independent system. That is, that he would take the Pittsburgh & West Virginia, and he would take the Wheeling & Lake Erie and the Western Maryland and have a line that reached

the big cities of Cleveland and Toledo, on the one hand, and the lower part of the coal fields in Ohio and Pennsylvania, on the other hand, and go right to the Baltimore harbor. And our understanding with him was this: That he would struggle to the best of his endeavors to get the Interstate Commerce Commission to approve of that. And if it approved of it he could have that stock back again at a price to be fixed at that time.

Mr. PECORA. Well, he said here today that he expected, under those circumstances, to be able to buy it back at the price at which he sold it.

Mr. COUNTY. I think he is mistaken. He will buy it back at the price that the Pennroad Corporation directors may determine, and for nothing less.

The CHAIRMAN. The Pennroad Corporation never intended or contemplated doing any operating business, did it—the ownership and operation of railroads, did it?

Mr. COUNTY. No. We did not expect to operate railroads, but we expected to have experts that would be put on railroads, and get representation on boards of directors to protect our interests fully.

The CHAIRMAN. Your purpose was not to acquire railroads so much as it was to make valuable investments?

Mr. COUNTY. Exactly, Senator Fletcher. Nevertheless, nobody makes a big investment so far as I know of, of anything like this size here, who does not expect to have an expert in and near the property, whether on the board or off the board, to see what is going on.

Mr. PECORA. Who is the expert that your people had on it?

Mr. COUNTY. On what?

Mr. PECORA. On the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway?

Mr. COUNTY. Mr. Lee is one of our experts, but we have our own officers in the Pittsburgh region, who are right over that property all the time and know its operations from day to day.

The CHAIRMAN. Did the Pennsylvania Railroad name Mr. Lee as a director of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway?

Mr. COUNTY. No, sir. The Pennroad Corporation arranged that.

The CHAIRMAN. The Pennroad Corporation did that?

Mr. COUNTY. Yes, sir.

The CHAIRMAN. So that the directors there are not altogether named by Mr. Taplin?

Mr. COUNTY. Not at all. Mr. Taplin is in a delightful relation of being given charge of his property and keeping on operating it, but the moment that Mr. Taplin is not satisfactory to us, the stock, although registered in his name, belongs to the Pennroad Corporation and out he goes.

Mr. PECORA. Who asked Mr. Lee to become the president of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. COUNTY. I did. I selected him.

Mr. PECORA. Why?

Mr. COUNTY. I selected him because he had been the treasurer of the Pennsylvania Railroad for a long time. And prior to that he had been the assistant treasurer of the railroad company, and he had been connected with financial matters, under suitable direction, for probably 30 years.

Mr. PECORA. You are connected with another company, called the Pennsylvania Co., are you not?

Mr. COUNTY. Yes, sir. I am a vice president of that corporation.

Mr. PECORA. And also a director of it?

Mr. COUNTY. Yes, sir.

Mr. PECORA. That corporation is a wholly owned subsidiary of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., isn't it?

Mr. COUNTY. Exactly.

Mr. PECORA. And is a holding company?

Mr. COUNTY. Yes. I might explain that it is the chief instrument by which the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. gathered together its ownership of the lines west of Pittsburgh. Originally under the charter granted by the State of Pennsylvania the Pennsylvania Railroad had authority to build a line from Harrisburg to Pittsburgh, and there it stopped. Our predecessors very quickly realized, and so did the State of Pennsylvania very quickly realize, that without a longer haul that would take us to the Mississippi River and the Great Lakes the Pennsylvania Railroad itself would have a doubtful living. Accordingly the State of Pennsylvania gave it a broad charter, the broadest kind of a charter in those days, not only to construct and own railroads in the State of Pennsylvania but elsewhere; to buy other railroads, to guarantee railroads, and it began the buying of a series of weak railroads, financing and guaranteeing their obligations, purchasing more stocks, consolidating them, until it has this admirable system that reaches the Great Lakes and St. Louis and Cincinnati, and so forth. As the holder of those stocks and for a long time the operator, up until 1918, it was the supervisor of operations of all those western lines, but the financing was kept entirely separate from the Pennsylvania Railroad, and—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). The Pennsylvania Co. as such could have bought the various holdings of these other railroad company stocks that were purchased by the Pennroad Corporation, couldn't it?

Mr. COUNTY. It could.

Mr. PECORA. It had ample power under its charter to do it?

Mr. COUNTY. Absolutely.

Mr. PECORA. It appears from the record before this committee practically beyond all controversy that the organizers of the Pennroad Corporation were all directors of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., like yourself.

Mr. COUNTY. Yes, sir; and so announced.

Mr. PECORA. Now, why wasn't the Pennsylvania Co. used in the purchase of those holdings of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co., the Seaboard Air Line Railway Co., and other railway company stocks purchased by the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. COUNTY. At the inception of the Pennroad Corporation, or at least when it was being thought out, you must remember that the Pennsylvania Co. had been restricted to, or had grown up entirely upon, the ownership of stocks connected with the Pennsylvania Railroad system. Therefore the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., because of its owning all the stock of the Pennsylvania Co., would have had to raise all the new capital for a company of its purpose, like the Pennroad, and that it was deemed inadvisable to do.

Mr. PECORA. Why?

Mr. COUNTY. Because it would have scattered the ownership in order to get the money from the public, the only source of reliance we have. The stock of the Pennsylvania Co. would have had to be sold or distributed to the public so as to use it as a means of getting more capital, and—

Mr. PECORA (interposing). Could not the Pennsylvania Co. have authorized an increase of its capital stock, and could not that stock have been purchased by the Pennsylvania Railroad?

Mr. COUNTY. No, sir. Because the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. had not the funds for that purpose, had not enough funds to meet all of its own necessities at that time, and for this purpose also.

Mr. PECORA. Could not it have sold additional securities for the purpose of raising such funds?

Mr. COUNTY. No. It had its own hands full to try to get over the period which so closely followed governmental control, and the bad years of 1921, 1922, and a part of 1923.

Mr. PECORA. But this was in 1929.

Mr. COUNTY. We had all we could do to look after the affairs of the Pennsylvania Railroad.

Mr. PECORA. But at the time when the Pennroad Corporation was organized its stock was offered entirely to the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.?

Mr. COUNTY. Exactly. But that was a new corporation, and into what fields it would go nobody knew. Whether it would hold the stocks it purchased nobody knew. What its plan would be in the field of railroads nobody knew. Therefore instead of taking the experiment and trying to enlarge the Pennsylvania Railroad, which had a lot of mortgages on it in addition to stock; or taking the Pennsylvania Co., which had no property to mortgage except its own securities, a new and independent company was tried, which was launched by an appeal to Pennsylvania Railroad stockholders: "Here is an opportunity. If you wish to take your share of it you can. If not the Pennroad Corporation reserves the right to sell its stock to others." That was a purely voluntary matter.

The CHAIRMAN. The Pennsylvania Co. could have done that, couldn't it?

Mr. COUNTY. No, sir. Not without giving other people an ownership in the underlying stocks of the Pennsylvania Railroad System, which we hold together in the Pennsylvania Co. so that we could carry out the plan of consolidation by which some day, if we all live, and the restrictions of the various States are removed, we will have a united Pennsylvania Railroad system from the Atlantic to the Mississippi River, and from the Great Lakes to the Potomac River. Until that occurs we cannot afford to scatter the stock of the Pennsylvania Co. about, or give anybody else an ownership in it.

The CHAIRMAN. Then the stock of the Pennsylvania Co. is owned by the Pennsylvania Railroad?

Mr. COUNTY. That is right.

The CHAIRMAN. And the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. were to own the Pennroad Corporation. So you had the same stockholders in either case.

Mr. COUNTY. We did not know whether that would eventuate or not. But it did eventuate in the first blush to a large extent in the

case of the Pennroad Corporation stock, but after that there was a great change in the ownership of the stock all over the country.

Mr. PECORA. That was when the Pennroad Corporation increased its issue of capital stock.

Mr. COUNTY. Before that. There was quite a large distribution of the stock.

Mr. PECORA. Why was the voting-trust agreement entered into at the outset of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. COUNTY. Not knowing what the future held in store the best thing to do was to keep the property all together.

Mr. PECORA. What property do you mean?

Mr. COUNTY. The Pennroad property, so that there might be a uniform policy carried out by experienced people.

Mr. PECORA. A uniform policy of what kind?

Mr. COUNTY. To serve the investment policy.

Mr. PECORA. The investment in railroad property?

Mr. COUNTY. Anything. Railroad properties and others.

Mr. PECORA. Well, the three voting trustees that were chosen were all officers and directors of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co.

Mr. COUNTY. They were directors of the Pennsylvania Railroad but not officers.

Mr. PECORA. General Atterbury is one of the trustees and he was the president of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., wasn't he?

Mr. COUNTY. He was at that time, but I think he only occupied that position for a very short time, as trustee, I mean.

Mr. PECORA. He occupied it for a long time, didn't he?

Mr. COUNTY. I don't know. I don't recall. According to this memorandum I am handed here he held it from the formation of the Pennroad Corporation in April of 1929 to the 10th of April 1930.

Mr. PECORA. Well, he held it for nearly a year?

Mr. COUNTY. Nearly a year; yes.

Mr. PECORA. Couldn't the Pennsylvania Co. have issued securities, and couldn't they by a voting trust agreement too—

Mr. COUNTY (interposing.) No.

Mr. PECORA (continuing.) Have secured this unity?

Mr. COUNTY. We did not believe that to be a wise step, because, as I say—

Mr. PECORA (interposing.) Well, if it is considered to be wise to do it in the case of the Pennroad Corporation—

Mr. COUNTY (interposing.) That was an open field, with an independent instrumentality.

Mr. PECORA (continuing.) How independent was it when the common stock was put into a voting trust for 10 years, which robbed the investor during that period of 10 years' time of a voice in the management of the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. COUNTY. I do not think you can say it robbed them of that. That was exactly how the company was to be held, according to announcements made. And the inherent strength of that policy was the cause of the stock being subscribed for. I venture to say if there had been no voting trust it is very questionable if we would have had the success in forming it.

Mr. PECORA. Do you think that the people who bought the stock of the Pennroad Corporation at the outset did so because they knew

that the three voting trustees were directors of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., and they had confidence in their management?

Mr. COUNTY. Not only that but the other factors.

Mr. PECORA. That was one of the factors?

Mr. COUNTY. Yes.

Mr. PECORA. And you disagree with Mr. Taplin's observation that people who buy stock do so blindly?

Mr. COUNTY. I certainly do. I think he made that statement in connection with annual reports. I will agree that there are plenty of stockholders who do not read annual reports.

Mr. PECORA. No. He made that statement specifically in answer to a question as to whether they make their investments blindly.

Mr. COUNTY. I think I would not subscribe to that at all. We make our investments, those connected with the Pennsylvania Railroad, for instance, because it has had a dividend rate for 70 years in every calendar year, because it has continuity of management and strength in serving the country.

The CHAIRMAN. The Pennroad Corporation was to be of benefit to the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. What benefit has the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. been to the Pennroad Corporation?

Mr. COUNTY. Well, I think probably through its managers is one thing, the advice that they gave. I am one of them myself and I have to speak for them with that feeling. I think my experience there of 43 years in the company, in all phases of railroad financing, is of inestimable benefit to the Pennroad Corporation. I am only speaking for myself. And here is Mr. Morris, one of our directors, and he is chairman and was for many years president and director of one of the strongest trust companies in Philadelphia. Here is Mr. Mellon, of Pittsburgh, a distinguished banker. And if you go down the list you will find they are men of broad experience and men of distinguished position in business and affairs, the kind of men you would choose to let hold every penny you have in the world.

Mr. PECORA. Is that why these men are permitted to engage in transactions of \$38,000,000, to be carried on by word of mouth?

Mr. COUNTY. Yes, sir; because when we bind ourselves that is considered preferable in good business circles, not all business circles, depending upon the people you are dealing with—

Mr. PECORA. (interposing). Then you have to depend upon the recollection of individuals?

Mr. COUNTY. No, sir. It is always dependent upon the cash payment when there is a delivery of the stock.

Mr. PECORA. Well, what good is that if the terms themselves are to be left to individual recollections of conversations?

Mr. COUNTY. If the Pittsburgh & West Virginia sale had not been completed then the situation would have remained as it was before—the Pennroad Corporation would have retained its money, and Mr. Taplin would have retained his stock.

Mr. PECORA. Do you consider that a better way to do business where \$38,000,000 is involved than basing it upon a written agreement?

Mr. COUNTY. I do with Mr. Frank Taplin, because we had known him for 30 years or more, and he keeps every obligation he makes.

Mr. PECORA. And for that reason it was better to have his spoken word than a written agreement?

Mr. COUNTY. It wasn't necessary to have a written agreement. I have seen more lawsuits result from written agreements than from oral views. If you want to get into a first-class lawsuit, have a written agreement to buy stock and have the market fall away from it in a month.

Mr. PECORA. And if you want to avoid an agreement, have it by word of mouth also?

Mr. COUNTY. If you want to have a definite settlement after a word-of-mouth agreement, in case the man does not produce the goods he does not get the money. That was Mr. Taplin's case.

Mr. PECORA. But the wise counsellors of the Pennroad Corporation also approved the agreement of October 29, 1929, under which the corporation obligated itself to buy 402,000 shares of Seaboard Air Line stock, whereas it had only intended to buy 125,000 shares; is that it?

Mr. COUNTY. Without going into the details of it, they approved that arrangement. In fact, they had to take 402,000 shares as the result of going into a syndicate, and it shows the responsibility you take when you go to a syndicate.

Mr. PECORA. Why did those wise men go into that syndicate agreement with Dillon, Read & Co.?

Mr. COUNTY. Because that was the best way we knew under the circumstances that then prevailed. It might have gone the other way. It must be remembered that a long time elapsed between the negotiations and the time of the approval by the Interstate Commerce Commission. But it must have been a splendid thing to have done or the Commission would not have approved of it. The fact that the market falls away from you illustrates the effect of not making quick settlements in any financial transaction.

Mr. PECORA. Mr. Taplin testified in June of 1930 before the Interstate Commerce Commission—and you heard him repeat it here, or affirm this morning—that one of the reasons why he went into the negotiations to sell to the Pennroad Corporation those 222,930 shares of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co.'s stock in September of 1929 was because he foresaw a financial storm and he wanted to unload, to use his own expression, the stock of the Pittsburgh & West Virginia Railway Co. Did you learn that for the first time today?

Mr. COUNTY. I did sir, but I think Mr. Frank Taplin did not foresee the kind of hurricane that we had. He was in this position, or this is my explanation of it: He was in the position where either you or myself would be as the manager of a syndicate, of seeing the price rise to a place where he thought he would have a very good profit, and that that was the time to choose to take advantage of his price.

Mr. PECORA. No. He says he did it at that time because he saw a financial storm coming, not because prices were rising.

Mr. COUNTY. Oh, as to a financial storm coming, he was at the head of the game, with all this rise, if I remember right, at the end of October. In my experience, and I have had a very broad one, I did not see, and I did not see one banker, either here or abroad, that saw anything like this storm forthcoming, not one, nor business man either.

The CHAIRMAN. The bankers of the world seem to have been the poorest hands that the world had on that subject. The same was true in Europe as in this country.

Mr. COUNTY. I think that is so.

The CHAIRMAN. Speaking about the great advantage to the Penn-road Corporation of having directors of such marked ability and standing, and men of such great affairs, was that the thing that led them to take stock, shown by the statement, that cost them \$51,000,000 which subsequently, according to this statement, had a market value of \$5,000,000?

Mr. COUNTY. Senator, of course it depends on whether we are speaking with foresight or hindsight. May I give you this illustration? In that same period all of the governments of the world were bankrupt; and this dear old country of ours that we love so much has gone off the gold standard, although written in the bond is "I will pay you in gold."

Let me give you another illustration, which is probably more definitely to the point. The Pennsylvania Railroad stock sold for \$110 a share. It has since sold for \$6.50 a share. Both of those prices represent hysteria of the worst kind. I would not be at all surprised, in the impetus of the country, to see it go over \$50. But my foresight may be entirely wrong.

The CHAIRMAN. I hope you are right. I think conditions are somewhat better.

Mr. COUNTY. Thank God for it!

Mr. PECORA. Of how many companies were you a director in 1929?

Mr. COUNTY. I suppose, somewhere from 125 to 150. That is my job. My position with the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. is this: I am vice president of finance and also of corporate relations; and in the Pennsylvania system alone, between the companies which are directly in the system and the companies in which we have a joint ownership with other railroads, such as terminal companies, there are something like 150 companies. It is my particular job to sit on those boards; but there is a great deal of humbug about that statement—not about me, but about that statement; and I will just explain it in a moment.

I am the president of the Delaware Railroad. If Senator Townsend here, he knows where that is located; or Senator Goldsborough knows where that railroad is. I sit on that board, and we hold about three meetings a year. To do what? To take from the Pennsylvania Railroad the guaranteed dividends it pays upon the stock and handle their distribution, to submit a report to our stockholders at the annual meeting, and to answer any questions that they may put to us. When you just multiply that by 50, there is not a bit of business of those companies that could not be transacted, if you got them all together, in 3 days. They are leased and chiefly owned by the Pennsylvania Railroad Co., with guaranteed dividends, and they do not operate their properties; they are operated by the Pennsylvania Railroad.

In the new era which is coming on, when everybody sees it the way we see it in the railroad business, under the broad powers of the Federal Government we will have a transportation system without any State borders. That is, we can engage in rail transportation with

one company; we can engage in bus transportation or truck transportation or air transportation or steamship transportation, and we will be under proper regulation. Now, until that day occurs, with the variety of laws that we have to deal with, with the variety of taxation systems, which is the chief thing for keeping them separate, and so on, we must put up with the ways we have at present. Even with all its failings, the companies that are now embraced in the Pennsylvania system at one time in their lives were equal to 700 different corporations. We have got them down to about 150 now; and if we keep on, with the help of the Government and with the help of business and of progress, we will get them down further to 3 or 4 or 5.

So in time, I think I may say to Senator Goldsborough, even the dear name of the old Delaware Railroad will be "Pennsylvania Railroad." I hope I have made that very clear. The reason I have made that clear is this—and I am glad that you have given me the opportunity: If you look at the chart illustrating the work of a simple railroad man like myself, you will see spider webs woven in and out to describe what I am doing. There is the whole thing I am doing.

May I also say this—and probably my associates will forgive my wandering: The greatest holding company in the world is the United States of America. It was incorporated and given certain limited powers to do for the States what severally they could not do for themselves. It has gone along in this broad field. It has financed them; it has taken them over, and even when we have given it all those broad powers, when it comes to dealing with business questions, what do we have? It must have a separate corporation for each activity of the Government, such as the Reconstruction Finance Corporation, farm bureaus, the Shipping Board, the waterways, and so forth, and there is a good substantial business reason for that. In time I hope all will be successful. That is my earnest hope. Nevertheless, they require these separate entities, although, as I say, it is the greatest holding corporation in the world, and the best.

You will excuse my wandering into the field of philosophy.

THE CHAIRMAN. Do you approve generally of these holding corporations, such as the Pennroad Corporation and the Pennsylvania Co.?

MR. COUNTY. I do, of the Pennsylvania Co., Senator. I will speak later on about the Pennroad Corporation. The Pennsylvania Co. has been in operation since 1870. Let me tell you some things about it, because it illustrates what the Pennroad Corporation could do at any time.

When we wished to extend our system west of Pittsburgh including what is now the Pittsburgh, Fort Wayne & Chicago Railroad Co., those companies had broken down absolutely. The Pennsylvania Co., the holding company, got from the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. the rails of the old Portage Railroad owned by the State, and those rails were leased from the Fort Wayne & Chicago; and that is how we began to go westward. In time I expect the Pennroad Corporation, if we are allowed by law—and we will not do it unless we are—to take a very marked part in stabilizing the financial condition of those companies in which it has investments.

We will if we are let alone. That is exactly what the United States is doing for the States. That is what we propose by these holding companies to do.

It is very true, Senator, that there have been unfortunate holding companies, but nevertheless we must not subject them to pitiless criticism at a time when the whole world, following the war, has shaken the vitals of mankind and produced nothing but poverty from one end of the world to the other.

Mr. PECORA. One of the criticisms directed to holding companies is based upon the fact that in the issuance of their securities the organizers or inciters are allowed to get options on the best securities at prices much lower than those at which the securities are offered to the general public. That is a very sound criticism, is it not?

Mr. COUNTY. It is a very sound criticism; but let us not inject that into this thing. The clear conception of the advice we got from the bankers, and which was sustained by your own judgment, was this: Form this company. If the stockholders of the Pennsylvania Railroad Co. want it to succeed let it alone.

Mr. PECORA. Let me interrupt you just a moment. The Pennroad Corporation, as I recall it, had among its initial board of directors five or six directors who were directors and officers of banks and other financial institutions in and around the city of Philadelphia?

Mr. COUNTY. That is quite right, sir.

Mr. PECORA. Why did it have to go to a firm of private bankers for financial advice?

Mr. COUNTY. Because the firm of private bankers—the business they carry on is very decidedly different from a bank and trust company. If you look at those men who are on the board—

Mr. PECORA. The Pennroad Corporation went to Kuhn, Loeb & Co. for their advice.

Mr. COUNTY. Surely. In other words, we went after advice as to the character of corporation and the scope of it which we thought would best meet the situation.

Mr. PECORA. Was there no banking and financial experience among the banking directors who were officers and directors of the Pennroad Corporation to give them that advice?

Mr. COUNTY. No, sir; because they are engaged in a totally different kind of banking business. They do not take large issues of securities and get syndicates up.

Mr. PECORA. Neither did Kuhn, Loeb & Co. in this instance get syndicates up. They advised against it.

Mr. COUNTY. In this case they did; but they are accustomed to deal in a broad way with securities—what is the kind of securities to market? What is the best way to market them? What kind or character must they have to meet the market demands?—because market demands for securities change just as rapidly as women's hats.

Mr. PECORA. Do you think commercial bankers are not in touch with those conditions?

Mr. COUNTY. I do not think they are so able as the other bankers to sell new issues of securities. After all, the banks are small in the city of Philadelphia. It is a very conservative city. The banks are admirably managed and they are very strong. The business of a

national bank, of course, is not to buy a lot of securities. That is only a part of their job. It is making loans to all those big industries in the city of Philadelphia, commercial loans. The scope of a trust company is different, because it, again, makes loans and manages trust estates. Our people are interested in that kind of work and they understand it thoroughly. When a security is submitted to them, they can review and pass upon it. This was a new step entirely to us, and under new conditions which we had never faced before.

MR. PECORA. And there were not enough bankers with financial experience represented on the board to enable the company to operate without seeking and paying handsome prices for the advice of private bankers?

MR. COUNTY. That is exactly the case. We have eminent lawyers on our legal staff, and when a case of any importance occurs we certainly go to the best experts in the business. The Government does the same.

I should say for the services of Kuhn, Loeb & Co. that they have had a long experience in all of these matters, and that is of the highest importance, because it touches not only conditions in this country but abroad. The men are eminently qualified for it; and I do not know of any firm whose participation with us in offering securities for sale, such as the Pennsylvania Railroad does, will more assuredly mean success than Kuhn, Loeb & Co.

SENATOR GOLDSBOROUGH. "The Government does the same" must be a compliment to you, Mr. Pecora.

MR. PECORA. I don't know that he intended that for me.

MR. COUNTY. I did. You are brought in here as a specialist. Why did not the Government get someone else?

MR. PECORA. The Government gets such services cheaper than a corporation.

MR. COUNTY. Sometimes.

MR. PECORA. One of the directors at the outset was Mr. James S. Alexander?

MR. COUNTY. Yes.

MR. PECORA. Mr. James S. Alexander was then, I think, chairman of the board of the Guaranty Trust Co. of New York?

MR. COUNTY. Mr. Alexander at that time had practically retired. Mr. Alexander I had known for 20 years, and he was the president of the National Bank of Commerce in New York. He was a Scotsman, certainly by instinct, and one of the finest bankers I ever met.

MR. PECORA. He was connected with the Guaranty Trust Co.?

MR. COUNTY. Yes.

MR. PECORA. And they operated an investment affiliate known as the "Guaranty Co."?

MR. COUNTY. Yes.

MR. PECORA. Which was in the business of issuing and selling securities?

MR. COUNTY. Yes.

MR. PECORA. Didn't you think he had an experience that qualified him to give advice to the Pennroad Corporation as a director of it, with regard to the kind of securities it should issue and how it should market them?

Mr. COUNTY. To advise, yes; but Mr. Alexander did not come on as an original director of the Pennroad Corporation. He came on later. If he had been on the board, his advice would have been listened to. But there were 10 other people on that board who had us persuaded that that was the proper path to travel.

And another thing is this: Kuhn, Loeb & Co. had a greater and broader knowledge of all plans of finance; and I must again repeat that the cheapest thing we do is to pay the best experts

Mr. PECORA. I think that is all I want to ask.

The CHAIRMAN. That is all.

Mr. COUNTY. Thank you, gentlemen.

The CHAIRMAN. The subcommittee is now adjourned subject to the call of the chairman. It has been suggested that we probably will not meet before October 3; but we might change that date at any time. It is very probable that we will have no further hearings until about October 3; but the Chair has the right and the authority to call a session at any time he sees fit to do so. At present we stand adjourned subject to the call of the chairman, which will probably be about October 3.

(Whereupon, at 5:30 p.m., the subcommittee adjourned subject to the call of the chairman.)